

22nd
**International
 Vasculitis
 Workshop**
**21 – 25 February 2026
 Melbourne, Australia**

**Abstracts of the 22nd International Vasculitis Workshop,
 Melbourne, Australia, 22-25 February 2026**

(Version 1.1)

Welcome

The 22nd International Vasculitis Workshop, held in Melbourne, Australia, features over 500 Scientific abstracts and over 950 attendees from a variety of medical, research and health care backgrounds, as well as patients and carers from the vasculitis community.

Melbourne is the home of ANCA, as anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) were discovered at St. Vincent's Hospital, Melbourne, over 40 years ago. This discovery provided a foundation for understanding of the diseases granulomatosis with polyangiitis, microscopic polyangiitis and to some degree eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis. These conditions are now collectively known as the ANCA-associated vasculitides. Over time, the scope of the Workshop has broadened from a focus on these disease alone to now include all forms of vasculitis.

On behalf of the hosts, The Australia and New Zealand Vasculitis Society (ANZVASC), we are pleased to welcome the vasculitis community to Melbourne for this, the first International Vasculitis Workshop to be held in the Southern Hemisphere and the second outside of Europe and North America.

Richard Kitching, Catherine Hill and Vicki Quincey
 Workshop Co-convenors

Previous International Vasculitis Workshops

1. 1983 Cambridge, United Kingdom (M. Lockwood, C. Pusey)
2. 1988 Copenhagen, Denmark (A. Wiik, N. Rasmussen)
3. 1989 Noordwijkerhout, The Netherlands (F. van der Woude, C. Kallenberg)
4. 1990 Washington, DC, USA (J.C. Jennette, R. Falk)
5. 1992 Lubeck, Germany (W. Gross)
6. 1995 Paris, France (P. Lesavre, L.H. Noel)
7. 1996 Rochester, USA (R. DeReeme)
8. 1998 Birmingham, United Kingdom (P. Bacon)
9. 2000 Groningen, The Netherlands (C. Kallenberg, J.W. Cohen Tervaert)
10. 2002 Cleveland, USA (G. Hoffman, L. Calabrese)
11. 2003 Prague, Czech Republic (V. Tesar)
12. 2005 Heidelberg, Germany (K. Andrassy)
13. 2007 Cancun, Mexico (L.F. Flores-Suarez)
14. 2009 Lund/Copenhagen, Sweden/Denmark (M. Segelmark, N. Rasmussen)
15. 2011 Chapel Hill, USA (R. Falk, J.C. Jennette)
16. 2013 Paris, France (L. Guillevin)
17. 2015 London, United Kingdom (C. Pusey, A. Salama)
18. 2017 Tokyo, Japan (Y. Arimura)
19. 2019 Philadelphia, USA (P. Merkel)
20. 2022 Dublin, Ireland (M. Little, M. Clarkson)
21. 2024 Barcelona, Spain (M. Cid, G. Espígol-Frigolé)
22. 2026 Melbourne, Australia (A.R. Kitching, C. Hill, V. Quincey)

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This is the Version of Record.

Abstracts and titles within the Workshop App are presented as submitted. In this publication, some abstracts have been reformatted and undergone minor changes for stylistic consistency.

O-01

RNA sequencing of giant cell arteritis lesions uncovers the molecular landscape of early treatment response and reveals predictors of refractory and relapsing disease

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is primarily managed with high-dose glucocorticoids despite significant toxicity. Tocilizumab offers a glucocorticoid-sparing alternative, but access is limited, and high glucocorticoid dependence remains a major therapeutic challenge. Here, we delineate the molecular landscape of early glucocorticoid response in GCA tissue, revealing biological insights and candidate pathways for therapeutic intervention. Additionally, we identify molecular predictors of refractory/relapsing disease that may improve GCA management.

Methods: RNA-sequencing of baseline temporal artery biopsies from GCA (n=108; mean age=73.9 [59-91]; %female=58.8) and non-GCA individuals (n=16; mean age=65 [46-84]; %female=68.7) was performed. Differential expression (DE) analysis across stratified groups based on glucocorticoid exposure (median=5 days [0-23]) was conducted to reveal genes/pathways persistently dysregulated or suppressed during treatment. Additionally, comparisons with refractory/relapsing GCA (UK tocilizumab requirement) and patients permanently discontinuing glucocorticoids within 18 months were performed. All findings were corrected for multiple testing.

Results: DE analysis revealed extensive transcriptional changes across steroid exposure groups (≤ 3 , 4-6, ≥ 7 days) with a predominance of upregulated genes (~75%) and the greatest number of DE genes (n=3,902) during early response (≤ 3 days). After ≥ 7 days, upregulated genes and pathways diverged from the core immune activation signature, showing more vascular and stromal profiles. The cytokine/cytokine receptor pathway was one of the most significantly dysregulated pathways across all timepoints ($p=7.12 \times 10^{-18}$). Upregulation of multiple CC and CXC subfamily chemokines was observed at ≤ 3 days, with CCL4 and CXCL1/2/3/13 remaining persistently elevated after ≥ 7 days of treatment. Correspondingly, IL1A/12/13/17A/17E/29/35, LTB, IFNA and IFNG were upregulated ≤ 3 days with only IFNG remaining persistently elevated after ≥ 7 days. Dysregulated CHa cascades such as JAK-STAT pathway ($p=5.1 \times 10^{-2}$) were observed in patients who experienced refractory/relapsing disease.

Conclusions: We identified persistently dysregulated genes and pathways in GCA patients post-glucocorticoid treatment, highlighted potential therapeutic targets, and found early molecular signatures predictive of refractory/relapsing GCA. Further analyses are underway.

O-02

Digital FDG PET/CT as first-line diagnostic modality for cranial giant cell arteritis: results from an international prospective cross-sectional study

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Background/Aims: Diagnosis of giant cell arteritis (GCA) is challenging and relies mainly on temporal artery biopsy and/or Doppler ultrasound (DUS). Although FDG PET/CT is the test of choice in patients with suspected large vessel (LV)-GCA, its use was previously limited for cranial artery GCA (C-GCA) detection, primarily due to the small size of these arteries. Digital PET/CT devices have significantly improved PET resolution and allow accurate imaging of smaller structures. This study investigates the diagnostic accuracy of digital PET/CT and DUS in patients with suspected GCA.

Methods: Patients aged ≥ 50 years with suspected GCA based on classical symptoms and inflammatory markers (CRP ≥ 10 mg/L and/or ESR ≥ 30 mm/h) were prospectively enrolled in 5 centres across Canada, France, and the Netherlands. Exclusion criteria included corticosteroids >3 days prior to PET/CT or prior history of vasculitis. PET/CT scans were interpreted independently by two blinded readers using visual grading scales; in case of disagreement, a third blinded reader adjudicated. Final clinical diagnosis at 6 months served as reference standard.

Results: Eighty-four subjects (47 women, 37 men; mean age: 72 years; mean CRP: 70.7 mg/L) met the inclusion criteria, with mean follow-up of 27 months (range 6-74). GCA was diagnosed in 44/84 (52.4%) patients. Of these, PET/CT correctly identified 38 cases: 16 had isolated C-GCA, 6 had isolated LV-GCA, and 16 had both. Sensitivity of PET/CT increased from 50.0% (95%CI: 34.6-65.4%) when assessing large vessels alone to 86.4% (95%CI: 72.7-94.8%) with the addition of cranial vessel evaluation, while specificity remained unchanged at 100.0% (95%CI: 91.2-100.0%). DUS demonstrated sensitivity 68.2% (95%CI: 52.4-81.4%) and specificity 92.5% (95%CI: 79.6-98.4%). PET/CT inter-observer agreement was near-perfect for both C-GCA ($\kappa=0.950$) and LV-GCA ($\kappa=0.909$).

Conclusions: Digital FDG PET/CT demonstrates high diagnostic accuracy and inter-observer reliability for diagnosing C-GCA, supporting its potential role as a first-line modality in evaluating suspected GCA.

O-03

The role of leucine rich alpha-2 glycoprotein-1 in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a rare autoimmune disease characterised by inflammation of small/medium vessels, driven by autoantibodies against proteinase 3 (PR3) and myeloperoxidase (MPO), leading to neutrophil activation and endothelial injury. Leucine-rich alpha-2 glycoprotein-1 (LRG1), secreted by neutrophils, endothelial cells, and hepatocytes, has been implicated in AAV. This study investigates LRG1 as a biomarker or mediator in AAV.

Methods: Serum and urine LRG1 were measured by ELISA in active AAV (aAAV, n=154), remission AAV (rAAV, n=100), IgA nephropathy (IgAN, n=14) and healthy volunteers (HV, n=102). Associations with demographics, clinical features, BVAS, ANCA titre and CRP were assessed. Lrg1 mRNA expression in kidney biopsies was analysed by RNAscope. Neutrophil LRG1 release and localisation to NETs were evaluated following stimulation with conventional and ANCA IgG.

Results: Serum LRG1 was significantly higher in aAAV than rAAV, IgAN or HV (197.8 vs 84.1, 80.8, 58.6 µg/ml; P<0.01). It correlated with BVAS (r=0.50), ANCA titre (r=0.47) and CRP (r=0.54, all p<0.0001). Steroid treatment reduced serum LRG1. Urine LRG1 was significantly elevated in aAAV (3419 vs 193 ng/ml in remission) independent of urine creatinine/protein and correlated with urinary CD163 (r=0.38, p=0.024). RNAscope localised Lrg1 to crescents, interstitial infiltrates and tubules, with highest expression in crescentic disease, correlating with % crescentic glomeruli (r=0.62, p=0.024). RNAscope revealed Lrg1 expression localised to active glomerular lesions, and both urine LRG1 and tissue Lrg1 correlated with Berden disease class. Immunofluorescence confirmed LRG1 in neutrophil granules, released after stimulation with FMLP, LPS, PMA and ANCA-IgG. LRG1 was detected on ANCA-induced NETs.

Conclusions: LRG1 is a potential diagnostic and activity biomarker in AAV, distinguishing active disease from remission, and reflecting renal involvement. Urine LRG1 may enable non-invasive monitoring. Localisation to crescents and release from activated neutrophils/NETs supports a pathogenic role, highlighting LRG1 as a potential therapeutic target.

O-04

Kidney outcomes in ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis according to induction immunosuppression across histopathological groups: the REASSESS study

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Background/Aims: Cyclophosphamide (CYC) and rituximab (RTX), alone or in combination, are the mainstays of induction therapy in anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-glomerulonephritis. It is unknown whether the response to induction therapies is differentially affected by kidney histopathological features.

Methods: This is a retrospective, multicentric study including patients with biopsy-proven ANCA-glomerulonephritis. Cases were grouped according to kidney histopathology, using the Berden classification. Kidney recovery at 6 months was defined as an increase in eGFR \geq 15 ml/min/1.73m² or the ability to discontinue kidney replacement therapy; kidney failure was defined as sustained eGFR <15 mL/min/1.73m² or long-term kidney replacement therapy. Multivariable regression models were used to explore factors independently associated with kidney outcomes across Berden classes.

Results: The cohort included 304 patients, with median baseline eGFR of 20 ml/min/1.73m² (IQR 11-35). Induction immunosuppression was CYC in 59%, RTX in 17% and RTX-CYC in 24%. Overall, 50% reached the kidney recovery endpoint and 19.4% had kidney failure over a median follow-up of 42 months (IQR 18-72). In the crescentic Berden class, the RTX group had lower chances of kidney recovery than CYC (OR 0.235, 95%CI 0.051-0.993, p=0.049); a similar trend was found in comparison with RTX-CYC (OR 0.204, 95%CI 0.029-1.219, p=0.082). In the crescentic Berden class, RTX monotherapy was marginally associated with increased risk of kidney failure, compared to both CYC (HR 3.34, 95%CI 0.96-9.89, p=0.056) and RTX-CYC (HR 5.29, 95%CI 0.99-33.14, p=0.051). No significant differences were observed in the other Berden classes.

Conclusions: Patients with crescentic class ANCA-glomerulonephritis receiving RTX monotherapy may have worse kidney outcomes compared to those treated with CYC-based regimens. Further studies are needed to validate these results and better understand how to personalize treatment.

O-05

Inhibiting claudin-1 preserves kidney function and limits histological injury in experimental ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Glomerulonephritis in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) may progress rapidly while immunosuppression is being commenced, suggesting adjunct therapies would be valuable. Claudin-1 (CLDN1) is a transmembrane tight junction protein aberrantly exposed in crescentic glomerulonephritis, promoting pro-fibrotic pathways. The monoclonal antibody (mAb) lixudebart (ALE.F02) selectively blocks exposed CLDN1 on activated renal epithelial cells and is not known to have immunosuppressive effects. This study investigated CLDN1 as a potential therapeutic target in a new MPO-AAV model.

Methods: Mice were primed with G-CSF and MPO-AAV was induced by transferring a cocktail of 3 mouse anti-mouse MPO mAbs on day 0 and day 10 (0.75mg/dose). Treatment with either anti-CLDN1 mAb, control mAb or cyclophosphamide and dexamethasone (CYC/DEX) commenced 6 days after disease induction. Disease was studied on days 6 and 21.

Results: On day 6, anti-MPO mAb induced necrotizing crescentic glomerulonephritis (glomerular crescents 31.6±3.7%, segmental necrosis 13.3±1.4%) and renal impairment (sCr anti-MPO mAb 40.5±2.1, irrelevant mAb 16.7±1.3µmol/L, P=0.0003). By day 21, there was progressive glomerular fibrosis (collagen-stained surface area day 6: 4.1±0.3%, day 21: 12.5±0.6%). Treatment with either CYC/DEX or anti-CLDN1 mAb from day 6 reduced haematuria, glomerular crescents (anti-CLDN1 mAb 19.1±1.7%, control mAb 31.4±2.6%, CYC/DEX 12.7±2.0%, p<0.0001) and limited segmental necrosis (anti-CLDN1 mAb 7.1±1.1%, control mAb 11.1±1.2%, CYC/DEX 4.2±0.7%, P=0.0006) at day 21. Both anti-CLDN1 mAb and CYC/DEX preserve kidney function (sCr anti-CLDN1 mAb 24.3±1.0, control mAb 34.1±0.8, CYC/DEX 24.2±1.5 µmol/L, P<0.0001) and reduce glomerular fibrosis (collagen-stained surface area: anti-CLDN1 mAb 9.7±0.7%, control mAb 12.5±0.6%, CYC/DEX 6.4±1.2%, P=0.0003). Renal leukocyte infiltrates (immunostaining and flow cytometry) were reduced by CYC/DEX but not anti-CLDN1 mAb (CD45+ cells: anti-CLDN1 1.19x10⁶±6.44x10⁴, control mAb 1.23x10⁶±10.72x10⁴, CYC/DEX 0.71x10⁶±3.20x10⁴, P=0.0006).

Conclusions: Treatment with anti-CLDN1 mAb in experimental MPO-AAV improved histological injury and kidney function. This study supports CLDN1 inhibition as a potential therapeutic strategy in the treatment of AAV.

Outcomes of very early treatment with mepolizumab in newly diagnosed EGPA: the MEPEARL study

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Background/Aims: Mepolizumab is effective in long-standing EGPA, but evidence on very early use is lacking.

Methods: Multinational retrospective cohort of adult EGPA patients (European EGPA Study Group) treated with mepolizumab 100 or 300 mg/4 weeks. "Very early" treatment was defined as the initiation within 3 months of EGPA diagnosis. Early-treated patients were compared with those treated later. Outcomes were remission (BVAS=0 with glucocorticoid \leq 4 mg/day) at 3, 6, 12, 24 months; glucocorticoid withdrawal; and VDI progression using inverse-probability-weighted landmark analyses.

Results: Of 561 patients included, 107 (19%) received very early mepolizumab (100 mg, n=47; 300 mg, n=60). Compared to later treatment (>12 months), early patients were older (55.4 ± 12.6 vs 48.7 ± 13.7 years, $p<0.001$), had lower BVAS (10 ± 10 vs 12 ± 8 , $p=0.048$), less peripheral neuropathy (43.3% vs 55.7%, $p=0.024$), but more gastrointestinal involvement (19.6% vs 12.0%, $p=0.040$). Initial dose distribution (100 vs 300 mg) was similar ($p=0.60$). In the early group, remission rates were 19.0%, 29.7%, 49.3% and 56.6% at 3/6/12/24 months, respectively. Within early starters, 300 mg outperformed 100 mg at 3–6 months (31.3% vs 11.5%, $p=0.025$; 45.5% vs 14.9%, $p=0.002$). Late treated showed higher remission rates at 3–6 months, whereas rates converged with no significant difference at 12 and 24 months. Proportion achieving glucocorticoid withdrawal increased over time in both strategies (24 months: 43.4% early vs 38.3% late; $p=0.40$), with no significant difference at any time point. Weighted risk of any VDI increase over the 12-month window was lower in early-treated patients than in those treated later. Over 24 months, 12 dose escalations (100 to 300 mg for inefficacy), 1 de-escalation (adherence), and 9 discontinuations occurred (3 adverse events within 12 months and 6 inefficacy after 12 months).

Conclusions: Very early mepolizumab treatment is associated with meaningful remission and steroid-sparing, without excess damage accrual. Compared to available literature [Wechsler-NEJM 2017; Bettiol-A&R 2022], early treatment accounted for higher remission.

O-07

Atypical presentation of the immunodominant human PR3 T cell epitope by HLA-DR15 to CD4⁺ T cells induces autoimmune kidney injury

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Background/Aims: PR3-AAV is associated with HLA-DP4 and HLA-DR15. Its study in rodents is limited in part due to poor homology between rodent and human proteinase 3 (hPR3). This study aims to identify the immunodominant CD4⁺ T cell epitope of hPR3 and its nephritogenicity in the context of HLA-DR15.

Methods: The immunodominant CD4⁺ T cell epitope was identified by IL-17A/IFN- γ ELISPOT ten days after immunization of hPR3.DR15 transgenic mice with hPR3 protein and peptides. hPR3 peptides presented by antigen-fed splenocytes were identified by immunoaffinity purification of HLA-DR15-peptide complexes and immunopeptidomics. The crystal structure of HLA-DR15-immunodominant PR3 peptide was resolved using X-ray crystallography. Epitope-specific TCRs of CD4⁺ T cells from immunized hPR3.DR15 mice and HLA-DR15⁺PR3-AAV patients were identified via single-cell TCR $\alpha\beta$ sequencing. The epitope's nephritogenicity was assessed by inducing anti-PR3 glomerulonephritis in hPR3.DR15 mice.

Results: Immunization with hPR3 protein and peptides identified hPR3 hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ as the sole peptide consistently eliciting autoimmunity. The full 16-mer length of hPR3 hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ is required for optimal autoreactivity as truncating hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ into 12-15 mers showed reduced reactivity and poor HLA-DR15 binding. Immunopeptidomics revealed hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ as one of only two peptides naturally presented by hPR3.DR15 splenocytes. The HLA-DR15- hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ crystal structure revealed a novel ligand binding mode with ten rather than nine amino acids occupying the HLA-DR15 antigen-binding cleft. hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁-specific TCRs of HLA-DR15-hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ tetramer-binding CD4⁺ T cells from immunized hPR3.DR15 mice and five HLA-DR15⁺PR3-AAV patients exhibited clonal expansion, biased TCR usage, and shared features between mice and human. Compared with OVA₃₂₃₋₃₃₉-immunized controls, hPR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁-immunized hPR3.DR15 mice challenged with anti-basement membrane globulin displayed more glomerular injury (5.9 \pm 2.1% vs. 37.1 \pm 14.3% glomeruli affected, $p < 0.05$), with increased glomerular and interstitial CD4⁺ T cell and macrophage infiltration.

Conclusions: PR3₂₁₆₋₂₃₁ is the immunodominant and nephritogenic CD4⁺ epitope in HLA-DR15⁺ PR3-AAV. Its unique binding to HLA-DR15 has fundamental implications for epitope prediction and understanding CD4⁺ T cell responses.

O-08

Complement receptor C5aR1 correlates with inflammatory responses and albuminuria driven by glomerular uPAR upregulation in renal vasculitides

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Background/Aims: Avacopan is a novel promising treatment for antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) targeting the complement system by blocking C5a receptor C5aR1. Notably, avacopan has previously been shown to improve long-term kidney function by early reduction of albuminuria. However, a mechanistic link between C5aR1 signalling and proteinuria remains elusive. Therefore, we here pursued a transcriptome array-based approach to dissect molecular signatures associated with C5aR1 in renal vasculitides.

Methods: C5aR1 mRNA expression levels (reporter ID: 210845_s_at, platform: Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array, altCDF v10) were extracted from microdissected samples of renal vasculitis (glomerular: n=23, tubulointerstitial: n=21). Pathway analysis was performed for gene enrichment associated with PLAUR mRNA expression with a correlation threshold of ≥ 0.5 by using reactome (<http://reactome.org>), pathways with a predefined entities value of $p \leq 0.001$ were included. Correlative findings were confirmed by spatial transcriptome and immunohistological analysis.

Results: We here identified a predominant glomerular expression of C5aR1 in renal vasculitis as compared to the tubulointerstitial compartment ($p < 0.0001$). Furthermore, glomerular C5aR1 induction correlated with impaired kidney function (eGFR: 0.0193). Gene set enrichment identified various inflammatory signatures including neutrophil degranulation and innate immunity, and particularly enrichment of urokinase plasminogen activator receptor (uPAR). uPAR itself also correlated with impairment of kidney function in renal vasculitis and particularly active glomerular lesions (cellular crescents and necrosis, $p < 0.0001$). Notably, we also identified a strong correlation with albuminuria.

Conclusions: The therapeutic implications of targeting uPAR in renal vasculitides are promising, and ongoing research endeavours are aimed at unravelling the complexities of uPAR as a potential diagnostic marker and therapeutic target for this challenging renal pathology, especially in proteinuric kidney diseases. We here expand our current knowledge and link C5aR1 to inflammatory responses driven by glomerular uPAR upregulation and provide first evidence for a mechanistic link to albuminuria in renal vasculitides.

O-09

A genome-wide association study uncovers genetic susceptibility for polyarteritis nodosa

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Background/Aims: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) is a rare medium vessel vasculitis affecting multiple organs. While its aetiology remains unknown, immune mechanisms are thought to contribute to the pathogenesis of PAN. The aim of this study was to identify genetic susceptibility loci associated with PAN by conducting the first genome-wide association study (GWAS) in this disease.

Methods: A total of 142 patients and 1,215 controls from Turkey, along with an independent cohort of 86 patients and 1,720 controls of European ancestry from the UK Biobank, were included in our study. Genotyping was performed using Illumina arrays or obtained from publicly available data, and genotype imputation was conducted with the TOPMed R2 reference panel. Quality control and genetic association analyses were performed in PLINK, adjusting for population structure.

Results: Following quality control, 132 patients and 1,211 controls from Turkey, and 76 patients and 1,546 controls from the UK Biobank were retained for genetic analysis. A total of three million single-nucleotide polymorphisms were analysed in the Turkish cohort, identifying two genetic susceptibility loci reaching genome-wide significance ($p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$). Significant associations were detected in HLA-B/MICA (rs9266353, OR [95% CI]= 0.36 [0.27-0.49], p -value= 3.46×10^{-11}) and MEFV (rs61752717, OR [95% CI]=4.37 [2.79-6.83], p -value= 9.85×10^{-11}), the latter being a rare variant previously linked to Familial Mediterranean Fever. A meta-analysis with the UK Biobank confirmed the association in the HLA-B/MICA region and revealed seven suggestive associations ($p < 1 \times 10^{-5}$), including SEMA4D (rs75058492, OR [95% CI]= 2.3 [1.63-3.25], p -value= 2.49×10^{-6}) and PACRG (rs9365501, OR [95% CI]= 0.41 [0.28-0.61], p -value= 9.88×10^{-6}), among others.

Conclusions: This study supports a genetic contribution to PAN aetiology and provides novel insights into its genetic susceptibility. Larger cohorts will be essential to validate and extend these findings.

O-10

Pathogenic insights from gene-based burden analysis of rare-coding variants in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a chronic, systemic inflammatory vasculitis of the medium and large arteries, which left untreated can lead to vision loss. Current GCA management entails treatment with high-dose glucocorticoids, which have a significant profile of adverse effects. Although genome-wide association studies have established the contribution of common genetic variants to GCA risk, the impact of rare-coding variants has yet to be comprehensively assessed. Identification of variants/genes may highlight molecular pathways and potential novel drug targets.

Methods: We performed genome-wide gene-based burden analyses using SKAT-O, a statistical method that combines burden and variance-component tests to estimate the association between rare genetic variants and a phenotype. Whole exome sequencing was performed by Regeneron Genetics on 1,500 GCA patients from the UKGCA Consortium (median age = 71y, 68.9% female), whilst 10,000 control samples (with no history of autoimmune diseases) were retrieved from UK Biobank. Rare-coding variants (minor allele frequency <1%) were functionally annotated and SKAT-O applied to those classed as either M1 (predicted loss-of-function, pLOF) or M2 (pLOF and missense variants). We also performed sub-analyses of 1,497 UKGCA patients with clinicodemographic data on cranial ischaemic complications (CICs) recorded at GCA presentation. Samples were categorised as no CICs (n=570), transient (n=672) or permanent (n=255).

Results: In the primary case-control analysis, we tested 4,674 and 17,266 gene-sets in the M1 and M2 groups, respectively. Following Bonferroni-correction, we found 123 and 603 significant ($P < 2.90 \times 10^{-6}$) gene-trait associations in the M1 and M2 groups, respectively. We observed no significant associations with genes on the Genomics England Autoinflammatory disorders panel. We identified no significant associations between subgroups in the CIC sub-analyses.

Conclusions: This study highlights the enrichment of rare-coding variants in GCA which may present as novel therapeutic targets, but currently there is no indication of an association with CIC at presentation.

O-11

Phenotype-specific immune signatures in Behçet's disease: a transcriptomic and cytokine based approach

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Background/Aims: Behçet's disease (BD) is a chronic multisystem inflammatory disorder with heterogeneous phenotypes, most commonly mucocutaneous, ocular, and vascular. Clarifying the differential contributions of innate and adaptive immune mechanisms across these subgroups may advance personalized therapeutic strategies.

Methods: Serum samples were collected from BD patients during active disease (aBD) and remission (rBD), classified by phenotype. Patients with overlapping or gastrointestinal/neurological involvement were excluded. Pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokine concentrations were quantified using sandwich ELISA. Transcriptomic profiling of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) was performed with Illumina NovaSeq6000 sequencing. Quality control included FastQC, Trimmomatic, HISAT2 alignment to hg38, and HTSeq read quantification. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified using DESeq2 and NOISeq. Comparative analyses focused on innate immunity, inflammasome activity, adaptive pathways, and angiogenesis-related gene networks.

Results: Forty-one aBD patients (median age 29 years; M/F 9/32), 35 rBD patients (M/F 9/26), and nine healthy controls (HC) (M/F 3/6) were analysed. Phenotypic distribution among aBD was: 19 mucocutaneous (m-aBD), 11 ocular (o-aBD), and 11 vascular (v-aBD). IFN- γ levels were elevated in aBD versus rBD (116 vs. 92 pg/ml, $p=0.022$). IL-35 was higher in HC compared with both aBD and rBD ($p=0.05$). IL-17-related cytokines were reduced in o-aBD but increased post-treatment, whereas they decreased in m-aBD and v-aBD. Transcriptome analysis confirmed lower Th17-related gene expression in o-aBD. Vascular BD displayed marked upregulation (4–13 fold) of angiogenesis and haematopoiesis-related genes (VEGF, HIF1A, FLT3). Distinct innate immune activation and inflammasome-related signatures further differentiated v-aBD from other groups.

Conclusions: Innate immunity and Th1-driven adaptive responses play central roles in BD pathogenesis, with phenotype-specific patterns. Suppressed Th17 responses in o-aBD may underlie the limited efficacy of IL-17 blockade in uveitis. Vascular BD is characterized by enhanced angiogenesis and inflammasome activation, offering insights for phenotype-tailored therapeutic strategies. These findings refine the immunopathogenic map of BD and may inform precision medicine approaches.

O-12

Single-cell analysis identifies monocyte signatures of disease activity and clinical subtypes in Behçet's disease

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Background/Aims: Behçet's disease (BD) is a chronic, relapsing vasculitis with limited therapeutic options. Monocytes are central to BD pathogenesis, yet how their transcriptional programmes shift with treatment and across clinical phenotypes remains unclear. We applied single-cell transcriptomics of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) and focused on classical, intermediate, and non-classical monocyte dynamics in BD.

Methods: A total of 50 PBMC samples from 46 individuals—34 BD patients (mucocutaneous, ocular, vascular) and 12 healthy controls—were profiled by scRNA-seq (10x Genomics GEM-X) with antibody-based hashing. After PBMC-wide clustering/annotation in Seurat v5, we modelled cell-type composition with sccomp and then subsetted monocytes (classical, intermediate, non-classical) for differential expression analyses spanning (i) BD patients vs healthy controls, (ii) phenotype-specific contrasts, and (iii) active vs remission disease state comparisons. Functional enrichment analyses identified overrepresented pathways.

Results: After QC, 251,924 PBMCs were analysed, recovering all major immune populations. BD demonstrated overall monocyte expansion, most pronounced in active disease and greatest in mucocutaneous BD. Classical monocytes upregulated interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs) and exhibited activation of cytokine-signalling pathways. Non-classical monocytes displayed a distinct signature with upregulated stress-response genes, cytotoxicity-associated effectors, and inflammasome components. Active-versus-remission analyses revealed treatment-reversed modules, including suppression of pre-treatment interferon signatures marked by GBP family members (e.g., GBP1/5). Phenotype comparisons showed: mucocutaneous BD with broad enrichment of interferon-stimulated genes; ocular BD with heightened NF- κ B/TNF signalling; and vascular BD with prominent heat shock protein (HSP)-mediated stress responses.

Conclusions: This study provides a comprehensive single-cell map of PBMCs in BD and reveals transcriptional remodelling across monocyte subsets toward a pro-inflammatory state. Interferon/JAK-STAT pathway activity and NF- κ B/TNF signalling emerge as candidates for stratified intervention, while GBP-family ISGs nominate testable biomarkers of disease activity and pharmacodynamic response. Our dataset prioritizes pathways that may influence tissue-specific manifestations in BD and provides a framework for mechanistic studies.

O-13

Transcriptomic profiling reveals mast cell signatures and active immune processes in chronic ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: In ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis (AAV-GN), histopathological classifications guide prognosis but the molecular mechanisms underlying different histopathological patterns remain poorly understood. We conducted a retrospective study to integrate transcriptomic signatures with histopathological findings, aiming to refine our understanding of AAV-mediated renal injury, identify potential therapeutic targets and improve prognostication.

Methods: We performed targeted RNA expression profiling of 750 immune-related genes using NanoString technology on kidney biopsy specimens from 199 AAV-GN patients selected from the Maine-Anjou and RENVAS registries. Transcriptomic signatures were analysed in relation to glomerular lesions (normal, crescentic, sclerotic), Berden classification, tubulointerstitial involvement, Renal Risk Score and ANCA Kidney Risk Score. pathway enrichment analyses identified key molecular signals. Immune cell deconvolution was performed to estimate leukocyte subsets. Gene-based signatures for predicting histological features were developed using LASSO regression.

Results: Transcriptomic profiles revealed robust immune activation across all histopathological classes. Contrary to the notion of “burnt-out” lesions, sclerotic glomeruli displayed strong expression of immunoinflammatory pathways, including TGF- β , mTOR, and immunometabolism pathways. Mast cell-related genes (e.g., CPA3, TPSAB1/B2) were enriched in advanced lesions (sclerotic glomeruli and interstitial fibrosis), which was further confirmed by immunohistochemistry. Tubulointerstitial damage showed a gradient of innate and adaptive immune responses. Gene-based signatures accurately predicted histological features ($R^2 \geq 0.88$).

Conclusions: This study highlights previously unrecognized molecular complexity in AAV-GN, identifying mast cells as potential mediators of chronic kidney damage and showing that even sclerotic lesions harbor immune activation. These findings provide new insights into disease mechanisms and identify novel therapeutic targets for personalized medicine approaches in AAV-GN.

O-14

Exploring the lifecourse “exposome” in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a systemic, relapse/remitting vascular autoimmune disease with an incompletely described aetiology. Various lifecourse exposures have been epidemiologically linked to AAV including Epstein-Barr virus, Streptococcus and Staphylococcus infections, and compounds like silica however there has been no detailed research into how lifecourse exposures influence AAV pathophysiology. Viral exposures are being linked to autoimmune diseases such as multiple sclerosis, Sjogren’s, systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis. We hypothesised that the lifecourse “exposome” may be overlooked in terms of AAV aetiology.

Methods: Herein we describe the peptide-level viral antigen lifecourse “exposome” of AAV patients, with a pilot cohort (40 AAV patients, MPO n=20, PR3 n=20) using VirScan, a PhIP-seq approach, implementing novel biostatistical workflows, Phippery and Bayesian Estimation of Enrichment in R.

Results: We have found sex, MPO-specific, age*sex, and creatinine effects on total virus antibody enrichment in this cohort. We have identified 17 viral peptides that are significantly associated with MPO ANCA, while 3 are associated with PR3 ANCA. Ongoing work is leveraging healthy controls VirScan data to investigate potential antigenic molecular mimicry at the viral proteome-level using a combination of linear and 3-D molecular modelling tools.

Conclusions: In this pilot cohort, MPO AAV patients show greater enrichment of viral antibodies than their PR3 counterparts, while female patients show greater enrichment than males. Female and male AAV patients appear to experience different age effects on their antibody repertoires. Some ANCA-epitope viral “molecular mimics” are enriched in this cohort, including EBNA2, a transcription factor, demonstrated to modulate autoimmune risk loci in other autoimmune cohorts including MS, RA. We aim to expand this analysis beyond viral exposure and interrogate novel PhIP-seq datasets generated in this cohort regarding non-viral antigenic exposures and finally, leverage matched AAV HLA sequence data, investigating predicted binding between putative molecular mimics and AAV-associated HLA alleles.

O-15

Age-related antigen discovery in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: The striking restriction of giant cell arteritis (GCA) to individuals over 50 years old suggests that age-related molecular changes may drive pathogenesis in this disease. The specific age-related mechanisms triggering this large-vessel vasculitis remain unknown, limiting diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Early histologic and recent spatial genomics studies of temporal artery biopsies reveal extensive antibody deposition in diseased tissue, suggesting autoantibody responses to unknown vascular antigens may play a role in disease pathogenesis.

Methods: To identify novel autoantibodies in patients with systemic vasculitis, a phage immunoprecipitation sequencing (PhIP-Seq) study was conducted among 956 patients with 6 different types of vasculitis and compared the results to over 60,000 samples from individuals without vasculitis. PhIP-seq is an unbiased approach to identify autoantibody targets across the entire human proteome. This method utilizes a library of 47-amino-acid peptides that cover the human genome cloned into T7 phage that are immunoprecipitated with patient antibodies and analysed via next-generation sequencing.

Results: PhIP-seq revealed autoantibodies targeting medin in 12 (5.1%) of 235 patients with GCA and 0% of individuals without vasculitis. Anti-medin autoantibodies were absent in other types of vasculitis except for 1/183 (0.5%) patients with Takayasu arteritis.

Conclusions: Unbiased, proteome-wide PhIP-seq identified autoantibodies to medin, connecting age-related amyloid accumulation to disease pathogenesis in GCA and implicating medin as a candidate autoimmune antigen. Medin is the most common human amyloid, found in the medial layer of large arteries of nearly all individuals over 50 years old. Medin is derived from the protein MFGE8, which has been associated with GCA in genome-wide association studies. Despite the relatively low seroprevalence, these antibodies may be clinically significant due to their high specificity for GCA and an established association between deposition of medin and pathology in GCA. A study seeking to validate these findings is under way.

O-16

Impact of relapse on accrual of damage in patients with relapsing ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Treatment for ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) aims to rapidly achieve remission and prevent relapses. Damage can result from disease or treatments administered. The RITAZAREM trial recruited patients with AAV at relapse and re-induced remission with rituximab (RTX) and glucocorticoids (GC). Patients achieving remission were randomised at month 4 to receive RTX (1000mg every 4 months; 5 doses) or azathioprine (AZA, 2 mg/kg/day) until month 24, and followed for 36–48 months. This post-hoc analysis assessed the impact of relapse on accrual of damage.

Methods: Patients randomized and followed for at least 12 months were included. Relapse was defined as return of disease activity with BVAS/WG ≥ 1 , and major relapse as development of item of major disease activity on BVAS/WG. Damage was measured using the Combined Damage Assessment (CDA).

Results: 98/165 patients relapsed: major in 39 and 32 had multiple relapses. Relapse was associated with a 2.28-fold increased hazard of acquiring a new item of damage (Cox model with relapse as time-dependent covariate). In multivariate analysis adjusting for ANCA (MPO vs PR3), flare (severe vs non-severe), GC induction (1 vs 0.5mg/kg/day), maintenance therapy (RTX vs AZA), and the occurrence of a serious adverse event, only relapse remained significantly associated with accumulation of damage. CDA increased over time across the whole cohort, but a significant mean change in the CDA from randomization was observed only in relapsing patients. No difference in increase in CDA was found between patients with single vs. multiple, or major vs minor relapses. Among patients who relapsed, CDA increased by 0.47 units/year, compared to 0.27 in individuals without relapse (linear mixed-effects model).

Conclusions: Among patients with relapsing AAV who achieve remission after re-induction therapy, additional relapses are associated with risk of developing new damage. Prevention of relapse and accrual of damage should be a priority in the management of AAV.

O-17

Myeloperoxidase antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies in interstitial lung disease and interstitial lung abnormalities: prevalence and risk of progression to microscopic polyangiitis in a UK cohort

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Background/aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis confers significant morbidity and mortality. Interstitial lung abnormalities (ILA) are common, and it is unknown how many patients progress to ANCA-associated interstitial lung disease (ILD). MPO-ANCA is frequently detected in the initial evaluation of ILD without concurrent features of vasculitis, although the risk of ANCA-associated vasculitis progression is not well described in European populations.

Methods: Here, we evaluated the presence of myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA at baseline in a large UK ILD and ILA cohort and progression to ANCA-associated vasculitis without initial features of active vasculitis.

Results: Baseline MPO-ANCA were present in 30/1026 (2.92%) patients with ILD and 1/83 (1.20%) with ILA. Patients diagnosed with hypersensitivity pneumonitis had the highest incidence of MPO-ANCA (3.23%). The presence of baseline MPO-ANCA conferred a 22.6% risk of developing microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) with a mean time to MPA development from ILD diagnosis of 546.9 (S.E.M±247.1) days. A higher baseline MPO-ANCA titre was associated with an increased risk of developing MPA (49.8U/ml (±38.1) vs 10.3U/ml (±14.7)) (p<0.001).

Conclusions: These findings suggest the need for clinical vigilance for vasculitis emergence in patients with baseline MPO-ANCA.

O-18

Timing, risk factors, and outcomes of IgA vasculitis nephritis: implications for follow-up duration

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Background/Aims: The optimal follow-up period for children with IgA vasculitis (IgAV) at risk of nephritis (IgAVN) is debated. Although IgAVN typically develops within 6 months, later onset has been reported. Prognosis for isolated haematuria is thought to be favourable, but evidence is limited. The aim of the study was to describe clinical characteristics of IgAVN and assess factors influencing outcomes.

Methods: From a national cohort of IgAV patients (2010–2024, EULAR/PRINTO/PRES criteria), we selected those with IgAVN followed ≥ 6 months at the largest tertiary centre. Statistical methods included t-test, log-rank test, and univariate Cox regression.

Results: Of 739 IgAV patients, 155 developed IgAVN. Ninety-two were followed >6 months. Median age at IgAVN diagnosis was 7.6 years. Nephritis occurred a median of 4 days (range 0–559) after IgAV onset. Fourteen patients (15.2%) had nephritic and six (6.5%) nephrotic syndrome. The majority presented with combined haematuria/proteinuria (43.5%) or isolated haematuria (41.3%); hypertension was seen in 22.8%. Joint and gastrointestinal symptoms increased nephritis risk. Treatments included glucocorticoids (50.5%), NSAIDs (33.3%), and immunosuppressants (17.2%). Persistent urinary abnormalities were present in 36.9% at 6 months, decreasing to 15.2% at 12 months ($p < 0.01$). Outcomes were favourable in 84.8%, suboptimal in 14.1%, and 1.1% developed renal failure—in a patient initially presenting with isolated haematuria. No significant outcome differences were observed between isolated haematuria and non-nephrotic proteinuria ($p = 0.74$), or between 6- and 12-month follow-up ($p = 1.0$). Notably, 4% developed IgAVN between 6 and 12 months.

Conclusions: IgAVN most often develops early but may occur after 6 months. Most children have favourable outcomes, and isolated haematuria does not confer a better prognosis than non-nephrotic proteinuria. Follow-up should be extended to at least 12 months.

O-19

Ophthalmic manifestations in relapsing polychondritis

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Background/Aims: Ocular involvement (OI) in relapsing polychondritis (RP) has not been well characterized. This study aimed to describe clinical features, and use of immunosuppressive agents (ISs) in patients with RP with and without OI.

Methods: Adult patients with RP were enrolled in a multicentre prospective observational cohort. Data included demographics, clinical manifestations, and IS use.

Results: Among 219 patients with RP, 105 (48%) had an OI, most commonly episcleritis (41%), scleritis (35%), and uveitis (22%). Overlapping episcleritis and scleritis were found in 10 (10%) patients, scleritis and uveitis in 9 (9%), and all three in 3 (3%). In the subset of patients (n=117) with longitudinal data 21(18%) had an OI at diagnosis, and 35 (30%) developed OI later. Scleral thinning and blindness were observed in 3 (7%) and 1 (2%) patient with OI, respectively. Patients with OI vs. without OI had higher rates of fever (n=24, 27%; vs n=15, 12%; p=0.007), arthritis (n=57, 63%; vs n=61, 47%; p=0.020), rash (n=32, 36%; n=15, 12%, p<0.001), oral ulcers (n=29, 32%; n=25, 19%; p=0.038), genital ulcers (n=20, 22%; n=10, 8%; p=0.003), cough (n=56, 62%; n=58, 45%, p=0.010), wheezing (n=31, 34%; n=26, 20%, p=0.020), sensorineural hearing loss (n=30, 33%; n=26, 20%, p=0.040), auricular deformity (n=16, 18%; n=7, 5%; p=0.006), and nasal bridge collapse (n=16, 18%; n=8, 6%; p=0.009). Patients with OI vs. without OI had higher rates use of non-biologic IS (n=79, 88%; n=95, 74%; p=0.010) and infliximab (n=22, 24%; n=10, 8%; p<0.001); use of GC was similar (n=82, 91%; n=121, 94%, p=0.560).

Conclusions: OI is common in RP, often developing after diagnosis, and may cause multiple eye problems. OI is associated with more severe disease, organ damage, and frequent use of IS. Monitoring for OI is important, as it may indicate more aggressive disease and guide treatment.

O-20

Musculoskeletal involvement in Takayasu arteritis assessed by PET/CT: an age-related tendency towards a PMR-like pattern

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a large-vessel vasculitis primarily affecting the aorta and its branches, usually in young adults. Musculoskeletal involvement in TAK has not been systematically characterized; while spondyloarthritis-like peripheral features have been reported¹, a polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR)-like pattern remains unclear. FDG-PET/CT enables semi-quantitative assessment of subclinical musculoskeletal inflammation and may clarify these patterns. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and distribution of musculoskeletal involvement in TAK using PET/CT compared with age- and sex-matched controls, and to explore whether a PMR-like pattern is associated with older age.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 95 PET/CT scans of clinically active TAK patients fulfilling ACR-1990 criteria. Musculoskeletal regions (joints, entheses, trochanteric, interspinous ligaments) were assessed semi-quantitatively using SUVmax and SUVmean. Lesion-to-liver ratios >1 defined positivity. Vascular activity was quantified by PETVAS. Controls were 49 individuals with negative work-up for lung masses.

Results: Patients (mean age 38.7±13.8;81F/14M) had mean PETVAS 3.9±7.2. No clinical arthritis, enthesitis or bursitis was observed. Vascular uptake was most frequent in the aortic arch (16.8%). Enthesitis rates were comparable between groups (p=0.650). Arthritis was more frequent in controls by SUVmax (p=0.047), whereas SUVmean suggested higher prevalence in TAK. Bilateral shoulder uptake was more frequent in TAK (11.6% vs. 4.1%, p=0.137), and bilateral hip uptake occurred at similar rates (11.6% vs.10.2%, p=0.804). Combined bilateral shoulder–hip uptake also tended to be higher in TAK (6.3% vs. 0%, p=0.072), though none reached statistical significance. Subclinical arthritis was associated with older age in TAK (62.4±8.9 vs.47.6±12.9 years, p=0.004). PMR-like shoulder–hip patterns were age-related, while enthesitis tended to occur in younger patients.

Conclusions: Subclinical musculoskeletal FDG uptake was generally more frequent in TAK, with PMR-like distributions emerging in older age and enthesitis in younger patients. These findings suggest that, in older individuals, TAK may display GCA/PMR-like musculoskeletal features. Larger cohorts and standardized imaging protocols are warranted. References: 1.Abacar.2024,May;43(5):1571-1578

O-21

Development of new arterial damage in Takayasu's arteritis

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Background/Aims: Damage is an irreversible consequence of disease. This study aimed to evaluate new arterial damage in Takayasu's arteritis (TAK).

Methods: Patients with TAK enrolled in a multicentre, prospective, observational cohort from North America, or seen at a single centre in Turkey, with data on vascular imaging were included. Imaging data at initial and last visit were compared to identify new lesions (stenosis, occlusions, aneurysms) in previously unaffected territories. Variables associated with new arterial damage were evaluated.

Results: The study included 204 patients with TAK with longitudinal imaging: 92% female; mean \pm SD age 41.2 (13.3) years; median (25th, 75th percentile) disease duration from diagnosis 0.85 (0, 4.2) years; median duration of follow-up 7.2 (4.2, 10.4) years. 95 patients (47%) were enrolled \leq 180 days from time of diagnosis (the "recently diagnosed" group). Median (25th, 75th percentile) time from first available imaging study to last available imaging study was 4.1 (1.6, 8.4) years. 72 patients (35%), 31 (43%) with recently diagnosed disease, had new arterial lesions in a previously unaffected territory. 36 patients (50%) had \geq 2 new lesions (range 2-9). The most commonly observed new lesions were left carotid artery (23 patients), abdominal aorta (12), left subclavian artery (12), celiac artery (12), right carotid artery (11), superior mesenteric artery (10). 73% of new lesions were stenotic. No differences were found among patients with and without new arterial lesions based on age, sex, time between imaging studies, recent diagnosis, or treatment.

Conclusions: Nearly one-third of patients with TAK develop new, often multiple, arterial lesions during follow-up, indicating significant burden of disease despite treatment. The majority of new lesions are stenotic. Serial imaging remains important to monitor disease progression in TAK. To better capture the longitudinal arterial damage that occurs, indices of damage in TAK should include data derived from vascular imaging.

O-22

Impact of immunosuppression on collateral formation in Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Takayasu's arteritis (TAK) is a rare, granulomatous large-vessel vasculitis affecting the aorta and its major branches typically seen in young females. Progressive luminal stenosis may be compensated by collateral vessel formation, though the effect of immunosuppressive therapies on this process remains poorly understood. This study investigates whether treatment influences collateral formation and progression in TAK.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted on 123 TAK patients from a tertiary vasculitis clinic between 2007–2025. All had at least two high-quality magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) scans. Patients were grouped into no therapy, only conventional DMARDs (cDMARDs), or biologic DMARDs (bDMARDs). Collateral presence and progression were evaluated by side-by-side MRA review. Multivariable logistic regression assessed associations between treatment and collateral progression, adjusting for clinical and temporal confounders.

Results: Collateral vessels were observed in 51% of patients at baseline. Thirteen patients demonstrated collateral progression, while five developed new collaterals. Univariate analysis showed significantly lower odds of collateral progression with bDMARDs compared to cDMARDs (OR=0.263, p=0.047); this was attenuated in adjusted models. Time between scans was the strongest predictor of collateral progression (OR=1.020, p=0.012). Prior vascular surgery was associated with reduced collateral progression (OR=0.154, p=0.033).

Conclusions: Biologic therapies in TAK may blunt clinically important collateral formation. Biologics may limit angiogenesis by selectively suppressing IL-6 and TNF-driven VEGF signalling, whereas cDMARDs may allow persistence of low-grade inflammatory stimuli that facilitate arteriogenesis. The observed trend toward reduced collaterals in bDMARD patients, though not statistically significant in adjusted models, aligns with proposed antiangiogenic effects of intensive immunosuppression. These findings support further studies to determine when biological treatments can be stopped in TAK. Planned withdrawal of biologic treatment in those in remission may promote collateral formation in those with symptomatic or organ threatening chronic arterial stenoses improving outcomes and quality of life for those living with TAK.

O-23

A withdrawal study of colchicine in Behçet syndrome

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Background/Aims: Previous randomized-controlled studies reported conflicting results regarding the effectiveness of colchicine on oral ulcers in Behçet syndrome (BS). We aimed to assess mucocutaneous disease activity after 12 weeks in BS patients who discontinued colchicine.

Methods: This is a single centre, randomized-controlled, single-blind trial (NCT06146192). BS patients with mucocutaneous and joint disease but no major organ involvement for at least 2 years were included. An independent observer who was blinded to group allocations performed all assessments. At the end of a 12-week observational period during which all patients continued to use colchicine, patients were randomized to continue or withdraw colchicine for 12 weeks. Randomization was stratified (1:1) according to disease activity, disease duration, sex. Primary endpoint was the mean number of oral ulcers at week 12 after randomization.

Results: A total of 141 patients were randomized to continue (70; 45F/25M) or withdraw (71; 46F/25M) colchicine. The mean number of oral ulcers at week 12 was higher in colchicine withdrawal group compared to patients who continued colchicine (2.7 ± 2.6 vs 0.9 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.001$). This significant difference was observed among both patients who were active at randomization (4.3 ± 2.6 vs 1.4 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.001$), and in those with minimal disease activity (1.1 ± 1.7 vs 0.5 ± 1.0 , $p = 0.046$). The number of genital ulcers, erythema nodosum-like lesions and papulopustular lesions, pain of oral and genital ulcers, and Behçet's disease current activity form (BDCAF), Behçet's syndrome activity scale (BSAS) scores were higher in the colchicine withdrawal group. Major organ manifestations were observed in 4 patients in the colchicine withdrawal group; deep vein thrombosis (n=2), myocarditis (n=1), and peripheral artery disease (n=1).

Conclusions: The significantly higher number of oral ulcers and other mucocutaneous lesions in patients who discontinued colchicine suggests that colchicine is effective for oral ulcers in some patients with BS and supports its efficacy in managing mucocutaneous involvement of BS.

Two-year efficacy of anti-interleukin-5/receptor therapies according to anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody status in patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: The MANDARA trial (NCT04157348), comparing anti-interleukin-5/receptor (anti-IL-5/R) therapies, demonstrated that over 60% of patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) achieved remission, and over 40% discontinued oral glucocorticoids (OGCs). This analysis evaluated the efficacy of anti-IL-5/R therapies in patients with EGPA according to ANCA status over the combined 1-year double-blind (DB) and first year of the ongoing open-label extension (OLE) periods.

Methods: Patients entering the OLE, either continued benralizumab or switched from mepolizumab to benralizumab. Remission (defined as Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS)=0 and OGC \leq 4 mg/day), OGC reduction and disease activity (BVAS and Vasculitis Damage Index [VDI]), was assessed according to patients' ANCA status, up to Week 104. ANCA-positive patients were defined as those positive for myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA and/or proteinase 3 (PR3)-ANCA at study screening or with a historical record of ANCA-positivity.

Results: Of 128 patients, 35 (27.3%) were ANCA-positive and 93 (72.7%) were ANCA-negative at trial entry (baseline). BVAS and VDI scores were similar between the ANCA-positive and -negative groups at baseline, whereas the proportion of patients who had an ACQ-6 score \geq 1.5 was higher, and the time since diagnosis was shorter in the ANCA-positive versus -negative group. At Week 104, the proportion of patients achieving remission was similar, regardless of ANCA status (ANCA-positive: 65.7%, ANCA-negative: 64.5%; difference: 3.18; 95% confidence interval: -15.19, 21.56, $p=0.7341$). During Weeks 101–104, 65.7% and 69.9% in the ANCA-positive and -negative groups, had a reduction in OGC dose of \geq 50% from baseline, and 45.7% versus 43.0%, respectively, were fully withdrawn from OGCs. The proportion of patients with \geq 1 relapse was similar between ANCA-positive (37.1%) and ANCA-negative groups (44.1%). Most patients had \leq 3 or no relapses (ANCA-positive: 97.1%; ANCA-negative: 93.5%).

Conclusions: In patients with EGPA, historic or baseline ANCA status was not associated with response to treatment with anti-IL-5/R therapies.

Efficacy and safety of upadacitinib in giant cell arteritis: 2-year results from the re-randomized, double-blind SELECT-GCA phase 3 trial

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Background/Aims: In SELECT-GCA, upadacitinib 15 mg (UPA15) demonstrated superior rates of remission, fewer flares, and reduced glucocorticoid (GC) use vs placebo (PBO) in giant cell arteritis (GCA). This study reports 2-year outcomes from the trial.

Methods: In the 52-week (W) PBO-controlled period 1 (P1), patients with active GCA were randomized to UPA15/UPA7.5 QD with 26W GC taper or PBO with 52W taper. The 52W blinded extension (P2) included patients with ≥ 24 Ws of consecutive remission before W52. Patients receiving UPA were re-randomized (2:1) to continue UPA or switch to PBO. Patients receiving PBO remained on PBO. Efficacy was evaluated through W104. Safety included all patients with ≥ 1 dose study drug in P1 who continued same treatment in P2, with exposure-adjusted treatment-emergent adverse events (TEAEs) reported through 2 years.

Results: Of 428 patients, 181 (42%) entered P2 after ≥ 24 Ws of sustained remission before W52; 91% completed the study, 82% remained on study drug. From W52–104, 68.6% of patients on continuous UPA15 maintained remission vs 28.6% who switched to PBO. Continuous UPA15 reduced risk of flare by 90% from W52–104 and reduced cumulative GC exposure vs switching from UPA15 to PBO. Safety was similar between UPA and PBO in patients who continued same treatment in P2. Rates of serious TEAEs were lower for both UPA doses than PBO. Compared to PBO, UPA15 showed lower rates of serious infections but higher rates of herpes zoster and elevated CPK. One VTE occurred with UPA15 and none in other groups. No MACE or deaths occurred in P2.

Conclusions: In SELECT-GCA, continuous UPA15 in patients achieving ≥ 24 Ws of remission during period 1, rather than switching to PBO, was associated with maintenance of remission. No new clinically significant safety risks were identified.

O-27

Drug-free survival in giant cell arteritis – efficacy and safety of the Norwich prednisolone regimen

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Background/Aims: There is no consensus prednisolone regimen for Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA). The Norwich prednisolone regimen (NPR) delivers 164.6 mg/kg lean body mass over 100 weeks. It was designed to optimise the risk of relapse. The best estimate of drug-free remission is reported to be 21%. 80% of patients experience steroid-related adverse events (SrAE). We present the relapse risk, drug-free survival and risk of SrAE of NPR .

Methods: Retrospective analysis of consecutive patients with GCA treated with NPR between 2017–2022. Our follow-up protocol includes checks of HbA1c, blood pressure, osteoporosis prophylaxis and ultrasonography to diagnose relapse. Relapse rate at 100 and 150 weeks (the last 50-weeks off prednisolone), incidence of SrAE including new diabetes, myocardial-infarction, stroke, hypertension, fractures, psychosis, infection and adrenal insufficiency, were noted.

Results: 255 consecutive patients with GCA (171 female) were included. Median (IQR) age at diagnosis 76 (10) years. 220/24/11 were diagnosed on ultrasonography/ temporal artery biopsy/ 18-FDG-PET/CT. 179/46/30 had cranial/extracranial/mixed phenotype. 166/255 (65.1%) came off prednisolone at 100 weeks, 143/255 (56.1%) remained off prednisolone at 150 weeks. 35 died; 77 relapsed at a median (IQR) of 82 (41) weeks, at a median (IQR) daily prednisolone dose of 2 (5.5) mg and a median (IQR) total cumulative dose of 7.0 (1.5) g. 96/255 (37.6%) patients experienced SrAE by 100 weeks, including 19/255 (7.5%) diabetes, 3/255 (1.2%) myocardial infarction, 5/255 (2.0%) stroke, 5/255 (2.0%) hypertension, 15/255 (5.9%) osteoporotic fracture, 3/255 (1.2%) psychosis, 37/255 (14.5%) infection requiring hospital admission (2 required ITU), 25/255 (9.8%) had symptomatic adrenal suppression.

Conclusions: The Norwich prednisolone regimen is effective – 65% complete the regimen without relapse. Drug-free survival is sustained in 56% over the next 50 weeks. The SrAE risk of 38% is lower than previously reported. Our work demonstrates that the NPR is effective and safe for managing GCA.

Serious infectious complications in ANCA-associated vasculitis: incidence and the impact of plasma exchange and glucocorticoid regimen

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Background/Aims: Serious infections are a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). This study assessed their incidence and the impact of plasma exchange (PLEX) and glucocorticoid (GC) regimens on risk of serious infections.

Methods: This was a post-hoc analysis of the PEXIVAS study (NCT00987389), a randomized trial comparing: 1) PLEX versus no-PLEX; and 2) standard- versus reduced-dose GC regimens in patients with severe AAV, including active glomerulonephritis and/or diffuse alveolar haemorrhage. The study objectives included evaluation of incidence, timing, site and aetiology distribution, and the impact of randomized therapies on the 1-year risk of serious infection (requiring intravenous antibiotics or hospitalization).

Results: Over a median follow-up of 35 months (interquartile range: 18-51 months), 286/704 patients (41%) experienced 510 serious infections. Recurrent infections occurred in 127 (18%) patients. The incidence of first serious infection was 9.1 per 100 person-years (95% CI: 8.1–10.2), while the overall event rate was 25.1 (95% CI: 22.9–27.3). Incidence peaked at week 2 (18.6 per 100 patient-months), declined sharply by year 1, and stabilized thereafter. Respiratory tract infections predominated (46%), followed by urinary (15%) and gastrointestinal (14%). Patterns were consistent over time and across treatment groups. Within 12 months, 217 patients experienced a serious infection: 116/352 (33%) in PLEX vs. 101/352 (29%) in no-PLEX, and 117/351 (33%) in standard-GC vs. 100/353 (28%) in reduced-GC groups. Although numerically higher in PLEX and standard-GC arms, these differences were not statistically significant (PLEX: HR 1.18, 95% CI: 0.90–1.55; standard-GC: 1.26, 95% (CI: 0.96–1.65).

Conclusions: Serious infections are frequent and an early complication in severe AAV. While between-group differences in first infections in PLEX vs. no-PLEX and standard vs. reduced-GC were not statistically significant, the main PEXIVAS findings showed higher overall burden of infections with standard vs. reduced GC regimen.

Autopsy-based spatial analysis of ANCA-glomerulonephritis showing distribution of crescentic lesions

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Background/Aims: Little is known about the spatial organisation of glomerular lesions in ANCA-glomerulonephritis (ANCA-GN), because kidney biopsies are small and opportunities to study the entire kidney in acute disease onset are exceedingly rare. A central question in our evaluation of kidney biopsies is their representability. Whether ANCA-GN shows any spatial organisation has never been evaluated at whole-kidney scale. A rare, early and fatal case of granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), combined with spatial analysis driven by machine learning, allowed us to investigate these issues.

Methods: Two kidneys obtained at autopsy were available. From each, one full-length slice was taken, subdivided into sixteen paraffin-embedded sections, stained with standard histological stains, and digitized. Over 5000 glomeruli were available for evaluation. Glomerular lesions were classified based on the Berden classification. Spatial coordinates from each glomerular lesion type were vectorized to analyse distribution patterns, proximity relationships, and positioning relative to cortical boundaries and arterial structures. A supervised machine-learning model was trained to detect non-random organisation. To evaluate biopsy reliability, we simulated 1000 standard lower-pole biopsies.

Results: Lesions in 5019 glomeruli corresponded to the focal Berden class. Spatial analysis revealed no significant intra- or inter-lesion clustering, indicating a homogeneous distribution of glomerular lesions. Subtle anatomical trends—such as enrichment near the outer cortex or adjacent to vessels—were observed in 3/16 sections, and the machine-learning model independently detected spatial trends in 9/16 sections. Of 1000 simulated biopsies, 910 were adequate, with focal class predicted in ~90%.

Conclusions: This analysis of early GPA demonstrates an even distribution of glomerular lesions, supporting good reliability of renal biopsy for diagnostic and prognostic assessment. Weak but reproducible anatomical trends suggest that subtle microanatomical or immune factors may influence where injury develops. Spatial pathology and computational modelling can refine the interpretation of renal injury in ANCA-GN and open new avenues for AI-driven studies.

O-30

Transcriptome analysis of temporal artery and aortic lesions highlights vessel-specific chemotaxis in GCA

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is an inflammatory vasculitis of medium and large arteries with a spectrum of phenotypes. Cranial-GCA is associated with blindness and positive temporal artery (TA) biopsies, while large-vessel GCA more often presents with PMR and aortic complications. The basis for differing vessel involvement is unknown. Histopathology shows T-cell–dominant infiltrates in TAs, while more B-cells and developed artery tertiary lymphoid organs (ATLOs) are found in aortas. We hypothesize that gene expression differences, particularly in pathways of cell recruitment and adhesion, may underlie these patterns.

Methods: Three transcriptome analyses were completed: (1) TA biopsies from biopsy-positive GCA (n=21) versus controls (n=30), RNAseq; (2) aortic tissue from GCA (n=19) versus atherosclerotic controls (n=19), RNAseq (GSE224526); (3) sarcoid versus controls across four tissues (skin, lacrimal gland, orbit, lung; GSE32887, GSE105149, GSE58331, GSE16538), microarray. Differential expression (DE) was assessed with DESeq2 or GEO2R. Pathways of chemokines, cell adhesion molecules (CAM), and fibrosis-related genes (FRG) were obtained from Reactome and FibROAD.

Results: DE genes included 2,261 in GCA-TA, 9,078 in GCA-aorta, and 1,142 in sarcoid. The 135 genes shared across all most likely reflect non-specific granulomatous inflammation. Genes (1,777) significant in both GCA-TA and GCA-aorta but not sarcoid included 35 CAM, 9 chemokines, and 48 FRG. TA-specific genes (342) included 5 CAM, 4 chemokines, and 13 FRG; CCL22 was most upregulated ($\log_2FC4.0$) of these chemokines and is known to recruit activated t-lymphocytes, a hallmark of TA lesions. Aorta-specific genes (6,714) included 40 CAM, 13 chemokines, and 85 FRG; CXCL13 was most upregulated ($\log_2FC4.4$), and has been reported elevated in circulating B cells in GCA-PMR. CXCL13 may be an integral agent in ALTOs in aortic lesions.

Conclusions: This integrated transcriptome-wide analysis in TA and aortic tissues in GCA highlights vessel-specific chemotaxis, advancing understanding of vascular involvement and informing biomarker and therapeutic development.

O-31

In vivo expansion of regulatory T cells via an engineered IL-2 mutein to suppress anti-basement membrane disease

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Background/Aims: Anti-glomerular basement membrane (anti-GBM) disease is a fulminant small-vessel vasculitis characterised by rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis and pulmonary haemorrhage. Despite plasma exchange and aggressive immunosuppression, kidney outcomes remain poor, highlighting the need for more targeted and disease-modifying therapies. Regulatory T (Treg) cells play a central role in maintaining immune tolerance and have emerged as a promising therapy for autoimmune diseases. We engineered a novel IL-2 mutein with enhanced selectivity for Treg cells and tested its therapeutic effects for experimental anti-GBM disease.

Methods: We engineered a novel IL-2 mutein, STS718, by introducing point mutations to enhance Treg selectivity and fusing it to a human IgG1 Fc domain to prolong its half-life. Binding affinity and bioactivity of STS718 toward IL-2 receptors were assessed using surface plasmon resonance analysis and pSTAT5 assays in HEK-Blue reporter cells and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs). The therapeutic efficacy of STS718 was tested in experimental anti-GBM mouse models. Naïve CD4 T cells of healthy donors and PBMCs of anti-GBM patients were cultured with STS718 to further confirm its ability to expand human Treg cells.

Results: STS718 exhibited reduced affinity for IL-2 receptor IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ but comparable affinity for IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$, compared with wild-type IL-2-Fc of human, rat, and mouse. STS718 expanded Treg cells in mice and cynomolgus monkeys in a time- and dose-dependent manner, without significantly activating effector T cells. Proof-of-concept studies demonstrated that sustainable Treg expansion by STS718 effectively suppressed the progression of experimental anti-GBM disease in mice. Furthermore, STS718 was able to induce the expansion of human Treg cells in vitro from naïve CD4+T cells of healthy donors and from PBMCs of patients with anti-GBM disease.

Conclusions: The engineered IL-2 mutein ST718 selectively expand Treg cells in vivo and represents a promising immunotherapy for anti-GBM disease, with the potential to reduce reliance on nonspecific immunosuppression in severe vasculitis. **Keywords:** regulatory T cells; interleukin-2 mutein; autoimmunity; autoimmune glomerulonephritis; immunotherapy

O-32

Secukinumab in patients with polymyalgia rheumatica: week 52 results of a phase 3, multicentre, randomized, double blind, placebo-controlled trial (REPLENISH)

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) is the second most common inflammatory rheumatic disease of older adults (≥ 50 years) and is associated with long-term glucocorticoid (GC) use. Nearly half of PMR patients relapse despite GC treatment, and increased cumulative GC exposure is associated with multiple adverse outcomes. Elevated IL-17A levels and Th17 cells are observed in patients with PMR. Secukinumab, a fully human monoclonal antibody, selectively neutralizes IL-17A. The Phase 3 REPLENISH trial (NCT05767034) evaluated the efficacy and safety of secukinumab in PMR patients.

Methods: REPLENISH is a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial that enrolled adults aged ≥ 50 years with relapsing PMR. Patients were randomized (1:1:1) to receive secukinumab 300 mg (SEC-300), 150 mg (SEC-150), or placebo for 52 weeks, each combined with a protocol-specified 24-week prednisone taper regimen. The primary objective was to determine superiority of SEC-300 over placebo in achieving sustained remission at week (WK) 52. Key secondary endpoints included complete sustained remission, cumulative GC dose, patient-reported outcomes and safety at WK52.

Results: Overall, 381 patients were randomized. The study met its primary and all secondary endpoints. The proportion of patients achieving sustained remission at WK52 was significantly higher in both secukinumab arms vs. placebo (SEC-300: 41.2% vs. 20.4%, $p=0.0002$; SEC-150: 40.6% vs. 20.4%, $p=0.0003$). Patients in the secukinumab arms used significantly lower GC dose during the trial than in the placebo arm (adjusted annual GC dose: SEC-300=1603.7 mg, SEC-150=1683.2 mg, placebo=2093.0 mg). Secukinumab showed a consistent safety profile in alignment with approved indications and no new safety signals were identified.

Conclusions: Both doses of secukinumab, combined with a 24-week prednisone taper, demonstrated significant efficacy, including a GC-sparing effect, in patients with PMR, doubling the proportion of those achieving sustained remission compared to placebo plus a 24-week prednisone taper. Safety was in alignment with the known safety profile of secukinumab.

Kidney endpoints in ANCA-associated vasculitis – proposal of the European Vasculitis Society Focus Group

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Background/Aims: Numerous clinical trials have investigated kidney outcomes in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Definitions vary greatly with an unmet need for a reliable assessment on recovery and long-term stability of kidney function for both established and newly developed drugs. Kidney response criteria require optimization to better define kidney endpoints for drug development.

Methods: A European Vasculitis Society (EUVAS) Focus Group formed to review the literature and discuss the wide range of definitions used for kidney endpoints in ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis (ANCA GN).

Results: The group created a proposal outlining standardized clinical assessments in ANCA GN encouraging initial and repeat kidney biopsies. The aim is to determine the ideal timepoint of haemoproteinuria resolution, the optimal treatment response and kidney recovery as well as long-term kidney function trajectories. A delta-eGFR of 15-20 ml/min at week 52 was suggested as a surrogate marker for recovery while future pharmaceutical studies are encouraged to publish their delta-eGFR at week 12, 26 and 52. The group created a proposal for definitions of active disease, treatment response and refractory disease, remission and kidney failure.

Conclusions: Formulating a set of action points, the aim is to standardize terminology and drive the creation of reliable kidney endpoints. To reach expert consensus, the EUVAS focus group will now perform a Delphi method involving the larger scientific community.

O-34

Smarter care for ANCA-associated vasculitis patients: digital care pathways drive efficiency and reduce healthcare utilization

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Background/Aims: We evaluated the impact of digital care pathways (dig-CPs) on healthcare utilization (HCU) of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) patients. Dig-CPs integrate AAV-specific, risk-stratified pathways with remote monitoring of patient reported outcomes (PROs) on quality of life and disease symptoms. A nurse practitioner triages PROs daily to guide timely clinical interventions.

Methods: Dig-CP technology of DEARhealth was implemented as standard of care for AAV patients in late 2022 at the Nephrology outpatient clinic. Alongside a remission induction pathway, three risk-based maintenance pathways were introduced (high, medium and low risk). We analysed contacts with healthcare providers (HCP) between January 2022 and May 2025, examining associations with dig-CP usage and PRO outcomes. PROs included the patient global assessment of disease activity (PGA; 0-10) and the AAV-PRO questionnaire (0-100%, based on 29 questions scored 0-4).

Results: Of 199 AAV patients in care, 115 (58%) used dig-CPs and 84 (42%) did not. A total of 260 dig-CPs were initiated, mostly maintenance pathways (44% high risk, 26% medium risk, 17% low risk). Frequency of HCP contacts correlated strongly with the assigned risk-profiles ($p < 0.001$). Average annual HCP contacts per patient declined from 6.5 in 2022 to 5.7 in 2023 and 5.5 in 2024. This decline was solely driven by reduction among dig-CP users ($p = 0.02$), while no change was observed in non-users ($p = 0.32$). Nurse practitioner involvement was also significantly higher among dig-CP users (21% of contacts), compared to non-users (5%) ($p = 0.01$). Moreover, poor PRO scores predicted increased HCU (≥ 3 contacts) in the next three months, with odds ratios up to 5.1 [IQR 2.7–9.9] for PGA scores of ≥ 7 and 4.7 [IQR 2.8–8.0] for AAV-PRO scores of $> 40\%$.

Conclusions: Dig-CPs effectively reduced outpatient contacts and facilitated care transition to nurse practitioners. They also enable early identification of patients at risk for increased care needs, enabling proactive interventions.

O-35

New insights into ANCA-associated vasculitis care and outcomes in England from process mining of whole-population data within the National Disease Registration service

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Background/Aims: We aimed to study real-world clinical pathways and treatment for all people with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in England using multiple NHS datasets available to the National Disease Registration Service (NDRS, NHS England), including Hospital Episode Statistics, ONS Mortality and Primary Care prescribing.

Methods: We used validated methodology to identify patients with an ICD-10 coded diagnosis of Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA), Microscopic Polyangiitis (MPA) or Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA). Applying an algorithm to best identify diagnosis date, we generated a whole-population cohort of 3626 patients (GPA: 2089; MPA: 903; EGPA: 634) diagnosed between 2016-19. We used process mining to explore healthcare pathways and events (such as mortality and treatments including oral steroids) one year prior and up to 3 years post-diagnosis.

Results: In the year prior to (but not including) diagnosis, 63% of patients had an outpatient attendance in a specialty plausibly due to early symptoms of AAV. This varied according to disease subtype. The most frequent specialty attendance for GPA was Otolaryngology (29% of patients) and for EGPA was respiratory medicine (37% of patients). For MPA there was less prior activity, consistent with shorter prodrome compared to other subtypes. Mortality rate was 10% at 3 years (371/3626), highest in first 30 days post-diagnosis. Amongst all survivors at 3 years, ≥ 1 out-patient attendance/month was observed in approximately 50%. 46% had ≥ 1 steroid prescription in the 90-day period prior to the end of 3 years.

Conclusions: Process mining of whole-population data indicates potential opportunities for earlier diagnosis amongst patients receiving out-patient care who are subsequently diagnosed with AAV. At 3 years post-diagnosis, there continued to be high burden of healthcare utilisation and steroid dependency, highlighting ongoing need for better treatment strategies. This reproducible methodology can be scaled to support analysis of impact of new therapies on pathways and outcomes.

O-36

Dwayne: a chatbot for vasculitis patient support and education powered by artificial intelligence

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Background/Aims: People with vasculitis often struggle to access clear and accurate information outside of short clinic visits. Internet searches can be misleading, prioritising sponsored results over actual useful content. Tools like ChatGPT can provide inaccurate information and are prone to hallucinations. These issues can heighten anxiety and leave important questions unanswered. The challenge is greater for those with disabilities, literacy/language barriers. To address this, Vasculitis Ireland Awareness (VIA) partnered with ReganByte to create Dwayne, a chatbot powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI) that provides free, 24/7 access to medically verified information in more than 50 languages, available via speech or text on the VIA website.

Methods: Dwayne was co-designed with patients, clinicians, and data protection experts. It uses a locked and verified knowledge base using only resources from VIA and Vasculitis UK, significantly reducing the risk of hallucinations. Accessibility features include multilingual capability, speech input, and adaptations for different literacy levels, such as explaining vasculitis in simple terms for children. Regular analysis of anonymous queries identifies recurring themes and guides updates.

Results: Since launch on Rare Disease Day 2025, Dwayne has supported over 500 conversations and answered more than 1,700 queries in >10 languages. Common topics included: - Whether symptoms were vasculitis-related or something more urgent, and what symptoms to expect. - How safe vaccinations are while on immunosuppressants. - How to manage vasculitis day-to-day. Patients valued the safe, anonymous space to ask questions and felt more confident and prepared before appointments. Clinicians described it as “accurate and measured with appropriate caveats ... quite remarkable” and “trustworthy and safe.”

Conclusions: Dwayne provides trusted, accessible information while capturing the real questions patients ask. It reduces misinformation, supports confidence, and offers a scalable model for other rare diseases.

O-37

Performance of the Southend giant cell arteritis probability score in a single-centre New Zealand fast-track pathway

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Background/Aims: To assess the performance of a GCA fast-track pathway (FTP) in Auckland, New Zealand, and externally validate the Southend giant cell arteritis probability score (GCAPS) in predicting and excluding giant cell arteritis (GCA) in a different population and healthcare system to where it has previously been validated.

Methods: This is a retrospective cohort study of patients referred for suspected GCA between 1 January 2021 to 31 July 2024. Data on demographic and clinical characteristics, timepoints through the pathway, investigations, treatment and final diagnosis were collected. GCAPS was retrospectively calculated and an area under the curve (AUC) was generated for the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) of its performance in identifying GCA.

Results: Of the 137 patients included in the study, 61 (45%) were ultimately diagnosed with GCA, while 76 (55%) were diagnosed with non-GCA conditions. The mean (SD) time from referral to assessment was 9.64 (7.56) days. Twenty-two (16%) were assessed within 72 hours, 62 (45%) were assessed within one week, 113 (82%) within two weeks, and 129 (94%) within three weeks. Individual components of GCAPS that had a statistically significant association with a final diagnosis of GCA (p -value < 0.05) in this cohort included polymyalgia, fever, weight loss, cranial or limb claudication, scalp tenderness and elevated CRP. The GCAPS had an AUC of 0.91 (95% CI 0.86-0.96), and a binary cut-off score of 9 demonstrated 100% sensitivity.

Conclusions: GCAPS demonstrates utility as a practical and effective tool for excluding giant cell arteritis in our cohort.

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The Eastern Network Kidney Inflammatory Disease (ENKID) MDT at 24 months: advancing access to high-cost drugs, clinical trials, and complex case management in renal autoimmunity

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Background/Aims: Glomerulonephritis (GN) accounts for 20%–25% of chronic kidney disease and is a major cause of end-stage kidney disease. A 1,420-patient ANCA vasculitis (AAV) study found specialist MDT access was associated with reduced emergency hospitalisations and serious infections. Regional networks provide collaborative decision-making, equitable access to expertise, clinical trials and high-cost drugs (HCDs). However, a 2024 UK GN survey found 59% of nephrologists lacked regional MDT access. To address this in the East of England (EoE), the Eastern Network Kidney Inflammatory Disease MDT (ENKID) launched in May 2023.

Methods: ENKID is led by a specialist vasculitis, lupus and primary GN service. A secure database records referrals, recommendations and treatment decisions from fortnightly virtual MDTs. A quorate MDT requires four GN consultants, a renal pharmacist, specialist nurse and coordinator.

Results: Over 24 months, 229 case discussions for 198 patients were held across 43 ENKID MDTs, averaging 15 attendees (65% consultants) from six centres per meeting. Referral reasons were HCD access (42%, n=96), complexity and HCD (46%, n=106), complexity alone (12%, n=27), and trial eligibility (9%, n=20). ANCA associated vasculitis represents one-third of ENKID referrals (33%, n=65), followed by IgA nephropathy (19%, n=38), membranous (18%, n=35), and lupus nephritis (15%, n=29), with the remainder minimal change/FSGS, rarer diseases or diagnostic uncertainty. Including rituximab, a HCD was endorsed in 71% and alternatives recommended in 29% of HCD referrals.

Conclusions: ENKID highlights the integral role of regional MDTs in improving vasculitis and autoimmune kidney disease care across a wide geographical distribution. High caseload and attendance demonstrate unmet need, aligning with the UK government's mandate for rare autoimmune disease networks. Integrated within the EoE renal network, providing governance, training, HCD access and outcome reporting, it serves as an exemplar for improving GN patient care and service accessibility in the UK.

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Delayed diagnosis and high healthcare utilisation in VEXAS syndrome: a case series and cost analysis

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Background/Aims: VEXAS syndrome (Vacuoles, E1 enzyme, X-linked, Autoinflammatory, Somatic) is a recently recognised inflammatory disorder caused by somatic mutations in the UBA1 gene. Its heterogenous and non-specific clinical presentation can lead to incorrect diagnosis and treatment, ultimately resulting in increased morbidity and healthcare costs. We evaluated the healthcare resource burden and iatrogenic harm associated with diagnostic delays in two patients with VEXAS syndrome. We also assessed whether earlier UBA1 mutation testing is justified in the investigation of undifferentiated systemic inflammation.

Methods: We conducted a case series of two patients with VEXAS syndrome at tertiary health services in Melbourne, Australia. Healthcare costs were quantified from initial symptom onset to confirmatory diagnosis by UBA1 mutation testing.

Results: Both patients were middle-aged Caucasian men presenting with recurrent periorbital inflammation, auricular chondritis, and pyrexia. Initial management was directed toward presumed orbital cellulitis, and then pyrexia of unknown origin and undifferentiated autoinflammatory disease. Prior to VEXAS diagnosis, patient A had 11 hospital encounters, while patient B had 27 hospital encounters. Both patients underwent extensive imaging and procedures including temporal artery, orbital, pinna and bone marrow biopsy. Cumulatively, patient A received 2,613 mg prednisolone while patient B received 1,790 mg prednisolone prior to diagnosis. Mean time to diagnosis was 30 weeks (range 18, 42). The mean pre-diagnosis healthcare cost was AUD 71,815 (range 66,488, 77,141), compared with AUD 829 for a serum UBA1 mutation test. Upon receiving a formal diagnosis of VEXAS syndrome, both patients were placed on appropriate treatment (tocilizumab and azacitidine) and remain stable.

Conclusions: Given the morbidity and financial consequences of delayed diagnosis, and comparatively low cost of UBA1 mutation testing, our study supports early genetic testing in patients with clinical features of VEXAS syndrome.

Clinical patterns, predictive factors and impact of relapses in a large multicentre cohort of ANCA-associated renal vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Relapses are common in ANCA-associated vasculitis with kidney involvement (AAV-KI) and contribute significantly to long-term morbidity. However, their clinical patterns, predictors, and impact on kidney outcomes remain incompletely defined, and current relapse-prediction scores have limited applicability in this population, challenging individualized therapeutic management.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective multicentre study including 460 adults with AAV-KI diagnosed between 2000 and 2025 across 7 French centres. Relapse incidence, clinical presentation, and impact on outcomes were evaluated. Predictors were identified using Cox proportional hazards and landmark models at 6, 12, and 24 months. The performance of existing relapse scores (Junek, FRS, REACT) was assessed and compared to newly developed models.

Results: Over a median follow-up of 62 months, 107 patients (23%) experienced 135 major relapses. The cumulative relapse incidence at 10 years was 31%. GPA phenotype was associated with a higher and delayed relapse risk compared to MPA. Relapses frequently involved new organ systems and could occur even in patients on dialysis. Relapses were independently associated with worse kidney function trajectory and reduced kidney survival (adjusted HR 4.20, $p < 0.001$), with a cumulative deleterious effect over time. Predictors of relapse included higher eGFR at diagnosis and follow-up, GPA phenotype, percentage of sclerotic glomeruli, and ANCA positivity during follow-up. Neither early relapses nor persistent haematuria predicted subsequent relapses. The Junek, FRS, and REACT scores showed poor discrimination (C-index ≤ 0.56) but our multivariable models did not reach clinically relevant predictive abilities either.

Conclusions: Relapses in AAV-KI are phenotype-dependent, and detrimental to kidney outcomes. Current predictive tools are insufficient. These findings underscore the need for dynamic, phenotype-specific risk models incorporating longitudinal biomarkers such as ANCA status and kidney function evolution.

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Risk factors for relapse in childhood IgA vasculitis: the role of skin, renal, and biomarker profiles

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis (IgAV), the most common childhood vasculitis, is typically self-limiting but relapses in a substantial subset, causing morbidity, higher healthcare use, and potential kidney damage. This study aimed to identify clinical and laboratory predictors of relapse using univariate time-to-event and categorical outcome analyses.

Methods: Data from 808 children diagnosed with IgAV (EULAR/PRINTO/PRES criteria, 2009–2024) across five paediatric rheumatology centres were analysed; 184 were enrolled prospectively. Retrospective analyses included (1) Cox proportional hazards models for time to first relapse and (2) multinomial logistic regression comparing no, single, and multiple relapses. Prospective analyses used Andersen-Gill Cox models. Covariates included skin, arthritis, gastrointestinal (GI), nephritis, haematuria, proteinuria, serum calprotectin, and complement levels.

Results: Relapses occurred in 144 patients (median age 6.1 years; male-to-female ratio 0.64:1); median time to first relapse was 1.2 months. In Cox models, severe rash (HR=27.99), nephritis (HR=27.69), haematuria (HR=25.73), and long-term rash (HR=3625.63) strongly predicted relapse. Haemoglobin was linked to higher early hazard (HR=1.03), while IgG (HR=0.92) and proteinuria (HR=0.57) reduced risk. Multinomial regression confirmed age, severe rash, nephritis, haematuria, and hand rash as predictors of relapse; long-term rash predicted multiple relapses (OR=9.75), while face rash was linked to single relapse only. ASTO was weakly protective. In the prospective cohort, severe skin involvement (HR=11.72) and higher serum calprotectin (HR=1.001/unit) increased relapse risk. Arthritis (HR=0.11) and GI involvement (HR=0.27) were protective.

Conclusions: Severe and prolonged skin involvement, nephritis, and elevated serum calprotectin are strong predictors of relapse in paediatric IgAV, whereas arthritis and GI symptoms reduce risk. Findings highlight serum calprotectin as a potential biomarker and support individualized follow-up strategies.

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GOOD-IDES-02 - a randomized controlled phase 3 trial testing imlifidase treatment in anti-GBM disease (CT.gov trial: NCT03157037 EU clinical trial: 2022-500121-33-01)

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Background/Aims: Imlifidase enzymatically cleaves and temporarily decreases all IgG antibody subclasses. Anti-GBM disease is the most severe form of small vessel vasculitis with low renal survival probability. Imlifidase previously showed promising results in a single arm phase 2 trial (GOOD-IDES-01, NCT03157037) compared to historic controls.

Methods: In the GOOD-IDES-02 trial, patients with severe anti-GBM disease were randomized 1:1 to receive a single dose of imlifidase followed by plasma exchange, or to start treatment with plasma exchange. All patients received corticosteroids and cyclophosphamide according to a standardized protocol. Important exclusion criteria were eGFR >20 ml/min/1.73m², and anuria >24 hours before screening. Primary outcome was eGFR at 6 months and key secondary outcome was dialysis independency at 6 months. Safety was also assessed.

Results: 48 centres in 14 countries were activated; 50 patients (25 women) with a mean age of 58 years were included between May 2023 and Dec 2024. 11 patients in both arms were dialysis dependent at randomization. In the active arm, anti-GBM levels fell below the pre-specified level in 24 patients at day 2, compared to 1 patient in the control. Despite this, neither the primary (median eGFR 22.3 vs 18.5 ml/min; p=0.31) nor the key secondary (56 % vs 62.5 %; p= 0.32) outcomes were met. The safety profile was comparable between the two arms and in keeping with previous imlifidase clinical trial experience.

Conclusions: This is the first randomized controlled trial evaluating this novel mode of action in anti-GBM disease. The key efficacy outcomes were not met and the reasons for this are to be determined. The outcome in the standard of care arm was much above expectations, showing that swift introduction of standard of care and a very intense plasma exchange regimen can achieve significantly improved results than previous cohort studies have indicated.

O-43

Maintenance of remission with rituximab versus azathioprine in newly diagnosed or relapsing eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis: a prospective, randomised, controlled, double-blind trial

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Background/Aims: In eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA), guidelines recommend considering maintenance therapy after remission to reduce the risk of relapse and toxicity. However, data from randomised trials are lacking. The primary objective of this trial is to compare rituximab (RTX) with azathioprine (AZA) maintenance therapy on the duration of remission in EGPA patients who have recently achieved remission of their vasculitis.

Methods: Within 30-360 days of achieving vasculitis remission from newly-diagnosed or relapsing EGPA, patients were randomised to receive 500 mg RTX every 6 months for 18 months (4 infusions) plus placebo AZA for 24 months or AZA (2 mg/kg/day, 24 months) plus placebo RTX infusions. The primary endpoint was the number of weeks a patient remained in remission (BVAS=0) with prednisone ≤ 7.5 mg/day over the 28-month study period. Secondary endpoints included the proportion of participants who remained in remission (i) with prednisone ≤ 7.5 mg/day; (ii) regardless of prednisone dose; (iii) with prednisone ≤ 4 mg/day at months 3, 12, and 18; rate of vasculitis relapse; rate of significant asthma/rhinosinusitis exacerbations; cumulative glucocorticoids; safety; and quality of life.

Results: Ninety-eight patients were randomised between March 2018 and June 2022. No difference in remission duration was observed between RTX and AZA recipients ($p=0.378$). There were also no significant differences for the following secondary outcomes: percentage of participants remaining in remission with prednisone ≤ 7.5 mg/day, with any prednisone dose, or with prednisone ≤ 4 mg/day at months 3, 12, or 18; vasculitis relapse rate; rate of significant asthma and/or rhinosinusitis exacerbations; glucocorticoids; and quality of life. One patient in the AZA group died of SARS-CoV2 infection before the vaccine was developed. No difference in serious adverse events was observed.

Conclusions: Following an EGPA diagnosis or vasculitis relapse, RTX did not demonstrate superiority to AZA in maintaining vasculitis remission, reducing asthma/rhinosinusitis exacerbations, or sparing glucocorticoids.

O-44

A randomised study of rituximab and belimumab sequential therapy in PR3-ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: B cell activating factor (BAFF) antagonism combined with CD20 B cell depletion may enhance B cell targeting in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) leading to better ANCA suppression and clinical disease control.

Methods: In this multicentre, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial, adults with PR3-ANCA positive AAV received rituximab plus belimumab or rituximab plus placebo, with a standardised corticosteroid taper and no maintenance immunosuppression. Therapy was given for 52 weeks, followed by 52 weeks of observation. The primary endpoint was time to ANCA negativity (<2.0 IU/L). Secondary endpoints included B cell kinetics, remission, relapse, and safety.

Results: Thirty-five patients were randomised; 34 were evaluable. In the per protocol cohort (n=32), PR3-ANCA negativity occurred in 5/17 (29.4%) on rituximab–belimumab compared to 2/15 (13.3%) on rituximab–placebo (HR 4.70, 95% CI 0.65–33.8; p=0.12). ANCA levels at 52 weeks were 3.4 IU (IQR 2.5–12.4) and 12.0 IU (IQR 6.2–29.5) in rituximab-belimumab versus rituximab placebo. Both groups achieved B cell depletion by week 12; belimumab delayed B cell reconstitution, with reduced total and naïve B cell counts at 12 and 18 months. In the intention to treat population (n=34), 0/17 rituximab-belimumab and 3/17 rituximab-placebo had progressive disease before remission. Remission was achieved faster with rituximab-belimumab (42 vs 91 days; HR 2.29, 90% CI 1.08–4.85; p=0.031). Relapse occurred in 6/17 (35%) patients in the rituximab–belimumab arm versus 9/17 (53%) in the rituximab–placebo arm (HR 0.64; 95% CI 0.23–1.80; p=0.40). In belimumab patients, ANCA re-emergence occurred after belimumab withdrawal, in 4/5 patients. No relapses occurred during ANCA negativity. Rates of serious adverse events were comparable.

Conclusions: Combination therapy with rituximab-belimumab was associated with delayed B cell reconstitution and a trend towards greater PR3-ANCA negativity. There was a faster time to remission and a trend towards lower relapse rates in the rituximab-belimumab group.

O-45

Treatment effect of secukinumab versus adalimumab for patients with active Takayasu arteritis: a prospective study over a two-year period

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Background/Aims: T helper 17 plays a key role in the pathogenesis of Takayasu arteritis (TAK). However, treatment evidence for targeting interleukin 17A is limited. We aimed to investigate effect of glucocorticoids (GC) and secukinumab compared with GC and adalimumab in patients with TAK.

Methods: This prospective study enrolled 104 patients with active TAK (secukinumab: n=46; adalimumab: n=58). The primary endpoint was complete remission (CR) with GC \leq 10 mg/day at 6 months. Secondary endpoints included CR with different GC target doses at 6, 12, 18, and 24 months, sustained CR, alterations of immune-cells and molecule signatures, and safety.

Results: Patients' average age was 32.73 (SD 11.19) years, with 90 (86.54%) female. They were prospectively followed up for a median of 24 (IQR 14, 54) months. Adalimumab group achieved a relatively higher CR rate at 6 months (32/58 [55.17%] vs. 19/46 [41.30%], OR 2.1, 95% CI: 0.93-4.81, P = 0.07). However, the rates of CR at 12, 18, and 24 months and sustained CR at 12 and 24 months were similar between the two groups (all P >0.05). Exploratory analysis showed that secukinumab demonstrated an inhibitory effect in B cells and tended to achieve relatively higher CR and sustained CR rates at 12 months (13/20 [65.00%] vs. 4/12 [33.33%], OR 1.95, 95% CI: 0.82-4.62, P = 0.14) in the B cell ratio-high (>15.7%) subgroup. However, in the B cell ratio-low subgroup, the adalimumab treatment attained significantly higher CR and sustained CR rate at 12 months (19/39 [48.72%] vs. 5/25 [20.00%], OR 2.44[95% CI: 1.04-5.69], P = 0.03; 17/39 [43.59%] vs. 4/25 [16.00%], OR 1.95[95% CI: 0.82-4.62], P = 0.03).

Conclusions: Secukinumab has similar treatment effects with adalimumab in TAK treatment. Baseline B cell ratio might be an important factor guiding adalimumab or secukinumab treatment selection.

O-46

The efficacy of low-dose naltrexone in improving self-reported physical health in patients with vasculitis: the LoDoNaVasc trial

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Background/Aims: Low-dose naltrexone (LDN) has been promoted as effective in treating fatigue, pain, and other features of inflammatory diseases. The LoDoNaVasc trial aimed to determine if LDN is effective in improving health-related quality of life among patients with vasculitis.

Methods: LoDoNaVasc was a multi-centre, randomized, double-blind, cross-over, placebo-controlled trial. Patients with vasculitis were eligible if their baseline PROMIS Global Physical Health score was ≤ 40 (0-100 scale), vasculitis was in remission or very low disease activity, and doses of immunosuppressive therapies (including prednisone) or medications to treat pain, fatigue, or mood, were stable ≥ 12 weeks.

Patients were randomized to receive either LDN 4.5 mg/day for 6 weeks followed by placebo for 6 weeks or placebo for 6 weeks followed by LDN 4.5 mg/day for 6 weeks. The primary outcome, measured at weeks 6 and 12, was change in PROMIS Global Physical Health.

Results: Sixty enrolled and randomized patients contributed data at weeks 0, 6, and 12. Among 29 patients who received LDN during the first period, mean improvement in PROMIS Global Physical Health was 1.54 (standard deviation 5.17). Among 31 patients who received placebo during the first period, mean improvement was 3.84 (5.12), $p = 0.09$. During the second period, the mean score in the first group (transitioning from LDN to placebo) declined by a mean of 0.28 (5.07), and the mean score in the second group (transitioning from placebo to LDN) declined by 1.27 (4.51), $p = 0.42$. In multivariable analysis, the mean difference between the first and second treatment periods was 3.47 (0.91), favouring the first period, $p < 0.01$, the mean difference between LDN and placebo was mean 1.65 (0.91), $p = 0.07$, and the difference between LDN first and placebo first was -0.55 (1.02), $p = 0.59$. No significant impact of LDN was seen in outcomes related to individual domains of physical or mental health.

Conclusions: The LoDoNaVasc trial demonstrated no benefit of LDN over placebo in patients reporting reduced global physical health. This trial addressed an issue important to both patients and clinicians, using a patient-reported measure as the primary outcome.

O-47

Modulation of gut microbiota by nutritional interventions in Bechet's syndrome: the randomized, cross-over, open-label, controlled MAMBA trial

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Background/Aims: Pilot data support the modulation of gut microbiota (GM) through butyrate-enriched dietary interventions in patients with Behçet syndrome (BS). This study evaluated the effects of three dietary interventions on clinical outcomes in patients with BS.

Methods: A randomized, open-label, crossover, controlled study was conducted in patients with BS, who were assigned to a random sequence of three 12-week-long interventions of isocaloric mediterranean diet (MD), supplemented with butyrate (Bt), and lacto-ovo-vegetarian diet (VD), elapsed by two washout periods of 1.5 months each. The primary outcome was the difference across interventions in disease activity, by means of the Behçet's Disease Current Activity Form (BDCAF). Secondary outcomes included changes the frequency of oral ulcers (OU), and in gastrointestinal symptoms, measured by the Symptoms Severity Score (SSS).

Results: Of the 96 eligible participants, 91 (94.8%) were randomized. The final analysis included 70 patients who completed the intervention, 67 the MD-Bt intervention and 69 the VD intervention. We found no significant changes in the BDCAF across diets. However, the frequency of OU significantly decreased during the MD-Bt [pre: median 3.3 (IQR 2.5-4.1) vs. post: 0.4 (0.2-0.5); $p < 0.0001$] and the VD intervention [pre: 4.7 (4.1-5.4) vs. post: 0.4 (0.2-0.6), $p < 0.0001$]. Gastrointestinal symptoms improved with the and MD-Bt diets (mean decrease in SS: -11.5% with and -17.6% with MD-Bt), with notable reductions in abdominal bloating (mean decrease: -13.5% with and -22.6% with MD-Bt) and pain severity.

Conclusions: While butyrate-enriched dietary interventions had limited impact on overall disease activity, they significantly reduced the frequency of OU and improved gastrointestinal symptoms in BS.

O-48

Renal disease and risk stratification in paediatric anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis — insights from the Pediatric Vasculitis Initiative

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated glomerulonephritis (ANCA-GN) is a severe and frequent manifestation of paediatric ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). At diagnosis, 25–30% of children require dialysis, and within a year, 40–50% develop permanent kidney damage; nearly one-third progress to kidney transplantation. While prognostic measures exist for adult-onset ANCA-GN, paediatric-specific tools are lacking. Differences in paediatric cases, such as higher baseline eGFR, distinct histology, and greater recovery potential, may limit the applicability of adult models. We aimed to evaluate adult-derived risk tools in paediatric ANCA-GN and explore urinary proteins and metabolites as early, non-invasive biomarkers.

Methods: This study included 115 children (mean age 12.9 years, 72% female) with biopsy-proven ANCA-GN from the international Paediatric Vasculitis Initiative. Baseline and/or follow-up data included ANCA serotype (50% PR3-ANCA, 46% MPO-ANCA), eGFR, dialysis requirement, and histopathology. Adult risk tools (Berden classification, Renal Risk Score, baseline eGFR) were applied to predict CKD, ESKD, and KDIGO stage at post-induction (3–6 months), 12 months, and last follow-up. Urine from 30 children with renal or non-renal AAV was analysed at diagnosis for candidate protein and metabolite biomarkers.

Results: At diagnosis, 93% of biopsies had <25% of both interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy. This is unexpected given evidence of renal damage in ~50% of patients within 12 months of diagnosis and limits predictive utility of adult risk scores reliant on chronic changes. Urinary usCD163 and/or usCD25 were detected in 67% of children with ANCA-GN, and usCD25 alone was found in 30% of non-renal AAV cases. Pilot metabolomics revealed distinct urinary profiles in children with AAV with and without glomerulonephritis and with preserved versus impaired kidney function.

Conclusions: Paediatric ANCA-GN presents unique challenges and differs meaningfully from adult disease. Validation and adaptation of adult risk models, alongside development of paediatric-specific biomarkers, are essential to improve renal prognostication in children.

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Novel autoantibodies towards organ enriched proteins enable patient stratification in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a rare autoimmune disorder causing inflammation of the blood vessels and characterized by the presence of anti-proteinase 3 (anti-PR3) and anti-myeloperoxidase (anti-MPO) autoantibodies. Improved patient stratification based on organ involvement could guide more personalized therapeutic strategies. Our aim is to characterize the autoantibody repertoires in AAV patients with different organ involvement.

Methods: Plasma from 100 AAV patients and 30 healthy controls enrolled at Linköping university hospital was collected at single timepoint. AAV patients where 51% MPO-positive and 49% PR3 positive. The sample set was screened for autoantibodies towards 369 antigens representing 272 unique proteins, using our in-house generated bead-array based on the Human Protein Atlas antigen resource. The array included antigens representing proteins selected from our previous studies on vasculitis as well as proteins enriched in the tissues and cell types involved in AAV.

Results: We identified novel autoantibodies with higher prevalence in the AAV group compared to controls. Among these, we confirmed several autoantibodies previously discovered in an independent cohort and reported in our published studies on AAV. The identified novel autoantibodies bind to proteins enriched in endothelium and intestine. In addition, we confirmed 92% of the anti-MPO-positive samples, underscoring the robustness of our assay. Finally, using the targets selected from the AAV versus healthy comparison, we identified a distinct patient cluster, including mainly patients with kidney involvement, and characterized by high levels of anti-MPO and anti-Scl70/TOP1 antibodies.

Conclusions: Our study expands the autoantibody landscape in AAV, identifying novel candidate autoantibodies targeting tissue- and cell-enriched proteins. The discovery of a distinct cluster of patients with kidney involvement, highlights the utility of autoantibody profiling for patient stratification and support in future tailored clinical management strategies.

A stronger type I interferon signature distinguishes ANCA-associated vasculitis phenotypes and predicts kidney prognosis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) causes severe multisystemic organ damage. The main phenotypes, microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), share similarities but differ in clinical presentation and outcome. To uncover their molecular differences, we performed transcriptomic profiling of kidney tissue, then focused on type I interferon (IFN-I) pathway activation in kidney and blood and its clinical implications.

Methods: We analysed two independent cohorts (Maine-Anjou and RENVAS registries) totalling 193 AAV patients with glomerulonephritis. NanoString nCounter transcriptomic profiling, qPCR, MxA immunohistochemistry, and serum inflammatory molecules quantification were conducted. Comparative analyses of MPA vs. GPA (and MPO-AAV vs. PR3-AAV) were validated using independent public datasets (including kidney spatial transcriptomic datasets, European cDNA Renal Biobank and blood from the RAVE trial).

Results: The kidney IFN-I signature found in AAV-GN is upregulated in MPA/MPO-AAV compared to GPA/PR3-AAV and controls. qPCR, immunohistochemistry, and analysis of external datasets confirmed these findings. This IFN-I signature, close to the one found in lupus nephritis, is linked to the extent of pDC infiltration. Renal IFN-I activation correlated with increased kidney fibrosis, independently of kidney function. High renal IFN-I signatures were linked to lower kidney survival, independently of kidney function and pathological scores. MPA kidneys also exhibited higher mast cell and T cell infiltration. Systemic analyses showed elevated IFN α and interferon-related inflammatory molecules in all AAV patients, but a stronger IFN-I gene signature was found in immune cells from MPA.

Conclusions: This study identifies an IFN-I signature in AAV, especially in MPA/MPO-AAV, underscoring its potential role in disease heterogeneity and kidney pathology. IFN-I emerges as a potential prognostic biomarker and therapeutic target in AAV, particularly for MPA. Further studies are needed to clarify its mechanisms and explore IFN-I modulation in clinical trials.

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Retinal optical coherence tomography as a biomarker of vascular injury and treatment response in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are at increased risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Non-invasive biomarkers to stratify risk and monitor treatment are urgently needed. Retinal optical coherence tomography (OCT) provides direct assessment of the chorioretinal microvasculature. We investigated whether OCT metrics reflect vascular injury and treatment response in AAV.

Methods: We conducted three complementary studies. First, 90 patients with active AAV underwent retinal OCT at diagnosis and following treatment-induced remission, alongside 70 matched healthy controls. Second, 35 patients in long-term disease remission underwent OCT with endothelial function testing (forearm plethysmography) and arterial stiffness assessment (pulse wave velocity). Third, 32 patients in remission were randomised in a double-blind randomised trial to six weeks of irbesartan (angiotensin receptor blocker) or sparsentan (dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonist). A nested sub-study of 19 patients underwent OCT at baseline and six weeks. All imaging used the Heidelberg SPECTRALIS Spectral-Domain OCT device.

Results: Compared to controls, patients with active AAV (mean age 59±16 years; 57% male; eGFR 59 (26-86) mL/min/1.73m²) had thinner choroids (187±82 versus 220±84 µm; P<0.01). Following remission, choroidal thickness increased by ~10% (P<0.001). In remission (59±14 years; 66% male; eGFR 75 (62-89) mL/min/1.73m²), reduced choroidal thickness correlated with impaired endothelial function (r=0.45; P<0.01) and increased pulse wave velocity (r=-0.57; P<0.001). In the randomised trial (64±12 years; 63% male; eGFR 62 (38-71) mL/min/1.73m²), sparsentan increased choroidal thickness by ~10% whereas irbesartan had no effect (+14.3±7.6 versus -4.0±9.8 µm; P<0.001).

Conclusions: Retinal OCT metrics reflect systemic vascular injury in AAV, improve with disease remission, and respond to dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonism. OCT provides a dynamic, non-invasive biomarker of vascular health with potential as an endpoint in clinical trials.

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Plasma peptides as potential biomarkers of venous thromboembolic events in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: During active phases, patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) have increased risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE). No validated biomarkers predict VTE, so prophylactic anticoagulation is generally not recommended. Renal involvement (defined by presence of haematuria) is a known risk factor, while the role of other disease-related conditions remains unclear. Pathophysiological factors linked to active disease may also contribute to the development of VTE.

Methods: From the RAVE trial, 14 patients who developed VTE (VTE-group) were compared to 14 matched controls who did not experience VTE (non-VTE group). A quantitative targeted protein mass spectrometry was performed on plasma samples at baseline to assess inflammatory and coagulation-related peptides. The obtained panel including 162 peptides was compared between the groups, adjusting for baseline clinical and serological characteristics (age, gender, creatinine, BVAS, PR3, alveolar haemorrhage).

Results: Compared to controls, VTE patients had significantly higher plasma levels (expressed as a percentage of a calibrator plasma) of three peptides at baseline: serum amyloid A-4 protein (SAA4) [1.7 in VTE group, 1.2 in non-VTE group], lipopolysaccharide-binding protein (LBP) [1.4 vs 1.0], alpha-1-acid glycoprotein-1 (AGP) [2.1 vs 1.7]. A Cox Proportional Hazards Model was performed on these significant variables: elevated levels of SAA4 were associated with an increased risk of VTE (HR 2.09, 95% CI: 1.28-3.42), similarly as LBP (HR 1.82, 95% CI: 1.12-2.93) and AGP (HR 1.67, 95% CI: 1.05-2.65). After adjusting for baseline clinical variables, SAA4 and LBP hold significance: SAA4 showed the strongest association (HR 5.36, 95% CI: 2.02-14.18), and LBP the narrowest CI (HR 2.05, 95% CI: 1.06-3.97).

Conclusions: In subjects with active AAV, elevated SAA4 and LBP plasma levels were associated with higher VTE risk. Both proteins are involved in inflammation and may influence the coagulation process. These markers could help identify patients prone to VTE, suggesting monitoring and personalised treatment strategies.

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IgG anti-pentraxin 3 autoantibodies distinguish EGPA from severe asthma and nasal polyposis

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) overlaps phenotypically with severe eosinophilic asthma (SEA) and chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyposis (CRSwNP).

Circulating IgG anti-Pentraxin-3 (PTX3) autoantibodies have been described in EGPA. We compared anti-PTX3 prevalence and levels across EGPA, SEA, CRSwNP, and healthy controls (HC), and evaluated diagnostic performance for distinguishing EGPA.

Methods: We conducted a single-centre, cross-sectional study, including consecutive patients with EGPA (n=104), SEA (n=76), CRSwNP (n=63) and HC (n=101). Anti-PTX3 levels were measured using a standardized, in-house ELISA. Optical density (OD) read at 405 nm. Liquid-phase inhibition assays were performed to evaluate potential assay interferences. ROC analysis for EGPA vs healthy controls yielded an AUC of 0.720 (95%CI 0.65-0.79). Youden-optimal cut-off for OD was 0.210 (sensitivity 44%, specificity 96%). Group comparisons used Kruskal–Wallis with Dunn’s post-hoc tests and chi-square for proportions.

Results: Anti-PTX3 prevalence was higher in EGPA (44.2%) than in SEA (15.8%) and CRSwNP (7.9%) (p<0.001). Median OD was higher in EGPA (0.18) than in SEA (0.11) and CRSwNP patients (0.07), p<0.001. Among EGPA patients, 38 (36.5%) were ANCA-positive and 46 (44.2%) were anti-PTX3-positive; 14 (13.5%) were double-positive, 56 (53.8%) single-positive (anti-PTX3-only 30.8%; ANCA-only 23.1%), and 34 (32.7%) double-negative. Anti-PTX3 identified 48.5% (32/66) of ANCA-negative EGPA, increasing overall serologic yield from 36.5% (ANCA alone) to 67.3% (ANCA or anti-PTX3). Overlap was modest (Jaccard index 0.20). Inhibition assays reduced signal, supporting specificity. Anti-PTX3 were not associated with ANCA status or baseline clinical features. Among 31 patients with paired follow-up samples, seropositivity for anti-PTX3 declined from 15/31 (48.4%) to 10/31 (32.3%) (McNemar p=0.046); seven negativisations occurred over 579 person-months (incidence 1.21 per 100 person-months).

Conclusions: Anti-PTX3 autoantibodies are significantly more prevalent in EGPA than in SEA and CRSwNP and show limited overlap with ANCA. These findings support anti-PTX3 as a complementary biomarker to aid early recognition of EGPA.

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Rheumatoid factor (RF) in patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA): a red flag for vasculitis relapse

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Background/Aims: The present study was conducted with the objective of evaluating the frequency and prognostic significance of rheumatoid factor (RF) in patients diagnosed with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA). A particular emphasis was placed on the potential role of RF in predicting vasculitis relapses.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted, encompassing patients diagnosed with EGPA who underwent RF testing at the diagnosis. Clinical and laboratory data were prospectively collected starting from diagnosis and throughout the following 60 months. Relapse was defined as the new onset, recurrence, or worsening of systemic signs or symptoms (excluding asthma and nasal polyps exacerbations) associated with a BVASv3>0. A Random Forest machine learning model was developed to identify relapse predictors, with support from SHAP analysis.

Results: 83 patients diagnosed with EGPA were included in the present study, 45.8% of whom were found to have positive RF. During follow-up, 19.3% of patients experienced at least one relapse. Patients with a positive RF test had a significantly higher relapse rate than those with a negative RF test (39.5%vs2.2%, p=0.003). Patients with a positive RF test had a higher frequency of mononeuritis multiplex and elevated CRP levels at diagnosis. The Kaplan-Meier analysis demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in 5-year relapse-free survival in patients with RF-positive (p<0.001). The Random Forest model identified RF positivity as the strongest relapse predictor (VIMP 0.2031, 95%CI -0.012 to 0.307), outperforming established variables such as ANCA positivity and age at disease onset. Subsequent SHAP analysis confirmed that negative RF was associated with a greater relapse-free probability (phi +0.1469).

Conclusions: RF is a prevalent and clinically significant biomarker in EGPA. In our cohort, it is associated with increased systemic relapse risk. These findings suggest that RF may define a distinct immunopathogenic subset of EGPA, characterised by increased systemic inflammation and vasculitic phenotype.

O-55

Clinical phenotypes associated with alpha-1 antitrypsin Z and S alleles among patients with vasculitis and positive anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies to proteinase 3 or myeloperoxidase

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Background/Aims: Alpha-1 antitrypsin (A1AT), a serine protease inhibitor, is the primary endogenous inhibitor of proteinase 3 (PR3), a major target antigen of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Two separate genome-wide association studies found that mutations in SERPINA1, the gene encoding A1AT, are associated with increased risk of developing AAV. This study evaluated clinical characteristics of patients with AAV with and without A1AT deficiency alleles.

Methods: A1AT genotype was determined from DNA of 2526 patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis or microscopic polyangiitis in a combined international cohort. Clinical characteristics were compared by genotype. The highest odds ratio (OR) for an organ system among features affecting ≥ 10 total patients and ≥ 5 per group, adjusted for age/sex/race, is reported.

Results: MM (wild-type) genotype accounted for 84.6% (n=2138) of the cohort, while MS was the most frequent abnormal genotype (8.4%; 212), followed by MZ (5.6%; 141); SZ, SS, and ZZ each comprised $\leq 0.6\%$ (9, 12, 14 patients, respectively). As compared to patients with AAV and wild-type A1AT, patients with abnormal alleles more commonly had a clinical diagnosis of GPA and PR3-ANCA or negative ANCA, along with arthralgias (OR 1.47) and/or orbital mass (OR 2.29). With two abnormal alleles, skin and nervous system features were more common (OR 5.86 and 3.72, respectively). When evaluating patients with PR3- and MPO-ANCA separately, Z and S alleles appeared to confer differential clinical manifestations. Patients with a Z allele and PR3-ANCA, as compared to MM with PR3-ANCA, more commonly had skin and nervous system features (OR 2.82, 2.14), while patients with an S allele and MPO-ANCA more commonly had ear/nose/throat, eye, and skin findings (OR 2.58, 3.26, 7.48).

Conclusions: Across both PR3-ANCA and MPO-ANCA positive patients, A1AT alleles are associated with different clinical phenotypes in AAV. These results provide additional evidence linking A1AT to the pathophysiology of AAV.

O-56

Cardiac involvement in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: a cross-sectional study

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are rare systemic diseases characterized by high morbidity and multi-organ involvement. Cardiac involvement is an important prognostic factor but remains insufficiently studied in AAV. This study aims to investigate the prevalence and characteristics of cardiac disease in AAV.

Methods: A cross-sectional single- centre study enrolled AAV patients attending Rheumatology or Nephrology clinics at our hospital after written consent. Protocol included clinical assessment, electrocardiography, echocardiography and cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR). Clinical, laboratory and treatment data were collected at enrolment and retrospectively from AAV diagnosis.

Results: CMR was performed in 72 of 84 patients: 43% (n=31) women; 66.7% (n=48) GPA, 19.4% (n=14) MPA, and 13.9% (n=10) EGPA. 66.7% (n=48) were PR3-positive and 20.8% (n=15) MPO-positive at AAV diagnosis. Median age at diagnosis and enrolment was 60.3 and 69.2 years, respectively. In 50% (n=36) of patients, ≥ 1 cardiac abnormality was detected on CMR. Abnormal CMR findings was more frequent in men than women (63% vs. 32%, $p = 0.005$). By disease phenotype, abnormal CMR findings occurred in 47.9% of GPA (n=23), 50% of MPA (n=7), and 60% of EGPA patients (n=6), $p=0.7$. By ANCA positivity, no difference in frequency of CMR abnormalities was found between MPO-positive patients (8/15; 53.3%) and PR3-positive patients (22/48, 45.8%) $p=0.4$. The most common pathology was fibrosis/previous myocarditis (33.3%): 33.3% in GPA (n=16), 21.4% in MPA (n=3), and 50% in EGPA (n=5). This was followed by ischemic heart disease (13.9%): 12.5% in GPA (n=6), 7.1% in MPA (n=1), and 30% in EGPA (n=3) and heart failure (11.1%): 12.5% in GPA (n=6), 14.3% in MPA (n=2), and 0% in EGPA.

Conclusions: Cardiac involvement is common in AAV, with CMR abnormalities found in half of patients. The predominance of fibrosis or prior myocarditis indicates a significant burden of subclinical cardiac disease that warrants greater clinical awareness.

O-57

Is there a seasonal pattern in giant cell arteritis? revisiting the evidence in a large monocentric cohort over 30 years

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is the most common systemic vasculitis in adults aged >50 years. Several studies have suggested that disease onset might follow a seasonal pattern, potentially reflecting immunological changes or environmental triggers. However, available evidence is conflicting, often based on retrospective analyses, small sample sizes, or diagnosis/biopsy dates rather than true symptom onset. We aimed to clarify whether GCA exhibits seasonal or monthly variation by analysing a large, well-characterized single-centre cohort with systematically recorded dates of symptom onset.

Methods: We included all consecutive patients with a clinically confirmed diagnosis of GCA, validated at the last available follow-up, and a documented date of symptom onset between December 1994 and November 2023 at the Immanuel Krankenhaus Berlin-Buch, Germany. Symptom onset dates were grouped into meteorological seasons and analysed for uniformity using exact multinomial tests. Monthly variation was assessed with negative binomial regression models adjusted for long-term temporal trends with b-splines. Seasonality was modelled using month-by-month specification, four-season grouping, and cosinor functions. Subgroup analyses were performed by sex and phenotype (cranial vs extracranial).

Results: 1149 patients met inclusion criteria (median age 72 years, 35% male). The seasonal distribution of symptom onset was balanced: spring 25.4%, summer 24.0%, autumn 23.6%, winter 27.0% (p=0.36). No significant seasonal variation was observed within subgroups. In contrast, month-by-month analysis revealed significant heterogeneity (p=0.002), with higher incidence in January compared to February (+88%) and September (+67%), and in December compared to February (+80%). This monthly clustering was more evident among women and patients with cranial-only disease, though subgroup differences were not statistically significant. Alternative models imposing regular sinusoidal or seasonal patterns provided inferior fit compared with the flexible month-by-month model. Long-term analyses showed stable relative seasonal distributions despite changes in referral patterns over three decades.

Conclusions: GCA did not follow a clear seasonal distribution but showed modest monthly clustering.

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Nationwide epidemiological survey of polyarteritis nodosa in Japan conducted by JPVAS

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Background/Aims: This study aimed to estimate the number and sex ratio of patients with polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) in Japan and clarify their epidemiological and clinical characteristics.

Methods: We conducted a nationwide epidemiological survey using stratified random sampling from a nationwide list of hospitals. The first survey was aimed to estimate the number of PAN patients during the 2020 fiscal year. The secondary questionnaire was sent to facilities treating PAN patients to collect detailed information on clinical findings and treatment for each patient.

Results: In the first survey, 868 patients were reported by 2,235 hospitals out of 4,148 hospitals selected from a total of 15,628 hospitals. The male-to-female ratio was 1:1.2. Based on these numbers, the number of patients with PAN in Japan was estimated to be 2,200 (95% confidence interval, 1,800–2,700). In the second survey, we collected information on 547 patients. The mean age at diagnosis was 51.7 ± 17.6 years. Among organ manifestations, skin involvement (82.3%) and joint/muscle involvement (51.5%) were most frequently reported. Most patients (97.8%) were prescribed oral glucocorticoids, and glucocorticoid pulse therapy was administered to 21.9%. Concomitant immunosuppressants were used in 80.5%. Frequently administered agents included azathioprine (59.3%), cyclophosphamide (49.3%), and methotrexate (30.7%). Remission was achieved in 91.2%, but recurrence occurred in 47.8% of cases. Of the 547 patients, 15.9% met the diagnostic criteria for cutaneous arteritis: the male-to-female ratio was 1:3.8, and the mean age at onset was 47.7 ± 14.8 years. In addition, 22 patients had paediatric-onset PAN, defined as disease onset at age 18 years or younger, and exhibited a higher frequency of fever and skin involvement.

Conclusions: This epidemiological study revealed the number and sex ratio of patients with PAN in Japan, along with their clinical characteristics, as well as the features of paediatric-onset PAN and cutaneous arteritis.

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The characteristics and treatment outcome of Takayasu arteritis and giant cell arteritis in Japan from a nationwide prospective cohort study: JPVAS

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a large-vessel vasculitis affecting the aorta, major branches, coronary, and pulmonary arteries. Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is also a large-vessel vasculitis that primarily affects individuals over the age of 50, causing inflammation in the aorta and its branches in the head and neck, as well as the temporal and ophthalmic arteries. Although Japan has a relatively high prevalence of TAK, real-world data on diagnosis, clinical features, and treatment response remain scarce, and its distinction from giant cell arteritis (GCA) is still debated. This study aimed to prospectively clarify the current clinical characteristics, treatment patterns, and outcomes of TAK and GCA in Japan.

Methods: A nationwide prospective registry enrolled patients newly diagnosed with TAK or GCA between April 2015 and March 2018 at 30 centres. Clinical data, imaging findings, treatments, and outcomes were collected for three years. Disease activity was defined as absent if symptoms remained stable for ≥ 6 months.

Results: A total of 191 patients were registered (TAK n=74, GCA n=117). TAK showed more aortic/first-branch involvement, while cranial and musculoskeletal symptoms were more common in GCA; polymyalgia rheumatica occurred only in GCA and ulcerative colitis only in TAK. PET-CT was performed in $\sim 60\%$ of patients. HLA-B52 positivity was 60% in TAK vs 25% in GCA. Initial prednisolone doses were similar (TAK 40 mg/day, GCA 37 mg/day), but biologic use was higher in TAK. Remission was achieved earlier in GCA, yet relapse rates ($\sim 40\%$) and time to relapse were similar. Imaging progression accompanied $\sim 60\%$ of TAK relapses but only $\sim 20\%$ of GCA relapses.

Conclusions: This first nationwide prospective registry revealed key differences between TAK and GCA in Japan, including vascular distribution, genetic background, and treatment response. These findings may inform optimized diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for large-vessel vasculitis.

O-60

Clinical heterogeneity of IgA vasculitis: a cluster-based approach to risk stratification

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis (IgAV) is usually self-limiting with good prognosis, though some patients develop gastrointestinal or renal complications. The aim of the research was to identify clinical subgroups of IgAV through cluster analysis using clinical and laboratory parameters.

Methods: Children diagnosed with IgAV or IgA vasculitis nephritis (IgAVN) between 2019–2024 at three Croatian paediatric centres were included. Parameters for clustering were: joint, gastrointestinal, and renal involvement; severe skin changes; CRP, ESR, C3, C4; blood in stool; haematuria (microscopic/persistent); and proteinuria. Ward's D linkage in R was applied. Associations between relapse rate, age at diagnosis, and cluster allocation were analysed using generalized linear models with post hoc comparisons.

Results: The study included 184 patients (45% male), median age 6.3 years (range 4.4–7.9). Cluster analysis identified four subgroups: Cluster 1 (smallest): arthritis with elevated ESR/CRP; Cluster 2: arthritis ± inflammatory markers, no systemic involvement; Cluster 3: arthritis plus renal involvement, occasional gastrointestinal symptoms; highest burden of multi-organ involvement, including nearly all patients with decreased C3. Cluster 4 (largest): arthritis with gastrointestinal involvement, occasional inflammatory marker elevation. Severe skin changes occurred across all clusters. Patients in Cluster 3 were 3.5 times more likely to be ≥7 years at diagnosis ($p=0.005$) and had a 5-fold higher relapse risk ($p=0.001$) compared with other clusters.

Conclusions: Cluster analysis revealed four distinct IgAV subgroups with differing organ involvement. The subgroup with renal disease was linked to older age at diagnosis and higher relapse rates, underscoring the need for closer monitoring. These findings highlight the heterogeneity of IgAV and support tailored approaches to follow-up and management based on early clinical presentation.

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Characterizing ANCA-specific B cells in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a severe autoimmune disease, characterized by ANCAs targeting myeloperoxidase (MPO) or proteinase-3 (PR3). ANCA-specific B-cells have a central role in AAV pathophysiology, but current knowledge of their markers and dysregulated pathways is limited. Aim of this study is to characterize ANCA-specific B-cells in AAV patients to gain pathophysiologic insight and identify novel treatment targets.

Methods: B-cell receptor repertoires and whole transcriptomes of B-cells were analysed with single cell RNA sequencing combined with CITE-seq in 15 AAV patients and 5 healthy controls (HCs). 250 monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) were expressed of highly expanded and/or mutated B-cells. Their target antigens were screened with ELISAs and affinity was measured with bio-layer interferometry (BLI). Neutrophils of HCs were isolated, ethanol-fixed and stained with mAbs to study ANCA staining patterns.

Results: AAV patients had significantly increased clonally expanded antibody-secreting cells (ASC) and expanded and hypermutated IgA+ B-cells as compared to HCs. Light chain rearrangements and lambda usage were higher in AAV. Expanded B-cell clones demonstrated upregulated genes involved in antibody production, B-cell survival and migration in AAV versus HC. We identified 24 clonal families targeting MPO (7 anti-MPO+, 2 anti-PR3+ patients) and 4 clonal families targeting PR3 (3 anti-PR3+ patients). Most MPO-specific B-cells were clonally expanded IgA+/IgG+ ASCs with increased somatic hypermutations. PR3-specific B-cells were clonally expanded IgG+ switched memory B-cells, all expressing IGHV1. BLI demonstrated that the affinity of these ANCAs was 10⁻⁷–10⁻⁸ KD(M) for their antigens. Neutrophil staining confirmed c-ANCA and p-ANCA patterns for respectively PR3- and MPO-specific ANCAs.

Conclusions: Concluding, our scRNA sequencing data reveals significant alterations in B-cell populations and their functional characteristics, suggesting a potential ongoing mucosal immune activation. Our characterization of ANCA-specific B-cells and their dysregulated activation provides insight into the pathogenic mechanisms underlying AAV.

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Spatial transcriptomics reveals differential immune and tissue responses in kidney biopsies from patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis according to the ANCA serotype

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Background/Aims: Kidney involvement in ANCA-associated vasculitis is frequent, severe, and a major determinant of long-term patient prognosis. In patients with kidney disease, outcome is influenced by histological class, with crescentic class associated with poorer outcomes than focal class, and by ANCA specificity, with MPO-ANCA patients experiencing worse renal outcomes and PR3-ANCA patients higher relapse rates. We aimed to better understand these determinants studying spatial immune and tissue transcriptomic programmes in kidney biopsies.

Methods: Visium HD spatial transcriptomics (10x Genomics) was performed on 12 kidney biopsies: 5 MPO-ANCA (2 focal, 3 crescentic), 5 PR3-ANCA (2 focal, 3 crescentic), and 2 post-transplant kidney controls without clinical or histological evidence of rejection. Clustering was performed following the Visium HD multi-sample integration analysis pipeline from 10X Genomics using Seurat R package v5.3.0. and differential gene expression analyses were conducted between groups to identify biological determinants linked to ANCA features and histological class.

Results: All major expected kidney structures were identified, including vascular, tubulo-interstitial, and glomerular compartments. Immune clusters were significantly expanded in both MPO-ANCA and PR3-ANCA kidneys compared with controls. Both patient groups displayed strong immune activation, with enrichment for neutrophil degranulation, complement activation, and humoral immune response. Direct comparison between MPO-ANCA and PR3-ANCA patients showed that MPO-ANCA kidneys were enriched for extracellular matrix remodelling, profibrotic pathways and greater signs of tissue injury, whereas PR3-ANCA kidneys exhibited stronger inflammatory programmes with higher immune signatures such as neutrophil, B cell, and complement activation. Other ongoing analyses focus on differences between focal and crescentic classes to identify the factors that drive the transition from focal to crescentic patterns and contribute to disease severity.

Conclusions: These results reveal distinct immune and tissue transcriptomic profiles in MPO-ANCA and PR3-ANCA renal disease. These findings highlight the heterogeneity of the disease and may support precision medicine strategies in ANCA-associated vasculitis.

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The phenotype and function of low density neutrophils in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Low density neutrophils (LDN) are increasingly recognised to be present at elevated frequency in patients with inflammatory conditions, including anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Proinflammatory properties of LDN, reported in systemic lupus erythematosus, suggest potential roles in disease pathogenesis. We characterised phenotypic and functional properties of LDN in AAV.

Methods: LDN were isolated from blood using negative immunomagnetic selection and density centrifugation. ANCA IgG was purified from plasma exchange fluid. Surface phenotype was determined with spectral flow cytometry. Phagocytosis and reactive oxygen species (ROS) were measured using conventional flow cytometry. NETosis was assessed by staining for citrullinated histone-3 (H3Cit). IL-8 release was quantified by ELISA of supernatants. Survival was determined by fluorescence and luminescence assays for necrosis and apoptosis.

Results: Patients with active AAV (aAAV) had increased frequency of LDN, compared to patients in remission (rAAV) and healthy donors (HD) (median 18%, 7% and 2% of total neutrophils respectively, $p < 0.0001$). Compared to normal density neutrophils (NDN), the LDN population contained more cells with banded (15% vs 0%, $p = 0.0003$) or hyposegmented nuclei (46% vs 9%, $p < 0.0001$). LDN surface phenotype was heterogeneous, containing mature and immature subtypes based on CD10/CD16 expression. Some aAAV-specific LDN clusters expressed activation markers (LOX-1, MPO, PR3, CD11b), while others had higher CD80 and HLA-DR, suggesting antigen-presenting capability. Phagocytosis of *E. coli* BioParticles did not differ between LDN and NDN in AAV. Baseline ROS generation was higher in CD10- LDN from aAAV compared to rAAV and HD (median expression index 2.3×10^7 , 1.6×10^6 and 5.2×10^6 respectively). LDN from patients with aAAV and HD both exhibited spontaneous NETosis. LDN from aAAV released ~10-fold more IL-8 than matched NDN following ANCA stimulation. LDN survived ~50hrs longer in untreated culture than NDN.

Conclusions: LDN are a heterogeneous population containing proinflammatory phenotypes that may contribute to AAV pathogenesis.

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Kidney-targeted immunomodulatory nanomedicine for experimental glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: Glomerulonephritis (GN), a frequent manifestation of autoimmune disease, is a major contributor to chronic kidney disease. Current therapies improve outcomes but come with challenges such as adverse effects and drug resistance. Strategies that combine immunomodulation with tissue repair are needed. We aim to investigate the therapeutic potential of our novel immunomodulatory-lipid nanoparticle (LNP) in anti-glomerular basement membrane (anti-GBM) GN.

Methods: Anti-GBM GN was induced in C57BL/6 by immunisation with sheep globulin subcutaneously (day 0), followed by intravenous administration of sheep anti-mouse GBM globulin (day 4). Mice received 1 mg/kg of immunomodulatory-LNP, empty-LNP, or saline intraperitoneally on day 8, and outcomes were assessed on day 21.

Results: Ex vivo imaging of DiR-labelled immunomodulatory-LNP demonstrated enhanced and sustained kidney accumulation in anti-GBM GN compared to healthy mice (7.81×10^8 vs. 2.19×10^8 p/sec/cm²/sr at 24 hours; 8.56×10^8 vs. 1.45×10^8 p/sec/cm²/sr at 72 hours; $p < 0.05$). Immunomodulatory-LNP improved survival compared to the saline group (83% vs. 33%, $p < 0.05$); reduced crescents ($24 \pm 4\%$ vs. $42 \pm 6\%$, $p < 0.05$) and urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (151 ± 10 vs. 230 ± 30 mg/g, $p < 0.05$); and preserved podocyte marker, nephrin ($56.1 \pm 7\%$ vs. $38.7 \pm 5.7\%$ expression per glomerulus, $p < 0.05$). Treatment of human undifferentiated podocytes with immunomodulatory-LNP promoted differentiation, indicated by a reduction of Vimentin mRNA ($\log_2\text{RQ} -0.9 \pm 0.6$, $p < 0.05$) and S100A4 mRNA ($\log_2\text{RQ} -2.4 \pm 0.5$, $p < 0.05$) from the non-treated group. Immunomodulatory-LNP reduced IL-6 level in DMSO-injured human podocyte (0.51 ± 0.14 vs. 0.80 ± 0.14 OD₄₅₀, $p < 0.05$). Human PBMCs treated with immunomodulatory-LNP showed a tenfold rise in Treg frequency and reductions in Th1 and Th17 frequencies to one-fifth and half of non-treated cells, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Our novel immunomodulatory-LNP exhibited a favourable therapeutic index in animals, with an LD₅₀ of 6 mg/kg and ED₅₀ of 0.5 mg/kg (therapeutic index = 12).

Conclusions: Immunomodulatory-LNP is a promising disease-targeted therapy for GN that reduces kidney injury, promotes podocyte differentiation, and regulates immune cells with a favourable safety profile.

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Crosstalk between Th1 CD4+ T cells and adventitial fibroblasts characterises the immune perturbation in relapsing giant cell temporal arteries

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Background/Aims: Relapsing giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a major clinical challenge. The pathobiology of this disease-state is poorly understood. Although fibroblasts have been mapped in GCA-onset arteries, their putative mechanistic role and interplay with established immune culprits is unknown.

Methods: Transcriptomic datasets were obtained from three UK centres. Temporal arteries (TA) from 14 donors (n=6 GCA-onset, n=8 GCA-relapse) were processed for single-cell-RNA-sequencing (10xGenomics). Spatial transcriptomics (GeoMx/Nanostring) was performed on paired onset–relapse TAs (n=8), using CD90/CD45-labelled regions of interest. The primary comparison was onset versus relapse. Differential abundance was determined using EdgeR and differential gene expression using DESeq2. Trajectories were inferred by Monocle/scVelo; and cell-cell interactions using CellChat. Predicted fibroblast–T-cell interactions were validated in-vitro using transwell co-cultures of CD3/CD28-stimulated PBMCs with autologous relapse fibroblasts (bulk-RNAseq), complemented with TA immunostainings.

Results: In total 16,182 TA cells were analysed. Compared to baseline, relapse TA were characterised by enrichment of CD4+T-cells with a Th1 phenotype (IFNG, TBX21, CXCR3) (logFC 1.9, p<0.05) and a perturbed fibroblast subset expressing interferon response genes (CXCL9, STAT1, HLA-DRA, ICAM1), macrophage-attracting chemokines (CCL2, CCR4) and markers of tissue-remodelling (FAP, MMP9, TIMP1) (logFC 2.381, p<0.05). Trajectory analysis predicts that these differentiated from universal fibroblasts and gave rise to myofibroblasts. Adventitial FAP+fibroblasts histologically demonstrated proximity to CD4+T-cells, with a subset co-expressing phospho-STAT1, supporting the predicted T-cell fibroblast interactions. When co-cultured with PBMCs, relapse fibroblasts upregulated pro-inflammatory and MHC-II genes (STAT1, CXCL9, HLA-DRA/DPA1, ICAM1, p<0.05). Spatial transcriptomics further corroborated localisation of perturbed fibroblasts around adventitial lesions, and confirmed enrichment of Th1-cells (CXCR3, TNFRSF18, IL12) around adventitial fibroblasts in GCA-relapse.

Conclusions: We demonstrate that relapsing GCA is distinguished from onset, characterised by interferon mediated cross-talk between Th1-cells and adventitial fibroblasts. Perturbed adventitial fibroblasts can differentiate to myofibroblasts, responsible for vascular remodelling. Taken together these data provide a putative framework for the future targeting of relapsing GCA.

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C5a/C5aR1 pathway is activated in GCA lesions and blocking C5aR1 with avacopan reduces Th1-related cytokine expression in cultured arteries from patients with GCA

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Background/Aims: Despite therapeutic advances with novel agents with glucocorticoid-sparing effect, patients with giant-cell arteritis (GCA) require further reduction in glucocorticoid (GC) exposure, as the elderly are particularly vulnerable to GC-related side effects. In patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis, blocking the C5a receptor-1 (C5aR1) with avacopan has allowed a remarkable decrease in GC exposure. However, the involvement of the complement system in GCA remains unexplored. **Aim:** To perform transcriptomic and proteomic analysis of cultured temporal artery biopsies (TABs) from GCA patients and controls, to explore complement regulation/activation and to assess the impact of C5aR1 blockade in cultured GCA arteries.

Methods: Nanostring nCounter Human Inflammation panel was applied to RNA from 11 GCA arteries cultured ex vivo with or without tocilizumab. Protein array (Ray-Biotech) was applied to the supernatants. RT-PCR of C5aR1 was performed in fresh-frozen TABs (10 patients, 10 controls). C5aR1 expression was explored by immunofluorescence. TABs from 5 GCA patients were cultured ex vivo untreated or exposed to avacopan (10 µg/mL) for 5 days.

Results: Transcriptomics revealed up-regulation of complement pathways in cultured GCA samples. C5a fragment was present in the supernatant of GCA arteries but absent in controls. C5aR1 was upregulated in fresh-frozen GCA temporal arteries and expressed by inflammatory cells, endothelial cells and scattered vascular smooth muscle cells. Searching for transcripts regulated by AP-1 (C5aR1 signalling) but not by transcription factors in the classical IL-6, IFN- γ or GM-CSF signalling, revealed 5 transcripts (CYSLTR1, MBL2, PTGER3, TLR2, TNF α) increased in GCA and not reduced by tocilizumab. Among them, avacopan was able to diminish TNF α and other Th1 related transcripts.

Conclusions: C5a presence in the supernatants of cultured GCA arteries indicates local activation of the alternative complement pathway. Our findings suggest that C5aR1 blockade may contribute to disrupt inflammatory pathways in GCA. Exploring transcriptomic and functional impact of avacopan on cultured TABs is underway.

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Outcomes of patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis treated with immune checkpoint inhibitors: a case series

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Background/Aims: Immune checkpoint inhibitor (ICI) use, which has expanded across multiple oncologic indications, can lead to immune-related adverse events. In diseases with high morbidity, such as ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), this is particularly concerning. Only 5 patients with preexisting AAV receiving ICI therapy have been reported. We assessed the outcomes of patients with AAV treated with ICI in a tertiary care centre.

Methods: Retrospective study of patients with AAV receiving ICI therapy at Mass General Brigham was performed. Demographics, AAV diagnosis and history, underlying malignancy, and ICI regimen were retrieved from patients' electronic health records. AAV relapse was defined as recurrence of AAV clinical manifestations that required treatment intensification.

Results: Six patients with preexisting AAV (mean age 68.8; males 83.3%; GPA 83.3%; PR3+ 66.7%; kidney involvement 66.7%; prior relapse 50%) received ICI therapy for a mean (SD) period of 15 (15.8) months. Treated malignancies included 2 melanoma cases and 1 case each of lung, bladder, oesophageal, and endometrial cancer. Pembrolizumab was the most commonly ICI used (83.3%). At ICI initiation, AAV was in treatment-free remission for >1 year in 5 patients, and 1 patient was on rituximab due to relapse 3 months prior. While on ICI treatment, 1 patient with GPA relapsed (arthralgias, increased PR3 titres, and biopsy-proven lung nodule/mass). ICI was temporarily held and AAV remission was achieved with glucocorticoids and rituximab. ICI-therapy re-assumption was well tolerated without subsequent relapse during 41 months of follow-up. The other 5 patients (3 with relapse pre-ICI therapy) maintained AAV remission. In terms of malignancy outcomes, 4 patients died, 1 achieved complete remission, and 1 was lost to follow-up during the study period.

Conclusions: One of 6 patients with AAV relapsed while on ICI-therapy. Larger studies with longer follow-up are needed to better characterize the effects of ICI-therapy on the risk of AAV relapse.

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Obinutuzumab induces and maintains remission in refractory or relapsing ANCA-associated vasculitis – a case series

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Background/Aims: B-cell depletion with anti-CD20 therapy is the current cornerstone of management in organ- or life-threatening ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Guidelines recommend the use of rituximab or cyclophosphamide for remission induction and rituximab for remission maintenance. Obinutuzumab is a newer humanized type 2 anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody and is postulated to result in deeper tissue B cell depletion. It has an emerging role in rituximab-intolerant patients and in rituximab-refractory disease. To date, only nine cases in two case series have been published on the use of obinutuzumab in rituximab-intolerant AAV patients.

Methods: This single-centre case series reports the clinical outcomes of five patients who received obinutuzumab therapy for refractory or relapsing PR3+ granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA). All patients satisfied the 2022 ACR/EULAR classification criteria for GPA. Patient demographics, disease manifestations, previous treatments, indication for obinutuzumab, outcomes, and potential complications are reported.

Results: One male and four female patients with refractory or relapsing GPA received obinutuzumab. Three had multi-system involvement while one had isolated episcleritis/scleritis and another, severe isolated ENT disease. All patients had refractory or relapsing disease despite guideline-directed induction therapy with rituximab and cyclophosphamide. For induction of disease remission, obinutuzumab was administered at one or two doses of 1000mg at week 0 and week 2. Maintenance treatment consisted of one or two 1000mg infusions at six- to twelve- monthly intervals. Obinutuzumab was effective in inducing and maintaining disease remission. During a median follow-up of 14 months (range: 4-51 months), obinutuzumab was well tolerated with two infections noted (one serious adverse event with SARS-CoV-2 infection requiring hospitalization).

Conclusions: This case series illustrating obinutuzumab use in five patients with GPA adds to the limited published literature. Obinutuzumab use in the management of rituximab-refractory or relapsing AAV appears to be efficacious and well tolerated. Results of use thereof in larger clinical studies are awaited.

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Daratumumab treatment for refractory granulomatosis with polyangiitis: a case report and review of the literature

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Background/Aims: Refractory anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody (ANCA) vasculitis remains a significant management challenge with no evidence-based treatment options. Up to one-third of patients fail to achieve remission with standard induction regimens, and persistent disease activity is linked to substantial morbidity and mortality.

Daratumumab, an anti-CD38 monoclonal antibody is emerging as a novel therapeutic agent in antibody-mediated autoimmune diseases. By depleting long lived plasma cells which escape the action of rituximab due to absence of CD20 expression, daratumumab targets an increasingly recognised mechanism driving refractory ANCA vasculitis.

Methods: We report the case of a 17-year-old patient with severe life-threatening granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and multi-system manifestations including significant nasopharyngeal disease, glomerulonephritis, pulmonary involvement and pachymeningitis. Remission was not achieved despite intensive immunosuppression, including 4 pulses of intravenous methylprednisolone, methotrexate, rituximab, cyclophosphamide, avacopan and intravenous immunoglobulin. Pachymeningeal, nasopharyngeal, tracheal and pulmonary disease progressed, and oral corticosteroid maintenance could not be tapered below 15 milligrams (mg) daily. Daratumumab was subsequently initiated according to multiple myeloma protocols.

Results: Daratumumab led to marked symptom improvement, radiological stability and for the first time prednisolone was weaned below 5 mg daily. Serological parameters improved with reduction in ANCA proteinase 3 and immunoglobulin titres, reflecting depletion of autoantibody-secreting plasma cells.

Conclusions: To date, only four cases of daratumumab treatment for refractory ANCA vasculitis have been reported in the literature. Here, we present an additional case demonstrating its efficacy in severe, multi-system refractory GPA, and to our knowledge, the first reported case of pachymeningitis responding to daratumumab. This case highlights daratumumab as a promising therapeutic option in ANCA vasculitis and other autoantibody mediated diseases, warranting evaluation of its safety and efficacy in controlled clinical trials.

O-70

Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) for diffuse alveolar haemorrhage due to small vessel vasculitis, a single-centre case series.

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Background/Aims: Diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH) is a life-threatening complication of systemic small vessel vasculitides. ECMO is a potentially life-saving supportive therapy for acute respiratory failure but DAH may be seen as a contraindication due to risk of coagulopathy and worsening haemorrhage. We describe the management and clinical outcomes of vasculitic DAH requiring ECMO at our centre since 2012.

Methods: We performed a retrospective observational study of patients managed by our vasculitis service, who required ECMO for DAH between April 2012 and June 2025. Eligible patients had a confirmed diagnosis of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, anti-glomerular basement membrane (anti-GBM) disease, or ANCA-negative small vessel vasculitis.

Results: Nine patients received ECMO for DAH due to vasculitis during the study period. Five (56%) were male, median age of 54 years (16 to 67 years). Six (67%) were PR3-ANCA positive, two (22%) MPO-ANCA positive and one (11%) ANCA and anti-GBM negative. The mean interval from admission to hospital to ECMO initiation was 5.6 days, with a mean ECMO duration of 19.8 days. Average intensive care and hospital stays were 36.8 and 55.8 days, respectively. All patients received high-dose corticosteroids. Induction immunosuppression included a combination of intravenous cyclophosphamide and rituximab in four, cyclophosphamide alone in one, and rituximab alone in three. Eight patients (89%) also underwent plasma exchange; median 7 sessions (range 5-12). Three received high-dose intravenous immunoglobulin. Survival to hospital discharge was achieved in eight patients (89%), all of whom achieved good functional recovery. A 54 year-old man died due to multiorgan failure from uncontrolled disease activity including myocarditis.

Conclusions: Our institutional experience demonstrates favourable outcomes with ECMO in patients with severe acute respiratory failure due to vasculitic DAH, across a wide age range. Further research is needed to inform referral and acceptance practices for ECMO in patients with AAV and related conditions.

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Acute coronary arteritis at presentation of Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a large-vessel vasculitis affecting the aorta and its proximal branches. Coronary involvement in TAK contributes to significant morbidity. The pathophysiology and pattern of disease differs from conventional atherosclerosis, with a greater propensity for rapidly progressive, ostial and aneurysmal disease. Previous analysis of our cohort using computed tomography coronary angiography (CTCA) revealed severe silent coronary artery disease in 22%, but little is known about the prevalence of acute coronary arteritis in this patient population. We highlight the specific diagnostic and interventional challenges of acute coronary arteritis in TAK.

Methods: A database of 169 patients with TAK at a UK single centre was retrospectively reviewed. Demographic and clinical data were collected, including TAK angiographic classification, imaging, immunosuppressive treatment and coronary intervention.

Results: Five patients with acute coronary arteritis at presentation were identified. All five patients presented with acute coronary syndrome or angina (median CRP 12.9mg/L, 80% hsTnI <15ng/L), and multi-vessel coronary and peripheral arterial involvement. Aortitis was present in 60%. 4/5 patients had ≤2 conventional cardiovascular risk factors. All patients underwent CTCA, positron emission tomography (PET) and magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) imaging. All patients received glucocorticoids, 3/5 (60%) intravenous tocilizumab and 3/5 (60%) mycophenolate mofetil. One patient developed early graft restenosis following coronary bypass surgery. One patient re-presented with angina six months after initiation of tocilizumab and required percutaneous stenting. Three patients symptomatically improved following immunosuppression and did not require intervention.

Conclusions: Coronary arteritis may be the initial presentation of TAK. Early recognition and instigation of immunosuppression improved short and long-term outcomes and reduces the need for coronary intervention. Optimal control of inflammation is important prior to any revascularisation to avoid procedural complications and restenosis. Multimodality imaging plays a crucial role in diagnosis and therapeutic monitoring by identifying pre-stenotic disease and allowing visualisation beyond the endolumen.

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Distinguishing infectious from non-infectious aortitis: two cases highlighting clinical clues to aid differentiation

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Background/Aims: Aortitis is defined as inflammation of the aortic wall and can lead to aneurysm, rupture and death. Early recognition of the underlying cause is necessary for treatment to prevent permanent consequences of vessel inflammation. We present two cases of infectious aortitis with significant diagnostic uncertainty.

Case 1: A 73-year-old gentleman presented with a six-week history of back pain and constitutional symptoms. Investigations showed raised inflammatory markers and an infrarenal inflammatory aneurysm on angiography. There was no improvement with broad spectrum intravenous antibiotics, so he was commenced on prednisolone 50mg daily. Eventually, due to aneurysm progression he underwent an open repair and intra-operative biopsies showed micro-abscesses with a 16s RNA positive for *Carpnocytophagia canimorsus*.

Case 2: A 73-year-old gentleman presented with a one-day history of abdominal pain. Initial investigations showed a C-reactive protein of 53 mg/L and angiography revealed an infra-renal aortic aneurysm. He was managed with blood pressure control, with symptomatic improvement. An autoimmune screen showed an elevated IgG4 level of 1.04g/L, and a multidisciplinary team meeting concluded that the lesion was not amenable to biopsy. He received a presumptive diagnosis of IgG4-RD aortitis and commenced prednisolone 50mg daily. Three months later he developed new fevers. A repeat scan showed increasing enhancing soft tissue surrounding the abdominal aorta which was then biopsied. PCR was positive for *Mycobacterium bovis*, yielding a diagnosis of BCG-aortitis.

Conclusions: It is particularly important to distinguish between infectious and non-infectious causes of aortitis as infectious aortitis carries higher rates of vascular complication and mortality. Previous studies have shown that patients with infectious aortitis are more likely to be males, have multiple comorbidities and shorter duration of symptoms compared to non-infectious aortitis but there remains significant clinical heterogeneity. A high index of suspicion is necessary to correctly identify and treat infectious aortitis before complications arise.

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Isolated pulmonary Takayasu's arteritis with co-existing axial spondyloarthritis: successful control with secukinumab

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Background/Aims: Isolated pulmonary Takayasu's arteritis (TAK) is a rare and aggressive form of large-vessel vasculitis. It is often refractory to standard immunosuppressive therapies, and treatment becomes more complex when associated with co-existing immune-mediated disease such as axial spondyloarthritis. Evidence suggests an immunogenetic overlap between TAK and axial spondyloarthritis, with a reported prevalence of co-occurrence of up to 20%. There is limited evidence to guide therapy in such overlap cases.

Methods: We describe the clinical course of a 28-year-old woman with isolated pulmonary TAK. She was diagnosed radiologically 11 years earlier with a vasculitic pulmonary mass and stenosis of multiple pulmonary arteries after presenting with chest pain and worsening exercise tolerance. She initially failed methotrexate and tocilizumab but subsequently achieved stable disease control with infliximab for seven years. Disease progression then occurred following development of anti-TNF antibodies, with worsening breathlessness and radiological evidence of progressive pulmonary vasculitis, including new vessel-wall thickening and amputation of lingular branches on CT. She was switched to intravenous cyclophosphamide, which induced recovery of pulmonary symptoms. Soon afterwards, she developed acute inflammatory back pain with lumbar enthesitis and MRI-confirmed sacroiliitis consistent with active axial spondyloarthritis. Following multidisciplinary review, secukinumab was initiated in June 2025.

Results: The patient received four doses of cyclophosphamide (total 5g) before commencing monthly secukinumab (anti-IL-17A) 150mg subcutaneously. Treatment resulted in rapid resolution of axial symptoms, complete corticosteroid withdrawal, and sustained stability of pulmonary TAK on serial imaging. Both conditions remain well-controlled at subsequent follow-up.

Conclusions: This case highlights the therapeutic challenge of managing isolated pulmonary Takayasu's arteritis complicated by axial spondyloarthritis. It demonstrates the limitations of conventional DMARDs and biologics, and the potential efficacy of IL-17A inhibition as a novel therapeutic approach capable of controlling both vasculitis and spondyloarthritis. These findings add to the emerging evidence base for IL-17A blockade in large-vessel vasculitis.

Mepolizumab 100 vs 300 mg/4 weeks for eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA): a 24-month retrospective cohort study by the European EGPA study group

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Background/Aims: Mepolizumab is approved at 300 mg/4 weeks for eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA), but is frequently used at 100 mg/4 weeks (asthma dosage) in clinical practice.

Methods: We recruited patients with EGPA treated with mepolizumab at EESG centres. Complete and partial responses (CR and PR) were defined as BVAS=0 with prednisone \leq 4 mg/day or $>$ 4 mg/day.

Results: 265 patients started mepolizumab at 100 mg/4 weeks, and 289 at 300 mg/4 weeks. At beginning, the median BVAS was 4 (IQR 2-7) and 3 (2-6) in the two groups. The median prednisone dose was 10 (5-16) and 7.5 (5-15) mg/day; 7% and 10% were off-corticosteroids. At 3 months (T3), CR was achieved by 23/237 (10%) patients on 100 mg/4 weeks and 58/278 (21%) on 300mg/4 weeks; PR on 75/237 (32%) and 129/278 (46%) (overall $p < 0.001$). The median prednisone dose was 5 (3-10) and 5 (2.5 – 7.5) mg/day, respectively; 12% and 20% were corticosteroid-free. At T6, CR was achieved by 56/235 (24%) patients on 100 mg/4 weeks and 110/289 (38%) on 300mg/4 weeks, while PR on 63/235 (27%) and 86/289 (30%) ($p < 0.001$). The median prednisone dose was 5 (0-6) and 4 (0 – 5)

mg/day; 25% and 30% were off-treatment. At T12, 77/214 (36%) patients on 100 mg/4 weeks and 128/259 (49%) on 300mg/4 weeks had a CR, while 41/214 (19%) and 50/259 (19%) a PR ($p < 0.01$). The median prednisone dose was 2.5 (0-5) mg/day in both groups; 35% and 44% were off-corticosteroids. At T24, CR was achieved by 64/162 (40%) patients on 100 mg/4 weeks and 86/165 (52%) on 300mg/4 weeks, while PR by 31/162 (19%) and 27/165 (16%) ($p = n.s.$). The prednisone dose was 2.5 (0-5) and 0 (0-5) mg/day; 44% and 53% were corticosteroid-free.

Conclusions: Mepolizumab 300 mg/4 weeks seems associated with higher response and lower corticosteroid exposure.

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Factors associated with risk of infection in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: RITAZAREM was a randomized controlled trial comparing rituximab (RTX) and azathioprine (AZA) for maintenance of remission in relapsing ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). The objective was to identify factors associated with risk of infection.

Methods: Cox regression models analysed the association of patient characteristics with infections. Variables included age, sex, ANCA type, co-morbidities, organ involvement, damage, use of glucocorticoids and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, and immunoglobulin levels. Two models were created: i) for the induction of remission phase, and ii) for the maintenance of remission and follow-up phase.

Results: 62 of 187 subjects had at least one infection in the induction phase. Factors associated with risk of infection were chronic lung disease (Hazard ratio [HR] 1.79, 95% confidence interval [CI] 1.01-3.18, P=0.048), active pulmonary nodules or cavities (HR 2.04, 95%CI 1.14-3.65, P=0.016), IgM (g/L) at Baseline (HR 0.56, 95%CI 0.32-0.98, P=0.044), and time-varying trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole use (HR 0.56, 95%CI 0.33-0.97, P=0.040). Time-varying glucocorticoid dose was not associated with infection (HR 0.99, 95%CI 0.97-1.02, P=0.496). 128 of 170 subjects had infectious events in the maintenance and follow-up phases. Infections during induction were associated with subsequent infections during maintenance (HR 2.35, 95%CI 1.61-3.44, P<0.001). Pulmonary fibrosis (HR 2.46, 95%CI 1.05-5.74, P=0.038) and large airway obstruction (HR 2.78, 95%CI 1.17-6.62, P=0.021) were also associated with infections but use of trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole or IgM levels at Month 4 were not associated. Risk of infection did not differ between subjects assigned to RTX or AZA.

Conclusions: In AAV, pre-existing chronic lung disease and damage are associated with risk of infection. Infectious events during treatment to induce remission are associated with subsequent events during maintenance. Choice of RTX vs. AZA for maintenance of remission does not change the risk of infection. Prophylaxis with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and higher IgM are associated with lower risk of infection during the induction phase.

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Patterns of sinonasal symptoms in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Sinonasal disease is prominent in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), yet studies lack detailed information about severity and types of sinonasal symptoms. Using an international patient research network, we examined patterns of sinonasal symptoms in AAV using the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test-22 (SNOT-22), a validated patient-reported outcome for chronic rhinosinusitis.

Methods: Patients with AAV were recruited January-May 2025 and rated 26 sinonasal symptoms (scale 0-5), including the SNOT-22 plus four vasculitis-specific items: nasal crusting, blood-tinged nasal discharge/crusts, nosebleeds, and nasal pain. Multivariable regression identified characteristics associated with higher scores. Sinonasal symptoms associated with disease activity were determined using LASSO logistic regression. K-means clustering defined symptom-based subgroups.

Results: 721 participants with AAV from 25 countries were included and 276 (38%) had active disease. Mean total SNOT-22 score was 38 (range 0-122) and was higher in active disease vs. remission (mean score 45 vs 32, $P < 0.01$). In multivariable linear regression, higher total scores were independently associated with active disease ($\beta = 9.4$, [6.4-12.5]), prior sinus disease ($\beta = 12.3$, [7.7-16.9]), age ($\beta = -0.2$, [-0.3,-0.04]), female sex ($\beta = 4.9$, [1.6-8.2]), current smoker ($\beta = 13.3$, [4.1-22.5]), recent infection ($\beta = 6.1$, [3.9-8.3]), seasonal allergies ($\beta = 3.6$, [1.6-5.7]), and nasal antibiotic use ($\beta = 9.1$, [2.2-16.1]). LASSO-based variable selection identified 6 sinonasal symptoms associated with active disease (fatigue, blood-tinged nasal discharge/crusts, dizziness, ear pain, thick nasal discharge, frustrated/restless/irritable) and 1 item associated with remission (sneezing). Four clusters emerged from symptom-based analysis. Cluster 3 showed increased active disease and infections in contrast to Cluster 4.

Conclusions: There is substantial heterogeneity in sinonasal symptoms among patients with AAV. Compared to patients in remission, active patients report higher fatigue, blood-tinged nasal discharge/crusts, and dizziness, and lower scores for sneezing. A detailed understanding of the sinonasal symptom profile in AAV may improve clinical monitoring. Future studies examining longitudinal changes in sinonasal profiles/clusters and their association with relapse and treatment response are needed.

Renal function trajectory in AAV using FAIRVASC data: preliminary results

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Background/Aims: Anti Neutrophil Cytoplasmic Antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitides (AAVs) are autoimmune diseases characterized by inflammation of small vessels, frequently affecting renal function. Thanks to advances in diagnosis and treatment, renal deterioration is now more gradual and less evident, making it increasingly important to monitor estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) over time as a marker of renal functionality. FAIRVASC, a federated European network that harmonizes clinical data across multiple national registries, enables large-scale analyses of kidney outcomes in AAV.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective multicentre study using FAIRVASC data from four national registries: the Czech Registry of ANCA-Associated Vasculitis, the French Vasculitis Study Group (FVSG) registry, the German GeVas registry, and the Irish Rare Kidney Disease (RKD) registry. Patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) or microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), all with renal involvement at diagnosis and at least one eGFR measurement, were included. The primary outcome was the trajectory of eGFR over time, assessed through linear mixed-effects models. Clinical and serological variables were analysed as predictors of baseline kidney function and its longitudinal evolution.

Results: A total of 1,501 patients were included in the final analysis. MPA patients present with lower eGFR values at diagnosis but their recovery over time seemed more favourable as compared to GPA patients. Patients with PR3-ANCA start with higher eGFR than MPO-ANCA patients, but with no significant difference in eGFR recovery over time. Male patients have higher eGFR at diagnosis than female patients. The number of extra-renal manifestations at diagnosis is associated with higher initial eGFR values.

Conclusions: This study represents, to date, the largest multicentre analysis of the longitudinal evolution of eGFR in AAV patients. Preliminary results are consistent with the literature, and this work lays the foundation for future methodological developments, particularly the integration of longitudinal analysis of eGFR with time-to-event models, using joint modelling approaches.

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RETRACE-renal trajectory clustering: a study of end-stage kidney disease onset in relation to creatinine trajectory clusters

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Background/Aims: End-stage kidney disease (ESKD) is a major complication of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Early prediction of renal outcomes remains challenging. Building on our prior work, we investigated whether six-month creatinine trajectories and eGFR slopes combined with histology information could stratify long-term risk of ESKD.

Methods: Patients with GPA or MPA with renal involvement were identified from the RITA-Ireland Vasculitis Registry. Of 754 patients, 324 with ≥ 2 values were eligible for inclusion. Early creatinine trajectories were initially modelled using linear mixed-effects models. Six-month creatinine data (N=257) were then clustered with K-means. Predictors of ESKD was assessed using Fine-Grey competing-risk survival models, considering death as a competing event.

Results: Creatinine trajectory clustering identified three distinct clusters: Stable (n=122), Improving (n=77), and Declining (n=58), which showed significant differences in 5-year ESKD risk ($p < 0.00071$). The Improving group, despite having higher baseline creatinine level and more anti-MPO-positive patients, had the lowest five-year ESKD rate (2%). Interestingly, the dominant Berden histological classification in the Stable (9%) and Declining (22%) groups, with much higher ESKD probability, was “focal”, whereas that in the Improving group was “crescentic”. In a multivariate model controlling for Berden class, diagnosis, ANCA specificity, age and sex, membership of clusters B and C remained significantly different from cluster A.

Conclusions: Combining creatinine trajectory with histology identifies a sub-group with apparently benign histology who did not respond well to therapy. Incorporating dynamic biomarker assessment into histology scoring systems improves discrimination.

Concordance between presenting clinical features and relapse in granulomatosis with polyangiitis.

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Background/Aims: To investigate the concordance between organ involvement at diagnosis and relapse in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and factors associated with new disease features at relapse.

Methods: Data from a national database of newly diagnosed patients was analysed. Clinical features were recorded at diagnosis and relapse, grouped by organ system, and categorized as either major or minor manifestations. Odds ratios (ORs) and hazard ratios were used to assess associations between baseline features and first relapse. Independent predictors of new organ involvement at relapse were identified using multivariable logistic regression.

Results: Among 795 GPA patients (median follow-up 3.5 years), 394 (50%) relapsed; organ involvement at relapse was available for 376 patients. Relapses most often affected ENT, lungs, and kidneys. Organ involvement at diagnosis strongly predicted recurrence in the same organ: eyes (OR 5.26), cardiovascular system (OR 4.69), lungs (OR 4.29), kidneys (OR 3.36), and mucocutaneous system (OR 3.24). Major manifestations that strongly predicted recurrence were scleritis, pachymeningitis, subglottic stenosis, and worsening renal function. For 56% of patients, the first relapse affected only the initially involved organs. Of the 165 patients with new organ manifestations, these were rarely isolated (n = 34) and usually occurred alongside involvement of at

least one previously affected organ (n = 131). In multivariable analysis, systemic, ENT, and lung manifestations at diagnosis were associated with a lower risk of new organ disease at relapse.

Conclusions: Although new features can still emerge, organ involvement at diagnosis strongly predicts relapse patterns and can inform risk assessment and patient education.

O-80

Dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonism improves endothelial function and fibrinolysis in ANCA vasculitis: a randomised, double blind, active control clinical trial

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Background/Aims: Endothelial dysfunction and arterial stiffness are major contributors to cardiovascular disease (CVD) in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Endothelin-1 drives both processes. We investigated whether sparsentan, a dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonist, improves vascular function compared with irbesartan, an angiotensin receptor blocker.

Methods: Thirty-two patients with AAV in long-term remission entered a randomised, double-blind, active-control, parallel group study. Following withdrawal of previous renin-angiotensin system (RAS) inhibition, patients were randomised 1:1 to six weeks of treatment with either sparsentan or irbesartan. Endothelial vasomotor function was assessed by gold standard venous occlusion plethysmography following randomised intra-arterial infusions of acetylcholine (ACh, endothelium-dependent vasodilator) and sodium nitroprusside (SNP, endothelium-independent vasodilator). Endothelial fibrinolytic capacity was assessed by stimulated tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) release. Arterial stiffness was measured by gold standard pulse wave velocity (PWV). The primary endpoint was the change from baseline to week six in ACh-mediated vasodilatation.

Results: All patients completed the study (64±12 years; 69% male; blood pressure (BP) 134/82 mmHg; eGFR 58±22 mL/min/1.73m²; time from diagnosis 5.4 (3.8-12.1) years). At baseline, 75% of patients were prescribed both a RAS and sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor. Baseline BP, endothelial vasomotor and fibrinolytic function, and PWV did not differ between treatment arms. Sparsentan increased endothelium-dependent vasodilatation by 46±48% (P=0.02), whereas irbesartan had no effect (-0.08±40%, P=0.39). Endothelium-independent responses were unchanged. Sparsentan markedly enhanced stimulated tPA release over the 6-week study period [+277 (140-352) % versus +11 (-18-44) %, P<0.001]. Both sparsentan and irbesartan reduced PWV (sparsentan: -1.4±0.7 m/s, irbesartan: -0.8±0.5, both P<0.0001 versus baseline), but sparsentan conferred greater protection (P=0.007 for sparsentan versus irbesartan). Both drugs were well tolerated.

Conclusions: Dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonism improves endothelial vasomotor and fibrinolytic function and reduces arterial stiffness in AAV. These findings support dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor blockade as a promising strategy to reduce cardiovascular risk, justifying longer-term outcome studies.

O-81

Pneumococcal vaccine responses in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis: results of the ACQUIVAS trial

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Background/Aims: Pneumococcal (Pn) vaccination is advised for patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) to reduce infection risk from *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The effect of rituximab (RTX) on Pn vaccine responses is poorly understood. The ACQUIVAS trial aimed to determine if RTX reduced Pn vaccine immunogenicity, and whether a 13-valent Pn polysaccharide conjugate vaccine (PCV-13) followed by a 23-valent Pn polysaccharide vaccine (PPV-23) prime-boost strategy improved serological responses.

Methods: AAV patients in remission on RTX or non-RTX immunosuppression received PCV-13 at Month 0. Those who had not received PPV-23 within 5 years also received PPV-23 at Month 6. The primary outcome was a twofold increase in $\geq 6/12$ Pn serotype-specific antibodies (SSAb) from baseline 28 (+/-7) days post-PCV13. Secondary outcomes included Pn SSAb titres 28 (+/-7) days post-PPV-23 (month 7) and the number of Pn SSAs above a protective threshold of $\geq 0.35\mu\text{g/mL}$

Results: 105 patients (61% male; 53 RTX, 52 non-RTX) were recruited between October 2018 and May 2022. Median age was 66.9 years (range 40.3-90.1) in the RTX and 69.7 (43.0-85.8) in the non-RTX group. Median time since RTX was 60 weeks (18-540). In the non-RTX group, 26 received azathioprine, 20 mycophenolate mofetil and 6 methotrexate. The primary outcome was achieved in 4/52 (7.7%) RTX and 21/47 (44.7%) non-RTX patients (difference 37%, 95% CI 21%–53%; $p < 0.001$). By month 7, 7/31 (22.6%) RTX and 12/22 (54.5%) non-RTX patients had a twofold increase in $\geq 6/12$ serotypes relative to baseline, with 59.4% of RTX and 54.5% of non-RTX patients having > 8 Pn serotypes $\geq 0.35\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Conclusions: Overall, 48% of patients failed to meet the primary endpoint. Although boosting with PPV-23 augmented responses in some RTX-treated patients, more non-RTX patients achieved a twofold increase in $\geq 6/12$ serotypes overall. Together, these data suggest that alternative vaccination or protection strategies against Pn infection should be considered, particularly in RTX-treated patients.

O-82

Post-transplant malignancies in kidney recipients with ANCA-associated vasculitis: a multicentre matched cohort study

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Background/Aims: Kidney transplantation (KT) is the optimal therapy for kidney failure but is associated with long-term complications, including post-transplant malignancies (PTM). Patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) represent a unique subgroup, cumulatively exposed to pre- and post-transplant immunosuppression, yet PTM risk in this population remains poorly defined.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective, multicentre study across 12 French transplant centres using the ASTRE registry. We identified 190 kidney transplant recipients (KTR) with kidney failure due to AAV glomerulonephritis and matched them (1:2) with 380 controls from the same centres. Detailed clinical and oncological data were extracted from medical charts. Outcomes included PTM and non-melanoma skin cancers (NMSC, considered separately), their timing, characteristics, risk factors, and impact on post-transplant outcomes.

Results: After a median follow-up of 5.6 years, the cumulative incidence of PTM at 10 years was similar in AAV-GN (23%) and control (22%) groups. Urological, digestive, and respiratory cancers predominated in both groups, with comparable delays to onset and stage at diagnosis. In the whole cohort, in multivariable analysis, the main independent predictor of PTM was older recipient age (HR 1.04 [1.02-1.07] per year, $p < 0.001$). In AAV recipients, smoking (HR 5.22 [1.39-19.6] for active vs. never, $p = 0.014$) and HLA-DR mismatch (HR 1.95 [1.11-3.45], $p = 0.021$) significantly increased PTM risk. PTM did not significantly affect graft survival or rejection, but it markedly worsened patient survival: mortality risk rose 3-fold in controls and nearly 7-fold in AAV recipients.

Conclusions: In the era of modern immunosuppression, KTR with AAV are not at higher overall risk of PTM compared to matched controls. However, once cancer develops, its prognostic impact is particularly severe in AAV recipients. To optimize long-term outcomes, these findings underscore the need for vigilant cancer surveillance, smoking cessation, and individualized post-transplant care in this vulnerable population.

The association between age at diagnosis and health-related quality of life in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) can occur throughout the lifespan and impacts health-related quality of life (HRQoL). This study examined the relationship between age at diagnosis of AAV and HRQoL.

Methods: The sources were two longitudinal cohorts of adults with AAV: the Vasculitis Patient-Powered Research Network (VPPRN, online patient-reported data) and the Vasculitis Clinical Research Consortium (VCRC, at expert centres). Cohorts were stratified by age at diagnosis (years): <18, 18-40, 41-65, and >65. Descriptive statistics were summarized. Multivariable linear regressions assessed associations between age at diagnosis and Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) scores (VPPRN) and 36-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36) scores (VCRC). Both models adjusted for gender, glucocorticoid use, and age at HRQoL assessment; VCRC model also adjusted for non-disease-specific damage.

Results: Analysis included 1867 (VPPRN) and 653 (VCRC) patients with AAV. Use of glucocorticoids and damage impacted HRQoL in both cohorts. HRQoL as per all PROMIS domains were reduced across all patient age sub-cohorts. When adjusted, the PROMIS scores for those diagnosed at younger ages were better for fatigue, sleep disturbance, depression, pain interference, and satisfaction with participation in social roles; the same for physical functioning; and worse for anxiety, compared to those diagnosed at older ages. In the adjusted model there were no significant differences in HRQoL based on age at diagnosis for any of the SF36 domains.

Conclusions: Patients with AAV have impaired HRQoL, the degree of which in some domains is associated with age at diagnosis. These differences vary based on database design and cohort composition. Understanding the mechanisms by which age at diagnosis impacts HRQoL will be useful for developing targeted interventions for people of all ages with AAV.

O-84

Frailty and mortality among patients with giant cell arteritis and polymyalgia rheumatica

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Background/Aims: The objective of this study was to describe the risk of mortality-stratified by frailty among patients with giant cell arteritis (GCA), polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR), and matched controls.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective inception cohort using the US-based TriNetX electronic health records network. Adults with new-onset PMR or GCA were included if age ≥ 50 years and: 1) ≥ 2 ICD-9/10-CM codes, 2) ≥ 1 year of prior follow-up (baseline), and 3) one prednisone prescription within 30 days of first code (index date). Matched general population control cohorts for PMR and GCA were constructed using 1:3 nearest-neighbour matching on the following variables: sex, race/ethnicity, regional location, birth year, year of cohort entry, and year of cohort exit. Frailty was measured using a validated claims-based frailty index during the baseline. Multivariable Cox proportional cause-specific hazard ratios (aHR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to assess the risk of mortality.

Results: Of 60,039 included patients, 17,955 had PMR, 4,963 had GCA, and 37,121 were matched controls. Compared to matched general population controls, the risk of death was elevated among patients with GCA but not PMR. In the overall cohort, the risk of death was increased in pre-frail and frail patients as compared to non-frail patients. In the stratified analysis, as compared to non-frail general population controls, the risk of death was elevated for non-frail (aHR 1.52, 95% CI 1.20-1.92) and frail patients with GCA (aHR 2.91, 95% CI 1.82-4.66). In a stratified analysis, compared to non-frail general population controls, the risk of death was elevated in frail patients with PMR (aHR 1.86, 95% CI 1.17-2.96) but not in non-frail patients with PMR (aHR 0.96, 95% CI 0.79-1.15).

Conclusions: Frailty in patients with GCA and PMR identifies a group of patients at risk for mortality and highlights the value of frailty assessment.

O-85

Outcome of adult IgA vasculitis in a tertiary care centre

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Background/Aims: IgA Vasculitis(IgAV) is considerably rarer in adults. There is only limited worldwide data on adult IgAV. This study aims to describe clinical profile and outcomes of IgAV patients over last 2 decades.

Methods: Data regarding clinical presentation and outcomes of patients aged > 16 years who fulfilled EULAR/PRES/PRINTO classification criteria, with histopathologic evidence (skin/renal biopsy-proven), were recorded from electronic medical records.

Results: Altogether, 72 biopsy-proven IgAV patients were followed for a median duration of 48 months. 81% had symptom onset during winter months (September-February). At baseline, 100% (72), 63.88% (46), 58.33% (42), and 55.55% (40) had skin, renal, joint, and GIT involvement, respectively. Severe GIT involvement was present in 12.5% (9). Initially, 41 (56.94%) patients received systemic glucocorticoids alone, and 31 (43.05%) patients received an additional immunomodulator with glucocorticoids. During follow-up, 45 (63.38%) patients attained complete remission (CR) at 6 months, and 22 (30.98%) had attained CR on subsequent follow-up. Among patients who attained CR (67), 32 (47.76%) patients relapsed. The most common relapse was renal (25/32). Out of 46 patients with renal involvement, 20 (43.47%) had persistent abnormal urinalysis (PAU), and a substantial decline (20%) in eGFR was recorded in 10.86%. A multivariate analysis showed generalised purpura ($p < 0.001$) as an independent predictor of renal involvement. Factors associated with PAU in multivariate analysis were absence of baseline immunomodulation ($p = 0.025$) and fibrinoid necrosis ($p = 0.042$). Male sex was an independent predictor of relapse (HR=5.778, $p = 0.013$). Relapse-free survival in patients who received systemic glucocorticoids alone [median estimate for relapse is 49.616 months (CI- 34.963, 64.269)] was comparable with systemic glucocorticoids with additional immunosuppressant [median estimate for relapse is 67.610 months (CI- 40.133, 95.087) ($p = 0.895$)]. From 46 patients with renal involvement, 5 developed chronic kidney disease (CKD). Fibrinoid necrosis was an independent predictor for the development of CKD ($p = 0.029$ and HR=10.125).

Conclusions: In our cohort, 81% had symptom onset during winter months, and 63.88% had renal involvement at onset. Relapses were observed in 47.76% of patients. Factors associated with failure to achieve 6-month CR were absence of baseline additional immunosuppression ($p = 0.025$) and fibrinoid necrosis ($p = 0.042$). Relapse-free survival in patients who received systemic glucocorticoids alone was comparable with systemic glucocorticoids with additional immunosuppressant ($p = 0.895$).

O-86

Pregnancy outcomes following use of rituximab and B cell depletion during pregnancy

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Background/Aims: There is limited data on the impact of rituximab and gestational B cell depletion on the pregnancy outcomes of women who received rituximab for autoimmune diseases.

Methods: This is an extended retrospective analysis of women who received rituximab for autoimmune disease and were depleted of B cells during their pregnancy. We examined pregnancy outcomes and maternal complications.

Results: We identified 36 pregnancies, including 2 twins, with a median maternal age of 32. 14 patients were diagnosed with granulomatosis with polyangiitis, 4 with lupus nephritis, 1 with polyarteritis nodosa, 1 with membranous nephropathy, 1 with systemic lupus erythematosus, and 1 with immune complex glomerulonephritis. Last rituximab was a median of 2.6 (IQR 0.95-5.95) months before the estimated date of conception (EDC). 16% (6/36) received rituximab after the EDC. The median creatinine at the EDC was 0.78 (0.65-0.96). Of the 31 pregnancies with B-cell data, 10 had B-cell recovery (>5 B cells/mm³) during pregnancy, while 21 patients delivered while still depleted of B cells. 61% (22/36) were on a maintenance of azathioprine, low-dose prednisone, or a combination during pregnancy. 86% (31/36) resulted in viable pregnancies, 1 resulted in foetal demise, and 4 (11%) were first-trimester miscarriages. 32% (10/31) of the pregnancies resulted in pre-term deliveries (less than 37 weeks) with low birth weights (<2500 grams). 42% (15/36) of pregnancies involved maternal complications, 47% (7/15) resulted in c-sections. 2 patients had pyelonephritis, 7 had prepartum hypertension, 3 had postpartum hypertension, 5 had preeclampsia, and 3 had gestational diabetes. 2 patients had a disease flare during pregnancy, 1 had bronchus and subglottic stenosis flares during all 3 pregnancies which lead to bronchitis during the last pregnancy and 1 had a flare of scleritis during both pregnancies.

Conclusions: The pregnancy outcomes of women who have depleted B-cells during pregnancy due to rituximab treatment are generally favourable.

O-87

Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) and long-term risk of cardiovascular disease: large-scale propensity-matched global retrospective cohort study

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Background/Aims: Despite progress in the treatment of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in recent years, long-term morbidity and mortality rates attributable to active vasculitis and infections remain high. Cohort analyses suggest an increased risk of cardiac comorbidity in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA). The objective of the present study was to analyse mortality and cardiovascular outcomes in patients with EGPA using a comprehensive clinical database.

Methods: In this retrospective cohort study, data from electronic health records of the US-based TriNetX network database were analysed. Patients over the age of 18 with the diagnostic code of EGPA and patients without vasculitis as matched controls were included (1:1). Propensity score matching was performed for demographic variables and comorbidity to optimize between-group comparability. Hazard ratios (HR) related to mortality and cardiovascular outcomes (cerebrovascular disease, myocardial infarction, peripheral arterial disease, chronic ischemic heart disease, heart failure, cardiac arrest, ischemic stroke, haemorrhagic stroke, arterial embolism and thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, venous disease, carditis) were calculated by univariate Cox regression after analysis of the matched cohort using the Kaplan-Meier method. The Log-Rank Test was used to determine P values.

Results: A total of 2.651 patients with EGPA were identified (mean age 55.2±16.1years, 57.1%female). The unadjusted and adjusted relative risk (RR) of mortality was increased (RR6.60%) in comparison to matched controls (HR: 1.55, P<0.001). The risk of arterial embolism and thrombosis (HR: 2.76; P=0.003) and pulmonary embolism (HR: 2.49; P<0.001) was increased. Moreover, cardiac-associated morbidity was increased in EGPA: chronic ischemic heart disease [HR: 1.46; P<0.001], heart failure [HR: 2.11; P=0.016], cardiac arrest [HR: 2.20; P=0.004], carditis [HR: 3.02; P<0.001], cerebrovascular disease (HR: 1.33, P= 0.016), and ischemic stroke (HR: 1.74; P<0.0001).

Conclusions: The overall risk for death and cardiovascular events was increased in patients with EGPA, highlighting the need for targeted monitoring of organ-specific comorbidities.

Kidney transplantation in childhood-onset ANCA-associated vasculitis: long-term outcomes and prognostic factors in a global cohort

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Background: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is rare among children and results in kidney failure in up to 30% of cases. There is limited knowledge about kidney transplantation in this population. We assessed outcomes of kidney transplantation in patients with childhood-onset AAV.

Methods: Patients diagnosed with AAV during childhood (≤ 18 years) who had received kidney transplantation were included in a multicentre retrospective cohort. We determined rates of kidney failure, chronic graft dysfunction (eGFR permanently < 60 mL/min/1.73 m²) and relapse, and assessed prognostic factors. Patients were matched 1:2 for age, sex and era of transplant with non-AAV transplant recipients followed at SickKids Hospital (Toronto, Canada) and their outcomes compared.

Results: We included 72 patients, of whom 53 (74%) had microscopic polyangiitis and 19 (26%) granulomatosis with polyangiitis. The median age at diagnosis and transplantation was 12 and 14 years, respectively, and 52 (72%) were female. After a median of 53 months, 70 (97%) were alive, 62 (86%) had a functioning graft, and 44 (61%) had an eGFR ≥ 60 ml/min/1.73 m². Patient and kidney survival was comparable to that of non-AAV recipients, while time to chronic graft dysfunction was significantly better among AAV patients ($p=0.02$). AAV relapse occurred in 8 patients (11%) a median of 71 months after transplantation. All but one patient recovered and maintained a functioning graft. Acute rejection was the only independent predictor of graft failure (HR 12.11, 95% CI 1.19-122.49). ANCA-positivity at the time of transplantation was associated with chronic graft dysfunction (HR 4.16, 95% CI 1.71-10.13) and AAV relapse (HR 23.1, 95% CI 2.67-200.28).

Conclusions: Kidney transplantation in patients with childhood-onset AAV shows prognosis comparable to the general transplant population and low rates of AAV relapse. Positive ANCA at the time of transplantation may portend a poorer graft outcome and a higher risk of relapse.

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P-001

Incidence of anti-neutrophil antibody-associated vasculitis in a Portuguese urban population

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Background/Aims: There are important geographical variations in the epidemiology of Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). However, epidemiological data from Portugal are lacking. This study aimed to estimate the incidence of AAV in an urban multi-ethnic Portuguese population.

Methods: We identified incident cases of AAV diagnosed between January 2014 and December 2024 in residents of Amadora-Sintra, two municipalities in the Lisbon metropolitan area. Case ascertainment used multiple sources: hospital databases from Internal Medicine, Nephrology, and Pulmonology departments; ANCA-positive cases from the Clinical Pathology Laboratory; and the National Health Codification System database. Cases were classified as microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), or eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA), according to the 2012 Chapel Hill Consensus nomenclature, and further categorized by ANCA serotype: myeloperoxidase (MPO-ANCA), proteinase 3 (PR3-ANCA), or ANCA-negative. Population denominators were obtained based on data from the 2021 census. Incidence rates and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated assuming a Poisson distribution.

Results: Overall, 68 patients with AAV were identified, 34 (50.0%) with MPA, 21 (30.9%) with GPA and 13 (19.1%) with EGPA. Regarding ANCA-serotype, 46 (67.6%) patients were ANCA-MPO, 15 (22.1%) were ANCA-PR3 and 7 (10.3%) were ANCA-negative, of which 5 had EGPA. Median age of this population at diagnosis was 67 (58-74) years, 35 (51.5%) were male patients. The estimated incidence of AAV was 13.0 per million person-years (95%CI 11.0-15.3). The incidence of MPA, GPA and EGPA were 6.5 (95%CI 5.0-8.1), 4.0 (95%CI 2.9-5.4) and 2.5 (95%CI 1.6-3.6) cases per million person-years, respectively. The annual incidence of MPO-AAV was significantly higher than that of PR3-AAV (incidence rate ratio 3.1; 95% CI, 1.8–5.3).

Conclusions: In line with other Southern European epidemiologic studies, MPO-AAV had higher incidence compared to PR3-AAV in our population. To our knowledge, this is the first epidemiological study of AAV conducted in Portugal.

P-002

Ten-Year experience with ANCA-Associated Vasculitis in the United Arab Emirates: findings from the Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi Registry

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Background/Aims: Data on ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in the Middle East, particularly in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), remain limited. To address this gap, we established the first AAV registry at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi to characterize demographic, clinical, laboratory, and outcome profiles of patients over a 10-year period.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective cohort study of patients diagnosed with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), eosinophilic GPA (EGPA), and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) between April 2015 and April 2025. Demographics, comorbidities, clinical manifestations, laboratory parameters, immunological profiles, treatment patterns, and outcomes were collected. Comparative analyses were performed using Chi-square and one-way ANOVA tests.

Results: A total of 64 patients were included (GPA: n=42; EGPA: n=17; MPA: n=4). The mean age at diagnosis was 39.2±17.8 years, and 57.8% were female. UAE nationals accounted for 65.6%. Common features included shortness of breath (70.3%), cough (67.2%), ENT involvement (67.2%), and fatigue (68.8%). Subtype differences were significant for pulmonary symptoms, chest pain, ENT involvement, rash, and mononeuritis multiplex (p<0.05). Laboratory findings showed marked eosinophilia in EGPA (p=0.0004), higher protein-creatinine ratios in GPA (p=0.0037), and ESR variation across groups (p=0.0013). Immunological patterns were distinct: PR3-ANCA predominated in GPA (66.7%), MPO-ANCA in EGPA (50%) and MPA (100%), while dual positivity was rare.

Treatment included corticosteroids (93.8%), rituximab (59.4%), azathioprine (51.6%), cyclophosphamide (29.7%), and mepolizumab (66.7% in EGPA, p<0.001). Plasmapheresis was used in 14%. Outcomes included end-stage renal disease requiring dialysis (12.5%) and mortality (4.7%). Asthma was highly prevalent in EGPA (94.4%), with montelukast exposure noted in 38.9%.

Conclusions: This first UAE-based AAV registry highlights distinct demographic and clinical patterns across GPA, EGPA, and MPA. Findings demonstrate a high burden of pulmonary and renal involvement, subtype-specific immunological signatures, and evolving treatment practices, particularly with biologics. These data support earlier recognition, personalized management, and improved outcomes in the region.

P-003

Increase in granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis incidence in Poland during the COVID-19 pandemic

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), and eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) are rare autoimmune diseases. Reported incidence varies by study design, period, geography, and population. This study aimed to update annual incidence rates of GPA, MPA, and EGPA in Poland and analyse trends during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: The study included newly diagnosed AAV cases between January 1, 2018, and December 31, 2023, in paediatric and adult populations across Poland. Incidence was assessed based on first hospitalizations coded with ORPHAcodes for EGPA, GPA, or MPA. Due to local reporting practices, GPA and MPA were analysed jointly. Diagnoses were made by clinicians, and all nationwide hospitalizations were included.

Results: A total of 2,474 new AAV cases were identified, forming the largest vasculitis cohort analysed in Poland. Median age at diagnosis was 50–54 years for EGPA and 55–59 years for GPA/MPA, with a slight female predominance.

The average annual incidence of EGPA per million population was as follows: 2018: 2.11 (95% CI: 1.67–2.62), 2019: 1.77 (95% CI: 1.38–2.25), 2020: 1.18 (95% CI: 0.86–1.58), 2021: 1.74 (95% CI: 1.35–2.22), 2022: 2.33 (95% CI: 1.87–2.87), 2023: 2.18 (95% CI: 1.73–2.70). No statistically significant differences were observed across the years.

The average annual cumulative incidence of GPA and MPA per million population was: 2018: 8.15 (95% CI: 7.27–9.10), 2019: 9.07 (95% CI: 8.14–10.07), 2020: 6.69 (95% CI: 5.90–7.57), 2021: 8.63 (95% CI: 7.72–9.61), 2022: 10.09 (95% CI: 9.10–11.15), 2023: 11.16 (95% CI: 10.12–12.28).

Conclusions: EGPA incidence remained stable, while GPA/MPA showed a marked rise following a temporary decline in 2020, likely linked to reduced access to systemic disease diagnostics during the pandemic. The consistent seasonal peak in winter, together with the post-pandemic upward trend, suggests possible environmental or infectious triggers.

P-004

Estimating the burden of severe granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis in Australia using hospital administrative data

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Background/Aims: Previous estimates of hospital care for GPA and MPA are limited to single hospitals or health districts. No population-level study has been conducted in Australia to date. This study aimed to estimate the number of patients who received admitted care for granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) in the Queensland public health service between calendar years 2014–2024 to inform estimates of the total burden of AAV in Australia.

Methods: This retrospective observational study utilised the Queensland Health Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC) which collects data on admissions to public hospitals in the state of Queensland, Australia. Episodes of care were identified for patients with International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, Australian Modification (ICD-10-AM) codes M31.3 (GPA) and M31.7 (MPA) as either a principal diagnosis or additional diagnosis. Patient records were linked through the Queensland Health Master Linkage File (MLF), enabling the identification of unique individuals and reducing the risk of double counting. Distinct patients were enumerated annually and aggregated over five-year periods to further minimise duplication across calendar years. Population estimates for Queensland during the study period were obtained from the Australian Bureau of Statistics.

Results: The number of distinct patients admitted annually in Queensland increased from 157 (2015) to 234 (2024). Distinct patients with GPA and MPA increased from 577 (2015 – 2019) to 683 (2020–2024). This translates to 3.43% compounding annual growth rate (CAGR) in distinct patients receiving care. This is higher than population CAGR of Queensland (1.58%) over the same timeframe.

Conclusions: Over the 10-year period, the number of patients requiring hospital care for GPA and MPA in Queensland have increased more than population growth. This suggests that other factors including better care and improved diagnosis may contribute to the increasing prevalence and burden of GPA and MPA on the healthcare system.

P-005

Investigation of temporal clustering of ANCA-associated vasculitis using multiple changepoint Poisson process models

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Background/Aims: In clinical practice, there is a perception of short periods of high ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) incidence, followed by longer periods with little to no cases, suggesting that AAV diagnoses are clustered in time and therefore probably associated with a defined environmental trigger. Building on a prior pilot study, we now use data from Ireland, Sweden, Denmark, United Kingdom, Czechia and Spain to model AAV diagnosis events from each registry using multiple changepoint Poisson process models.

Methods: We first analysed data from the RITA-Ireland registry and validated results in four additional AAV inception cohort registries from diverse regions across Europe. We then analysed population level datasets from the Sweden and Danish registries, both of which have full case ascertainment. Only prospectively recruited cases were included. Poisson process changepoint models were applied to data from each registry separately to assess whether the interval between diagnosis events deviated from that expected from a random time series. The empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) of the interval between each date of diagnosis for each cohort was compared to simulated data.

Results: 2,015 cases were available for inclusion. Simulated data almost exactly matched the observed ECDF in each of the seven sites. No significant difference in incident diagnosis patterns was found for any cohort. Standardised residuals did not exhibit any consistent pattern across registries. Similar results were observed when patients with GPA and MPA were analysed separately.

Conclusions: Contrary to our hypothesis, and the perception in clinical practice that there may be “runs” of AAV diagnoses, we failed to identify short-term, high-intensity clusters of diagnosis events in a diverse set of geographically dispersed cohorts. The observed occurrence of AAV diagnoses over time closely corresponded to the expected behaviour of a random temporal diagnosis distribution.

P-006

Familial associations between ANCA-associated vasculitis and other autoimmune diseases

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is likely to result from interactions between genetic and environmental factors. Genetic polymorphisms associated with AAV often involve loci impacting common immune pathways, however the prevalence of autoimmune/inflammatory diseases in relatives of AAV patients is unclear. This study assesses the relationship between AAV and autoimmune/inflammatory diseases in first-degree relatives.

Methods: Patients with AAV (cases) from a tertiary hospital were age- and sex-matched one-to-one with control patients that had non-immune kidney disease and not any autoimmune/inflammatory diseases in a case control study. Participants were asked whether their first-degree relatives had autoimmune/inflammatory diseases. The likelihood of a positive family history was compared between cases and controls using conditional logistic regression. The risk of first-degree relatives of cases having autoimmune/inflammatory diseases was explored using generalised estimating equations.

Results: There were 145 AAV cases matched with 145 controls. A family history of autoimmune/inflammatory diseases was reported by 46.2% of those with AAV and 16.6% of controls. After adjustment for participant age and number of known family members, AAV cases were seven-times more likely to have a positive family history compared to controls (OR 7.25, 95% C.I. 3.27, 16.09). After adjustment for other factors, first-degree relatives of AAV participants were four-times more likely to have an autoimmune/inflammatory disease compared to a relative of a control (OR 4.03, 95% C.I. 2.46, 6.62). The most common types of autoimmune/inflammatory disease in first-degree relatives of cases and controls were musculoskeletal/connective tissue (4.2% vs. 0.8% respectively) and endocrine (3.9% vs. 1.0%).

Conclusions: A history of autoimmune/inflammatory disease in first-degree family members is associated with an increased chance of a person developing AAV. Conversely, the presence of AAV in a first-degree relative is associated with having an increased chance of having an autoimmune/inflammatory disease. This implies a shared familial susceptibility between AAV and these diseases.

P-007

Changing epidemiology of anti-glomerular basement membrane disease

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Background/Aims: Anti-GBM disease is rare. Dual anti-GBM and ANCA-positivity is observed in about a third of cases; 70-80% historically were MPO-ANCA. With increasing availability of highly sensitive serological assays, more low-titre or false-positive anti-GBM antibody results are being reported.

Methods: Case series assessing all new first positive anti-GBM results (January 2017 and July 2025) identified from a central immunology database and measured using the EliA fluoroenzyme immunoassay (Phadia 2500/5000) with recombinant human α 3(IV) collagen; clinical and laboratory data were obtained from electronic health records.

Results: 159 patients had at least one positive anti-GBM antibody titre; 72 (45.3%) had confirmed anti-GBM disease (54% (n=39) confirmed on biopsy and the remainder had a consistent clinical phenotype and were treated); 72 (45.3%) did not have confirmed disease. 15 (9.4%) were excluded due to insufficient data. In seropositive patients without anti-GBM disease (n=72), false positives were linked to recent aortovascular/valvular pathology or intervention (n=20), bland urinary sediment with preserved renal function (n=15), \geq 4 additional autoantibodies (n=30), and alternative biopsy findings (n=21).

Of 72 patients with anti-GBM disease, 49% (n=35) were female, median age 64 years and 32% (n=23) were ANCA-positive; 18% (n=13) PR3-ANCA and 14% (n=10) MPO-ANCA. More than half of PR3-positive cases were diagnosed from 2024 onwards (54%, n=7). Between 2017-2023, 49 cases were diagnosed (median 7 annually, range 5–9). However, in 2024, 10 cases were observed and in the first 7 months of 2025, 13 cases have already been identified. Median serum creatinine at presentation was 700 μ mol/litre (range 35-3494 μ mol/litre). Pulmonary haemorrhage occurred in 26% (n=19). A smoking history was documented in 53% (n=38).

Conclusions: False-positive anti-GBM antibody results, due to non-specific multiple auto-antibody binding, are increasingly recognised, highlighting the need to interpret serology within clinical context. Our findings may indicate rising incidence of anti-GBM disease and a greater proportion associated with PR3-ANCA.

P-008

Dual positive anti-neutrophil cytoplasm and anti-glomerular basement membrane antibody positive vasculitis: a proposed classification and case series

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Background/Aims: Anti-glomerular basement membrane (aGBM) disease and anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitides (AAV) are rare diseases. Up to 40% of patients with clinical diagnosis of aGBM disease have positive ANCA, and 5% of patients with clinical diagnosis of AAV have detectable aGBM antibodies. As relapse risk varies between AAV and aGBM disease, we hypothesised that this outcome would also vary in double positive disease according to the dominant manifestation. We report a case series of aGBM+AAV and AAV+aGBM, with the following proposed

Methods: Classification: 1. aGBM+AAV: aGBM disease with linear IgG staining on kidney biopsy and no clinical features of vasculitis outside lung or kidney, with co-existent serum ANCA positivity. 2. AAV+aGBM: clinical AAV with aGBM antibody (pauci-immune kidney biopsy).

Dual positive patients with kidney biopsies were identified from Imperial College London and RITA-Ireland Vasculitis registries. Clinical, biochemical and histopathological features at presentation, renal replacement therapy (RRT) requirement, end stage kidney disease (ESKD), renal recovery, treatment, relapse, and death were analysed between the groups.

Results: Of 52 patients included, 37 (71%) had aGBM+AAV and 15 (29%) had AAV+aGBM. Anti-MPO antibody was detected in 75%, and anti-PR3 antibody in 25%. Those with aGBM+AAV were numerically more likely to require RRT on presentation (59.5% vs 33.3%, $p=0.07$) and progress to ESKD (78.6% vs 21.4%, $p=0.2$) than AAV+aGBM. Dialysis-requiring aGBM+AAV patients were more likely to recover renal function (36.4% vs 12.5%, $p=0.37$). Use of maintenance therapy was similar between AAV+aGBM and aGBM+AAV (61.5% vs 79.4% respectively, $p=0.27$), as was relapse rate (20% vs 29.7%, $p=0.7$).

Conclusions: AAV and aGBM disease are rare vasculitides, whose overlap occurs at a higher frequency than expected by chance. This case series highlights differences between AAV+aGBM and aGBM+AAV, but surprisingly no excess relapse propensity in AAV+aGBM. This work informs a proposal for a clinical classification to guide future care pathways.

P-009

Current state of racial, ethnic, sex, and geographical diversity in ANCA-associated vasculitis and giant cell arteritis trials

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Background/Aims: Adequate representation in randomized controlled trials (RCTs) is crucial to ensure generalizability and address healthcare disparities. This systematic review summarizes the current state of representation in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) and giant cell arteritis (GCA).

Methods: A systematic literature review using PubMed, EMBASE, CINAHL Complete, Europe PMC, ClinicalTrials.gov, and the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform was performed (PROSPERO CRD42023457996). Pharmacologic phase 2,3, and 4 RCTs (2010-2023) were included. Two authors independently reviewed the titles, abstracts, and full texts. Data extraction included demographics, year of publication, trial phase, sponsor category, and location of enrolling sites. U.S. enrolment sites were categorized at the county level using Urban-Rural Classification Scheme and into Medically Underserved Areas (MUA).

Results: 32 AAV (3954 participants, mean age 58.6 years) and 9 GCA RCTs (773 participants, mean age 71.7) were included. Less than 35% of trials reported race or ethnicity in their results. Among 14 trials including data on race, median percentage was highest for white (89.2%) followed by Asian (3.7%) and Black (1.4%) participants. Among 10 trials including data on ethnicity, median percentage of Hispanic or Latino participants was 2.0%. Out of 40 trials that reported data on sex, 49.9% were female.

European centres participated in 78.1% of AAV and 88.9% of GCA RCTs; North American centres participated in 34.4% of AAV and 55% of GCA RCTs. No trials were conducted in Africa. Out of a total of 172 U.S. participating sites, 69.8% were located in MUAs and in large metropolitan areas.

Conclusions: Enrolment in AAV and GCA RCTs has been primarily concentrated in Europe, North America, and Australasia. In the U.S., most participating sites are located in large metropolitan areas. The representation of diverse racial and ethnic groups has been limited across these trials, highlighting the need to ensure adequate representation.

P-010

Rare AutoImmune SELF-management (RAISE) programme development: effectiveness of survey recruitment methods in ensuring inclusion of a broad range of people with rare autoimmune rheumatic diseases

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Background/Aims: Rare autoimmune rheumatic diseases (RAIRDs) impact on health-related quality of life. A UK patient survey is underway to determine content of a self-management and psychological support intervention. This study aims to explore effectiveness of recruitment methods.

Methods: Participants recruited via National Health Service (NHS) Rheumatology clinics or social media platforms including patient charities (RAIRDA, Scleroderma & Raynaud's UK, Sjögren's UK, Lupus UK, Vasculitis UK, Myositis UK). Surveys completed online. Data analysed descriptively.

Results: Total 612 participants to date: 122 (20%) recruited via NHS clinics (H), and 490 (80%) via social media (S). Mean (SD) age H=54.58 (13.92), S=59.87 (13.57); majority female (H=84%, S=91%). There was a difference in response for people with SLE (H=23%, S=3%, X²=50, P=<0.001) and GCA (H=2.5%, S=12.7%, X²=9.7, P=0.0018) compared to other RAIRDs. This difference was not seen in: Sjogren's disease (H=27%, S=30%), ANCA-associated vasculitis (17%; 22%), Scleroderma (9%, 10%), inflammatory myositis (2.5%, 4.5%), antiphospholipid syndrome (1.6%, 0.4%), Behcet's disease (3.3%, 5.7%), large vessel vasculitis (1.6%, 2%), polyarteritis nodosa (0.8%, 0.2%), Takayasu arteritis (0.8%, 2%), central nervous system vasculitis (0.8%, 1%).

Responses for people from the global majority ethnic group were lower (H=20.5%, S=5%), than white English/Welsh/Scottish/Irish group (H=79%, S=94%); with lower odds of social media response for global majority participants (OR=0.2, 95% CI 0.72 to 0.56; P=0.002).

Differences were seen in response rates for the following educational and employment categories: no formal education (H=11%, S=3% (X²=9.38, P=0.002) or retired (H=34%, S=47% (X²=6, P=0.01) compared with other levels of education and employed respectively.

Conclusions: The findings suggest differences in how people respond to a patient survey of self-management and support needs, specifically people with SLE, GCA and those from the global majority. Men are under-represented. This supports using multiple recruitment methods to facilitate broader participation in research.

P-011

Cocaine related vasculitis: from local to systemic disease

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Background/Aims: Cocaine use (often levamisole-adulterated) can provoke a broad spectrum of vasculitic phenomena ranging from localized midline destructive lesions to systemic disease. We describe a retrospective series of patients with confirmed ongoing cocaine use and vasculitis

Methods: We reviewed medical records from 2022 to 2025 of patients presenting with vasculitis and documented active cocaine use. We collected data on demographics, clinical manifestations (ENT, respiratory, renal, skin, neurologic), immunologic profile (ANCA by indirect immunofluorescence [IIF], PR3, MPO, human neutrophil elastase [HNE] antibodies) other serologies, hematologic parameters, treatments and outcomes.

Results: Nine patients were identified (6 male; mean age 37.5 ± 6 years). In 7/9, cocaine use was confirmed via urine. Midline destructive ENT involvement (CIMDL) occurred in 6/9; in 3/9 limited to ENT, in the rest accompanied by systemic features: arthritis, alveolar haemorrhage, nephritic syndrome, cutaneous purpura and mononeuritis multiplex. None had neutropenia. Cutaneous involvement in 3/9. Immunology: 8/9 were ANCA-positive. Among these, 6/8 showed exclusively cytoplasmic ANCA (c-ANCA) by IIF; 7/8 positive by PR3 in 6/7, MPO in 1/7. Two patients had concomitant anti-elastase (HNE) reactivity along with PR3, i.e., "double positivity." Four patients also had ANA or antiphospholipid antibodies. Treatment: 6/9 received immunosuppression (corticosteroids \pm other agents). One patient died; four lost to follow-up; in four, lesions stabilized alongside apparent cessation of cocaine use.

Conclusions: Our series corroborates recent literature showing that many features overlap between primary granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and cocaine (or levamisole)-associated vasculitis. Key distinguishing features reported in reviews include: more frequent neutropenia, cutaneous involvement, multiple autoantibody positivity's (ANA, antiphospholipid) and HNE antibodies in drug-associated cases. Although in our cohort c-ANCA/PR3 predominated and anti-elastase reactivity was less frequent, these serologic markers alone could not reliably distinguish GPA from cocaine-induced disease. Clinical presentation (ENT destruction, systemic involvement) also overlapped. Biopsy findings (granulomatous inflammation, necrosis) are often non-specific or incomplete in both settings.

Given the lack of a pathognomonic clinical, serologic, or histologic profile to distinguish GPA from cocaine-induced vasculitis, clinicians should systematically assess for substance use.

P-012

Levamisole-adulterated cocaine-induced vasculitis: expanding the clinical and autoimmune spectrum through the largest global experience

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Background/Aims: Up to 88% of cocaine is tainted with levamisole, anthelmintic withdrawn from the market due to toxicity. Since 2010 Levamisole-Adulterated Cocaine-Induced Vasculitis (LACIV) patients have been reported.

Methods: We describe the clinical, histopathological, and serological manifestations of 87 LACIV cases between December 2010 and August 2025.

Results: Patients were all mestizos, mean age 34.9 years (SD 8.3), male:female ratio 3.6:1 and median time to diagnosis was 12 months. Cutaneous manifestations predominated: retiform purpura (80.4%), ear necrosis (59.7%), and pyoderma gangrenosum (18.4%). Biopsies (n=47) revealed leukocytoclastic vasculitis (46.8%), pyoderma gangrenosum (34%), and thrombotic vasculopathy (31.9%), with mixed patterns in 36.2%.

Renal involvement occurred in 51.7%. Among 32 biopsies, immune complex-mediated extracapillary glomerulonephritis (40.6%) was most frequent, followed by pauci-immune proliferative glomerulonephritis (25%), membranous glomerulonephritis (18.7%), and immune complex-mediated membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (12.5%); Eight patients (17.7%) progressed to end-stage kidney disease. Patients with nephritis were more often male, ANCA-positive, and less likely to present pyoderma gangrenosum ($p < 0.05$). Extra-cutaneous involvement was present in 94%: arthritis/arthralgia (57.4%), fever (21.8%), hepatosplenomegaly (13.7%), lymphadenopathy (11.5%), genital necrosis (10.3%), digital necrosis (6.9%), venous thrombosis (5.7%) and alveolar haemorrhage (4.6%).

Cytopenias were frequent: anaemia (80.4%), lymphopenia (62%), leukopenia (23%), thrombocytopenia (11.5%), and neutropenia (11.4%). ANCA were positive in 93% of cases, with a predominance of p-ANCA (82.8%), anti-MPO (65%), and mixed patterns (30%). Lupus anticoagulant was positive in 72.5%, ANA (64.7%), and hypocomplementemia (51.1%). Treatment included corticosteroids (81%), methylprednisolone (33.3%), and immunosuppressants (51.7%, mainly cyclophosphamide). Most improved, although three patients died.

Conclusions: This study represents the largest series of LACIV reported worldwide, highlighting its wide clinical spectrum, multisystemic compromise, and striking autoimmune profile. LACIV is characterized by severe cutaneous manifestations, high frequency of ANCA positivity, and significant renal involvement. Recognition of its distinct clinical, histopathological, and serological patterns is critical to avoid misdiagnosis with primary systemic vasculitides.

P-013

Antiphospholipid antibody profile in patients with levamisole-adulterated cocaine-induced vasculitis (LACIV): A 15-year experience

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Background/Aims: Up to 88% of cocaine is tainted with levamisole, an antihelminthic drug that was banned due to toxicity. The association with vasculitis (LACIV) has been extensively studied. We describe the positivity rate of antiphospholipid antibodies (aPL) and its association with thrombotic events in a series of LACIV cases between December 2010 and August 2025.

Methods: Retrospective case series.

Results: 87 patients with LACIV were included. Mean age was 34.9 years (SD \pm 8.3). Male:female ratio was 3.5:1; 21% had thrombocytosis and 11% thrombocytopenia. Lupus anticoagulant (LA) was positive in 72.5%, IgM anticardiolipin and anti- β -2 glycoprotein antibodies in 19%, IgG anticardiolipin in 8%. Double positivity was present in 16% and triple positivity in 5%.

Cutaneous manifestations predominated: retiform purpura (80.4%), ear necrosis (59.7%), and pyoderma gangrenosum (18.4%). Skin biopsies (n=47) revealed micro-thrombotic vasculopathy in 31.9%. Patient with the most severe skin involvement presented double-positive aPL profile and thrombotic vasculopathy.

Four cases of deep vein thrombosis (4.6%) were identified; the majority affecting lower limbs (75%), one with upper limb involvement (25%). Two of them were seropositive for LA only (50%), and one of them was seronegative. In one case, concomitant acute superficial venous thrombosis was documented. This patient had a triple-positive aPL profile.

Pulmonary thromboembolism was described in only one case (1.1%), with concomitant intracavitary thrombus and LA positivity. No cases of arterial thrombotic events were identified. No association was found between aPL positivity and macro- or microthrombotic events ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions: In this large series of patients with LACIV, antiphospholipid antibody positivity, particularly LA, was highly prevalent. Despite this, thrombotic events were infrequent and no significant association was found between aPL profile and clinical thrombosis or histological vasculopathy. These findings suggest that aPL in LACIV may represent an epiphenomenon of immune dysregulation rather than a true prothrombotic risk factor.

P-014

Risk of vasculitis associated with hydralazine use: a population-based retrospective cohort study

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Background/Aims: Hydralazine is a selectively used cardiovascular medication with case reports and case series demonstrating a link between the use of hydralazine and ANCA-associated vasculitis. The objective of this study is to assess the risk of vasculitis associated with hydralazine use compared with an angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor or angiotensin receptor blocker (ACE/ARB).

Methods: This population-based, retrospective cohort study was conducted among adults >66 years old (mean age 73.0, SD 7.2) who were newly prescribed hydralazine in Ontario, Canada from 2008 to 2021. Overlap weighted Cox proportional hazards regression was used to examine the association between hydralazine use (active comparator ACE/ARB) with new onset vasculitis. The exposure was newly dispensed hydralazine in an outpatient setting. The main outcome was a diagnosis of vasculitis using ICD-10 codes.

Results: From a total of 583,136 eligible adults (55.2% female, median follow up 5.4 years), 40,748 individuals were dispensed hydralazine and 542,388 an ACE/ARB. Hydralazine use compared to ACE/ARB was associated with a higher risk of vasculitis during follow-up (Hydralazine: 329 events [0.8%]; ACE/ARB 2,712 events [0.5%], absolute risk difference 0.3%; hazard ratio, 1.20; 95% CI, 1.04-1.37). Results were no longer significant when accounting for the competing risk of death.

Conclusion: Despite an established relationship, vasculitis associated with hydralazine is a rare event. Use of hydralazine is unlikely to be associated with a clinically meaningful increased risk of vasculitis.

P-015

Evaluation of methodological variability in ANCA detection between IIF, CLIA and LIA

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) against MPO and PR3 are established biomarkers for ANCA-associated vasculitis. This study compared three diagnostic approaches - indirect immunofluorescence (IIF), chemiluminescence immunoassay (CLIA), and line immunoassay (LIA) - for ANCA detection.

Methods: A total of 94 samples were analysed by IIF (Inova Diagnostics, Werfen) and CLIA (Quanta Flash MPO/PR3, Inova Diagnostics, Werfen). In addition, MPO and PR3-ANCA were determined using LIA (ANCA-3 Blot, TestLine). The concordance between the assays was determined by calculating the percentage of positive and negative samples and Cohen's kappa coefficient.

Results: The agreement between CLIA and LIA was fair for both MPO ($\kappa = 0.238$) and PR3 ($\kappa = 0.267$). The agreement between IIF pANCA and CLIA MPO was slight ($\kappa = 0.191$), while the agreement with LIA MPO was fair ($\kappa = 0.392$). For IIF cANCA, agreement with CLIA PR3 was very low ($\kappa = 0.098$), but substantial with LIA PR3 ($\kappa = 0.665$).

In a subset of IIF ANCA-negative samples ($n=52$), MPO- and PR3-specific reactivity was observed significantly less frequently with LIA than with CLIA: only 1 MPO- (1.9%) and 1 PR3-positive sample (1.9%) (and no double-positives) were detected with LIA, compared with 20 MPO- (38.4%), 19 PR3- (36.5%), and 7 double-positive samples (13.5%) identified with CLIA.

Conclusions: The agreement between the IIF patterns (pANCA, cANCA) and the antigen-specific assays (CLIA, LIA) was limited, partly due to incomplete agreement with MPO and PR3. The lower agreement between CLIA and LIA likely reflects methodological differences. MPO/PR3 positivity was more common with CLIA, even in IIF-negative samples, indicating assay-dependent variability and possible false-positive results. While CLIA provides high sensitivity, it may reduce specificity. Therefore, a practical algorithm is recommended: in cases of MPO/PR3-ANCA positivity by CLIA but negative IIF, an LIA reflex test should be performed to rule out false-positive results.

P-016

Less is more - experience of ANCA algorithm change in a tertiary hospital laboratory

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Background/Aims: ANCA antibody testing forms an important part of ANCA vasculitis diagnosis. ANCA testing algorithms vary between laboratories and with international guidelines. ANCA testing requests at ICPMR, a tertiary referral laboratory, prior to 20 January 2025, involved indirect immunofluorescence (Euroimmun IIFT Granulocyte Mosaic 13) in combination with PR3 and MPO testing (Werfern Bio-Flash). A request for PR3 and/or MPO resulted in testing to PR3 and/or MPO only. However, with increasing medical expenditure, a more efficient and cost saving ANCA algorithm was implemented, with a request for ANCA having only ANCA-IIF performed (PR3 and MPO only tested if ANCA fluorescence positive), unless PR3 and/or MPO specifically requested.

Methods: A retrospective study was performed from the period 20th July 2024 to 20th July 2025 comparing pre and post algorithm change (ANCA ordering, ANCA result, Medicare costing and other relevant clinical information).

Results: In the 6 months prior to the algorithm change, there were 4205 ANCA, 217 MPO and 161 PR3 requests. The ANCA immunofluorescence pattern was positive for c-ANCA (n=118), p-ANCA (n=96), non-specific ANCA (n=440), and negative in 3551 samples. In total, 4422 samples were tested for MPO, with 272 positive samples (6.2%), and 4366 samples were tested for PR3 with 150 positive samples (3.4%).

In the 6 months after the algorithm change, there were 4596 ANCA, 1372 MPO and 1320 PR3 requests. The ANCA-IIF pattern was positive for c-ANCA (n=175), p-ANCA (n=137), non-specific ANCA (n=639), and negative in 3645 samples. In total, 1372 samples were tested for MPO, with 200 positive samples (14.6%), and 1320 samples were test for PR3 with 129 positive samples (9.8%).

Based on the Medicare item costing, it was estimated the algorithm change has led to ~30% in saving.

Conclusions: ANCA algorithm change had led to reduction in unnecessary testing with associated saving. The number of PR3 and MPO detected remained similar post the algorithm change.

P-017

Diagnostic performance of myeloperoxidase and proteinase-3 antibodies by ImmunoCAP fluorescent enzyme immunoassay

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody (ANCA) associated vasculitides (AAV) are traditionally diagnosed by positive ANCA on indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) slides, followed by confirmatory specific immunoassay for myeloperoxidase (MPO) or proteinase-3 (PR3) antibodies. These immunoassays are reportedly highly sensitive and specific for AAV diagnosis, however this may vary depending on platform used. Due to locally observed cases of false positive results, we sought to assess the performance characteristics of the ImmunoCAP fluorescent enzyme immunoassay (FEIA) for detection of MPO/PR3 antibodies.

Methods: All positive MPO/PR3 antibody results over a 5-year period were collated at Central Sydney Immunopathology Laboratory. We analysed electronic medical records to identify the associated diagnosis for all cases, including those known to contribute to MPO/PR3 positivity such as inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), cocaine use, and antithyroid medications. Potential confounding laboratory results which may contribute to false positive results (e.g. paraprotein, rheumatoid factor, anti-cardiolipin IgG) were also collected.

Results: Only 84 of 222(37.8%) patients with a positive MPO or PR3 autoantibody had a diagnosis of AAV. Of the 138 cases without a diagnosis of AAV, 72(52.2%) had IBD. All IBD cases had positive PR3 antibodies, but were noted to have lower levels (mean = 8.8U/mL) than those associated with AAV (mean = 30.0;p-value<0.05). Only 11 PR3-positive IBD patients had a corresponding c-ANCA positive pattern. We found 20%(n=66) of cases had neither AAV or IBD, of which 29 had a laboratory abnormality that may contribute to laboratory interference and false positivity.

Conclusions: We found a high rate of false positive results for MPO/PR3 antibodies via the ImmunoCAP FEIA in the real-world laboratory setting. Our results support the importance of correlating these results with IIF, clinical findings, and biopsy diagnosis, and emphasise the need for clinician education to ensure ANCA testing is performed only where there is a high pre-test probability of AAV.

P-018

Differential diagnosis of ANCA vasculitis subtypes with Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy of serum

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis is defined by antibodies against proteinase 3 (PR3) or myeloperoxidase (MPO). These subtypes differ in prognosis and may require tailored therapy. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy can distinguish active disease from healthy controls [1], [2]. We investigated whether FTIR spectroscopy with machine learning (ML) can classify patients by ANCA specificity.

Methods: Serum FTIR spectra were obtained from 19 anti-PR3-positive patients, 19 anti-MPO-positive patients (RITA Ireland biobank, TCD), and 12 healthy controls. Spectra were acquired in attenuated-total reflection mode on an Agilent Cary 620 spectrometer with the DxCover slide system. Support vector machine (SVM) models were trained following dimensionality reduction with principal components analysis or uniform manifold approximation and projection.

Results: UMAP-SVM models discriminated anti-MPO from anti-PR3 spectra with F1-score ~ 0.79 (range 0.66 to 0.82). Vasculitis spectra were distinguished from controls with diagnostic accuracy up to $F1 \sim 0.94$.

Conclusions: In this proof of concept study, coupling vibrational spectroscopy with ML provides a novel approach for classifying patients with ANCA vasculitis. Further work is underway to scale this up to addressing the question of estimating relapse propensity.

P-019

Audit of severe asthma patients on biological therapy in the Macarthur region, Australia: unmasking a higher prevalence of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA)

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Introduction/Aims: Severe asthma is heterogeneous, and patients uncontrolled on maximal therapy may have underlying Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA), a systemic necrotizing vasculitis. Biological therapies have revolutionized severe asthma management but highlighted the need for accurate diagnosis. This audit assessed EGPA prevalence in severe asthma patients receiving biological therapy in the Macarthur region, NSW, Australia.

Methods: A retrospective audit was performed on severe asthma patients receiving biological therapy within the Macarthur healthcare catchment. Patient records were systematically reviewed and assessed against four established diagnostic and classification criteria for EGPA: the Lanham diagnostic criteria [1], the 1990 American College of Rheumatology (ACR) classification criteria [2], the 2022 ACR/European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (EULAR) classification criteria [3], and the MIRRA/MANDARA inclusion criteria [4]. This multi-criteria approach ensured comprehensive diagnostic evaluation.

Results: At least 30 patients in the Macarthur catchment met EGPA classification criteria across the applied frameworks. Given the Macarthur region's population of approximately 330,000 people, this represents a prevalence of 91 cases per million population. This finding is substantially higher than reported global estimates ranging from 15.3 to 35 cases per million people [1,5], representing approximately 2.6-fold higher than the upper range of global estimates and 6-fold higher than lower estimates.

Conclusions: EGPA prevalence in the Macarthur region among severe asthma patients on biological therapy is significantly higher than anticipated. This underscores the importance of maintaining high clinical suspicion for EGPA in patients with severe, difficult-to-treat asthma, particularly those with eosinophilia, before they reach the fulminant vasculitis phase. Therapies that dampen T2 inflammation may prevent progression to fulminant EGPA. Important limitations include that classification criteria may overestimate diagnosis, and consensus diagnostic criteria for clinical practice are urgently needed. These findings suggest EGPA may be substantially under-diagnosed in the general population, warranting focused screening in high-risk populations and prospective validation studies.

P-020

Identification of clinical phenotypes and the significance of rheumatoid factor positivity in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: To identify clinical phenotypes in patients with EGPA and to evaluate the significance of rheumatoid factor (RF) positivity.

Methods: Patients classified as EGPA according to the EMA algorithm between 2003 and 2024 in two centres, with at least 6 months of follow-up, were retrospectively reviewed. Clustering analysis was performed using hierarchical clustering analysis, followed by two-step clustering. Factors associated with RF positivity (>3 ULN) were assessed by logistic regression.

Results: Thirty-six patients (M/F: 26/10, mean age at diagnosis 44.6 ± 16 years, median follow-up: 39[125] months, MPO-ANCA positivity 19[52.8%], RF positivity 14[35%]) were included. No association was found between MPO-ANCA and baseline findings.

In the four-variable analysis (Mononeuritis multiplex [MNM], cardiomyopathy, purpura, RF positivity), three subgroups were identified (silhouette score ≈ 0.51). Cluster-1 (n=19) was characterized by MNM, purpura, arthritis/arthralgia and defined as the vasculitic/inflammatory subgroup. Cluster-2 (n=6) included patients with cardiomyopathy in all cases and had the lowest ANCA positivity rate (16.7%). Cluster-3 (n=11) included patients without MNM and cardiomyopathy, with no relapses during follow-up and showed the highest ANCA positivity (72.7%) but no RF positivity. Cluster-1 showed significantly higher eosinophil levels at month 6 ($p=0.03$), with higher relapse rates in Cluster-1 and -2 compared to Cluster-3 ($p=0.02$).

RF positivity was associated with MNM (OR=6.7[[1.5–29.6]) and arthritis/arthralgia (OR=6.1[1.4–29.9]) and a numerically lower rate of pulmonary infiltrates (50% vs. 81.8% $p=0.07$) at diagnosis. During follow-up, RF positive patients had a shorter time to first relapse (32.8 ± 9.5 vs. 122.6 ± 19.0 log-rank $p=0.003$).

Conclusions: In clustering analysis, patients with higher baseline BVAS and RF positivity showed higher eosinophil levels during follow-up and were prone to relapse. In contrast, 40% of patients did not have cardiac, neurological involvement or RF positivity, demonstrated a milder phenotype. These findings suggest that RF positivity reflects increased B-cell activity and high disease activity at baseline may be a predictor of future relapses.

P-021

Pathological differences between adult-onset IgA vasculitis and IgA nephropathy

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis (IgAV) is more common in children, and studies focusing on adult-onset cases are relatively limited. Furthermore, IgAV and IgA nephropathy (IgAN) are difficult to distinguish pathologically due to their similar renal findings, and the difference between them remains unclear.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed clinical and pathological differences between 32 adult IgAV patients and 96 IgAN patients, all aged 18 or older, who underwent renal biopsy at our hospital between January 2012 and February 2023.

Results: Clinically, IgAV was significantly presented extra-renal symptoms such as purpura and hematochezia compared to IgAN. Moreover, levels of CRP (1.309 ± 0.42 vs. 0.186 ± 0.05 mg/dL, $p=0.014$), D-dimer (4.56 ± 1.71 vs. 0.73 ± 0.15 $\mu\text{g/dL}$, $p=0.003$), and C3 (110.34 ± 3.40 vs. 98.65 ± 2.04 mg/dL, $p=0.008$) were significantly higher in the IgAV.

In contrast, no significant differences was observed in haematuria ($p=0.377$), spot urine protein/creatinine ratio ($p=0.348$), or serum creatinine levels ($p=0.507$) at the time of renal biopsy. Pathologically, IgAV showed significantly higher incidences of endocapillary proliferation ($p<0.001$), necrotizing lesions ($p<0.001$), and peritubular capillaritis ($p=0.005$) under light microscopy. On the other hand, global glomerulosclerosis ($p=0.007$) was significantly more frequent in IgAN. In immunofluorescence staining, fibrinogen deposition both in mesangium (84.4% vs. 33.3%, $p<0.001$) and capillary (21.9% vs. 5.6%, $p=0.009$) was significantly higher in IgAV than IgAN. Electron microscopy study showed significantly higher incidences of endocapillary proliferation (21.9% vs. 8.3%, $p=0.039$) and expansion of the subendothelial space (67.7% vs. 37.2%, $p=0.003$) in IgAV.

Conclusions: From our renal pathologic perspective, IgAV is a systemic inflammatory disease involving acute to subacute vascular endothelial damage, whereas IgAN is a chronic progressive nephritis, allowing for differentiation although both diseases arise from IgA-related immune mechanisms.

P-022

Triggers and organ involvement of IgA vasculitis: Is there a need to split up IgA Vasculitis?

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Background/Aims: Adult IgA vasculitis (IgAV) is rare and often more severe than in children. It can be secondary to FMF, ankylosing spondylitis, malignancy, chronic liver disease, or drugs. Data on triggers in adults remain limited. This study aimed to evaluate triggers and organ involvement in adult IgAV using a nationwide prospective database (TRVaS).

Methods: Adults (>16 years) with IgAV were enrolled. Demographic, clinical, and histopathological data were analysed, and subgroups were compared based on triggers and outcomes.

Results: A total of 216 patients were included (59.3% male; median age 50 years). Gastrointestinal involvement was more frequent in younger patients (≤ 25 years: 53.8% vs 26–65 years: 29.2%, $p=0.01$), while renal involvement tended to be higher in the elderly (≥ 65 years: 75.0%, $p=0.06$). A potential trigger was identified in 70.4% of cases: infections (46.3%) and drugs (39.8%). Infections were significantly more frequent in younger patients (≤ 25 years: 51.3% vs ≥ 65 years: 20.8%, $p=0.03$), whereas drugs were more common in the elderly (≥ 65 years: 62.5%, $p=0.03$). Among associated diseases (21.2%), FMF was the most frequent (11.1%). Malignancy was more common in elderly patients (≥ 65 years: 20.8%, $p=0.01$), particularly gastrointestinal cancers ($p=0.01$). Gastrointestinal involvement was more frequent in the post-infectious subgroup (41.0% vs 27.6%, $p=0.04$). During a median follow-up of 13 months, patients with malignancy showed a trend toward more severe skin disease, though not statistically significant.

Conclusions: Adult IgAV is frequently associated with identifiable triggers and comorbidities, with age-related differences: younger patients and post-infectious cases had more gastrointestinal involvement, while drug-related disease and malignancy predominated in the elderly. These findings highlight the heterogeneity of adult IgAV and support the need for multinational studies to confirm subgroup-specific patterns.

P-023

Clinical characteristics of giant cell arteritis in South Australia: the South Australian Giant Cell Arteritis Registry update for 2025

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Background/Aims: The South Australian Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA) Registry provides valuable insights into disease patterns, demographics, treatment outcomes, in Australians with GCA. We aimed to describe the clinical characteristics of registry participants.

Methods: Patients with a diagnosis of GCA, enrolled in the registry between January 1991 and August 2025 were included in the study. Data were collected using participant surveys and structured case note reviews; a subset underwent HLA-DR4 typing. Results are presented as percentages or medians with interquartile ranges (IQR).

Results: A total of 324 patients were included. The median age was 76 years (71–81), 70% were female, and 94% were of Northern European/Caucasian background. The median BMI was 25kg/m²(23–28), 11% currently smoked, and 33% reported former smoking. HLA-DR4 positivity was observed in 53% of the 171 with HLA-DR4 typing. Polymyalgia rheumatica prior to GCA diagnosis was reported in 35%. Common presenting manifestations were temporal headache (79%), other headache (76%), visual disturbance (73%), malaise (70%), fatigue (68%), and jaw claudication (67%). Within seven days of steroid initiation, the median ESR was 60 mm/hr (50–60), CRP 43.5 mg/L (16.5–104.4), and platelets 359×10⁹/L (269–455). Median initial prednisolone dose was 60 mg/day (50–60 mg). Most frequent were thin skin/bruising (62%), sleep disturbance (48%), change in facial appearance (44%), muscular weakness (44%) and weight gain (44%). Common baseline comorbidities included hypertension (52%), osteoporosis (39%), hypercholesterolemia (35%), ischaemic heart disease (17%), and diabetes (13%).

Conclusions: The registry highlights key demographic and clinical characteristics of GCA in South Australia and highlights the considerable burden of glucocorticoid-related toxicity within this elderly cohort. These findings emphasise the urgent need for effective steroid-sparing strategies and the further utilisation of this representative GCA cohort provides a robust foundation for future research.

P-024

Hospitalisation and emergency department visits for patients with giant cell arteritis in South Australia

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) causes significant morbidity related to disease burden and treatment-related complications. Incidence rates and healthcare costs are predicted to double with population aging. There is no Australian data on current healthcare utilisation. This study aimed to quantify the burden of GCA in South Australia (SA) using data linkage across administrative health data sets.

Methods: Patients aged ≥ 50 with a positive temporal artery biopsy (TAB) were identified from the SA GCA Registry from 1992-2022. Emergency (ED) presentations and hospital admissions, with ICD-10-AM diagnosis codes, were obtained between 2001-2022 for both patients and controls (matched 4:1 on age, sex, and geographic area) using the SANT Data-linkage framework. Outcomes were analysed using recurrent event time-to-event models comparing GCA patients with age-matched controls, with adjustments for sex and calendar year.

Results: 435 GCA patients (median (IQR) diagnosis age:76 (71,81), 65% female) and 2124 controls were included in the analysis. Both ED and hospital admissions were increased in GCA patients compared to controls (HR 1.74, $p < 0.001$ and HR 1.73, $p = 0.01$ respectively) with events highest within 12 months of GCA diagnosis. Mean length of stay was equivalent for GCA patients and controls. GCA patients were more likely to have a principal admission diagnosis of infection (HR 1.53, $p = 0.008$), cerebrovascular disease (HR 1.99, $p = 0.01$), osteoporosis (HR 4.0, $p = 0.041$), pulmonary embolus (HR 4.35, $p = 0.01$), diverticulitis (HR 4.74, $p = 0.002$), and atherosclerosis (HR 9.73, $p < 0.001$). Elixhauser comorbidity score was determined cumulatively at the end of follow-up as a surrogate for patients' overall health status, suggesting no difference between GCA patients and controls (age-adjusted mean difference = -0.1, $p = 0.59$).

Conclusions: This study is the first in Australia to determine the significant burden of GCA, particularly in the 12 months following diagnosis. Improved understanding of healthcare utilisation will enable appropriate resource allocation and research prioritisation to improve patient outcomes.

P-025

Validation of the 2022 ACR/EULAR classification criteria for giant cell arteritis in the Gold Coast Hospital and Health Service: a retrospective study

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Background/Aims: We aimed to validate the use of the 2022 American College of Rheumatology/ European League Against Rheumatism classification criteria (2022 ACR/EULAR criteria) for giant cell arteritis (GCA) as a diagnostic tool in patients considered at risk for GCA in the Gold Coast Hospital & Health service (GCHHS).

Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional cohort study was conducted on patients who presented to the Gold Coast University Hospital and Robina Hospital between April 2019 to May 2023.

Results: 307 patients were included in our analysis (mean age 72.69 years, 69.7% females). 66 patients were diagnosed with GCA by their treating rheumatologist. When using the 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria cutoff score of ≥ 6 , the sensitivity of the 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria compared to rheumatologist diagnosed GCA was 100% (95%CI 94.6% to 100%) and specificity 61.8% (95%CI 55.4% to 68.0%). Area under Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve was 0.9571.

Conclusions: 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria for GCA may be a useful diagnostic tool alongside clinical assessment in patients with possible GCA. A cutpoint of 8.5 improved specificity.

P-026

Clinical, laboratory, and imaging features differentiating polymyalgia rheumatica, giant cell arteritis, and their overlap

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) and giant cell arteritis (GCA) are inflammatory conditions of the elderly. While PMR typically causes proximal joint and soft tissue pain, GCA carries risk of irreversible complications such as vision loss and stroke. Overlap of PMR and GCA complicates diagnosis and management. This study compared clinical, laboratory, and imaging features across isolated PMR (iPMR), isolated GCA (iGCA), and PMR-GCA overlap to identify diagnostic discriminators and pitfalls.

Methods: iPMR, iGCA, or PMR-GCA followed at a single centre between May 2020 and August 2025 were enrolled.

Results: Among 104 patients, 59 had iPMR, 33 iGCA, and 12 PMR-GCA. Median ages were similar (71–74 years). Female predominance was highest in PMR (76%). Diagnostic delay was shorter in PMR-GCA (3 months) versus PMR (6 months). Acute phase reactants were higher in GCA and PMR-GCA (CRP 62 vs. 33 mg/L; ESR 75 vs. 53 mm/h; $p < 0.05$). Ferritin was significantly higher in iGCA ($p = 0.009$). Clinical features clearly separated groups: PMR showed predominant shoulder (89.8%) and hip pain (81.4%) with morning stiffness (67.8%, all $p < 0.001$). In iGCA, headache (78.8%), temporal tenderness (51.5%), jaw claudication (39.4%), and vision loss (51.5%) were key discriminators ($p < 0.001$). In the PMR-GCA, headache (83.3%) and jaw claudication (66.7%) coexisted with proximal joint symptoms. Vision loss was often permanent (64.7%) and bilateral in 29.4%. Imaging supported diagnosis: ultrasonography and PET-CT were most useful in iGCA/PMR-GCA, whereas MRI was more contributory in iPMR ($p = 0.006$). All patients received corticosteroids; high-dose (75.8%) and pulse steroids (39.4%) were more common in iGCA ($p < 0.001$). Methotrexate use was frequent in PMR-GCA (41.7%), while tocilizumab was mainly prescribed in iGCA (42.4% vs. 11.9% in iPMR, $p = 0.003$). Remission rates exceeded 97% across groups, though steroid-related adverse events were more frequent in iGCA (30.3%).

Conclusions: PMR and GCA exhibit distinct clinical and laboratory profiles, with overlap cases demonstrating mixed patterns. Recognition of GCA components, especially vision-threatening features, is critical for timely intervention. Imaging modalities add diagnostic value—ultrasound and PET-CT for GCA, MRI for PMR.

P-027

Incidence of large vessel complications and outcomes in polymyalgia rheumatica: a multi-centre data analysis from 24 Korean hospitals

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) and giant cell arteritis (GCA) likely represent a continuum within the GCA–PMR spectrum disorder (GPSD). Although up to half of GCA patients report PMR symptoms and 10–20% of PMR patients may later develop GCA, the presumed low GCA incidence in Korea raises concern for under-recognition of large-vessel disease. We evaluated post-PMR occurrence of large vessel vasculitis (LVV), aortic complications, cerebrovascular/cardiovascular (CV) events, and anterior ischemic optic neuropathy (AAION), and assessed glucocorticoid-related comorbidities.

Methods: We conducted a multicentre retrospective cohort using de-identified OMOP-CDM data from 24 Korean hospitals. Patients were aged ≥ 50 years with a first PMR diagnosis (KCD M31.5, M31.6) before January 1, 2023. Outcomes were defined by KCD codes and counted only if occurring on or after the index date. Year-by-year cumulative prevalence was summarized for 1997–2024. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of Kyung Hee University Hospital (IRB No. KHUH 2020-01-047).

Results: Among 1,970 PMR patients, cumulative prevalence increased steadily across outcomes through 2024. CV events rose to 341 patients ($\approx 17.3\%$); osteoporosis to 522 ($\approx 26.5\%$); malignancy to 227 ($\approx 11.5\%$); and in-hospital deaths to 101 ($\approx 5.1\%$). Aortic complications were first detected in the early 2010s and reached 15 ($\approx 0.8\%$) by 2024. Incident LVV and GCA remained uncommon, plateauing at 33 ($\approx 1.7\%$) and 23 ($\approx 1.2\%$), respectively, by 2023–2024. AAION was not observed. Cumulative curves were mostly monotonic, indicating that, despite low absolute numbers for LVV/GCA, vascular events and steroid-related comorbidities accrued over calendar time after PMR diagnosis, reflecting substantial long-term morbidity in PMR beyond classic GPSD progression to GCA.

Conclusions: In a large Korean PMR cohort, GCA, LVV, and AAION were rare, consistent with a lower background GCA incidence. Nevertheless, vascular events, osteoporosis, malignancy, and mortality accumulated meaningfully, underscoring the need for proactive surveillance and targeted risk mitigation throughout the disease course.

P-028

Histological reporting of temporal artery biopsies: a comparative analysis

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Background/Aims: In 2023, the Society for Cardiovascular Pathology introduced consensus guidelines with a standardised temporal artery biopsy (TAB) reporting template to improve diagnostic consistency of giant cell arteritis (GCA). We examined the reporting of key histologic features (i.e. intima/media hyperplasia, internal elastic lamina disruption (IEL), inflammation, presence of giant cells, thrombus, calcification, and luminal narrowing) in reports from 2010, 2017 and 2024 in South Australia.

Methods: A retrospective analysis of all TAB reports from South Australia's public pathology service from 2010, 2017 and 2024 was conducted. The key histologic features were assessed for completeness of reporting and changes in reporting over time ($p < 0.05$ for trend was deemed significant).

Results: There was a total of 294 reports ($n=76, 92$ and 126 for 2010, 2017 and 2024, respectively). The reporting of a number of key histological features increased significantly between 2010 and 2024: IEL (55.3% to 73.0%), inflammation (66.0% to 93.3%), and despite low numbers, calcification (16.6% to 37.1%), lumen involvement (13.8% to 38.8%) and thrombus (8.3%, 27.2%). However, the reporting of giant cells remained relatively stable (51% to 63%, $p=0.67$), as did intimal or media layer changes ($p=0.10, p=0.24$ respectively). Finally, among cases with negative or indeterminate GCA findings ($n=232$), the acknowledgment of skip lesions and/or false negatives increased significantly over time, from 13.8% in 2010 to 51.0% in 2024.

Conclusions: Despite the introduction of the guidelines, many key histologic factors remain unreported. The increasing recognition of skip lesions and false negatives emphasises the evolving diagnostic challenges in pathological assessment. These findings support the use and refinement of structured reporting to enhance diagnostic precision in GCA.

P-029

A retrospective audit of treatment decisions following temporal artery biopsy result in a giant cell arteritis fast-track clinic in Western Australia

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Background/Aims: Imaging or temporal artery biopsy (TAB) confirmation of giant cell arteritis (GCA) diagnosis should be sought to optimise diagnostic certainty, though gold standard remains expert opinion. Diagnosis via TAB is considered 100% specific, although sensitivity is only around 77%. We sought to assess the association between TABs and subsequent steroid therapy in a modern GCA Fast-Track clinic setting.

Methods: We audited all patients who underwent TAB at the Royal Perth Hospital GCA Fast-Track clinic, using standardised clinical data collected retrospectively, between November 2019 and June 2023. GCA pretest probability scores (GCAPS) were calculated, and TABs reviewed.

Results: Of 98 patients, 50 (51.0%) were high-probability, 36 (36.7%) intermediate-probability, and 12 (12.2%) low-probability GCA using GCAPS. 36 (36.7%) TABs were diagnostic; 34 (94.4%) of these being high-probability and 2 being intermediate-probability cases. 7/98 (7.14%) TABs were equivocal. 81.6% were performed within 14 days of steroid initiation and 80.6% had specimens >10mm. TAB negative likelihood ratio was 0.28 as compared to 6-month final physician diagnosis. Of 50 patients with negative TAB and treatment data available, 31 patients had steroids stopped, while 9 of 12 (75.0%) high-risk, 9 of 28 (32.1%) intermediate-risk, and 1 of 10 (10.0%) low-risk patients had steroids continued.

Conclusions: Steroids were frequently continued despite negative TABs, especially in high and intermediate-risk groups. Steroid cessation occurred more often in patients with a negative TAB who had low pre-test probability of GCA. Confident de-diagnosis is as important an outcome as diagnostic certainty for GCA.

P-030

Histiocytosis as a difficult competitor in the differential diagnosis of vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Vasculitis represents a heterogeneous group of disorders defined by systemic manifestations and multi-organ involvement. A broad spectrum of neoplastic, infectious, and inflammatory conditions may mimic vasculitis, posing significant diagnostic challenges. Among these, histiocytoses are rare entities with frequent multi-organ involvement that can closely resemble vasculitis in both clinical presentation and imaging findings. This study aimed to evaluate the characteristics of patients with histiocytosis.

Methods: Histiocytosis cases were identified among vasculitis mimickers registered in the Hacettepe University Vasculitis Research Center (HUVAC) database. Patients with Erdheim-Chester Disease (ECD) or Langerhans Cell Histiocytosis (LCH) who were followed at the Rheumatology clinic from 2014 onwards were included. Patient demographics, symptoms, dates of diagnosis and last visit, organ involvement, laboratory and imaging features, pathology reports, comorbidities, and treatments were recorded.

Results: This study included six patients with ECD (one female, five males) and three with LCH (two females, one male). The mean age at diagnosis was 51 years (SD: 17), and the mean interval from symptom onset to diagnosis was 28 months. Among ECD cases, large-vessel involvement was observed in five patients (83%), most commonly accompanied by perirenal–retroperitoneal, cardiac, and long-bone involvement. LCH cases demonstrated a more heterogeneous distribution: one presented with pulmonary involvement, one with hypothalamic–pituitary axis and bone disease, and one with mediastinal and large-vessel involvement. At diagnosis, erythrocyte sedimentation rate ranged from 12–40 mm/h and C-reactive protein from 9.8–59 mg/L. Pathological assessment of ECD cases frequently showed CD68/CD163 positivity, and the BRAF V600E mutation was identified in three patients. LCH cases exhibited CD1a and S100 positivity.

Conclusions: Histiocytosis can mimic large vessel vasculitis with clinical and imaging findings, particularly with aortic involvement in ECD. Therefore, considering histiocytosis is critical for an accurate diagnosis and initiating appropriate therapy for patients being evaluated for suspected vasculitis.

P-031

Takayasu arteritis in a Latin American population: clinical and angiographic features from two Peruvian tertiary centres

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TA) presents with diverse clinical features, but in Latin America, data about it remains scarce. We aimed to describe the clinical and angiographic features of patients with TA from a Latin American (Peruvian) population.

Methods: Patient data were obtained between 2008 to 2024 from electronic medical records in two tertiary centres in Peru. Demographic data, clinical features, and angiographic involvement were examined. The sites of arterial involvement, including affected aortic segments and branch vessels, were assessed based on the radiology reports. Angiographic patterns were categorized using the Numano classification system. Numano types were inferred by two rheumatologists from narrative reports of radiologists, using a standardized data abstraction tool. For the bivariate analysis, patients were grouped as Type V or non-Type V patterns. Additionally, we described fulfillment of the classification criteria set for each patient.

Results: Fifty-eight patients were included; 53 (91.4%) of the total were women. The mean age at diagnosis was 33.9 (12.7) years. A history of tuberculosis was reported in 10 (17.2%) patients. Regarding the classification criteria, 87.9% met the 1990 ACR criteria set, while 96.6% met the 2022 ACR/EULAR one. The most frequent symptom was upper limb claudication (63.8%). The most common physical finding was pulselessness (89.7%). Carotid (65.5%) and subclavian (62.1%) arteries were the most affected. Mean daily dose of prednisone was 35.4 (\pm 16.9). Methotrexate was the most used immunosuppressive drug (70.7%). Numano type V was the most common angiographic pattern (50%). In the bivariate analysis, tuberculosis history, murmur and heart failure were more frequent in Type V ($p=0.037$, $p=0.035$ and $p=0.023$, respectively).

Conclusions: In our cohort, Numano type V was the most prevalent angiographic pattern and was significantly associated with tuberculosis history, murmur and heart failure. These findings highlight the need for further studies on disease patterns and management strategies.

P-032

Prevalence of pathogenic UBA1 variants in idiopathic polyarteritis nodosa.

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Background/Aims: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) is a necrotizing vasculitis that predominantly affects medium-sized arteries. VEXAS (vacuoles, E1 enzyme, X-linked, autoinflammatory, somatic) syndrome can present with medium-sized vessel vasculitis, mimicking PAN. Screening for VEXAS syndrome in cohorts of idiopathic PAN has not been performed. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of pathogenic UBA1 variants in a cohort of idiopathic PAN.

Methods: We included patients with idiopathic PAN attending a referral centre in Mexico City. Diagnosis was established according to the 1990 ACR criteria, the EMEA classification algorithm, and/or the 2012 Chapel Hill Consensus definitions. Adult patients with childhood-onset PAN fulfilling the 2008 Ankara (EULAR/PRES/PRINTO) criteria were also included. Sanger sequencing of exons 3, 14, and 16 of the UBA1 gene was performed to identify pathogenic UBA1 variants.

Results: We included 19 patients with idiopathic PAN. Twelve were female (63.2%), with a median age at diagnosis of 27 years (IQR 15–42) and a median age at inclusion of 43 years (IQR 22–65). Twelve patients (63.2%) had systemic PAN and seven (36.8%) had cutaneous PAN. Eleven (57.9%) presented with adult-onset and eight (42.1%) with childhood-onset disease. The most frequent manifestations were musculoskeletal (78.9%), cutaneous (73.7%), constitutional (73.7%), and peripheral nervous system involvement (47.4%).

One patient carried the p.Met41Thr UBA1 mutation with a variant allele frequency of 18%. This patient was a man with disease onset at 48 years, presenting with fever, polymorphous skin lesions (erythematous macules, nodules, livedo racemosa) with biopsy-proven neutrophilic vasculitis of medium-sized vessels and septal and lobular panniculitis, arthralgias, myalgias, polyneuropathy, orchitis, macrocytosis, and transient leukocytosis.

Conclusions: The prevalence of VEXAS syndrome in this idiopathic PAN cohort was 5.3%. Given this low prevalence, UBA1 mutation testing in PAN should not be routinely performed in the absence of typical VEXAS manifestations, such as late-onset disease in males and characteristic haematological features.

P-033

Clinical and socio-demographic features of IgG4-related disease patients: data from a Peruvian tertiary centre

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Background/Aims: IgG4-related disease (IgG4-RD) is a systemic autoimmune fibroinflammatory condition that can involve several organs. We aimed at describing the clinical and socio-demographic features of these patients from a Latin American (Peruvian) tertiary centre.

Methods: Patients who were diagnosed between August 2017 and November 2024 according to either the Umehara diagnostic criteria or the clinical acumen of the attending physician were included. Clinical, demographic and histopathological features as well as phenotypic classification were evaluated. Relapse was defined as the appearance of a new organ manifestation or need of increasing therapy, regardless of serum IgG4 levels. The ACR/EULAR 2019 classification criteria were applied.

Results: Twenty-five patients were evaluated; 13 (52%) of them were female. The median (interquartile range) age and disease duration were 55.5 (24.0-76.0) years and 8 (4–43) months, respectively. The most frequent phenotype was the classic Mikulicz syndrome with systemic involvement [13 (52%)]. Five (20%) patients were classified as definitive diagnosis according to the Umehara criteria whereas 8 (32%) patients met the 2019 ACR/EULAR classification criteria. Regarding treatment, the daily prednisone dose was 40 (30-47.5) mg/d and leflunomide (36%) was the most used immunosuppressive drug used. Eight (32%) patients experienced a relapse.

Conclusions: In our cohort, IgG4-RD patients were younger, female sex slightly predominated and classic Mikulicz syndrome with systemic involvement was the most frequent phenotype. On the other hand, less of one third of the patients fulfilled the diagnostic and classification criteria sets for IgG4-RD.

P-034

IgG4 related disease: a retrospective observational single-centre study

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Background/Aims: IgG4 related disease (IgG4-RD) is a chronic fibro-inflammatory condition with raised IgG4 levels and accumulation of plasma cells and fibrosis in the affected tissue.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective observational study of patients seen at Guy's Hospitals, London. Data was collected for clinical presentation, inflammatory markers, immunoglobulin subsets, autoantibody profiles, imaging and histopathology and compared to the 2019 ACR/EULAR criteria. Data was also collected post standard-of-care treatment, including patient clinical outcomes and improvement.

Results: The study included a multi-ethnic cohort of 83 patients with multi-organ involvement. The median age at diagnosis was 58 years (11-84). None of the patients had positive serology for ANA, dsDNA, or ENA. Seventy one patients underwent biopsies, and 50 patients PET-CT scans as part of their workup. Fifty-nine of 83 patients (71.1%) were classed as confirmed IgG4-RD with a score of >20 on ACR/EULAR criteria. Of the confirmed patients, 49/59 (83.1%) had biopsies consistent with IgG4-RD, and 26/34 (74.3%) had PET-CT showing active inflammation. IgG subclass analysis showed significantly higher IgG4 levels in the confirmed IgG4-RD group, in which 31/43 patients had high IgG4 levels. Patients were treated with corticosteroids (68/83 patients) ± DMARDs – Methotrexate (n=21), Mycophenolate (n=16), Azathioprine (n=8), Cyclophosphamide (n=5) and Rituximab (n=15). Post-treatment IgG4 levels as well as inflammatory markers were significantly reduced in those patients with confirmed IgG4-RD disease and correlated with clinical improvement. Of the Rituximab patients, 11/15 (73.3%) showed improvement. During follow-up, 15 patients were lost to follow-up and 5 patients died.

Conclusions: The majority of patients met the 2019 ACR/EULAR criteria, but there remain patients with negative biopsies and/or normal serum IgG4 levels. IgG4-RD often responds to corticosteroids but may require other immunosuppressive therapy. Treatment with biologics such as B cell depletion therapy results are encouraging in patients resistant to conventional DMARDs.

P-035

Dynamic long-term remission off therapy states in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) typically follows a relapsing-remitting course. Some patients achieve long-term remission off therapy (LTROT), representing a distinct clinical phenotype and model for investigating immune tolerance.

Methods: Patients were recruited from the RITA-Ireland Vasculitis (RIV) Registry. LTROT state was defined as sustained remission for >2 years without immunosuppression, with follow-up until death or last review. Participants had a diagnosis of AAV or double-positive disease (anti-GBM/AAV) and ≥27 months follow up. Six LTROT states were defined by ANCA status and corticosteroid use. To assess immune signatures, single-cell RNA sequencing was performed on LTROT donors and healthy controls.

Results: Among 598 eligible recruits, 204 (34.1%) entered an LTROT state. Distribution by first LTROT state was: Level1 (ANCA-, no steroids) 20%; Level2 (ANCA+, no steroids) 26%; Level3 (any ANCA, no steroids) 25%; Level4 (ANCA-, ≤10mg prednisolone) 8%; Level5 (ANCA+, ≤10mg prednisolone) 9%; Level6 (any ANCA, ≤10mg prednisolone) 11%. 9% of patients entered an LTROT state multiple times. The cohort comprised 97 MPA (35.9% of total MPA population), 82 GPA (29.7%), 12 EGPA (41.4%) and 13 double-positive (56.5%). 97 (47.5%), 97 (47.5%) and 10 (4.9%) were anti-MPO, anti-PR3 and ANCA negative respectively. Median LTROT duration was 437 days (IQR 152–1101). Post-LTROT relapse occurred in 58 patients(28.4%).

The actuarial probability of exiting the LTROT state was not significantly different across LTROT levels (log-rank p=0.659). ANCA positivity was associated with a trend towards earlier exit from LTROT (HR 1.57, 95%CI 0.93–2.65; p=0.091); use of low dose corticosteroids was not associated with LTROT exit (HR 0.91, 95%CI 0.55–1.50; p=0.70). Transcriptomic analysis revealed persisting differences between patients in the LTROT state and healthy controls, particularly in the classical monocyte and NK cell populations.

Conclusions: These findings identify LTROT as a valuable cohort for studying tolerance mechanisms. Ongoing multi-state modelling will further clarify the dynamics of LTROT state.

P-036

Dynamic prediction of relapse in ANCA-associated vasculitis using real-world data

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Background/Aims: In ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), relapse risk varies over the disease course. We propose a machine learning pipeline using irregular longitudinal real-world data to predict relapse and address two questions: (1) whether historic data improves performance, and (2) whether neural networks or tree-based ensembles are more effective.

Methods: Using RITA Ireland Vasculitis data on GPA and MPA patients, we applied a three-phase pipeline feature engineering, patient-level bootstrapping for multiple train/test splits, and model training/evaluation. Four models were fitted to dynamically predict relapse within 12 months: Model 1 is a simple Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network and Model 2 is a Random Forest (RF), both trained using only the index-visit (no history) features. Model 3 is a history-aware LSTM trained on each patient's full time series, while Model 4 is a random forest trained on summary statistics from patient history plus current clinical status.

Results: Among 514 patients, 200 (39%) experienced 560 encounters, which were followed by a relapse within 12 months. Across the four models, the LSTM without history (Model 1) performed best, ROC-AUC 0.80 (0.78–0.82), PR-AUC 0.79 (0.77–0.81), precision 0.60 (0.55–0.65), recall 0.70 (0.67–0.73), specificity 0.70 (0.67–0.73), and F1 score 0.64 (0.61–0.68). The two RF models (Models 2 & 4) displayed similar metrics and were slightly less accurate than Model 1 (ROC-AUC 0.75; PR-AUC 0.69; recall 0.60; specificity 0.79). The history-aware LSTM (Model 3) matched the ROC-AUC of the RF models (0.75) but had a lower PR-AUC (0.64) with recall of 0.64 and a specificity of 0.75.

Conclusions: We propose a modelling architecture for predicting relapse in AAV over multiple time points that supports multiple feature representations and leverages both current and historical clinical data. In internal validation, the LSTM model performed best, and historical data did not improve either model type

P-037

Deriving time-dependent estimates of immunosuppression exposure in autoimmune disease from real-world data

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Introduction/Aims: Relapse risk in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is closely linked to immunosuppressant exposure, but modelling their effect over time is challenging due to complex real-world recording of multiple oral and intravenous regimens. We propose an “immunosuppressive therapy intensity score” (ITIS) that integrates medication data to estimate a patient’s overall immune status at a given time.

Methods: Using the RITA-Ireland Vasculitis Registry, we derived a sigmoidal ITIS function incorporating route (IV/oral), dose, and interval since treatment, where the ITIS=0 indicates no immunosuppression. Three parameters of the function, A (starting intensity), n (decay rate), and d (half-life, the point when the pharmacodynamic effect reduces to 50%) were estimated across a range of standard treatment types and doses, and using clinical expert opinion elicitation via survey. Parameter values were estimated using linear interpolation between defined doses, and age, B-cell and lymphocyte counts were incorporated when available. When multiple medications were active contemporaneously, the final ITIS was calculated as the sum of individual values.

Results: We illustrate the ITIS using two case scenarios from the data. Case 1: Taking azathioprine 100mg daily for 20 months: ITIS=0.5. After reducing the dose to 50 mg, the score dropped to 0.43. With dose increase to 150mg, the score rose to 0.56, dropping to zero after discontinuation. Case 2: After rituximab 1000mg IV, the ITIS remained high (0.78) for 90 days post-infusion before declining gradually to 0.35 after five months, at which point the patient received an additional 600mg dose (ITIS=0.75); the combined effect of both doses gave a score of 1.1.

Conclusions: We describe for the first time a pragmatic ITIS that numerically represents the overall immunosuppressive treatment status of a patient at a specific time point. This provides a single continuous variable that can be used in statistical models as a proxy of immunosuppression exposure.

P-038

Kidney relapse predicts long term eGFR decline in de novo ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis: a large real-life dataset

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis (AGN) often progresses to chronic-or end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), hugely impacting patient outcome. ESKD prediction tools overlook key factors such as relapse and comorbidities and fail to account for the heterogenous nature of disease. With use of real-world data, this study examines eGFR's slope in de novo AGN as upcoming surrogate marker for kidney outcomes, implementing relapsing disease, well-established comorbidities and repeat kidney biopsies.

Methods: This single centre observational study recruited patients with biopsy-proven de novo AGN retrospectively from the Limburg Renal Registry (1981-2019), and the prospective PROMAVAS cohort, with follow-up until February 2025. The eGFR slope was modelled to define an acute (0–24 months) and chronic (>24 months) slope. Linear mixed-effects models assessed the impact of comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, diabetes), treatment, and kidney relapse on eGFR's slope. Initial and repeat biopsies were scored using established ESKD prediction tools to validate findings and assess the effects of relapsing AGN on histological activity and chronicity.

Results: 266 patients were included with a median follow-up of 7.4 years (IQR 3.1-12.8). The acute eGFR slope peaked at 24 months, then declined by -1.21 mL/min/1.73m²/year thereafter. Kidney relapse and hypertension were independently associated with a change in chronic eGFR of -2.14 (95% CI, -2.69 to -0.28) and -1.47 mL/min/1.73m²/year, respectively. Each additional relapse contributed to an increased -0.59 mL/min/1.73m²/year decline. First repeat biopsies (n/N=36/61, 59%) showed progressive chronicity (median MCCS, 4 versus 1; p<0.001).

Conclusions: Analysis of the eGFR slope in AGN reveals that the initial 24-month period represents a critical window for renal recovery. Patients in stable remission without hypertension fare well, whereas kidney relapse and hypertension drive accelerated decline, underscoring the need for sustained remission and cardiovascular risk control to improve kidney outcomes in AGN. Repeat biopsies provide interesting insight of chronic scarring, challenging for more optimal treatment modalities.

P-039

Interstitial ANCA-associated vasculitis associates with severe kidney injury independent of glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: Although crescentic antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated glomerulonephritis (GN) is a common histological finding reflecting glomerular small vessel vasculitis, it is reasonable that manifestation of AAV could also contribute to interstitial small vessel vasculitis. Therefore, we here aimed to expand our current knowledge focusing on interstitial vasculitis in ANCA GN by systematic histological scoring of vascular lesions analogous to Banff.

Methods: A total number of 49 kidney biopsies with confirmed renal involvement of AAV at the University Medical Center Göttingen were retrospectively included between 2015 till 2020. A renal pathologist evaluated all biopsies and was blinded to clinical data collection and analysis.

Results: Among all active and chronic tubulointerstitial lesions analogous to the Banff scoring system, the only association between severe kidney injury requiring RRT was observed for interstitial vasculitis in AAV reflected by peritubular capillaritis (ptc, $p=0.0002$) and arteritis (v, $p=0.0069$), affecting 5/49 (10.2%) and 11/49 (22.4%) of renal biopsies, respectively. Interestingly, no association between interstitial vasculitis (ptc and v correlating with severe kidney injury) and any glomerular lesion in ANCA GN (also correlating with severe kidney injury) was observed, thereby confirming that interstitial vasculitis contributes to severe kidney injury independent of ANCA GN.

Conclusions: Taken together, by using the Banff scoring system we here expand our current knowledge of renal interstitial lesions in AAV revealing peritubular capillaritis and arteritis as important histological alterations associated with severe kidney injury in a considerable subset of AAV independent of crescentic ANCA GN.

P-040

The Death in ANCA Glomerulonephritis-Estimating Risk (DANGER) and the 2009 Five-Factor scores as predictor of mortality in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis with or without glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: The aim of this study was to evaluate the performance of the DANGER and 2009 Five-factor scores (2009-FFS) in ANCA-associated vasculitis patients with and without glomerulonephritis (GN) from a Latin American (Peruvian) cohort.

Methods: Patients with microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis from the Almenara Vasculitis Cohort (a single-centre cohort from Peru), who had at least one visit between January 1990 and December 2024 were included. Mortality data were obtained from the Peruvian Department of Health's vital statistics department. Mortality prediction was assessed at baseline by the DANGER score (low-, intermediate- and high-risk categories) and the 2009-FFS (0, 1 and ≥ 2 categories). The first includes four variables: age at diagnosis, history of hypertension or cardiac disease, and creatinine and haemoglobin levels at diagnosis. Unadjusted and adjusted Cox regression models were performed.

Results: Two-hundred twenty-six patients were included, being the majority women [155 (68.6%)]. Their mean age and follow-up time were 59.4 (12.6) and 7.9 (7.2) years, respectively. MPA was the most frequent diagnosis [178 (78.8%)]. During their follow-up, 110 (48.7%) patients had died. The 5-year mortality risks for the DANGER score were 17.2%, 36.8% and 71.4% (low, intermediate and high risk, respectively) whereas for the 2009-FFS they were 9.9%, 14.9% and 40.3% (0, 1 and ≥ 2 categories, respectively). In the global population, both the DANGER score and the 2009-FFS had good discrimination (log-rank $p < 0.001$). In GN patients, the DANGER score had better discrimination than the 2009-FFS (log-rank $p = 0.024$ and $p = 0.076$, respectively). In the non-GN patients, both the DANGER score and the 2009-FFS had good discriminant validity (log-rank $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: The DANGER score had good performance in AAV patients with or without GN in this Latin American cohort whereas the 2009-FFS had no good performance in GN patients. Studies in other populations are necessary to validate these findings.

P-041

The French Vasculitis Study Group relapse score in ANCA-associated vasculitis patients: data from the Almenara vasculitis cohort

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Background/Aims: The aim of this study was to evaluate the performance of the French Vasculitis Study Group Relapse Score (FRS) in ANCA-associated vasculitis patients from a Latin American (Peruvian) cohort.

Methods: Patients with microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis from the Almenara Vasculitis Cohort (a single-centre cohort from Peru), enrolled between January 2015 and January 2025, were included. Remission was defined if the Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) was equal to zero for ≥ 3 consecutive months. Relapse was defined as the recurrence and/or appearance of ≥ 1 new vasculitis manifestation(s) after patients had been on remission ≥ 3 months. The FRS includes three factors (PR3-ANCA, age ≤ 75 years and estimated glomerular filtration rate ≥ 30 mL/min/1.73 m²); each of these factors provides 1 point and the score ranges from 0 to 3. For this study, scores were categorized into three groups: group A (0-1 points), group B (2 points) and group C (3 points). Unadjusted and adjusted Cox regression models were performed.

Results: Eighty-nine patients were included, most of them were women [60 (67.4%)]. Their mean age and follow-up duration time were 59.3 (11.5) and 3.5 (2.7) years, respectively. MPA was the most frequent diagnosis [65 (73.0%)]. Fifty (56.2%) patients had a flare. There were 29 (32.5%) patients in group A, 45 (50.6%) in group B and 15 (16.9%) in group C. The 5-year relapse risk as per the FRS was 60.0% for group A, 56.8% for group B and 60.9% for group C, thus exhibiting poor discrimination among the groups (log-rank $p=0.620$).

Conclusions: The FRS failed to predict relapses in this Latin American AAV population. A small number of patients in each group and a predominance of MPA patients in this cohort may explain these findings. Studies in other populations are needed to determine the FRS's value.

P-042

Clinical significance of coagulation parameters and von Willebrand factor in relation to major organ involvement in ANCA-Associated Vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a group of autoimmune disorders affecting small- to medium-sized vessels, with high morbidity and mortality due to renal involvement and pulmonary haemorrhage. Haemostatic abnormalities may contribute to both thrombotic and haemorrhagic complications. The relationship of coagulation parameters, including von Willebrand factor (vWF) antigen and cofactor levels, with diagnosis, renal involvement, and haemorrhagic complications was evaluated

Methods: This retrospective, single-centre study included 46 patients (26 males, 20 females; 33 with granulomatosis with polyangiitis [GPA], 13 with microscopic polyangiitis [MPA]). Clinical data and laboratory parameters were analysed at active and remission state. Serum vWF antigen and cofactor levels were categorized as low, normal, or high based on reference values.

Results: Pulmonary haemorrhage occurred in 18 (39.1%) and renal dysfunction in 24 (52.2%) patients. During active disease, pulmonary haemorrhage was associated with higher CRP, ESR, neutrophils, creatinine, and LDH, alongside lower haemoglobin and lymphocytes ($p < 0.05$). Coagulation profiles showed trends toward prolonged aPTT, elevated fibrinogen, and low D-dimer. In remission, most coagulation parameters normalized. Notably, vWF antigen was elevated in nearly all active GPA (81.8%) and MPA (100%) cases, and remained significantly higher in MPA than GPA during remission (63.6% vs. 20.0%, $p = 0.012$). Renal dysfunction was also linked to higher remission vWF antigen levels (50% vs. 16.7%, $p = 0.026$), while pulmonary haemorrhage showed a similar trend (50% vs. 22.7%, $p = 0.076$). vWF antigen and cofactor correlated strongly with LDH in active disease ($r = 0.48$ and 0.754), and this association persisted in remission. Both vWF parameters exhibited strong internal correlation across disease phases ($r \approx 0.8$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusions: Our findings highlight that endothelial injury and systemic inflammation contribute to both thrombotic and haemorrhagic complications in AAV. Elevated vWF antigen and cofactor levels, particularly their correlation with LDH, may reflect ongoing endothelial dysfunction beyond the active phase. vWF emerges as a potential prognostic biomarker for major organ involvement. Prospective multicentre studies to validate its role in risk stratification and personalized management is needed.

P-043

Ear-nose-throat manifestations of granulomatosis with polyangiitis and eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Ear–nose–throat (ENT) involvement is a frequent manifestation of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV), particularly in GPA and EGPA. This study aimed to evaluate and compare ENT clinical features in patients with GPA and EGPA.

Methods: Patients were recruited from the Rheumatology and ENT–Head & Neck Surgery Departments (outpatient and inpatient services) at King Saud University Medical City. Eligible patients had confirmed GPA or EGPA based on relevant serology, histopathology, and imaging findings. All patients fulfilled either the 1990 ACR or 2022 ACR/EULAR classification criteria. Each participant underwent comprehensive clinical, audiological, imaging, and laboratory evaluation conducted jointly by a rheumatologist and ENT specialist.

Results: A total of 50 patients were enrolled: 35 with GPA (20 women) and 15 with EGPA (8 women). The mean age at diagnosis was 35.4 (SD 13.7) years (GPA: 35.2; EGPA: 35.9; $p=0.4$), median age 34 years. Upper respiratory tract involvement was present in 90% of patients and was the predominant manifestation in both diseases, followed by lung (60%) and renal involvement (28%). Among 48 patients <60 years, hearing loss was reported in 24, including 10 (20%) with subclinical loss on audiometry. Sensorineural hearing loss was most common ($n=18$, 37.5%), followed by conductive loss ($n=4$, 6%). Hearing loss was significantly more prevalent in patients >34 vs. ≤34 years at diagnosis (80% vs. 29%, $p<0.001$). No cases of septal perforation, saddle-nose deformity, or subglottic stenosis (SGS) occurred in EGPA, whereas SGS was documented in 14.2% of GPA patients.

Conclusions: Hearing loss, including subclinical forms, was highly prevalent in GPA and EGPA, particularly in older age group. These findings highlight the need to incorporate routine audiometric evaluation into clinical practice. Objective audiometry should be integrated into disease activity assessments, complementing patients' reports and history-taking rather than relying solely on subjective measures of hearing impairment.

P-044

A retrospective cohort of 31 patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis: clinical spectrum, laboratory findings, treatment and outcomes from a Brazilian tertiary centre

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare vasculitis characterized by asthma, eosinophilia, and systemic involvement. Despite several epidemiological studies worldwide, no descriptive study has been conducted in Brazilian patients, which motivated us to perform this analysis.

Methods: We conducted a single-centre retrospective cohort study of patients fulfilling either the 2022 ACR/EULAR or 1990 ACR classification criteria, followed at a tertiary outpatient referral centre from January 2000 to July 2025. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, prognostic, and treatment data were collected from electronic medical records.

Results: The cohort comprised 31 patients, with a mean age of 66.1 ± 12.9 years; 54.8% were male, 64.5% White, 22.6% Mixed-race, and 12.9% Black. Median follow-up was 52 months (range 1,9–176). Main features included asthma (83.9%), ENT involvement (74.2%), rhinosinusitis (71.0%), constitutional symptoms (58.1%), cutaneous vasculitis (54.8%), neuropathy (48.4%), nasal polyposis (35.5%), renal disease (12.9%), cardiac involvement (12.9%), and alveolar haemorrhage (6.5%). At diagnosis, 35.5% had a Five-Factor Score ≥ 1 . Median eosinophil count at diagnosis was $3,400/\mu\text{L}$. At last follow-up, mean Vasculitis Damage Index was 3.4 (range 1–7). ANCA positivity occurred in 48.4%. p-ANCA was positive in 29.6% and c-ANCA in 17.9%. MPO-ANCA was detected in 38.9% and PR3-ANCA in 5.6%.

Treatments included azathioprine (67.7%), methotrexate (29.0%), mycophenolate (19.4%), cyclophosphamide (45.2%), mepolizumab (12.9%), rituximab (6.5%) and corticosteroids alone (16.1%). Relapse occurred in 29.0% (16.1% vasculitic, 16.1% respiratory). Four patients (12.9%) died.

Conclusions: In this cohort, EGPA patients were predominantly older adults, mostly White, with high rates of asthma, ENT disease, neuropathy, and cutaneous involvement. Nearly half were ANCA-positive, with MPO predominance. Despite therapy, patients accumulated significant long-term damage and relapse was frequent. Mortality was consistent with international cohorts. To our knowledge, this is the largest Brazilian EGPA cohort reported to date, helping to better characterize the profile of patients with this vasculitis in Brazil.

P-045

Monitoring disease activity in EGPA: a scoping review

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare vasculitis characterized by eosinophilic inflammation, asthma, and often Anti Neutrophil Cytoplasmic Antibody (ANCA) positivity. Monitoring disease activity is essential given its relapsing course and the need to minimize immunosuppression. However, validated tools specifically tailored to EGPA remain scarce, as most existing instruments were developed for other ANCA-associated vasculitides. This review aims to systematically evaluate current methods, biomarkers, imaging studies or other procedures to monitor disease activity in EGPA.

Methods: A systematic scoping review of PubMed was conducted for studies published between 2005 and March 2025. The studies were considered eligible if they included ≥ 5 EGPA patients. Case reports, reviews, and non-English publications were excluded. Data extraction covered study design, patient characteristics, definitions of remission/relapse, biomarkers or imaging tools, key findings.

Results: Of 874 records screened, 59 studies met inclusion criteria. Clinical studies frequently adopted MIRRA trial definitions of remission (Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score, BVAS=0, prednisone ≤ 4 mg/day), but criteria varied across studies, with the most adopted secondary endpoints being oral glucocorticoid sparing, changes in eosinophil count and in pulmonary function. Biomarker investigations explored inflammation markers, eosinophil counts, eosinophil-related proteins, immunoglobulin subclasses, cytokines, but none achieved consistent reliability in distinguishing active from inactive disease. Imaging and procedures included pulmonary function tests, high-resolution CT, FeNO, echocardiography, OCT-angiography, and cardiac MRI. Among these, cardiac MRI demonstrated high sensitivity in detecting subclinical fibrosis and inflammation, though prognostic implications remain debated. No single marker or tool was validated for routine monitoring.

Conclusions: Current monitoring of EGPA relies primarily on clinical assessment and BVAS, which insufficiently capture systemic and organ-specific activity. Promising biomarkers and advanced imaging techniques warrant further validation. Future research should prioritize harmonizing definitions of remission and relapse, distinguishing systemic from organ-specific activity, and integrate clinical, biomarker, and imaging approaches to develop EGPA-specific monitoring strategies.

P-046

Clinical and prognostic differences between male and female patients with giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a systemic vasculitis affecting adults over 50 years. Women often show stronger inflammatory responses and higher relapse rates, while men more frequently develop cranial ischemic events. We investigated how sex impacts disease phenotype, treatment response, and long-term outcomes in GCA.

Methods: Retrospective cohort of GCA patients diagnosed between January 1999 and March 2025 at a tertiary rheumatology centre. Categorical and continuous variables were compared using appropriate tests. Multivariable logistic and linear regression assessed associations with clinical and laboratory parameters. Time-to-event outcomes (relapse, GC suspension, mortality) were evaluated using Kaplan–Meier and Cox regression.

Results: A total of 231 patients were included (64.5% female, n=149), mean age at diagnosis 74.2±8.5 years. In multivariable models, females had higher ESR (B -9.72, p<0.001) and lower haemoglobin (B 0.77, p<0.001).

Median follow-up was 36.0 months (IQR 66.3). Females had more relapses (74.4% vs 54.0%, p=0.005), higher cumulative GC doses (12,173.2±7432.4 vs 9730.3±7411.2 mg, p=0.040), and longer follow-up (46.5 vs 23.5 months, p<0.001). Restricting to the first two years, sex differences were no longer significant. In adjusted Cox regression, male sex was associated with a lower hazard of GC suspension (HR 0.45, p=0.004), reflecting earlier discontinuation in females. Seventy-three patients died (38 women, 35 men). Mortality was higher in men overall (42.7% vs 25.5%, p=0.004) and within two years (20.7% vs 7.4%, p=0.001). Kaplan–Meier analysis confirmed a survival difference (p=0.034). However, in adjusted Cox models, sex was not an independent predictor of mortality (HR 1.50, p=0.359).

Conclusions: Women with GCA exhibited stronger inflammatory profiles and higher relapse frequency and GC exposure; however, these differences lost significance after adjusting for follow-up time. Men had higher mortality and were less likely to discontinue GC. Sex influences disease expression and treatment course, but not major long-term outcomes like relapse or survival.

P-047

The Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas): 2 year follow-up data on 284 patients with GCA

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is the most common vasculitis in people over 50 years of age, with an incidence of 20 to 30 per 100,000. Most prospective data were collected from randomized controlled trials, which were limited in terms of cohort size and follow-up time. The GeVas registry is the first prospective registry study for vasculitis in German-speaking countries, allowing the evaluation of this rare disease in a large patient cohort. Baseline data, including follow-up data up to two years of GCA patients are presented here.

Methods: GeVas is a prospective, web-based, and multicentre registry documenting organ manifestations, organ damage, and treatment regimens for various forms of vasculitis.

Results: After a total of six years, 284 GCA-patients were enrolled in the GeVas registry. 55,4% were female (154/278) and 44,6% were male (124/278). The median age of the patients at the time of recruitment was 68 years (IQR:57;78). Seventy-three percent (192/277) were enrolled in the registry due to a newly diagnosed GCA, and 27% (75/277) due to a relapse resulting in a change of treatment. At the initial assessment, most patients (90,1%, 246/273) described general symptoms. Ocular symptoms were reported by 34,8% of patients (95/273). Cranial symptoms were documented in 79,5% of cases (217/273).

At initial assessment, all patients (279/279) were receiving immunosuppressive treatment, of whom 98,9% received prednisolone (276/279), 11,8% cyclophosphamide (33/279), 20,4% methotrexate (57/279), and 49,5% tocilizumab (138/279). At three months, 61,3% of patients (100/163); at one year 87% of patients (95/109) and after 2 years 92,8% (77/83) of patients were in remission. During the follow up 10% of the patients (27/270) had a relapse.

Conclusions: Our study cohort showed similar data compared to other studies regarding demographics, clinical manifestations, and diagnostics. However, our data differed from those of previous studies regarding treatment regimens.

P-048

Ultrasound findings of joint involvement in polymyalgia rheumatica associated with giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) often co-exists with giant cell arteritis (GCA). We previously reported that joint inflammation in PMR is characterized mainly by tenosynovitis, tendinitis, and ligamentitis, rather than large-joint synovitis. However, the musculoskeletal ultrasound (MSUS) features of PMR associated with GCA remain unclear. This study investigated whether joint involvement patterns differed between GCA-associated PMR (GCA-PMR) and isolated PMR.

Methods: Between 2016 and 2024, we enrolled 20 patients with GCA-PMR and 40 patients with isolated PMR. The clinical background and MSUS findings were systematically compared. The examined sites included the long head of the biceps tendon (LHBT), supraspinatus, subscapularis, subacromial–subdeltoid bursa, glenohumeral joint, suprapatellar bursa, medial/lateral tibiofemoral joint, medial/lateral collateral ligaments (MCL, LCL), and popliteus tendon. Gray scale (GS) and power Doppler (PD) signals were semiquantitatively scored (0–3). Positive findings were defined as a GS ≥ 2 or PD ≥ 1 .

Results: Baseline characteristics, CRP/ESR, and MMP-3 did not differ significantly between groups. In GCA-PMR, 80% met the 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria, and the remainder were diagnosed using MRI or FDG-PET. Vascular ultrasound showed temporal artery halo signs in 40% of patients and axillary arteritis in 60%, while FDG-PET revealed aortic uptake in 70%. Neither group exhibited pure synovitis of the shoulder or knee. Tendinous and ligamentous lesions were present in both groups but were significantly less frequent in GCA-PMR (LHBT 63% vs. 98%, $p = 0.0009$; PopT 50% vs. 95%, $p = 0.0001$; MCL 26% vs. 58%, $p = 0.0297$; LCL 10% vs. 73%, $p < 0.0001$). The median total GS and PD scores were lower in GCA-PMR (GS 2.5 [IQR 1–4.5]; PD 1.5 [IQR 0.5–4]) than in isolated PMR (GS 8.0 [IQR 6–10]; PD 13.0 [IQR 10.5–16]).

Conclusions: MSUS indicated that joint inflammation in GCA-associated PMR was milder than that in isolated PMR, suggesting distinct disease activity profiles.

P-050

Variability in the reporting of diagnostic US in GCA: a quality improvement project in Australian Healthcare

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Background/Aims: Ultrasound (US) is recommended as the first-line investigation for suspected giant cell arteritis (GCA). Integration of US into fast-track clinics has transformed GCA management and improved outcomes across Europe. The technique remains heavily user dependant and is relatively novel in Australia. Variability in operator technique and reporting may limit its utility in Australia. This audit aimed to evaluate variability in the reporting of US for suspected GCA across Australia.

Methods: This clinical audit has been approved as a quality assurance activity (63119). US scans for suspected GCA from three Australian tertiary hospitals reported between 1st January and 31st December 2024 were obtained. Sources included 2 fast-track GCA clinics (FT) and 3 tertiary hospital radiology departments (RD). There are no current recommendations on the reporting of US in GCA. Reports were assessed against European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (EULAR) recommendations for the acquisition of US for suspected GCA, focusing on clinical indications, anatomical clarity, vessel descriptors, measurements, and clinical correlation.

Results: Results significantly varied between FT (37 reports) and RD (75 reports). FT clinics more commonly documented clinical indications (100% vs 86.6%). RD reports more commonly provided details regarding specific vessels imaged (78.6% vs 20.5%), although mislabelling occurred. FT clinics more commonly included axillary arteries (37.8% vs 8%). Both groups primarily described the “halo sign,” though wall descriptors varied. RD reports more frequently documented compressibility, and some included non-standard descriptors such as “tenderness on probe.” Wall thickness measurements were uncommon (FT 5.4% vs 28.0%). Only one FT report included an OMERACT GCA Ultrasound Score (OGUS). FT clinicians always gave clinical recommendations.

Conclusions: This first Australian audit highlights substantial variability in US reporting for suspected GCA, with inconsistencies in terminology, omission of key findings, and absence of structured conclusions. Development of standardised reporting standards may reduce variability in reporting.

P-051

Prognostic significance of vascular imaging features in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Imaging methods like Vascular Ultrasound (VUS) and FDG-Positron Emission Tomography (FDG-PET) have become cornerstone in the diagnosis giant cell arteritis (GCA). However, their impact on disease management and prognosis remains uncertain. We aimed to evaluate the prognostic significance of vascular imaging features in GCA.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed all patients in our prospective vasculitis cohort diagnosed with GCA up to September 2025. The institutional imaging protocol includes VUS and subsequent FDG-PET for all patients. GCA was classified as cranial (C-GCA) when limited to cranial arteries or large-vessel (LV-GCA) when extracranial large vessels were involved. The primary outcome was GCA relapse, defined by recurrence of symptoms with elevated inflammatory markers and/or imaging evidence of vascular inflammation. Relapse predictors were analysed using Cox proportional hazards models.

Results: Fifty-six patients were included (median age 72 [66–80] years; 52% female). Fifteen (27%) had C-GCA and 41 (73%) LV-GCA. Median follow-up was 32 (16–53) months. All patients received corticosteroids (mean starting dose 42.0 ± 17.8 mg), 64% tocilizumab, and 25% methotrexate or leflunomide. At last follow-up, 62% remained on corticosteroids. Twenty patients (36%) relapsed, with an incidence rate of 0.13 per year (95% CI 0.085–0.21). LV-GCA was independently associated with increased relapse risk compared with C-GCA (HR 5.1, 95% CI 1.2–22.8; $p=0.034$, age-adjusted). Among 22 patients with follow-up FDG-PET (median 13 months after baseline), 6 (27%) had normal vascular uptake and 16 (73%) had persistent vascular uptake (score ≥ 1). Relapse was less frequent in those with normal uptake (1/6, 17%) compared with non-normal uptake (10/16, 63%; $p=0.048$).

Conclusions: LV-GCA was associated with a higher risk of relapse. Persistent vascular FDG uptake may also predict relapse, suggesting that imaging stratification could inform long-term management. These findings require validation in larger cohorts.

P-052

18F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography imaging assessment within a randomized controlled trial in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: A recent randomized controlled trial (RCT) failed to demonstrate efficacy of guselkumab to treat giant cell arteritis (GCA). This ancillary study compared FDG-PET imaging collected within the trial to clinical and laboratory-based assessments of disease activity.

Methods: Patients with new-onset or relapsing GCA were randomized to guselkumab or placebo plus tapered glucocorticoids in an international, multicentre RCT. FDG-PET was performed at the baseline visit prior to randomization and repeated at disease flare or the Week 52 visit (clinical remission off glucocorticoids). FDG-PET scans were interpreted as active or inactive by two readers and the PET Vascular Activity Score (PETVAS) was calculated to quantify arterial FDG uptake. FDG-PET findings were compared to clinical assessment, acute phase reactants, and glucocorticoid use at each visit.

Results: Baseline FDG-PET scans were interpreted as active vasculitis in 28 (55%) of 51 patients. FDG-PET activity at enrolment was not associated with clinical symptoms, acute phase reactants, or risk of flare. Younger age (70 vs 76 years; $p=0.03$), and female sex (89% vs 48%, $p<0.01$) were significantly associated with increased FDG-PET activity. There were no differences in prior glucocorticoid dose (median 780mg) or duration (median 23 days) between patients with baseline active versus inactive FDG-PET scans. FDG-PET scans were active in 17/21 (81%) during clinical flare and in 14/20 (70%) at Week 52. Subsets of patients had persistently active ($n=21$) or inactive ($n=9$) PET scans at all timepoints, independent of clinical assessment.

Conclusions: Vascular FDG-PET activity may be discordant with clinical assessment, particularly in subsets of patients with GCA. Imaging-based outcome measures should remain exploratory in future therapeutic trials.

P-053

Clinical outcomes of patients with cancer and incidental large-vessel 18-FDG uptake on PET/CT

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Background/Aims: Incidental FDG uptake in large-vessels has been noted on 18-FDG-PET/CT in patients with cancer. This has been variably thought to be LVV by rheumatologists and often ignored by oncologists. 18-FDG-PET/CT has never undergone formal validation to OMERACT standards for the diagnosis of LVV. We therefore do not know if this uptake is false positive. We attempt to understand the noise in the signal.

Methods: We reviewed the notes of consecutive patients undergoing 18-FDG-PET/CT over 10-years (2011-2020) for suspected cancer. For patients with cancer and large-vessel uptake, we noted the type of cancer, clinical outcome at 12 months, and the intention to treat as LVV.

Results: Between 2011-2020, 17 patients had a cancer and 18-FDG large-vessel uptake. Their median (IQR) age was 72.0 (3.0). 12 were male. The cancers were - 5 gastric, 6 lung, 2 lymphoma, 1 ENT, 1 breast, 1 renal, 1 melanoma. Vascular territories involved included - 13 thoracic-aorta, 3 abdominal-aorta, 7 immediate aortic branches (carotid, vertebral, subclavian, axillary, inferior mesenteric, common iliac), and 3 scans did not specify the extent of involvement. The median (IQR) SUV if specified (n=5) was 3.0 (0.3). All patients received cancer treatment (surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy or combination). 2 chemotherapy regimens included steroids. At 12 months, 4 patients had died of their cancer, 2 were receiving treatment, 2 palliative treatment and 9 in remission. 1/17 (5.9%) patients were treated as having LVV based on previous history of PMR. None of the other 16 suffered complications of untreated vasculitis.

Conclusions: In most cases physicians did not feel that incidental large-vessel uptake on 18-FDG-PET/CT represented vasculitis. To our knowledge, this is the first study reporting outcomes of incidental large-vessel uptake of 18-FDG in the context of a cancer. 18-FDG-PET/CT may not be as specific for LVV as has been conventionally accepted.

P-054

Direct comparison of the diagnostic performance of four imaging modalities in patients diagnosed with giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: This study directly compares the diagnostic performance of colour Doppler ultrasound (CDUS), fluor-18-deoxyglucose positron emission tomography computed tomography (FDG-PET/CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and contrast enhanced CT in Japanese patients diagnosed with giant cell arteritis (GCA).

Methods: 37 patients were diagnosed with GCA in our institution from April 2016 to July 2025. We retrospectively collected data from these patients and compared the prevalence of abnormal findings of each modality. Imaging results of whole body FDG-PET/CT, cranial MRI, contrast enhanced CT were evaluated by diagnostic radiologists, CDUS were performed and evaluated by experienced rheumatologists in the field of GCA. The temporal, facial, occipital, maxillary arteries were defined as cranial arteries, the aorta, axillary, subclavian, vertebral, carotid, arteries were defined as extracranial arteries. Stratification for GCA subtype was performed according to results of all four modalities.

Results: Among the 37 patients, CDUS, whole body FDG-PET/CT, MRI, and contrast enhanced CT were performed in 89.1%, 94.5%, 37.8%, and 70.2%, respectively. The prevalence of abnormal findings were 74.3% for CDUS, 76.9% for FDG-PET/CT, 42.8% for MRI, and 45.5% for contrast enhanced CT. The prevalence of cranial and extracranial lesions detected by CDUS, FDG/PET-CT, MRI, and contrast enhanced CT was 47.1%/60.0%, 11.5%/76.9%, 31.6%/61.5%, and 15.0%/55.6%. 5 patients had isolated cranial GCA, 23 patients had isolated extracranial GCA, and 9 patients had both cranial and extracranial arteries involved.

Conclusions: CDUS, FDG-PET/CT had a higher prevalence of abnormal findings, compared to contrast enhanced CT and MRI. CDUS was able to detect more cranial artery involvement, whereas FDG-PET/CT was able to detect more extracranial artery involvement. In our institutional cohort, the proportion of isolated extracranial GCA was observed to be higher than in previous reports.

P-055

Imaging associates of histological inflammation in patients with Takayasu arteritis

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Introduction/Aims: There is an unmet need to understand the correlation of histological activity and vessel wall imaging abnormality in patients with Takayasu Arteritis(TAK). We aimed to determine the prognostic value and association of imaging abnormalities with histopathological inflammation in TAK.

Methods: Details of patients with TAK from 2015-2025, who had arterial tissue retrieved during aortic valve/aneurysm repair surgery were retrospectively recorded. Those who had undergone PET-CT/CT-angiogram within 3-months pre-procedure were included. Surgical biopsies were reviewed by experienced pathologist. Area-wise association of histological inflammation and imaging characteristics, with post-surgery complications and long-term imaging progression were analysed using non-parametric tests.

Results: Among 15 patients(10 females, mean age 28.9 ± 8.7 years, disease duration 9[IQR:14] months), 10(66.7%) had evidence of active/chronic inflammation in arterial wall biopsies. Activity on imaging were noted with contrast enhancement on CT-angiograms in 4 of 12 scans and PET uptake on 18FDG-PET/CT in 3 (total 4 scans). All patients with imaging evidence of inflammation showed histological inflammation. PET-activity and CT contrast-enhancement had sensitivity and specificity of 66.7% and 100%, with 50% and 75% NPV respectively for detecting inflammation. Imaging inflammation was associated with biopsy inflammation($p=0.042$) and granuloma/giant cells in biopsy ($p=0.044$). Histopathology revealed chronic changes including intimal fibrosis/ulceration in 10 cases, and adventitial sclerosis in 12 cases.

There was no association between pre-operative CRP/ESR values and histological inflammation or PET uptake/CT-enhancement in ascending-aortic imaging.

Despite histological inflammation, 7/10(70%) had good procedural outcomes during follow-up. In contrast, 1(25%) of patients without inflammation had progression of aneurysm after surgery. Ascending aortic wall thickening($n=9$) was the only imaging parameter which trended to be associated with good surgical outcomes($p=0.052$).

Conclusions: CTA and 18-FDG-PET/CT had a sensitivity and specificity of 66.7% and 100% respectively for detecting arterial wall inflammation in aneurysmal TAK. Histological or imaging activity did not associate with poor surgical outcomes.

P-056

Does the combined arteritis damage score (CARDS) in the diagnosis of Takayasu arteritis predict prognosis and need for biologic therapy?

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a chronic large-vessel vasculitis in which prognosis varies widely. Established activity scores such as ITAS or acute-phase reactants (CRP, ESR) lack predictive value for long-term outcomes. The Combined Arteritis Damage Score (CARDS) was developed for large-vessel vasculitis, but its prognostic utility has not been assessed. This study investigated the value of CARDS and wall thickness (WT) at diagnosis in predicting the need for biologic therapy in TAK.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 25 TAK patients fulfilling ACR 1990 criteria and followed for ≥ 18 months (median age 31 years; F/M: 21/4). All underwent baseline CTA/MRA scored blindly by a rheumatologist and interventional radiologist. CARDS (stenosis, occlusion, aneurysm/dilatation), WT (present/absent), and modified CARDS (mCARDS = CARDS + WT) were calculated. Patients were divided by biologic treatment (BT, n=15) versus non-biologic (non-BT, n=10). ROC analysis assessed predictive performance.

Results: Demographics and activity indices (ITAS, CRP, ESR) did not differ between groups. However, CARDS, WT, and mCARDS scores were significantly higher in the BT group: CARDS median 4.5 vs. 1.4 ($p=0.003$), WT 7 vs. 1.5 ($p<0.001$), mCARDS 11.4 vs. 4 ($p<0.001$). Mild and moderate/severe stenosis and WT were significantly enriched in BT patients (all $p\leq 0.03$). The most frequently involved regions were subclavian and common carotid arteries. ROC analysis showed strong predictive value: AUC 0.748 (CARDS), 0.837 (WT), and 0.847 (mCARDS), all $p<0.0001$. Optimal cut-offs predicted future biologic use with high sensitivity/specificity (e.g., mCARDS ≥ 8.2 : 75% sensitivity, 83% specificity). Inter-reader reliability was excellent ($\kappa>0.98$).

Conclusions: CARDS, WT, and especially mCARDS at diagnosis provide robust prognostic information in TAK. While traditional activity scores and acute-phase markers failed to differentiate groups, higher CARDS/mCARDS values strongly predicted the need for biologic therapy. These easily applicable imaging-based scores may guide early risk stratification, closer follow-up, and timely escalation to biologics, potentially preventing irreversible vascular damage. Validation in larger, multi-ethnic cohorts is warranted.

P-057

Do surrogate markers replace positron emission tomography activity in the assessment of patients with Takayasu arteritis?

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Background/Aims: Assessing disease activity is a challenge in Takayasu arteritis (TAK), since patients thought to be in remission may present progressive disease. The aim of this study is to evaluate the association between positron emission tomography (PET) activity in asymptomatic patients and those with nonspecific symptoms of disease activity and serum cytokines, pentraxin 3 (PTX3), as well as with signs of arterial inflammation detected by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) angiography.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted. TAK patients underwent clinical assessment and PET-MRI. Serum PTX3 and the following cytokines were measured: tumour necrosis factor (TNF) α , interleukin (IL)-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-1ra, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-13, IL-17A, IL-18, interferon (IFN) γ , and macrophage colony-stimulating factor (M-CSF).

Results: A total of 59 patients were included in three groups: active disease (n=12), uncertain disease activity (i.e., fatigue or elevation of inflammatory tests) (n=18), and clinical remission (n=29). PET activity frequency was: 66.7%, 33.3% and 10.3% in each group. Patients were divided into three groups: active disease (n=12) (group 1), PET activity in patients with uncertain disease activity or in remission (n=9) (group 2), and absent PET activity in patients without active disease (n=38) (group 3). Arterial wall inflammation was more frequent in group 2 than in group 3 (p<0.0001) and in group 1 compared to group 3 (p=0.007), but no differences were found between groups 1 and 2 (p=0.158). Serum PTX3 levels were associated with clinical disease activity (group 1) but not with PET activity (groups 2 and 3) (p=0.023). In the multivariate analysis, vessel wall inflammation was a predictor of PET activity [odds ratio=67.8 (95% confidence interval: 5.4-847.9); p=0.001].

Conclusions: PET activity had a strong association with inflammation in the arterial wall by MRI angiography, but not with serum biomarkers. Serum PTX3 levels were associated with clinical activity in TAK.

P-058

Retinal optical coherence tomography as a biomarker of microvascular dysfunction and disease activity in large vessel vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Microvascular dysfunction is important in the initiation and propagation of inflammation in large vessel vasculitis (LVV). Reliable detection of these changes might allow earlier identification of disease and inform disease activity. Retinal optical coherence tomography (OCT) rapidly and non-invasively evaluates the eye's microvasculature which may be affected in systemic diseases such as LVV. Here, we examined the relationship between LVV disease activity and retinal OCT in a prospective clinical study.

Methods: We compared OCT metrics – including retinal thickness, macular volume, and choroidal thickness - between adult patients with active LVV and age - and sex-matched healthy subjects. LVV patients underwent interval OCT imaging after >6 months. Additionally, we evaluated associations between OCT metrics and clinical, serological, and imaging-based markers of LVV disease activity.

Results: Twenty-five patients with LVV and 25 matched healthy subjects were recruited. Compared to healthy subjects, patients with active LVV had a thinner retina and choroid and reduced macular volume ($P<0.05$ for all). In those with LVV, treatment-induced disease remission reversed choroidal thinning at most macular locations assessed ($P<0.01$). We observed significant correlations between choroidal thickness and both positron emission tomography/magnetic resonance imaging (PET/MRI)-derived and serological (angiopoietin-2, osteopontin, soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1) markers of LVV disease activity ($P<0.05$).

Conclusions: Patients with active LVV have chorioretinal thinning compared to matched healthy subjects likely reflecting systemic microvascular dysfunction. This reverses with successful disease treatment. OCT metrics also link to novel imaging and serological measures of LVV disease activity. Together, these findings support retinal OCT as a feasible biomarker for assessing and tracking disease activity in LVV, warranting validation in larger cohorts.

P-059

Biological therapies may improve the long-term outcomes of vascular interventions in patients with Takayasu arteritis: a multicentre retrospective study

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Background/Aims: In patients with Takayasu arteritis (TAK), inflammation of the vessel wall can lead to the development of segmental stenosis, occlusion, dilation, and/or aneurysm formation. Vascular interventions may be required in the presence of symptomatic signs of arterial stenosis and severe aneurysm. This study aimed to evaluate outcomes and complications of vascular interventions in patients with TAK.

Methods: Patients who underwent vascular interventions before and after the diagnosis of TAK from eight tertiary hospitals were evaluated retrospectively. The indications for vascular interventions, the stage of the disease, the type of vascular intervention, early and late results, and complications were recorded. Restenosis was evaluated when patients were symptomatic or according to the results of imaging studies performed for any reason.

Results: A total of 119 patients with 201 lesions were included (185 stenotic/occlusive, 16 aneurysms/dissections). The most common indication was limb claudication (36%). Among the procedures, 61.2% (n=123) were performed while receiving immunosuppressive therapy following the diagnosis of TAK. Procedures comprised stent placement (57.7%), balloon angioplasty (16.4%), TEVAR/EVAR (2%), bypass grafting (21.9%), and endarterectomy (2%). Early success rate was 91.5%. During follow-up, restenosis occurred in 43.7% of stenotic lesions, with a median time of 14.5 months. Rates were lower in procedures performed after diagnosis compared to before, though not statistically significant (45% vs 55%; p=0.19). Interventions during active disease had similar restenosis rates compared to inactive disease (45% vs 38%; p=0.5). Notably, patients receiving biologic therapy at the time of intervention had significantly reduced restenosis (30% vs 51%; p=0.04). Major complications occurred in 3% of endovascular and 12% of surgical procedures.

Conclusions: Vascular interventions can be performed safely in patients with Takayasu arteritis. The use of biological therapies was associated with lower restenosis rates, suggesting a positive long-term effect and support their use in managing patients undergoing vascular procedures.

P-060

The impact of aneurysm presence on the course of Takayasu arteritis: a retrospective tertiary centre experience

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a chronic large-vessel vasculitis characterized by stenosis, occlusion, dilatation, and aneurysm formation, which may cause severe cardiovascular complications and mortality. This study compared the clinical, laboratory, angiographic features, and outcomes of TAK patients with and without aneurysms.

Methods: A total of 231 TAK patients from Marmara University Rheumatology Clinic were retrospectively analysed underwent angiographic imaging at diagnosis, and aneurysms were confirmed by an independent radiologist. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, treatment, and outcome data were comparatively evaluated.

Results: Aneurysms were detected in 38 patients (16.4%), with 52 lesions identified. The most common localization was the ascending aorta (44%, n=23). Lesions were predominantly fusiform (81%), and 31.5% of patients had multiple aneurysms. All were present at diagnosis. No new aneurysm developed during follow-up. Compared with the non-aneurysm group, patients more often had type 5 angiographic pattern, aortic regurgitation (28% vs 15%; p=0.023), and greater use of biologics (55.3% vs 37.6%; p=0.045). In contrast, limb claudication (62% vs 39%; p=0.015) and neurological symptoms (40% vs 18%; p=0.013) were more common in patients without aneurysms. Baseline ITAS scores, cumulative steroid dose, number of relapses, and last-visit VDI scores did not differ significantly between the groups. Surgery was performed in eight patients (21%): five underwent bypass grafting and/or aortic valve replacement for ascending aortic aneurysm with valve involvement, one had a bypass for suprarenal abdominal aneurysm, and two underwent thoracic or abdominal endovascular repair. Major complications occurred in 50%, including postoperative death, pericardial effusion requiring reoperation, graft leak, and cerebrovascular event. Median follow-up was 53.5 vs 66 months in aneurysmal and non-aneurysmal groups, with higher mortality in the aneurysmal group (18.4% vs 7.7%).

Conclusions: Aneurysmal involvement occurs in 16.4% of TAK patients, typically early in the disease course, and is associated with a higher frequency of aortic regurgitation, increased use of biologic agents, and increased mortality. TAK patients with aneurysms at diagnosis represent a high-risk subgroup requiring close monitoring and aggressive management.

P-061

Neurological involvement and elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate at baseline predict future relapses in the Takayasu Arteritis Inception Cohort

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Background/Aims: We aimed to present the results of a Takayasu Inception Cohort established for the long-term prospective follow-up of newly diagnosed Takayasu arteritis (TAK) patients.

Methods: Patients who were diagnosed with TAK within the previous 12 months were included. Patient data were recorded in the Takayasu Arteritis Registry, an international electronic database. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to assess the discriminatory power of the relapse prediction model. An ROC curve was constructed using the probabilities obtained from the model.

Results: The study included 239 TAK patients from 20 tertiary centres in Turkey (age:43.0±13.2 years, F/M:199/40). The median symptom duration at diagnosis was 12 (range:0-408) months. According to angiographic classification, 55% of the study group had type I and 20% had type V disease. One hundred ninety-nine (83%) patients received corticosteroid (CS) treatment at the time of diagnosis. In addition, 60% received methotrexate, 19% azathioprine, 5% cyclophosphamide, 4% leflunomide, and 3% mycophenolate mofetil.

147 patients (62%) had >3 months follow-up (mean 51.7±40.7 months). Remission was observed in 91% of patients. At least one relapse was observed in 34% of these patients. Neurological involvement (OR:3.78, 95%CI:1.26–11.34, p=0.018) and baseline ESR (OR:1.02, 95%CI:1.001–1.004, p=0.015) were factors associated with relapse in logistic regression analysis. There was also a trend toward significance for ophthalmologic involvement (OR:10.61, p=0.06). The variables included in the nomogram model (baseline ESR, neurological and ophthalmologic involvement), had moderate discriminatory power (AUC=0.655) in predicting the risk of relapse. The mortality rate during follow-up was 4.8%. During follow-up, biologic agents were selected in 37 (25%) patients. Radiographic progression was observed in 24 (18%) patients.

Conclusions: Long-term follow-up of our Takayasu arteritis inception cohort demonstrates that 30% of patients develop relapses within 4 years of diagnosis despite immunosuppressive therapy. Baseline ESR and neurological involvement were identified as independent predictors of relapse.

P-062

Assessment of sarcopenia in patients with Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: We aimed to evaluate the impact of ischemia and inflammation on muscle mass and function, as well as their effect on secondary sarcopenia in Takayasu Arteritis (TAK).

Methods: 103 patients diagnosed with TAK according to the ACR 1990 criteria and age and sex matched 75 healthy volunteers were included. The muscle strength of the participants was assessed using handgrip and chair stand tests, while muscle mass was evaluated through two distinct methods: bioelectrical impedance analysis(BIA) and ultrasonography(US). Prevalence of sarcopenia was defined using the updated European Working Group on Sarcopenia in Older People (EWGSOP2) and International Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine (ISarcoPRM) algorithms.

Results: According to ISarcoPRM algorithm, sarcopenia was observed in 30(29.13%) of the TAK group and 9(12%) of the healthy control (HC) group($p < 0.001$). Based on EWGSOP2 algorithm, 61 participants (59.2%) in the TAK group were diagnosed with sarcopenia, while 20 participants (26.67%) in the HC group were sarcopenic ($p < 0.001$).

The agreement between EWGSOP2 and ISarcoPRM algorithms was poor ($p = 0.062$ $k = 0.153$ in kappa analysis). Muscle strength assessments were found to be lower in the patient group compared to the HC group ($p < 0.001$). There was no significant difference between the two groups in muscle mass according to measurement obtained by the BIA method. However, quadriceps muscle thickness (MT) and the Sarcopenia Thigh Adjusted Ratio (STAR) index were significantly lower in the TAK group ($p < 0.001$). In ultrasonographic measurements, muscle mass was found to be reduced in the extremity with arterial involvement ($p = 0.035$).

Conclusions: Muscle strength and muscle mass were observed to be significantly reduced in patients with TAK. Sarcopenia should be considered as a factor influencing both quality of life and activity management in the assessment and treatment of patients with TAK, and ultrasonography may serve as a useful screening tool in this population.

P-063

Predicting neurological severe ischemic events in supra-aortic Takayasu arteritis: a multicentre study using deep learning multi-feature fusion model

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Background/Aims: Severe ischemic events (SIEs) in the nervous system are a common and life-threatening complication of Takayasu arteritis (TAK), making accurate risk prediction clinically crucial. This study aims to develop and validate a novel deep learning-based model to improve the prediction of neurologic SIEs in TAK patients.

Methods: This multi-centre study recruited 359 TAK patients with supra-aortic vessel involvements from Zhongshan Hospital Fudan University, Shanghai, China as the primary cohort (training: n=300; internal validation: n=59). An independent external validation cohort of 53 patients was enrolled from three other Chinese medical centres. A deep learning predictive model was developed by employing convolution and point cloud neural networks to automatically extract vascular wall and morphological features, respectively, from magnetic resonance angiography images. These imaging-derived features were subsequently fused with features of clinical information processed by a foundation model, to construct a multi-feature fusion prediction model. The model's performance was evaluated by the C-index, hazard ratio (HR), Kaplan Meier survival analysis, and time-dependent receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves.

Results: In the primary cohort, neurological SIEs occurred in 57 (15.88%) patients in the primary cohort during a median follow-up of 20 (13-48) months. The multi-feature fusion model achieved superior predictive performance (C-index: 0.86, HR: 1.86, 95%CI: 1.28-2.70), significantly outperforming for models based on individual-feature (C-index 0.67 to 0.71) or dual-feature combinations (0.75 to 0.76). Crucially, the model demonstrated robust generalization in the independent external validation cohort, achieving a C-index of 0.79 and an HR of 1.86 (1.13-3.06). Time-dependent ROC analysis further confirmed the model's sustained superiority in both cohorts.

Conclusions: This pioneering study established an accurate and robust multi-feature fusion deep learning model for predicting neurologic SIEs risk in TAK. This model provides a reliable foundation for advancing individualized risk stratification.

P-064

Artificial intelligence can discriminate polyarteritis nodosa and cutaneous arteritis based on hematoxylin-and-eosin images of skin biopsy specimens

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Background/Aims: Diseases that develop necrotizing vasculitis of cutaneous muscular arteries include polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) and cutaneous arteritis (CA). It is difficult to distinguish them based on skin biopsy findings alone. This study demonstrated that artificial intelligence (AI) can discriminate them based on skin biopsy findings and revealed where AI focuses on the image.

Methods: Ninety-three hematoxylin-and-eosin images of CA and 19 PAN images were used. Among them, 85 CA and 17 PAN images were used to train AI; thereafter, AI was challenged to classify the remaining images. The same test images were evaluated by 26 pathologists with different years of experience.

Results: AI accuracy was 75.2%, whereas that of pathologists was 42.8%. Gradient-weighted class activation mapping (Grad-CAM) indicated that AI focused on connective tissues around the affected vessels rather than the affected vessels. Twenty-two of the 26 pathologists were randomly divided into two groups of 11 each, one of which referred to Grad-CAM images and was challenged in the second-round test of images different from the first round. The accuracy significantly improved after referring to Grad-CAM images, whereas it was equivalent to the first round without referring to Grad-CAM images. In the survey after the second-round test, pathologists who referred to Grad-CAM images suggested that inflammation and fibrosis in the surrounding connective tissues in PAN might be abundant compared to CA.

Conclusions: AI may be useful for histological differentiation between PAN and CA and can help pathologists improve the ability of discriminating PAN and CA based on histological findings of skin biopsy specimens.

P-065

Changing face of polyarteritis nodosa spectrum: results of a 20-year cohort

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Background/Aims: Increased viral hepatitis vaccination and introduction of monogenic vasculitis (DADA2, VEXAS, FMF), idiopathic Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) became a very rare disease. Additionally, each subgroup can have treatments targeting different pathways. This study aims to identify the clinical characteristics and outcome of all subgroups of PAN.

Methods: Our university hospital records and Hacettepe University Vasculitis Research Center (HUVAC) database searched PAN between 2005-2025. Etiologic/genetic factors, clinical features, histopathological and radiological findings, treatment, and outcome were recorded.

Results: Among 3025 patients in registry, 120 patients have been recorded as PAN, and 39.2% were paediatric onset. Of 20 patients with cPAN, two evolved into sPAN. Distribution of patients were idiopathic PAN (n= 70), FMF-related PAN (n= 28), DADA2 (n= 16), HBV-related PAN (n= 4), VEXAS (n= 1), and MDS-PAN (n= 1). Histopathological evaluation was conducted in 83 patients, revealing findings consistent with PAN in 58 cases. Radiological features suggestive of PAN were identified in 52 patients. Median follow-up 75.5 (21-153) months and 23 patients died.

Among the 118 patients for whom treatment data were available, the majority received corticosteroids (n=112) and immunosuppressive agents as cyclophosphamide (n=58), azathioprine (n=56), colchicine (n=53), mycophenolate mofetil (n=37), methotrexate (n=13), hydroxychloroquine (n=8), IVIG (n=14), and any biologics (27.9%) 33/118. Anti-TNF agents (n=20), anti-IL-1 therapies (n=7), anti-IL-6 (n=2), and interferon-alpha (n=4). At last visit, 22 PAN patients were off treatment.

Conclusions: Genetics as well as radiologic improvements are helpful for dissecting PAN. Evolving of cPAN into sPAN observed in 10% of patients. Approximately 30% of patients ever used biologics. Distinct clinical courses, treatment responses, and outcomes across PAN subgroups highlight the necessity of precise diagnosis to inform targeted therapy.

P-066

Muscle injury patterns on magnetic resonance imaging in patients with polyarteritis nodosa

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Background/Aims: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) frequently involves skeletal muscle, particularly in the lower limbs. Characteristic findings on magnetic resonance imaging of the legs (MRI-L) have been described.

Methods: We conducted a descriptive, cross-sectional, retrospective study of patients with systemic PAN and/or PAN limited to the lower limbs who underwent MRI-L between January 2011 and December 2024. Clinical, radiological, and anatomical features were recorded, including affected structures and patterns of muscle injury (diffuse, patchy, and speckled sponge-like).

Results: Sixty patients with PAN were identified, with a mean age of 38.3 years (SD 20.21). The most common symptoms were muscle weakness (73.3%), myalgias (68.3%), and calf pain (65%). Systemic PAN was diagnosed in 82% of cases. MRI-L was performed in 45% of patients. Muscle abnormalities were present in 92.3%, most frequently gastrocnemius oedema (41.6%) and involvement of all compartments of the lower limb (33.3%). Other affected sites included the soleus (8.3%), peroneus brevis (8.3%), quadriceps femoris (8.3%), and combined gastrocnemius and peroneus involvement (4.1%). Bilateral lesions were identified in 92%. The predominant injury patterns were patchy (58.3%) and diffuse (29.2%), with no cases of speckled sponge-like pattern. Fascial involvement occurred in 15.7%. Bone abnormalities were present in 41.6%, exclusively as bone marrow oedema, most frequently in the tibia (60%).

Conclusion: Skeletal muscle involvement in PAN occurs in nearly half of patients. In this cohort, MRI-L was performed in 27 patients and detected muscle abnormalities in 92.3% of them (25/27), most commonly with patchy and diffuse patterns. The gastrocnemius and all compartments of the lower limb were the most frequently affected regions, while bone involvement was also common. These findings underscore MRI-L as a valuable non-invasive tool for characterizing myositis in PAN.

P-067

Clinical assessment of radiologically defined clinically isolated aortitis in a single centre study

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Background/Aims: Aortitis in the absence of systemic vasculitis is termed clinically isolated aortitis (CIA). Our purpose was to describe a cohort of patients with CIA and compare characteristics with aortitis associated with rheumatic diseases.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of 32 patients with non-infectious aortitis in our centre. We analysed demographic variables, symptoms, laboratory data, imaging, treatment, outcomes, and mortality. Quantitative variables were described using percentages and medians with interquartile range (IQR).

Results: Out of 32 patients, 10 were classified as CIA and 22 had other inflammatory diseases (approx. 1:2 ratio) - fourteen had GCA, 4 had TAK, 2 with GPA, 1 each with IgG4-RD and ankylosing spondylitis, classified according to the ACR/EULAR criteria. All patients underwent PET-CT confirming isolated aortitis; none had an artery biopsy. Among the CIA patients, median duration of follow-up was 65 months (IQR 42-72). Three patients were asymptomatic, seven had constitutional symptoms (fever, weight loss, sweats, fatigue), and one reported abdominal/back pain. The diagnosis was incidental in two cases. All patients had negative infection screen and serological markers for rheumatologic conditions. Six (60%) patients had involvement of abdominal aorta only, 2 thoracic aorta, and 2 had abdominal and thoracic aortitis. Six patients (60%) were treated with Glucocorticoids (GCs) and Methotrexate, 2 with GCs alone, 1 with GCs and MMF. 1 patient had resistant disease requiring Tocilizumab. Four patients had a follow-up PET-CT imaging: 2 showed reduction in FDG avidity, 1 had a stable tracer uptake, and 1 had no evidence of persistent aortitis. All the CIA patients demonstrated improvement at follow-up (clinical/ESR/CRP)

Conclusion: Our CIA patients had male predominance, between 6th-7th decades, consistent with previous literature. Aneurysms were more common in CIA patients than GCA/TAK. There is no fixed protocol for CIA but DMARDs and glucocorticoids are helpful.

P-068

Periaortitis (retroperitoneal fibrosis): Impact of IgG4-related disease classification and immunosuppressive treatment on the clinical trajectory

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Background/Aims: A subset of periaortitis (retroperitoneal fibrosis) cases falls within the IgG4-related disease spectrum, where multidisciplinary care—particularly between urology and rheumatology—and the use of immunosuppressive agents may influence disease course and relapse risk. This study aimed to describe clinical features, treatment strategies, and predictors of relapse.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed patients from the rheumatology and urology clinics of Hacettepe University (2000–2024), including presenting manifestations, organ involvement, imaging, serum IgG4, histopathology, treatments, and surgical interventions. Relapse was defined as radiological progression or new lesions, increased acute-phase reactants, change in immunosuppression, or need for surgery.

Results: Among 64 patients (78.1% male; mean age 50.9±11.8 years), multisystem involvement was seen in 29 (45.3%). Histopathology was available in 55, of whom 45 (81.8%) were consistent with IgG4-RD. Only two patients followed solely by urology received corticosteroid monotherapy, whereas all under rheumatology or joint care were treated with corticosteroids, with additional cyclophosphamide (53.3%) or rituximab (46.7%) in some cases. Overall, 49 (76.5%) patients underwent intervention or surgery. Mean serum creatinine declined from 3.24 mg/dL (range 1.3–5.2) pre-procedure to 1.32 mg/dL (0.9–1.7) at 6th months.

Over a median follow-up of 4.5 years (IQR 8.8), relapse was documented in 21 of 63 patients (33.3%). The median relapse-free interval was 3.1 years (IQR 4.5). Elevated baseline CRP levels were significantly associated with relapse (6.3±5.9 vs. 2.7±3.3 mg/dL; p=0.04) and emerged as an independent predictor in multivariable analysis (OR=1.2; 95%CI:1.02–1.40; p=0.03). ROC analysis indicated a moderate discriminative performance of CRP for relapse prediction (AUC=0.66; 95% CI:0.48–0.85; p=0.08). The optimal threshold was identified as 3.7 mg/dL, with a sensitivity of 60% and specificity of 82%.

Conclusion: Nearly half of periaortitis (RPF) patients had additional organ involvement, and histopathology confirmed IgG4-RD in over 80%. Despite greater awareness and immunosuppressive use, one-third relapsed, while multidisciplinary care positively impacted outcomes.

P-069

Assessment of psychometric properties of the relapsing polychondritis disease activity index

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Background/Aims: The Relapsing Polychondritis (RP) Disease Activity Index (RPDAI) has not been extensively tested in patient cohorts. This study assessed the psychometric properties of RPDAI.

Methods: Using data from a single-centre, prospective RP cohort, we evaluated cross-sectional and longitudinal associations between the RPDAI (0-228, excluding the renal, sternoclavicular/manubriosternal chondritis, and C-reactive protein items due to missing data) and physician global assessment (PhGA, 0-10), 4-point categorical disease activity (CatDA; remission, low, medium, or high), and patient global assessment (PtGA, 0-10). Changes in PhGA and PtGA scores by ≥ 2 were considered meaningful.

Results: Among 117 patients, 76 had follow-up [5.8 months (IQR 4.3- 6.6)]. RPDAI correlated well with PhGA ($r=0.6$), but not with PtGA ($r=0.3$). Median RPDAI and PhGA were 0 (IQR 0), 0 (0-0.5) for remission ($n=25$). For low disease activity ($n=100$), RPDAI was 13 (IQR 9-22) and PhGA was 2 (IQR 2-3). For moderate/high activity, RPDAI was 22 (IQR 18-29) and PhGA 4 (IQR 4-5) ($p<0.01$). PtGA was 3 (IQR 1-3) for remission ($n=24$), 5 (IQR 3-7) for low activity ($n=93$), and 7 (IQR 4-8) for moderate-high activity ($n=50$) ($p<0.01$). In the remission group, only 3 patients reported a PtGA of 0. In longitudinal analyses, median RPDAI decreased by -9.0 (IQR -16 to 1) when CatDA decreased ($n=26$), increased by 5.9 (IQR 0.75 to 9.0) when CatDA increased ($n=8$), and remained stable in unchanged CatDA ($n=42$; -1.9; IQR -11.25 to 1.75) ($p<0.01$). Similarly, changes in RPDAI correlated significantly with changes in PhGA ($p<0.01$). Changes in PtGA were not significantly associated with RPDAI changes ($p=0.8$).

Conclusions: RPDAI correlates well with PhGA and CatDA, discriminates remission vs disease activity, and captures longitudinal changes. Correlation between RPDAI and PtGA is weaker. RPDAI has potential for use in clinical trials, but supplementation with patient-reported outcomes may be necessary.

P-070

Evolution in risk stratification for renal outcomes in ANCA-associated vasculitides using established scores and histopathological criteria in a large European cohort

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Background/Aims: Glomerulonephritis is a frequent and severe manifestation of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Prognostic models have been developed to estimate the risk of end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), most recently the ANCA renal risk score (ARRS) and the ANCA kidney risk score (AKRiS). We aimed to evaluate both scores in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) separately, in comparison with histology.

Methods: In this retrospective study, 220 biopsy-proven AAV patients (1998–2021), classified by the 2020 ACR/EULAR criteria, were analysed. Follow-up every six months documented the composite renal endpoint: death, dialysis, transplantation, or persistent ESKD (eGFR <15 ml/min/1.73 m² at ≥6 months). Risk stratification was performed by histology, ARRS, and AKRiS. Kaplan–Meier curves, log-rank tests, ROC analysis, and Harrell’s C were used.

Results: Compared to GPA, MPA biopsies showed more global sclerosis, interstitial fibrosis, and tubular atrophy. Most cases were histologically focal or mixed, transitioning mainly into low- and medium-risk AKRiS categories. Crescentic and sclerotic classes clustered in higher risk groups. Medium-risk histology frequently shifted into lower AKRiS categories. Kaplan–Meier curves showed clear endpoint stratification. ROC analysis confirmed superior prognostic performance for AKRiS (AUC 0.76) over ARRS (AUC 0.70), with consistently higher AUCs in MPA than GPA. Concordance index was high for AKRiS (C = 0.899). Compared to ARRS, 67.7% of patients remained in the same category, 24.5% were reclassified lower, and 7.7% higher.

Conclusions: AKRiS effectively predicts progression to ESKD and a broad composite renal endpoint in a large European AAV cohort, outperforming ARRS. Despite histological and clinical differences between GPA and MPA, AKRiS provided robust stratification under comparable treatment regimens.

P-071

Kidney transplant outcomes in paediatric ANCA-Associated Vasculitis patients: a retrospective review from a single-centre in Western Canada

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Background/Aims:

Anti-neutrophilic cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a rare and life-threatening paediatric autoimmune disease. Positive ANCA, either proteinase 3 (PR3-ANCA) or myeloperoxidase (MPO-ANCA), defines AAV. Paediatric AAV typically presents as pulmonary-renal syndrome with ANCA-associated necrotizing crescentic glomerulonephritis leading to rapid kidney function deterioration and eventually end-stage renal disease. In adult AAV patients, kidney transplantation is an effective renal replacement therapy. Currently, there is a paucity of data on paediatric AAV kidney transplant outcomes. This study describes transplant outcomes in paediatric AAV patients across tertiary centres in Western Canada; with this sub-study describing patients at the Alberta Children's Hospital.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study included five paediatric AAV patients who underwent kidney transplantation between 2007 and 2025. Standardized chart review assessed pre- and post-transplant outcomes.

Results: One male and four females were reviewed. Median age at diagnosis was 15.5 years (range 10.6-16.7). All were MPO-ANCA positive. Median presenting eGFR was <10mL/min/1.73m² (range 5-26). Induction therapy included pulse methylprednisolone (followed by steroid taper, n=5); rituximab (n=4) or cyclophosphamide (n=1, due to CNS involvement); and plasma exchange (n=3). Four patients required acute dialysis at diagnosis; all progressed to chronic intermittent haemodialysis and/or peritoneal dialysis. Median time from diagnosis to transplant was 11 months (range 7-28) and all were in remission. Median age at transplant was 17.6 years (range 11.5-18.3). Four patients received a living-donor kidney. Median duration of follow-up post-transplant was 23 months (range 3-36). Median eGFR at last follow-up was 102mL/min/1.73m² (range 53-112). None experienced graft loss or rejection. Significant post-transplant complications included clostridium difficile (n=1); neutropenia (n=1); and EBV-mediated pre-lymphomatous lesion (early-stage post-transplant lymphoproliferative disorder, n=1). There were no post-transplant AAV recurrences or deaths.

Conclusions: Kidney transplantation is safe and effective in our limited cohort of paediatric ANCA-AAV patients. Although post-transplant complications occurred, there were no deaths or vasculitis recurrences.

P-072

Ocular involvement in granulomatosis with polyangiitis: a single centre experience

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Background/Aims: Ocular involvement in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) varies from mild manifestations like episcleritis to vision threatening manifestations like retinal vasculitis, optic neuritis, and scleral perforation. Though some studies have reported ocular involvement in up to 50% of GPA patients, there are few that detail these in a large cohort. The objectives of this study were 1. To describe the ophthalmic manifestations and their outcomes in GPA patients. 2. To compare the systemic manifestations of the GPA patients with and without ocular involvement. 3. To compare ocular GPA patients with and without scleritis (the commonest ocular manifestation)

Methods: This was a single centre retrospective study. Demographic, clinical, laboratory and treatment details of all GPA patients were collected and ophthalmology records of all patients with ocular involvement were reviewed.

Results: 179 GPA patients were included, of whom 107 (59.8%) had ocular involvement. The most common presentations were scleritis (46.8%), episcleritis (22.3%), uveitis (13.8%) and keratitis (10.6%). Frequent ophthalmic complications were cataract, scleral melt and retinal detachment. Ocular relapses were noted in 23.9% and systemic relapses in 46.7% cases. There were 12 (11.2%) deaths in the ocular GPA cohort. Ocular GPA patients had less frequent constitutional, pulmonary and cardiac manifestations compared to GPA patients without eye involvement. There was no difference in outcome (mortality, relapse, infection, vasculitis damage index - VDI) between GPA patients with or without ocular manifestations. Ocular GPA cases with scleritis were older, more commonly presented with pain and redness, required cyclophosphamide for treatment more often, but exhibited more delayed systemic relapses with a better final VDI.

Conclusion: Ocular GPA patients had less frequent cardio-pulmonary involvement but similar outcomes compared to GPA patients without eye involvement. Patients with scleritis were older, required more aggressive immunosuppression, but fared better than patients with other kinds of ophthalmic manifestations.

P-074

Clinician views concerning the prevalence and impact of granulomas on the diagnosis, management, and outcomes of ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: It is unclear whether clinicians agree which manifestations of AAV are associated with necrotizing granulomas or if their presence affects clinical decision-making.

Methods: We surveyed physicians experienced in caring for individuals with AAV, querying: experience with AAV; beliefs concerning how granulomas affect the diagnosis, treatments, and outcomes of AAV; beliefs concerning the frequency with which granulomas are found in 36 manifestations of AAV; and degree to which granulomas change choice of induction therapy for specific manifestations of AAV. We analysed responses using descriptive statistics and multivariable linear regression.

Results: We received 142 responses from 35 countries. Responses had a median Likert response ≥ 5 on a 7-point scale (equal to 'partially agree') that granulomatous manifestations respond differently to therapy, increase risk of relapse, and increase organ damage. Four of 36 manifestations were believed to be caused by granulomas in a median of $\geq 75\%$ of cases (on a scale of 0 = never to 100 = always caused by granuloma), 19 in a median of $\leq 25\%$ of cases, and 13 in intermediate medians. The perceived degree to which granulomas caused manifestations was not associated with changes in therapy to induce remission in severe AAV (p-values 0.26 to 0.93 across scenarios).

Conclusions: Physicians experienced in vasculitis generally agree on which manifestations of AAV are and are not caused by granulomas and that granulomatous inflammation alters the natural history and treatment of AAV. However, the presence of granulomatous manifestations did not alter treatment choices to induce remission in severe AAV.

P-075

Thyroid dysfunction among patients with AAV and TAK: Is thyroid an organ involved in MPA?

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Background/Aims: We aimed to assess thyroid functions in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) and Takayasu's arteritis (TAK).

Methods: Our prospective database reviewed (2014-2024) and identified 275 cases of AAV and 223 cases of TAK. Patients without any thyroid function test were excluded. Data regarding demographics, age at diagnosis, organ involvement, treatments, comorbidities, thyroid function tests (at time of diagnosis, and during disease course), thyroid autoantibodies, and ultrasonography findings if performed, were recorded retrospectively.

Results: A total of 235 patients with AAV—GPA (n=139; 68F/71M), MPA (n=22; 15F/7M), EGPA (n=63; 37F/26M), and unclassified (n=11; 5F/6M)—and 161 patients with TAK (139F/22M) were analysed. Thyroid dysfunction preceded the diagnosis of AAV in 30 patients and TAK in 4 patients. Follow-up duration was a median of 5 years (2–8) for AAV and 7 years (4–12) for TAK. Thyroid dysfunction was observed much more in patients with MPA compared to GPA, EGPA, and TAK [14 (63.3%) of MPA patients vs 18 of (12.9%) GPA, 8 of (12.6%) EGPA, and 19 (11.8%) of TAK] (p<0.001). For the AAV group, patients with thyroid dysfunction were older at diagnosis and more frequently exhibited MPA subtype, MPO-ANCA positivity, chronic kidney disease, and renal involvement, whereas mucocutaneous and ENT involvement were less common (all p<0.05). For the TAK group, thyroid dysfunction was not associated with differences in age, clinical manifestations, or comorbidities.

Conclusions: We observed higher thyroid dysfunction compared to the VCRC data (just assessed hypothyroidism) and similar to the Cambridge and Sweden cohorts. There is no doubt that higher thyroid dysfunction in patients with MPA raises the question of whether the thyroid is an organ involved in MPA.

P-076

Central nervous system involvement in ANCA-associated vasculitis: a multicentre, retrospective cohort study from the TRVaS Database

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Background/Aims: Central nervous system (CNS) involvement of ANCA-associated vasculitides (AAV) is uncommon but represents one of the most severe complications. Data are limited to small case series. This study is aimed to describe the clinical features and outcome of patients with AAV-related CNS involvement using TRVaS (Turkish Vasculitis Study Group web-based prospective registry).

Methods: Of 701 AAV patients from eight rheumatology centres, 31 cases with CNS involvement were identified (4.42%). Clinical features, organ involvement, and imaging findings were analysed. Functional status was assessed by modified Rankin Scale (mRS).

Results: Of 31 patients, 18 (58.1%) were female, with a mean age of 54.7 ± 16.8 years. GPA was the most frequent subtype (n=26, 83.9%). CNS involvement was present at diagnosis in 24 patients (77.4%). Involvement patterns were as cerebral parenchymal lesions in 13 patients (41.9%), hypertrophic pachymeningitis (HP) in 12 (38.7%), pituitary involvement in 5 (16.1%), cranial nerve disease in 2 (6.5%), and spinal granuloma in 1 (3.2%); 2 patients (6.5%) had both HP and parenchymal disease. Headache (80.6%) was the most common symptom, followed by motor deficit (35.5%), visual impairment (29.0%), gait disturbance (19.4%), and diabetes insipidus (12.9%). Upper respiratory tract involvement (91.7% vs. 52.6%, p=0.04) and periorbital inflammatory syndrome (75.0% vs. 31.6%, p=0.02) were more common in the HP group. During a median 48 (2-228) months follow up, BVAS decreased from 17 to 4; median mRS improved from 2 (at baseline) to 0.5 at (last visit) (Table). One patient deceased due to non-vasculitic causes.

Conclusions: CNS involvement occurs mainly with patients with GPA and mostly at diagnosis. Cerebral parenchymal lesions and hypertrophic pachymeningitis are the most frequent patterns. HP is associated with upper respiratory tract and orbital disease, possibly defining a distinct subgroup. More than 90% of patients improved during follow-up, with 40% achieving complete and 50% partial response.

P-077

High burden of neurological manifestations in ANCA-associated vasculitis: data from Colombia

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) presents neurological involvement in one-third of patients, differentially affecting the central and peripheral nervous systems. We describe patients with neurological involvement in an AAV cohort.

Methods: We conducted a descriptive study of patients with neurological manifestations in an AAV cohort hospitalized in two centres in Medellín, Colombia, between January 1, 2014, and December 31, 2022.

Results: Of the 139 patients with AAV, 62 (44.6%) presented with neurological manifestations. The mean age at diagnosis was 61 years (IQR 20). Among patients with neurological involvement, GPA was diagnosed in 46.8% of cases, followed by MPA in 35.5% and EGPA in 16.1%. Peripheral neuropathy was observed in 51 out of 62 patients (82%), described as sensory neuropathy in 36 (58.1%) and multiple mononeuropathy in 23 (37.1%). Four patients (6.4%) had cranial nerve involvement, and 14 (22.6%) reported headache. Hypertrophic pachymeningitis was documented in 9 of 62 (14.5%) patients (6.5% of the total cohort), including one (1.6%) case of hypophysitis. Seizures occurred in two patients (3.2%). Twenty-eight patients (58.3%) were anti-MPO positive and 33% were anti-PR3 positive. Neurological involvement was associated with elevated ESR and CRP levels, with a mean of 94 mm/h (IQR, 56) and 12.3 mg/dl (SD, 10.5), respectively. Forty-five patients (83.3%) received glucocorticoid pulses, 44 (73.3%) were treated with cyclophosphamide, and 11 (18%) with rituximab. There was one in-hospital death (1.6%). Infectious complications developed in 18 patients (29.5%), and 11 (18%) required ICU admission.

Conclusion: In this Colombian cohort of AAV, nearly half of patients presented with neurological involvement, a higher prevalence than that reported in European cohorts. Peripheral neuropathy was the most frequent manifestation (36.7%), and hypertrophic pachymeningitis was more common than previously described. These findings highlight regional differences in the neurological spectrum of AAV and underscore the need for early recognition in Latin American patients.

P-078

Clinical profile, treatment outcomes, and predictors of progression in limited granulomatosis with polyangiitis: insights from an Indian Registry

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) may present in limited (L-GPA) or severe (S-GPA) forms. L-GPA is generally considered less severe; however, a subset progresses to severe disease. The aim of this study was to compare the clinical profile and treatment outcomes of L-GPA and S-GPA, and to identify predictors of progression from limited to severe disease.

Methods: This was a registry-based, prospective observational study. All GPA patients recruited until June 2025 were included. Patients without severe pulmonary ($\text{SpO}_2 < 92\%$ or progressive alveolar haemorrhage), renal (haematuria or creatinine $> 1.4 \text{ mg/dL}$), or life/organ-threatening manifestations in the eye, nervous system or gastrointestinal tract requiring maximal therapy like pulse steroid were classified as L-GPA; rest were classified as S-GPA [1]. Demographic, clinical, and therapeutic data were compared. Logistic regression identified predictors of relapse and progression.

Results: Among 335 ANCA vasculitis patients, 227 GPA patients with complete records were analysed: 81 (35.7%) had L-GPA and 146 (64.3%) had S-GPA. ANCA positivity was seen in 93.8% of L-GPA, with PR3-ANCA predominance (87.7%). ENT and ocular involvement were most frequent, with ocular disease significantly higher in L-GPA. Constitutional, pulmonary, renal, neurological, and musculoskeletal involvement were significantly less common in L-GPA. For L-GPA, cyclophosphamide (50.6%) was the most frequent induction agent, followed by methotrexate (27.2%) and rituximab (22.2%). Remission maintenance agents were rituximab (35%), methotrexate (32.5%) and azathioprine (28.7%). Relapses were similar, but mortality was significantly higher in S-GPA. Progression from L-GPA to S-GPA occurred in 12 patients (14.8%) after a mean of 0.31 ± 0.82 years. Relapse frequency was the strongest predictor of progression, with each flare increasing risk by 166%. Among L-GPA patients, constitutional symptoms, subglottic stenosis, and azathioprine use as a maintenance agent independently predicted relapse.

Conclusions: L-GPA comprised one-third of GPA cases. Despite lower mortality, nearly 15% progressed to severe disease.

Reference: 1. Arthritis Rheum. 2003;48(8):2299-2309.

P-079

Phenotypic distinctions between sinonasal and laryngeal manifestations of GPA

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Background/Aims: ENT manifestations of granulomatosis with polyangiitis include subglottic stenosis (SGS) and sinonasal destruction. It is unknown why such varying clinical presentations arise, or how they relate to ANCA status. We aimed to compare predictive clinical and serological factors in development of sinonasal and laryngeal presentations.

Methods: This monocentric retrospective cohort study investigated 136 GPA patients in a combined ENT-vasculitis clinic over 5-years. We identified 39 GPA patients with SGS and 97 with sinonasal disease. Multivariate analysis using binomial logistic regression assessed clinical risk factors and ANCA status in development of sinonasal or laryngeal disease.

Results: Cohort demographics demonstrated no significant differences in mean age, social deprivation, sex, obesity or ethnicity on univariate analysis. Cocaine use, smoking and gastro-oesophageal reflux disease (GORD) demonstrated significant differences and were included in a multivariate model. GORD was significantly associated with development of laryngeal disease ($p=0.006$, $OR=4.6$). Smoking was strongly associated with development of sinonasal disease ($p=0.019$, $OR=5.3$). PR3-ANCA ($p<0.001$, $OR=15.6$) and cANCA ($p<0.001$, $OR=9.17$) were found to be strongly predictive of sinonasal disease. pANCA ($p=0.016$, $OR=2.95$) and ANCA negative serology ($p=0.004$, $OR=5.23$) were predictive of laryngeal disease. MPO-ANCA was strongly associated with laryngeal disease but not significant in multivariate analysis controlling for GORD.

Conclusions: Sinonasal and laryngeal GPA have distinct risk factors and ANCA profiles and their management should be tailored appropriately. Smoking and GORD may provide local inflammatory insults that explain anatomical predilection for development of vasculitis in the nose and larynx respectively. GORD has not previously been implicated in GPA and our findings prompt consideration of adjunctive anti-acid therapy in routine management of laryngeal GPA. "Upper airway" or "Head and Neck GPA" is not single entity and organ-specific granularity is required to adequately manage and research this disease.

P-080

Cocaine associated granulomatosis with polyangiitis is phenotypically distinct

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Background/Aims: In addition to cocaine-induced sinonasal midline destructive lesions (CIMDL), there is growing suspicion of cocaine and/or adulterants mimicking or potentiating systemic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA). We aimed to determine whether GPA patients with any history of cocaine exposure (GPAC+) have a distinct phenotype by comparing sinonasal disease severity, organ involvement and ANCA serology.

Methods: This monocentric retrospective cohort study of 127 GPA patients seen over a 5-year period compared 106 GPA, 21 GPAC+ and 12 CIMDL patients. The primary outcome measure was nasal destruction score (NDS) calculated from computed tomography. Secondary outcome measures included clinically assessed sinonasal destruction, organ involvement, and ANCA serology. Kruskal-Wallis H testing and Chi-Squared tests compared ordinal and binomial variables respectively.

Results: GPAC+ and CIMDL patients have more extensive sinonasal destruction than GPA ($p < 0.05$) on imaging and direct rhinoscopy. In contrast to GPA, GPAC+ had no renal ($p < 0.001$) and rare otological involvement ($p < 0.05$). GPAC+ patients had similar levels of sinonasal, ocular and respiratory involvement. All groups were predominantly PR3+ but GPAC+ patients were more commonly (52%) p-ANCA+ ($p < 0.05$), in contrast to the typical (57%) c-ANCA pattern seen in GPA.

Conclusions: GPAC+ patients have a distinct phenotype with the pattern of organ involvement suggesting dose-dependent effect from direct exposure to cocaine or its adulterants. An atypical pattern of PR3+/pANCA expression, also seen in CIMDL, may hint at distinct pathogenesis. It is important to distinguish GPA patients with cocaine exposure as it was common (17%) and there may be important implications for response to systemic therapies.

P-081

ANCA: A prognostic tool of sinonasal destruction in GPA

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) are implicated in the pathogenesis of granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA). This is usually associated with PR3/cANCA positivity but can demonstrate alternative antibodies or none. We evaluated ANCA expression as a prognostic tool of clinically and radiologically assessed sinonasal destruction in GPA.

Methods: This monocentric retrospective cohort study investigated 127 GPA patients in a quaternary ENT vasculitis clinic over 5-years. Patients were stratified by ANCA immunofluorescence and PR3 or MPO antibody positivity. The primary outcome measure was nasal destruction score (NDS) calculated from computed tomography. Secondary outcome measures included presence of patient cosmetic concern, external deformity (saddle nose/alar collapse) and septal perforation. Logistic regression assessed ANCA status as a predictive factor for extent of destruction whilst controlling for gender, smoking and cocaine exposure.

Results: Ordinal logistic regression found odds of higher NDS on CT were significantly raised in patients with PR3 positivity (OR 4.5, 95%CI 1.2-16.6, $p < 0.05$), or p-ANCA immunofluorescence (IF) (OR 8.4, 95%CI 2.5-28, $p < 0.001$). Binomial logistic regression found p-ANCA IF predictive of patients' cosmetic concerns (OR 4.5, 95%CI 1.3-16, $p < 0.05$), external deformity on examination (OR 4.1, 95%CI 1.2-14.6, $p < 0.05$) and septal perforation (OR 15.5, 95%CI 2.8- 85.3, $p < 0.01$)

Conclusions: GPA patients with p-ANCA+ IF have far greater odds of developing destructive sinonasal disease as assessed clinically and on cross-sectional imaging. PR3+ AAV also demonstrates greater sinonasal destruction on CT. Risk stratification by ANCA status may better inform treatment decisions with regards to systemic immunosuppression, especially in ENT-limited disease with limited other markers of disease.

P-082

Characteristics and outcomes in patients with ANCA-associated interstitial lung disease without ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Previous research has described anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) associated interstitial lung disease (ILD), but understanding of outcomes in isolated ANCA-positive ILD without systemic vasculitis is limited. This study aims to characterize the features, disease course, and outcomes of isolated ANCA-associated ILD.

Methods: Adult patients at University of South Florida clinics from 2015 to 2025 with isolated ANCA-associated ILD without initial systemic manifestations of vasculitis were included in the study. ANCA positive mimics such as autoimmune hepatitis, Hepatitis C, HIV, endocarditis, and drug-induced were excluded.

Results: Thirteen patients with ANCA-associated ILD were identified with mean age 61 years old. Twelve patients had positive perinuclear ANCA (p-ANCA), ten with Myeloperoxidase antibody. Three patients had positive cytoplasmic ANCA (c-ANCA), two with Proteinase3 antibody. The ILD pattern was usual interstitial pneumonia (UIP) in nine patients, nonspecific interstitial pneumonia in three patients, and uncharacterized in one patient. At baseline, average functional vital capacity and diffusion capacity of lungs for carbon monoxide was 71% and 49% predicted, with mean change +1.9% and -2.9% respectively over the study period.

During average follow up duration of 84 months, seven patients developed systemic vasculitis, six microscopic polyangiitis and one granulomatous polyangiitis, on average 72 months after diagnosis. All newly diagnosed vasculitis patients received rituximab or cyclophosphamide. ILD remained stable or improved in six vasculitis patients, and two isolated ANCA-positive patients. Four patients passed away during the study, three with respiratory failure due to sepsis, one of unknown cause. Three deceased patients had vasculitis.

Conclusions: The most observed pattern of ANCA-associated ILD was MPO-ANCA with UIP pattern. 53% of patients with isolated ANCA-associated ILD developed systemic vasculitis, after years of latent disease, suggesting a smouldering process. Increased attention to ANCA-associated ILD patients may yield earlier detection of ANCA vasculitis, mitigating disease progression and improving outcomes.

P-083

Pulmonary manifestations of granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a group of multisystemic, relapsing autoimmune diseases associated with several pulmonary manifestations. Despite their association with increased mortality and reduced health-related quality of life, there is limited knowledge of the epidemiology and complications of pulmonary manifestations in AAV.

Methods: This study retrospectively analysed a large, multicentre longitudinal cohort of individuals with two forms of AAV, granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), followed between 2006 and 2023. Data included diagnosis, demographics, comorbidities, time of disease onset, and pulmonary manifestations of disease. Measures of both disease activity and damage were recorded. Results were summarized across disease sub-types and manifestations.

Results: Data from 1026 individuals were analysed, including 860 with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and 166 with microscopic polyangiitis (MPA). Pulmonary manifestations were seen at any time in the disease course within 81.2% of individuals: 710 (82.6%) with GPA and 123 (74.1%) with MPA. Pulmonary manifestations were reported in 644 (62.7%) of individuals at disease onset and 455 (44.3%) at the time of a relapse. Nodules and cavities, diffuse alveolar haemorrhage, and inflammatory infiltrates were the three most common manifestations across the cohort. Nodules and cavities were the most frequent manifestation seen in GPA and diffuse alveolar haemorrhage in MPA. Multiple pulmonary manifestations were seen within 42.2% of individuals and pulmonary manifestations were seen in 40.6% of episodes of relapse. 17.4% of those with pulmonary manifestations sustained pulmonary damage from their disease.

Conclusions: Pulmonary manifestations are common in both GPA and MPA, at both time of diagnosis and at relapse, and are associated with development of permanent damage. Systematic assessments of individuals with GPA/MPA for pulmonary involvement will likely improve detection of these manifestations.

P-084

Cardiac involvement in granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis – an underdiagnosed entity?

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Background/Aims: Cardiac involvement in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) may be underdiagnosed, due to an absence of standardized screening approaches and potentially a subclinical course. Our aim was to describe the extent of cardiac screening and the rates of diagnosis of any cardiac disease, cardiac vasculitis and describe the clinical phenotype of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis patients from a tertiary vasculitis centre in Cambridge, United Kingdom.

Methods: This retrospective study enrolled patients with a new diagnosis or relapse of GPA/MPA between 01/2022 and 08/2024. Demographics, clinical characteristics, laboratory and imaging studies were recorded. Patients were grouped according to 1. no cardiac disease, 2. any cardiac disease and 3. cardiac vasculitis. Groups were compared to identify risk factors for cardiac vasculitis.

Results: A total of 274 patients were enrolled, of whom 113 had MPA (41.24%) and 161 had GPA (58.76%). We identified cardiac disease in 98 (35.8%), of whom 38 (38.8%) were symptomatic. Valvular disease was the most prevalent group of cardiac diseases (20.8%). Patients with any cardiac disease were older ($p < 0.001$), more frequently male ($p = 0.001$), ANCA-myeloperoxidase (MPO) type ($p = 0.029$), had higher Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score - BVAS ($p = 0.035$), lower estimated glomerular filtration rate ($p = 0.006$) compared to the non-cardiac group. Cardiac vasculitis was detected in 46 (16.8%), with age ≤ 50 years (HR 2.587; $p = 0.026$), inpatient management (HR 2.181; $p = 0.044$) and BVAS > 8 (HR 1.612; $p = 0.007$) as independent risk factors for cardiac vasculitis. BVAS ≤ 3 (HR 0.214; $p = 0.036$) was associated with a lower risk of cardiac vasculitis. Younger inpatients with newly diagnosed GPA/MPA, high disease activity and multisystem involvement are at high risk for cardiac vasculitis.

Conclusions: Cardiac involvement in GPA and MPA is more common than previously described, often asymptomatic and without screening may be underdiagnosed. Our findings confirm the importance of cardiac screening in asymptomatic patients.

P-085

Cardiac involvement in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis – a single centre retrospective observational study

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Background/Aims: Cardiac involvement is a major cause of mortality in patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA). There are limited data on long-term outcomes.

Methods: Single centre retrospective observational study assessing outcomes of patients diagnosed with EGPA and cardiac involvement between March 2007-May 2023. Data presented as median (interquartile range, IQR).

Results: 24 patients with cardiac involvement are included. Median follow-up was 44 months (IQR 33-112). 22/24 (92%) had cardiac involvement at time of EGPA diagnosis. Cardiac symptoms were reported in 14/24 (58%), with one case each of cardiogenic shock and cardiac arrest. Abnormalities were detected in 14/20 electrocardiograms (70%) and 13/16 echocardiograms (81%). All 21 cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) scans performed showed abnormalities, including myocarditis or T2-weighted oedema in 15/21 (71%), and late gadolinium enhancement in 19/21 (90%). One patient underwent an endomyocardial biopsy and this demonstrated eosinophilic myocarditis.

Median troponin was 1198 (82-11,206) ng/L, brain natriuretic peptide 361 (46-793) ng/L, eosinophil count 8600 (3900-14100)/ μ L, Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score 16 (14-20), C-reactive protein 101 (36-193) mg/L. 9/24 (37.5%) were ANCA-positive (6 anti-MPO, 3 anti-PR3).

All patients received oral prednisolone with an initial daily dose of 60 (44–60) mg; 13 received intravenous methylprednisolone. Induction therapies included cyclophosphamide plus rituximab (n=10), cyclophosphamide alone (n=4), rituximab alone (n=2), mycophenolate mofetil (n=3), other agents (n=3). Two patients received prednisolone monotherapy. Maintenance treatment included azathioprine (n=11), mycophenolate mofetil (n=8), rituximab (n=3), benralizumab (n=4) and mepolizumab (n=2).

One patient experienced cardiac relapse four years after induction therapy, and another underwent mitral valve replacement 10 months after induction therapy. Both received cyclophosphamide for induction. No deaths are reported in this study.

Conclusions: Cardiac involvement in EGPA is often asymptomatic but readily detected by CMR, which should be the diagnostic modality of choice. Combination immunosuppressive induction therapy appears effective for sustaining long-term cardiac remission in EGPA.

P-086

Cardiac involvement of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis: a case series from a northern Spanish hospital

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare ANCA-associated vasculitis. Cardiac manifestations, such as myocarditis or valvular disease, are a major cause of mortality. However, many cases remain subclinical and are missed without advanced imaging. While transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) is routinely used, cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (CMR) offers greater sensitivity for detecting myocardial inflammation and fibrosis. This study aimed to describe cardiac involvement in a cohort of EGPA patients.

Methods: A retrospective descriptive study was conducted at the University Hospital of Navarra, including 14 adult EGPA (2006 and 2025). Clinical, laboratory, and treatment data were collected from medical records. Notably, only one patient underwent CMR, limiting the assessment of subclinical myocardial involvement in the remaining cases.

Results: Cardiac involvement was identified in 5 out of 14 patients (35.7%). One patient had EGPA-related cardiomyopathy with focal subendocardial fibrosis on CMR, reduced LVEF (35%), and underwent mechanical mitral and aortic valve replacement. Another had atrial fibrillation with normal TTE. Two showed isolated valvular abnormalities, and one had left ventricular hypertrophy with valve dysfunction. Most had asthma and ENT involvement. All had eosinophil counts >2,000 cells/ μ L; three were ANCA-P positive, and two ANCA-C positive. All received corticosteroids; four received immunosuppressants, and three were treated with biologics. Three patients (60%) experienced relapses in the last year, and all developed complications, including infections and cardiovascular events.

Conclusions: This updated real-world series illustrates the typical eosinophilic and respiratory phenotype of EGPA. Despite treatment, relapses and complications remain frequent. Cardiac involvement was notable, including valvular or structural abnormalities. In one patient, cardiac MRI revealed focal subendocardial fibrosis and confirmed EGPA-related cardiomyopathy. These findings highlight the importance of systematic cardiac screening and suggest that cardiac MRI should be considered in all patients with suspected or unclear cardiac symptoms.

P-087

Heart failure and predictors of outcome in eosinophilic myocarditis: insights from a real-world cohort study

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Background/Aims: In eosinophilic diseases, cardiac involvement with heart failure critically impacts prognosis. This study aimed to delineate development of cardiac function, treatment regimens including heart failure pharmacotherapy, and outcomes to identify prognostic biomarkers in eosinophilic myocarditis (EM) across various inflammatory disorders.

Methods: Retrospective single-centre cohort of all EM patients treated at LMU University Hospital (January 2010–May 2025). Clinical, laboratory, and imaging data were collected at baseline, first, and final follow-up. Subgroup and longitudinal differences were tested with appropriate parametric/non-parametric methods; linear regression and correlation identified biomarkers.

Results: Of 419 patients screened, 51 had EM (51% female, age 50±14 years). Inflammatory diseases included eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) (n=29), idiopathic hypereosinophilic syndrome (i-HES) (n=16), drug-associated/hypersensitivity myocarditis (n=7, 4 with EGPA/i-HES) and isolated EM (n=3). While all laboratory parameters improved after a median of 34 months [IQR 16–79], overall left-ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) remained impaired (48.3±12.0%, n=39) and independent of positive baseline endomyocardial biopsy or cardiac magnetic resonance imaging. Left-ventricular end-systolic and end-diastolic volume indices (LVESVI/-EDVI) significantly increased over time (36 [28–62] to 51 [29–101] mL/m² body surface area and 80 [67–96] to 93 [68–140] mL/m², respectively). Glucocorticoids were broadly applied as induction- and maintenance-therapy with a high drug-burden over time. Steroid-sparing drugs were used less frequently and administration of guideline-concordant heart failure pharmacotherapy was insufficient. 5 patients died, all of them had reduced baseline LVEF. Baseline N-terminal pro-brain-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP), LVEF and a clinical composite score (Sartorelli 2022) were significantly associated with follow-up LVEF, LVEDVI and LVESVI ($\rho/r=\pm 0.44-0.72$, $R^2=0.19-0.46$, p from <0.05 to <0.0001).

Conclusions: EM severely affects cardiac function. We propose three readily accessible prognostic biomarkers across different inflammatory diseases that may aid in timely therapeutic intervention. Gaps in immunomodulatory and heart failure treatment underscore the need for prospective studies addressing biomarker-guided strategies to improve outcomes in eosinophilic cardiomyopathy.

P-088

Frequency, aetiologies, and prediction of diffuse alveolar haemorrhage

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Background/Aims: Alveolar haemorrhage (AH) is a life-threatening condition with varied aetiologies, including capillaritis, bland haemorrhage, and infection. Diagnosis often relies on subjective assessment of bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) appearance, which can influence empiric glucocorticoid (GC) use. Misdirected treatment may be harmful, highlighting the need for tools to rapidly distinguish aetiologies, including among patients with known autoimmune diseases and/or immunocompromise. We aimed to describe the frequency and aetiologies of bloody BAL return and externally validate a model for identification of immune-related AH which was previously limited to immunocompetent individuals.

Methods: In this IRB-approved retrospective study, we searched eight years of bronchoscopy reports. One procedure with bloody BAL return of non-bronchial origin was included per patient. With the exception of lung transplant recipients, both immunocompromised and immunocompetent patients were included. Clinical data, treatments, and outcomes were collected. We validated the Picard score (0–10), which incorporates symptom duration >11 days, fatigue, arthritis/arthralgia, and proteinuria (>300g/dL) to identify capillaritis. Discrimination was assessed with the C-statistic (AUC, 95% CI), calibration was evaluated across four models.

Results: Among 12,057 bronchoscopies, 1,229 patients had bloody BAL return. Infection was the most frequent aetiology (68.9%, n=846); capillaritis accounted for 2.9% (n=36). Median Picard score was 2 (range 0-8). Higher scores were strongly associated with capillaritis (OR=1.72, 95% CI=1.37-2.16; C-statistic=0.78, 95% CI=0.68-0.88). Treatment decisions often diverged from scoring; 11.6% of patients with low scores (<4) received GCs despite not ultimately having capillaritis, whereas 14.3% of those with high scores (≥4) were initially untreated with GCs prior to diagnosis of capillaritis.

Conclusions: Bloody BAL return is common, identified in more than 10% of bronchoscopies. Capillaritis accounts for a minority, reinforcing the need for diagnostic tools. Our data support the use of the Picard score in patients regardless of immunocompromised status, which may aid earlier detection and reduce inappropriate GC use.

P-089

Incidence of ischaemic vision loss among patients with polymyalgia rheumatica and giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: The objective of this study was to quantify the risk of ischemic vision loss among patients with polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR), giant cell arteritis (GCA), and matched population controls.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective inception cohort using the US-based TriNetX electronic health records network. Adults with new-onset PMR or GCA were included if age ≥ 50 years and: 1) ≥ 2 ICD-9/10-CM codes, 2) ≥ 1 year of prior follow-up (baseline), and 3) one prednisone prescription within 30 days of first code (index date). Matched general population control cohorts for PMR and GCA were constructed using 1:3 nearest-neighbour matching on the following variables: sex, race/ethnicity, regional location, birth year, year of cohort entry, and year of cohort exit. The primary outcome was ischemic vision loss, defined by ICD-9/10 codes for ischemic optic neuropathy and retinal artery occlusion. Multivariable Cox proportional cause-specific adjusted hazard ratios (aHR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to define the risk of ischemic vision loss.

Results: Of 52,287 patients, 16,001 had PMR, 3,054 had GCA, and 33,232 were matched controls. Median follow-up time was 3.8 years. The incidence of ischemic vision loss over the entire follow-up period (10 years) was highest for GCA (9.2 per 1,000 person-years) followed by PMR (1.7 per 1,000 person-years), GCA controls (1.5 per 1,000 person-years), and PMR controls (1.4 per 1,000 person-years). Ischemic vision loss was increased in GCA as compared to PMR (aHR 5.36, 95% CI 4.09–7.02) and GCA as compared to matched-controls (aHR 5.69, 95% CI 3.95–8.18). No significant differences were observed for PMR as compared to matched controls (aHR 1.10, 95% CI 0.86–1.41).

Conclusions: In this large retrospective cohort study, patients with PMR had no increased risk of ischemic vision loss as compared to the general population or to patients with GCA.

P-090

Tocilizumab for perioperative management of cardiovascular surgery in patients with Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Patients with Takayasu arteritis (TAK) often undergo cardiovascular surgeries and endovascular therapies to repair dilatation/aneurysm and stenosis/occlusion of the aorta and coronary arteries. TAK patients undergoing cardiovascular surgeries should be introduced into remission by adequate immunosuppressive treatment to reduce surgery-related complications. We reported the efficacy of tocilizumab (TCZ) for refractory patients with TAK (ARD2018, Rheumatology2020). To reduce the glucocorticoids (GCs) dosage as much as possible before surgery, we used subcutaneous TCZ for TAK patients undergoing cardiovascular surgeries in the National Cerebral and Cardiovascular Center (NCVC). We examined the suitable duration of temporal TCZ discontinuation during the perioperative period.

Methods: Clinical information of the patients was collected after obtaining approval from the research ethics committees of the NCVC (R21076-2). We enrolled ten consecutive patients with TAK treated with TCZ, who underwent cardiovascular surgery at the NCVC from December 2019 to June 2025.

Results: The inflammatory markers were not elevated in any of the patients before surgery. The mean PSL dose was 8.0 mg/day at the time of the operation. Three patients showed postoperative complications, including chest re-exploration for haemostasis and myocardial infarction. Delayed wound healing was observed in two patients. Relapse of TAK was not observed in any of the patients. The mean number of days from final administration of TCZ to the operation was 17.7 days, and the mean number of days from the operation to TCZ re-administration was 16.9 days.

Conclusions: TCZ might be a promising treatment strategy for patients with TAK undergoing cardiovascular surgery to reduce the dosage of GCs. After confirming the induction of remission of the patients, TCZ administration should be discontinued 2–3 weeks before surgery. After confirming the postoperative wound healing, TCZ administration should be resumed 2–3 weeks post-surgery. This timeline will reduce postoperative complications and relapse of TAK associated with discontinuing TCZ.

P-091

Non-pulmonary arterial involvement in Behçet's Disease: A multicentre retrospective case series

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Background/Aims: In Behçet's disease (BD), arterial involvement represents a significant clinical challenges with serious complications. This study aimed to evaluate the characteristic features, affected vessels, lesion types, treatments, and outcomes of BD patients with arterial involvement.

Methods: Sixty-five BD patients were included in this retrospective cohort study and the data were collected from medical records.

Results: Fifty-nine patients (90.8%) were male. The median (Q1-Q3) follow-up duration was 4 (2-12.8) years. The most commonly affected vessels were the aorta (n=21, 32.3%) and femoral artery (n=19, 29.2%). Aneurysm (n=50, 63.2%) and thrombosis (n=18, 22.7%) were the predominant lesions. Fourteen (21.5%) patients experienced arterial involvement under immunosuppressive (IS) therapy (azathioprine, n=13; infliximab, n=1). Eleven (16.9%) had cardiac involvement. Cyclophosphamide and azathioprine were the most commonly used ISs (66.3% and 67.7%, respectively). Surgical and/or interventional procedures were performed on 39 (60%) patients, with 32 (82%) procedures being successful. During follow-up, a second arterial event occurred in 10 patients (15.3%), and a third in 2 (3%). Despite treatment, 9 (13.8%) patients had active disease at their last visit. Mortality was observed in 6 (9.2%) patients, mostly in patients with both arterial and cardiac involvement.

Conclusions: Arterial involvement in BD mostly presents with aneurysms in especially male patients. About half of patients need surgical intervention in addition to IS therapy. During follow-up, relapse developed in 15,3%, indicating a lower rate than in venous disease. While arterial involvement in BD is generally associated with more severe outcomes, the risk of relapse appears to be lower compared with venous involvement. Mortality was found 9,2%, mostly in patients with both arterial and cardiac involvement.

P-092

Neuropsychiatric burden in Behçet's disease beyond neuro-Behçet's: evidence from cross-sectional psychometric and clinical assessment

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Background/Aims: Neuro-Behçet's disease(NBD) represents overt neurological involvement in Behçet's disease(BD). However, neuropsychiatric symptoms may occur even without clinical NBD. We assessed the prevalence of neuropsychiatric signs/symptoms in BD patients without neurological involvement, compared with NBD, familial Mediterranean fever (FMF), and healthy controls(HC).

Methods: In this cross-sectional observational study, BD patients fulfilling ISG criteria were classified as mucocutaneous, ocular, or vascular phenotypes; NBD, FMF, and HC served as comparators. Structured face-to-face interviews captured demographics and clinical data. Psychometric testing included the Beck Depression Inventory(BDI), Beck Anxiety Inventory(BAI), and Mini-Mental State Examination(MMSE). Headache features and neurological examination were recorded; available neuroimaging was reviewed.

Results:135 BD without neurological involvement as mucocutaneous(n=69), ocular(n=26), and vascular(n=40), and 17 NBD, 37 FMF, and 29 HC were enrolled. Age at symptom onset was earlier in mucocutaneous/ocular BD and later in vascular/NBD(p<0.001). Current smoking was most frequent in NBD(58.9%). Headache was common across groups—mucocutaneous 72.5%, ocular 69.2%, vascular 67.5%, NBD 52.9% p=0.012); migraine predominated and peaked in FMF(64.7%). Neurological examination was largely normal; tandem gait difficulty occurred in ocular BD 15.4%, vascular BD 12.5%, and NBD 12.5%. Cognitive impairment (MMSE ≤23) was more prevalent in BD phenotypes than HC: mucocutaneous 39.7%, ocular 38.5%, vascular 15.0%, NBD 37.5%, HC 10%(p<0.001). Depressive symptoms were higher in BD groups, with moderate-to-severe depression in mucocutaneous BD 33% and NBD 25%(p=0.021); anxiety severity did not differ significantly across groups. Neuroimaging was unremarkable outside NBD.

Conclusions: Neuropsychiatric manifestations—headache, depressive symptoms, and cognitive impairment—are frequent in BD even without overt neurological involvement. The disproportionate burden in mucocutaneous and ocular phenotypes (despite normal imaging) suggests potential contributions from socioeconomic factors, treatment intensity/adherence, and persistent subclinical inflammation. Proactive screening and early management of neuropsychiatric symptoms should be incorporated into routine BD care to improve quality of life and reduce unnecessary referrals and testing even in the absence of NBD.

P-093

Impact on vasculitis disease activity of immune checkpoint Inhibitors used for treatment of cancer in patients with pre-existing vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) have transformed cancer therapy but can provoke immune-related adverse events (irAEs). Patients with autoimmune disease, including vasculitis, were excluded from pivotal clinical trials, and the risk of disease flares with ICI therapy remains poorly defined.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective review of electronic health records of oncology patients with a prior history of vasculitis who received ICI therapy at our centre. Vasculitis subtypes were classified according to the 2012 Chapel Hill Nomenclature.

Results: We identified seven patients with pre-existing vasculitis. Five (71%) were women, and the median age was 66 years (IQR 60–70). Underlying malignancies included lung cancer (n=4), renal cell carcinoma (n=2), and melanoma (n=1). ICI administered were pembrolizumab (n=4), durvalumab (n=2), and ipilimumab/nivolumab (n=1).

Pre-existing vasculitis comprised eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA; n=1), IgA vasculitis (n=2), MPO ANCA-vasculitis (n=1), giant cell arteritis (GCA; n=2), and polyarteritis nodosa (PAN; n=1). All patients were in remission at ICI initiation.

During treatment, five patients (71%) experienced vasculitis flares, defined as recurrence of prior disease manifestations. Clinical features were heterogeneous: one patient developed a severe cutaneous PAN flare; two experienced concomitant severe irAEs in addition to flare (grade 3 pneumonitis with MPO-ANCA vasculitis; grade 4 pancreatitis with EGPA); and four patients had multi-organ involvement. Median time to flare was 39 days (IQR 25–43 days).

Most flares responded to corticosteroids; one severe PAN flare required additional immunosuppression. ICIs were discontinued in two patients, and three underwent rechallenge. Cancer outcomes were four deaths, two remissions, and one stable disease.

Conclusions: Clinically significant flares were common in patients with pre-existing vasculitis receiving ICIs, but most were manageable with corticosteroids, permitting cancer treatment to continue in most. Pre-existing vasculitis should not be viewed as an absolute contraindication to ICI use, although close monitoring and early recognition of flares are essential.

P-094

The Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas): bDMARD treatment in non organ-/life-threatening AAV from 2019 to 2025

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Background/Aims: The EULAR recommendations 2022 update for AAV suggested biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drug (bDMARD) therapy with rituximab (RTX) as first-line option for non-organ/life-threatening disease in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) (1), although no randomized controlled trial has specifically addressed this subgroup. It remains unclear to what extent these recommendations have changed treatment decisions.

Methods: GeVas is a prospective, multicentre registry documenting organ involvement, damage, outcomes, and therapies in vasculitis in German-speaking countries. We analysed induction therapy in patients with GPA and MPA presenting with non-organ/life-threatening disease between June 2019 (start of the registry) and June 2025. Non organ-/life-threatening disease was defined according to the EULAR recommendations 2022 update (1). Data was analysed by propensity score-weighting for initial BVAS and Pearson's chi-square test with Rao-Scott adjustment for weighted categorical data. Normalized percentage of weighted cases was calculated for presentation.

Results: Of 389 patients with AAV (GPA: 277, MPA: 112), 77 (20%) had a non-organ/life-threatening disease (40% female (n=31), 13% MPA (n=10)). Of these, 20 (25.9%) received conventional synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drug (csDMARDs) therapy (Methotrexate n=14 (70%), Azathioprine n=5 (20%), Leflunomide n=1 (7%), MMF n=1 (5%)) and 57 received bDMARD therapy (all RTX). Comparing the time interval June 2019-June 2022 and August 2022-June 2025, the proportion of bDMARD treated patients increased from 73.4% to 84.8% and the proportion of csDMARDs treated patients decreased from 26.6% to 15.2%.

Conclusions: The majority of patients with non organ-/life threatening AAV were treated with bDMARDs. This proportion increased after June 2022, coinciding with the presentation of EULAR recommendations.

Reference: 1. Hellmich B, et al. EULAR recommendations for the management of ANCA-associated vasculitis: 2022 update. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2024 Jan 2;83(1):30-47. doi: 10.1136/ard-2022-223764.

P-095

Rituximab versus cyclophosphamide for inducing remission in ANCA-associated vasculitis with severe kidney impairment

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Background/Aims: RAVE and RITUXIVAS trials established rituximab (RTX) therapy in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). However, RAVE excluded patients with severe kidney involvement (creatinine >354µmol/L). Whilst RITUXIVAS did not, treatment included RTX with 2 cyclophosphamide (CYC) pulses. The aim was to assess outcomes of AAV patients with severe kidney involvement when treated with solely RTX or CYC together with high dose steroids.

Methods: Outcomes were retrospectively examined for AAV presentations with severe kidney involvement (creatinine >354µmol/L) between 2010-2023. The primary outcome was a composite measure of independent kidney function and relapse free survival at 12 months.

Results: Amongst 107 newly diagnosed AAV patients, 66 received pulsed CYC with steroids (39 received plasma exchange (PLEX)), and 41 received RTX with steroids (7 PLEX). At presentation, there was no significant difference in, renal replacement therapy requirement (CYC, 56% vs RTX, 71%; p=0.129), creatinine (511 vs 538 µmol/L; p=0.399) or eGFR (9 vs 7 mL/min/1.73m²; p=0.372). 52% of CYC patients, and 49% of RTX patients met the primary outcome (p=0.783). At 12 months, there was no significant difference in independent kidney function (CYC, 65% vs RTX, 56%; p=0.582). eGFR recovered at similar rates between CYC and RTX (3 months: 23.5 vs 28.0, p=0.291; 6 months: 28.5 vs 28.6, p=0.884; 12 months 28 vs 31, p=0.439). At 12 months, 94% of CYC cohort were alive compared to 83% of RTX (p=0.068). Of the seven RTX deaths, six were secondary to COVID-19 or severe pre-existing comorbidities. Eight CYC patients relapsed within 1 year compared to one RTX patient (p=0.079). 11% of CYC patients required treatment change to RTX due to tolerability issues, compared to zero RTX patients changing to CYC (p=0.31).

Conclusions: This large retrospective cohort of newly diagnosed AAV patients with severe kidney involvement suggests that RTX with steroids appears as efficacious as CYC with steroids.

P-096

Effectiveness and safety of cyclophosphamide in induction therapy for elderly patients with microscopic polyangiitis and renal impairment: A 32-case series

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Background/Aims: Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) predominantly affects elderly individuals in Japan; however, the effectiveness and safety of adding cyclophosphamide (CY) to glucocorticoid (GC) induction therapy in this population remain uncertain, particularly with respect to disease severity. Although current guidelines recommend CY/Rituximab for remission induction, most clinical trials exclude elderly patients, and treatment decisions in real-world clinical settings are often based on renal pathology or physical frailty rather than systemic disease activity. We aimed to evaluate the impact of CY in elderly patients with MPA stratified by disease severity.

Methods: In this single-centre retrospective study, we reviewed 32 elderly patients with MPA (≥ 70 years) and renal involvement treated between 2001 and 2016. Patients were classified into CY (n=15) and non-CY (n=17) groups based on whether CY was added to GC induction therapy, with treatment decisions guided by clinical and pathological findings. Baseline characteristics, clinical outcomes, and serious adverse events (SAEs) were compared over a 2-year period. Patients were further stratified into mild and moderate-to-severe MPA based on a validated clinical scoring system incorporating age, renal function, CRP, and pulmonary involvement.

Results: Patient backgrounds were comparable across groups. Overall survival and ESRD rates did not differ significantly in the total cohort or in mild MPA patients (n=21). However, in the moderate-to-severe MPA patients (n=11), two-year survival was significantly higher in the CY group (100% vs. 25%, $P=0.010$). Vascular SAEs (e.g., cerebral/pulmonary haemorrhage) occurred exclusively in the non-CY group during active vasculitis phases, often leading to poor functional outcomes. GC-related toxicity scores were similar between groups.

Conclusions: Assessment of systemic vasculitis activity is essential in elderly patients. CY use in moderate-to-severe MPA patients may offer a safe and meaningful survival benefit, without increasing infection risk or GC-related toxicity, supporting its inclusion in individualized induction therapy strategies for selected elderly MPA patients.

P-098

Glucocorticoid toxicity and clinical outcomes associated with duration of glucocorticoid use in individuals with granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis treated with avacopan in a real-world setting

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Background/Aims: There is limited understanding regarding concomitant glucocorticoid (GC) use in patients with GPA/MPA receiving avacopan and how GC use associates with outcomes.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective study evaluating outcomes according to GC treatment duration following avacopan initiation (12/2021-5/2024) in a real-world cohort of patients with GPA/MPA. Outcomes included remission (BVASv3=0) at months 6 and 12, relapse, kidney measures, and Glucocorticoid Toxicity Index–Metabolic Domain (GTI-MD) at 12 months. Patients were grouped by initial GC regimen duration (<2 vs. ≥2 months following avacopan initiation).

Results: Among 95 patients (45% with GCs <2 months), baseline characteristics were overall similar between the two groups (<2 vs. ≥2 months), including newly-diagnosed (74.4% vs. 67.3%, p=0.449), GPA (46.5% vs. 59.6%, p=0.202), and others. However, those receiving <2 months had younger age (55.2 vs. 62.2 years, p=0.042), less lung involvement (34.9% vs. 55.8%, p=0.042), lower GC dose (30 vs. 40 prednisone-equivalent mg, p=0.027), and lower cumulative 12-month GC exposure pre-avacopan initiation (1250 vs. 2872mg, p=0.003) compared with the ≥2 month group. Those receiving <2 months had lower cumulative 12-month GC exposure after avacopan initiation (median 280 vs. 1820 prednisone-equivalent mg, p<0.001) and were more often GC-free at 12 months (100% vs. 76.9%, p=0.001). The <2 vs. ≥2 month group had similar remission at month 6 (88.4% vs. 86.5%, p=0.789) and month 12 (93.0% vs. 96.2%, p=0.496), relapse (25.6% vs. 32.7%, p=0.449), urine protein:creatinine improvement among those with baseline >0.2g/g (67.4% vs. 72.7%, p=0.620), dialysis use (7.4% vs. 3.7%, p=0.552), median days to avacopan discontinuation (182 vs. 221, p=0.643), and GTI-MD improvement (46.5% vs. 40.4%, p=0.548). All outcomes were unchanged after adjusting for age, sex, lung involvement, and baseline GC dose.

Conclusion: In this cohort of GPA or MPA patients receiving avacopan, shorter GC treatment duration after avacopan initiation was associated with similar effectiveness.

P-099

Reduced glucocorticoid dose in ANCA-associated vasculitis: outcomes of an initial half-dose glucocorticoid regimen compared with historical controls

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Background/Aims: The treatment of microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) has shifted toward reduced glucocorticoid (GC) regimens following PEXIVAS and LoVAS. Since April 2022, Juntendo University Hospital changed the initial GC dose from prednisolone (PSL) 1.0 mg/kg/day to 0.5 mg/kg/day, defined as the Half dose group. We compared outcomes with historical controls.

Methods: We retrospectively reviewed patients with MPA or GPA who received remission induction at Juntendo University Hospital between January 2017 and December 2024. Treatment generally consisted of GC pulse therapy followed by PSL 0.5 mg/kg/day, combined with rituximab (RTX). After initiation of oral therapy, PSL was tapered by 5 mg every two weeks, with continuation of PSL 5 mg/day up to 52 weeks, with dose adjustments at physician discretion. Categorical variables were compared using Fisher's exact test, and continuous variables with the Mann–Whitney U test.

Results: A total of 61 patients in the historical control group and 43 in the Half dose group were enrolled. The median age was 73 years, with 75 females, 73 MPA cases, and 31 GPA cases. Baseline BVAS was 15 (11–20) vs. 14 (12–17) ($p=0.87$). Initial GC dose was 50 (40–57) vs. 25 (20–30) mg/day ($p<0.001$). Concomitant agents during induction included intravenous cyclophosphamide (IVCY) in 54% vs. 0% ($p<0.001$), RTX in 21% vs. 95% ($p<0.001$), and avacopan in 10% vs. 79% ($p<0.001$). Within 52 weeks, mortality was 13% vs. 5% ($p=0.19$), remission 79% vs. 95% ($p=0.22$), and GC dose at week 52 was 9 (5–12) vs. 5 (0–5) mg/day ($p<0.001$).

Conclusions: The Half dose group did not worsen outcomes. The establishment of optimal regimens for severe manifestations such as myocarditis and diffuse alveolar haemorrhage remains an important unmet need.

P-100

Uncovering the relationship between cumulative corticosteroid use and complications in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody associated vasculitis: a reflection on patient journeys

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Background/Aims: Anti neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) associated vasculitis (AAV) is a rare autoimmune small vessel vasculitis affecting 13 Australians/million annually. Cytokines prime neutrophils, exposing proteinase 3 (PR3) and myeloperoxidase (MPO) antigens. ANCA binds to degranulate neutrophils, causing an inflammatory cascade leading to endothelial injury, and necrotising granuloma formation, affecting organs including kidneys, lungs, and skin. Immunosuppression is required to induce and maintain remission, utilising corticosteroids and/or steroid-sparing agents. It has been suggested that active vasculitis results in <15% of mortality, whereas corticosteroid-associated complications; infection, cardiovascular disease, and malignancy—account for a far higher proportion. This has prompted a paradigm shift toward greater reliance on steroid-sparing agents.

The aim of this study was to assess complications experienced by AAV patients in relation to cumulative corticosteroid dose.

Methods: Patients were enrolled in the ANZVASC Quality and Disease Registry. Data on demographics, disease parameters, treatments, and complications were extracted. A graph visualising steroid use and complications since diagnosis was produced. Regression analysis investigated the correlation between cumulative steroid dose and total complications.

Results: From 11 patients total, 74 complications were recorded with 20 (27%) categorised as steroid-related; weight gain, sleep disturbance, post-steroid arthralgias and others including steroid induced pancreatitis and hyperglycaemic episodes. Non-steroid complications included infections, malignancy, vasculitis flares, drug reactions/toxicity and thrombotic events. A statistically significant positive correlation was found between cumulative steroid dose and total complications ($p = 0.0013$, 95% CI).

Conclusions: Higher cumulative steroid dose was associated with increased complications, particularly steroid-specific effects that impaired quality of life. These findings support reducing steroid reliance in favour of steroid-sparing agents for both induction and maintenance. While corticosteroids remain essential for acute flares, future studies should assess the long-term safety and efficacy of newer agents such as avacopan to reduce cumulative steroid exposure and its associated morbidity.

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Glucocorticoid-sparing strategy does not necessarily improve outcomes in ANCA-associated vasculitis: The multicentre REVEAL cohort study

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) remains a life-threatening condition with a poor prognosis. This study aimed to comprehensively examine the clinical features and treatment outcomes of microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), and eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA). In addition, we compared the prognosis of AAV over time using data from REVEAL cohort.

Methods: Patients diagnosed with AAV were enrolled in the cohort through June 2024. MPA was diagnosed according to Chapel Hill Consensus definitions; GPA was identified using Watts' algorithm or 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria; and EGPA met Lanham criteria, 1990 ACR classification criteria, or 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria. Of the 555 registered patients, 460 newly diagnosed, treatment-naive cases were analysed (MPA: 283; GPA: 66; EGPA: 111).

Results: Among patients with AAV, those with MPA had significantly higher age, five-factor score, C-reactive protein, serum creatinine (Cr), and a higher prevalence of myeloperoxidase-ANCA positivity at onset (all $P < 0.0001$). Although the Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score was initially highest in EGPA, no significant differences were observed among groups at 12 months after onset. The Vasculitis Damage Index also showed no differences at 12 and 24 months after onset. The 5-year survival rate for MPA was significantly lower at 67.6% ($P < 0.0001$). Multivariable analysis among AAV patients identified age and Cr as factors significantly associated with mortality. Importantly, patients diagnosed before 2018 (median diagnosis year) received higher glucocorticoid (GC) doses at 3, 6, 12, and 24 months compared to those diagnosed later (all $P < 0.0001$). However, overall survival did not differ between patients diagnosed pre-2018 and post-2019. Cause-specific analysis suggested more vasculitis-related deaths in patients diagnosed after 2019 ($P=0.006$).

Conclusions: Recent GC-sparing strategies were not associated with improved survival. These findings highlight the need for individualized approaches to GC tapering based on patients' risk factors and disease severity.

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Safe effective therapy with low-dose glucocorticoid in ANCA-associated vasculitis (SAFE-LOW): Protocol for a pilot randomised controlled trial

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Background/Aims: Induction therapy for anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is effective, but treatment-related toxicities, notably infections and glucocorticoid-related side effects, contribute significantly to patient morbidity and mortality. Observational studies suggest a combination of rituximab and cyclophosphamide induction with low doses of glucocorticoids provide adequate disease control with low infection rates. A dedicated trial examining such a regimen is required to confirm its safety and efficacy in patients with severe AAV.

Methods: SAFE-LOW is a pilot, open-label, randomized controlled trial in patients with new or relapsed AAV with severe renal involvement (estimated glomerular filtration rate < 40ml/min). Participants will be randomized 1:1 to the intervention (rituximab-cyclophosphamide combination, 2 doses 2 weeks apart each, with a 4-week prednisone taper to 0mg), or the control (standard of care induction, left to the discretion of the treating clinician) arms. There will be no up-front use of avacopan in either arm. Primary outcomes are recruitment rate and adherence to the prednisone taper in the intervention arm. Key secondary outcomes include serious infections, change in kidney function, end-stage kidney disease, death and change in the AAV-Patient-Reported-Outcome score. The trial sponsor is the Ottawa Hospital Research Institute and SAFE-LOW is funded by the Vasculitis Foundation, The Ottawa Hospital Academic Medicine Organisation Innovation Fund and Physician Services Incorporated.

Results: SAFE-LOW will take place at two tertiary care centres in Ontario, Canada (The Ottawa Hospital and St. Joseph's Healthcare Hamilton). Ethical approval was obtained and the trial is registered at clinicaltrials.gov (NCT06983821). Recruitment of 36 patients over 3 years is planned and is expected to commence in October 2025.

Conclusion: SAFE-LOW is the first controlled trial to investigate the glucocorticoid-sparing ability of rituximab-cyclophosphamide combination. If feasibility is demonstrated, a larger full-scale trial will be pursued.

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A prospective, perpetual, multi-centre, registry-based trial emulation study comparing glucocorticoid sparing therapies in ANCA-associated vasculitis: study rationale and design

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) has evolved from an acutely fatal illness into a chronic, relapsing inflammatory condition. Immunosuppressive regimens, typically comprising glucocorticoids alongside rituximab and/or cyclophosphamide, remain the cornerstone of therapy. However, treatment has long been associated with substantial toxicity, particularly related to prolonged glucocorticoid exposure. Recent clinical trials have demonstrated the feasibility of glucocorticoid-sparing strategies, yet the optimal therapeutic approach remains uncertain, especially in real-world populations characterised by diverse clinical phenotypes and comorbidities.

This study aims to emulate a randomised, controlled trial using real-world data to examine and compare the effectiveness and toxicity of pre-specified glucocorticoid-sparing induction regimens for AAV across multiple clinical centres. The primary hypothesis is that either the combination of cyclophosphamide and rituximab, or the addition of avacopan to induction therapy, will result in a meaningful steroid-sparing effect. Additionally, the study will investigate whether particular regimens confer greater benefit within specific patient subgroups.

Methods: This is a prospective, perpetual, multi-centre, registry-based trial emulation study run by the Australia and New Zealand Vasculitis Quality and Disease Registry. Participating centres will enrol patients with new or relapsing AAV receiving one of several pre-specified induction regimens. The primary outcome is remission at six months. Secondary outcomes will include sustained remission at twelve months, relapse rates, renal outcomes, and adverse events. Patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis, anti-glomerular basement membrane co-positivity, or those enrolled in concurrent clinical trials will be excluded.

Conclusions: This pragmatic study will generate generalisable, real-world evidence to support more tailored and tolerable approaches to AAV induction therapy. It is designed to evolve in parallel with clinical practice and to support rapid translation of emerging data into patient care.

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Initial impact of plasma exchange in patients with severe ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: A single administration of plasma exchange (PLEX) can reduce the plasma concentration of complement and immunoglobulins by 60%, which is beneficial for treating cases of severe anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (AAV). However, without additional immunosuppressive therapy, this effect does not persist for more than 4 to 10 weeks.

The PEXIVAS trial reported that in patients with severe AAV, PLEX (administered seven times over two weeks) did not significantly reduce the risk of mortality or end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) over the entire 7 years of follow-up (hazard ratio [HR], 0.86; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.65 to 1.13; P=0.27) or at 12 months (HR, 0.77; 95% CI, 0.56 to 1.06). This finding served as the basis for the downgrading of recommendations for applying PLEX in AAV by the American College of Rheumatology and the European League Against Rheumatism. However, considering the transient effects of PLEX, it is possible that the initial conclusion of the PEXIVAS trial, which was based on the analysis of long-term outcomes, may have overlooked the short-term but significant benefits of PLEX.

Methods: We conducted a preliminary visual re-analysis of the primary outcome (death or ESKD) of the PEXIVAS trial at earlier time points (3, 4.5, 6, and 12 months).

Results: A visual inspection of Figure 1A in the PEXIVAS paper indicated that the degree of separation between the Kaplan-Meier survival curves for the PLEX group and the control group peaked around 3 to 6 months. We manually digitized the survival curves using GeoGebra (www.geogebra.org), which yielded estimated HRs of 0.76, 0.66, 0.68, and 0.83 at 3, 4.5, 6, and 12 months, respectively (Figure).

Conclusions: We suggest that a re-analysis of the short-term effects of PLEX on mortality would be invaluable and could lead to the development of more refined recommendations regarding the application of PLEX in AAV.

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Short and long-term maintenance treatment with glucocorticoids in GPA and MPA patients: a retrospective two-centre study

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Background/Aims: To evaluate whether prolonged glucocorticoids (GC) maintenance reduces relapse and affects safety or damage accrual in rituximab-treated GPA/MPA patients.

Methods: We retrospectively included GPA/MPA patients induced with cyclophosphamide or rituximab and maintained on rituximab (MAINRITSAN). Outcomes included relapse rates, severe infections, hospitalizations, and VDI change. Time-varying Cox models considered GC exposure as a time-dependent covariate and adjusted for BVASv3.

Results: 37 patients (26 GPA, 11 MPA, 36 ANCA-positive) were followed for a median of 45 [IQR 34–59] months. Median GC exposure was 22 [IQR 11–47] months, with a cumulative dose of 10,346 [IQR 7,865–15,642] mg. 22 (59.5%) patients discontinued GCs, mostly within 2 years, while 15 (40.5%) patients remained on long-term GCs. 9 relapses occurred (2 major, 7 minor) after a median of 28 [13–37] months (5.79/100 PY). Relapse incidence was 9.30/100 PY while on GC and 0/100 PY off-GC (no events off-GC). Relapse risk did not differ by disease or ANCA phenotype. Relapse-free survival was higher in patients stopping GCs (HR 4.6, 95% CI 1.18–18.13; log-rank p=0.028). Relapsing patients had longer GC exposure (45 [28–61] vs 15.5 [9–25.8] months, p=0.041) and higher GC dose (5 [0–5] vs 0 [0–4] mg/day, p=0.049) at last follow-up visit. In Cox models, BVAS at diagnosis was not associated with relapse (HR 1.03, 95%CI 0.89–1.18), whereas GC exposure showed complete separation. No differences were observed between patients on and off GC regarding VDI change, hospitalizations and severe infections requiring hospitalization or intravenous antibiotics (5.79/100 PY).

Conclusions: In rituximab-maintained GPA/MPA patients, prolonged GC therapy beyond two years did not provide clear relapse prevention and was not associated with differences in severe infections, hospitalizations, or damage accrual. These findings support early GC tapering and discontinuation to minimize steroid exposure, acknowledging limitations of small sample size and potential selection bias.

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Age at diagnosis and use of maintenance immunosuppression in individuals with a new diagnosis of ANCA-associated vasculitis: a retrospective cohort study

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Background/Aims: Prior studies have reported decreased use of maintenance immunosuppression and prolonged glucocorticoid (GC) exposure among older adults with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). The objective of this study was to describe current maintenance treatment patterns in patients with newly diagnosed AAV by age group.

Methods: We identified patients with AAV from the TriNetX database between 2000–2025. Inclusion required ≥ 2 AAV diagnostic codes within 365 days and an index treatment with rituximab or cyclophosphamide. Patients were stratified by age: <65 , 65–74, and ≥ 75 years. The outcome was use of maintenance treatment regimens: rituximab, oral immunosuppressive therapy (IST: azathioprine, methotrexate, or mycophenolate), and GC during the first 24 months after induction. Medication use was calculated among individuals with available follow-up at the end of each 6-month interval. Demographics, comorbidities, and induction therapies were described.

Results: A total of 2,886 patients met inclusion criteria: 1,872 <65 years, 673 aged 65–74, and 341 aged ≥ 75 . Older patients had higher comorbidity burden and renal disease at baseline. Rituximab was the most common induction therapy (76.7%), followed by cyclophosphamide (19.9%), the latter more frequently used in younger patients.

Rituximab was the predominant maintenance agent across all age groups. At 6–12 months, rituximab was prescribed in 45.2% of <65 , 45.0% of 65–74, and 49.6% of ≥ 75 -year-olds. At 18–24 months, use declined to 37.5%, 39.3%, and 41.4%, respectively. Oral IST was more frequent in younger adults (25.0% <65 , 20.3% 65–74, 17.2% ≥ 75 at 24 months). GC prescriptions remained common, with 31.4%, 30.9%, and 31.2% of patients in each age group continuing therapy at 24 months.

Conclusions: In this large real-world cohort, rituximab was the predominant induction and maintenance therapy irrespective of age, while oral IST was more frequently used in younger adults. Nearly one-third of patients remained on glucocorticoids at 24 months.

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Failure of rituximab to induce remission among patients with relapsing ANCA-associated vasculitis in the RITAZAREM trial

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Background/Aims: Rituximab is an established treatment to induce remission for ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). The RITAZAREM trial enrolled patients with relapsing AAV who all received re-induction treatment with rituximab (375 mg/m²x4) in addition to glucocorticoids. This post-hoc descriptive analysis describes the characteristics and management of patients who responded poorly to rituximab re-induction.

Methods: Following rituximab, Population 1: Protocol defined remission (BVAS/WG ≤1 and prednisolone dose ≤10mg/day at month 4); Population 2: Complete remission (BVAS=0 and prednisolone dose ≤10 mg/day at month 4). Comparisons to the overall RITAZAREM trial cohort were made using the t-test or the Mann–Whitney U test for continuous variables. The Chi-square test was applied to contingency tables.

Results: Of 188 patients, 16 (8.5%) failed to achieve complete remission: 6 (3.2%) failed to achieve protocol-defined remission (Population 1) and 10/188 (5.3%) failed to achieve complete remission (BVAS/WG = 1) (Population 2). No differences were observed between these poorly responding patients and the overall cohort regarding historical organ involvement. Of the 6 from population 1 who failed to achieve remission, 5 received additional glucocorticoids, 4 additional other immunosuppression: cyclophosphamide (1), mycophenolate mofetil (1), methotrexate (2), and plasma exchange (1). Ear/nose/throat symptoms were present in all patients in Population 2 at enrolment. Among patients randomized to rituximab or azathioprine, the percentage of relapses during the trial in patients with a BVAS/WG=1 at month 4 (population 2) was 85.5% compared to 56.8% for those with a BVAS/WG=0 (p<0.001). These patients also tended to relapse earlier (16.7 months (SD 9.5) vs. 21.7 months (SD 12.1)).

Conclusions: Within a group of patients with relapsing AAV receiving rituximab for re-induction of remission, 8.5% failed to achieve complete remission. Failure to achieve complete remission was associated with ENT involvement at time of relapse and a high subsequent relapse rate.

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Comparative efficacy of low-dose rituximab (500 mg) and ultra-low-dose rituximab (200 mg) in maintaining remission in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV)

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Background: Rituximab (RTX) has been shown to achieve high remission-induction and sustained maintenance rates across multiple studies and clinical trials in patients with AAV. In this interim analysis of an ongoing study, we aimed to compare the relapse rate, B cell depletion rate and hypogammaglobulinemia after receiving fixed protocol ultra-low dose (200mg, ULD biannually) and low dose (500mg, LD biannually) rituximab for maintenance of remission in patients with AAV.

Methods: Patients satisfying ACR / EULAR criteria for either granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) or microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), in complete remission and receiving rituximab maintenance therapy for > 12 months, were recruited across 4 centres in India between 1st April 2023 - 1st April 2025. Based on the dose of maintenance rituximab used as per physician's discretion, the patients were subdivided into either LD or ULD group. Details of clinical presentation, disease activity as assessed by BVASvs3 and laboratory investigations were collected prospectively at recruitment (T0), 3 monthly follow up until the last follow up visit or relapse whichever occurred earlier.

Results: Among 35 patients (GPA= 30, MPA = 5) recruited, 18 and 17 patients received ULD and LD maintenance rituximab respectively. All the parameters at diagnosis except age and disease duration were similar in both groups. During median follow-up of 12 (IQR 9-15) months, 1 patient given LD rituximab had major flare with renal involvement (BVAS=11) at 6 months while another 1 patient developed sepsis at 15 months follow up and died. Among patients receiving ULD rituximab, one developed exacerbation of colitis and succumbed. The CD19 B cell count, and IgG levels at the last visit did not differ significantly between LD and ULD group.

Conclusion: In this proof-of-concept study, frequency of relapse, mortality, B cell depletion and adverse events were comparable between both LD and ULD rituximab group.

Clinical outcomes of rituximab for remission maintenance therapy in Japanese patients with microscopic polyangiitis and granulomatosis with polyangiitis: A retrospective multicentre cohort study (J-CANVAS)

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Background/Aims: Rituximab (RTX) has been established as a standard remission maintenance therapy for ANCA-associated vasculitis. However, in Japan, where clinical characteristics and disease distribution differ and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) is predominant, the efficacy of this remission-induction therapy has not been sufficiently evaluated. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of RTX in remission maintenance among Japanese patients with MPA or granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA).

Methods: Study design was a retrospective observational study. The participants were MPA or GPA patients from Japanese nationwide AAV registry. Japanese patients with MPA or GPA who had achieved remission and entered the maintenance phase were included from the registry. Induction and maintenance therapy were defined as treatment up to 24 weeks and treatment thereafter, respectively. Exposure was the use of RTX during maintenance therapy. The primary endpoint was defined as major relapse-free survival at 104 weeks.

Results: A total of 633 patients with MPA or GPA were included in the analysis (MPA: 463; GPA: 170), with 150 patients in the RTX group and 483 in the non-RTX group. At 104 weeks, the survival rate was 98.5% in the RTX group (2 deaths) and 91.7% in the non-RTX group (33 deaths). Major relapses occurred in 4 RTX-treated patients and 20 non-RTX-treated patients. The major relapse-free survival rate at 104 weeks was 92.8% in the RTX group and 83.5% in the non-RTX group, with a significantly higher rate observed in the RTX group (HR for severe relapse or death: 0.30; 95% CI, 0.14–0.67; $p = 0.003$).

Conclusions: Even in a predominantly MPA Japanese cohort, our findings suggest that rituximab is associated with lower relapse rates in the maintenance of remission therapy compared to other maintenance therapies for patients with MPA or GPA.

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Biosimilars of rituximab in ANCA-associated vasculitis compared to the originator (BRAVO): 24-month follow-up of a multi-centre cohort

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Background/Aims: To evaluate the effectiveness and safety of rituximab biosimilars compared to the originator in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA).

Methods: We recruited 207 adults with GPA or MPA who started the rituximab originator or a biosimilar for induction or maintenance, or switched from originator to biosimilar maintenance (2018-2023). The primary outcome at 24 months was time to relapse (new vasculitis activity after achieving remission, requiring treatment). Secondary outcomes included major relapses, serious adverse events (SAEs), and change in Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI).

Results: At baseline, 132 started induction (58 originator, 74 biosimilar), 59 started maintenance (23 originator, 36 biosimilar), and 16 switched from originator to biosimilar. Mean age was 56.7 (SD 17.5), 52% were female, 70% had GPA, and 47% had ≥ 1 prior relapse. Most in the induction originator (51/58, 88%) and biosimilar (64/74, 86%) groups achieved remission and received ≥ 1 rituximab maintenance dose. Over 274 person-years of maintenance (n=174, excluding the 'switch' group), 12 participants experienced relapses. Relapse rates were 5.4 (95% CI 2-11) per 100 person-years during originator maintenance and 3.7 (95% CI 2-8) per 100 person-years during biosimilar maintenance (HR 0.83; 95% CI 0.3-2.7, adjusted for age and prior relapse). Major relapse rates were similar between groups (3 in each). In mixed-model repeated-measures regressions, VDI change was not significantly different between originator and biosimilar induction subgroups (p=0.27) or maintenance subgroups (p=0.06). SAEs were consistent across originator and biosimilar induction (both 9 per 100 person-years) and maintenance groups (both 11 per 100 person-years). The 'switch group' relapse rate was 3.2 (95% CI 0.2-16) per 100 person-years and SAE rate was 18.8 (95% CI 7-42) per 100 person-years.

Conclusions: We did not observe significant differences in effectiveness or safety between the rituximab originator or biosimilars in GPA or MPA during 24 months of follow-up.

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Estimating two-year risk of relapse in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Individuals with anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (ANCA, AAV) differ in their risk of relapse. Estimation of an individual's risk may inform decision-making around monitoring and treatment.

Methods: We performed a post hoc analysis of participants with newly diagnosed or relapsing AAV with an estimated glomerular filtration rate <50 mL/min/1.73m² or diffuse alveolar haemorrhage enrolled in a trial assessing the effects of plasma exchange and a reduced glucocorticoid dosing regimen who achieved disease remission. We estimated risk of relapse within two years of remission. We first identified candidate predictors from the literature. Candidate predictors measured in our data set and associated with relapse within two years of remission underwent further selection using Lasso regression and time-to-event analysis. Model stability was assessed with variable inclusion, multiple shrinkage methods, and VanderWeele's E. Model discrimination was assessed using concordance statistics, and calibration using the slope.

Results: We included data from 649 trial participants of whom 100 experienced a relapse within 2 years of remission. The final risk estimation model included sex, use of oral cyclophosphamide or rituximab as induction agent, ANCA subtype, non-haemorrhagic respiratory involvement or mucous membrane/eye involvement at presentation, and eGFR at remission. The optimism-corrected Harrell's area under the receiver operator curve 0.709 (95% confidence interval 0.707-0.710). The calibration slope was 0.99 (95% [CI] 0.65-1.34).

Conclusions: Our model estimates the risk of relapse for individuals with AAV within two years after achieving disease remission. Estimating the risk of relapse may inform clinicians' and individuals' monitoring and treatment decisions.

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Immunosuppression reduces intervention rates for subglottic stenosis in granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Subglottic stenosis (SGS) is a recognised manifestation of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), reported in 10–25% of granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) patients, and often associated with frequent endoscopic interventions. Emerging evidence suggests a role for immunosuppression in reducing relapse and procedural burden, however treatment guidance remains heterogeneous. We evaluated whether systemic immunosuppression reduces intervention rates in patients with SGS-GPA in a combined ENT-vasculitis service.

Methods: We performed a retrospective observational study of 77 patients with SGS referred to our combined ENT-vasculitis clinic in the years 2015-2025. Demographics, AAV diagnosis, ANCA status, biopsy findings, immunosuppressive therapy, and frequency of endoscopic dilatations were recorded. Intervention rates (procedures per year) were calculated for periods before and after initiation of systemic immunosuppression.

Results: Of 77 patients, 67 had a diagnosis of AAV. ANCA testing was positive by IIF in 49 and by ELISA in 24 patients. Subglottic biopsy demonstrated pathognomonic features of AAV (vasculitis or granuloma) in 9 (13.4%) patients. Sixty-three patients received systemic immunosuppression (Rituximab, Azathioprine, MMF, Methotrexate or combination). Median intervention rate fell from 1.0 per year (IQR 1.0–1.67) pre-treatment to 0.34 per year (IQR 0.09–0.8) post-treatment ($p < 0.0001$), representing an average reduction of 61%. Rituximab achieved a greater median reduction (67%) than other DMARDs (50%) on paired analysis. While both groups showed statistically significant reductions post immunosuppression, there was no statistically significant difference between the two treatment groups, reflective of the small non-Rituximab treated sample size.

Conclusions: In this single-centre retrospective cohort study, systemic immunosuppression was associated with a clinically and statistically significant reduction in endoscopic dilatation frequency for patients with GPA-SGS. Rituximab appeared most effective, though further studies are needed to confirm superiority. Future work will include subgroup analysis to identify serological and clinical predictors of response, allowing the identification of patients most likely to benefit from immunosuppressive therapy.

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Tracheobronchial stenosis in granulomatosis with polyangiitis: immunosuppressant use and airway dilation frequency

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Background/Aims: Tracheobronchial stenosis (TBS) affects 13–27% of patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and can cause life-threatening airway compromise. Despite advances in GPA treatment, TBS remains difficult to manage, with frequent relapses and high procedural burden. We aimed to retrospectively evaluate the relationship between immunosuppressant use and frequency of airway relapse in patients with TBS-GPA.

Methods: We performed a retrospective review of patients with TBS-GPA seen at Johns Hopkins between 2013–2024. Demographics, clinical characteristics, immunosuppressant exposure, and tracheal dilation dates were abstracted. Follow-up duration and cumulative patient-years of drug exposure were calculated to enable longitudinal assessment. The primary outcome was airway relapse, defined as need for balloon dilation. Multivariable mixed-effects Poisson regression was used to assess associations between immunosuppressant exposures (rituximab, cyclophosphamide, methotrexate, azathioprine, leflunomide, mycophenolate) and dilation incidence, adjusting for age at TBS diagnosis, years since TBS diagnosis, ANCA status, GPA severity, and intralesional glucocorticoid injections.

Results: 56 patients with TBS-GPA were included, with mean follow-up of 9.9 years. 33 received rituximab, 24 methotrexate, 16 leflunomide, 13 azathioprine, 5 cyclophosphamide, and 4 mycophenolate. In the adjusted mixed-effects Poisson model, patient-years on leflunomide were associated with a 64% lower incidence of tracheal dilations compared to periods off leflunomide (IRR 0.36, $p = 0.002$). No statistically significant associations were observed for the other immunosuppressants measured. Among other tested covariates, age under 40, severe GPA, and concomitant glucocorticoid injections were associated with higher dilation frequency.

Conclusions: Leflunomide use was associated with reduced need for tracheal dilations in TBS-GPA, highlighting it as a promising treatment option warranting further evaluation. Younger age and the presence of concomitant severe GPA manifestations were also identified as risk factors for airway relapse.

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Cyclophosphamide vs rituximab induction therapy for ANCA-associated vasculitis. A systematic review and meta-analysis

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) survival rates have improved with advancement in therapeutics. Induction regimens traditionally include cyclophosphamide (CYC) and/or rituximab (RTX), in addition to glucocorticoids. The impact on mortality in AAV stratified by induction therapy is not known. The aim of this study was to compare 12-month mortality in people with AAV who received CYC versus RTX induction therapy.

Methods: A systematic literature review was undertaken to identify studies assessing 12-month mortality after CYC or RTX for AAV induction therapy. A meta-analysis was conducted to estimate pooled results using a random effects model. The homogeneity of the study results was assessed using the I^2 statistic and sensitivity analysis was undertaken to assess the impacts of study populations and study design on any statistical heterogeneity.

Results: 1579 studies were screened and 47 studies included in the analysis. The overall mortality at 12 months for CYC was 10.6% (95% CI 8.3-13.1) and RTX was 6.1% (95% CI 3.3-9.5). The difference in 12-month mortality between induction therapies was 4.6% (95% CI 3.9-5.2; $p < 0.001$) favouring RTX. Analysis from 5 studies that directly compared these treatments showed a small non-statistically significant reduction in mortality for CYC (difference=1.34%, 95% CI -6.5-3.7; $p=0.59$). The difference in 12-month mortality rate in those treated for GPA was 6.7 (95% CI 2.7-11.0) favouring RTX induction. Subgroup sensitivity analysis was conducted based on year of treatment, sex, age, granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and BVAS, all of which showed reduced but not statistically significant mortality in the RTX group.

Conclusions: Overall, there was a statistically significant difference favouring RTX in 12-month mortality rates after CYC or RTX induction treatment for AAV. Subgroup sensitivity analysis considering study populations consistently supported this result although only treatment for GPA reached statistical significance. Further direct studies between CYC and RTX induction are required.

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The quality of ANCA-associated vasculitis guidelines - is there fault in our stars?

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Background/Aims: Several guidelines for the management of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) have been developed by different bodies. However, there is no data on whether they are methodologically sound and address all needs. Therefore, we have aimed to appraise current guidelines, identify gaps and provide recommendations for improvement.

Methods: We have assessed the methodological quality of 11 guidelines. Guidelines were appraised using the Appraisal of Guidelines for Research and Evaluation II (AGREE II) instrument which consists of 23 appraisal criteria/items across six domains (D). Four reviewers independently appraised all guidelines, and scaled domain scores were calculated.

Results: The average score of all guidelines was 4.5±0.8 out of 7.0. British Society for Rheumatology 2025 scored highest (5.8) and was the only guideline unanimously recommended for use. In D1/Scope and purpose, all guidelines achieved high scores. In D2/Stakeholder involvement, major gaps were identified in including the views and preferences of the target population (2c), with few guidelines including patient representatives, addressing patient participation or considering patient views. In D3/Rigour of development, all except two guidelines had a score of >70%. Implementation of a procedure for updating the guidelines (3h) and external review (3g) were addressed poorly in most guidelines. In D4/Clarity of presentation, all guidelines except one received a score of >90%. D5/Applicability had the lowest scores, due to gaps in criteria for monitoring and auditing guideline implementation (5d), resource/cost implications (5c), lack of advice/tools for implementation (5a) and inadequate addressing of facilitators/barriers in guideline application (5a). D6/Editorial independence was well addressed in all guidelines.

Conclusions: Several aspects of AAV guidelines could be improved, particularly the inclusion of patient views and preferences, the processes for translating guidelines into clinical practice (including advice and tools), and the criteria for monitoring guideline implementation. These improvements are important to ensure AAV guidelines are not only methodologically robust but also patient-centred and clinically useful.

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Avacopan in Australian adults with ANCA-associated vasculitis: a multi-centre retrospective study

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Background/Aims: Avacopan initially became available in Australia for ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) via a managed access program. We conducted a retrospective multi-centre study on avacopan use in adults with AAV.

Methods: De-identified data at 0, 3 and 6 months, then 6-monthly were collected (demographics, AAV manifestations, treatments and test results, and the indication/duration of avacopan) from Australian centres prescribing avacopan until 31/07/2024 (beginning ≥ 3 months prior).

Results: Thirty-one patients from 13 centres were included (16 males). Eighteen were PR3-ANCA+, and 17 had granulomatosis with polyangiitis. Clinical status when commencing avacopan was newly diagnosed (8/31), recently relapsed (7/31), ongoing disease (14/31) and remission (2/31). The most frequent active sites were renal (18/31), pulmonary (9/31) and ear/nose/throat (9/31). Indications were: glucocorticoid-sparing agent (29/31), severe/treatment-resistant/refractory disease (19/31), and clinical opinion that avacopan would be more effective than glucocorticoids (17/31). Other treatments at commencement included rituximab (n=25) and cyclophosphamide (n=3); all received glucocorticoids. In the prior 12 months, a median cumulative dose of 1,855mg prednisolone (interquartile range [IQR] 1,085-3,990mg) was prescribed. Median follow-up was 238 days (IQR 127-424). Four died and one was lost to follow-up. Eight ceased avacopan (three due to gastrointestinal symptoms). At 6 months, 24 patients were reviewed: 19 were taking avacopan (13/19 in remission; 4/5 not taking avacopan in remission), and 13 were receiving glucocorticoids (median 6-month cumulative prednisolone dose 2,629mg, IQR 1,936-4,818mg). Of 11 patients reviewed at 12 months, 8 remained on avacopan (6/8 in remission; 2/3 not taking avacopan in remission) and 6 were receiving glucocorticoids (median 12-month cumulative dose 3,750mg, IQR 1,998-5,995mg). Of four patients commencing avacopan with eGFR < 15 , two had sustained renal improvement, one stabilised, and one reached renal failure.

Conclusions: Avacopan was typically prescribed as a glucocorticoid-sparing agent for new or ongoing active AAV. Most patients achieved remission 6 and 12 months after commencing avacopan.

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Clinical outcomes of real-world avacopan use in ANCA-associated vasculitis: a multicentre, retrospective study

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a systemic autoimmune disease with high morbidity and mortality, partly due to treatment-related toxicities from glucocorticoids (GCs). Avacopan, an oral C5a receptor (C5aR1) inhibitor, demonstrated efficacy and GC-sparing effects in the ADVOCATE trial, leading to FDA approval in 2021. Data describing real-world avacopan use outside of clinical trials are limited. We aim to evaluate clinical outcomes and GC-sparing effects of avacopan in patients with AAV treated in routine practice across Mayo Clinic sites.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective, multicentre cohort study of adults diagnosed with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) or microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) per 2022 EULAR/ACR criteria who received avacopan during induction therapy at Mayo Clinic (Minnesota, Arizona, Florida and Wisconsin) between October 1, 2021, and June 31, 2024. Patients required ≥ 12 months of follow-up. Outcomes included remission (BVAS=0), complete remission (BVAS=0 and no prednisone), relapse, renal replacement therapy (RRT) and survival.

Results: Sixty-four patients were included (mean age 58.1 years; 56.3% female). Over half initiated avacopan at first diagnosis (56.3%) and 53.1% in the inpatient setting. Median follow-up was 12.06 months (IQR: 12.02-12.35). Remission was achieved in 93.8% with a median time of 2.6 months; 70.3% achieved complete remission (median 4.3 months). Fourteen patients (21.9%) relapsed (median of 5.7 months), including 8 with major relapse. A prednisone dose of 0 mg was achieved in 73.4% at a median of 4.0 months. RRT was initiated in 8 patients (12.5%). One patient (1.6%) died during follow-up.

Conclusions: This multicentre study represents one of the largest post-marketing, real-world cohorts of at least 12 months of follow-up in avacopan use. Patients experienced high remission rates, meaningful GC tapering, and clinically relevant renal outcomes. These findings provide critical evidence on how avacopan is being utilized in routine practice and inform treatment expectations beyond clinical trial settings.

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One year real-world effectiveness with avacopan in granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis in a large healthcare system

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Background/Aims: Avacopan has been approved for adjunctive use in adults with severe active granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) or microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) in the US. Here we describe 12-month effectiveness and safety outcomes for avacopan users within the Mass General Brigham (MGB) healthcare system.

Methods: This ongoing retrospective cohort study involves patients prescribed avacopan for GPA/MPA from 12/1/21-4/1/24. Sustained remission is defined as remission at months 6 and 12 (Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score version 3 [BVAS v3] of 0 and no glucocorticoids [GCs] for GPA/MPA within 1 month before month 6 or month 12, respectively), without relapse between months 6-12. Relapse is defined as: 1) ≥ 1 major BVAS v3 item, 2) ≥ 3 minor items, or 3) 1 or 2 minor items for ≥ 2 consecutive visits. We also assessed other disease- and treatment-related outcomes, including the Glucocorticoid Toxicity Index-Metabolic Domains (GTI-MD).

Results: Among 119 patients prescribed avacopan (mean age 59.4 years; 70% female, 66% newly-diagnosed, 55% MPO-ANCA+, 50% with GPA, median baseline BVAS v3=12, 55% receiving rituximab), 103 (86.6%) initiated avacopan. Of these 103, organ involvement included kidneys (56%), lungs (49%) and ear/nose/throat (ENT) (42%).

Of the 95/103 (92.2%) with 12-month follow-up, 61.1% had sustained remission, 94.7% had a BVAS v3=0, 87.4% were GC-free (median time to GC discontinuation: 84 days), 3.2% relapsed between months 6-12, and 40% remained on avacopan, and 25% discontinued avacopan due to adverse events. Median cumulative prednisone-equivalent 12-month GC exposure was 1050mg. Sustained remission was similar among those with baseline kidney, lung, and ENT involvement. The majority (56%) had no net worsening of metabolic GC toxicity over 12 months (i.e., AIS ≤ 0).

Conclusions: Among avacopan initiators with GPA/MPA and 1-year follow-up, most discontinued GCs within 3 months and had sustained remission at 12 months, and a minority had avacopan-related adverse events and/or worsening of GC toxicity.

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Real-world avacopan safety data from an early access program mirrors data from registration trials in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Avacopan safety has been demonstrated in 239 patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) or microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) from Phase 2 (CLEAR and CLASSIC) and 3 (ADVOCATE) clinical trials. Following its approval, the real-world safety of avacopan has been reported in several small cohorts. Here we describe safety in patients from an Early Access Program (EAP).

Methods: Safety data were analysed for patients with severe, active GPA/MPA receiving avacopan through the EAP across 14 countries between February 2019 and March 2025 (data cut-off).

Results: 317 patients received ≥ 1 dose of avacopan with a median treatment duration of 8 months (IQR 4.0-13.0). 105 patients received avacopan beyond 12 months; median duration was 15 months (IQR 13.0-21.0) and the longest treatment exposure was 49 months. A total of 179 adverse events (AEs) were reported, with 59/317 (18.6%) patients experiencing ≥ 1 AE. 32/317 patients (10.1%) experienced a total of 70 serious AEs. The highest incidence of AEs assessed by system organ class (SOC) were 'General disorders and administration site conditions' (6.6%), 'Infections and infestations' (5.4%) and 'Gastrointestinal disorders' (4.7%), with nausea, diarrhoea and COVID-19 being the most frequently reported events.

13 AEs associated with hepatic test elevations were reported in 8/317 patients (2.5%), 4 of which were considered serious. Avacopan was paused or discontinued in 6/8 patients. 16 serious infections were reported in 10/317 patients (3.2%). 4/317 (1.3%) patients died; 1 due to complications from a chest intervention followed by multiple infections, 1 due to cerebral haemorrhage, and 2 were reported as deceased with limited information.

Conclusions: Findings from the largest international real-world dataset to date support the known avacopan safety profile even when treatment is prolonged beyond 12 months. AEs by SOC were generally consistent with those in clinical trials, with no new safety signals.

P-120

AvacoStar, a real-world evidence study of avacopan in ANCA-associated vasculitis: baseline characteristics of initial patients

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Background/Aims: Avacopan is approved by the EMA for the treatment of adults with severe, active GPA or MPA, in combination with rituximab/cyclophosphamide. The primary objective of AvacoStar is to evaluate the incidence of defined medical events of special interest (MESIs) during long-term follow-up in a real-world cohort of participants commencing avacopan for severe, active GPA or MPA. MESIs include liver injury, cardiac safety, serious infections, and malignancy.

Methods: AvacoStar (NCT05897684) is a non-interventional post-authorisation long-term safety study, which will enrol 500 patients in Germany and the UK (250 treated with avacopan, and 250 treated with a rituximab/cyclophosphamide-based regimen without avacopan). Patients aged ≥ 18 years with severe, active GPA/MPA at the time of induction therapy are eligible and will be followed for up to 7 years. We present baseline characteristics of the first 314 patients included in the study.

Results: As of October 2024, 314 patients have been enrolled ($n=182$ avacopan cohort; $n=132$ non-avacopan cohort). Current SoC at the participating centre was identified as the most common reason for selecting the avacopan or non-avacopan regimen (72.5% avacopan cohort; 72.9% non-avacopan cohort). Most patients enrolled were newly diagnosed (73%). The avacopan cohort had more patients with renal involvement (83.0% vs 73.5%), longer disease duration since diagnosis (2.5 vs 2.2 years), and more frequent use of rituximab plus cyclophosphamide for induction therapy (35.1% vs 8.0%) than the non-avacopan cohort.

Conclusions: At the time of data collection, most baseline characteristics were comparable in general between the cohorts with some imbalances. The initial findings indicate that the outcomes of the study could provide valuable and applicable information about the safety and usage patterns of avacopan. Limitations of this analysis include missing data, a higher recruitment rate in the avacopan cohort at the time of the data cut and data variability from routine clinical practice.

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Interim report on post-marketing surveillance of avacopan, a C5a receptor antagonist, for microscopic polyangiitis and granulomatosis with polyangiitis—one year report

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Background/Aims: To report the interim results of a post-marketing surveillance (PMS) being conducted to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of avacopan in patients with microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) in Japan as a condition of its regulatory approval.

Methods: Patient background data, the incidence of adverse events (AEs) and adverse drug reactions (ADRs), and effectiveness of avacopan during the first 12 months of treatment were evaluated, as of March 26, 2025.

Results: A safety analysis was performed on 421 patients: 232 females (55.1%); mean age 70.7 ± 13.4 years; 332 (78.9%) with MPA and 88 (20.9%) with GPA; and 339 (80.5%) with MPO-ANCA and 52 (12.4%) with PR3-ANCA. AEs and serious AEs occurred in 229 (54.4%) and 82 (19.5%) patients, and ADRs and serious ADRs occurred in 163 (38.7%) and 53 (12.6%) patients, respectively. The most frequent AE by Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities, System Organ Class was hepatobiliary disorders in 87 (20.7%) patients. ADRs related to hepatic function disorder, one of the important identified risks in the risk management plan in Japan, was reported in 86 (20.4%) patients, which were serious in 19 (4.5%) patients. ADRs related to serious infections, another important identified risks in Japan, was reported in 24 (5.7%) patients. Among patients whose MPA/GPA status was active at the start of avacopan treatment, the disease was no longer active in 186 (70.7%) of 263 patients at Month 3, in 177 (75.6%) of 234 patients at Month 6, 106 (77.9%) of 136 patients at Month 9, and 103 (81.7%) of 126 patients at Month 12. Relapse occurred in 36 (8.6%) of 418 patients.

Conclusions: This PMS revealed the safety and effectiveness of avacopan over 12 months of treatment in patients with MPA and GPA in real-world clinical practice.

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Patient Profiles, Treatment Patterns, and Economic Burden Among Users of Avacopan in the United States

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Background/Aims: Avacopan is an adjunctive treatment for adults with severe active granulomatosis with polyangiitis or microscopic polyangiitis (GPA/MPA). This study aimed to describe patient characteristics, treatment patterns, and economic burden among users of avacopan.

Methods: This retrospective cohort study examined US-based IQVIA PharMetrics® Plus claims data from Oct 2021 to Mar 2024. Patients age ≥ 18 years with ≥ 1 avacopan claim (index date: first avacopan claim date) and ≥ 12 months pre-index continuous data were included. Patient characteristics, economic burden, and GPA/MPA medication use were described in both the baseline and follow-up periods; avacopan treatment patterns were described in the follow-up period.

Results: Of 183 patients prescribed avacopan (58.5% female; median age, 53 years), 98.9% received systemic glucocorticoids and/or other immunosuppressive therapy prior to initiating avacopan, and 59.6% had kidney involvement (8.2% on dialysis); rheumatologists (62.8%) were the most common prescribers. The proportion of patients with ≥ 1 hospitalization and ≥ 1 emergency department visit was 49.7% and 50.8%, respectively, pre-avacopan (n=183), and 28.3% and 30.4% post-avacopan initiation (n=46). Mean inpatient hospitalization costs and emergency department visit costs were \$32,570 and \$1,461 (US dollars, annualized to follow-up) pre-avacopan (n=183), and \$14,798 and \$879 post-avacopan (n=46). The average length of hospital stay was 8.2 days pre-avacopan and 5.2 days post-avacopan. In 121 patients with a ≥ 90 -day supply or ≥ 3 avacopan claims in the variable follow-up, 4.1% had a dialysis claim and 17.4% had evidence for relapse. Among those with 12-month follow-up (n=42), mean total oral prednisone-equivalent daily dose (PEDD) decreased from 19.8mg to 10.6mg between 90 days pre- and post-avacopan initiation. The proportion of patients with < 7.5 mg PEDD 90 days pre- and post-avacopan initiation increased from 35.0% to 57.1%.

Conclusions: A majority of users of avacopan with background immunosuppressive therapy had kidney involvement at baseline. Most patients have decreased glucocorticoid exposure post-avacopan initiation.

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Real-world use of avacopan in ANCA-associated vasculitis patients receiving haemodialysis

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Background/Aims: ADVOCATE - a Phase 3 trial of avacopan in AAV excluded patients with eGFR <15 mL/min/1.73 m² or those on haemodialysis (HD). A post-hoc analysis of 50 patients with baseline eGFR ≤20 mL/min/1.73 m² demonstrated that avacopan improved renal recovery. Further real-world evidence (RWE) is needed to inform the optimal use of avacopan in this high-risk group. We, therefore, aimed to summarize the experience of avacopan use in AAV patients receiving HD.

Methods: An EMBASE search for citations published to May 15th, 2024, describing avacopan use in AAV patients receiving HD, and searches of recent meeting abstracts were conducted. Reviews and editorials were excluded.

Results: A total of 501 citations were identified and screened, and 462 were excluded following abstract review; 39 manuscripts underwent full-text assessment. Ten studies met the inclusion criteria; however, two case studies were excluded as avacopan use and HD were not concomitant. Across the eight selected studies, 22 patients were dialysis-dependent. Of these, 12 were able to discontinue HD following a treatment regimen that included the recommended standard dose (30 mg twice daily) of avacopan. Avacopan was generally well tolerated in dialysis-dependent patients, as no new safety concerns were identified. Two of the RWE studies presented aggregated patient safety data, preventing linkage to specific patients; however, all reported safety data in these studies were consistent with the safety profile of avacopan. In studies where adverse event (AE) data could be linked to patients receiving HD, a total of five AEs (neutropenia, two cases of hospital-acquired pneumonia, fungal infection, and Enterococcus infection) were noted in 2 dialysis-dependent patients.

Conclusions: Evidence from real-world studies of avacopan use in patients receiving HD i) suggests that avacopan potentially supports renal recovery, and ii) showed no new safety signals.

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Remission induction for ANCA-associated vasculitis with avacopan and minimal steroid dosing

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Introduction: The ADVOCATE trial showed that avacopan is non-inferior to high-dose glucocorticoids (GCs). However, avacopan patients received a mean cumulative steroid dose of 1676mg over 12 months, with real-world studies also using substantial GC doses. Our study evaluates the effectiveness and safety of a minimal-GC Avacopan regimen against standard-GC care in a large UK cohort.

Methods: This retrospective, two-centre cohort study included 126 newly diagnosed or relapsed ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) patients, with 70 receiving an avacopan-based regimen and 56 receiving high-dose GC. The avacopan group followed a minimal steroid dosing protocol: prednisolone 30mg for one week, then 20mg for another, without intravenous methylprednisolone. Outcomes assessed included sustained remission at 12 months, survival, relapses, renal function, urinary biomarkers, safety and patient-reported outcomes (AAV-PRO).

Results: Baseline characteristics were well-matched. The 12-month median cumulative prednisolone dose was 390mg in the avacopan group versus 3535mg in the GC group. Clinical efficacy was comparable, with sustained remission in 92.9% in the avacopan group versus 91.1% in the GC group ($p=0.75$). Relapse rates were similar (5.7% vs 10.7%; $p=0.45$), and both groups showed significant renal function improvements. The Median increase in eGFR over 12 months in the Avacopan group was 21ml/min/1.73m² vs 18ml/min/1.73m² in GC group ($p = 0.32$). The avacopan cohort demonstrated favourable outcomes in patients with baseline eGFR <15ml/min/1.73m² and over an extended follow-up of 24 months. Safety profiles were similar, with low severe infection rates (6% vs 9%) and one death in each group. AAV-PRO values were similar between the two groups. Urinary biomarkers (CD163, MCP-1, C5a) revealed comparable and sustained reduction in all 3 markers.

Discussion: Our findings indicate that a minimal GC avacopan regimen achieves clinical outcomes comparable to high-dose GC while substantially reducing cumulative steroid exposure. This suggests that real-world practices can minimize GC usage without sacrificing efficacy or safety.

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Avacopan in combination with rituximab and low-dose cyclophosphamide for the treatment of severe ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis

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Background: Avacopan, an oral C5a receptor inhibitor, is a novel treatment for ANCA-associated vasculitis. There are limited data regarding avacopan use in those with severe renal disease and alongside combination rituximab-cyclophosphamide remission-induction regimens. This study aimed to evaluate safety, glucocorticoid use, and renal recovery in patients treated with avacopan in combination with rituximab and low-dose cyclophosphamide for severe ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis (ANCA-GN).

Methods: Single-centre observational cohort study of patients with ANCA-GN treated with avacopan, rituximab and cyclophosphamide for remission-induction therapy. The observation period was from December 2022 to August 2025. Data reported as median (\pm IQR) unless otherwise stated.

Results: To date, 104 patients (median age 66, 53% male, 84% new-onset disease, 58% MPO-ANCA positive) have been treated with this regimen and have at least 12 months follow-up. At baseline, BVAS was 17 (14-21), eGFR 24 (12-40) ml/min/1.73m², urinary protein:creatinine ratio (uPCR) 144 (83-241) mg/mmol, and 24% had alveolar haemorrhage.

The median doses of rituximab and cyclophosphamide were 2g and 3.2g (3.0-3.5), respectively, and 18% received adjunctive plasma exchange. The median dose of IV methylprednisolone was 500mg (250-500), oral prednisolone 420mg (210-675), with steroid-treatment duration 12 (7-42) days. At 12 months, eGFR and uPCR improved to 47 (21-75) ml/min/1.73m² and 26 (0-157) mg/mmol, respectively. In those who presented with eGFR \leq 20ml/min/1.73m² (n=43), median eGFR increased from 13 (9-18) to 31 (11-45) ml/min/1.73m², and 10/16 recovered independent kidney function from initial RRT requirement, by 6 months.

Mild (requiring oral antibiotics) and severe (intravenous) infections occurred in 17% and 10% of patients, respectively. Overall survival at 12 months was 96%.

Conclusions: This series suggests that avacopan is well-tolerated and facilitates glucocorticoid minimisation in patients with severe ANCA-GN, including those with eGFR $<$ 20ml/min/1.73m², when used in combination with rituximab and low-dose cyclophosphamide. Long-term follow-up of this cohort is ongoing.

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Inhibition of C5a-receptor with avacopan in childhood-onset ANCA associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Childhood ANCA-associated Vasculitis (cAAV) is a severe and potentially life threatening disease most often presenting with renal and/or pulmonary involvement. cAAV is often ANCA positive with PR3 or MPO antibodies. AAV is treated aggressively with ivMP pulses, oral steroids, Rituximab (or cyclophosphamide) sometimes with plasmapheresis for induction of remission. In the Advocate trial, avacopan showed the ability to taper steroids quicker with less side-effects. We here report our 8 paediatric patients who received avacopan as part of their AAV treatment.

Methods: a retrospective review of our cAAV patients who received avacopan for the treatment of their AAV.

Results: Eight patients (4 male, 4 female) have received avacopan as part of their treatment. MPO positive in 4 patients, and PR3 positive in 4 patients. Average age at diagnosis 14.1 years (range 8.8 – 16.8 years). Avacopan in 4 patients within 4 weeks of diagnosis. In 3 patients within 4 months of diagnosis and in one patient within the first year due to a flare with severe pulmonary bronchial stenotic disease. All patients tolerated avacopan without any side-effects. All patients were able to taper their prednisone. In three of the patients who received avacopan early in their disease steroids were tapered to stop within 3 months of diagnosis. One patient has stopped avacopan due to receiving a kidney transplantation. All others are still receiving avacopan with a range of 3 months – 2years of follow-up.

Conclusion: In the induction cohort 80% of patients on avacopan was able to stop steroids within 3 months of diagnosis. In this case series of avacopan in childhood AAV, no side-effects were noted and all patients tolerated avacopan. A clinical trial is underway to support our findings and allow cAAV to benefit from avacopan and less steroid toxicity.

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Real-world outcomes and adherence among avacopan users ≥ 65 years: insights from United States claims data

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) are the most common types of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis. Older people with GPA/MPA are understudied in clinical trials, potentially impacting their use of new therapies. This study aims to describe patient characteristics, real-world treatment patterns, and outcomes among avacopan users ≥ 65 years in the US.

Methods: This retrospective analysis included administrative claims from the Medicare Fee-for-Service (FFS) and MORE² Registry[®] databases from 10/07/2021 to 12/31/2023 (FFS) or 06/30/2024 (MORE²). In a subset analysis of 167 total patients, adults ≥ 65 years with ≥ 1 avacopan claim (index date: first avacopan claim) and continuous enrolment for 12 months before (baseline) and after (follow-up) index date were included. Outcomes included baseline characteristics, avacopan-specific treatment patterns, and kidney/non-kidney manifestations and other immunosuppressant use among patients who did not discontinue avacopan (no gap ≥ 90 days).

Results: Fifty-three patients met the inclusion criteria (mean: 74.8 years; 54.7% female). The median Deyo-Charlson Comorbidity Index was 4.0 (moderate). For patients with ≥ 2 avacopan claims ($n=47$), the most common specialists to initially prescribe avacopan were rheumatologists and internal/family medicine practitioners (34.0% each). At 12 months, 25 patients did not discontinue avacopan; of these, most had chronic kidney disease at baseline (80.0%) and follow-up (76.0%). Chest involvement was the most common non-kidney manifestation during baseline (56.0%) and follow-up (52.0%). The mean prednisone-equivalent daily doses (PEDD) in the 90-day pre- and 271-to-360-day post-index periods were 15.1 and 6.9 mg/day, respectively. The median proportion of days covered (PDC) was 0.8; 53.2% of patients had PDC ≥ 0.8 at 12 months.

Conclusions: Among real-world patients ≥ 65 years prescribed avacopan in the US, disease characteristics were consistent with known GPA/MPA epidemiologic profiles. During the 12-month follow-up, most patients showed high adherence and reductions in PEDD. Additional studies investigating longer follow-up and comparative effectiveness are needed.

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Renal function improvement with avacopan in elderly patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis during remission maintenance

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Background/Aims: Avacopan, a C5a receptor inhibitor, has been shown in the ADVOCATE trial to achieve sustained remission with prednisone tapering and to improve renal function in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). However, its efficacy in elderly patients during remission maintenance remains unclear. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of avacopan, with a particular focus on renal outcomes, in elderly AAV patients.

Methods: We retrospectively observed eight AAV patients in remission who received avacopan 60 mg/day at our hospital for more than 12 weeks. Changes in renal function (eGFR), proteinuria (UPCR), CRP, and prednisone dose were assessed compared with baseline.

Results: The cohort consisted of one male and seven females with a median age of 82 years. One patient had PR3-AAV and seven had MPO-AAV; four received rituximab for induction therapy. After 12 weeks, eGFR increased by 8.4% (39.2 → 42.5 mL/min/1.73 m²), UPCR decreased by -0.23 g/gCr, CRP declined by 30% (0.8 → 0.5 mg/dL), and ANCA titres decreased from 17.4 to 8.5. The median prednisone dose was reduced from 7 mg to 4 mg. Two patients developed liver dysfunction, which improved after dose adjustment.

Conclusions: Although limited by small sample size, these findings suggest that avacopan may improve renal function and serve as a safe and effective treatment option for elderly AAV patients with residual disease activity during remission maintenance.

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Pharmacogenomics in clinical practice - an elderly female with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) on avacopan

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Background/Aims: Pharmacogenomic testing can improve clinical outcomes by enhancing therapeutic efficacy and improving clinical safety, especially in elderly patients with drug interactions and life-threatening medical condition such as AAV.

Results: 74-year-old female with stage 3 chronic kidney disease secondary to diabetes presented with a vasculitic rash and acute kidney injury. She developed rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis due to biopsy proven crescentic MPO- (myeloperoxidase) AAV with titres 60 U/mL (normal <3.5U/mL). She received induction treatment with two doses of rituximab 800 mg and steroids. Her cumulative steroid exposure was 2265mg resulting in myopathy and hyperglycaemia, prompting transition to Avacopan 30mg bd at week 12 with steroid cessation. Gastrointestinal intolerance to Avacopan required dose reduction. Additional concentration-dependent adverse drug reactions (ADR) were observed with bradycardia secondary to digoxin and epistaxis from apixaban (trough level 400ng/mL). These medications share common cytochrome (CYP) P450 enzymatic and p-glycoprotein (PGP) dependent kinetics, prompting pharmacogenetic profiling. Normal metabolic phenotypes for CYP3A4 and CYP3A5 isoenzymes were detected. However, a homozygous variant (3435TT) was identified for the ABCB1 gene responsible for coding PGP. This genotype is associated with reduced expression of intestinal PGP, decreased drug clearance, increased risk of accumulation and toxicity. Co-administration of amiodarone compounded CYP3A4 and PGP inhibition for a period. All ADRs resolved on dose reduction of Avacopan to 10 mg BD, Apixaban to 2.5 mg daily and digoxin to 62.5 mcg daily. She remains in sustained remission from AAV at 40 months.

Conclusions: Avacopan is a new treatment agent for AAV with CYP3A4 drug interactions. However, PGP dependent elimination has not been elucidated. Our case suggests p-glycoprotein is involved in Avacopan clearance, given normal CYP3A4 phenotype, PGP-dependent drug toxicities and symptom resolution on dose reductions. In addition to drug-drug interactions, pharmacogenetic profiling provides novel and valuable information on genetic factors influencing Avacopan kinetics.

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How long should avacopan be continued for ANCA-associated vasculitis with severe renal impairment? Insights from cases where discontinuation was unavoidable

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Background/Aims: The C5a receptor inhibitor avacopan demonstrated efficacy for ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in the ADOVOCATE clinical trial. However, the optimal duration of its use beyond the induction phase remains undiscussed. This study focused on cases where avacopan had to be discontinued early due to hepatic dysfunction, comparing their remission rates with those who were able to continue avacopan.

Methods: We compared the remission rates between 4 cases that discontinued avacopan early due to adverse effects and 12 cases that continued treatment among patients with AAV administered avacopan at our hospital from 2022 to 2024. Remission is defined as a state in which BVAS version 3 score is 0, and the oral prednisolone dose is 5 mg/day or lower.

Results: There was no difference in eGFR between the continuation group (C) and discontinuation group (D) (C: D = 19.8: 23.1 mL/min/1.73 m²). All cases except one GPA were MPA. All patients received rituximab. The initial mean daily PSL dose was 8.3 mg in group C and 12.5 mg in group D. The reason for discontinuation of avacopan was hepatic dysfunction in all cases, and all patients discontinued within 2 months. In Group C, 8 patients (66.7%) achieved remission. In group D, 3 patients (75%) achieved remission. Of the 11 patients who achieved remission, only 1 patient in Group D relapsed. Six of the 11 patients who achieved remission received rituximab every 6 months. Kaplan-Meier analysis showed no difference in remission rates between the two groups (P=0.81).

Conclusions: No difference in remission rates was observed between the group that discontinued avacopan within two months and the group that continued treatment. Further investigation is needed to determine the optimal duration of avacopan administration. However, factors such as relapse risk and the administration method of concomitant immunosuppressants require consideration.

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Avacopan discontinuation and subsequent outcomes in ANCA-associated vasculitis: a scoping review and single-centre Canadian cohort analysis

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Background/Aims: Real world data regarding treatment discontinuation of Avacopan for ANCA-associated Vasculitis (AAV) and subsequent outcomes is still limited. This study aims to assess the reporting on avacopan discontinuation and disease outcomes in the existing literature, and within a cohort of patients at the Toronto Vasculitis Clinic (TVC).

Methods: A scoping search of PubMed and Embase (2015-June 18, 2025) identified articles involving AAV patients treated with avacopan. Eligible studies were randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case series, and case reports. When reported, data relating to avacopan discontinuation and subsequent outcomes were extracted. Following this, a single-centre analysis of the 45 AAV patients treated with avacopan between December 2022-September 2025 from the TVC was performed.

Results: Of 245 articles screened, 48 were included in the final synthesis after full-text review, including 590 patients. 71% (34/48) of studies reported avacopan duration. Of these, 146 patients in 19 studies had discontinued avacopan. Disease status at- or post-discontinuation were reported in only 12 studies, for 40% (59/146) of patients. Of those reported, 72% (36/50) were in remission at avacopan discontinuation. Reporting on follow up and outcomes 6+ months post-discontinuation was minimal, with 95% (19/20) in remission.

In our study, 26/45 TVC patients discontinued avacopan after a mean of 14.5 months (2-24). 65% due to remission after completing ≥ 12 months, and 15% due to side effects. Overall, 73% (19/26) were in remission at time of discontinuation; 94% (16/17) and 100% (9/9) were in remission at 6- and 12-months follow up respectively. 73% (19/26) were off prednisone at discontinuation, 65% (11/17) at 6-months, and 89% (8/9) at 12-months follow up.

Conclusions: Outcomes after avacopan discontinuation are just beginning to be studied and published. In our study, most patients who stopped avacopan were in sustained remission at 6-12 months post-avacopan, without steroids.

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The effect of avacopan in the maintenance therapy of ANCA-associated vasculitis: a single centre experience in Japan

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Background/Aims: Avacopan (AVA) is used to treat ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), and has been shown to reduce glucocorticoid (GC) use and improve renal outcomes during remission induction. However, data on its use during the maintenance phase remain limited. This study aimed to evaluate the clinical impact of AVA initiated during the maintenance phase of AAV.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of 10 patients with AAV who began AVA during the maintenance phase at our hospital between 2023 and 2025. All patients had been diagnosed and treated for over one year prior to starting AVA. Clinical parameters, including GC dosage and renal function, were assessed from one year prior to AVA initiation through up to two years post-initiation.

Results: Ten patients (8 MPO-MPA, 1 MPO-GPA, and 1 PR3-GPA) (6 females, 60%) who initiated AVA during the maintenance phase at our hospital. At the start of AVA, the mean age was 70.1 ± 9.8 years (oldest 85 years). At onset, BVAS averaged 14.2 ± 4.8 , but was 0 at AVA initiation. The median time from initial remission to AVA start was 5.2 years. One year prior to the initiation of AVA, the mean eGFR was 42.6 ± 15.6 mL/min/1.73m². At the time of AVA initiation, the mean eGFR was 41.2 ± 13.9 mL/min/1.73 m², and PSL dose was 6.2 ± 2.0 mg/day. Rituximab was used in 70% of cases. Over the follow-up period, no relapses, deaths, or renal deaths occurred. PSL was reduced in 50% of patients, with a final dose of 4.0 ± 1.3 mg/day. Final eGFR improved to 49.1 ± 20.9 mL/min/1.73m², reflecting an $8.5 \pm 17.4\%$ increase from baseline, with some cases showing improvement up to 31.7%.

Conclusion: These results showed that initiating AVA during the maintenance phase may help maintain renal function and reduce GC-dose in AAV patients, particularly in elderly populations in real-world clinical practice.

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Real-world use and extended treatment outcomes of avacopan in ANCA-associated vasculitis: insights from the multicentre European AVAC-EUR study

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Background/Aims: Avacopan was approved in Europe in 2022 for the treatment of active and severe ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Clinical study data are limited to 1 year with no structured data on extended (EXT) avacopan treatment. Between 2020-2025, an early access program (EAP) enabled avacopan use until its commercial availability. The AVAC-EUR study is designed to study the real-world clinical practice of early access avacopan, to improve our understanding of avacopan-based treatment strategies in AAV, including the use of avacopan beyond 1 year.

Methods: AVAC-EUR is a multicentre, European retrospective observational study that included AAV patients treated with avacopan since EAP was initiated. A descriptive analysis of demographics, disease and treatment characteristics was performed, along with a comparative analysis on clinical outcomes, including relapses, hospitalizations and infections, amongst AAV patients receiving avacopan ≤ 1 year and EXT-avacopan (>1 year), with a follow-up of ≥ 1.5 years.

Results: AVAC-EUR included 108 patients (Italy 42.6%, Netherlands 32.4%, Spain 14.8%, Sweden 7.4%, Belgium 2.8%) with a median [IQR] age 61 [51–73] years, 48.1% females and disease duration of 8.8 [1.7–66.0] months. Avacopan-based treatment strategies included predominantly rituximab (84.3%), and cyclophosphamide (20.4%). Avacopan was started around induction regimen with high-dose in 69.4% and 21.2% with low-dose corticosteroids; 5.6% received no steroids. Examining 38 (71.7%) AAV patients with EXT-avacopan versus 15 (28.3%) with ≤ 1 year avacopan, all patients achieved remission (BVAS 0 at 6 months) and throughout the follow-up course cumulative steroid dose and rituximab maintenance were similar. Within the first year, infections and hospitalizations were more frequent in avacopan ≤ 1 year. EXT-avacopan did not increase infections or hospitalizations and showed fewer relapses (0.13 vs 0.35 per patient-year, $p=0.08$).

Conclusions: In European real-world practice, avacopan during EAP was predominantly combined with rituximab and steroids. Extended treatment beyond 1 year may lower relapse risk without increased infections or hospitalizations.

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Efficacy of avacopan therapy beyond 12 months in ANCA-associated vasculitis: insights from real-world practice

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Background/Aims: In the ADVOCATE phase 3 trial, avacopan was associated with superior sustained remission, improved eGFR and glucocorticoid sparing at week 52. We aimed to evaluate the impact of extended avacopan use beyond 52 weeks.

Methods: Retrospective single-centre case series of all avacopan-treated patients. Data extracted from electronic records.

Results: Fifty-two patients completed ≥ 52 weeks of avacopan; 17 (33%) continued beyond. Thirteen (76%) had relapsing disease and multi-system involvement with manifestations across patients including subglottic/endobronchial disease, orbital involvement, cavitating pulmonary lesions, pulmonary haemorrhage, myocarditis and glomerulonephritis. They had extensive prior immunosuppression (median 3 agents, range 1–8); 6/13 had received ≥ 8 g rituximab and 5/13 ≥ 8 g cyclophosphamide, 5/13 were steroid-dependent >5 years. Additional prior therapies included abatacept, adalimumab, alemtuzumab, infliximab and IVIG.

Reasons for continuing were substantial benefit after refractory disease, ongoing active disease, ongoing glucocorticoid taper, and potential for further improvement in renal parameters.

15/17 completed ≥ 18 months; mean age 56.2 ± 17.2 years; 60% male (n=9). Eight (53.3%) had GPA, six (40%) MPA, and one (6.6%) dual anti-GBM/PR3-ANCA. Most had relapsing disease (73.3%); 26.6% were newly diagnosed. Maintenance therapy was rituximab 12/15, methotrexate 1/15 IVIG 1/15, prednisolone alone 1/15. No unexpected safety events occurred.

Mean prednisolone dose decreased from 32.6 ± 23.8 mg at baseline to 9.3 ± 15.1 mg at 12 months and 3.3 ± 4.0 mg at 18 months. 2/15 (13.3%) were off glucocorticoids when commencing avacopan therapy, 6/15 at 12 months (40%) and 8/15 at 18 months (53.3%). In nine with baseline eGFR < 90 ml/min, mean eGFR improved from 39.2 ± 21.2 to 46.11 ± 20.55 and 48.0 ± 23.3 ml/min; urine ACR declined from 124.1 ± 98.7 to 90.9 ± 92.5 (12 months) and 53.8 ± 79.2 mg/mmol (18 months).

Conclusions: Extended use of avacopan beyond 52 weeks was associated with further glucocorticoid reduction, improved disease control and kidney benefit in this complex set of patients.

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Systematic review of efficacy and safety of avacopan in real-world clinical practice

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Background/Aims: Avacopan, a complement 5a receptor (C5aR) antagonist, is a therapeutic option for patients with antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV), and is used as a steroid-sparing agent. The efficacy and safety of avacopan were established in the pivotal phase III ADVOCATE trial. However, there remains a paucity of real-world evidence to confirm these findings across diverse clinical settings and populations.

Methods: We conducted a systematic review of 13 real-world studies evaluating the clinical outcomes of avacopan in patients with AAV. Using a meta-analytic approach, we compared efficacy and safety outcomes reported in these studies with those of the main trial. Key endpoints included clinical remission, and incidence of adverse events.

Results: The aggregated real-world data demonstrated that the median time from diagnosis of AAV or relapse and initiation of avacopan was 22 days (range: 6-54 days). The clinical remission rates at 6 months as assessed in 313 patients were 89% (95% CI: 83-93%), while the rates of serious infection were 13% (95% CI: 9-18%). We observed a heterogeneity between populations when hepatotoxicity was assessed in real-world cohorts, with this signal being particularly pronounced in Japanese populations.

Conclusion: Avacopan has been found to demonstrate both safety and high efficacy in the treatment of AAV in real-world settings, with remission rates exceeding and serious infection rates comparable to those observed in clinical trial data. However, the higher incidence of hepatotoxicity in certain populations underscores the need for careful monitoring and pharmacovigilance studies to clarify risk factors and guide patient selection.

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An ongoing, randomised, phase II, double-blind, experimental medicine study of obinutuzumab versus rituximab in ANCA-associated vasculitis: ObiVas

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Background/Aims: In ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), B-cell depletion with rituximab – a type I anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody (mAb) – is standard of care. However, rituximab fails to induce remission in some patients and even in responders, repeated dosing is necessary to prevent disease relapse. Obinutuzumab – a humanised, type II anti-CD20 mAb – has demonstrated efficacy in lupus nephritis and more potently depletes tissue B cells than rituximab in pre-clinical models.

Methods: ObiVas is an ongoing randomised, phase II, double-blind controlled trial comparing the effects of rituximab and obinutuzumab in induction treatment of proteinase 3 ANCA (PR3-ANCA)-positive AAV. 26 patients (newly diagnosed or relapsing) were recruited from a single centre and randomised 1:1 to receive 1000mg rituximab or obinutuzumab on Days 1 and 15, alongside tapering glucocorticoids. The primary endpoint is CD19+ B-cell depletion in nasal-associated lymphoid tissue (NALT), assessed as change from baseline to week 26. Secondary endpoints compare the safety and clinical efficacy of both Investigational Medicinal Products (IMPs) and their impact on immune biomarkers. Exploratory analyses are investigating effects on the secondary lymphoid tissue microenvironment. Patients are followed through to week 78.

Results: Recruitment was completed in January 2025, and the final NALT biopsy was in July 2025. All 26 patients received both IMP doses. At screening, the mean age of participants was 59.6 years (standard deviation (SD) 11.9) and 19 (73%) were male. 15 (57.6%) were newly diagnosed and 5 (19.2%) had prior rituximab exposure. The mean Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score-Wegner's Granulomatosis (BVAS/WG) was 6.7 (SD 3.1), the mean C-reactive protein (CRP) was 46.4 mg/L (SD 63.0) and the mean PR3-ANCA titre was 81.2 IU/ml (SD 60.5).

Conclusions: ObiVas is an ongoing phase II trial in AAV with a biomarker primary endpoint. Recruitment was completed on schedule, and the final trial visit is expected in July 2026.

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Obinutuzumab treatment for antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis

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Background: Anti-CD20 therapy with rituximab serves as the cornerstone for both induction and maintenance treatment in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Obinutuzumab, a humanized type II anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody, is designed for more potent and sustained B-cell depletion with improved tolerability. Due to the paucity of clinical evidence regarding obinutuzumab in AAV, we undertook this study to assess its efficacy and safety profile.

Methods: Twelve consecutive patients with AAV who received first obinutuzumab treatment between September 2022 and December 2024 were included in this retrospective study. Clinical and pathological data were collected at predefined time points.

Results: Four patients received obinutuzumab for induction therapy, and 8 for maintenance therapy. The median follow-up duration after obinutuzumab administration was 11 months. For those receiving obinutuzumab for induction therapy, only 1 patient progressed to end-stage renal disease after COVID-19 infection, while the other 3 achieved sustained complete remission. For those receiving obinutuzumab for maintenance therapy, no relapse occurred. Among all the patients, three experienced at least one severe adverse event following obinutuzumab therapy. B-cell reconstitution typically began 9–12 months after obinutuzumab administration, with some patients exhibiting delayed reconstitution beyond 2 years. Concomitant with B-cell depletion, ANCA levels gradually declined in most patients and became undetectable in half. Notably, ANCA levels continued to decrease for up to one year after obinutuzumab administration, even after B-cell reconstitution began.

Conclusion: Obinutuzumab was effective and well-tolerated in AAV patients, supporting its potential as an alternative anti-CD20 therapy for AAV.

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Preliminary results from the phase II ImlifidARDSe.01 trial of imlifidase plus standard of care in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Pulmonary haemorrhage in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) remains a life-threatening manifestation with high morbidity and mortality. The PEXIVAS trial showed inconclusive results on the benefit of plasma-exchange, while ANCA titre kinetics were not reported. However, the rationale for rapid antibody removal remains strong. Imlifidase, an IgG-degrading enzyme derived from *Streptococcus pyogenes*, has shown promise in rapidly reducing pathogenic IgG in kidney transplantation and anti-glomerular basement membrane disease. We aimed to study safety and efficacy of imlifidase plus standard of care in AAV.

Methods: This monocentric, open-label phase II trial aims to enrol 10 adult patients with new or relapsing active AAV, ANCA titres > 50 AU/ml, and pulmonary haemorrhage. All participants will receive a single intravenous dose of imlifidase plus standard of care (high-dose glucocorticoids and either cyclophosphamide or rituximab). Primary endpoints are safety and seroconversion of ANCA-titre within 24h after imlifidase infusion. Secondary endpoints include ANCA titre dynamics, improvement in lung and kidney function, and 90-day survival.

Results: To date 6 patients have been included and treated. All patients showed ANCA cleavage greater than 90 % with a median reduction of 94,6 % and IQR of 93,8 – 99 % within 24 hours. 10 adverse events were observed in 4 patients with 4 severe adverse events in 2 patients. These included infections, pneumothorax and steroid-induced diabetes mellitus type 2. All of these SAEs were determined to be unrelated to imlifidase.

Conclusions: This is the first interventional trial investigating imlifidase in AAV with pulmonary haemorrhage. Early findings indicate rapid, and highly effective ANCA cleavage with positive safety profile. These preliminary data support the feasibility and potential efficacy of combining imlifidase with standard immunosuppression to achieve rapid ANCA depletion and clinical stabilization.

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SGLT2i Benefits in ANCA Vasculitis – retrospective analysis of global health records

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Background/Aims: SGLT2i improve renal and cardiovascular outcomes in chronic kidney disease. Evaluating the benefits of SGLT2i in patients with RPGN is challenging as patients with a rapid loss of function within a few weeks will less likely receive SGLT2i for nephroprotection than patients with less aggressive disease. Proposals for prospective randomised controlled SGLT2i trials in ANCA vasculitis have unfortunately not been funded and the protective role of SGLT2i in vasculitis has therefore not been confirmed.

Methods: Using the TriNetX global federated health network, we searched for patients with a new diagnosis of ANCA vasculitis receiving SGLT2i with the primary endpoint end stage kidney disease (ESKD).

Results: An initial analysis revealed a significant benefit between the two groups (SGLT2i vs control, n= 1530, HR 0.403 p = 0.0004) in 1:1 propensity matched patients for age, gender, ethnicity, eGFR and comorbidities (hypertension, stroke, diabetes, neoplasm, ischaemic heart disease, heart failure). As hypothesised, significant number of patients in the control group reached died within the first 3 months (7% vs 2.3%). We then selected patients with a new diagnosis of vasculitis since 2018 only, removed patients suffering from ESKD within 3 months of diagnosis.

Here, 728 patients were included in each arm. SGLT2i use was associated with a reduced rate of Kidney replacement therapy (KRT) (HR 0.566, 95% CI 0.324–0.989). This analysis showed an absolute risk reduction of 4.5% over five years, corresponding to a number needed to treat (NNT) of 22. The wide confidence interval around the primary outcome reflects the relatively low number of events in both arms.

Conclusions: In this real-world analysis, SGLT2i use in patients with vasculitis was associated with a reduction in ESKD and death, with an NNT of 22 over five years. These findings suggest renal-protective effects of SGLT2i in systemic vasculitis transferrable from other kidney conditions.

Efficacy of anti-interleukin-5/receptor therapies on specific disease manifestations of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Results from the 1-year double-blind period and first year of the ongoing open-label extension (OLE) of the MANDARA trial (NCT04157348) demonstrated that >60% of patients with eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA), achieved remission; additionally, >40% discontinued oral glucocorticoids (OGCs). This analysis focuses on changes in individual items of active disease and long-term damage in EGPA over the same two-year period.

Methods: Patients (without active life- or organ-threatening manifestations at trial entry) who completed the double-blind period, could enter the OLE, during which they continued benralizumab (benra/benra) or switched from mepolizumab to benralizumab (mepo/benra). The protocol encouraged reduction in OGCs. Disease activity was measured by the Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score, while items of damage were measured by the Vasculitis Damage Index, up to Week 104.

Results: In total, 128 patients entered the OLE. At baseline, the most commonly reported airway-related manifestations were asthma (25.8% of patients), paranasal sinus involvement (15.6%), and bloody nasal discharge/crusts/ulcers/granulomata (14.1%). All of these manifestations resolved rapidly in most patients and were present in <4% of patients by Week 104. Sensory peripheral neuropathy (9.4%), arthralgia/arthritis (7.8%) and myalgia (6.3%) were the most reported non-airway manifestations at baseline, and their frequency also decreased rapidly to <3% by Week 104. Cutaneous (3.9%) and renal manifestations (1.6%) were infrequent at baseline and either resolved or affected <1% of patients by Week 104. Cardiac manifestations were absent at baseline; however, ischaemic cardiac pain and congestive cardiac failure experienced by one patient (0.9%), were present at Week 60. Overall, 29 new items of damage in 25 patients were recorded up to Week 104.

Conclusions: Among patients with EGPA, after two years of treatment with anti-IL-5/R therapies, mostly associated with substantial reductions in OGCs, there is little disease progressive organ damage, suggesting a durable effect for reducing both airway- and non-airway-related manifestations.

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Classification of relapses of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis after two years of treatment with anti-interleukin-5/receptor therapy

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Background/Aims: Results from the ongoing open-label extension (OLE) of the MANDARA trial (NCT04157348) have demonstrated that >60% of patients with EGPA achieved remission after two years of anti-interleukin-5/receptor (anti-IL-5/R) therapies. This analysis describes the types of relapses occurring in patients during the combined 1-year double-blind (DB) period and first year of the OLE.

Methods: 140 patients were randomized to the DB period, and 128 patients entered the OLE where they continued benralizumab (benra/benra) or switched from mepolizumab to benralizumab (mepo/benra). Relapse was defined as the presence of 1) active vasculitis (Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score >0); OR asthma; OR sinonasal disease, leading to 2) an increase in oral glucocorticoid dose to >4 mg/day; OR initiation or increase in other immunosuppressive therapy; OR hospitalisation for worsening EGPA. Relapses were classified as asthma-related, sinonasal-related, 'other' (not asthma or sinonasal-related), or a combination of these three types.

Results: During the DB period, 21 (30%) patients in each treatment group experienced a relapse; 15 (22.7%) patients in the benra/benra group and 20 (32.3%) patients in the mepo/benra group experienced a relapse during the OLE. 127 relapse events were reported during the DB (n=64) and first year of the OLE (n=63). Of these, 60 relapses occurred in the benralizumab (during the DB) or benra/benra group, and 67 in the mepolizumab (during the DB) or mepo/benra group. Over two-years, 103 (81.1%) relapses involved asthma and/or sinonasal disease: 40 (31.5%) asthma, 27 (21.3%) sinonasal, 16 (12.6%) asthma-sinonasal, and 8 (6.3%) asthma-sinonasal-other. There were 24 (18.9%)

exclusively 'other' types of relapses. The most common disease manifestations associated with the 'other' category of relapse were arthralgia/arthritis, myalgia and sensory peripheral neuropathy.

Conclusions: Among patients with EGPA treated with anti-IL-5/R therapies, the majority of relapses were airway-related. Arthralgia/arthritis, myalgia and sensory peripheral neuropathy were the most common manifestations of non-airway relapses.

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Comparative observational study of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis in patients treated with mepolizumab versus conventional immunosuppressants

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA) is a systemic vasculitis marked by asthma, eosinophilia, and multi-organ involvement. While corticosteroids and immunosuppressants are standard treatments, biologics like mepolizumab offer targeted therapy for eosinophil-driven inflammation. However, real-world comparative data remain scarce.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective study of 14 adult EGPA patients followed at the University Hospital of Navarra (2006–2025). Patients were grouped by treatment: those receiving mepolizumab (\pm rituximab) and those treated with other immunosuppressants. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and therapeutic data were collected. Eosinophil counts and serological markers in mepolizumab group were obtained prior to biologic initiation to avoid bias. Bivariate comparisons were performed using Mann-Whitney U and Fisher's tests.

Results: A total of 14 patients with EGPA were analysed: 6 received mepolizumab (\pm rituximab), and 8 were treated with other immunosuppressants. Asthma and ENT involvement were common in both groups. Although not statistically significant, cardiac involvement (50% vs. 14%) and myopathy (33% vs. 0%) were more frequent in the mepolizumab group, while peripheral nervous system involvement was more common in the non-mepolizumab group (57% vs. 17%). No significant differences were found in baseline immunological markers. Disease duration was significantly shorter in the mepolizumab group (median 29.5 vs. 210 months; $p = 0.008$), reflecting the more recent introduction of biologics. The cumulative prednisone dose over the past year was numerically higher in the mepolizumab group (2050 mg vs. 570 mg; $p = 0.133$), reflecting greater disease burden prior to switching to biologic therapy.

Conclusions: Although limited by small sample size, this study highlights distinct treatment patterns and clinical profiles in EGPA. Trends suggest that patients treated with mepolizumab may present with more active or refractory disease, including higher rates of cardiac and muscular involvement. Further studies are warranted to evaluate the steroid-sparing potential and long-term outcomes of biologic therapy in EGPA.

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Concomitant use of mepolizumab (MEP) early in the treatment of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) contributes to early glucocorticoids (GC) taper and eventual GC discontinuation

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Background/Aims: EGPA treatment requires glucocorticoids (GC), but the eventual discontinuation of GC has become a more realistic goal with the use of an IL-5 inhibitor. The aim of this study is to develop an optimal treatment strategy by examining the role of mepolizumab (MEP) in discontinuing GC and the differences depending on the timing of initiation of MEP combination therapy based on real-world clinical data from a single-centre cohort.

Methods: Medical records of 58 EGPA patients who visited to our institute until February 28, 2025, and could be followed up for more than 6 months were retrospectively collected from the EGPA cohort of our hospital and statistically analysed.

Results: GC was discontinued by the time of final follow-up in 21 of 34 patients in the MEP combination group and in 2 of 24 in the non-combination group ($P < 0.001$). Without maintenance phase cases, patients ($N = 26$) who underwent initial and re-induction therapy were divided into two groups: those who started MEP within 1 month (early group, $N = 18$) and those who started MEP more than 1 month later (late group, $N = 8$). When examining the mean dose trends from GC initiation to 12 months, the early group was able to reduce PSL doses significantly more rapidly than the late group at 2 and 3 months after initiation. The late group were started MEP in average of 65 ± 26 days after GC started, demonstrating a more rapid taper in GC dose after MEP started.

Conclusion: MEP contributes to achieving final GC-free status regardless of when it is administered in combination during any treatment phase. However, initiating its administration earlier, within one month of the start of induction therapy, may contribute to early reduction of GC dose and a reduction in the total dose.

Mepolizumab as first line treatment for eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA): a retrospective cohort study by the European EGPA Study Group

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Background/Aims: The efficacy of mepolizumab in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) refractory to conventional immunosuppressants is well established, while data on its use as first treatment are lacking.

Methods: We included patients receiving mepolizumab 100 or 300 mg/4 weeks as first-line treatment option for EGPA, at centres belonging to the European EGPA Study Group. Previous use of glucocorticoids was accepted. Complete and partial responses (CR and PR) were defined according to literature [Wechsler, NEJM 2017; Bettiol, A&R 2022].

Results: 151 patients received first-line mepolizumab treatment (79 female; median age 59, IQR 51-67 years; 29% ANCA+), as compared to 403 patients starting after conventional immunosuppressants.

Among first-line users, 84 (56%) patients started at the dosage of 100 mg/4 weeks, and 67 (44%) at 300 mg/4 weeks. Among non-first line mepolizumab users, 181 (45%) started on 100mg/4 weeks and 222 (55%) on 300mg/4 weeks.

At time of treatment beginning, the median BVAS was 4 (IQR 2-7) and 4 (2-6) in the two groups.

At 3 months, CR and PR were achieved in 18/135 (13%) and 55/135 (41%) of first-line users, as compared to 63/380 (17%) and 149/380 (39%) of non-first line users ($p=n.s.$ for CR).

At 6 months, 35/142 (25%) and 44/142 (31%) of first-line users were on CR and PR, respectively, as compared to 131/382 (34%) and 105/382 (27%) of non-first line users ($p<0.05$ for CR).

At 12 months, 56/118 (47%) and 20/118 (17%) of first line users had achieved CR and PR, as compared to 146/349 (42%) and 70/349 (20%) of non-first line users ($p=n.s.$).

At 24 months, 46/89 (52%) of first line users were on CR and 12/89 (13%) on PR, as compared to 107/245 (44%) and 49/245 (20%) of non-first line users ($p=n.s.$).

Conclusions: Mepolizumab is associated with good long-term response rates, irrespectively of the treatment line.

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Analysis of timing of mepolizumab initiation for remission induction on clinical outcomes in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA): a single centre experience in Japan

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Background/Aims: Mepolizumab (MPZ) is an effective treatment for eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA). However, the impact of starting MPZ early in the disease course remains unclear. This study aimed to evaluate whether initiating MPZ therapy soon after EGPA diagnosis improves clinical outcomes.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 40 EGPA patients (12 men, 28 women; 17 MPO-ANCA positive) treated with MPZ at our centre from 2018 to 2024. Patients were divided into two groups: Early (MPZ started within 6 months of EGPA onset) and Late (MPZ started more than 6 months after onset). Clinical parameters including Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) and prednisolone (PSL) doses were assessed. Remission was defined as BVAS of 0 and PSL ≤ 4 mg/day.

Results: The Early group included 16 patients, and the Late group 24. The groups were similar in age at onset (59.0 ± 11.7 vs. 56.2 ± 12.4 years) and BVAS at onset (12 ± 7 vs. 13 ± 5). The mean interval from onset to MPZ initiation was 76.3 ± 60.2 days in the Early group and over 4,467 \pm 8,356 days in the Late group. PSL dose at MPZ initiation was higher in the Early group (30.8 ± 19.1 mg/day) than in the Late group (5.6 ± 2.6 mg/day). At 24 months, the Early group had significantly lower PSL requirements (1.6 ± 1.9 vs. 3.7 ± 2.5 mg/day) and higher remission rates (93 vs 45 %) compared to the Late group.

Conclusions: These results showed that long-term MPZ therapy is effective and safe in EGPA management. Starting MPZ within six months of disease onset may reduce glucocorticoid dependency and improve remission rates after two years, supporting early MPZ initiation in clinical practice.

Switching the dose of mepolizumab in patients with Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA): a European EGPA Study Group retrospective multicentre real-world study

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Background/Aims: Mepolizumab is effective in controlling disease activity in patients with Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA). In clinical practice, both 100 mg and 300 mg/4 weeks regimens are used, but data on dosage switching and clinical outcomes after switch are lacking.

Methods: We included patients with EGPA treated with mepolizumab at centres belonging to the European EGPA Study Group and the French Vasculitis Study Group, who switched from 100 mg to 300 mg/4weeks or vice versa for any reason. Complete and partial responses (CR and PR) after switching were assessed according to the literature [Wechsler, NEJM 2017; Bettiol, A&R 2022].

Results: 170 patients were included: 141 switched from 100 to 300 mg/4 weeks, and 26 from 300 to 100 mg/4 weeks; 3 switched from 100 mg/4 weeks to 100 mg/3 weeks, and 2 from 100 to 200 mg/4 weeks.

Dose increase was due to treatment inefficacy, particularly for asthma (n=77) or ENT (n=69) symptoms. 16 patients increased their dose for other reasons, including pulmonary involvement (n=7), skin rash (n=2), and other causes (n=7). After dosage increase from 100 to 300 mg/4 weeks, 41% achieved CR and 28% had PR, after a median time of 4 months (IQR 3–6). Only 2 patients experienced worsening of asthma or ENT symptoms.

Conversely, dose de-escalated to 100 mg every 4 weeks was mostly due to remission (n=22), and 4 patients decreased for safety or adherence issues. Among patients who decreased dosage to 100 mg/4 weeks, 6 (23%) reported a worsening of asthma or ENT symptoms.

Conclusions: Increasing mepolizumab dose to 300 mg/ 4 weeks provides additional clinical benefit in EGPA patients with suboptimal response to 100 mg/ 4 weeks. De-escalation from 300 to 100 mg/ 4 weeks seems safe in patients with sustained remission.

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Longitudinal impact \geq 6 years of anti-IL-5 therapy in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA)

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Background/Aims: MIRRA (Mepolizumab) and MANDARA (Benralizumab) Clinical Trial results paved the way for anti-IL5 therapeutics in EGPA. This Real-World Longitudinal study conducted over 6 years aims to analyse the long-term outcome for a cohort of patients commenced on mepolizumab 100mg.

Methods: In this retrospective descriptive study, 20 EGPA patients commenced on MEPO, were assessed for clinical response and immunosuppression change at Pre-MEPO, MEPO commencement, 12,24,36,48,60,72,84 M time -points.

Results: All 20 patients remain on treatment at Year 6. Two patients were switched to dupilumab and one to tezepelumab. 17 patients are on mepolizumab, benralizumab or reslizumab with on-going treatment. The mean steroid maintenance dose reduced by 50% in 12M and continued to decrease to 72M; Mean \pm SD [M0] 17.48 \pm 10.4, [M12] 9.05 \pm 5.6, [M72] 3.436 \pm 5.5. 11 patients are no GC therapy, and 5 on adrenal replacement only. Reduction in bolus steroid doses also occurred. Mean \pm SD [M0] 2.52 \pm 1.97, [M1] 1.4 \pm 1.3, [M72] 0.45 \pm 0.87. Adjuvant conventional immunosuppressants (ACIS), reduced over time from 10/20 (50%) at M0 to 4/20 (20%) by M24, to 3/20 (15%) at 6 years. Hospital admissions are reduced with treatment Mean \pm SD [M0] 1.25 \pm 1.4, [M1] 0.05 \pm 0.22, [M72] 0.15 \pm 0.48. Clinical benefits include improvement in FEV1 (M0) 2.11 \pm 0.66 to (M12) 2.39 \pm 0.62 and (M72) 2.4 \pm 0.68 and the (m)asthma quality of life questionnaire (M0) 3.44 \pm 1.3 and (M72) 5.2 \pm 1.1. ANCA serology normalized, BVAS reduced from median 5 [3-7], to 0 [0-1] by 24M. At 6yrs, n= 11 BRZ, MEPO[7], Res[1], DUP[1]. One patient required cyclophosphamide along with anti-IL5 therapy for myocarditis. Two patient have Rituximab, one for EGPA/ Rheumatoid arthritis overlap.

Conclusions: Anti-IL 5 therapy offers a long-term strategy for reduction GC burden, reduced hospital admission and improvement in clinical parameters including lung function. Well-tolerated, anti-IL5 agents can be used singularly or in conjunction with other immunosuppressants. Switching between agents is an option for continued treatment.

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Anti-IL-5 Receptor blockade therapy in relapsing eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) – a longitudinal study

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Background/Aims: The MANDARA Clinical Trial has underscored the role for Benralizumab in the management of relapsing EGPA. The aim of this study is to analyse the outcome of anti-IL5 cytokine receptor blockade with benralizumab (BRZ) therapy, focusing upon steroid minimization in a real-world cohort for ≥ 60 months.

Methods: In this retrospective descriptive study, 8 refractory EGPA patients received 30mg BRZ 4 weekly for the first three doses, followed by 8 weekly thereafter. Immunotherapy assessment time points including PRE-BRZ commencement up to M60s after initiation.

Results: All 8 patients commenced on BRZ have continued BRZ therapy throughout the analysis timeframe median duration 68M (range 67 – 77M)], due to clinical benefit. At T0, the mean prednisolone dose was 9.75mg, at T12 (5.21mg), T24 (3.18mg) and at last follow-up \geq T60 1.06mg. Six patients are no longer on corticosteroids and one is on an adrenal insufficiency program. Adjuvant conventional immunosuppressants numbers (ACIS) remained static with regard to low-dose MMF n=3, over time. One patient had 2 cycles of cyclophosphamide for myocarditis, with adjuvant BRZ well tolerated.

Conclusions: The relapsing nature of EGPA places a dependency of therapy on steroids. This study demonstrated ongoing continuity of anti-IL5 with reduction in GC, achieving cessation in a high proportion. This is in conjunction with high rates of disease remission and tolerability. This study demonstrates that anti-IL5 receptor therapy serves as a favourable model for steroid and conventional immunosuppressant minimization in EGPA in the longer-term real world setting.

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Concordance between treatment guideline and daily clinical practice in the management of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis: A web-questionnaire survey conducted by JPVAS

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) represents a distinct clinical subtype of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). In Japan, treatment recommendations for EGPA are provided in the 2020 Treatment Guide (in Japanese) and the 2023 Clinical Practice Guidelines for AAV; however, the extent to which these guidelines are referenced in daily clinical practice by physicians managing EGPA remains unclear. In this study, we aimed to examine real-world clinical practices in the treatment of EGPA across Japan and evaluate concordance with national treatment guidelines.

Methods: A cross-sectional, web-based survey was conducted by JPVAS between February 14 and 19, 2024. Physicians from rheumatology, pulmonology, and neurology departments who had treated EGPA within the past 24 months were invited to complete a 17-item questionnaire. The survey evaluated actual prescribing behaviour, future treatment preferences, responses to two clinical scenarios, and the frequency of guideline use.

Results: A total of 220 responses were obtained, comprising 110 rheumatologists (50.0%), 55 neurologists (25.0%), and 55 pulmonologists (25.0%). The majority of participants were male (87.7%) and hospital-based physicians (97.7%), with 70.9% in their 30s or 40s. Regarding actual prescribing behaviour, cyclophosphamide (77.3%) and mepolizumab (73.2%) were frequently used with glucocorticoids (GCs) for remission induction. In future treatment preferences for remission induction, GC monotherapy was the most commonly selected option overall (31.4%), but its use decreased to 14.8% for severe cases. GC plus mepolizumab was the most frequently selected regimen for both maintenance and relapse. Responses to clinical scenarios revealed partial divergence from guideline-based recommendations, particularly regarding the limited use of immunosuppressants and the preferential use of mepolizumab.

Conclusions: This study revealed a modest but clear evidence–practice gap in EGPA management in Japan. Broader dissemination of updated guidelines and enhanced interdisciplinary collaboration may help align clinical practice with evidence-based standards and improve patient care.

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A phase 2, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial of NS-229, a selective JAK1 inhibitor, for treatment of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare form of ANCA-associated vasculitis that in almost all patients involves asthma, rhinosinusitis, and eosinophilia. Although the aetiology of EGPA is not known, there are data supporting a key role of several cytokines and both the humoral and cellular immune pathways in the pathophysiology of this disease. Glucocorticoids remain the mainstay of treatment for EGPA, although drugs that inhibit IL-5, including both mepolizumab and benralizumab, are now routinely prescribed to treat EGPA. Despite these treatments, relapses are common, and many patients do not achieve sustained remission. NS-229 is a novel, highly-selective JAK1 inhibitor expected to act on eosinophils, T cells and B cells, all associated with the pathophysiology of EGPA.

Methods: NS229-P2-01 study is a phase 2, multicentre, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled, randomized, trial of NS-229 compared with placebo in subjects with EGPA. A total of 45 subjects will be enrolled and randomized into NS-229 or placebo groups in a 2:1 ratio. Patients with EGPA are eligible for this trial if they have active disease within 60 days of baseline despite use of OGCs. Patients on background treatment with an IL-5 inhibitor are eligible for the trial. The primary efficacy endpoint of the trial is the proportion of subjects in remission at Week 28 with OGC \leq 4.0 mg/day with several secondary endpoints.

Results: The NS229-P2-01 trial is currently ongoing in Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Spain, the United Kingdom, and the United States.

Conclusions: The NS229-P2-01 trial in EGPA includes several novel aspects for a randomized trial in EGPA, including testing of a JAK1 inhibitor, inclusion of patients on background treatment with anti-IL5 therapy, and a mix of efficacy outcomes that includes remission, relapse, worsening, and patient-reported outcomes. Recruitment into this trial is expected to be completed in 2025.

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IgA vasculitis with renal involvement: clinical practice variation and trial feasibility in Australia and New Zealand

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis (IgAV) is the most common form of childhood vasculitis and is often self-limited. Less common, adults more often have severe, relapsing disease. Evidence is limited and generally extrapolated from IgA Nephropathy. The aim of this study was to establish the current standard of care and feasibility of a platform clinical trial (enrolling children and adults) with renal biopsy proven IgAV in Australia and New Zealand (ANZ).

Methods: an electronic survey was circulated to adult and paediatric nephrologists, rheumatologists and immunologists in ANZ in August 2025.

Results: There were 41 respondents from 27 health services (4 NZ, 1 ACT, 11 NSW, 4 QLD, 5 SA, 1 TAS, 3 WA, 12 VIC). 21 cared for adults, 17 children and 3 both. Most were nephrologists (32 nephrologists, 7 rheumatologists and 2 immunologists) with 44% having more than 15 years' experience post fellowship. Analysed via centre, paediatric centres reported an incidence of 6.7 new patients per year (4-12) with biopsy proven IgAV requiring immunosuppression. Adult centres reported 2.6 new patients per year (1-10). Paediatricians were less likely to pursue a diagnostic biopsy (11 vs 100%).

When presented with several clinical scenarios there was significant variation in care. With milder disease, 50% paediatric respondents initially usually managed patients conservatively, compared to 24% of adult physicians, and nominated higher doses of corticosteroids for shorter duration. In severe IgAV (RPGN) adult physicians were more likely to use cyclophosphamide (62% vs 40%) and plasma exchange (19% vs 5%), compared to paediatricians who were more likely to use rituximab (45% vs 33%). 89% health services expressed interest in a platform clinical trial.

Conclusions: Effective therapies for IgAV with severe renal involvement are urgently needed. Substantial practice variation reflects equipoise about optimal treatment and it is feasible to explore clinical trial opportunities in ANZ.

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Plasma exchange for refractory IgA vasculitis

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Background/Aims: IgA Vasculitis (IgAV) in adults often has a relapsing/refractory course. Plasma exchange (PLEX) has been used in other vasculitides but it is unclear if it may have a role in IgAV. We present outcomes of patients with IgAV treated with PLEX at our centre.

Methods: Clinical records of adult patients who met 1990 ACR classification criteria for IgAV were screened and those receiving ≥ 1 course (5 sessions) of PLEX identified. Response was defined as an improvement in Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) 1 month after PLEX course completion and categorised as “partial” (BVAS ≤ 3 and prednisolone ≤ 10 mg/day) or “complete” (BVAS=0). Relapse was defined as BVAS >3 after initial response.

Results: Among 179 patients with IgAV, 12 (7%) received ≥ 1 course of PLEX for refractory or relapsing disease. Eight patients had active skin involvement and 10/12 (83%) nephritis. PLEX was combined with glucocorticoids and various immunosuppressive agents, including cyclophosphamide (5/12). All but one patient reported a response at 1 month, which was “complete” in five (42%). Ten patients (91%) relapsed a median of 3 months (IQR 2-7) after PLEX and 8/10 (80%) resumed PLEX and achieved response. Six patients (50%) continued a “chronic” regimen of PLEX (1-2 monthly sessions) for a median of 85 months (25-141), as this was the only therapy that could control skin (4/6) and/or kidney manifestations (3/6). Three patients (25%) developed kidney failure and two (17%) died during follow-up.

Conclusions: In this small cohort, PLEX was associated with improved disease control. Many patients experienced further relapses but some maintained remission through a “chronic” PLEX regimen. As highlighted by the high risk of death or kidney failure, more effective therapies for IgAV are needed but PLEX should be considered as a rescue treatment in severe/refractory cases.

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Phenotype-driven use of infliximab versus adalimumab in Behçet's disease: comparative effectiveness, safety, and drug survival in a single-centre cohort

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Background/Aims: Behçet's disease (BD) manifests across a wide clinical spectrum, from mucocutaneous lesions to sight- or life-threatening ocular, vascular, and neurological involvement. While colchicine and conventional immunosuppressants are effective in many patients, biologics are required for severe or refractory disease. Tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (TNFi), particularly infliximab (IFX) and adalimumab (ADA), are widely used. This study compared the indications, effectiveness, safety, and drug survival of IFX and ADA in BD.

Methods: 87 BD patients (started first 45 IFX, 42 ADA) who received TNFi between April 2020 and April 2025 were enrolled. Demographics, clinical phenotypes, treatment details, and adverse events were analysed.

Results: At baseline, vascular (51.1% vs. 26.2%, $p=0.015$) and neurological involvement (15.6% vs. 2.4%, $p=0.036$) were more frequent in the IFX, while ocular involvement was more common in ADA (45.2% vs. 28.9%). Initial complete remission rates were similar (IFX 75.6% vs. ADA 78.6%). At last follow-up, complete remission remained comparable (88.9% vs. 76.5%, $p=0.158$). However, relapses were more frequent (37.8% vs. 16.7%, $p=0.024$) and occurred earlier in IFX (median 8 vs. 13 months, $p=0.047$). Drug survival was similar (80% vs. 85.7%), with switches required in 20% (IFX) and 11.9% (ADA). IFX-treated patients more often received pulse steroids (53.3% vs. 11.9%, $p<0.001$), cyclophosphamide (33% vs. 0, $p<0.001$), and anticoagulants (33.3% vs. 14.3%, $p=0.033$). Concomitant azathioprine use exceeded 60% in both groups. Safety was favourable: adverse event rates were low and similar (15.6% vs. 16.7%), mainly mild infections or infusion/injection reactions; no serious adverse events occurred.

Conclusions: Both IFX and ADA demonstrated high effectiveness and acceptable safety in severe BD. IFX was predominantly used for vascular and neurological phenotypes requiring aggressive regimens, often in combination with cyclophosphamide and anticoagulants, whereas ADA was preferred in mucocutaneous and ocular disease. Despite higher relapse frequency with IFX, overall remission and drug survival were comparable. These findings emphasize phenotype-driven selection of TNFi and support individualized treatment strategies in BD.

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Impact of glucocorticoid tapering in giant cell arteritis: analysis from the SELECT-GCA trial

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Background/Aims: Serious infections (SI), herpes zoster (HZ), and opportunistic infections (OI) were assessed during glucocorticoid (GC) treatment and post-taper in patients with giant-cell arteritis (GCA) receiving upadacitinib 7.5mg or 15mg (UPA7.5/UPA15)+26-week GC-taper or placebo (PBO)+52-week GC-taper in SELECT-GCA.

Methods: GCA patients had prior exposure to ≥ 40 mg prednisone (or equivalent) daily, and baseline prednisone ≥ 20 mg daily. Kaplan-Meier was used to analyse adverse events through week 52. Event rates were per ≥ 1 event of same type.

Results: Baseline GC doses for UPA and PBO were similar. SI rates were lower with UPA than PBO through week 52 (UPA7.5, 7.9 [95% CI: 3.2–16.3]; UPA15, 7.9 [4.3–13.2]; PBO 12.7 [6.6–22.2] events/100 patient-years [E/100PY]). HZ rates were higher with UPA15 vs PBO (7.3 [3.9–12.5] vs 4.2 [1.2–10.9] E/100PY) and UPA7.5 (4.5 [1.2–11.6] E/100PY). OI rates were low but numerically higher with UPA15 vs PBO (2.2 [0.6–5.8] vs 1.1 [0–5.9] E/100 PY); none for UPA7.5.

In UPA-treated patients, SI rates were comparable during GC-taper (difference \leq week 26 UPA – PBO: 0.3 [-5.8–6.4] and -0.3 [-5.4–4.8] E/100PY for UPA7.5 and UPA15, respectively). Rates were lower post-taper with UPA vs PBO (>week 26 to 52: UPA7.5, -5.1 [-12.1–1.9]; UPA15, -4.6 [-11.1–2.0] E/100PY). HZ rates were similar with UPA during GC-taper (UPA7.5, -3.1 [95% CI: -7.8–1.6]; UPA15, 1.4 [-4.0–6.8] E/100PY) and post-GC taper (3.4 [95% CI: -0.4–7.2] and 1.7 [-0.2–3.6] E/100PY). Of 4 OI with UPA15, 3 occurred during GC-taper, 1 post-taper.

Conclusions: SI rates at 52 weeks were lower with UPA+26-week GC-taper vs PBO+52-week GC-taper, especially post-taper with UPA, suggesting GC use may increase SI risk. GC tapering did not affect HZ rates with UPA. Results support UPA15 with standardized GC tapering to reduce GC burden in older adults with higher infection risk.

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Glucocorticoid-sparing agents: indications in polymyalgia rheumatica

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) is an inflammatory disorder of older adults, primarily treated with glucocorticoids (GC). Despite guideline-based tapering, up to half of patients remain on GC two years after diagnosis, exposing them to cumulative toxicity. Although targeted therapies have emerged as promising alternatives, no consensus exists regarding the cumulative GC dose that should trigger GC-sparing strategies. The aim of this study was to model cumulative GC exposure across different PMR patient profiles and identify thresholds supporting timely initiation of GC-sparing therapies.

Methods: Standardized prescription models were developed following ACR/EULAR guidelines, accounting for body weight (50, 70, 100 kg) and relapse scenarios. Relapses were assumed to occur at week 24 and at subsequent tapering steps. Two models simulated GC-dependence at 10 mg/day and 5 mg/day over three years. Cumulative doses were compared across scenarios and submitted to a panel of French PMR experts, who were asked to define thresholds for introducing GC-sparing treatments.

Results: Cumulative GC doses ranged from 1.8 g (50-kg patient without relapse) to 11.4 g (100-kg patient with persistent 10-mg dependence over three years). Body weight and up to three isolated relapses had modest impact (<1.5 g variation across weights; +0.7 g for each of the relapses). In contrast, sustained dependence below 5–10 mg/day markedly increased exposure, with 3.4- to 6.1-fold higher doses compared to non-relapsing patients. Among 20 experts, the median cumulative threshold for initiating GC-sparing therapy was 3 g (IQR 2.75–4.5).

Conclusions: Our models highlight that GC dependence, even at low maintenance doses, drives substantial cumulative exposure in PMR. While weight and occasional relapses play a minor role, repeated failure of tapering rapidly escalates cumulative burden beyond toxicity thresholds reported in the literature. As the GC-dependency is highly associated to the first relapse, anti-IL6R might be proposed as soon as first relapse.

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Association of baseline frailty with glucocorticoid duration in an inception cohort of older adults with polymyalgia rheumatica

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Background/Aims: To examine the association between baseline frailty and the duration of glucocorticoid (GC) treatment in older adults with polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR).

Methods: We conducted an inception cohort study using Medicare claims from 2016–2022. Patients aged ≥ 66 years were included if they had: 1) ≥ 1 inpatient or ≥ 2 outpatient claims for PMR (ICD-10-CM M35.3) within 30–365 days, 2) GC prescriptions of 7.5–30 mg/day within 30 days of diagnosis with cumulative use ≥ 200 mg over ≥ 120 days, and 3) ≥ 1 year of baseline and ≥ 2 years of follow-up enrolment. Patients with prior PMR or giant cell arteritis were excluded. Frailty was defined using a validated claims-based frailty index during baseline, and classified as frail, pre-frail, and non-frail. The outcome of interest was GC discontinuation, defined as no GC prescriptions for ≥ 3 months. Multivariable adjusted hazard ratios (aHR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated using Fine and Gray competing risk models to account for death. Analyses were stratified by time period: the first year and years 2–5, to avoid proportional hazard violations.

Results: Among 17,695 patients, 30.7% were non-frail ($n=5435$), 56.7% pre-frail ($n=10,041$), and 12.6% frail ($n=2219$). Mean (SD) age was 77.9 (6.8) years, 91.5% were White, and 60.7% female. During follow-up, 1,256 deaths occurred (682 pre-frail, 464 frail).

In the first year, frail (aHR 1.91, 95% CI 1.10–1.29) and pre-frail (aHR 1.07, 95% CI 1.02–1.12) patients were slightly more likely to discontinue GC compared to non-frail patients. However, in years 2–5, frail (aHR 0.34, 95% CI 0.30–0.38) and pre-frail patients (aHR 0.73, 95% CI 0.68–0.77) were significantly less likely to discontinue GC. GC-sparing agents were prescribed in only 3.61% of patients during follow-up.

Conclusions: Frailty was common among older adults with PMR and was strongly associated with prolonged GC use beyond the first year.

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Harms associated with glucocorticoid use in auto-immune diseases: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Background/Aims: Glucocorticoids (GC) are associated with multiple adverse effects, but the magnitude of risk attributable to GC is not well established. We aimed to quantify the harms associated with higher versus lower GC exposure for the treatment of auto-immune diseases.

Methods: We searched MEDLINE, Embase and Cochrane register of controlled trials (inception to March 2023) for randomized controlled trials in adults that compared higher GC exposure to a lower one (lower dose/duration, or placebo/no-GC) for treatment of acute manifestations of auto-immune diseases. The outcomes were GC-related side effects (infection, serious infection, weight gain, cushing features, diabetes complications, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, mood disturbance, sleep disturbance, ophthalmic complications, and bone complications) and overall mortality. We calculated relative risks (RR) and absolute risk differences (ARD) with 95% confidence intervals (95%CI) for outcomes.

Results: There were 98 studies included (n=10,481 patients). For higher GC compared to lower/no-GC, there is high quality evidence of increased diabetes complications (RR 1.34 [1.01-1.70], ARD 1.2% [0%-2.3%]), moderate quality evidence of increased serious infections (RR 1.70 [1.09-2.66], ARD 4.9% [2.1%-7.7%]), and hypertension (RR 1.33 [0.99-1.77], ARD 2.6% [0.8%-4.4%]), but a reduction of mortality (RR 0.89 [0.78-1.01], ARD 0.4% [-1.3%-0.5%]). There is low quality evidence of increased infections (RR 1.36 [1.09-1.69], ARD 6.2% [1.4%-11.0%]), weight gain (RR 2.45 [1.70-3.53], ARD 9.9% [5.3%-14.4%]), cushing features (RR 1.53 [1.06-2.21], ARD 7.5% [2.3%-12.8%]), dyslipidaemia (RR 1.46 [1.08-1.98], ARD 5.5% [0.6%-10.4%]), mood disorders (RR 1.38 [1.05-1.82], ARD 1.4% [0.2%-3.1%]), sleep disturbance (RR 1.70 [1.07-2.72], ARD 8.6% [2.4%-14.7%]), fractures (RR 1.79 [0.99-3.21], ARD 1.4% [0.4%-2.5%]), ophthalmic complications (RR 1.17 [0.75-1.85], ARD 1.0% [-1.1%-3.0%]) and osteonecrosis (RR 1.16 [0.42-3.21], ARD 1.2% [-3.0%-2.4%]).

Conclusions: This study provides quantifiable measures of the adverse effects associated with higher GC exposure. These results can inform on management decisions when weighing the risks against potential benefits from greater GC exposure.

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Cost-effectiveness of tocilizumab in glucocorticoid-dependent polymyalgia rheumatica: results from the SEMAPHORE trial

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Background/Aims: The SEMAPHORE trial demonstrated the clinical benefit of tocilizumab (TCZ) in corticosteroid-dependent polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR). The aim of this study was to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of TCZ in this setting based on SEMAPHORE data.

Methods: SEMAPHORE was a multicentre, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial including 101 patients with active PMR, defined by PMR-AS CRP >10 and prednisone ≥10 mg/day. At week 24, 67.3% of TCZ patients achieved the primary endpoint—PMR-AS CRP <10 with prednisone reduction—versus 31.4% with placebo. Serious adverse events (SAEs) were slightly more frequent with placebo (19 vs. 17; NS).

The cost analysis included direct medical costs (drug and SAE management). Health utility was assessed every 12 weeks over 6 months using SF-6D and EQ-5D, expressed as quality-adjusted life years (QALYs). Incremental cost-utility ratios (ICURs) were calculated as cost difference divided by QALY difference between TCZ and placebo. Bootstrapping (25,000 iterations) provided 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Primary analyses were per protocol using EQ-5D.

Results: The per-protocol population comprised 82 patients (40 TCZ, 42 placebo). Over 24 weeks, mean ±SD total direct cost per patient was €5,315 ±1,446 in the TCZ group versus €1,232 ±2,005 with placebo. Drug cost accounted for 85.4% in the TCZ arm. QALY gain over 24 weeks was 0.31 vs. 0.29. The ICUR for TCZ versus placebo was €242,320/QALY (95% CI: €-1,969,752; 2,344,139), far exceeding the accepted €50–100,000/QALY threshold.

Conclusions: In glucocorticoid-dependent PMR, the ICUR of TCZ during the first 6 months is markedly above conventional thresholds. Cost-effectiveness may improve with targeted use in high responders or reduced acquisition costs, notably with biosimilars. However, the 6-month horizon may not fully capture long-term glucocorticoid-related adverse events.

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Revisiting the cost-effectiveness of tocilizumab in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Giant Cell Arteritis is a systemic vasculitis associated with significant morbidity, largely due to the adverse effects of high-dose and prolonged glucocorticoid therapy. Tocilizumab has demonstrated efficacy in reducing disease flares and glucocorticoid exposure, offering a steroid-sparing alternative. Recent real-world evidence has provided more robust and precise estimates of the relationship between current daily and cumulative oral glucocorticoid doses and the risk of developing a wide range of glucocorticoid-related adverse events. Given these findings, we revisited the cost-effectiveness of tocilizumab using an updated economic model based on the original 2017 Health Technology Assessment (HTA) submitted to NICE. The aim of this study was to assess the cost-effectiveness of Tocilizumab plus 26-week steroid tapering compared to placebo plus 52-week steroid tapering in patients with GCA.

Methods: A semi-Markov model with monthly cycles and a 10-year horizon was developed to simulate treatment outcomes in the GiACTA trial population. Health states included active GCA, initial remission, relapse, subsequent remission, and death. GCA-related complications and steroid-induced adverse events were modelled as health state modifiers.

Results: Tocilizumab plus glucocorticoids was associated with higher total costs and greater QALYs compared to glucocorticoids alone, yielding an ICER of £4,680 per QALY gained. Tocilizumab reduced the incidence and costs of major adverse events, including fractures, diabetes, and infections, resulting in £19,336 in cost savings. Event rates per 100 patient-years were consistently lower in the tocilizumab arm. Sensitivity analyses confirmed the robustness of these findings.

Conclusions: Tocilizumab, when combined with a 26-week glucocorticoid taper, is a cost-effective treatment for GCA, providing clinically meaningful gains in QALYs and significant reductions in glucocorticoid-related morbidity and associated costs. This analysis was conducted using the list price of tocilizumab, and cost-effectiveness is expected to improve further with the availability of lower-cost biosimilars. These findings support expanding the use of tocilizumab in GCA to include newly diagnosed patients.

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Secukinumab in the real-world management of giant cell arteritis: results from a multicentre Italian cohort

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Background/Aims: To evaluate the effectiveness, persistence and safety of subcutaneous secukinumab in giant cell arteritis (GCA).

Methods: We conducted a multicentre retrospective study across 11 Italian centres including GCA patients treated with subcutaneous secukinumab. Primary outcome was clinical remission (absence of GCA symptoms with normalization of CRP/ESR); secondary outcomes were drug retention, glucocorticoid-sparing, and safety. Retention was estimated with Kaplan–Meier methods. Drug failure was defined as discontinuation due to primary or secondary failure, intolerance, drug reactions, adverse events, or emerging contraindications.

Results: Among 32 patients (68.6% female; median age 74.5 years [IQR 70.2–80.0]) included, secukinumab was administered at 300mg/4w in 87.5% of cases and 150mg/4w in 12.5%. At secukinumab start, median disease duration was 21.5 months [7.8–50.3]). At diagnosis, 46.9% had cranial GCA, 37.5% large-vessel GCA, and 40.6% both. Visual symptoms were reported in 11 patients. Most patients had prior therapy failure (53.1% methotrexate; 71.9% tocilizumab). Before starting secukinumab, 27 patients (84.4%) had experienced at least one relapse, and 16 (50.0%) had two or more. Median follow-up was six months.

Clinical remission was observed in 74% (20/27) patients at 3 months, 79% (15/19) at 6 months and 89% (8/9) at 12 months. Median prednisone dose decreased from 7.5 mg/day [0.9–19.0] at baseline to 3.75 mg/day [0–5.0] at last follow-up; 22.7% discontinued prednisone. Median CRP and ESR remained stable from baseline ($p=0.60$ and $p=0.15$, respectively).

Six- and twelve-month drug retentions were 89.8% and 70.7%, respectively. Five (18.5%) patients discontinued treatment (4 relapses; 1 pericarditis). No injection-site reactions were reported. There was one death (suicide) at 12 months, and 15 infections, with only one requiring hospitalization.

Conclusions: In this multicentre real-world cohort, largely pre-treated with conventional and biologic agents, secukinumab was associated with high short-term retention, frequent clinical remission among evaluable patients, and meaningful glucocorticoid-sparing effect.

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Exposure to anticoagulant agents and the risk of major adverse cardiovascular events in newly diagnosed giant cell arteritis (GCA): a population-based study

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Background/Aims: Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA) is the most common vasculitis in adults and carries an increased risk of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE). Although anti-thrombotic therapy is frequently prescribed in clinical practice, its impact on cardiovascular outcomes in GCA remains uncertain. This study investigates whether anticoagulants exposure in newly diagnosed GCA patients reduces the risk of MACE.

Methods: Patients with biopsy-confirmed GCA from the population-based Skåne vasculitis cohort (southern Sweden) were included and matched (1:10) to controls by sex and age. MACE, defined as stroke, myocardial infarction, or pulmonary embolism, were identified via ICD codes in the Skåne Healthcare Register. Exposure to anticoagulants was assessed within 6 months before and 1 month after diagnosis, using ATC codes recorded in the regional drug register for both outpatient prescriptions and in-hospital-administered drugs. Cox-regression models were fitted to estimate the Hazard ratio (HR) of MACE among exposed vs. non-exposed.

Results: 651 patients with GCA and 5923 controls were included. 117 cases (18%) and 955 (16%) controls were exposed to anticoagulants around diagnosis. At one-year post-diagnosis, 38 cases (5.8%) and 96 controls (1.6%, $p<0.001$) experienced MACE, increasing by two years to 49 (7.5%) and 192 (3.2%; $p<0.001$), respectively. Within the GCA cohort, exposed patients presented a higher risk of MACE compared to non-exposed both at one year (15% vs. 3.7%, $p=0.001$) and at two years (16% vs. 5.6%, $p<0.001$). In adjusted model (for diabetes, hypertension and atrial fibrillation), drug exposure was associated with increased risk of MACE (HR 7.21, 95% CI 1.9–27.3, $p=0.004$ at one year; HR 4.33, 1.58–11.9, $p=0.004$ at two years).

Conclusions: Despite comparable rates of exposure, GCA patients have a significantly higher risk of MACE than controls. Within the GCA cohort, anticoagulants exposure around diagnosis is associated with increased MACE risk at 1 and 2 years.

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Impact of tocilizumab on haemostasis and bleeding in autoimmune diseases

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Background/Aims: Tocilizumab (TCZ), a humanized monoclonal antibody targeting the interleukin-6 receptor, is widely used for the treatment of autoimmune diseases such as giant cell arteritis, Takayasu arteritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Growing clinical experience has revealed rare but clinically relevant bleeding complications. We comprehensively reviewed the current knowledge on TCZ-related haemostatic changes and bleeding complications in vasculitis and other autoimmune diseases and provide suggestions for management strategies.

Methods: We conducted a narrative synthesis of the available literature on the impact of tocilizumab (TCZ) on haemostasis, particularly in patients with autoimmune diseases. Relevant publications were identified through targeted searches of PubMed/MEDLINE and Embase up to 13 August 2025, additional references were retrieved by manual review of citations from key articles. Eligible sources included mechanistic studies, preclinical models, clinical trials, observational cohorts, and case reports on IL-6 blockade and haemostasis.

Results: By inhibiting the IL-6/IL-6 receptor signalling pathway, TCZ can induce hypofibrinogenemia, thrombocytopenia, and rarely factor XIII (FXIII) deficiency. Consistent reporting of these side effects is lacking in landmark trials. Thrombocytopenia occurs in 5-20% of patients but is mostly mild. Hypofibrinogenemia is the most frequent haemostatic change with cohort studies reporting incidences of 29-75%; up to 40% of patients reaching levels <1.5g/l. In those with hypofibrinogenemia, mild bleeding complications occur in 0-29%. The clinical spectrum of bleeding with a possible relationship with TCZ use extends to postoperative bleeding, severe hematomas and diffuse intravascular coagulation. Routine coagulation parameters are frequently normal, masking significant hypofibrinogenemia or FXIII deficiency.

Conclusion: In light of expanding TCZ use, clinicians should consider targeted laboratory monitoring of platelets, fibrinogen and FXIII, especially in patients with risk factors for bleeding like advanced age, use of antithrombotic drugs and in the peri-operative setting. In patients at risk of bleeding with stable inflammatory disease, a short pre-operative interruption of TCZ may be advisable.

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Efficacy of colchicine in difficult to treat Takayasu arteritis with persistent systemic inflammation

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Background/Aims: The transcriptome studies suggest role of IL-1 pathways in pathogenesis of TAK. Colchicine exerts anti-fibrotic effect on arterial wall in patients with cardiovascular disease by acting on the IL1 pathway in neutrophils and macrophages. In this study, we report the efficacy of colchicine in patients with difficult to treat TAK (D2TTAK).

Methods: Details of patients satisfying ACR EULAR 2022 criteria for TAK who received colchicine were recorded retrospectively. Inability to achieve complete remission in spite of at least 2 disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) was considered as D2TTAK. Complete remission was defined as no new signs and symptoms of TAK with normal inflammatory markers and no angiographic progression. Response to colchicine was defined as attainment of Indian Takayasu arteritis score (ITAS 2010) of 0 with either normalisation or 2-fold decrease in CRP without progression in angiography, if available.

Results: 10 patients [9 females, age: 27.9± 4.6 years, symptom duration: 42.4± 18.6 months] received colchicine either as monotherapy (n=4) or add-on therapy to other DMARDs (n=6). The indications for initiating colchicine were raised CRP in all, with evidence of clinical activity or angiographic progression in 3 and 2 patients respectively, despite prior therapy with 4 (2-6) DMARDs. During a follow up of 18.2± 4.7 months, 9 patients were clinically inactive with ITAS 2010=0 while CRP normalised/decreased in 9 (90%) patients. Repeat imaging at 11 (8-12.8) months in 8 patients showed stable/regressed disease in 6 (75%) while progression in 2 patients. Overall, 7 (70%) patients had response to colchicine as per composite outcome. The median CRP, ESR and steroid dose reduced significantly after initiation of colchicine.

Conclusions: In this first report, colchicine was an effective and safe add-on therapy for controlling disease activity in patients with D2TTAK with persistent systemic inflammation despite multiple DMARDs.

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Efficacy of leflunomide in active Takayasu arteritis: a randomized double-blind placebo-controlled trial

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Background/Aims: To investigate the efficacy and safety of leflunomide (LEF) versus placebo for Takayasu arteritis (TAK).

Methods: This randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial recruited 116 active patients from six centres across China. Patients were randomized 1:1 to receive prednisone (0.6 mg/kg/d, p.o.) and LEF (20 mg/d, p.o.) or placebo for 24 weeks. By week 24, patients in LEF group not achieving clinical remission discontinued; the others received LEF (20 mg/d) from week 25 to week 52. The primary outcome was clinical remission at week 24.

Results: Forty-nine and 52, 45 and 48 patients were included in LEF and placebo group of modified intention-to-treat (mITT) and per-protocol set (mPPS). In mITT population, clinical remission was achieved in 44/49 (89.8% [81.3-98.3]) LEF- vs. 45/52 (86.5% [77.3-95.8]) placebo-treated patients. The same trend was observed in mPPS analyses. Lower prednisone dose (11.6 [3.8] vs. 13.7 [6.7] mg/d, $p = 0.07$) and greater reduction in least square mean (6.1 [-0.5 to 11.8]) was demonstrated in LEF group at week 24. Post hoc analyses indicated a risk difference (LEF minus placebo) of 16.2% (0.7–28.6) in previously treated subgroup. Adverse events were observed in 13 (24.5%) LEF- and 22 (39.3%) placebo-treated patients. Serious adverse events were reported in six LEF- and three placebo-treated patients. One death was reported in placebo group.

Conclusions: The primary endpoint was not met, but results suggest potential benefits for LEF to reduce prednisone dose and induce remission in previously treated patients, serving as an alternative choice for TAK.

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Long-term outcome of molecular targeted drugs in Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Molecular targeted drugs such as tocilizumab (TCZ) and tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (TNFi) are increasingly used in Takayasu arteritis (TAK), particularly in relapsed cases. However, data on their long-term effectiveness and switching patterns remain limited. We aimed to evaluate the long-term efficacy and switching outcomes of these agents in TAK.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of 135 patients with TAK treated at Tohoku University Hospital, one of the leading referral centres for TAK in Japan. All patients fulfilled either the ACR/EULAR classification criteria or the JCS diagnostic criteria. Clinical characteristics, use and switching of molecular targeted drugs, retention rates, treatment response, and safety outcomes were evaluated between 2018 and 2024.

Results: Fifty-five patients (40.1%) received molecular targeted drugs. TCZ was most commonly used (n=43), followed by TNFi (n=19), JAK inhibitors (n=6), abatacept (n=2), rituximab (n=1), and ustekinumab (n=2). 11 patients required ≥ 2 agents; five used ≥ 3 . Median follow-up duration was 63 months. Retention rates were 70.0% for TCZ and 78.9% for TNFi. TCZ was discontinued in 12 cases due to relapse (n=5), infection (n=3), worsening extra-arterial comorbidities (n=3), or adverse events (n=1). Eight of these patients were successfully switched to TNFi and remained on therapy with low-dose prednisolone. Notably, 16 TCZ-treated patients discontinued glucocorticoids, with 12 remaining relapse-free and stable on imaging. Patients with extra-arterial manifestations (e.g., ulcerative colitis, arthritis, hearing loss) or history of vascular surgery were more likely to discontinue TCZ. Serious adverse events included severe colitis (n=3) and infective endocarditis (n=2) under TCZ therapy. The mean prednisolone dose decreased from 10.2 mg/day before treatment to 3.6 mg/day at last follow-up.

Conclusions: Molecular targeted therapies demonstrated durable efficacy and steroid-sparing effects in TAK. TNFi was a viable option after TCZ failure. These findings highlight the need for tailored treatment algorithms in relapsed or refractory TAK.

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Outcomes of an intravenous-to-subcutaneous infliximab (CT-P13) strategy in Takayasu arteritis: a proof-of-concept prospective study

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Background/Aims: To evaluate persistence, outcomes, safety, and remission maintenance after switching from intravenous infliximab (IV-IFX) to subcutaneous infliximab (SC-IFX, CT-P13) in patients with Takayasu arteritis (TA).

Methods: Prospective single-centre observational study of consecutive adults with TA in sustained clinical, laboratory, and PET remission switched from IV-IFX to SC-IFX 120 mg every 2 weeks. Assessments at baseline, 6 and 12 months included Indian Takayasu Clinical Activity Score (ITAS2010), Disease Extent Index for Takayasu Arteritis (Dei.TAK), PET vascular activity score (PETVAS), C- reactive protein/Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (CRP/ESR), Large-Vessel Vasculitis Index of Damage (LVVID), and safety data. The primary objective was 12-month drug persistence. Secondary outcomes included remission rates, changes in ITAS2010, Dei.TAK, PETVAS, acute-phase reactants (CRP, ESR), damage accrual (LVVID), and safety.

Results: Nine women (median age 35 [IQR 28–44] years) were included. The median IV-IFX exposure prior to the switch was 60 [IQR 24–72] months. Twelve-month drug persistence was 77.8%. One patient discontinued early due to an injection-site reaction, and another experienced a relapse at 12 months that required a therapy change. At 12 months, 87.5% (7/8) patients remained in remission. CRP and ESR remained stable ($p=0.297$ and $p=0.068$, respectively). PETVAS was similar to pre-switch values ($p=0.589$). No progression of vascular damage was observed. No serious adverse events occurred.

Conclusions: IV-to-SC IFX switching was feasible, well tolerated, and generally maintained remission over 12 months in most TA patients, with stable metabolic imaging and no damage progression. These findings support SC-IFX as a practical maintenance strategy, warranting confirmation in larger multicentre cohorts.

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Use of JAK inhibitors in patients with refractory Takayasu arteritis: A worldwide retrospective study

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Background/Aims: In this worldwide multi-centre study, we aimed to assess the efficacy and safety of Janus-Kinase Inhibitors (JAKi) in patients with TAK refractory to conventional and biologic treatments.

Methods: Patients with a diagnosis of TAK were included in this retrospective study. Physician global assessment (PGA) was used as the gold standard definition of activity. Complete remission was defined as no new signs and symptoms of vascular disease assessed by a physician, normalization of acute phase reactants (APR) and reduction of GC dose under 10 mg/day of prednisolone or its equivalent at the third month of treatment. Partial response was defined as at least 50% decrease in PGA score, APR and at least 50% reduction of initial GC dose at the third month.

Results: Data were collected from 25 patients with TAK (mean age:34.5±11 years; female/male:24/1; mean disease duration:8.1±6 years) from 8 centres. All patients were refractory to both conventional immunosuppressives (ISs) and biologic agents, but for 2 patients who were refractory only to conventional ISs. Sixteen (64%) patients received >1 biologic agent before JAKi initiation. At the 3rd month of the treatment, 6 (35%) of the patients were in complete remission, and 2 (12%) patients were in partial remission. Among 16 patients having ≥3 months follow-up, remission according to PGA was achieved in 11 (68%) patients. The median duration of treatment with JAKi was 16 (6-71) months. During follow-up, 30% (4/13) of the patients experienced a relapse and 4 patients discontinued JAKi.

Conclusions: This study showed that JAKi achieved clinical remission in around 2/3 (68%) of TAK patients with refractory disease to conventional ISs and biologics. GC dose could be decreased to ≤ 4 daily mg in 75% of patients. Our results suggest that JAKi may be an effective option for the treatment of patients with TAK refractory to multiple biologic treatments.

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Interleukin 6 receptor inhibition by tocilizumab monotherapy is effective and safe in active chronic periaortitis: preliminary results of a single arm multi-centre study

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Background/ Aims: The fibroinflammatory condition chronic periaortitis (CP) is a rare form of vasculitis that mostly affects the abdominal aorta and iliac arteries. Fibrous encasement of the ureters leading to renal affection may complicate clinical courses. Therapeutic approaches alternative to steroid-based regimen are urgently requested. Inhibition of the interleukin 6 receptor by Tocilizumab (TCZ) has emerged as a safe and efficacious treatment option in many immune-mediated conditions. Therefore, we aimed at evaluating its efficacy and safety in active CP.

Methods: A multi-centre study was conducted enrolling 13 patients with active CP that received TCZ (8 mg/kg IV every 4 weeks) mostly as monotherapy for at least 6 months. Clinical, laboratory and imaging data (including abdominal computed tomography [CT] scan and 18F fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography [18FDG-PET]) were assessed at baseline, month 6, 12 and 24. Rates of partial remission (PR) and complete remission (CR) at months 6 and 12 were the primary endpoints. Adverse event (AE) rate was registered.

Results: At baseline, the mean age was 64±14 yrs with 5/12 (41.7%) being female patients. The max. thickness of periaortic tissue on CT scan was 12 mm (IQR 9-20), the standardized uptake value (SUV) was 8 (IQR 4.5-8.0) indicating high metabolic activity on PET scan. Relative mass shrinkage on CT scan was 0.3 (IQR 0.3-1.0; mo. 6) and 1.0 (IQR 0.6-1.0, mo. 12). CR was achieved in 4/12 (33.3%, mo. 6) emerging to 6/12 (50%, mo. 12). PR occurred in 5/12 (41.7%, mo. 6) patients and 4/12 (33.3%, mo. 12) of cases. No severe AE occurred according to CTCAE.

Conclusions: We here provide evidence for TCZ monotherapy being an effective and safe treatment option in active CP. To our knowledge, this is the largest study with the longest patient follow up conducted thus far in the field of CP research.

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Development and internal validation of a multivariable prediction model for early mortality in individuals with ANCA-associated vasculitis and severe infection

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Background/Aims: Individuals with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are highly susceptible to severe infections, which can result in premature death. Currently, no predictive models are available to forecast mortality in this setting. This study aimed to create such a predictive model.

Methods: A linked dataset was used. This comprised routine administrative healthcare data covering all individuals in Scotland who had experienced a hospital admission. AAV patients were identified using ICD-10 codes. All subjects had experienced at least one hospital admission associated with infection. The candidate predictive factors considered were demographic data, comorbidities and medications prescribed within the community setting. The primary outcome was mortality either before discharge from hospital or within a 30-day period following discharge. Model development utilised logistic regression and a backward selection procedure, which involved fitting fractional polynomials to continuous variables. Elastic net penalized logistic regression was then applied to shrink the model coefficients. To assess model performance, optimism-adjusted performance metrics were estimated using bootstrapping.

Results: The study cohort comprised 1,015 patients, among whom 157 (15.5%) experienced the outcome. The final predictive model demonstrated that increased age, increased time since AAV diagnosis, the presence of specific comorbidities (including liver disease, metastatic cancer, renal disease, and diabetes), and recent exposure to glucocorticoids were independent predictors of the mortality end point. Following internal validation, the optimism-adjusted model performance indicators were: calibration slope 0.967, calibration in the large 0.004 and concordance (c) statistic 0.713. A calibration curve showed the model was well calibrated.

Conclusions: The development of this predictive model represents an important step in developing tools to estimate the risk of mortality in individuals diagnosed with AAV who face the challenge of severe infection.

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Performance of histopathological scores and classification in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis: data from the Almenara vasculitis cohort

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Background/Aims: Renal involvement in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) patients largely determines their prognosis. Thus, predicting progression to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in these patients is essential to guide therapeutic decisions. Histopathological scores and classifications have been developed and validated, but they have rarely been evaluated in Latin American populations. We aimed to evaluate the performance of four renal scores in AAV patients from a Latin American (Peruvian) cohort.

Methods: Patients from the Almenara Vasculitis cohort (a single-centre cohort from Peru) were included. These patients are mainly Mestizo. The histopathological scores used were the Renal Risk Score (RRS) and the Improved RRS (IRRS), whereas histopathological classifications used were the Berden's classification and the Mayo Clinic Chronicity Score (MCCS). A survival analysis using a Cox regression model was performed using a composite endpoint (ESRD and death).

Results: Fifty-two patients were evaluated; 30 (57.7%) of them were women. Their mean age and follow-up were 55.9 (13.2) and 3.93 (3.39) years, respectively. Twenty-four patients died and 7 developed ESRD. In the adjusted model, high-risk group from the RRS (HR: 3.69; 95%CI: 1.27-10.74; p=0.017), intermediate- (HR: 3.76; 95%CI: 1.13-12.52; p=0.031) and very high-risk (HR: 25.74; 95%CI: 2.23-296.76; p=0.009) groups from the IRRS, and severe group from the MCCS (HR: 19.20; 95%CI: 1.53-241.29; p=0.022), were associated with the composite endpoint compared to the lower-risk groups. The Berden's classification was not associated with the outcome.

Conclusions: In AAV patients from a Latin American cohort, the RRS, the IRRS and the MCCS predicted the risk of the combined end-point: death or progression to ESRD. Because of the small number of patients included, further studies are needed to corroborate these findings in Latin America.

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The impact of kidney relapse on long-term kidney function in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Relapse of kidney disease is a predictor of end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), but its effect on long-term kidney function remains unclear. This study evaluated trajectories of estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) before and after relapse in the PEXIVAS trial.

Methods: This post-hoc analysis included patients who achieved remission within 12 months and had ≥ 2 subsequent eGFR assessments. Those developing ESKD before 12 months were excluded. Propensity score matching was performed based on sex, ANCA subtype, eGFR at randomisation, and enrolment time. Time 0 was defined as the relapse date for relapsers, and for non-relapsers the relapse month of their matched relapsers. eGFR slopes were estimated using linear mixed-effects models, and mean eGFR was compared using generalized linear mixed models. Subgroup analyses examined ANCA subtype and baseline eGFR.

Results: Of 704 participants, 459 were included with a median follow-up of 3.4 years (IQR 2.4-4.7). 51 (11.1%) had a “kidney relapse” after 12 months (median time: 28 months from randomisation). Baseline characteristics were comparable between those with and without kidney relapse, including median eGFR at 12 months (41.3 vs. 42.7 mL/min/1.73 m²). Mean eGFR was lower in relapsers at relapse and remained lower thereafter. Non-relapsers showed a stable slope (+0.8 mL/min/1.73 m²/year), whereas relapsers declined steeply before relapse (-5.3 mL/min/1.73 m²/year). After relapse, decline attenuated (-1.5 mL/min/1.73 m²/year). Slopes differed before Time 0 ($p=0.025$), whereas no difference was observed after Time 0 ($p=0.80$). Slopes did not differ by ANCA subtype or baseline eGFR, although patients with MPO-ANCA had lower absolute eGFR than patients with PR3-ANCA.

Conclusion: Kidney relapse precipitates acute loss of kidney function and is preceded by steep decline in eGFR. Thereafter, decline does not differ from non-relapsers, though eGFR remains lower. These findings underscore the need for early detection of relapse and regular follow-up monitoring.

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Time to renal replacement therapy determinants in ANCA-associated vasculitis - data from Polish Vasculitis Registry (POLVAS)

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody–associated vasculitis (AAV) frequently leads to severe renal damage requiring immunosuppressive treatment and dialysis. Kidney function deterioration and timing of dialysis initiation reflect disease severity, and may influence prognosis and therapeutic decisions. The aim of this study was to evaluate clinical factors associated with time to dialysis initiation in AAV.

Methods: We analysed 827 POLVAS patients with renal involvement; 182 required renal replacement therapy. Thirty cases were excluded due to dialysis preceding diagnosis, and 12 for missing data. Demographics, diagnosis (MPA, GPA, EGPA), plasma exchange (PLEX) use, laboratory parameters, and survival were assessed.

Results: Median time from diagnosis to dialysis was 1.5 months overall and 13 months among patients not dialyzed at diagnosis. Patients with MPA started dialysis earlier (1 month overall; 3 months if not dialyzed at diagnosis) than GPA (7 and 26 months, respectively; $p=0.005/p<0.001$). No EGPA patients required dialysis. Dialysis timing did not differ by sex (male and female median 1.5 months; $p=0.74$) or PLEX use (median 1 vs 2 months; $p=0.15$). Among patients not dialyzed at diagnosis, medians were 19 vs 10 months by sex ($p=0.59$) and 15 vs 13.5 months by PLEX status ($p=0.8$). Older age correlated with shorter time to dialysis ($\rho=-0.33$, $p<0.001$ overall; $\rho=-0.18$,

$p=0.083$ non-dialyzed). Higher creatinine at diagnosis also correlated with earlier dialysis ($\rho=-0.46$, $p<0.001$). Survival was not significantly associated with dialysis timing ($p=0.059$ overall; $p=0.73$ non-dialyzed). PLEX correlated with higher frequency of temporary dialysis ($p<0.001$).

Conclusions: Median time to dialysis initiation was 1.5 months overall and 13 months in patients not requiring immediate dialysis. Earlier dialysis was linked to older age, higher creatinine, and AAV subtype (shorter in MPA than GPA). PLEX was associated with temporary renal recovery but not with chronic dialysis timing. Baseline renal impairment remains an important prognostic factor in AAV.

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Analysis of ANCA-associated vasculitis chronic haemodialysis inpatient cases at our dialysis facility

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) often results in kidney damage, with a high rate of dialysis initiation. However, research on relapse rates and prognosis after transitioning to chronic haemodialysis remains limited.

This study aimed to assess the current status of AAV chronic haemodialysis patients at our dialysis facility, and provide insights into their challenges.

Methods: The study included 23 AAV chronic haemodialysis patients (35 admissions) who were admitted to our facility from January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2023 (8 years). The average age was 79.6 years (range: 69–95 years), with 4 males and 19 females. All patients had microscopic polyangiitis. MPO-ANCA was present in 22 cases (1 case with concurrent anti-GBM and PR3-ANCA), PR3-ANCA alone: 1 case.

This retrospective study analysed hospitalization causes, immunosuppressive therapy, relapse history, prognosis, and causes of death in AAV chronic haemodialysis patients.

Results: Most were in remission (86%), with primary reasons for admission including decreased activities of daily living, infections, heart failure, and vascular access surgery. Comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, and dementia, which are steroid-sensitive conditions, were prevalent. No patients were on immunosuppressive drugs, though 66% had been using steroids (average 10.8 mg/day) at the time of admission. There was no significant difference in vasculitis relapse rates between the pre- and post-dialysis periods (average 1 year 3 months and 3 years 5 months, respectively): HR (95% CI): 0.564 (0.112-2.849), p-value: 0.4880, Cox regression (pre- and post-dialysis: 0.115 and 0.066 episodes/person-year). No deaths were attributed to vasculitis; the predominant causes of mortality included infections and heart failure, which are common causes of death among chronic haemodialysis patients in Japan.

Conclusions: In AAV patients on chronic dialysis, attention should be given to complications such as infections and heart failure, and relapse should be carefully monitored. Steroid reduction or discontinuation should be considered whenever possible.

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High activity of factor XI and C1 inhibitor in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis may be related to an increased risk of thrombotic events - a preliminary study

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a rare, systemic disease often leading to thrombotic vascular damage. Previous studies have suggested prothrombotic changes in the pathogenesis of AAV. We studied the parameters of contact activation system, including factor (F)XI, FXII, and C1 inhibitor (C1inh) in patients with AAV compared to healthy controls.

Methods: In this case-control study, 37 patients diagnosed with AAV and 37 age- and sex-matched healthy controls were enrolled. The activity of FXI and FXII was measured by coagulometric methods (FXI:C and FXII:C), and antigens FXI and FXII levels were measured using immunoenzymatic method (FXI:Ag and FXII:Ag). The activity of C1inh was measured by chromogenic method (C1inh:Ac). The diagnosis of AAV was based on the ACR/EULAR 2022 classification criteria.

Results: Patients with AAV had 21.6% higher FXI activity (FXI:C) as compared to controls (median: 126.9% vs. 104.4%, $p < 0.001$). No differences were observed for FXI:Ag, FXII:C and FXII:Ag between analyzed groups. Notably, C1inh:Ac was 20.1% higher in AAV patients than in controls (median: 129.0% vs. 107.4%, $p < 0.001$). Among the entire analyzed group, the age of AAV patients showed a significant positive correlation with FXI:C ($r = 0.35$, $p = 0.003$), FXI:C was positively correlated with FXII:C ($r = 0.30$, $p = 0.008$), and FXI:C also showed a positive correlation with C1inh:Ac ($r = 0.46$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Our findings indicate that AAV patients activity of FXI and C1inh are elevated as compared to healthy controls. These findings were associated with increased generation of thrombin in vitro as measured by ETP, Lag time and Peak TG in AAV patients as compared to controls which may suggest their potential role in the context of thrombosis-related events. Further studies are needed to explore the clinical implications of these alterations and potential effects of factor XI inhibitors as antithrombotic agents in the setting of AAV.

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Dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor blockade improves nocturnal blood pressure dipping in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis: observational and interventional studies

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Background/Aims: Patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are at increased risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Impaired nocturnal blood pressure (BP) dipping, defined as <10% day to night drop, and arterial stiffness likely contribute to this risk. We examined (i) whether active AAV is associated with abnormal diurnal BP and arterial stiffness patterns, (ii) the impact of disease remission on these patterns, and (iii) the effects of dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor blockade.

Methods: Thirty-two patients with active AAV underwent 24-hour ambulatory BP and arterial stiffness monitoring at diagnosis and again in disease-remission. Separately, 32 patients in established remission were randomised to six weeks of sparsentan (dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor antagonist) or irbesartan (angiotensin receptor blocker [ARB]) with ambulatory BP and arterial stiffness monitoring.

Results: In active AAV (64±16 years; 53% male; eGFR 49±33 mL/min/1.73m²), mean BP was 127±16/75 ±10 mmHg. Seventy nine percent of patients had abnormal nocturnal dipping (mean systolic/diastolic dip -3.5±9.4/-6.4±11.2 mmHg). Baseline mean pulse wave velocity (PWV) was 9.5±2.2 m/s and mean augmentation index (Aix) was 26.7±7.1 %. With remission, BP improved (120±15 /72±11 mmHg, P<0.05) and dipping partially normalised (59% abnormal; mean dip -8.2±7.4/-10.7±7.0 mmHg), with improvement in Aix to 24.3±7.1 % (P<0.05), but no change in PWV (9.4±2.2m/s, P=0.72).

In the double-blind randomised trial (64±12 years; 69% male; eGFR 58±22 mL/min/1.73m²), baseline BP was controlled (124±14/75±8 mmHg), but abnormal dipping remained common (sparsentan 79%, irbesartan 64%). At six weeks, both treatments lowered BP similarly, but only sparsentan improved nocturnal dipping (36% of patients versus 0%, P<0.05).

Conclusions: AAV is characterised by loss of nocturnal BP dipping during active disease, which improves but does not normalise in remission. Dual endothelin-angiotensin receptor blockade improves BP dipping compared with ARB alone and may reduce future CVD risk in this population.

Major adverse cardiovascular events in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis: results from a European multicentre cohort study

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (AAV) causes systemic inflammation and vascular injury. This predisposes patients to endothelial dysfunction, accelerated atherosclerosis and an increased risk of cardiovascular (CV) morbidity and mortality. Despite advances in control of traditional and disease-related risk factors, CV outcomes remain poor. This multicentre study aims to collect and analyse a comprehensive dataset on major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and clinical data on CV risk factors and management obtained during a longitudinal follow-up period.

Methods: The study included AAV patients from ten European nephrology and rheumatology centres between 2005 and 2019, who were followed-up for at least three years. A comprehensive dataset of clinical and laboratory variables, including AAV-related data, treatments and cardiovascular outcomes were collected. MACE were defined using the International Classification of Diseases criteria (ICD-10; I11, I20-25, I42-45, I50, I51, I61-69). Preliminary analyses were performed to assess the incidence and risk factors of MACE using Cox regression analysis.

Results: Of the 315 included patients, 57 patients (18.1%) experienced 73 MACE, over a median follow-up of 7.5 years. The most common first events were nonfatal stroke (16/57, 28.1%), acute heart failure (16/57, 28.1%) and nonfatal myocardial infarction (12/57, 21.1%), while fatal events such as cardiac death (2/57, 3.5%), fatal myocardial infarction (1/57, 1.8%) and fatal stroke (2/57, 3.5%) were less common. Recurrent MACE were frequent, affecting 12 patients with a second and 3 patients with a third MACE. A detailed analysis of the characteristics of patients at risk of MACE and their risk factors, with a focus on the impact of immunosuppressive treatments, is ongoing.

Conclusion: The incidence of MACE in this large European AAV cohort is comparable to existing data. This study will generate valuable data that could inform improvements in prevention of cardiovascular disease in AAV patients.

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Drivers of Cardiovascular Mortality in ANCA Vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Cardiovascular mortality is significantly higher in patients with antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) vasculitis compared to the general population assuming chronic inflammation drives escalated atherosclerosis.

Methods: We reviewed the prevalence and specifics of cardiovascular disease in our single centre ANCA vasculitis cohort investigating classical and vasculitis related risk parameters such as gender, smoking, antihypertension treatment, kidney function and organ failure.

Results: A total of 288 patients (2006 – 2025) were retrospectively reviewed. 34.03% had a recorded cardiovascular disease (CVD) event with 16.32% before and 17.71% following the diagnosis of ANCA vasculitis, significantly higher than the current estimate in the general population. Patients were fewer Never smokers (51.04%) compared to the general population; 40.28% recorded as Ex-smokers and a remaining 6.25% as Active smokers.

Active and Ex smokers demonstrated higher numbers of CVD in their past medical history prior to the onset of ANCA vasculitis compared to Never smokers (27.78%, 18.10% vs 13.61%). Following the diagnosis of vasculitis, CVD events did not differ between Never and Ex smokers (19.05% and 18.1%). 70.18% of patients received antihypertensive medication and 29.82% of patients did not. 15.28% of patients received sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitor treatment for proteinuric chronic kidney disease.

Conclusions: Smoking seems to worsen CVD related outcomes in ANCA vasculitis as previously suggested and there is a higher rate of Ex Smokers in the ANCA vasculitis cohort compared to the general population. Smoking cessation is therefore a priority, and structured programs and pharmacological aids are important to reduce the additional risk factor smoking.

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Pulmonary involvement in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: a cross-sectional study

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a multi-system disease often involving the lungs. Increased occurrence of pulmonary conditions, including interstitial lung disease (ILD) has been observed in patients with AAV. Although AAV-associated ILD can precede AAV diagnosis, it more commonly develops during the disease course. This study aimed to describe pulmonary involvement, with focus on ILD, in patients with established AAV.

Methods: This cross-sectional single centre study enrolled patients representing the three AAV phenotypes. Patients were recruited from the Rheumatology or Nephrology outpatient clinics at our hospital after giving written consent. All patients underwent clinical assessment and high-resolution computed tomography of the chest (Chest-HRCT).

Results: A total of 84 AAV patients were enrolled: 58 (69.0%) with GPA, 16 (19.0%) with MPA and 10 (11.9%) with EGPA. Median age at AAV-diagnosis was 60.4 (IQR:47.9-65.5) and median disease duration at inclusion was 8.0 years (IQR:5.0-12.3).

Chest-HRCT was performed in 79 patients (36 women (46%); 54 PR3+ (67%), 21 MPO+ (27%). Normal Chest-HRCT findings were observed in 36 cases (43%).

Typical ILD, primarily with non-specific interstitial pneumonia (NSIP) pattern, was identified in six cases (7%): three were MPO-ANCA positive and three were PR3-ANCA positive. Additional ten patients (12%) showed potential ILD, defined as discrete but non-specific findings compatible for ILD; of these, seven were PR3-positive, one MPO-positive, and two were ANCA-negative.

Another ten patients (12%) exhibited residual parenchymal changes, and 12 patients (14%) had nodules, infiltrates or non-specific ground glass opacities warranting further examination for vasculitis, infection, or other causes. Emphysema was observed in five (6%) cases. No cases of ILD or potential ILD were observed in EGPA.

Conclusions: In this cross-sectional study, nearly 60% of cases with AAV had HRCT-Chest abnormalities indicative of pulmonary involvement. Findings ranged from ILD to features of active disease or residual parenchymal changes.

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The association between neurologic involvement and cumulative damage in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Neurologic involvement (NI) is common and often irreversible in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), but its relation to cumulative disease damage is unclear. This study evaluates the association between NI and cumulative damage in AAV.

Methods: We analysed data from adults with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), and eosinophilic GPA (EGPA) enrolled in the Vasculitis Clinical Research Consortium (2006-2021). Patients were grouped by presence of NI during their disease course. Neurologic damage items (NDI) were categorized as disease-specific (e.g., cranial nerve lesion, neuropathy) or non-disease-specific. Group differences were assessed using Kruskal-Wallis and Fisher's exact tests. Linear regression models estimated differences in Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI), ANCA Vasculitis Index of Damage (AVID), AAV-Disease-Specific Damage (AAV-DSD), and AAV-Non-DSD scores, adjusting for sex, age at diagnosis, and disease duration.

Results: Among 1322 patients, 526 (39.8%) had NI. NI was more common in older patients and EGPA. NI was associated with significantly higher VDI (0.6, 95% CI: 0.35, 0.86), AVID (1.1, 95% CI: 0.66, 1.54), and AAV-DSD (0.91, 95% CI: 0.71, 1.12) scores (all $p < 0.0001$). The AAV-DSD score remained higher after removing NDI. AAV-Non-DSD scores did not differ by NI status. NI was associated with higher damage scores for all scores in GPA and the AAV-DSD score in MPA. Damage scores did not differ by NI status in EGPA. NI was also associated with higher damage scores in ANCA-positive patients. Among patients with NI, those with GPA had higher damage scores than MPA and EGPA. Damage scores did not differ between those with central and peripheral NI.

Conclusions: Patients with AAV and NI experience greater neurologic and non-neurologic cumulative damage than those without NI. Differences are driven by disease-specific items. Patients with NI with GPA, PR3-ANCA, or MPO-ANCA accumulate the most damage. This highlights the burden of NI in AAV.

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Mental health screening and psychology referrals for patients with ANCA vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Mental health concerns are common, yet under-recognized in patients with ANCA vasculitis. This pilot study aimed to identify mental health needs by developing a screening tool and referral pathway to improve access to care and quality of life.

Methods: Forty-two vasculitis patients with ANCA vasculitis consented to participate, 21 completed screening using the Patient Health Questionnaire-2 and -9 (PHQ-2, PHQ-9), Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7), Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI), Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), Herth Hope Index (HHI), AAV-PRO, SF-36 and Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test-Consumption (AUD-C). Disease severity was measured using the Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) and Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI). Three voluntary sessions with a clinical psychologist were offered. Patient-reported outcomes were assessed at baseline and post-psychologist sessions.

Results: Thirteen patients (62%) attended psychology sessions. Five attended three sessions, one attended two, and seven attended one. Post-sessions, the AAV-PRO indicated improvements in systemic symptoms (mean 38.0 to 26.9), treatment side effects (33.1 to 22.3), social/emotional impact (28.2 to 21.1), and future concerns (30.7 to 22.7). SF-36 scores improved in energy/fatigue (38% to 50%) and sleep quality (PSQI 7.8 to 6.6). PHQ-9 and GAD-7 scores showed minor improvements (PHQ-9: 5.8 to 5.5; GAD-7: 4.15 to 4.38). AUD-C scores decreased from 3.0 to 2.38. Overall, 54% reported improved well-being, 70% perceived mental health benefits and satisfaction with care (mean 9.15/10).

Conclusions: Integrating mental health screening and referral is feasible and may improve patient-outcomes for patients with ANCA vasculitis. Future research should refine and validate a comprehensive screening tool with interpretation guidance and establish clear referral guidelines.

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Incidence of malignancies in ANCA-associated vasculitides: A single-centre observational study.

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Background/Aims: Previous studies have suggested an increased incidence of malignancies among ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) patients, predominantly linked to cyclophosphamide therapy. This study analysed the incidence of malignancies in patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) treated at an academic centre.

Methods: Data from 284 patients (232 GPA, 52 MPA) were analysed from 1988 to 2020 through case record review. Patients were monitored from diagnosis until death or most recent assessment. Multivariate logistic regression and Cox survival analysis were performed to identify risk factors.

Results: During a mean follow-up of 8.6 years, 29 patients (10.2%) developed 35 malignancies. Non-melanoma skin cancer was most common, followed by gastrointestinal, prostate, and bladder cancers. Among 17 renal transplant patients, 5 (29.4%) developed malignancies compared to 4.7% in non-transplant patients. Multivariate analysis revealed significant associations between cancer incidence and kidney transplantation (OR 4.21, $p=0.022$) and autoimmune comorbidities (OR 3.90, $p=0.006$). Age >60 years increased cancer risk 3.88-fold ($p=0.032$). Methotrexate use for remission maintenance showed protective effects, reducing cancer risk by 89% (OR 0.11, $p=0.024$). Generalized disease forms were protective compared to localized forms. No association was found between cancer incidence and cumulative cyclophosphamide dose. Mortality was higher in cancer patients (53.6% vs. 30.1%, $p=0.012$), but Cox analysis showed age as the only significant predictor of survival (HR 3.02, $p<0.001$).

Conclusions: Cancer incidence in AAV patients was 10.2% over 8.6 years, with kidney transplantation and autoimmune comorbidities as major risk factors. Methotrexate demonstrated protective effects against malignancy development. Age, rather than cancer diagnosis, was the primary determinant of mortality in this cohort.

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Impact of pre-disease frailty on clinical outcomes in elderly patients with MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis: a retrospective analysis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) frequently affects older adults in Japan, many of whom present with frailty—a condition marked by reduced physiological reserves and increased vulnerability to stressors. The impact of pre-disease frailty on clinical outcomes in AAV remains unclear.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 21 patients with MPO-AAV who received remission induction therapy between January 2019 and December 2024. Treatment regimens followed either the PEXIVAS or LoVAS trial protocols for glucocorticoid tapering, based on disease severity. Patients were classified into robust or frail groups according to their pre-onset Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS) score. We compared prognosis, incidence of serious infections (SIs) and adverse events (AEs), and changes in CFS scores over 6 months.

Results: No significant difference was observed in 6-month survival between groups. However, the frail group had significantly shorter SI-free ($p = 0.04$) and AE-free ($p = 0.01$) periods. CFS scores remained stable in the robust group, while the frail group showed greater fluctuations, with worsening frailty linked to AEs and infections.

Conclusions: Pre-existing frailty may predispose AAV patients to complications that further deteriorate frailty status. Early frailty assessment and stratified treatment - including early glucocorticoid tapering and use of agents such as rituximab or avacopan - should be considered to improve outcomes in older patients.

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Predicting serious infection in patients with anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Serious infections are a major cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Understanding what factors predict serious infection could inform strategies for prevention.

We evaluated characteristics associated with serious infection in the 6 months after treatment for AAV and assessed these factors as predictors of serious infection.

Methods: We estimated the risk of serious infection within 6 months of treatment initiation for AAV in the PEXIVAS trial, an international multi-centre randomised controlled trial comparing treatment with plasma exchange and no plasma exchange, and two glucocorticoid regimens in patients with new or relapsed AAV with GFR<50ml/minute or pulmonary haemorrhage. Serious infection was defined as infection requiring intravenous anti-microbials or hospitalisation. Candidate predictors of serious infection were selected based on existing literature on infection risk and fit to a multivariable empirical Bayesian elastic net regularisation model. Model performance was assessed using discrimination and calibration statistics.

Results: This analysis included 700 patients of whom 178 (25%) experienced serious infections within the first 6 months. Of 24 candidate predictors, 17 were included in the final model: age, body mass index, kidney replacement therapy, pre-existing cardiovascular and pulmonary disease, receipt of prophylaxis against *Pneumocystis jirovecii*, induction therapy (plasma exchange arm, glucocorticoid arm, and cyclophosphamide/rituximab), ANCA subtype, otorhinolaryngeal or respiratory involvement, disease activity, haemoglobin, and leukocyte count.

Although several factors selected in the final model were associated with risk of serious infection and model calibration was acceptable (calibration slope 1.0 [95% confidence interval (CI) 0.72-1.28]), discrimination for serious infection risk was poor (area under receiver operator curve of 0.68 (95%CI 0.63-0.72)).

Conclusions: Serious infections are common in patients with AAV, and several clinical factors are associated with serious infections. However, a multivariable model incorporating these factors was unable to discriminate well between those at risk or not.

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Red flags for severe infections in ANCA-associated vasculitis and outcome

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Background/Aims: Severe infections are a major cause of morbidity and mortality in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), particularly under immunosuppressive therapy. Real-world data on their frequency and predictors remain limited.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective cohort study of patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), or unclassified AAV treated at two tertiary referral centres between 2014–2024. Severe infection was defined as any episode requiring hospitalization. Demographics, comorbidities, organ involvement, TMP-SMX prophylaxis, and treatment exposures were collected. Predictors were assessed by univariable and multivariable logistic regression.

Results: Among 300 patients (52.0% female; 75.3% GPA, 18.4% MPA, 6.0% unclassified; 80.7% ANCA positive), the mean age at diagnosis was 48.2 (± 16.3) years. 37 (12.3%) of patients deceased at the end of median follow-up as 60.5 months (IQR 29.7–104.0). Severe infections occurred in 63 patients (21.0%), leading to 75 hospitalizations, including 24 ICU admissions (32.0%). Median hospital stay was 15.5 (IQR 8.0–28.0) days. One-third of infections occurred within the first year after diagnosis; %44.0 of infection events occurred within a month after the last CYC dose or 6 months after the last RTX dosing. Pulmonary infections were the most common cause (55.8%). We had TMP-SMX data for 69 pts, and 24 of the patients were on treatment. No significant differences observed in age at diagnosis, baseline BVAS, baseline immunoglobulin levels (IgG, IgM, IgA), or smoking history between patients with and without severe infections (all $p < 0.05$). Even having COPD or malignancy history was associated in univariate analysis, in multivariable analysis; hypogammaglobulinemia at any time, and chronic renal disease remained independent predictors.

Conclusions: During a five-year follow-up, one-fifth of patients have severe infections, mostly after CYC infusion/RTX period. Patients having chronic renal disease or on CYC/RTX therapy have an increased risk for severe infections. Monitoring of IgG levels can be useful in preventing severe infections.

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Immunogenicity and effectiveness of booster SARS-CoV-2 vaccinations on breakthrough COVID-19 infection in primary systemic vasculitis patients on immunosuppression

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Background/Aims: Patients with primary systemic vasculitis (PSV) on immunosuppression have been offered several SARS-CoV-2 vaccine doses to protect against severe COVID-19 infection, although their effectiveness in these patients is unclear. We aimed to assess the immunogenicity and effectiveness of a third through fifth SARS-CoV-2 vaccine dose in PSV patients on immunosuppression across the Ancestral, Delta and Omicron eras.

Methods: PSV patients from a UK-based multicentre observational cohort study investigating serological responses to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination in immunocompromised renal patients were followed for up to 24 months, and had sera tested for SARS-CoV-2 spike protein antibodies (anti-S IgG) post-vaccination. Neutralising antibodies (nAbs) were measured in a set of patients in a nested case control sub-study as a potential correlate of protection (CoP). Vaccine effectiveness (VE), and anti-S IgG titres as a CoP against first COVID-19 breakthrough infection (BTI) and hospitalisation were calculated in time-to-event analyses.

Results: 268 PSV patients were included. Post-third dose, adjusted anti-S IgG titres increased ($p < 0.001$), but not thereafter ($p > 0.05$). The proportion of patients seroconverting increased from 69.6% post-second to 79.4% post-third dose ($p = 0.033$). VE against first BTI of a third through fifth relative to two doses was 74–76% ($p < 0.05$). Anti-S IgG titres reduced COVID-19 hospitalisation risk (adjusted hazard ratio [HR] 0.78 [95% CI 0.62–0.98, $p = 0.033$]) but not BTI overall (adjusted HR 1.03 [95% CI 0.95–1.11, $p = 0.537$]). Ancestral nAbs correlated with protection post-second dose (Odds ratio [OR] 0.42 [95% CI 0.20–0.87], $p = 0.019$) but not thereafter ($p > 0.05$), whereas only Omicron BA.2 nAbs were protective (OR 0.83 [95% CI 0.70–1.00], $p = 0.045$) post-fourth dose which coincided with the Omicron era.

Conclusions: Only a third SARS-CoV-2 vaccine dose increased anti-S IgG titres, which were protective against severe infection and hospitalisation among PSV patients. However, further benefit was observed with third through fifth doses with nAbs against circulating variants reducing risk of BTI overall.

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Risk of Covid-19 and characterisation of the humoral response to Covid-19 vaccination in patients that received rituximab

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Background/Aims: Rituximab is widely used as treatment for autoimmune diseases, but B cell depletion can impair the development of protective antibodies. We assessed the impact of rituximab on humoral response and risk of Covid-19 among immunocompromised individuals.

Methods: The PROTECT-V trial enrolled immunocompromised individuals, including those receiving immunosuppression due to transplantation or autoimmune disease. Participants were randomised to receive sotrovimab or placebo as pre-exposure prophylaxis against Covid-19. We analysed clinical characteristics, anti-spike antibody titres (ELISA), and peripheral blood cells (TruCount) at baseline - prior to sotrovimab or placebo. Furthermore, we performed neutralisation of pseudoviral variants using sera of 14 participants matched for age, sex, date of enrolment, type of immunosuppression and Covid-19 status. All had baseline anti-spike titre >1000U/ml.

Results: Of 619 participants, 215 (34%) had received rituximab before enrolment. Rituximab-treated patients more frequently had depleted peripheral B cells (87% vs 8%, $p<0.001$) and extremely low baseline anti-spike antibody titres (<400U/mL) (58% vs 21%, $p<0.001$) compared to non-rituximab patients, despite a median of 5 Covid-19 vaccinations. The rate of Covid-19 infections was similar in both groups (21% vs 19%, $p=0.52$) and neither B cell count nor baseline anti-spike antibody titre were significantly associated with this outcome. 15% of infected rituximab-treated patients compared to 8% non-rituximab ($p=0.22$) were hospitalised.

All rituximab-treated patients had detectable neutralising antibodies against wild-type, BA.1 and BA.4 variants, 4/7 against XBB.1.5 and 5/7 against JN.1. Serum Neutralisation was not associated with rituximab exposure or symptomatic Covid-19.

Conclusions: Rituximab is associated with lower rates of seroconversion after Covid-19 vaccination; however, most patients who mounted a response had functional antibodies. The lack of association between both anti-spike titres and neutralising capacity and risk of Covid-19 suggests an important role for innate or cellular immunity in this patient population.

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Use of disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs in giant cell arteritis does not protect against vascular complications

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a large vessel vasculitis associated with severe vascular complications including occlusion, dissection, and aneurysm. Glucocorticoids (GC) remain the cornerstone of treatment, but disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) are increasingly used to improve disease control and reduce GC exposure. The effect of DMARDs on vascular complications, however, remains unclear. We aimed to evaluate their impact in GCA.

Methods: In this retrospective cohort study, patients with GCA were categorized into two treatment strategies: GC monotherapy vs adjunctive DMARD. The primary outcome was the occurrence of vascular complications. Associations between DMARD use and vascular complications were analysed using a Cox proportional hazards model with DMARD use as a time-dependent covariate. To address confounding by indication, a propensity score based on baseline characteristics and cardiovascular risk factors was included in the model.

Results: A total of 102 patients with GCA were included: 56 on GC monotherapy and 46 with adjunctive DMARD. At diagnosis, groups were comparable except for younger age (66 vs. 70 years, $P=0.023$), lower dyslipidaemia prevalence (13% vs. 32%, $P=0.024$), and higher ESR levels (88 vs 72 mm/h, $P=0.040$) in the DMARD group. Over 391 patient-years of follow-up, 32 vascular events occurred in 23 patients (22.5%; incidence 8.2 per 100 patient-years). Event rates were 9.5 and 3.1 per 100 patient-years in the GC and DMARD groups, respectively. DMARD use was not significantly associated with the development of vascular complications (adjusted HR 1.77, 95% CI 0.65-4.81).

Conclusion: This study found no significant protective effect of DMARDs on the development of vascular complications in GCA. These findings may reflect residual confounding by indication and should be interpreted with caution. Prospective studies with randomized treatment strategies are needed to clarify the impact of DMARD use on the development of vascular complications.

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Sotrovimab for pre-exposure prophylaxis against SARS-CoV2 in a vulnerable, patient population: results from the PROTECT-V trial

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Background/Aims: Despite introduction of vaccination against SARS CoV-2, there remains a need for pre-exposure prophylaxis in patients mounting suboptimal vaccine responses. Sotrovimab is a recombinant human monoclonal antibody directed against spike protein of SARS-CoV-2.

Methods: PROTECT-V is a platform trial evaluating prophylactic interventions against SARS-CoV2 infection in vulnerable adult patients at high risk of COVID-19 infection and its complications. Sotrovimab was the second agent added to the platform. Participants were randomized 1:1 to one dose of IV sotrovimab 2000mg or matched placebo. Primary endpoint was confirmed symptomatic COVID-19 infection at week 12.

Results: 619(314 placebo; 305 sotrovimab) patients in the UK were randomized between August 2022 and May 2024. 256(43.3%) had autoimmune disease. 588(297 placebo; 291 sotrovimab) received investigational medicinal product infusion. Median age was 64.4 years; 50.5% were female. 531(90.3%) of patients had received 4 or more doses of SARS CoV-2 vaccines before enrolment. Extremely low (<400U/ml) titres of anti-spike antibodies were observed in 192(32.7%) patients at baseline.

At week 12, 21 symptomatic COVID-19 infections were observed in the placebo and 17 in the sotrovimab group with a risk ratio of 0.80(95% CI 0.42–1.53) adjusting for age and disease group. 4/38(10.5%) patients were hospitalised (3 placebo, 1 sotrovimab). In view of the 250-fold reduction in EC50 with sotrovimab on pseudovirus testing for JN.1, a pre-specified efficacy analysis according to exposure period was performed.

Headache, dizziness and skin symptoms were the most common adverse events reported within 24 hours of infusion. None of the 194 serious adverse events were related to IMP.

Conclusions: Although safe and well tolerated, 2000mg sotrovimab did not demonstrate benefit over placebo for the prevention of symptomatic SARS-CoV2 infection. There was potential signal of benefit for sotrovimab before the emergence of JN.1 variant in late 2023 that rapidly became the dominant circulating variant in the UK.

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Optimizing patient care after B-cell-targeted therapies: updated Delphi consensus recommendations for the management of secondary hypogammaglobulinaemia in patients with autoimmune diseases

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Background/Aims: Through an international Delphi consensus process, we aimed to revise and expand the 2019 consensus recommendations for the management of B-cell-targeted therapy (BCTT)-related secondary hypogammaglobulinaemia (SHG) in patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases.

Methods: In the B-cell therapies in Autoimmunity Secondary Immunodeficiency Consensus Study ("BASICS"), evidence-based (clinical/real-world studies identified via systematic literature review; guidelines via supplementary search) and expert-informed statements were drafted by a 17-member international, multidisciplinary steering committee (StC) comprising clinicians and patient advocates. Draft statements were voted on by a Delphi panel of international experts experienced in using BCTT for autoimmune diseases and/or immunoglobulin replacement therapy (IgRT). Agreement on each statement was anonymously captured via a 5-point Likert scale and free-text feedback for a maximum of two panel voting rounds. Consensus on statement wording was defined as $\geq 75\%$ agreement. The StC refined non-consensus statements, considering feedback, before another voting round.

Results: Twenty-four draft statements were generated exploring themes including: risk factors for/susceptibility of developing SHG; SHG risk with newer BCTT drugs/biosimilars; monitoring SHG; immunological assessment besides SHG; the role of (and when to refer to) clinical immunology/multidisciplinary teams; IgRT utilization; when to stop IgRT; types of vaccines and utilization; role of antimicrobial prophylaxis; monitoring for infections; and management of neonates and pregnant patients. In voting round 1 (87–91% participation [N=69]), 23/24 statements reached $\geq 75\%$ consensus; 12 statements reached $\geq 95\%$ consensus. All 24 statements achieved consensus in round 2 (84% participation); all final recommendation statements will be presented.

Conclusions: The evidence-based, expanded and revised consensus statements and recommendations derived from this Delphi initiative are intended to improve clinical decision-making, harmonize care pathways and enhance outcomes for adult and paediatric patients at risk of SHG-related complications after BCTT for their autoimmune diseases.

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Do patients with giant cell arteritis have increased cardiovascular comorbidities than the general population?

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Background/Aims: To evaluate the prevalence and characteristics of cardiovascular comorbidities in patients with giant cell arteritis (GCA) from Türkiye, and to compare these findings with the general population.

Methods: TRVaS (Turkish Vasculitis Study Group prospective database) GCA Ankara longitudinal cohort was set up. Clinical, laboratory, imaging, and histopathological data were collected, and classification according to the 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria was verified. A cross-sectional analysis of in terms of cardiovascular comorbidities—including hypertension (HT), diabetes mellitus (DM), dyslipidaemia, peripheral arterial disease (PAD), cerebrovascular disease (CVD), deep vein thrombosis (DVT), and coronary artery disease (CAD; if present stenting or coronary artery bypass grafting [CABG])—were assessed before and after GCA diagnosis. The results were compared with >60 years general population (for HT 74%, for CAD 22%, for CVD 6%, for dyslipidaemia %18, for DM 35%).

Results: A total of 174 patients (62.1% female, mean age at diagnosis 69 ± 8.5 years) were included; Cranial GCA was found in 67.2%, large-vessel GCA in 25.3%. Prior to GCA diagnosis, CAD was observed in 18.4%, PAD in 2.9%, cerebrovascular disease in 4.6%, DVT in 0.6%, HT in 58.6%, DM in 24.1%, and dyslipidaemia in 17.8%. During a median follow-up of 27.5 months (IQR: 6–60), cumulative frequencies increased to 23% for CAD, 5.7% for PAD, 5.7% for CVD, 1.7% for DVT, 70.1% for HT, 32.8% for DM, and 28.2% for dyslipidaemia. Subgroup analysis revealed significantly higher DM prevalence in GCA + PMR compared with isolated GCA (43.7% vs. 26.4%; $p=0.018$).

Conclusions: Cardiovascular comorbidity frequencies in Turkish patients with GCA at diagnosis, appear broadly comparable to those of the general population. Long-term prospective data is essential to better define cardiovascular risk in GCA, particularly in the context of emerging targeted therapies.

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Atrial fibrillation in patients with giant cell arteritis compared to the general population

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Background/Aims: To study the occurrence of atrial fibrillation (AF) in patients with giant cell arteritis (GCA) compared to the general population in southern Sweden.

Methods: This is a population-based cohort study including all patients diagnosed with GCA in the region between 2000 – 2019. For each patient, 10 controls matched for year of birth, sex and area of residence were randomly selected from the general population. Using the population-based Skåne Healthcare Register we identified all cases with AF diagnosed 2000 – 2024. Only new-onset AF after the GCA diagnosis was considered. Incidence rates (IR) and incidence rate ratios (IRR) for AF were calculated overall, as well as by sex, age, and predefined time windows after GCA diagnosis.

Results: Among 1,055 patients (752 women, mean age 74.2) and 9,372 controls, AF occurred in 238 (22.6%) cases and 1,994 (21.3%) controls. The overall IR of AF was 26.0 vs. 23.2 per 1000 person-years (py) (IRR 1.11, 95% CI 0.97–1.28). In men, AF incidence was 31.3 vs. 27.6 per 1000 py in cases vs. controls, and in women 24.1 vs. 21.8 per 1000 py. AF incidence peaked within 3 months of GCA diagnosis (10.5 per 1000 py vs. 2.13 among controls, IRR 5.05, 95% CI 3.12–8.2). The IRR of AF remained significantly elevated throughout the first 24 months after GCA diagnosis (2.8 at 6 months, 2.2 at 12 months, and 1.6 at 24 months). AF occurrence adversely affected survival, adjusted hazard ratio for death was 1.95 (95% CI: 1.78–2.14).

Conclusions: The overall incidence rate of atrial fibrillation in patients with GCA is comparable to that of the background population. However, the risk is highest within the first 3 months after GCA diagnosis and remains significantly elevated during the first 24 months compared to controls.

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Antiplatelet therapy to prevent ischemic outcomes in patients with giant cell arteritis: a systematic review

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) carries a risk of ischemic events such as blindness, stroke, and myocardial infarction. Antiplatelet therapy may mitigate these complications, yet evidence remains conflicting and concerns about bleeding persist. We conducted a systematic review to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of antiplatelet therapy in GCA.

Methods: We searched MEDLINE, EMBASE, CENTRAL, ClinicalTrials.gov, and conference proceedings from August 1990 onward. Eligible studies included randomized or observational designs enrolling adults with either a new diagnosis or relapse of GCA, comparing standard of care with or without adjunctive antiplatelet therapy (aspirin, clopidogrel, ticagrelor, or prasugrel). The primary outcomes were new occurrences of composite ischemic events (stroke, permanent blindness, myocardial infarction, or ischemic death) and major bleeding, as defined by the International Society of Thrombosis and Hemostasis. Outcomes were assessed within one year of diagnosis of new disease or relapse. Two reviewers independently screened studies, extracted data, and assessed risk of bias.

Results: Out of 5325 records screened, six met eligibility criteria, representing 1008 patients. Because of significant methodological and reporting heterogeneity, a pooled effect estimate was not generated. Among patients not on antiplatelet therapy at diagnosis, cranial ischemic complications occurred in 3% (2/66) of those started on therapy versus 13% (14/109) of those who remained untreated; other components of the composite primary outcome were not reported. In patients already receiving antiplatelet therapy at baseline for another indication, the primary outcome occurred in 60/424 patients (14.2%), compared with 64/409 (15.6%) among those not exposed to antiplatelet agents. In the included articles, antiplatelet therapy was not associated with an elevated risk of bleeding.

Conclusions: Current evidence on antiplatelet therapy in GCA is inconclusive, with observational studies suggesting possible benefit without excess bleeding when antiplatelet agents are initiated at diagnosis. Definitive evidence requires a randomized trial. PROSPERO registration CRD42023441574.

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Severe vision impairment in Behçet's Syndrome: comparison of four different periods

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Background/Aims: There is consensus that the visual prognosis in Behçet syndrome (BS) uveitis has considerably improved in time. We wanted to quantitate this impression.

Methods: Medical records of 9289 BS patients registered between the years 1976 and 2019 were screened for uveitis and severe visual impairment (SVI). SVI was defined as an irreversible visual acuity of $\leq 20/200$ for at least 3 months. After exclusion of patients with inadequate data (n=527) the remaining 8762 patients were analyzed in 4 different time periods according to the registration year (G1: before 1990, G2:1990-1999, G3:2000-2009, G4:2010-2019).

Results: A total of 4409/8762 (50.3%) BS patients had uveitis history, and 776/4409 (17.6%) of them had SVI in either or both eyes. Males had more frequent and severe uveitis in all time periods. The frequency of bilateral SVI decreased in time both among the patients with initially no SVI or among the patients with initially unilateral SVI. This decrease was more pronounced among the males initially with no SVI. In men, the proportion of patients progressing from unilateral to bilateral SVI was higher in the before-2000 group (64/199, 32%) compared to the after-2000-group (19/118,16%) [$\chi^2=9.8, p=0.002$].

Conclusions: These data emphasize the strikingly different disease course of BS uveitis between males and females. They also confirm the contention that we can currently much more effectively manage BS uveitis. We propose that the SVI definition we use reflects better medical management rather than a milder natural disease course at recent times. Finally, our observations emphasize that drug trials in BS uveitis should either be conducted separately in either sex or include enough patients of either sex.

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Cardiovascular disease in Takayasu arteritis: experimental and questionnaire studies of vascular dysfunction, therapeutic targeting, and patient and physician perspectives

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Background/Aims: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a chronic large-vessel vasculitis associated with increased cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk. The mechanisms underlying this risk are poorly defined. Preliminary data suggest endothelin-driven endothelial dysfunction. We aim to characterise vascular dysfunction in TAK, assess a novel therapeutic strategy, and explore patient and physician perspectives on CVD risk reduction.

Methods: We designed an experimental study (NCT06887062) to compare endothelial function and arterial stiffness in 30 patients with TAK in remission versus matched controls. Patients then enter a 10-week, open-label trial of dual therapy with the endothelin receptor antagonist, bosentan (62.5 mg/day), and the sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor, dapagliflozin (10 mg/day). The primary endpoint is arterial stiffness assessed using gold standard pulse wave velocity; secondary outcomes include endothelial vasomotor function assessed by venous occlusion plethysmography, flow-mediated dilation, 24-hour blood pressure, retinal optical coherence tomography, and immune cell profiling. Concurrently, an online questionnaire investigates patient and physician views on CVD risk reduction in TAK.

Results: To date, 6/60 participants have been recruited to the experimental study, with full recruitment anticipated by July 2027. The interventional phase has commenced. The questionnaire is live and accruing responses.

Conclusions: This study will provide new insights into vascular dysfunction in TAK and evaluate combined endothelin receptor antagonism and SGLT2 inhibition as a therapeutic strategy. The questionnaire will clarify patient and physician perspectives, enhancing understanding of the burden of CVD in TAK and informing the design of targeted preventive approaches.

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Assessment of damage in relapsing polychondritis

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Background/Aims: Relapsing polychondritis (RP) is a rare multisystem inflammatory disease, with predilection for cartilaginous structures. Uncontrolled inflammation could lead to organ damage. We characterized the spectrum of organ damage and associated features in RP.

Methods: Damage items, as defined in the RP damage index (RPDAM), were assessed in patients with RP within an ongoing prospective cohort in association with demographics, clinical manifestations and immunosuppressive medication use.

Results: 136 patients had at least one study visit; median disease duration was 6.9 years, (IQR 3.6–11.5). Among the 67 (49.3%) patients with damage, 57.4% developed one, 17.6% two, 10.2% three, 8.8% four, and 1.4% six items of damage. Sensorineural hearing loss was the most common form of damage (30/133, 22.6%), followed by auricular deformities (22/134, 16.4%), tracheomalacia (20/134, 14.9%); bronchomalacia (20/134, 14.9%), nasal bridge collapse (19/134, 14.2%), and subglottic stenosis (12/134, 9%). The frequency of African American ethnicity (n=6, 9.4% vs n=0, 0%; p = 0.03), male sex (n=22, 32.8% vs. n=11, 15.9%, p = 0.03) and ocular involvement (n=33, 49.3% vs. n=15, 22.4%, p < 0.01) was higher in patients with damage than without damage. In patients with and without damage, use of glucocorticoids (94% vs. 90%, p = 0.37) and methotrexate (74.6% vs. 66.7%, p = 0.31) was similar. Infliximab (34.3% vs. 4.3%, p < 0.01) and tocilizumab (14.9 vs. 4.3%, p = 0.03) were more frequently used in patients with vs. without damage.

Conclusions: Organ damage is frequent in RP, often affecting multiple organs, and is associated with African American race, male sex, and ocular involvement. Patients with damage are more likely to receive biologics, possibly due to physician bias toward escalating therapy only with observable damage. These findings highlight the need for research to prevent and manage damage in RP.

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Long-term renal and survival outcomes in microscopic polyangiitis: a single-centre observational study

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Background/Aims: Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) frequently involves the kidneys and carries substantial risks of relapse and ESKD. While ANCA-associated vasculitides are extensively studied, data focusing on MPA remain limited.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed consecutive MPA patients fulfilling 2022 ACR/EULAR criteria and followed at a single centre (May 2004–May 2025). Clinical, laboratory and treatments data were collected at diagnosis, relapses and at last follow-up. Primary outcomes were all-cause mortality, relapse, and ESKD (requirement for chronic dialysis or kidney transplantation). Predictors were assessed using Cox regression (univariable and multivariable). ANCA negativity was included as a time-varying covariate in the survival models.

Results: 71 MPA patients were included (median age 66 years; 54.5% female); 98.6% were ANCA-positive, predominantly MPO-ANCA (91.5%). At diagnosis 94.4% had renal involvement. Induction comprised glucocorticoids alone (16.9%) or with immunosuppressants (83.1%), mainly cyclophosphamide (31%) and rituximab (19.7%). Mycophenolate mofetil (21.4%) was the most used maintenance agent. During follow-up, 90% achieved remission, 18.3% died, 26.8% relapsed and 26.8% progressed to ESKD. Among those with ESKD, 18.3% required dialysis and 7% underwent transplantation. Survival was lower in patients aged ≥ 65 years ($p=0.0019$), with rapidly progressive nephritis ($p=0.0263$), hypertension ($p=0.0251$), or dialysis at onset ($p=0.0445$). Faster ANCA negativity was independently associated with better survival (HR 0.76; $p=0.022$) while baseline hypertension with a lower relapse risk (HR 0.18; $p=0.016$). In the competing-risks framework, ESKD risk increased with higher BVAS ($p=0.002$), higher FFS ($p=0.003$), nephrotic-range proteinuria ($p=0.007$) and impaired renal function at diagnosis ($p<0.001$). No survival differences emerged by induction or maintenance regimen.

Conclusions: In this single-centre MPA cohort, renal involvement was common and one quarter progressed to ESKD. Despite high remission rates, relapses were frequent. Age ≥ 65 years, rapidly progressive nephritis and dialysis at onset predicted poorer survival, while quicker ANCA negativity was associated with improved survival. These findings support vigilant renal risk stratification and standardized follow-up in MPA.

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Increased baseline serum creatinine with histopathological findings can predicts early severe renal impairment in ANCA-associated vasculitis: A multicentre retrospective cohort study

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Background/Aims: This study aimed to identify clinical, laboratory, and histopathological predictors of progression to eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73 m² within 12 months in patients with GPA and MPA.

Methods: In this retrospective, multicentre cohort, patients with GPA or MPA and adequate renal biopsy were included. Cox regression model was designed with predictors, including demographics, AAV type, baseline labs, comorbidities, induction therapy, and renal histopathology. The renal outcome was defined as a persistent eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73m² from diagnosis or within 12 months.

Results: A total of 75 patients with AAV were included, with 18 patients in the eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73m² and 57 in the eGFR ≥30 at 12 months. GFR <30 group were older (median 65 vs. 52 years, p=0.030) and more frequently had microscopic polyangiitis (66.7% vs. 33.3%, p=0.012) and MPO-ANCA positivity (72.2% vs. 28.1%, p=0.005). No significant differences were observed in sex distribution, organ involvement, BVAS, or inflammatory markers between groups. Baseline laboratory data revealed markedly higher creatinine (497 vs. 206 μmol/L, p<0.001) and lower GFR (8.5 vs. 27 mL/min/1.73m², p<0.001) in the GFR <30 group, while proteinuria, haematuria, and ANCA titres were comparable. Induction treatment regimens, including pulse steroids, cyclophosphamide, rituximab, plasmapheresis, and haemodialysis, did not differ significantly. Renal biopsy showed fewer normal glomeruli (12.1% vs. 36.4%, p=0.012) and more sclerotic glomeruli (35.1% vs. 9.1%, p<0.001) in the GFR <30 group. Moderate-to-severe interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy were more frequent (p=0.007), as were arteriolar lesions (56.3% vs. 19.3%, p=0.013). Crescentic and fibrinoid necrosis percentages were not significantly different. Increased baseline creatinine strongly predicted poor early renal outcome: compared with creatinine 0–249, hazard ratios for progression were 17.1 (95% CI 1.15–254.1, p=0.040) for creatinine 250–499 and 48.0 (95% CI 2.30–1001.8, p=0.013) for creatinine ≥500.

Conclusions: Baseline renal function, independent of histopathology, strongly predicts early progression to severe renal impairment in AAV.

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Impact of histopathologic patterns on clinical outcomes in ANCA-associated vasculitis presenting with glomerulonephritis: a single-centre experience in Central Taiwan

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis is the most common cause of rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis (RPGN). Glomerular pathology is classified into four subtypes: focal, crescentic, mixed, and sclerotic. This study examined the correlation between histopathologic subtypes and clinical outcomes.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 40 RPGN patients who underwent kidney biopsy between July 2005 and December 2019, all demonstrating pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis. Histopathologic findings were classified by predominant glomerular subtype, and interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy (IFTA) were assessed. Patients were stratified by urgent haemodialysis (HD) requirement (n=15 vs. n=25). Patient and renal survival were analysed according to glomerular subtype and IFTA severity.

Results: Baseline eGFR was significantly lower in the urgent HD group (median [IQR]: 5.0 [4.3-6.1] vs. 10.6 [7.1-25.1] mL/min/1.73m², p<0.001). Pulmonary-renal syndrome was more prevalent in the urgent HD group (46.7% vs. 12.0%, p=0.024). ANCA positivity was detected in 36 patients (90.0%): 31 MPO-ANCA and 3 PR3-ANCA. Histopathologic subtypes included sclerotic (25.0%), crescentic (30.0%), focal (12.5%), and mixed (32.5%). The proportion of globally sclerotic glomeruli was significantly higher in the urgent HD group (42.1% vs. 20.0%, p=0.037). The proportion of cellular crescentic glomeruli did not differ between groups. IFTA exceeding 50% was observed in 33.3% of the urgent HD group versus 16.0% of the non-HD group. Long-term HD dependency occurred in 80.0% of patients requiring initial urgent HD compared with 28.0% in the non-HD group.

Conclusions: Higher proportions of sclerotic glomeruli are associated with urgent haemodialysis requirement. Patients requiring urgent HD at presentation have a substantially increased risk of long-term dialysis dependency, highlighting the prognostic value of early histopathologic assessment.

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The impact of the SARS-CoV pandemic on treatment patterns and long term kidney outcomes among incident ANCA vasculitis patients enrolled in the RITA Ireland Vasculitis (RIV) Registry and Biobank.

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Introduction/Aims: The Covid-19 pandemic posed a significant challenges to healthcare access and provision. We hypothesised that the pandemic may have altered induction immunosuppressive therapy in AAV with consequent effects on major adverse renal outcomes.

Methods: We compared baseline characteristics, immunosuppressive therapy and clinical outcomes in AAV patients enrolled in the RIV Registry between Mar-2020 Oct-2022 and compared it with pre-pandemic controls. The primary outcome was a composite of major renal adverse outcomes; death, ESKD, eGFR <15mls/min/1.73m² at 4 years.

Results: 114 Covid era patients were compared to 129 in the control group (Jan-2016 – Jul-2017). The Covid era mean age was 61.3 years (SD13.8), 42% were female. eGFR at presentation was 46.0 (SD38.7) ml/min/1.73 m². 11% required haemodialysis at presentation. 42% were PR3 positive. The control group mean age was 63.4 (SD14.0) years. 45% female. eGFR at presentation was 37.8 (SD33.7) ml/min/1.73 m². 19% required haemodialysis at presentation. 37.9% were PR3 positive. 40% of patients in the Covid group received Rituximab versus 31% of the controls. 18% of Covid patients received cyclophosphamide versus 31% of the controls. 25% of the Covid patients received methylprednisolone compared to 31% of the controls.

There was no significant difference in major renal adverse outcomes (Fig. 1) (log rank p=0.87). The eGFR at 4 years was 48.4 (SD38.7) ml/min/1.73 m² for the Covid era patients compared to 43.8 (SD30.5) ml/min/1.73 m² for the control group. 11.4% of the Covid era patients required dialysis in comparison to 17.0% of the control group

Conclusions: In Ireland, where strict public health measures were observed no effect of the Covid-19 pandemic could be identified in induction treatment patterns or long term kidney outcomes in patients recruited to the RITA Ireland Registry. Potential confounding factors include lack of enrolment outside specialist centres and missed diagnoses due to lack of healthcare access.

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Kidney failure in people with ANCA-associated vasculitis: a systematic review of outcomes

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Background/Aims: Kidney involvement in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (AAV) significantly increases morbidity and risk of mortality, particularly when there is progression to end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). This systematic review focused on the cumulative incidence of ESKD in people with AAV and assessed how changes in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) impact the risk of developing ESKD.

Methods: Literature searches were performed in the PubMed, EMBASE and Cochrane Library databases to identify studies that reported the incidence of ESKD and the impact of eGFR on ESKD risk, focusing on studies published in 2019–2024 with at least 100 participants followed up for a minimum of 3 years. Combined estimates of the cumulative incidence of ESKD over time and hazard ratios (HRs) quantifying the relationship between eGFR and ESKD risk were calculated.

Results: A total of 49 studies (19,301 patients) reported the incidence of ESKD, while 19 studies (4,513 patients) reported the relationship between eGFR and ESKD risk. The cumulative incidence of ESKD ranged from 2.9 to 59.6% at 1 year of follow up, and from 9.4 to 51.4% at 10 years of follow up. ESKD incidence was 13.7% and 23.6% at 1 and 10 years of follow up, respectively, in the pooled analysis. The meta-analyses assessing the impact of eGFR on ESKD risk showed that 1 mL/min/1.73 m² increases in eGFR at diagnosis and at 6 months after diagnosis were associated with 5–6% and 7–8% reductions in ESKD risk.

Conclusions: This systematic review indicates that people with AAV remain at high risk of ESKD, with lower eGFR at diagnosis and at 6 months after diagnosis associated with poorer kidney outcomes. However, the pooled estimates should be used with caution, given that baseline patient characteristics and observed outcomes varied greatly across studies.

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Treatment and outcomes in anti-glomerular basement membrane disease

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Background/Aims: KDIGO 2021 Glomerular Diseases Guidelines recommend treatment for anti-Glomerular Basement Membrane (GBM) disease except in patients dialysis-dependent at presentation, with 100% crescents or >50% global glomerulosclerosis on biopsy, and no pulmonary haemorrhage.

Methods: Case series of all patients diagnosed with anti-GBM disease between January 2017 and July 2025 in 2 UK tertiary centres. Clinical and laboratory data were obtained from electronic records.

Results: Of 72 patients with anti-GBM disease, 49% (n=35) were female, median age 64 years and 32% (n=23) were ANCA-positive; 18% (n=13) PR3, 14% (n=10) MPO-ANCA. Median creatinine at presentation was 700µmol/litre (range 35-3494µmol/litre). Pulmonary haemorrhage occurred in 26% (n=19). Patients received a median of 7 plasma exchange (PLEX) sessions (range 0–51) and 3 doses of intravenous cyclophosphamide (range 0-8).

Twenty-eight patients (38.9%) were dialysis independent at presentation; 3/27(11.1%) progressed to end stage kidney disease by 12 months. Of the 44 (61.1%) patients requiring dialysis at presentation, 5/42 (11.9%) recovered renal function; these 5 had a median creatinine at presentation of 777 µmol/litre and 14 PLEX sessions (range 7–38).

Renal biopsy was performed in 54.2% (n=39); 3/39 had 100% crescents and four >50% global sclerosis. One with 100% crescents, and 2/4 with >50% global sclerosis did not require dialysis at presentation and remained dialysis independent at 12 months. Of those requiring dialysis at presentation who underwent a biopsy, 13/39 (33.3%) had <10% normal glomeruli (2/13(15.4%) recovered renal function); 7 patients had ≥10% normal glomeruli and 2/7(28.6%) recovered. Anti-GBM antibody titres were >600 in 41.6% (n=30); 73% were dialysis dependent at presentation (n=22). Only 1 was dialysis independent at 12 months.

Conclusions: Patients dialysis-independent at presentation largely maintained renal survival at 12 months, regardless of biopsy findings. Even with adverse histology or high creatinine, renal recovery was possible, supporting treatment in most patients with anti-GBM disease.

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ANCA vasculitis and renal transplantation: understanding recurrence and risk

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a systemic autoimmune disease that often affects the kidneys, with up to one-third of patients progressing to end-stage renal failure (ESRF) despite modern immunosuppression. Kidney transplantation is the preferred treatment, but relapse risk after transplant remains uncertain.

Methods: We performed a retrospective cohort study of patients with AAV who underwent kidney transplantation between 2014 and 2025 at Addenbrooke's Hospital, Cambridge, UK. Data were collected from the Electronic health records and the transplant database, including ANCA subtype, organ involvement, therapies, transplant characteristics, infection and cancer incidence, and survival outcomes.

Results: Forty-nine patients underwent transplantation; 66% were male, with a mean age of 56 years (range 20–75). MPO-ANCA positivity was most common (65.3%). Donor sources were 63.3% DCD (Donation after Circulatory Death), 16.3% DBD (Donation after Brain Death), and 20.4% living donation; 83.6% had a mismatch grade ≥ 3 . AAV relapse occurred in 8.1% of patients, typically involving the kidney (6.1%) or ENT systems (2.0%) consistent with initial presentation. Among those who relapsed, half were ANCA negative and half persistently positive pre-transplant (even split between MPO and PR3). Persistent ANCA positivity overall was present in 40%. Infections occurred in 57%, highest in those treated with a cyclophosphamide based induction regimen prior to transplantation. Non-melanoma skin cancer accounted for most malignancies (52%), with highest risk in older patients and those exposed to azathioprine.

Conclusions: Relapse after kidney transplantation is uncommon but clinically significant, particularly in persistently ANCA-positive patients. Careful serological monitoring and tailored immunosuppression are essential, while balancing relapse prevention against infection and malignancy risks. This study may open new diagnostic and therapeutic perspectives in AAV transplantation, while larger multicentre studies are needed to clarify prognostic factors and guide optimal management.

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Major relapse in ANCA-associated vasculitis - a population-based cohort study

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Background/Aims: To determine the incidence rate, predictors, and outcome of major relapse in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in a population-based cohort.

Methods: The study included patients with AAV diagnosed between 2010 - 2019 in southern Sweden. Major relapse was defined as reappearance or worsening of AAV disease activity with a Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) >0, with one major or three minor BVAS items requiring re-induction with either cyclophosphamide or rituximab. To identify major relapses, we reviewed case records from all relevant hospitalizations (2010-2023) and rituximab administrations at Skåne University Hospital in Lund and Malmö. Patients were considered at risk of relapse if they were in remission while receiving <10 mg/day of prednisolone for at least three months. Incidence rates of major relapse were estimated as events per person-year (PY) at risk. PY was calculated from time patients judged as at risk until the earliest of relapse, death, or study end (2023-12-31). Predictors of major relapse were analysed using Cox regression

Results: During the study period, 150 patients (69 female) were at risk for relapse; 29 (19%) experienced major relapses over 726 years of follow up. The incidence rate of major relapse was 4/100 PY, higher in MPO-ANCA vs. PR3-ANCA patients (5.0 vs. 3.6/100 PY, p=0.3). Major relapse occurred in 29% of patients with chest involvement at diagnosis; the corresponding proportions were 18% for those with renal involvement and 16% for those with ENT involvement. Baseline chest involvement was independently associated with relapse (HR 4.37, 95% CI 1.45-13.19, p= 0.009). Relapse did not affect overall survival; adjusted HR for death was 1.20 (95% CI 0.57-2.49, P=0.6).

Conclusions: In our study, major relapse occurred in approximately one in five patients. Chest involvement at diagnosis emerged as a significant predictor. However, major relapse did not impact the overall survival of patients with AAV.

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Diabetes mellitus in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis vs. the General Population

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Background/Aims: Patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) have increased comorbidity, including cardiovascular disease and metabolic complications. This study estimated the incidence of new-onset diabetes mellitus (DM) following AAV onset and compared it with the general population in Southern Sweden.

Methods: We conducted a population-based cohort study of patients diagnosed with AAV between 2000-2019 (population ~701,000). For each patient, 10 controls matched by birth year, sex, area of residence were selected from the general population. Using the Skåne Healthcare Register and National Drug Register, we identified incident DM cases between 2000–2024 after AAV diagnosis (index date for controls), excluding patients with pre-existing DM. Incidence rates (IR) and incidence rate ratios (IRR) of DM were calculated. Time-dependent Cox regression models were used to study the impact of DM on survival.

Results: We included 297 AAV patients (48% women, mean age 63 years) and 2,558 controls. During 2,420 person-years (PY), 51 patients (17.1%) developed DM compared to 312 controls (12.2%) during 27,462 PY. IRs were 2.10/100 PY in AAV and 1.13/100 PY in controls, yielding an IRR of 1.85 (95% CI 1.35–2.53). The association was significant in women (IRR 2.47, 95% CI 1.60–3.81, $p < 0.001$) but not men (IRR 1.40, 95% CI 0.89–2.20, $p = 0.1$). The highest IRR occurred within three months of AAV diagnosis (16.0, 95% CI 7.86–32.6). DM significantly worsened survival (adjusted hazard ratio [HR] 1.58, 95% CI 1.26–1.97, $p < 0.001$), and overall mortality was more than doubled in AAV patients vs. controls (HR 2.36, 95% CI 1.94–2.88).

Conclusions: Patients with AAV have an almost twofold higher incidence of DM compared with the general population, with the greatest risk shortly after diagnosis, likely due to glucocorticoid exposure, highlighting the need for effective glucocorticoid-sparing therapies to reduce long-term morbidity and mortality.

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Osteoporosis in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: a cross-sectional study

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are rare systemic diseases with high mortality if untreated with immunosuppressives, including glucocorticoids. Per local treatment guidelines, all newly diagnosed cases receive osteoporosis prophylaxis. This study assesses osteoporosis prevalence in AAV.

Methods: Patients with AAV attending tertiary care in Skåne University hospital were enrolled after giving written consent. In this cross-sectional study, patients underwent Dual-energy X-ray (DXA) of hip, spine and whole body. Risk factors for osteoporosis were assessed. Fracture Risk Assessment score (FRAX) was calculated.

Results: The study included 84 patients: 58 (69.0%) with GPA, 16 (19.0%) with MPA and 10 (11.9%) EGPA; 45 % were women. The median age at diagnosis was 60.4 (IQR:47.9-65.5) and the median disease duration at inclusion was 8.0 years (IQR:5.0-12.3). DXA results were available in 80 patients; 46% (n=39) osteopenia, 19% (n=16) osteoporosis, and 31% (n=25) normal bone mineral density (BMD). Osteoporosis prevalence was 19% in GPA, 19% in MPA, and 30% in EGPA (p=0.4). The prevalence of osteoporosis was higher in women than in men (28% vs. 14%, p=0.1), while osteopenia were comparable (50% vs. 48%, p=0.8). Among patients <50 years (n=13), 1 had osteoporosis and 3 osteopenia. Mean age at AAV diagnosis did not differ between patients who later developed osteopenia (57.2 vs. 53.8 yrs., p=0.3) or osteoporosis (60.2 vs. 54.3 yrs, p=0.1). FRAX scores were available for 63 cases. The median fracture risk for hip fracture was 3% (IQR 1–6; no difference between sexes, p=0.1) and for major osteoporotic fractures 12% (IQR 7–22), with higher risks observed among women (p<0.001).

Conclusions: More than two-thirds of patients with AAV had low BMD (osteopenia or osteoporosis). Sex and age had less impact than expected. Early identification of at-risk patients and minimising glucocorticoid exposure may help reduce fracture risk.

Real-world clinical, humanistic, and economic burden of granulomatosis with polyangiitis and microscopic polyangiitis in China

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) are rare autoimmune diseases that can lead to substantial clinical and economic burden, yet data from China are limited. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the clinical, humanistic, and economic burden of GPA/MPA in Chinese patients.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective cohort study of adults with GPA or MPA managed at Xiangya Hospital (2010–2024). Patients were followed from the first visit with GPA/MPA (study index) until last visit or death. Data from the GPA/MPA registry, electronic records, and billing databases included demographics, clinical characteristics, comorbidities, treatments, and outcomes (mortality, end-stage kidney disease [ESKD], dialysis, severe infections). Healthcare resource utilization and direct costs were categorized by service type. Additionally, a cross-sectional survey of survivors assessed health-related quality of life (EQ-5D-5L, SF-12) and indirect costs.

Results: A total of 275 patients were included (mean age 60.5 years; 53.1% male; 87.6% MPA). At baseline, 46.9% had hypertension, 25.8% ESKD, and 12.4% diabetes. Among the 189 newly diagnosed patients, 80.4% received glucocorticoids in combination with other therapies. Over the post-index period (mean follow-up= 4.3 years), the mortality rate was 4.2 per 100 person years, 13.7% developed ESKD, and 13.9% experienced severe infections. Within 12 months post-index, patients averaged 22.5 hospitalization days, 6.6 outpatient visits, and direct medical costs of CN¥48,695 (81.7% for hospitalization). Among 189 survey respondents (66.8% of contacted patients), mean EQ-5D-5L utility was 0.815 (standard deviation [SD]: 0.246); the SF-12 scores for Physical Component Summary and Mental Component Summary were 38.9 (SD: 11.4) and 49.0 (SD: 10.0), respectively. Indirect annual costs averaged CN¥10,884, largely out-of-pocket (accounting for 55.7%).

Conclusions: GPA and MPA in China impose significant clinical, humanistic, and economic burdens. High mortality and ESKD risk, low physical HRQoL, and substantial costs highlight the need for improved management strategies and health policy support.

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Frailty measure as a proxy for infection in ANCA vasculitis – a proposal for infection risk modelling to optimize patient outcomes

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Background/Aims: ANCA vasculitis affects the elderly and often results in a rapid decline in general health. We aimed to better understand the interaction between ANCA associated inflammation and the impression of frailty to improve prediction modelling for adverse outcomes.

Methods: We performed a multi-centre retrospective analysis of newly diagnosed ANCA GN patients investigating the clinical frailty scale (CFS) at diagnosis for its association with clinical outcomes. Logistic regression analysis estimated the effect of CFS on infection, with adjustment for established risk factors. Elastic net regularisation selected predictors to be evaluated in a logistic regression framework for predictive performance.

Results: Working on a complete data basis, 305 patients were included in the analysis. The median CFS score at time of diagnosis was 3 with an IQR of 3-5. An association was detected between CFS score and mortality ($p=0.0358$), with 19.1% of patients dying with an initial CFS of 1-2, 30.1% with CFS of 3-4 and 41.4% with CFS of 5-7.

Multivariable logistic regression showed that CFS significantly associated with infection at 6 months (OR=1.53, 95% CI: 1.25-1.90, $p<0.001$), and at 12 months (OR=1.58, 95%CI: 1.30-1.95, $p<0.001$), independent of age, kidney function, lung disease and diabetes. Each increase of 1 point in the CFS was associated with 58% higher odds of severe infection during the first year of treatment. Elastic net regularisation retained CFS as the only key predictor among established risk factors, with moderate discrimination (AUC 0.69, 95%CI: 0.620-0.754), good calibration (Hosmer-Lemeshow $p=0.631$) and acceptable overall accuracy (Brier score 0.212).

Conclusions: CFS at diagnosis was a strong independent predictor of infection and mortality providing more prognostic information than established risk factors. Elastic net modelling found CFS the dominant predictor of infection, suggesting CFS assessment able to assist in stratifying infection risk and guiding intensity of therapy in ANCA vasculitis.

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The Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas): 12 months follow-up data on 230 patients with AAV

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Background/Aims: Prospective long-term observational data on the disease course of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) have been lacking in Germany to date. Herein, we present 12 months follow-up data from patients with newly diagnosed and relapsing AAV (inception cohort) enrolled in the Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas).

Methods: GeVas is a prospective, web-based, multicentre, clinician-driven registry designed to document organ manifestations, damage, long-term outcomes, and therapy regimens across various types of vasculitis in German-speaking countries.

Results: Between June 2019 and June 2025, 389 patients with AAV (Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA): 277, Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA): 112) were enrolled including 254 (66%) with new-onset and 131 (34%) with relapsing AAV. Median age was 61 years (19-88 years, range), and 179 (46 %) patients were female. Twelve-months follow-up data were available for 230 patients. At one year, 167 (73%) patients had achieved remission. Fourteen major (6%), and 21 minor relapses (9%) occurred during the first year. Six (3%) patients died within 12 months mainly from infections, none from active vasculitis. Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) decreased from 9 (5-14 IQR) to 0 (0-1 IQR). Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI) was 1 (0-2 IQR) after 12 months. For induction therapy most patients received glucocorticoids (n = 350, 90%), rituximab (n = 203, 52%) and/or cyclophosphamide (n = 145, 37%). The majority obtained rituximab (n = 120, 52%) to maintain remission.

Conclusions: Compared to other previously published European AAV cohorts from the United Kingdom (UK), Spain, Ireland, Poland, Germany and Switzerland, differences were observed in the prevalence of ANCA positivity, organ involvement, BVAS, treatment regimens, and clinical outcomes. Relapse, but also remission rates at 12 months were lower than previously reported. Notably, one-year survival and renal survival in our cohort exceeded previous reports. COVID-19 pandemic adversely affected patient recruitment.

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The Graz Vasculitis Registry (GRAVAS): rationale and clinical research protocol

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Background/Aims: Systemic vasculitides affect around 20 to 40 per million population per year and are considered as “common-rare diseases”. Severe multi-organ dysfunction might occur, however limited knowledge of underlying disease and diversity of clinical features are major barriers of successful treatment strategies. Registries are key contributors to achieve a sufficient sample size for clinical research studies, while multidisciplinary approaches that link clinical and outcomes data with a potential linkage to serial biologic specimen collection might help to bridge this gap.

Methods: The Graz Vasculitis Registry (GRAVAS) is a single-centre, multidisciplinary, web-based clinical database using the encrypted web application REDCap based on the European Vasculitis Society model registry to conduct clinical research in systemic vasculitis at the Medical University of Graz (MUG). Adult patients with the diagnosis of systemic vasculitis (new-onset disease or being treated for vasculitis) will be included. Clinical data will be compiled on a longitudinal basis and requested at a minimum of twelve-month intervals to coincide with routine clinical follow-up. Data will include, but will not be limited to, clinical characteristics, items of disease activity and damage, medication status, images of radiological examinations and predefined clinical outcomes.

Results: The study protocol has been reviewed and accepted by the Ethical Committee of the MUG, followed by a successful implementation and testing of the clinical database. The patient recruitment has started at the Division of Nephrology and is planned to be extended to the Divisions of Rheumatology and Immunology, and Angiology. For this aim, a multidisciplinary meeting was held discussing the development of a shared patient recruitment strategy and data collection process.

Conclusions: The GRAVAS registry supports multidisciplinary collaborative efforts to study patients with systemic vasculitis and their outcomes at the Department of Internal Medicine at the MUG and provides a reliable basis to initiate a national collaboration in Austria.

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The establishment of the Australia and New Zealand Vasculitis Quality and Disease Registry (ANZVASC-QDR): framework and protocols

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Background/Aims: When the Australia and New Zealand Vasculitis Society (ANZVASC) was established, a vasculitis quality and disease registry (QDR) was identified as a priority. The ANZVASC-QDR has been established, focussing on ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) with the option of enrolling patients with large vessel vasculitis (LVV).

Methods: In establishing the ANZVASC-QDR, ANZVASC worked with EUVAS using a EUVAS-designed REDCap data dictionary modified for ANZ but retaining EUVAS's compulsory questions, thus facilitating collaboration and data linkage. Community representatives were involved in development as Committee Members and ANZVASC Board Members.

Results: An opt-in registry has been established with quality and research functions, capable of enrolling incident and prevalent patients. The core dataset consists of an initial visit and yearly follow-ups. Data from additional visits can be entered for specific studies. Disease and treatment complications are recorded. Renal outcomes align with EUVAS definitions: temporary dialysis, eGFR<15 mL/min or dialysis for >90 days, and kidney transplantation. A large vessel vasculitis module was developed, based on the 2018 EULAR core data set for giant cell arteritis. Consumers contributed to the development of self-reported ethnicity, and the inclusion of a patient reported outcome measure (PROM) for physical activity (IPAQ-SF). Other PROMs used are the AAV-PRO and EQ-5D-5L. Data access and publication policies, adapted from those used by the ANZ Dialysis and Transplant Registry, were approved by the ANZVASC Board and publicised. The Monash Vasculitis Registry migrated to the ANZVASC-QDR and available participants reconsented. At 18/09/2025, eight sites in Australia and New Zealand were active in the ANZVASC-QDR (with governance underway at a further eight sites). 238 participants have been enrolled, with a median follow-up of 2 years (range 0-9).

Conclusions: The ANZVASC-QDR has been established as a multidisciplinary quality and disease registry for vasculitis in Australia and New Zealand that can align with European registries and datasets.

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Prioritised ANCA-associated vasculitis outcomes for reporting from the Australia and New Zealand Vasculitis Registry determined by patient-clinician consensus

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Background/Aims: Annual reports from the Australian and New Zealand Vasculitis Society Quality and Disease Registry (ANZVASC-QDR) will provide information about AAV and its care, but no studies define reporting outcomes for AAV registries. This study sought to prioritise AAV outcomes captured in the ANZVASC-QDR, determined by patient and clinician consensus.

Methods: Participants were AAV patients and clinicians from Australia, New Zealand, UK and Ireland, recruited by email and online advertising. Two Delphi survey rounds (Likert scale) scored 30 outcomes captured in the ANZVASC-QDR, followed by a pairwise comparison round ranking the top 15 outcomes from the first two rounds. This process determined the top eight final outcomes, with mandatory inclusion of the two highest-ranked outcomes for both patient and clinician groups, and the top-ranked patient-reported outcome measure (PROM). Scores and rankings of both groups were equally weighted.

Results: There were 233 participants (125 AAV patients, 108 clinicians) who completed the first round and 189 (81.1% retention rate) completed all three rounds (104 AAV patients, 85 clinicians), including 143 (75.7%) from Australia, 30 (12.9%) from UK and 11 (5.8%) from New Zealand. The top two ranked outcomes for patients were vasculitis relapse and vasculitis activity, and for clinicians were mortality and kidney failure. The top-ranked PROM was the AAV Patient-Reported Outcome tool (AAV-PRO). The remaining top-ranked consensus outcomes were non-glucocorticoid immunosuppressant use, glucocorticoid-associated complications and kidney function. Clinicians more highly prioritised mortality (physician-rank 1, patient-rank 12), kidney failure (physician-rank 2, patient-rank 8) and kidney function (physician-rank 5, patient-rank 10), while patients more highly prioritised the AAV-PRO (patient-rank 3, physician-rank 12).

Conclusions: This consensus process defines the community's prioritised reportable AAV registry outcomes, comprising objective clinical outcomes (mortality and kidney outcomes), disease status (activity and relapses), treatment related outcomes (type of immunosuppression given and glucocorticoid-associated complications) and an AAV-specific PROM.

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Health-related quality of life in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: a cross-sectional study

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a group of rare systemic diseases with a high reported impact on physical and mental quality of life. This study investigates health-related quality of life (HRQoL) in patients with AAV compared to Swedish population norms, with in-group comparisons.

Methods: A cross-sectional single-centre study enrolled patients with all disease phenotypes within AAV (GPA/MPA/EGPA). Patients attending Rheumatology or Nephrology outpatient clinics at our hospital were enrolled after giving their written consent. All patients were evaluated using the SF-36 instrument to measure HRQoL, with answers compiled into two overarching health-indices, a Physical Composite Score (PCS) and a Mental Composite Score (MCS). The PCS and MCS were compared to the Swedish population norm using student's t-test. In-group differences were tested with linear regression models, adjusted for sex and age. The scores have a minimum clinically important difference of 5 points.

Results: The study included 84 patients (58 (69.0%) GPA, 16 (19.0%) MPA and 10 (11.9%) EGPA). There were 38 (45.2%) women. Median age at diagnosis and disease duration at inclusion were 60.4 (IQR:49.1-65.5) and 8.0 (IQR:5.0-12.3) years, respectively. Patients with AAV had significantly worse PCS (43.1 CI:40.5-45.6) than the Swedish population norm (50 for both PCS and MCS). No significant difference was seen in MCS (48.6 CI:46.4-50.7). MPA was associated with a reduction in PCS (9.9 CI:3.2-16.6) and MCS (7.0 CI:1.9-12.0) compared to patients with GPA. Cardiovascular involvement at the time of diagnosis was associated with a reduction in PCS (16.9 CI:6.4-27.1). No associations were seen with the eGFR at diagnosis, ANCA type, other types of organ involvement, or the disease duration.

Conclusions: HRQoL is decreased in patients with AAV compared to the Swedish population norm in the physical but not mental domains. Both the physical and mental domains are worse in patients with MPA.

Validation of the Japanese version of the ANCA-associated Vasculitis Patient-Reported Outcome (AAV-PRO): A prospective multicentre cohort study in Japan (J-CANVAS-PRO)

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) includes microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), and eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA),

with clinical manifestations varying by disease type and ANCA serotype. The AAV-Patient-Reported Outcome (AAV-PRO) is a disease-specific health-related quality of life (HRQoL) measure for AAV consisting of six domains. This study evaluated the reliability and validity of the Japanese version of the AAV-PRO in AAV patients.

Methods: A multicentre observational study was conducted between February and June 2024 at 21 Japanese institutions in the J-CANVAS registry. Patients with MPA, GPA, or EGPA completed the Japanese versions of the AAV-PRO and EQ-5D-5L. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Test-retest reliability was evaluated using intraclass correlation coefficients in patients who completed the questionnaire twice within eight days. Validity was assessed via correlation with EQ-5D-5L (convergent validity), comparison by disease activity based on physician-assessed BVAS (known-groups validity; remission defined as BVAS=0 and active disease as BVAS \geq 1), and confirmatory factor analysis (construct validity).

Results: Among 392 patients who received the questionnaire, 290 responded (74%), and data from 263 patients were analysed; 219 patients were included in the test-retest analysis. The mean age was 71.3 years, and 59.7% were female. Diagnoses included MPA (n=132), GPA (n=67), and EGPA (n=64). Serotypes included MPO-ANCA (n=183), PR3-ANCA (n=33), and ANCA-negative (n=47). Internal consistency was acceptable in most domains. Test-retest reliability was supported by intraclass correlation coefficients above 0.6. Convergent validity was demonstrated by moderate negative correlations with EQ-5D-5L ($r = -0.404$ to -0.668). Known-groups validity was partially supported in five of six domains. Construct validity was partially supported by model fit indices.

Conclusion: The Japanese AAV-PRO demonstrates acceptable reliability and validity for assessing HRQoL in patients with AAV living in Japan.

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The AAV-PRO correlates with quality of life indices and adds to the assessment of Australian ANCA-associated vasculitis outpatients

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Background/Aims: To investigate the relationship between ANCA-associated vasculitis patient-reported outcome (AAV-PRO) domains and patient characteristics, other health related quality of life (HRQOL) measures, disease activity and damage in an Australian cohort.

Methods: Prospective observational study on AAV patients attending vasculitis clinic who were assessed at an outpatient visit using the AAV-PRO (six domains, each scoring 0-100, higher is worse), BVAS (activity), VDI (damage), SF-36, and patient and physician global health assessments (PtGA/PhGA).

Results: Eighty-eight patients participated (86% kidney involvement, 39% active disease). Systemic symptoms (SS, 36.0) and concerns about the future (CAF, 32.9) were the highest (worst) scoring domains. Physical function (PF) was lowest (22.9). Scores were similar between males and females. AAV-PRO domains were negatively correlated with SF-36 (-0.264 to -0.686, all $p < 0.05$, Spearman's Rho) and PtGA/PhGA (-0.361 to -0.648, $p < 0.01$), except organ specific symptoms (OSS/PhGA: -0.150). PR3-AAV patients had higher treatment side effects (TSE, 34.4 vs 23.2, $p = 0.01$, t-test) and CAF (40.1 vs 28.3, $p = 0.02$) scores than MPO-AAV. Patients >65 years old had higher TSE scores (32.6 vs 23.8, $p = 0.03$). Only PF scores were higher in active disease (29.8 vs 18.5, $p = 0.05$) and only PF correlated with VDI (0.373, $p < 0.01$), Years since Diagnosis (-0.303, $p < 0.01$) and (weakly) with BVAS (0.273, $p = 0.01$). Patients diagnosed >5 years ago had higher OSS (33.5 vs 23.3, $p = 0.03$), TSE (33.5 vs 23.3, $p = 0.01$), and CAF (38.5 vs 28.0, $p = 0.03$). Those with a VDI >3 (indicating significant chronic damage) reported a higher TSE (36.5 vs 24.2, $p = 0.02$) and CAF (43.3 vs 28.5, $p = 0.01$). Patients with renal involvement had higher SS scores (38.9 vs 24.6, $p = 0.03$).

Conclusions: AAV-PRO scores correlate well with established HRQOL measures, but not directly with disease activity or BVAS, thereby highlighting the potential value of the AAV-PRO in holistic clinical care.

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A study of changes in patient-reported outcome measures using AAV-PRO and their correlation with anxiety, depression, and fatigue in ANCA associated vasculitides

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitides (AAV) are chronic, multisystem autoimmune diseases requiring long-term immunosuppression, significantly impacting patients' quality of life. Patient perspectives often differ from physician assessments, highlighting the need for systematic evaluation of patient-reported outcomes. The aim of this study was to evaluate changes in patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) using the AAV-PRO questionnaire over 3 months and explore correlations between PROMs and anxiety, depression, and fatigue.

Methods: A longitudinal observational study was conducted in 101 patients with AAV at a North Indian tertiary care centre. Patients were assessed at baseline and after 3 months using the AAV-PRO questionnaire, Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7), and Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), with validated English and Hindi versions of each instrument. Disease activity and damage were measured using the Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVASv3) and Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI). Changes in PROMs and correlations with clinical and psychological measures were analysed.

Results: The cohort comprised 101 patients with AAV (mean age 46 ± 13 years, 61% females), predominantly Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (86.14%). Four patients (3.96%) had expired at follow-up. Baseline assessments showed significant fatigue in 64% of patients ($FSS \geq 36$), with anxiety ($GAD-7 \geq 5$) and depression ($PHQ-9 \geq 5$) each affecting 45%. The median total AAV-PRO score improved from 138.75 to 114.16 at 3 months ($p < 0.0001$), with all six domains showing significant improvement, especially Organ-Specific Symptoms and Physical Function. AAV-PRO scores correlated strongly with PHQ-9 ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$) and GAD-7 ($r = 0.67$, $p < 0.001$), but weakly with BVAS and VDI. Patients with active disease showed greater improvement across all domains.

Conclusions: AAV significantly impairs quality of life, with high rates of fatigue, anxiety, and depression. PROMs improved over time and reflected psychological burden more accurately than clinical measures, underscoring the need for integrated, patient-centred care.

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Health related quality of life in AAV is multifactorial

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Background/Aims: There are several known factors that affect health related quality of life (HRQoL) in inflammatory disease such as disease activity, physical function, fatigue, social status, and age, although results are not consistent. To what extent these factors explain impaired HRQoL in people with AAV in Sweden is sparsely studied. The aim was to explore determinants of HRQoL in AAV in Sweden.

Methods: Cross-sectional data was collected between 2008-2024 in Sweden. Adults with AAV answered The EuroQoL five-dimension three-level questionnaire (EQ5D index, visual analogue scale (EQ-VAS, 0-100), Multi Assessment of Fatigue (MAF), and The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Score (HADS). Disease activity was measured with Birmingham Vasculitis Score (BVAS) and BVAS >0 was considered as active disease.

Determinants of HRQoL (EQ5D index) were explored through a linear regression model including gender, age, educational level, living with someone, disease activity, disease duration, skin-, lung-, renal manifestations, fatigue, anxiety and depression.

Results: 232 patients with AAV answered all questionnaires, women 51.1%, mean age of 58 years (± 15), mean disease duration of 4,8 years (± 6), mean BVAS 6.2 (± 8.4), 25.8% with active disease. A minority of the patients (3,8%) had skin manifestations, 21,3% lung manifestations and 29,4 % renal manifestations.

When exploring HRQoL (EQ5D index) correlations show that patients with skin manifestations, although few in this cohort, reported lower levels of HRQoL. Patients with more fatigue also reported lower HRQoL as well as patients with depression. These correlations, although significant, are all considered weak or very weak/absent. The model provided explain 42,6% of factors determining HRQoL in AAV.

Conclusions: Patients with skin manifestations, patients with fatigue and patients with depression experience lower HRQoL. Our reported regression model explains only 42,6% of factors affecting HRQoL in AAV which points to the fact that HRQoL is multifactorial and needs further study.

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Rare Autoimmune SELF-management (RAISE) programme development: results from qualitative studies to explore the needs of underserved people with rare autoimmune rheumatic diseases in the UK

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Background/Aims: Rare autoimmune rheumatic diseases (RAIRDs) are multisystem diseases that impact on health-related quality of life. Patients share common experiences of coping with complex conditions. We aimed to explore perspectives of underserved populations with RAIRDs who are typically underrepresented in research.

Methods: Participants were identified via community networks and National Health Service clinics. Posters were translated. Six community focus groups in 3 centres were conducted. Data were analysed inductively.

Results: Thirty-nine participants recruited. Median age 53 years (range 21-84); female (86%); SLE (28%), Sjögren's disease (18%); ANCA associated vasculitis (AAV) (10%), Behcet's disease (8%), Myositis (8%), Scleroderma (8%), Takayasu arteritis (3%), cryoglobulinaemic vasculitis (3%), disease duration > 2 years (72%); White British/European (56%), British Pakistani (8%), British Bangladeshi (5%), African (5%), Caribbean (5%), Sri Lankan (3%), Mixed White/Black (3%), Greek Cypriot (3%), Hong Kong (3%), Latin American (3%), Indian (3%), Other British Asian (3%); college/university education (67%); employed (49%), unemployed (5%), disabled (unable to work) (10%), retired (26%). One overarching theme described "Challenges of navigating the patient journey". Subthemes included: "Rare, widespread, invisible symptoms", "Complex healthcare system", "Support for social and emotional impact", "Impact on work and finances", "Lack of healthcare professional knowledge about rare conditions", "Lack of specialised information".

Quotes included: "I've now got to look at my career because I'm being advised by rheumatology to either take an early retirement or medically retire". Male, AAV, 53. "when I went off sick, the people who work, I think they thought. What's she doing? She's skiving", Female, 60, Myositis. " ..when we have some kind of language barriers; we have to have more time to think about what we want to tell the doctor" Female, Behcets ,50.

Conclusions: These findings highlight the need for targeted resources and will inform the development of a self-management support intervention for people with RAIRDs.

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Long-term health-related quality of life and educational needs in AAV

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Background/Aims: Disease duration has been proven to associate with an increased need of educational support and lower Health related Quality of Life (HRQoL) in ANCA associated vasculitis (AAV). Longitudinal studies using the Educational Needs Assessment Tools (ENAT), and how educational needs relates to HRQoL are however scarce. The aim was to explore how educational needs and HRQoL changes over time among patients with AAV.

Methods: Longitudinal data was collected from adults with AAV in Sweden. Educational needs were captured by the ENAT questionnaire and HRQoL by EuroQoL five-dimension three-level questionnaire (EQ-5D index, 0-1) and visual analogue scale (EQ-VAS, 0-100) at baseline and after 24 months. Paired samples t-test was used to compare means between the two timepoints.

Results: 27 individuals (59% women) with GPA (n=23) and MPA (n=4) completed both questionnaires at baseline and follow-up. At baseline, mean age was 54 years, ranging from 20-76, mean years of education 13 (± 1.8), and mean disease duration 0.4 years, 85% were newly diagnosed. All individuals had an active disease, with a mean BVAS of 13,7, range 1-25 at baseline.

The mean total ENAT score decreased from 79.6 at baseline to 69.6 at 24 months ($p=0.032$).

Educational needs decreased within three of seven domains, 'Self-help measures' -2 ($p=0.016$), 'Treatments' -3.8 ($p=0.003$), and 'Support systems' -1.4 ($p=0.024$).

Mean EQ5D index at baseline was 0.639 and increased with mean by +0.169 ($p=0.006$) to 0.807 at 24 months, still not reaching full health. At the same time, mean EQ-VAS decreased over time (93 vs 71), although not statistically significant.

Conclusions: The educational needs decreased over time although still high after 24 months, and the HRQoL (EQ5D index) improved, although still impaired. These findings suggest that ongoing, tailored education adapted to the disease process is needed reduce AAV patients' informational needs and improve their HRQoL.

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The Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas): 12 months follow-up data on 43 patients with EGPA

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Background/Aims: Prospective long-term observational data on the disease course of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) have been lacking in Germany to date. Herein, we present 12 months follow-up data from patients with newly diagnosed and relapsing EGPA (inception cohort) enrolled in the Joint Vasculitis Registry in German-speaking countries (GeVas).

Methods: GeVas is a prospective, web-based, multicentre, clinician-driven registry designed to document organ manifestations, damage, long-term outcomes, and therapy regimens across various types of vasculitis in German-speaking countries.

Results: Between June 2019 and June 2025, 59 patients with EGPA were enrolled in the GeVas registry including 48 (81%) with new-onset and 11 (19%) with relapsing EGPA. Median age was 57 years (24-85 years, range), and 32 (54%) patients were female. Twelve-months follow-up data were available for 43 patients. At 1-year follow-up, 28 (65%) patients had achieved remission. Minor relapse occurred in 5 patients (12%) within the first year. No major relapses were reported. One (2%) patient died from cardiovascular disease in the first 12 months. Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) were detected in 15 (25 %) patients at baseline. At 12-months, 3 (7 %) patients had remained ANCA positive. Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) decreased from 9 (5-17, IQR) to 0 (0-3, IQR). Vasculitis Damage Index (VDI) was 1 (1-2, IQR) after 1 year. For induction therapy, most patients received glucocorticoids (n = 55, 93%) and cyclophosphamide (n = 35, 59%). At 1-year, patients mostly received anti-IL-5 therapy for maintenance therapy (n = 16, 37%). Complete withdrawal of glucocorticoids was achieved in 8 (19%) patients.

Conclusions: Baseline characteristics, remission rate, and one-year survival were comparable to prior studies. However, relapse rate and glucocorticoid withdrawal in our cohort was lower than previously reported. Consistent with earlier findings, ANCA prevalence decreased under treatment. COVID-19 pandemic adversely affected patient recruitment.

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Patient registry of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis in a Northern Spanish hospital

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare, systemic necrotizing vasculitis associated with ANCA, characterized by asthma, peripheral eosinophilia, and granulomatous inflammation affecting the respiratory tract and multiple organs. This study aims to describe the clinical, laboratory, and therapeutic features of EGPA patients managed at a tertiary referral hospital in northern Spain.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective descriptive study of 14 EGPA adult patients at the University Hospital of Navarra (2006-2025). Clinical, immunological, and treatment data were extracted from medical records. Variables analyzed included demographics, disease duration, organ involvement, eosinophil counts, ANCA profile, IgE and IgG4 levels, therapy received, relapses, and complications.

Results: The mean age was 64.4 years (SD \pm 16.4), with 50% female. Mean disease duration was 140.5 months (SD \pm 143.3). Asthma was present in 92.9% of patients, followed by ENT involvement (85.7%), pulmonary involvement (64.3%), skin (35.7%), peripheral nervous system (35.7%), cardiac involvement (35.7%), renal (28.6%), CNS (21.4%) and myopathy (14.3%). Eosinophilia was found in 92.9% of patients (median count of 5,764 cells/L). Elevated IgE levels were observed in 78.6%, and IgG4 in 21.4%. ANCA-P (anti-MPO) was detected in 64.2%, while ANCA-C (anti-PR3) was present in 14.3%. All patients received corticosteroids. Immunosuppressive therapy was used in 85.7%, mainly azathioprine and cyclophosphamide. Biologic agents were administered in 50%, primarily mepolizumab. Despite treatment, 42.9% experienced relapses in the last year, and all patients developed complications such as infections, fractures, or hospitalizations.

Conclusions: Asthma, ENT symptoms and pulmonary involvement were predominant. The cohort showed a typical eosinophilic and immunologic profile, yet high relapse and complication rates highlight the disease's burden. These findings underscore the need for tailored management and consideration of biologic therapies in refractory cases.

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Capturing what BVAS misses: patient-reported outcomes reflect disease activity and burden in EGPA

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Background/Aims: In EGPA, persistent asthma and ENT symptoms often remain clinically relevant despite therapy and may be under-captured by conventional activity scores. We evaluated whether patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), including the ANCA-associated vasculitis-PRO (AAV-PRO), sino-nasal outcome test (SNOT-22), and asthma control test (ACT) detect disease activity compared with Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score 3 (BVASv3).

Methods: EGPA patients starting biologics (anti-IL5/r or anti-IL4/13) were assessed prospectively from initiation (baseline). Clinical parameters and PROMs were recorded longitudinally, and correlations with BVAS were analysed. The AAV-PRO includes 29 items across six domains: organ-specific symptoms (OSS), systemic symptoms (SS), treatment side effects (TSE), social/emotional impact (SEI), concerns about the future (CAF), and physical function (PF).

Results: Forty patients (median age 54 years: 50% female; median disease duration 57.5 months) were enrolled. At baseline, despite prior immunosuppression and frequent ENT surgery, 60% reported ongoing ENT symptoms and 50% asthma symptoms, with median BVAS and VDI of 3.5 and 4, respectively. After 12 months of biologic treatment, BVAS reached zero ($p < 0.001$), with a concomitant reduction in prednisone dose ($p < 0.001$). Significant improvements were observed in SNOT-22 and all AAV-PRO domains, except CAF. The PROMs most strongly correlated with disease activity (BVAS) were PF ($p < 0.0001$), OSS ($p < 0.0001$), and SNOT-22 ($p = 0.0007$). ACT scores inversely correlated with symptom severity (higher ACT associated with fewer AAV-PRO-reported symptoms). No significant correlations were observed between BVAS and total AAV-PRO or ACT scores. At 12 months, despite clinical remission (BVAS=0, glucocorticoids < 5 mg/day), patients retained persistently elevated median SNOT-22 (23) and AAV-PRO (30) scores, reflecting ongoing perceived symptom burden.

Conclusions: In biologic-treated EGPA, PROMs reveal residual symptom burden not captured by BVASv3. Incorporating PROMs into routine assessment complements physician-reported activity, better reflecting patient burden and informing management.

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IgA vasculitis nephritis in childhood - a retrospective observational cohort study

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis is the most common systemic vasculitis in children, with nephritis (IgAVN) driving long-term morbidity. However, contemporary data on risk factors, renal outcomes, and treatment effectiveness remain limited. This study aimed to describe renal outcomes in Australian children with biopsy-proven IgAVN.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted across the two tertiary paediatric nephrology centres serving New South Wales and the Australian Capital Territory. Children aged 1–17 years with native kidneys and a histological diagnosis of IgAVN between 2014 and 2024 were included. Clinical data was extracted from medical records. Univariate and multivariate analysis was performed using Jamovi to identify factors associated with remission.

Results: A total of 70 children were included; 64% were male. Median ages at onset and biopsy were 7 years (IQR: 4–10) and 8 years (IQR: 4–11), respectively, with a median interval from presentation to biopsy of 43 days (IQR: 30–82). Median follow-up was 556 days (IQR: 254–1604). The average annual incidence of biopsy-proven IgAVN was 0.34/100,000 children. All patients presented with purpura, 91% presented with proteinuria; 73% with arthritis/arthralgia, and 60% with abdominal pain. Histology showed mesangial hypercellularity in 75%, endocapillary hypercellularity in 78%, segmental sclerosis in 53%, tubular atrophy in 5%, and crescents in 55%. Most patients received oral prednisolone (69%). Additional therapies used included pulsed intravenous methylprednisolone (61%), anti-metabolite agents (53%), renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system inhibitors (59%), and intravenous cyclophosphamide (14%). Overall, the 1-year remission rate was 47% and the 3-year remission rate was 60%. On multivariate analysis, older age at biopsy was independently associated with lower likelihood of remission (HR: 0.83; 95%CI: 0.69–1.00; p=0.05).

Conclusions: In this cohort, remission rates remained modest despite intensive immunosuppression. Older age at biopsy predicted poorer outcomes, underscoring the need for earlier recognition and more effective therapeutic strategies to optimise renal prognosis in paediatric IgAVN.

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Phenotype-based risk stratification and progression predictors in a multicentre Mexican cohort of adults with IgA vasculitis-associated nephritis

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Background/Aims: IgA vasculitis-associated nephritis (IgAVN) in adults is infrequent and often more severe than in the paediatric population. This study aimed to describe the clinical and histopathological characteristics, and renal outcomes in Mexican adults with IgAVN.

Methods: We conducted a multicentre retrospective study including patients with biopsy-proven IgAVN. Outcomes were renal relapse, >30% decline in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), need for renal replacement therapy, progression to end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), and mortality. Outcomes were analysed by survival analysis, and associated factors by Cox regression.

Results: Sixty-two patients were included; 33 (53%) were women, median age was 35 years (IQR 25–48), and median follow-up was 29 months (IQR 10–63). Skin manifestations occurred in 46 patients (74%). Median baseline eGFR was 85 ml/min/1.73 m² (IQR 41–121), and proteinuria was 1.7 g/g (IQR 0.8–3.5). Fifty-two patients (88%) were treated with prednisone. Four phenotypes for ESKD risk were identified: high (n = 10), moderate (n = 9), intermediate (n = 27), and low (n = 16). High-risk phenotype was associated with male sex (OR 5.9; 95% CI 1.32–41.78, p = 0.034), gastrointestinal manifestations (OR 3.73; 95% CI 0.92–18.9, p = 0.007), eGFR <60 (OR 5.49; 95% CI 1.27–24.52, p = 0.021), and Oxford T2 lesions (OR 11.9; 95% CI 1.46–128.23, p = 0.002). In Cox analysis, predictors of ESKD were eGFR <60, proteinuria, interstitial fibrosis, tubular atrophy, and inflammatory infiltrate. High- and moderate-risk phenotypes were also linked to relapse (HR 16.17, p = 0.020; HR 9.14, p = 0.041) and mortality (HR 16.18, p = 0.020; HR 9.15, p = 0.041).

Conclusions: In this multicentre IgAVN cohort, phenotype-based classification stratified the risk of ESKD, relapse, and mortality. These findings highlight the importance of early identification of high-risk patients and the implementation of targeted therapeutic strategies.

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Baseline clinical and laboratory predictors of new major organ involvement in Behçet's disease: results from an inception cohort

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Background/Aims: Behçet's disease (BD) is a chronic, multisystemic inflammatory disorder ranging from mucocutaneous to major organ involvement (MOI). The development of new MOI (nMOI) during follow-up is a major determinant of morbidity and mortality. This study evaluated the predictive value of baseline clinical and laboratory parameters for nMOI in an inception BD cohort.

Methods: In this prospective inception cohort, patients fulfilling ISG criteria were systematically assessed at baseline and follow-up. Demographics, clinical features, and laboratory parameters were recorded. MOI was defined as ocular, vascular, neurological, or gastrointestinal involvement.

Results: Ninety-four BD patients (median age 33 years, range 18–54; 60.8% male) were included; 15 (16%) developed nMOI during follow-up. Of these, 5 developed ocular, 8 vascular, 1 neurological, and 2 gastrointestinal involvement. Patients who developed nMOI were older at baseline (40 vs. 33 years, $p=0.06$). Baseline mucocutaneous features, including oral aphthae, were equally frequent, but folliculitis was more common in patients without nMOI (60.8% vs. 33.3%, $p=0.047$). Genital ulcers showed a non-significant trend (69.6% vs. 53.3%). During follow-up, patients with nMOI had higher rates of vascular complications including thrombophlebitis, deep vein thrombosis, and arterial involvement. Baseline acute phase reactants were significantly higher in patients who developed nMOI: CRP (23.6 vs. 5.5 mg/L, $p=0.034$) and ESR (25.5 vs. 11 mm/h, $p=0.005$). HLA-B51 positivity did not differ significantly between groups (27.8% vs. 40%, $p>0.05$).

Conclusions: In this inception BD cohort, higher baseline CRP and ESR were associated with subsequent nMOI development, suggesting that systemic inflammation and tissue injury markers may predict progression to major organ disease. Folliculitis and genital ulcers appeared more characteristic of a mucocutaneous-limited phenotype, potentially reflecting a lower risk of nMOI. HLA-B51 did not predict nMOI. Comprehensive baseline evaluation, with particular attention to acute phase reactants, may improve risk stratification and guide closer monitoring of patients at higher risk for severe disease.

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What happens to patients with Kawasaki disease in adulthood? Results of transitional rheumatology and cardiology clinics

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Background/Aims: Kawasaki disease (KD) is an acute medium-vessel vasculitis that affects children and is the leading cause of acquired heart disease in this population. While the acute phase of the disease is well documented, information on long-term outcomes in KD survivors transitioning into adulthood is limited. This study aimed to assess long-term cardiac and rheumatologic outcomes in adults with a childhood history of KD, focusing on echocardiographic findings and clinical examination for persistent or late-onset complications.

Methods: Patients with a history of childhood Kawasaki disease who presented to the Departments of Rheumatology and Cardiology were consecutively enrolled. All patients were Turkish. Demographic and clinical data were obtained from hospital records. All patients underwent cardiac examination including transthoracic echocardiography to assess coronary arteries, left ventricular function, valvular status, and pericardial involvement.

Results: A total of 23 patients with a childhood history of Kawasaki disease were included (mean age $19,3 \pm 2,9$ years; 47,8% female). The median interval between initial KD diagnosis and current evaluation was 14,8 years (IQR 11,4-17,1). Five patients had coronary involvement.

Echocardiographic findings: Coronary involvement was detected in five patients at diagnosis, but persisted only in one with a stable aneurysm at follow-up. Left ventricular function was preserved in all patients. Trace mitral regurgitation was observed in 16 cases and aortic regurgitation in one, while no myocarditis, pericardial effusion, or systolic dysfunction was identified.

Rheumatologic assessment of all were normal, with neither musculoskeletal manifestations nor vasculitic activity.

Conclusions: In adulthood, children without coronary involvement remained healthy; only one patient with coronary involvement had a stable coronary aneurysm. Although trace mitral regurgitation was common, it appeared clinically insignificant from a cardiology perspective, and long-term follow-up of these patients was planned.

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A retrospective analysis of mortality among patients with temporal artery biopsy at a public hospital

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Background/Aims: To describe the five and ten year mortality among patients with a temporal artery biopsy (TAB) performed at a public hospital for suspected GCA in Melbourne, Australia.

Methods: Patients who had a TAB performed between 1/1/2010 to 24/6/2021 at The Northern Hospital in Melbourne were included in this study. By retrospectively reviewing medical records, local data on demographics, investigations, cumulative steroid dose, five-year and ten-year mortality was collected. Data was analysed and ethics committee approval was obtained. Hypothesis testing was performed on mortality data using chi-squared tests for fixed endpoint analysis and log-rank test for survival analysis.

Results: During the 10-year study, 155 patients underwent TAB; 22 (14.2%) had positive biopsies and 39 (25.1%) were clinically diagnosed with GCA. The mean cumulative steroid dose was 10,124 mg (SD=6575.3mg) over the total course of their treatment; 18 (46.2%) stopped steroids, 14 (35.9%) continued, and 7 (17.9%) had incomplete records.

116 patients (74.8%) were not diagnosed with GCA: 32 (27.6%) had primary headache, 18 (15.5%) eye-related diagnoses, 17 (14.7%) other rheumatological conditions, 9 (7.6%) cervicogenic headache, 8 (6.9%) prednisolone-unresponsive headache, 3 (2.6%) neuralgia, 3 (2.6%) TMJ dysfunction, 7 (6.0%) other causes, and 19 (16.4%) unknown.

Five- and ten-year mortality rates were similar between GCA and non-GCA patients (23.1% vs 25.0% at five years ($p=0.81$); 30.8% vs 31.9% ($p=0.90$) at ten years), and survival analysis similarly did not show any significant differences between groups ($p=0.50$).

Conclusions: A quarter of patients who underwent TAB were diagnosed with GCA, of which steroid exposure was varied. Long-term mortality was comparable in GCA and non-GCA groups who had TAB performed, indicating that despite the need for careful diagnosis and ongoing management, overall survival outcomes are alike.

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Outcomes of ocular giant cell arteritis (GCA): A sub-group analysis of the South Australian GCA Registry

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a systemic vasculitis in which ocular involvement can cause irreversible vision loss. Despite prompt corticosteroid therapy, visual morbidity remains high. Tocilizumab, an interleukin-6 inhibitor (IL-6), has emerged as a treatment option. This study examined factors associated with vision loss and recovery in ocular GCA and compared outcomes in patients treated with or without tocilizumab.

Methods: GCA patients with any visual disturbance from 2019-2024 (n=59) were identified from the South Australian GCA Registry and data extracted from their ophthalmology notes. Demographics, visual acuity, functional outcomes, and treatment regimens were analysed. Visual loss was classified as mild (acuity $\geq 6/18$), moderate (6/18–6/60), or severe ($< 6/60$). Sub-group analyses compared outcomes between patients receiving tocilizumab and those treated with standard glucocorticoid therapy.

Results: Thirty (52%) patients had ophthalmologist-confirmed ocular GCA. 6 (20%) had mild visual loss, 2 (7%) moderate, and 16 (5%) severe. Less than half (43%) had documented visual improvement within 12 months. Among 23 patients who received tocilizumab, 11 (48%) demonstrated some visual recovery compared with 2 (29%) in the non-tocilizumab group, despite similar baseline visual loss severity (Fischer's exact $p=0.24$). Functional and social impact, such as loss of driving license, were reported in 13 (43%) cases.

Conclusions: Ocular GCA frequently results in severe, often permanent, visual impairment, with more than half of patients failing to improve. While a greater proportion of patients treated with tocilizumab showed visual improvement, the difference was not statistically significant, likely reflecting the limited sample size. Eccentric viewing could also account for apparent visual improvement, and obtaining reliable visual fields before commencing treatment in patients with severe GCA-related visual loss was a limiting factor. Early recognition and aggressive management remain critical to preserving vision, with IL-6 blockade warranting consideration as part of early therapy as it may improve visual recovery in GCA.

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Weight gain in year 1 following diagnosis with large vessel vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Large Vessel Vasculitis (LVV) is unique in that its treatment paradigms remain based around the use of high dose glucocorticoids. In Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA), glucocorticoid use alone is recommended until disease flare upon dose weaning. Glucocorticoid side effects are common and lead to significant morbidity including weight gain and adverse cardiovascular outcomes such as hypertension and impaired glucose control in a patient group at risk of accelerated coronary atherosclerosis.

Methods: Retrospective review of the clinical course of sequentially newly diagnosed patients with LVV over 1 year who received a standard tapering course of oral prednisolone. Weight gain was assessed by comparing baseline measurements with those at 12 months. Cumulative prednisolone dosage was recorded.

Results: 9 newly diagnosed patients were identified in whom serial weight measurements were available. 8/9 patients gained weight over 12 months with individual increases ranging from 3 to 20 kg. The mean weight gain was 8 kg (SD 6.1, median 8). The maximum recorded individual gain was 20 kg in an individual patient. The estimated cumulative prednisolone dose received over one year ranged from 1190 mg to 8580 mg, with a mean of 4479 mg (SD 2256 mg and a median dose of 3535 mg).

Conclusions: Weight gain in patients with LVV on a year-long weaning steroid regimen is common and often substantial, emphasizing the importance of monitoring metabolic side effects throughout steroid treatment. The modest association with cumulative steroid dose suggests multifactorial contributions, warranting further research into risk mitigation strategies. The use of GLP-1 agonists to reduce the weight gain and mitigate cardiovascular risk is attractive in this patient group and warrants dedicated study.

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Enhancing symptom capture in giant cell arteritis: the value of combined registry data from clinical records and patient surveys

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Background/Aims: Registries are uniquely positioned to integrate clinical record data and patient-reported information, offering a more complete view of disease presentation. We examined whether combining these sources improves ascertainment of presenting symptoms in giant cell arteritis (GCA).

Methods: We analysed 195 participants (69% female; mean age 74.4 years, range 55–92) from the South Australian GCA Registry with both case note review (CNR) and patient survey (PS) data. Thirteen presenting symptoms were compared across data sources. A symptom was classified as present in the combined registry dataset (CRD) if reported in either PS or CNR. Incidences were compared using McNemar's test.

Results: CRD achieved higher capture rates for all symptoms except blindness and stroke ($p < 0.05$). Data (CRD/PS/CNR, %) included: temporal headache (83/75/69), other headache (81/70/49), scalp tenderness (69/60/50), jaw claudication (73/64/60), visual disturbance (73/60/60), blindness (29/24/28), stroke (7/7/3), weight loss (44/36/31), loss of appetite (48/34/30), fatigue (72/64/42), malaise (74/70/39), fever (23/14/17), and polymyalgia rheumatica (60/50/39). Patient surveys more frequently identified certain symptoms (scalp tenderness, other headache, PMR, fatigue, malaise; $p < 0.05$) when comparing the incidence of reporting directly between PS and CNR, there was no difference for all other symptoms

Conclusions: Combining CNR and PS data substantially increases capture of GCA presenting symptoms, highlighting the complementary nature of patient and clinician reporting. Symptoms which impact patient wellbeing (fatigue, malaise, other headache) were more likely to be reported by PS than CNR. This study demonstrates the value in registries such as the South Australian GCA Registry which combine patient reported data with clinical records.

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Real world steroid burden, treatment patterns, and rheumatologists' perceptions on advanced therapy in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: This study assessed glucocorticoid (GC) burden, treatment patterns and rheumatologists' perceptions of advanced therapies (AT) for giant cell arteritis (GCA).

Methods: The Adelphi Real World GCA Disease Specific Programme™ survey of rheumatologists and patients with GCA in EU-5 and the United States (US) was used to record patients' demographics, treatment history, clinical characteristics and self-assessment, and rheumatologists' patient management approach and treatment perceptions.

Results: Of 196 rheumatologists surveyed, 846 patients with GCA (female: 63%; white: 94%; mean age: 71 years; median time since diagnosis: 15.2 months) were included. Most common treatments were GCs, tocilizumab [EU-5, 24%; US, 48%] and methotrexate [EU-5, 39%; US, 26%]. Median time to start tocilizumab was 3.8 months in the US and 6 months in EU5; for methotrexate, it was 5 months in both regions. Over the last 12 months, median cumulative GC doses were 4343mg, 5200mg and 2196mg for patients diagnosed <1, 1–2, and >2 years ago. Most rheumatologists aimed to taper to low dose GCs by 12 months (87%) and off GCs by 24 months (81%) post-diagnosis. The reported number of patients experiencing ≥1 GC-related AE was higher for rheumatologists compared to patients (74% vs 55%). Most rheumatologists (EU-5, 90%; US, 94%) agreed that ATs should be given early in GCA treatment to improve outcomes and reduce GC toxicity. Over 90% of rheumatologists believed the following AT attributes were important: maintenance of remission; achievement of GC-free remission; reduction of high-dose/cumulative GC use; to allow GC cessation; and to be safe, tolerable, and patient-compliant.

Conclusions: Although most rheumatologists aimed to taper patients off GCs by 24 months, 75% of patients were using GCs at 4 years. Rheumatologists and patients reported several AEs associated with GC use, and rheumatologists recognized the need for early and effective steroid sparing intervention with ATs.

A scoping review of measurement instruments of glucocorticoid toxicity

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Background/Aims: Glucocorticoids (GCs) are widely used as management of vasculitis and autoimmune rheumatic diseases (AIRDs). Despite well-established adverse effects (AEs) including osteoporosis, diabetes, infection and psychiatric comorbidities, the risk of toxicity has not been well quantified in clinical trials nor standardised across indications for use. The OMERACT Glucocorticoid-Related Adverse Effect working group established a core domain outcome set in 2021. Further work is required to establish appropriate measurement instruments for these core domains. This study aims to identify measures of GC toxicity, without restriction to AIRDs.

Methods: Medline, EMBASE, CINHALL and Cochrane Central were searched along with hand search of abstracts presented at major relevant rheumatology meetings (abstracts restricted to past 5 years (08/2019 – 08/2024) for studies referring to the use of exogenous glucocorticoids and reporting a clinician or patient reported outcome measure (PROM). Data extraction was performed in duplicate by 2 authors.

Results: 3694 individual records were identified and screened. 76 eligible studies were included for data extraction. 29 studies included a population with AIRD, of these 6 assessed patients with vasculitis (GCA, AAV). 33 assessed non-AIRD populations, 12 were not restricted to a specific disease. 1 encompassed AIRD and non-AIRD subjects. GCs were delivered systemically in 60 studies. From studies utilising clinician reported measures, bone fragility (n=31 papers) and mood disturbance (n=14) were frequently assessed, while fatigue (n=0), sleep disturbance (n=2) and appearance (n=1) were infrequently assessed. Conversely, studies utilising PROMs more frequently assessed fatigue (n=12), along with mood disturbance (n=23), sleep disturbance (n=16) and appearance (n=14). 25 PROMs and 46 clinician reported measures were identified.

Conclusions: 71 candidate instruments were identified for measurement of GC related AEs arising uniformly from AIRD and non-AIRD populations, with a high frequency of use of systemic glucocorticoids. PROMs were more likely to assess subjective AEs than clinician reported measures.

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Differences in clinical manifestations and long-term prognosis between juvenile-onset and adult-onset Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Differences in the clinical manifestations and prognosis of juvenile- and adult-onset Takayasu arteritis remain unclear. This study aimed to investigate the differences in clinical manifestations between juvenile- and adult-onset Takayasu arteritis and the long-term prognosis of glucocorticoid-free remission.

Methods: Patients attending Kyoto University Hospital between 2018 and 2024 with a disease duration of at least 3 years and onset before 60 years of age, and with a history of glucocorticoid treatment (juvenile-onset [<18 years]: $n=22$, adult-onset: $n=50$), were eligible for the study. Clinical characteristics, HLA, and the 30-year cumulative glucocorticoid-free remission rate were analysed using two-group tests, the log-rank test, and regression analysis.

Results: The age of onset (juvenile-onset vs. adult-onset) was 15.8 ± 3.6 years vs. 32.2 ± 10.1 years. No significant differences were observed in sex (female ratio: 100% vs. 100%) or observation period (22.7 ± 13.7 years vs. 21.3 ± 13.2 years). In the juvenile-onset group, aortic regurgitation was less frequent (27% vs. 53%), while renal artery stenosis was more frequent (18% vs. 4%). Numano classification type IIa was less frequent (14% vs. 28%), and type V tended to be more frequent (36% vs. 16%) in the juvenile-onset group. HLA-B*15 was more frequently observed in the juvenile-onset group (38% vs. 8%), with an odds ratio of 1.96 (95% confidence interval 1.39–36.0) for juvenile onset. The 30-year cumulative glucocorticoid-free remission rate was significantly lower in the juvenile-onset group compared to the adult-onset group (5% vs. 32%, $p=0.046$). The rate of steroid pulse therapy use tended to be higher in the juvenile-onset group (94% vs. 2%), while no significant differences were observed in the maximum prednisolone dose (35.9 ± 15.1 mg vs. 35.1 ± 24.6 mg), history of immunosuppressant use (55% vs. 52%), or history of biologic agent use (41% vs. 26%).

Conclusions: Juvenile-onset Takayasu arteritis has a worse prognosis compared to adult-onset, exhibiting differences in vascular lesions and HLA.

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The association between age at diagnosis and health-related quality of life in Takayasu's arteritis

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Background/Aims: Takayasu's arteritis (TAK) can occur throughout the lifespan and impacts health-related quality of life (HRQoL). This study examined the relationship between age at diagnosis of TAK and HRQoL.

Methods: The sources were two longitudinal cohorts of patients with TAK: the Vasculitis Patient-Powered Research Network (VPPRN, online patient-reported data) and the Vasculitis Clinical Research Consortium (VCRC, at expert centres). Cohorts were stratified by age at diagnosis: < 40 years (younger) and ≥ 40 years (older). Descriptive statistics were summarized. Univariable and multivariable linear regressions assessed associations between age at diagnosis and Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) scores (VPPRN) and 36-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36) scores (VCRC). Both multivariable models adjusted for glucocorticoid use and age at HRQoL assessment.

Results: Analysis included 218 (VPPRN) and 229 (VCRC) patients with TAK. Around two-thirds were diagnosed at <40 years old and >92% were female. Glucocorticoid use impacted HRQoL in both cohorts. In univariable analyses, there were only differences in sleep disturbance and physical functioning PROMIS scores by age at diagnosis. When adjusted, those diagnosed younger had worse sleep disturbance scores than those diagnosed older, with no difference in fatigue, depression, pain interference, satisfaction with participation in social roles, physical functioning, or anxiety scores. In univariable analyses, the SF-36 scores were better for the physical component, physical functioning, role limitations due to physical health, bodily pain, and vitality domains in those diagnosed younger versus older; in the adjusted model, there were no significant differences in SF-36.

Conclusions: Age at diagnosis with TAK is associated with HRQoL related to sleep disturbance, with worse results when diagnosed younger versus older. Glucocorticoid use also impacts HrQoL. Future studies of larger cohorts are needed to further assess the impact of age at diagnosis on HRQoL and guide interventional tools for people with TAK.

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Outcome of Takayasu arteritis patients with persistent laboratory activity and clinical quiescence (LACQ)

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Background/Aims: We aimed to determine and compare the presentation, course and angiographic outcome of TAK patients with laboratory activity and clinical quiescence (LACQ) and patients in clinical and laboratory remission (CLR).

Methods: Among adult patients with TAK, data of patients with LACQ, defined as presence of clinically stable disease (Indian Takayasu arteritis score, ITAS 2010<2) with raised CRP of >10mg/L on 2 consecutive visits 6 months apart was recorded retrospectively. Presence of new areas/worsening of thickness/narrowing/aneurysms on angiograms were considered as progression. Data of LACQ was compared with 71 TAK patients in CLR with ITAS=0 and CRP<6mg/L for >6 months after initiation of therapy.

Results: Among 874 patients screened, 96 (age at onset: 29.3±10.6 years, duration 22.0(0-63.0) months) satisfied the criteria of LACQ. Age at diagnosis was higher while frequency of Numano type-4 disease was lower for LACQ as compared with CLR. LACQ patients received lower initial dose of steroids than CLR [15.0 (5.0-30.0) vs 25 (17.5-35) mg/d, p<0.01]. Biologic DMARDs were used more commonly in LACQ than CLR (17.7% vs 4.5%, p=0.005).

During follow up of 31 (22-51.25) months, 15 (15.6%) and 18 (20.5%) of LACQ and CLR developed clinically active disease with ITAS≥2, p=0.5. Follow up angiograms (available for 76 and 71 patients respectively) showed progression in 22 (28.9%) and 17 (23.9%) of LACQ and CLR respectively, p=0.5. Mixed random effects regression model analysis showed serial CRP values to be higher in progressors than non-progressors after adjusting for steroid dose and time (regression coefficient=2.89), p=0.004. Re-classification of LACQ using CRP>16.5mg/L generated using ROC analysis showed angiographic progression in 41.9% of 43 patients which was higher than in CLR, p=0.059.

Conclusions: The clinical relapse and angiographic progression of TAK patients with LACQ were similar to patients in CLR. Persistent CRP values >16.5mg/L discriminated angiographic progressors and non-progressors during follow up.

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Evaluation of the effect of delivery mode on pregnancy outcomes in Takayasu arteritis: a large tertiary centre experience and the review of the literature

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Background/Aims: Despite a lack of data about the effect of delivery mode on fetomaternal outcomes in patients with Takayasu Arteritis (TAK), caesarean section is generally preferred in TAK with aortic involvement to prevent increase in intraabdominal pressure during vaginal birth. In this study, we aimed to investigate the relationship between fetomaternal complications, pregnancy outcomes and mode of delivery in TAK patients.

Methods: Patients with TAK who met the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) 1990 classification criteria and agreed to participate in the study were included.

Results: A total of 270 pregnancies of 106 patients were analysed. Infertility was observed in 6 (5.3%) of TAK patients, which was higher than the healthy Turkish population (HTP). Maternal pregnancy complications were seen in 18 (32%) and foetal complications were seen in 21 (37%) pregnancies with TAK. Among foetal complications, prematurity (PRM) and intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) rates were significantly higher in pregnancies after Takayasu arteritis (PATA). Live birth rates were significantly lower in PATA. Caesarean section rate increased and vaginal delivery rate decreased after the diagnosis of TAK. Fetomaternal complications were similar between the two delivery modes.

Pregnancies with PATA were planned in 25 pregnancies (55%) and unplanned in 20 pregnancies (45%). Unplanned pregnancies had more pregnancy complications (14 (25%) vs. 4 (7%) $p=0.002$)).

Conclusions: Our study results showed that prevalence of fetomaternal complications and the rate of caesarean section were increased in pregnancies of patients with TAK. In planned pregnancies, maternal complications were less common. We also found that vaginal deliveries in patients with TAK were not associated with an increase in delivery complications. For planned pregnancies of TAK patients, vaginal delivery can be considered as a possible mode of delivery under tight disease and blood pressure control, if gynaecologists do not prefer caesarean section for any other reason.

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Exercise practices among patients with Takayasu's arteritis: an international survey

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Background/Aims: Evidence-based exercise recommendations do not exist in Takayasu's arteritis (TAK). This study aimed to assess exercise practices and their impact on function in patients with TAK.

Methods: A survey of patients with TAK was conducted through the Vasculitis Patient-Powered Research Network (VPPRN). Participants were asked about frequency of exercise, exercise type, barriers to exercise, and physician recommendations about exercise. The Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder, and Hand Questionnaire (DASH) was used to quantify function of the upper extremity.

Results: 90 patients with TAK responded to the survey: median age=45 years (IQR 37-58); 90% female, and disease duration=11 years (IQR 6.3-24). Sixty-six participants (73%) reported that they currently exercise. Most patients reported exercising ≥ 3 days per week (68%), exercising for at least 30 minutes per session (68%), and consistently exercising for ≥ 6 months (77%). Respondents reported a variety of exercise activities: aerobic 81%, arm resistance 45%, leg resistance 38%. Shortness of breath (44%) and arm pain (42%) were the most common barriers to exercise. Physicians recommended exercise to 67 respondents (74%) but provided no specific instructions to 24 of these respondents (36%). Twenty-six respondents (29%) had a physician restrict exercise, typically without specific guidance. Twenty-three respondents (26%) reported concern about the safety of exercise. DASH scores were significantly lower for patients who did versus did not exercise (median 42 vs 51; $p=0.01$). Improvement in arm claudication was attributed to medication and exercise by 31% and 33% of respondents, respectively.

Conclusions: The majority of patients with TAK exercise regularly, but have concerns about safety of exercise, and do not receive clear guidance from their physicians about exercise activities or restrictions. A similar proportion of patients with TAK attribute improvement in upper extremity function to exercise compared to medication. There is an unmet need to develop safe and effective TAK-specific exercise programs.

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A cross-sectional study to compare patient reported outcomes (PRO) in patients with Takayasu's arteritis (TAK) treated with medical management or add-on endovascular interventions

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Background/Aims: We aimed to analyse Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMS) in patients with TAK who underwent endovascular procedures (EVAR) along-with medical management compared with those treated with medical management alone (DMARD only).

Methods: Consecutive patients with TAK at our clinics, who had at least one critically narrowed artery were included. PROMS including SF-36, Hospital anxiety and depression scale (HADS), details of clinical presentation, activity including Indian Takayasu arteritis activity score (ITAS 2010), C-reactive protein, ESR, Takayasu arteritis damage score (TADS) and prior procedures were noted. The PROMS of patients who have undergone at least one endovascular revascularization procedure at between 6 and 24 months prior to enrolment (EVAR) were compared with that of patients in DMARD only group. The Physical and Mental component scores were calculated.

Results: Among 93 patients enrolled, 39 and 54 patients were in DMARD-only and EVAR group. Among the EVAR group, 20, 37 and 2 patients underwent plain old balloon angioplasty (POBA), vascular stenting, or graft placement respectively at a median of 16.4 months prior to enrolment. The CRP, ESR, TADS and involvement of ascending aorta, arch and brachiocephalic trunk were more involved in DMARD only group while duration of disease was longer in EVAR.

The scores for physical functioning, role limitation due to physical health, pain, general health and health change domains of SF-36 score for EVAR group were significantly better than DMARD only group. HADS anxiety and depression scores were lower i.e. better for EVAR group.

Conclusions: Many of the domains of SF-36 scores including Physical component score (PCS) and both HADS scores were better in patients who were treated with add on EVAR as compared with DMARD only group. The DMARD only group had higher ITAS score, CRP and ESR values than EVAR group with a lower mean disease duration.

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Access to rheumatology care during the first year of polymyalgia rheumatica diagnosis: analysis from a national inception cohort

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Background/Aims: To describe the clinical and sociodemographic factors associated with receiving specialty care during the first year of a diagnosis of polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR).

Methods: We created an inception cohort using Medicare claims (2016–2022). Patients aged ≥ 50 years were included if they had: 1) ≥ 1 inpatient or ≥ 2 outpatient claims for PMR (ICD-10-CM M35.3) within 30–365 days, 2) glucocorticoid (GC) prescriptions of 7.5–30 mg/day within 30 days of diagnosis or between the first and second outpatient claim, with cumulative GC use ≥ 200 mg over ≥ 120 days of the first prescription period, and 3) continuous enrolment ≥ 1 year prior (without PMR or giant cell arteritis codes) and ≥ 1 year after the index date (first GC prescription). Covariates were collected during baseline. The outcome was rheumatology care, defined as ≥ 1 rheumatology visit within the first year. Multivariable Poisson regression was used to estimate relative risks (RR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for associated factors.

Results: Among 17,166 patients with new-onset PMR, 10,334 (60.2%) received rheumatology care within the first year. Of these, 3,636 (35.2%) were first seen after GC initiation, with a median (IQR) time to rheumatology visit of 56 (24–132) days. In adjusted analyses, older age (RR 0.91, 95% CI 0.90–0.92, per 5 years), rural residence (RR 0.81, 95% CI 0.77–0.84), and frailty (RR 0.91, 95% CI 0.85–0.96) were associated with a lower likelihood of rheumatology care. Female sex, higher social vulnerability, and greater local rheumatology density were associated with a higher likelihood. Patients initiated on GC doses outside the recommended guideline ranges were also less likely to see rheumatology.

Conclusions: In the U.S., 60% of patients with newly diagnosed PMR see a rheumatologist within the first year. Notably, those at greater risk of GC-related toxicity are less likely to receive specialty care.

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Determinants and outcomes of continuous rheumatology care in patients with a new diagnosis of polymyalgia rheumatica: findings from a national inception cohort

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Background/Aims: To describe factors associated with receiving continuous rheumatology care in patients with polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR), and treatment outcomes, including glucocorticoid (GC) use and osteoporosis care.

Methods: We created an inception cohort using Medicare claims (2016–2022). Patients ≥ 50 years were included if they had: 1) ≥ 1 inpatient or ≥ 2 outpatient claims with ICD-10-CM M35.3 within 30–365 days, 2) GC prescriptions 7.5–30 mg/day within 30 days of diagnosis with cumulative GC use ≥ 200 mg over ≥ 120 days, and 3) ≥ 1 -year baseline and ≥ 2 years follow-up enrolment, excluding prior PMR or giant cell arteritis. Rheumatology care was classified as continuous (≥ 2 visits/year), non-continuous (≥ 1 but < 2 /year), or none. Multivariable Poisson regression assessed factors associated with continuous care. Cumulative GC exposure, bone density screening, and osteoporosis medication initiation were compared across groups by level of rheumatology care.

Results: Among 13,132 patients with new onset PMR, 4,085 (31.1%) received continuous care, 3,782 (28.8%) non-continuous, and 5,265 (40.1%) none. Older age, rural residence, and frailty were independently associated with a lower likelihood of receiving continuous rheumatology care, whereas baseline osteoporosis diagnosis and higher rheumatology density were associated with a higher likelihood.

Mean cumulative doses of glucocorticoids differed by rheumatology care level: 2877 ± 2439.5 mg (non-continuous), 3523.9 ± 2780.3 (none), and 4211.6 ± 2299.9 mg (continuous). Bone density screening occurred in 56.0% of patients with continuous rheumatology care, 39.2% with non-continuous care, and 23.2% with none. Osteoporosis medications were prescribed in 19.4%, 11.3%, and 7.0%, respectively.

Conclusion: Continuous rheumatology care in patients with a new diagnosis of PMR is influenced by sociodemographic and clinical factors. It is associated with greater use of bone health interventions but also higher cumulative GC exposure, the latter possibly associated with more refractory disease in patients under rheumatology care.

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Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR): what's keeping the system from finding a sustainable solution?

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) affects over 200,000 people over the age of 55 in the UK but diagnosis rates are lower in the North of England compared to the South. With our charity partner PMRGCAuk, and by engaging patient groups, researchers, and health care professionals (HCPs), we aimed to uncover the causes of challenges to diagnosis, care and treatment of PMR in the North.

Methods: A Northern Outreach Lead (NOL) was appointed by PMRGCAuk to connect with the members of the PMR community including patients, HCPs, researchers and clinicians. A video comprising patient lived experiences, as told by them, was created. Finally, a series of multi-stakeholder events brought diverse people together to discuss system-level challenges. Qualitative thematic analysis of interviews with those involved in the project were also performed.

Results: Patients described PMR as an "isolating condition" with low public awareness. Guidelines appear to suggest a simple condition that is easily managed but patient experience does not often reflect this. Some of the confusing and contradictory messages were expressed in a poem, "Things we have heard about PMR". It emerged that the lack of perceived alternatives to glucocorticoids was a major driver of disconnects within the system: between patients and clinicians, and between primary and secondary care.

Conclusions: By listening to patients and frontline clinicians, we unravelled some of the system-level factors perpetuating barriers to effective care and support from healthcare services. Narratives about PMR need to shift from "nothing can be done" to more positive and hopeful stories.

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Rapid access strategy clinics for polymyalgia rheumatica – what do we know?

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Background/Aims: Polymyalgia Rheumatica (PMR) is typically diagnosed and managed in the community. The diagnosis can be challenging due to the absence of a single disease-specific test. Rapid Access Strategy (RAS) clinics may help and have been widely adopted for Giant Cell Arteritis, but their applicability to PMR is unestablished. To address this gap, this review compares existing RAS PMR clinic logistics.

Methods: A systematic review was carried out using PubMed and EMBASE (inception date to August 2025) with search terms matched with Medical Subject Headings and Boolean operators. Data were extracted on referral criteria, promotion, diagnostic work-up, treatment procedures, and follow-up.

Results: A total of 26 articles were retrieved for screening, of which six described RAS PMR clinics. However, two of these did not report on the number of patients referred for evaluation and were excluded. Of the remaining studies, all used structured referral criteria and specialist evaluation, including diagnostic assessment, but had variable use of supplementary investigations. Between 59% and 73% of patients attending specialist evaluation were diagnosed with PMR. Promotion initiatives, referral processes, and pre-evaluation glucocorticoid initiation varied, and the long-term glucocorticoid treatment was insufficiently reported. The sex distribution of those seen in the RAS clinics was not the same as community-based estimates of disease occurrence for PMR. Critically, no clinics provided a comprehensive cost-effectiveness analysis on outcomes.

Conclusions: Our review shows that RAS PMR clinics may have potential to affect diagnostic accuracy and inappropriate glucocorticoid initiation but underreported logistics limit comparability and hinder generalisation. Additionally, there appears to be selection bias in those seen in such services. Long-term management of glucocorticoid tapering was poorly documented, and no study included cost-effectiveness analysis, limiting conclusions about sustainability and scalability. Future research should evaluate diverse RAS models using robust cost-effectiveness analyses with extended time horizons to inform sustainable adoption.

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Enhancing general practice approaches to cutaneous vasculitis through a structured framework

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Background/Aims: Cutaneous vasculitis is a heterogenous condition defined by inflammation of blood vessels in the skin. While the prognosis is often favourable, distinguishing between self-limited cutaneous disease and systemic vasculitis is critical. General practitioners (GPs) are frequently the first point of contact, yet diagnostic uncertainty and variable referral practices can delay appropriate management. This initiative aimed to develop an educational framework to guide GPs in the recognition, investigation, and management of cutaneous vasculitis in community settings.

Methods: We reviewed current literature and synthesised practical diagnostic and management recommendations into a stepwise framework tailored for primary care. Key elements included systematic history-taking, focused examination, biopsy protocols, laboratory investigations, red-flag identification, and community-based management strategies. Educational tables and algorithms were developed to support clinical decision-making.

Results: The educational framework highlights critical features distinguishing types of cutaneous vasculitis, links clinical morphology to vessel size, and outlines appropriate first-line investigations. Key red flags—including constitutional symptoms, renal involvement, and pulmonary involvement—are emphasised to prompt urgent referral. Management recommendations stress treating underlying triggers, symptomatic relief, and timely referral to dermatology or rheumatology for systemic therapy when required. The framework also addresses common pitfalls, such as premature corticosteroid use prior to biopsy.

Conclusions: Structured educational resources can empower GPs to more confidently recognise and manage cutaneous vasculitis, improve diagnostic accuracy, and ensure timely referral when systemic disease is suspected. By integrating clear algorithms and red-flag recognition, this initiative strengthens the role of primary care in the multidisciplinary management of vasculitis. Broader dissemination of such an educational framework may improve patient safety, reduce diagnostic delays, and enhance collaboration between community and specialist care.

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An outcome survey of the utilisation, accessibility and value of the UK Eastern Network for Kidney Inflammatory Disease (ENKID) virtual multidisciplinary team meeting.

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Background/Aims: Patients with autoimmune kidney disease are complex, with sub-optimal management risking end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). Recent approvals for immune-targeted therapies have increased the need for specialist management to prevent ESKD and ensure equitable access to high-cost drugs (HCDs). The Rare Autoimmune Rheumatic Disease Alliance and UK parliament endorse networks for complex autoimmune rheumatic diseases. In 2023 the Eastern Network for Kidney Inflammatory Disease (ENKID) was convened to facilitate equitable access to HCDs. We report survey findings following the initial 18 months of ENKID multi-disciplinary team meetings (MDTs).

Methods: ENKID is hosted by a specialist renal autoimmune disease centre. Over 24 months, 229 case discussions for 198 patients were held across 43 MDTs, averaging 15 attendees per meeting. At the time of the survey, 33 MDTs had been held, involving 15 centres, 75 healthcare professionals with 164 patients discussed. An online survey evaluated accessibility, utilisation, and value.

Results: Forty responses were received from >10 East of England renal units. Respondents included consultants (n=29), renal trainees (n=6), pharmacists (n=4), and other (n=1). Of 39 responders, 21% attended all meetings, 31% monthly, 41% only with a case, and 8% had not attended due to workload. Thirty-four reported HCD approval for avacopan (74%), rituximab (56%), targeted-release budesonide (38%), belimumab (29%) and voclosporin (26%). Reported benefits included expert advice (90%), education (74%), HCD support (72%), sharing approaches to HCD implementation (67%) and trial access (54%). Forty-nine percent reported access to local MDTs for non-complex patients; 80% considered these sufficient for rituximab decisions in AAV, SLE and membranous nephropathy.

Conclusions: High case-load and attendance over 18 months highlights the need for ENKID. Survey responses (50% of attendees, majority of units) confirm high utilisation and value in specialist advice, education, and HCD access. With further HCDs on the horizon, robust networks such as ENKID are essential.

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Healthcare resource utilization and cost of illness in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Since the year 2000, several new treatments have been introduced for patients with anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). We aimed to analyse health care resource utilization and cost of illness in a population-based cohort of AAV.

Methods: We included 169 patients with AAV, each matched with 10 reference subjects (n=1,690) by age, sex, and area of residence. Diagnosis was between 2010 and 2019 in a defined geographical area, southern Sweden. Healthcare resource use was obtained from the Skåne Healthcare Register (SHR), covering primary, outpatient and inpatient care, prescribed drugs (from 2010), and hospital administered drugs (from 2014). Visits and episodes were costed using 2024 Diagnosis-Related Group prices; inpatient drugs by 2024 negotiated/list prices, and prescribed drugs adjusted to year 2024 prices using consumer price index. The impact of AAV on mean annual costs was estimated from 5 years before to 15 years after diagnosis using regression analyses.

Results: Health care use was limited for both AAV patients and controls up to 1 year before diagnosis. In AAV, costs rose in the year preceding diagnosis and remained higher than both controls and pre-diagnosis levels throughout follow-up. From 365 days before up to 365 days after diagnosis, AAV patients had EUR 28,562 (95% CI 24,144– 32,980) higher annual costs. During years 2–7, excess cost averaged EUR 9,870 (95% CI 6,483–13,258), and in years 8–15 EUR 5,491 (95% CI 1,091–9,891). Outpatient specialist care contributed 24%–49% of costs throughout follow-up, while inpatient care peaked around diagnosis (53% of cost). Hospital-administered drugs increased from 3% near diagnosis to 6-8% in later years.

Conclusions: This is the first Swedish health economic study in AAV. Despite advances and wider access to effective therapies, AAV remains associated with substantial and sustained increases in healthcare costs.

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Care gaps in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: exploring unmet needs and misalignments between patients and physicians

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) treatment guidelines emphasise the importance of effective communication between healthcare professionals (HCPs) and patients to facilitate shared decision making. This study investigates disconnects in communication/expectations between HCPs and patients.

Methods: A cross-sectional online survey was completed by AAV patients and HCPs across six European countries. HCPs had 2-35 years experience in relevant specialties and spent $\geq 60\%$ of their time in patient care. Patients were >18 years with a GPA/MPA diagnosis established ≥ 3 months earlier.

Results: The study included 170 HCPs (39% rheumatologists, 38% nephrologists) and 69 patients (80% GPA, 70% female, mean age 56 years, 48% in remission). Patients reported a longer, more challenging diagnostic process than HCPs, with greater emotional distress. According to patients, neurological and ENT symptoms had the greatest impact on quality of life, whereas HCPs focused on kidneys and lungs. Both groups agreed fatigue, pain, and sleep disruption were the most disruptive general symptoms. Patients >55 years and those with AAV >5 years were more likely to report disruption to mental health, outlook, and overall life. Sustaining remission, minimising treatment risks and addressing mental health were considerably more important unmet needs for patients than for HCPs. While 51% of HCPs and 57% of patients agreed patients should be involved in treatment decisions, only 26% of HCPs and 42% of patients felt this occurred. 40% of patients felt they received the best education; 64% required additional resources on treatment-related side effects. Patients had lower expectations than HCPs, with 59% of patients defining remission as significant improvement despite disease activity and 75% experiencing ≥ 2 symptoms during remission.

Conclusions: While both HCPs and patients value shared decision-making, differing priorities—clinical outcomes for HCPs versus long-term outlook, mental health, daily functioning for patients—highlight the need for more patient-centred AAV care.

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Developing quality standards for the diagnosis and management of giant cell arteritis in Australia

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Background/Aims: Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA) lacks established Australian quality standards for assessment, reporting, and monitoring care quality. The Australian Rheumatology Association (ARA) is developing the first quality standard for GCA diagnosis and management to address this gap and improve patient outcomes.

Methods: A quality standard advisory committee and multidisciplinary working group were established to develop the quality standard. Priority areas for quality improvement were identified through a structured process. Collaborative workshops and iterative surveys were used to formulate and refine quality statements with consensus defined as $\geq 70\%$ agreement among working group members.

Results: The ARA established an advisory committee in late 2024 to oversee development. Following February 2025 expressions of interest from ARA membership and organisational/consumer networks, a 28-member working group was formed including 15 rheumatologists (including dual training in clinical pharmacology, general medicine, and nuclear medicine), 3 consumers, 2 pharmacists, 1 registrar, neuro-ophthalmologist, neurologist, neuroradiologist, vascular surgeon, general practitioner, general physician, and rheumatology nurse practitioner.

Working group members nominated up to 10 priority areas for quality improvement, which underwent thematic grouping. Members attended two workshops, involving small and large group discussions to refine priority areas and formulate quality statements. This process resulted in 12 consensus draft quality statements.

Conclusions: Australia's first quality standard for GCA care is being developed through rigorous, multidisciplinary consensus processes. A national survey of healthcare professionals and people with GCA will be used to seek stakeholder consensus for 12 draft quality statements. Survey responses will be used to finalise statements, followed by development of corresponding quality indicators. Consumer and professional organisations will be invited to review and endorse the standard. This evidence-based standard will provide healthcare professionals, organisations, and policymakers with tools to benchmark service delivery, identify care gaps, and implement targeted improvements to enhance GCA care quality and patient outcomes across Australia.

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Establishing pathways – A public, private and executive partnership for temporal artery biopsies (TAB) to facilitate diagnostic reclassification and treatment de-escalation in a suspected GCA cohort

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Background/Aims: Temporal artery biopsy (TAB) can be an important test to aid the timely diagnosis and appropriate management of GCA. Access to TAB had been identified as a barrier to efficient care in our quaternary centre. We aim to describe a Quality Assurance process to address access to TAB in our centre.

Methods: The Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve, Control (DMAIC) model was used to establish a project design to improve access to TAB's. This activity was registered and approved under the local Quality Activity (GEKO 52734).

Results: Define: Create a robust referral pathway so a minimum of 90% of TABs occur in 2 weeks following rheumatologist referral.

Measure: Length of stay (LOS) time to biopsy and histopathology, diagnostic reclassification and treatment de-escalation, safety.

Analyse: Root causes of theatre access, surgical jurisdiction, patient triaging and interdisciplinary communication breakdown.

Improve: A public-private sector partnership was proposed and established following a multidisciplinary focus group. Finance and Executive stakeholders endorsed an initial 12-month pilot of the partnership.

From September 2024 - September 2025, 11 TAB occurred using this pathway. The average cohort age was 68.3 years (IQR 13) and 63.6% were female, 54.5% of these were outpatients. Average LOS was 1.6 days following a rheumatology consult (n=7 after removing 2 outliers with hospital stays for other reasons). Average time from referral to biopsy was 1.18 days (IQR 1) with 100% of biopsies occurring within 2 weeks and average return of histopathology was 2.55 days (IQR 2). Negative biopsies returned in 81.9% (n=9) of patients which enabled 100% of these patients to be re-diagnosed and cease or rapidly wean glucocorticoids. There were no reported complications.

Conclusions: The public-private sector partnership was successful in enabling a rapid access vascular biopsy pathway with 100% of biopsies happening within the standard of 2 weeks.

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Vasculitis-related harm: a retrospective analysis of litigation claims data from England for the Getting It Right First Time programme.

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Background/Aims: Delays in Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA) diagnosis and management can lead to irreversible visual loss. If preventable harm arises, litigation claims may be pursued. We used GCA-related litigation across all NHS Hospitals in England to identify trends and opportunities to improve care and reduce harm.

Methods: Number and cost of claims data across all specialities were extracted from NHS Resolution from 2018/19-2022/23 using keywords in free-text searches “giant cell arteritis” or “GCA”. Comparisons were made with 2013/14-2017/18 data, published in the 2021 Rheumatology GIRFT report. The relationship between hospitals having a formal GCA pathway in 2018 and occurrence of litigation was explored using χ^2 testing. Free-text claim data were analysed to generate themes and learning insights.

Results: The number of claims and costs doubled from 2013/14-2017/18 (n=22, cost = £6.6 million) to 2018/19-2022/23 (n=44, cost = £13.1 million). The most common injury was blindness/visual loss (n=40/44, 91%). Most claims related to delayed or failed diagnosis (n=38, 86%). The attributable specialty was ophthalmology (n=22), emergency medicine (n=8), rheumatology (n=3), general medicine (n=3), with single cases in neurology, respiratory, urology and dermatology. There was no evidence of an association between the presence of a formal GCA pathway and whether a hospital had experienced litigation (p = 0.733).

Conclusions: GCA-related litigation doubled in 2018/19-2023/23 compared to previous 5 years. Delays in diagnosis and treatment were the key underlying reason. Blindness was the main consequence. Litigation data may under-represent actual harm, highlighting the need for improvement in early diagnosis, immediate treatment and cross-specialty collaboration. All front-line professional assessing people with symptoms that can occur in GCA needs greater awareness of what action to take, using agreed and accessible national care pathways. Addressing this has the potential to reduce the harm and financial impact associated with delayed diagnosis and treatment in this high-risk condition.

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Practical pharmacogenomics in the clinic: EMR-linked and standalone solutions with Indream MediSupport

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Background/Aims: Integration of pharmacogenomic data into clinical practice remains challenging due to complexities in accessing genetic data and real-time clinical decision support. To address these limitations, Indream Healthcare has developed Indream Medisupport, an innovative platform designed for practical implementation of pharmacogenomics in routine clinical settings. This study highlights the capability of Indream Medisupport, emphasizing its interoperability with various Electronic Medical Record (EMR) systems and seamless integration with a patient-focused application, Indream MediChart.

Methods: We systematically reviewed and integrated pharmacogenomic guidelines from the CPIC (Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium), focusing on the TPMT gene (azathioprine metabolism), CYP2D6, and CYP3A5 (tacrolimus metabolism). Utilizing Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology, Indream Medisupport extracts relevant clinical data from various EMRs, irrespective of system compatibility. Concurrently, Indream MediChart collects de-identified patient genomic data, enabling immediate synchronization with Medisupport. This integration facilitates real-time pharmacogenomic alerts at the point of prescribing. To demonstrate the system's effectiveness, we created virtual dummy patient profiles representing TPMT, CYP2D6, and CYP3A5 variant haplotypes.

Results: Indream Medisupport effectively streamlined the integration of pharmacogenomic data into clinical workflows, enabling clinicians to receive real-time alerts about genetically influenced medication risks during prescribing. Unlike previous pharmacogenomic solutions, which often encountered implementation barriers due to EMR incompatibility or user-unfriendly interfaces, Medisupport's OCR technology offers versatile EMR integration.

Conclusions: While comprehensive pharmacogenomic guidelines exist, limitations remain regarding clinical recommendations for some enzyme-drug interactions due to insufficient empirical evidence. Nevertheless, known enzyme substrates suggest extensive pharmacogenomic implications for numerous medications. Indream Healthcare's pharmacogenomic database has catalogued hundreds of potential medication interactions, underscoring the broad applicability of genomic insights already achievable with existing patient genetic data. In conclusion, Indream Medisupport presents a scalable, practical model for routine clinical pharmacogenomics implementation, significantly addressing prior technological and logistical challenges.

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Whole team approach to connective tissue disease and vasculitis (CTDVAS): a survey study of healthcare professional perceptions of a weekly multidisciplinary team meeting

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Background/Aims: Connective tissue diseases and systemic vasculitides can be organ and life-threatening. British Society of Rheumatology 2025 ANCA-associated vasculitis guidelines highlight the need for coordinated multi-specialty care and timely access to definitive intravenous therapy. The Bristol Royal Infirmary (BRI) weekly virtual CTDVAS MDT includes all consultants, residents, nursing and admin. MDT is open to all BRI and Weston specialities. This survey explores healthcare professionals' perspectives.

Methods: An anonymous Microsoft survey was circulated to participants of the CTDVAS meeting. A 10-item questionnaire included questions on role and speciality. Participants were asked to respond to their agreement or disagreement to statements about the MDT in terms of supporting management of complex patients, education value, and initiation of targeted therapies using a 5-point Likert response (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree). Results analysed descriptively.

Results: Survey conducted August-September 2025. Respondents (n=25): Consultants (56%), Residents/fellow (36%), Nurses (8%). Specialities: Rheumatology (72%), Haematology (8%), Respiratory (8%), Cardiology (8%), Dermatology (4%). Twenty-three (92%) of respondents strongly agreed/agreed with the following, that the CTDVAS MDT: i) Improves diagnostic clarity, ii) Contributed effectively to management planning, iii) Provided education value, iv) Enhanced communication and collaboration within the rheumatology team and v) with other specialities and vi) supported professional development, knowledge and expertise in CTDVAS. Two neutral respondents. Twenty-four (96%) respondents strongly agreed/agreed that the MDT meant they can: i) Discuss urgent patients in timely way, ii) Discuss patients they are worried about, iii) Contribute to discussions about complex patients. 100% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed that the MDT supported starting definitive immunosuppressants (cyclophosphamide or rituximab) and 93% felt it supported novel therapies (e.g. avacopan). Twenty-one (84%) agreed the MDT is an enjoyable part of their week.

Conclusion: The BRI CTDVAS virtual weekly MDT is an effective platform to facilitating complex decision-making and collaboration, and initiation of definitive immunosuppression.

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Enhancing patient understanding and trust in AI healthcare tools: a fact sheet approach

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Background/Aims: The PARADISE project develops clinical decision support tools using longitudinal patient data to anticipate relapse events, with ANCA vasculitis as an exemplar autoimmune disease. As these tools rely on artificial intelligence (AI), it is essential that patients understand when AI is involved in their care, how reliable it is, and whether it has been safely developed and tested. To address this need, we designed a fact sheet to provide patients with key information about PARADISE AI system but aiming to be a more widely usable template.

Methods: Following an extensive review of publications from leading organisations and academic literature, patient consultation workshops with vasculitis patients from the PARADISE Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) group helped refine its focus. A survey, co-designed with PPI input and distributed to patients with vasculitis, identified the most relevant fact sheet elements. Consortium experts collaboratively drafted a clear and transparent explanation of the PARADISE algorithm, subject to further patient validation.

Results: The fact sheet is structured around nine key headings: health and care objective, description of the patient and health profiles of the data used for AI development and validation, quality and bias assessments of training data and applied corrections, the degree of autonomy of the AI-enabled software, jurisdictional approvals, evidence of effectiveness and safety, technical adoption guidance, clinical and patient usage guidance, and accountability. This framework provides a comprehensive overview designed to enhance patient trust and understanding of AI in healthcare.

Conclusions: The development of an AI Transparency Fact Sheet represents a milestone in promoting explainability and trust in AI healthcare solutions. By involving patients throughout the design process and integrating their feedback, the PARADISE project ensured the fact sheet is comprehensive and patient-centred. The resulting template offers a validated model that can be adopted by other initiatives developing AI systems in healthcare.

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A UK hospital-based clinical and research vasculitis nurse training course to promote the value of the specialist nurse role

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Background/Aims: The role of specialist nurses in supporting patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis and managing complex treatments is well recognised. Yet, structured opportunities for vasculitis nurse training and knowledge exchange across the United Kingdom are limited.

Methods: To address this unmet need, the Cambridge Vasculitis Training Centre was established in 2025. This centre aims to deliver a three-day practical clinical training programme for small groups of nurses, three times per year. Goals are to promote best practice in treatment, patient education and service delivery; strengthen theoretical knowledge of vasculitis; emphasise the nurse's role within a multiprofessional team; outline the contribution of research nurses to patient care, clinical trials and service development; and share practical strategies adaptable to local settings.

The nurse training programme combines clinical shadowing with interactive learning. Nurses observe ward rounds, outpatient clinics and infusion services, and review the operation of a nurse-led telephone advice line. Sessions with research nurses provide insight into clinical trials, integration of research into clinical practice and service innovation. A patient panel session ensures lived experience informs nursing practice.

Results: The first cohort attended in June 2025, with a second scheduled for October 2025. Feedback highlighted the balance of practical and classroom-based learning, the value of observing practices across different hospitals, and the potential to implement initiatives such as dedicated nurse telephone clinics and structured triage tools.

Conclusions: This national UK training programme addresses a clear gap in vasculitis nurse education, fosters collaboration, and strengthens professional networks. It is anticipated that the course will enhance patient care and reinforce the role of specialist nurses.

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Vasculitis Medical Preceptorship : An international, educational training programme empowering doctors to lead in vasculitis care and service provision

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Background/Aims: There is a recognised need to provide short-duration, high intensity, clinically focused training for doctors specialising in the diagnosis and management of vasculitis. To address this need, the Cambridge Vasculitis Training Centre, affiliated with the Vasculitis Service at Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Trust, designed an educational programme directed towards doctors approaching the end of their specialist training and newly qualified consultants. The programme was designed to focus on the multidisciplinary approach to care, the management of complex vasculitis cases, translational science, clinical research opportunities, and to provide insights into service delivery provision.

Methods: Over a six-month period, the faculty, through a series of meetings and discussions, designed a programme, combining participation in clinical service delivery and structured teaching. The programme incorporated opportunities to observe routine delivery of care including vasculitis wards rounds and outpatient clinics, supplemented by a carefully curated series of educational sessions delivered by specialists including clinicians and researchers from our hospital. The programme also incorporated participation in our regional and cross specialty multidisciplinary team (MDT) meetings as well as a research orientated day focusing on setting up an active research unit and collaborations with the University of Cambridge.

Results: A five-day training programme has been developed, with the first cohort of doctors enrolled and scheduled to complete the course in September 2025. As well as joining our ward rounds and clinics, the participants will spend a full day at one of the University of Cambridge colleges to engage in a series of small group teaching sessions and interactive case -based discussions with an expert panel.

Conclusions: The course will give attendees an in-depth understanding of vasculitis pathophysiology, the targets for treatment and the practical considerations required to establish and deliver a multidisciplinary vasculitis service.

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Comprehensive biospecimen repository for collaborative translational research in ANCA-associated vasculitis.

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Background: Translational research designed to better understand the pathogenesis of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), to elucidate and validate biomarkers of disease activity and treatment response, or to develop new treatment modalities requires timely access to biospecimens paired with comprehensive clinical data from diverse, well-characterized patient and control cohorts.

Methods: Approved by Mayo Clinic IRB, supported by funds from NorthStar Medical Radioisotopes and Mayo Foundation, the protocol was designed by the authors to create a biospecimen repository comprising longitudinal samples from 300 patients with AAV as well as age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HC) and disease controls (DC) in support of mechanistic studies. Specimens are processed immediately after sampling and stored at -80°C. Sample storage is organized using Labguru, a laboratory management software, matched with the clinical data. Specimens collected at each study visit include peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs, EDTA and ACD), DNA (PAXgene, first visit), RNA (PAXgene), cell-free DNA, plasma (EDTA and ACD), and serum.

Current Status: Over the course of the last 18 months, 164 of the target 300 patients with AAV, and 20 HC and >30 DC subjects have been enrolled. Of the AAV patients, 59% have PR3-AAV, 31% MPO-AAV, 10% ANCA-negative AAV. Diagnosis c/w ACR/EULAR 2022 classification categories were: 78% GPA, 13% MPA, 9% EGPA. Of the AAV patients, 22% have samples drawn at time of active disease, the remainder during remission after B-cell reconstitution. Work in progress: emphasis on recruitment of patients with active disease, MPO-AAV, MPA, EGPA and ANCA-positive ILD, age- and sex-matched HC and select DC.

Summary: The biospecimen repository is available in support of impactful collaborative translational research studies in ANCA-associated vasculitis. Inquiries should be directed to specks.ulrich@mayo.edu

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HLA associations in PR3-ANCA and MPO-ANCA vasculitis in an Irish population

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Background: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) comprises genetically and immunologically distinct subtypes, proteinase-3 (PR3)-ANCA and myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA. Genome-wide studies support the HLA locus as the dominant genetic risk region. We aimed to characterise the HLA genotypes of Irish patients with AAV.

Methods: We studied 458 AAV patients (251 PR3-AAV, 207 MPO-AAV) and 1,086 population controls (bone marrow registry donors). High-resolution (four-field) HLA genotyping was performed by next-generation sequencing. Allele, haplotype and amino-acid level associations were tested by logistic regression.

Results: PR3-AAV was strongly associated with HLA-DPB1*04:01 (OR 4.25, 95% CI 3.4–5.4; $p=7.51 \times 10^{-31}$). 96% of PR3-AAV patients carried ≥ 1 DPB1*04:01 allele and 56% were homozygous. Amino-acid analysis identified the DPB1 P1 peptide binding pocket motif GGPM (positions 84–87) as the principal signal (OR 12.8); only 0.8% (2/251) of PR3-AAV cases had an alternative P1 composition. The effect at DPB1 position 69 was independent of position 84. Protective signals included DPA1*02:01 and DPB1*03:01.

MPO-AAV was most strongly associated with HLA-DRB1*04:04 (OR 3.91, 95% CI 2.77–5.55; $p=1.03 \times 10^{-12}$). Previously identified associations at DQA1*03:01 and DQB1*03:02 were explained by correlation with DRB1*04:04. DPB1*03:01 was protective for MPO-AAV. At the position level, DRB1-33H (histidine) increased risk (OR 2.63) while 33N (asparagine) was protective (OR 0.41).

Conclusions: In a homogenous Irish cohort, PR3-AAV risk is overwhelmingly driven by DPB1*04:01 and a shared DPB1 P1 pocket motif (GGPM), implicating peptide-binding preferences in disease biology. MPO-AAV showed a distinct genetic profile DRB1*04:04, with a key effect at DRB1 position 33. High-resolution HLA sequencing and amino-acid level modelling can refine risk loci and suggest mechanistic hypotheses for antigen presentation in AAV.

Immunodeficiency, autoimmunity and ANCA-associated vasculitis/anti-GBM disease in the same family: a role for LRBA and AIRE

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Background/Aims: Genetic studies have identified several risk loci that contribute to susceptibility to ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). We report a family pedigree in which two members developed immune disorders and were found to carry variants in both LRBA and AIRE.

Methods: Both parents and the affected proband underwent whole-exome sequencing (WES). Flow cytometry analysis of T cells for phenotype and cytokine production were conducted.

Results: The proband, a 24-year-old Caucasian woman presented with severe MPO-AAV and anti-glomerular basement membrane disease requiring dialysis. The proband's mother had been diagnosed with CVID, autoimmune cytopenias and hypogammaglobulinaemia, and later developed granulomatous lymphocytic interstitial lung disease. The proband was treated with plasma exchange, glucocorticoids and rituximab, achieving a good clinical response (eGFR 50mL/min/1.73m² and no hypogammaglobulinaemia at 9 years), despite an MPO-AAV relapse two years after initial presentation (treated with re-induction, then maintenance rituximab). WES identified heterozygous variants in the LRBA gene (p.Arg1445*, a nonsense pathogenic variant likely affecting CTLA-4 function), and in the AIRE gene (p.Val301Met, a missense variant of unknown significance in a dominant negative hotspot region). Flow cytometry revealed, in the untreated proband's mother, low numbers and proportions of regulatory T cells (CD4+CD25+CD127^{low}) and high proportions of CD4+CD45RO+CXCR3+ cells, with most cells producing TNF and IFN-gamma. These populations were not abnormal in the proband, potentially due to 5 years of rituximab therapy.

Conclusion: Mutations in LRBA and AIRE contribute to autoimmunity, lymphoproliferation, and immunodeficiency. Our report expands the phenotypic spectrum by demonstrating that heterozygous variants in both genes may predispose to early-onset AAV in a digenic manner. Despite carrying identical mutations, the proband and her mother exhibited different immune phenotypes, underscoring the influence of genetic, epigenetic, and environmental modifiers. Dissecting the molecular pathways linking genetically-mediated immune dysfunction to AAV may inform precision approaches to therapy.

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Structures of proteinase 3 and the CD177 receptor complex reveals major autoantibody epitopes

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a life-threatening systemic vasculitis, characterised by anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibodies (ANCA) against proteinase 3 (PR3), a protease expressed intracellularly and on the surface of neutrophils. Most cell surface PR3 is bound to the receptor CD177, however the molecular mechanism of the interactions is not well understood. Previous studies have suggested that the hydrophobic patch on PR3 is involved in binding with CD177. We aimed to solve the structure of the PR3-CD177 complex, and CD177 alone, and determine whether the PR3-CD177 binding site is an important epitope for PR3-ANCA binding.

Methods: X-ray crystallography was used to solve the structure of PR3-CD177 complex and of an unliganded CD177 construct containing all four LU domains. The study was possible using a site-directed mutagenesis screen to identify stable PR3 variants that are readily expressed and purified from HEK293 cultures. We employed a panel of eight PR3-ANCA positive GPA patient plasma samples to test ANCA binding to our recombinant PR3 variants using ELISAs.

Results: Crystal structures revealed that the binding interface between PR3 and CD177 is mainly hydrophobic and involves the first two LU domains of CD177. The structure of unliganded CD177 shows that it is composed of two subdomains, each containing two tightly packed LU domains, that are connected by a flexible linker. Our standardised PR3-ANCA ELISAs show that for most GPA plasma samples, there is reduced ANCA binding when a recombinant PR3 variant that has the CD177-binding site masked was used.

Conclusions: The previously identified hydrophobic patch of PR3 is significantly involved in the binding interface between PR3 and CD177, and this site is a major autoantibody epitope that is targeted in most GPA patients examined in this study.

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Circulating peripheral helper T cells are expanded and associate with disease activity in granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Peripheral helper T (Tph) cells, a recently identified Th cell subset, have been implicated in various autoimmune diseases. However, their role in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) remains unclear. This study aimed to investigate the potential clinical significance of circulating Tph cells (cTph) in GPA.

Methods: Peripheral blood mononuclear cells were collected from 74 remission GPA-patients (rGPA), 26 active GPA-patients (aGPA) and 22 age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HCs). Flow cytometry was used to quantify cTph cells and their subset distribution. Single-cell multi-omics profiling was performed in an independent cohort (5 rGPA-patients, 5 aGPA-patients and 5 HCs). Plasma IL-21 levels were measured by ELISA, and associations between cTph cells and clinical parameters were evaluated.

Results: aGPA-patients showed an increased frequency and absolute number of cTph compared to rGPA-patients, and both GPA groups exhibited cTph2-skewed distribution compared to HCs. rGPA-patients with generalized disease exhibited higher cTph frequencies than those with localized disease. cTph cells from aGPA-patients displayed an activated phenotype and a transcriptional profile marked by pro-inflammatory and survival-associated genes. Plasma IL-21 levels did not differ significantly between the three groups. Notably, absolute counts of memory cTph and cTph2 cells correlated positively with clinical markers of disease activity, and were significantly elevated in GPA patients with higher c-ANCA titers.

Conclusions: cTph cells are expanded and exhibit an activated, pro-inflammatory profile with a cTph2-skewed distribution in aGPA-patients. Their association with disease activity supports a potential role in disease pathogenesis and highlights their potential as therapeutic targets, warranting further investigation.

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CCL5-producing GZMB⁺ cytotoxic lymphocyte mediate renal injury in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)–associated vasculitis (AAV) is a severe autoimmune disease characterized by necrotizing inflammation of small vessels and progressive renal injury. In this study, we aim to define the interplay between cytotoxic effector functions and the trafficking chemokine axis in both blood and kidney tissue from patients with AAV.

Methods: Single-cell RNA sequencing data from untreated AAV patients (n=8) and age-matched healthy controls (HC, n=5) were reanalysed from publicly available datasets. In parallel, Visium spatial transcriptomics data (GSE250138) from kidney biopsies of AAV patients (n=19) and histologically normal kidney regions (n=3) were analysed to map infiltrating immune populations.

Results: Analysis of PBMCs from patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) revealed a marked expansion of cytotoxic lymphocyte subsets compared with healthy controls (HC), including both CD8⁺ T cells and NK cells. CD8⁺ T cells from AAV patients showed robust upregulation of cytotoxic effector genes such as GZMB, PRF1, CCL5, NKG7, and GNLY, with reduced expression of GZMK. NK cells demonstrated a similar activation profile, with increased expression of GZMB, GZMH, and PRF1, consistent with an activated cytotoxic state.

Spatial transcriptomic profiling of kidney biopsies from AAV patients confirmed a striking accumulation of cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cells within inflamed glomerular and interstitial regions. These infiltrating cells expressed high levels of GZMB and CCL5 and were enriched for pathways related to cell killing, T cell activation, and regulation of neutrophil degranulation.

Conclusions: CCL5⁺GZMB⁺ effector CD8⁺ T cells emerge as a disease-associated population in ANCA vasculitis, coupling direct tissue cytotoxicity with the recruitment and amplification of local inflammation. These findings identify cytotoxic lymphocytes as key mediators of renal injury and suggest that therapeutic strategies targeting CD8 effector programs may provide novel avenues for intervention in ANCA-associated disease.

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Transcriptomic deconvolution to dissect the immunological mechanism of B cell depletion therapy in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Rituximab is an established B-cell–depleting remission induction and maintenance therapy in ANCA-associated vasculitis(AAV). The RITAZAREM trial showed repeat-dose rituximab reduces relapse risk compared with azathioprine, but relapses still occur with rituximab and became more frequent after treatment withdrawal.

This post-hoc genomic analysis of the RITAZAREM trial aims to use machine learning methods to identify gene expression trajectories and immune cell populations associated with key study endpoints. Interpretation of associated genes and cell types are used to inform our understanding of, and to predict, disease progression and treatment response.

Methods: Bulk RNA sequencing data from peripheral blood was analysed at major trial timepoints (baseline, month 4 (randomization), month 24 (final rituximab dose) and month 36 (off immunosuppression)). Transcriptomic deconvolution (MuSIC, SCDC, CIBERSORT) was undertaken to infer serial changes in peripheral immune cell frequencies. In parallel, matrix factorization was used to construct a low-dimensional representation of the data as latent trajectories, both at each timepoint (MOFA+) and longitudinally across all timepoints (MEFISTO). Once learned, per-sample factor weights were correlated to clinical covariates including all primary and secondary trial outcomes. Interpretation of outcome-associated trajectories was undertaken through systematic feature set enrichment against all feature weights to identify cell types and pathways associated with clinical outcomes.

Results: Bulk RNA sequencing data was analysed for 90% of trial participants (n=169; baseline n=162; month 4 n=143; month 24 n=117; month 36 n=111), including 80 maintained on rituximab, 73 on azathioprine, and 16 non-randomised. Latent patterns of gene expression describing >99% of variance in the source dataset were systematically correlated with clinical trial endpoints.

Conclusions: This study will generate high-resolution maps of immune reconstitution after treatment of AAV with rituximab, identifying latent patterns of gene expression and cell types associated with relapse and infection, and has the potential to support biomarker-driven personalised therapy in AAV.

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Characterization of B and T cell subsets at single-cell resolution in ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a small-vessel autoimmune vasculitis often accompanied by glomerulonephritis and impaired kidney function. While B and T cells are crucially important in AAV pathogenesis, most evidence relies on studies on peripheral blood, warranting thorough characterization of their subsets and interactions within target tissues.

Methods: We obtained core-needle kidney biopsies from five AAV patients with glomerulonephritis (AGN), one lupus nephritis (LN) and one nephrectomy control (NC), and isolated and processed live CD45+ immune cells for single-cell transcriptomic analysis. Subsequently, we performed B and T cell re-clustering, differential gene/protein expression, gene set enrichment and communication mapping using CellChat.

Results: 24 clusters and re-clustered B cell- and CD4+/CD8+ T cell-enriched subsets were identified. B cell subpopulations included follicular (CXCR5; NF-κB signature), atypical memory (CD11c; antigen-presentation), atypical/cytotoxic (HOPX, PRF1) and plasma (SDC1) cells, with the latter two enriched in AGN. Among 11 CD4+ T cell clusters, we identified Th1 (TBX21, IFNG) and Th17 (RORC, IL17A) cells—both increased in AGN compared to NC, with upregulated NF-κB signalling—two regulatory subsets (FOXP3; IL-2/STAT5 signalling), and follicular T helper cells (CXCL13), described for the first time in AGN. CD8+ T cell populations included inflammatory Tc1 (IFNG, TNF) and Tc17 (RORC, IL23R) cells, enriched in AGN compared to NC, and 3 CD45RA-expressing effector memory (Temra) populations. CellChat analysis revealed distinct B-T cell communication networks driving inflammation and regulation in AGN.

Conclusions: Profiling of B and T cells in AGN and NC kidney biopsies at single-cell resolution identified potentially pathogenic subsets and their signalling/communication patterns, offering novel targets for more directed therapies.

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The immunophenotype of autoantigen specific B cells in MPO-ANCA vasculitis patients with active disease and long-term remission off therapy (LTROT)

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Background/Aims: Autoantigen specific cells are a small but key subset of lymphocytes in Antineutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody (ANCA) vasculitis. ANCA-vasculitis patients are treated with predominantly B-cell depleting therapies, inviting risk of hypogammaglobulinemia, infections, and malignancy. We hypothesized that MPO-specific B-cells are immunophenotypically distinct in active disease and long-term remission off therapy (LTROT). Immunophenotyping target cell populations is the first step to designing directed therapies rather than broad immunosuppression.

Methods: Validated fluorescent MPO-tetramers and control tetramers (to exclude binding to non-MPO components) were utilized. Thawed cryopreserved peripheral blood mononuclear cells were incubated with tetramers and enriched for fluorophore-binding cells prior to flow-cytometry sorting for MPO-tetramer positive (Tpos) B-cells. Control populations included MPO-tetramer negative cells (Tneg) and isolated B-cells from residual fluorophore-negative cells (Aneg) followed by RNA isolation for library preparation and single cell sequencing.

Results: Tpos cells from patients produced MPO-ANCAs invitro, validating successful isolation of MPO-ANCA B-cells. The following samples were sorted: 3 active MPO-ANCA patients, 3 LTROT (two were paired) patients and 3 healthy individuals. All patients had positive MPO-ANCA titres clinically and we identified 5.15% MPO-ANCA specific B-cells (within CD19+ population), comparable to prior flowcytometry assays. Active patients' MPO-ANCA B-cells had higher proportion of plasma cells (60.3%) compared to LTROT (2.3% plasma-cells) and healthy individuals (2.9% plasma-cells). The LTROT Tpos population was remarkable for fewer memory B-cells (3.45%) compared to the active Tpos (16.5%) or healthy Tpos (36.2%). We found lower BCR diversity in the Tpos group (Chao1 diversity index) compared to Aneg.

Conclusions: This is the first study to compare the immunophenotype MPO-ANCA specific B-cells in active disease to LTROT using single cells sequencing. MPO-ANCA B-cells in active disease are predominantly plasma-cells. In LTROT, there are very few MPO-ANCA specific memory cells, suggesting an underlying immunological mechanism. The BCR analysis lays the foundation to identify disease specific clonotypes.

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B cells in Takayasu's arteritis show upregulation of genes involved in RNA alternative splicing, protein synthesis, and cell proliferation compared to healthy individuals

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Background/Aims: Aortic specimens from patients with large vessel vasculitis (LVV) have shown prominent B cells organizing into arterial tertiary lymphoid organ structures with germinal centres. The mechanisms that drive autoreactive B cell expansion or differentiation into effector populations in LVV have not been identified. We therefore sought to identify gene expression changes in LVV B cells (relative to healthy controls) to find more selective targets to support the development of new therapy candidates.

Methods: CD19+ cells were flow cytometry purified from patients with Takayasu arteritis (TAK) (n=7), giant cell arteritis (GCA) (n=1), or healthy controls (n=4) and single-cell RNA-seq/BCR-seq profiling was performed using the 10X Genomics platform. Pathway analysis was performed using g:Profiler.

Results: Seurat identified n=12 transcriptionally defined clusters, with no major differences in cluster distribution noted between TAK or HC individuals. Memory B cells from TAK patients showed n=192 upregulated genes relative to healthy donors (FC > 1.5, padj < 0.05), with transitional (n=21 genes), naïve (n=119 genes), and activated (n=19 genes) B cell subsets also showing upregulated genes in TAK patients. In Memory B cells, upregulated genes were involved in RNA alternative splicing (RBFOX2), mitochondrial function and metabolism (MT-ND3 and MT-ATP8), protein synthesis (RPS18 and RPL3), T cell co-stimulation (CD86), actin cytoskeleton rearrangement (TAGLN2 and ACTG1), and cell proliferation (DHFR and GAREM1). Pathway analysis on memory B cells additionally identified upregulation of B cell receptor signaling (THEMIS2 and GCSAM).

Conclusions: TAK patient B cells exhibit a distinct transcriptional program that might support interactions with autoreactive T cells and contribute to autoimmune disease liability. Upregulation of DHFR reinforces the rationale for methotrexate treatment. Future studies will be required to evaluate the functional consequences of these changes with respect to tissue damage in vasculitis.

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Identification of Anti-Peroxidasin Antibodies in Experimental Glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims

Peroxidasin (Pxdn) is an extracellular matrix (ECM) haem peroxidase. In the glomerular basement membrane (GBM) Pxdn catalyses the formation of sulfilimine bonds within type IV collagen. These bonds contribute to the structural integrity and stability of the ECM and grant immune privilege to the Goodpasture antigen. Autoantibodies to peroxidasin have been previously identified in patients with anti-GBM disease and myeloperoxidase anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (MPO-ANCA)-associated vasculitis (MPO-AAV).

Methods: Circulating anti-Pxdn IgG was identified using ELISA and confirmed using immunoblot. Kidney tissue expression of Pxdn was assessed using indirect immunofluorescence.

Results: Circulating anti-Pxdn IgG antibodies were detected in patients with anti-GBM disease and with active MPO-AAV, but not in patients with PR3-AAV. In rats with experimental GN, circulating anti-Pxdn IgG antibodies were detected in 85.7% of EAV rats by day 28 after immunisation. Anti-Pxdn titres correlated with disease severity as measured by proteinuria and proportion of glomerular crescents. There was no correlation between anti-MPO titres and anti-Pxdn titres, and rats which had been treated with an inhibitor preventing glomerulonephritis but with no effect on anti-MPO levels did not have detectable anti-Pxdn IgG. Direct IF of kidney tissue did not identify deposited IgG along the GBM. Indirect IF identified Pxdn expression in areas of segmental necrosis and glomerular injury. In EAG, anti-Pxdn IgG was detected in 86.7% of rats, with higher titres than in EAV, in keeping with a higher degree of glomerular injury.

Conclusions: In experimental GN, anti-Pxdn antibodies and glomerular Pxdn expression develop after the onset of glomerular injury and correlate with disease severity. In EAV, we could not identify anti-Pxdn IgG deposited along the GBM. As such, we suggest that in experimental GN anti-Pxdn antibodies may arise by a process of inter-molecular epitope spreading in the diseased glomerulus.

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Autoantigens on endothelial cells and expression profiles of endothelial proteins identified in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis without antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies

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Background/Aims: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a type of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, however, more than 50% of EGPA patients are ANCA-negative. Anti-endothelial cell antibodies (AECA) are abundant in multiple forms of vasculitis or vasculopathy. We aimed to identify target autoantigens for AECA in ANCA-negative EGPA, and then to identify expression profiles of endothelial proteins in ANCA-negative EGPA.

Methods: We screened ANCA-negative EGPA sera for the presence of AECA by western blotting and 2D gel electrophoresis (2DE) using proteins extracted from human lung microvascular endothelial cells from asthma patients (HLMVEC-AS). We performed mass spectrometry to identify candidate autoantigens from 2DE gels. Next, we analysed the proteins extracted from HLMVEC-AS treated with ANCA-negative EGPA sera using proteomics.

Results: Of the 582 proteins identified as candidate autoantigens for AECA, 66% were cytoplasmic proteins, 18% were nuclear proteins, 9% were cell membrane proteins, and 4% were extracellular proteins. Pathway analysis revealed that the identified proteins were mainly related to neutrophil degranulation. Next, proteomic analyses showed significantly different expression levels for 615 proteins in ANCA-negative EGPA and for 1038 proteins in healthy donors. 4775 proteins were similar in both. All of the 68 plasma membrane proteins were highly expressed only in ANCA-negative EGPA and were mainly associated with VEGFA/VEGFR2 signalling pathway that has been reported to be involved in asthma pathophysiology. Heat shock cognate 71 kDa protein (HSC70) with significantly higher expression levels in ANCA-negative EGPA was also a candidate autoantigen for AECA. Using ELISA, anti-HSC70 autoantibodies were detected in 30% of EGPA patients (n=10), but in none of healthy donors (n=7) and of ANCA-positive EGPA.

Conclusions: ANCA-negative EGPA patients express antibodies to autoantigens in endothelial cells. Further analyses of autoantigens for AECA and/or endothelial protein expression profiles can potentially lead to develop novel therapeutic molecules and biomarkers targeting endothelial cells.

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Clinical significance of serum anti-moesin antibody level in kidney diseases

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Background/Aims: Our previous study reported that anti-moesin antibody (aMAb) was a kind of MPO-ANCA binding to moesin, a component of endothelial cytoskeleton (Suzuki et al, NDT, 2014). Moreover, aMAb was shown to bind glomerular endothelial cell to introduce production of inflammatory cytokines and neutrophil infiltration. This study was to correlate aMAb level with clinical parameters in various kidney diseases.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, first-visit patients to the nephrology clinic were enrolled. They were diagnosed as ANCA-associate vasculitis (AAV), IgA nephropathy (IgAN), diabetic kidney disease (DKD), hypertensive nephrosclerosis (HN), membranous nephropathy (MN), lupus nephritis (LN), minimal change (MC), anti-GBM disease (aGBM), and IgA vasculitis (IgAV). Patients were divided into glomerulonephritis (GN) group (AAV, IgAN, MN, aGBM, LN and IgAV) and non-GN group (DKD, HN and MC). Patients were assessed for serum aMAb level, white blood cell count, CRP, eGFR, proteinuria, MPO-ANCA, complement components (C3 and C4), and 50% haemolytic complement activity (CH50). These were measured with the same specimen. Association between aMAb level and other parameters was examined.

Results: One-hundred and eight patients were included: 14 AAV, 42 IgAN, 22 DKD, 9 HN, 9 MN, 4 LN, 3 MC, 3 aGBM, and 2 IgAV. Patients in groups GN and non-GN were 74 and 34 respectively. In AAV group, aMAb positively correlated to CRP level ($R^2=0.333$) but negatively correlated to CH50 ($R^2=0.629$). In DKD group, aMAb negatively correlated to CH50 ($R^2=0.917$). Conversely, aMAb positively correlated to CH50 in IgAN group ($R^2=0.275$). Negative correlation of aMAb with CH50 was found in non-GN group ($R^2=0.445$) but not in GN group.

Conclusions: aMAb level negatively correlated to CH50 in AAV, DKD, and non-GN groups. The common point of these groups is severe damage of the small vessels. aMAb is suggested to cause endothelial injury via aberrant activation of the complement system.

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Latent murine cytomegalovirus infection drives effector T cell accumulation in the kidney and enhances experimental anti-myeloperoxidase autoimmunity and crescentic glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: Latent cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection is associated with worse clinical outcomes in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (AAV). Although CMV is renotropic, CMV's role in native kidney disease has not been assessed. These studies aimed to define the role of latent CMV infection in experimental anti-myeloperoxidase (MPO) glomerulonephritis and in crescentic glomerulonephritis.

Methods: C57BL/6J mice were infected with murine (M)CMV, which was latent by day 49 post-infection. Renal leukocyte populations were characterised in latency by immunohistochemistry, flow cytometry using fluorescinated anti-CD45 antibodies to distinguish intravascular (IV+) from tissue (IV-) leukocytes, and multiphoton microscopy. Commencing at day 49 post-infection, experimental anti-MPO glomerulonephritis, and nephrotoxic serum nephritis (NTN, days 21 and 35) were studied.

Results: CMV replication was detected in kidneys at day 5 post-infection, but was absent by day 10. During latency, MCMV infection increased IV+ and IV- intrarenal leukocytes, with a more than 6-fold increase in CD8+ T cells, displaying an effector-memory, pro-inflammatory phenotype. Intrarenal MCMV-specific CD8+ T cells were prominent (20.0±1.6% IV+, 14.9±0.8% IV-CD8+ cells, tetramer staining). In vivo multiphoton microscopy demonstrated that CMV induced more intravascular glomerular T cells and CX3CR1+CD8+ T cells within interstitial capillaries. In experimental anti-MPO glomerulonephritis (day 4), latency increased intrarenal CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, and macrophages. Intrarenal T cells in nephritic MCMV-infected mice exhibited heightened TNF/IFN γ production. MCMV-infected mice with anti-MPO glomerulonephritis developed increased proteinuria, but similar histological injury. In the more prolonged NTN model, a proxy for AAV, latent infection aggravated crescent formation (4.4±1.3 vs 12.4±2.8% day 21, 4.4±2.0 vs 14.6±3.7% day 35, p<0.03) with more CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, and CD11b+Ly6Chi monocytes. Chemotactic signals associated with their recruitment were upregulated.

Conclusions: Latent MCMV infection causes persistent pro-inflammatory intrarenal leukocyte accumulation in normal and diseased kidneys resulting in severity of anti-MPO autoimmune and crescentic glomerulonephritis. CMV may aggravate human crescentic glomerulonephritis.

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Cytomegalovirus driven immunomodulation amplifies kidney damage in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background: We have previously shown that cytomegalovirus (CMV) reactivates asymptotically in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in remission, and that CMV-specific CD4+CD28null T-cells associate with poor outcomes. We hypothesized that asymptomatic CMV reactivation may amplify kidney damage in active AAV.

Methods: Observational study of 50 CMV-seropositive and 20 CMV-seronegative patients with active AAV. We performed serial CMV PCR on blood and urine, phenotyped peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) via flow cytometry, and measured urinary soluble (us)MCP-1. Multiplex immunofluorescence was performed on kidney tissue.

Results: Asymptomatic CMV reactivation occurred in 52% of seropositive patients, with 96% occurring in the first three months. Reactivation was three times more common in patients with renal involvement (47% vs. 14%; $p=0.014$), and patients without reactivation had better eGFR recovery at 12 months (3.5ml/min difference; $p<0.001$).

We identified CD4+CD28null T-cells as a pro-inflammatory, cytotoxic, endothelial-homing subset. Their percentage correlated with lower eGFR at 12 months ($r=-0.3440$, $p=0.026$), and their numbers increased 1.7-fold following reactivation. CMV lysate stimulation of PBMC led to a CD4-dependent increase in glomerular cell death in seropositive patients in vitro ($p=0.017$), which directly correlated with percentage of CD4+CD28null T-cells in culture. In kidney tissue, CD4+CD28null T-cell infiltration strongly correlated with lower eGFR ($p=0.007$).

Additionally, a lower percentage of classical monocytes at baseline correlated with lower eGFR ($p<0.001$) and increased usMCP-1, suggesting their migration into the kidney. The percentage of CD4+CD28null T-cells was inversely related to that of classical monocytes in peripheral blood ($p=0.031$) and CMV lysate stimulation led to increased translocation of MPO on monocytes.

Conclusions: Asymptomatic CMV reactivation is associated with reduced renal recovery in AAV. Our findings suggest that CMV reactivation may amplify kidney damage by promoting the expansion of cytotoxic CD4+CD28null T-cells and by priming monocytes for ANCA-driven inflammation, highlighting a novel and potentially reversible mechanism of injury in AAV.

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The B-Cell activating factor pathway in the neutrophil - B cell axis of ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is an auto-immune disease characterized by inflammation of the small- to medium-sized blood vessels, in which B-cells and neutrophils play a central role. We propose a model which describes the crosstalk between these cells, focusing on B-cell activating factor (BAFF) and the relation to the maintenance and reinforcement of the inflammatory process. B-cells produce ANCAs, activating neutrophils that undergo NETosis, and BAFF, important for activation, proliferation, and differentiation of B-cells.

Methods: Available data from patients included in the PROMAVAS cohort were used to find support for the suggested model. BAFF levels were analysed and correlated with peripheral B-cell and neutrophil counts, ANCA levels, and expression of the BAFF-receptor (BR3) and Bruton's tyrosine kinase (BTK) by B-cells.

Results: 65 patients with MPO- or PR3-AAV (47% and 53%) with a major disease presentation requiring remission-induction therapy were included in the study. There were significant negative associations between BAFF levels and B-cell counts and BAFF levels and BR3 expression ($P=0.011$ and $P<0.001$). No significant relationships were found between BAFF levels and neutrophil counts or ANCA levels. In addition, BAFF levels were not related to an activated phenotype of the B-cells, as illustrated by BTK expression.

Conclusions: Results imply BAFF levels increase during active disease, probably due to B-cell migration to the site of inflammation and repopulation in the peripheral blood. Furthermore, B-cell activation seems to be controlled by downregulating BAFF-receptor expression on B-cells. Our data support a complex interplay between B-cells and neutrophils, but more research is needed to find contributing factors for the propagation of the inflammatory response as possible targets for future therapies.

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Thrombin cleaves annexin A1: A novel link of blood coagulation with innate immunity

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Background/Aims: Blood coagulation cross talks with the innate immune system during immunothrombosis. Neutrophils, fundamental players of innate immunity, are recruited to inflamed vascular sites where they amplify thrombin generation. Thrombin, in turn, can augment neutrophil recruitment. Previously, we have demonstrated the intricate link between neutrophil activation (neutrophil extracellular trap formation) and activation of the intrinsic blood coagulation pathway in hypercoagulability and increased thrombotic risk of patients with active ANCA-associated vasculitis. Annexin A1, a member of the annexin supergene family, is an anti-inflammatory and proresolving protein that inhibits neutrophil recruitment and function by activating formyl peptide receptors (FPRs) on the neutrophil surface with its N-terminal domain of 26 amino acids. In this presentation we report a novel link between blood coagulation and innate immunity by demonstrating that thrombin inactivates the anti-inflammatory Annexin A1 by cleaving off the FPR-interacting N-terminal domain.

Results: Fragmentation of circulating Annexin A1 was observed in plasmas of patients participating in the PROspective MAastricht Vasculitis Study, presenting with active ANCA-associated vasculitis. We observed a positive correlation between Annexin A1 fragmentation and D-dimer levels in these patients.

Conclusions: We hypothesize that thrombin cleavage of Annexin A1 contributes to pathogenesis of immunothrombosis in diseases with hyperinflammation such as ANCA-associated vasculitis.

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Activation of the alternative complement pathway and intrinsic coagulation cascade in active ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: The complement and coagulation cascades share a common evolutionary origin and are involved in host defence. Both cascades have been linked to the pathogenesis of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), indicating targets for treatment. Here, we studied both cascades and their clinical correlates.

Methods: Treatment-naïve patients with active AAV and major organ involvement were prospectively included. Activation markers of complement and coagulation were measured at presentation and quiescent disease after 6 months. Activation markers of complement were quantified using a multiplex assay (QuidelOrtho, MicroVue, San Diego, CA); coagulation factors were measured in complex with their natural inhibitors using in-house ELISAs.

Results: 37 patients (median age 63 years, IQR, 55–72) were included, of whom 32 (86%) presented with de novo AAV and 24 (65%) had ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis. Treatment was based on cyclophosphamide and/or rituximab in all. At presentation, C4d (8.1%), Ba (73%), Bb (35%), C3a (8.1%), C5a (19%), and sC5b9 (49%) were elevated, indicating predominant activation via the alternative pathway. Patients invariably presented with activation of the intrinsic pathway of coagulation, with elevated FXIIa:C1INH and FXIa:antithrombin (AT) in 100% and 70%, while the extrinsic pathway was activated in only 12% (i.e., FVIIa:AT). The common pathway of coagulation was activated in 27% (thrombin:AT [T:AT]). FXIa:AT ($\rho=0.41$, $P=0.020$) and T:AT ($\rho=0.40$, $P=0.020$) correlated with C3a, indicating an interaction between both cascades. At 6 months, activation markers of complement and T:AT, but not FXIIa:C1INH and FXIa:AT, significantly decreased. None of the markers were associated with risk of relapse, end-stage kidney disease and/or mortality.

Conclusion: The alternative pathway of the complement system and the intrinsic pathway of the coagulation cascade are involved in AAV and their activation markers, although not associated with clinical outcomes, correlate with disease activity. Future studies are needed to validate our findings and indicate new targets for treatment.

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Identification of C3 complement fragments in lesional tissues in anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: One proposed mechanism of tissue damage in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is the formation of neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) during extravasation of neutrophils into vessel walls. AAV is typically described as pauci-immune, with renal and other tissues reported as C3-negative. However, NETs can carry alternative pathway complement protein split products. This study aimed to use novel techniques to characterize complement activation and extended half-life product C3d in affected tissue in AAV.

Methods: Biopsies from patients with AAV (kidney, lung, sinus, skin), IgA nephropathy (IgAN, kidney), C3 glomerulonephritis (C3G, kidney), lupus nephritis (LN, kidney); and cutaneous leukocytoclastic vasculitis (LCV, skin) were stained using a novel anti-C3d monoclonal antibody (3d8b), and, in some instances, an anti-C3c polyclonal antibody (Dako).

Results: Active complement (anti-C3c) and C3d deposition (anti-C3d) were detected in the glomeruli of AAV, IgAN, C3G, and LN. Both semi-quantitative scoring and digital quantification revealed a moderate glomerular staining intensity in AAV and IgAN, and a higher intensity in C3G and LN. A distinct glomerular staining pattern with C3c/C3d was seen in AAV and IgAN with deposition more in mesangium than capillaries, as compared to C3G and LN in which C3c/C3d deposited equally in mesangium and capillaries. C3d deposition was also detected in extra-glomerular small vessels; 3/6 biopsies that tested negative for C3 by routine diagnostic immunostaining were positive for C3d. Active complement and C3d deposition were also detected in superficial dermal vasculature in LCV as well as in lung and sinus tissue in AAV.

Conclusions: Immunostaining for complement fragments, particularly C3d, reveals evidence of complement activation in multiple tissues in AAV, including biopsies deemed negative by routine C3 staining. These data indicate that glomerulonephritis in AAV is less "pauci-immune" than previously considered and suggest that an inhibitor of the alternative pathway anchored to C3d could mitigate inflammation-related damage in AAV.

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Circulating cell-free DNA in ANCA-associated vasculitis during active disease and remission: Potential markers for disease monitoring?

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Background/Aims: To avoid relapse patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are treated with immunotherapy. Disease monitoring is, due to lack of reliable biomarkers, complicated. Neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), containing mitochondrial (mtDNA) and nuclear DNA (nDNA), are thought to be a driving factor in early endothelial inflammation. The aim of this study was to explore whether levels of cell-free DNA (cfDNA) differ during active disease and remission and in healthy controls (HC).

Methods: Paired samples from 9 patients (4 female) with AAV, ages 23-84 (median=68), of which 6 had a GPA-diagnosis, were obtained during active disease and clinical remission as part of an ongoing observational prospective study. After DNA-extraction digital droplet PCR was performed to obtain levels of mtDNA and nDNA. To measure neutrophil elastase (NE) an ELISA was performed. Furthermore, samples from 28 HC (17 female), ages 28-85 (median=59), were analysed.

Results: Patients with AAV had significantly higher levels of both mtDNA and nDNA during active disease compared to HC; mtDNA (median 7110 and 1245.5 copies/ μ L respectively, $p < 0.0001$) and nDNA (median 3.5 and 1 copies/ μ L respectively, $p = 0.0001$), whereas during remission mtDNA but not nDNA was increased compared with HC; mtDNA (median 6400 and 1245.5 copies/ μ L respectively, $p < 0.0001$) and nDNA (median 0.96 and 1 copies/ μ L respectively, $p = 0.7341$). Patients with active disease showed significantly higher levels of mtDNA but not nDNA compared to remission; mtDNA (median=7110 and 6400 copies/ μ L respectively, $p = 0.0273$) and nDNA (median=3.5 and 0.96 respectively, $p = 0.0742$).

Further, levels of NE correlated with levels of nDNA, but not mtDNA, suggesting neutrophils are an important source of this DNA ($r(37) = 0.468$, $p = 0.003$).

Conclusions: This study supports the notion of dysregulated release/clearance of NETs, and potentially cfDNA from other sources, during active AAV. To further explore the potential use of NETs and cfDNA in disease monitoring, our local cohort will be expanded to include samples from other AAV-cohorts.

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T- and B-cell extracellular DNA release in ANCA-associated vasculitis and MPO autoimmunity: modulation by the mitochondria-targeted antioxidant SKQ1

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Background/Aims: Extracellular DNA (exDNA) contributes to autoimmune pathogenesis, traditionally attributed to neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs). Emerging evidence suggests adaptive immune cells also release exDNA. This study investigated T-cell exDNA release in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) compared with healthy controls (HC). In parallel we evaluated these mechanisms in a mouse model of myeloperoxidase (MPO) autoimmunity to examine if mitochondria-targeted antioxidant SKQ1, could reduce lymphocyte DNA release and autoimmunity to MPO.

Methods: T-cells were isolated from four AAV patients (one with active disease) and four HC and activated via CD3/CD28 in the presence or absence of SKQ1. exDNA release was assessed by live-cell fluorescence microscopy. Cytokines were quantified in culture supernatants. In parallel, MPO autoimmunity was induced in mice using MPO in complete Freund's adjuvant. Mice (n=10/group) were treated daily with SKQ1 or vehicle, and splenocytes were restimulated ex vivo with MPO. Confocal microscopy was used to assess exDNA release by CD4⁺ T-cells and CD19⁺ B-cells; MPO-ANCA levels and lymphocyte subsets were measured.

Results: Human T-cells released exDNA upon activation, with higher release in AAV patients versus HC (median %area 393×10^{-6} vs 61×10^{-6} , $p=0.0286$), most pronounced in active disease. Co-staining indicated mitochondrial origin and ROS involvement. SKQ1 reduced exDNA release in all patient samples and decreased IFN- γ , IL-17, and IL-10 production (all $p<0.02$). In mice, both CD4⁺ T and B-cells released DNA upon MPO restimulation, significantly reduced by SKQ1 ($p<0.02$). SKQ1-treated mice also showed lower MPO-ANCA titres, fewer central memory T-cells, and reduced CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ populations.

Conclusion: Both human and murine data demonstrate that MPO autoimmunity induces exDNA release in adaptive immune cells, potentially contributing to autoimmune pathology in AAV. SKQ1 which targets excess mitochondrial ROS effectively suppresses exDNA release, cytokine production, and autoantibody responses. These findings highlight mitochondrial ROS scavenging as a potential therapeutic strategy in vasculitis.

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A potential biomarker for nervous system irritation in giant cell arteritis - from inside extracellular vesicles

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is the most common vasculitis above the age of 50 years. Patients are at risk of losing sight or suffering from ischemic cerebral accidents. Identifying patients at risk of these severe complications and intensifying treatment if needed remains a big challenge and currently there are only small risk factors identified like suffering from jaw claudication. Extracellular vesicles (EVs) emerge as promising novel biomarkers because their content reflect the cell of origin and disease status of patients.

Methods: EVs were isolated from platelet-free-plasma of 4 GCA patients and 12 age and gender matched HCs using size exclusion chromatography. EVs were characterized by nanoparticle tracking analysis, microBCA, CryoEM, and imaging flow cytometry (IFCM). Mass spectrometry (MS) was used to identify and quantify pEV proteins from each donor.

Results: Rabphilin-3A (RPH3A) was solely found in the EVs from the 4 GCA patients and in none of the HCs. In total there were 8 protein significantly increased in EVs from GCA patients. The presence of RPH3A linked with the increased of Serum Amyloid A4 and Cathepsin G suggestive of neutrophil activation and acute-phase signalling.

Conclusions: The content of EV offers new potential biomarkers with RPH3A being solely present in patients with GCA. As this protein is known as a marker for neurodegenerative disease it could also shed light on the pathological process in GCA and potential neuroinflammation.

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Targeting the Gut–Neutrophil Axis as both the origin and potential therapeutic target for immune dysregulation in experimental myeloperoxidase Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV)

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a severe autoimmune small-vessel disease driven by neutrophil-mediated glomerular injury. While renal pathology is well characterised, the role of gut neutrophil activity remains unclear. We hypothesised that gut dysbiosis in MPO-AAV disrupts intestinal barrier integrity, facilitating translocation of bacterial endotoxins that trigger granulopoiesis and neutrophil activation via toll-like receptors (TLRs), culminating in neutrophil extracellular trap (NET) formation and deposition of myeloperoxidase (MPO) autoantigen. We aimed to (1) define the contribution of neutrophils and NETosis to gut barrier dysfunction, and (2) determine whether restoring microbial balance with acetate-producing, fibre-responsive bacteria mitigates disease.

Methods: A 20-day MPO-AAV model was induced in C57BL/6 mice fed either normal chow, high-fibre diet (HFD; n=8), acetate (n=8), or HFD + acetate (n=8). Kidneys and intestines were assessed for neutrophil infiltration and NET formation by confocal microscopy (MPO, DNA, H3Cit), alongside TLR2/4/9 expression. Serum lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-binding protein served as a marker of gut permeability, and MPO-ANCA titres were quantified.

Results: Normal chow-fed mice showed marked intestinal neutrophil infiltration, elevated NETosis, and increased renal TLR2, TLR4, and TLR9 expression compared with HFD, acetate, or HFD + acetate groups (all $P < 0.05$). Circulating LPS-binding protein was higher in controls versus treatment groups ($P < 0.05$), consistent with greater gut leakiness. Acetate and HFD + acetate significantly reduced glomerular leukocyte infiltration (CD4⁺ T cells, neutrophils, macrophages), crescent formation, albuminuria, and MPO-ANCA titres relative to controls (all $P < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Gut neutrophil dysregulation contributes to intestinal barrier breakdown and systemic inflammation in MPO-AAV. Dietary fibre and the short-chain fatty acid acetate restore microbial homeostasis, limit NET formation, and attenuate renal injury. Targeting the neutrophil–microbiota–metabolite axis offers a promising, low-toxicity adjunctive strategy for MPO-AAV.

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Skin microbiome shows differences between pathergy positive and negative patients with Behçet's syndrome

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Background/Aims: Gut, oral and genital mucosa microbiome studies in Behçet's syndrome have shown heterogeneous results including reduced bacterial diversity and decrease in butyrate-producing bacteria. A role of microorganisms and/or microbial products in pathergy positivity was proposed based on decreased positivity after surgical cleaning and increased positivity when patient's saliva and pneumococcal vaccine are applied to the pathergy site. We aimed to determine the skin microbiome of pathergy positive and negative patients with BS.

Methods: We compared the bacterial and fungal skin microbiome of 30 pathergy positive and 30 pathergy negative patients who were not treated with immunosuppressives. Skin samples were obtained by swabbing before the pathergy test and stored at -80C. The first 30 pathergy positive patients and 30 pathergy negative patients matched to the pathergy positive ones for demographic features were included.

Results: Bacterial diversity within each group(alpha diversity) was similarly high in both groups. Beta diversity analysis revealed that the bacteria in the two groups were different from each other in terms of genus and species. The pathergy negative group was rich in Betaproteobacteria, Burkholderiales, and *Ralstonia picketti*, while the pathergy positive group showed enrichment in *Nevskia soli*, *Staphylococcus haemolyticus*, and *Sphingomonas sanxanigenens*. Alpha diversity of fungal species was higher in the pathergy positive group. Beta diversity analysis showed that the fungi of both groups were similar. *Pseudopezicula tracheiphila* and *Aspergillus heterocaryoticus* were the most abundant fungi in the pathergy positive group, while *Aspergillus subversicolor* prevailed in the pathergy negative group.

Conclusions: The skin microbiota was different among pathergy positive and negative BS patients. Bacterial diversity was high and bacterial species were different among the two groups. Fungal diversity was higher in the pathergy positive group and there were similar fungi in terms of genus in both groups. The role of these differences in pathergy positivity needs to be further studied.

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Early ultrastructural lesions of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Although eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) has been considered as a disease belonging to anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, several studies have suggested that the mechanisms associated with eosinophils also play an important role in tissue damage.

Methods: We investigated the ultrastructural findings of sural nerve biopsy specimens obtained from 26 patients with EGPA. For electron microscopy, epoxy-resin-embedded specimens were cut into 70-nm-thick ultrathin transverse sections using an ultramicrotome. Sections were placed on a copper grid, stained with uranyl acetate and lead citrate, and viewed under a transmission electron microscopy.

Results: Findings suggestive of vasculitis, defined as the destruction of vascular structures with or without fibrinoid necrosis, were more frequently detected in the ANCA-positive group than in the ANCA-negative group (3 of 6 cases vs. 2 of 20 cases; $p < 0.05$). Attachment of eosinophils to vascular endothelial cells was observed, particularly at the junction between neighbouring endothelial cells, and some of these eosinophils appeared to escape from the vascular lumen to migrate into the extravascular interstitium. Irrespective of the ANCA status, most eosinophils in both the vascular lumen and extravascular interstitium appeared to be activated because they showed morphological changes suggestive of piecemeal degranulation. Eosinophils directly releasing their specific granules into the extracellular space were also occasionally observed. Some of the nucleus in eosinophils devoid of their plasma membrane lost the typical distinction between euchromatin and peripheral heterochromatin. Spread of nuclear chromatin resulting from the loss of nuclear envelope, suggestive of the occurrence of eosinophil ETosis, was also observed.

Conclusions: Both extravascular and intravascular eosinophils can induce tissue damage irrespective of the ANCA status in patients with EGPA. Even nuclear chromatin released into the extracellular space was also suggested to participate in the process of tissue damage by forming eosinophil extracellular traps, a phenomenon known as eosinophil ETosis.

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Membranous alterations in ANCA-associated vasculitis: Evidence for MPO involvement in immune complex formation

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Background/Aims: Renal lesions in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) usually present as pauci-immune necrotizing glomerulonephritis. However, electron microscopy has shown immune deposits in some cases. Myeloperoxidase (MPO) antigen has been observed to colocalize with IgG, raising the possibility that MPO contributes to immune complex formation in addition to its role in vasculitis. We investigated MPO and IgG localization in membranous lesions associated with AAV.

Methods: Kidney biopsies from three patients with AAV and membranous lesions, including follow-up specimens, were examined using formalin-fixed tissue. Immunohistochemistry included dual staining for MPO and IgG, as well as antigens implicated in membranous nephropathy.

Results: Of three cases, two were negative for major membranous nephropathy antigens, while one was positive for NELL-1. All including two following cases demonstrated mild MPO staining in the basement membrane colocalized with IgG.

Conclusions: These findings support a possible role for MPO in immune complex formation with IgG in membranous lesions of AAV. Further clinicopathological study in a larger cohort is warranted to clarify implications for renal pathogenesis and prognosis in AAV.

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Human MPO-ANCA from people with acute MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis is variably pathogenic in vitro and in vivo

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Background/Aims: While it is accepted that ANCA are pathogenic in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), plasmapheresis is variably effective and there is no direct in vivo evidence of human (h)MPO-ANCA's pathogenicity. Our study aims to define the in vivo pathogenicity of different hMPO-ANCAs.

Methods: Immunoglobulin G (IgG) fractions were purified from plasmapheresis effluents of seven patients presenting with active MPO-AAV and high titre MPO-ANCA. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) production was assessed from primed normal neutrophils stimulated by hMPO-ANCA-containing IgG fractions. Mice expressing human MPO and human FcγRIIIa (hMPO.hFCGR2A mice) primed with granulocyte-colony stimulating factor and lipopolysaccharide were used to determine hMPO-ANCA pathogenicity in vivo.

Results: Compared with normal human IgG, and after controlling for MPO-ANCA titres, all hMPO-ANCA-containing IgG fractions induced neutrophil ROS production. Some ANCAs were more potent than others, but hMPO-ANCA samples demonstrate similar response patterns in neutrophils from three donors. There was no association between ROS production and either hMPO-ANCA IgG subclasses or IgG titres specific for the pathogenic B-cell epitope MPO447-459. Compared with normal human IgG, transfer of hMPO-ANCA (from patient 1) to hMPO.hFCGR2A mice induced intrarenal neutrophil and inflammatory monocyte infiltrates with haematuria and crescentic glomerulonephritis in all recipients, but mice expressing human MPO without human FcγRIIIa developed only minimal disease (0.4±0.4% vs 15.5±1.9% crescents, P<0.0001). The three human MPO-ANCAs with the highest MPO-ANCA titres were transferred into hMPO.hFCGR2A mice. While all hMPO-ANCAs induced haematuria and glomerular crescents, severity (including leukocyte infiltrates) varied by donor (MPO-AAV patient 1: 12.6±1.3%, patient 2: 6.6±1.2%, patient 3: 2.0±0.3% crescents, P<0.001; serum cystatin-C 638.0±30.6, 526.0±31.3, 428.6±24.6µg/L, P=0.0084). In addition, different hMPO-ANCAs induced variable kidney pro-inflammatory gene expression and pulmonary leukocyte infiltrates.

Conclusions: Human MPO-ANCA from patients with active MPO-AAV is pathogenic in vivo in an FcγRIIIa-dependent manner, but different hMPO-ANCAs are variably pathogenic in vitro and in vivo.

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Endothelial damage is promoted by ANCA activated neutrophils in vitro and enhanced under hypoxic conditions

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Background/Aims: Neutrophils are key mediators of disease in ANCA associated vasculitis (AAV). Activation by pathogenic ANCA IgG promotes neutrophil adhesion and migration at the endothelium. Sites of inflammation and tissue injury are presumably hypoxic in AAV, however whether pathological hypoxia enhances neutrophil induced endothelial injury remains unknown.

Methods: Primary human glomerular endothelial cells (gEC) were either co-cultured directly with ANCA stimulated neutrophils, or neutrophil conditioned supernatants. Trans-endothelial migration (TEM), gEC injury (dextran flow through), ROS production, and activation (sICAM and sVCAM release) were measured at normoxia (21% O₂) or hypoxia (1% O₂). Neutrophil CD177 and gEC CD31 expression were measured using flow cytometry.

Results: Conditioned supernatants from ANCA-stimulated healthy-donor control (HC) neutrophils induced significant gEC injury, with increased dextran permeability of gEC monolayers. gEC activation was also seen with release of sICAM and sVCAM. Comparable findings were seen when conditioned supernatants from untreated aAAV neutrophils were used. In both contexts, these responses were enhanced in hypoxic conditions (1% O₂). In direct co-culture, ANCA-stimulated neutrophil TEM across intact gEC monolayers was significantly increased under 1% O₂. Hypoxia also enhanced ANCA-stimulated neutrophil-induced gEC activation, as evidenced by elevated sICAM/sVCAM release and gEC ROS production. In co-culture neutrophil CD177 expression and corresponding gEC CD31 expression were significantly increased following ANCA stimulation suggesting bidirectional activation; again, this was enhanced in hypoxia.

Conclusions: ANCA-stimulated neutrophils, or their secreted products, cause marked gEC injury, activation, and neutrophil TEM. Enhanced CD177-PECAM-1 interactions may facilitate TEM. Tissue hypoxia at sites of vasculitis injury may create a positive feedback loop amplifying ANCA-driven neutrophil endothelial damage. These findings highlight hypoxia as a critical modulator of neutrophil-endothelial interactions in AAV.

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Neutrophil CD11b is a pivotal PANoptosis marker correlated with disease activity in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Neutrophil-mediated inflammation plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Dysregulated neutrophil death has been implicated in promoting neutrophil priming and activation. PANoptosis, an inflammatory programmed cell death, participates in the development of various autoimmune diseases. The current study aims to identify the key PANoptosis-related marker and investigate its association with disease activity of AAV.

Methods: Gene microarray data of ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis (ANCA-GN) was downloaded from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO). PANoptosis-associated genes were sourced from GeneCards. The hub-marker of PANoptosis-related gene (PRG) was identified by integrating GO, KEGG, PPI network, WGCNA, LASSO-Logistic, and ROC analysis. Then levels of activated CD11b on neutrophils from peripheral blood were measured in AAV patients, and its associations with clinicopathological parameters of AAV patients were analyzed. Changes of intracellular metabolic pathways of neutrophils from AAV patients were further investigated. A small molecule inhibitor was used to explore the effect of intracellular fatty acid metabolism (FAO) on neutrophil CD11b activation and PANoptosis.

Results: CD11b was identified as the pivotal PRG in AAV by integrated bioinformatics analysis. The level of activated CD11b on neutrophils was significantly higher in active AAV patients compared with healthy controls, and this elevation was positively associated with disease activity, as evidenced by higher levels of hypersensitive C-reactive protein (hCRP), increased Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS), elevated serum creatinine levels at sampling and a higher proportion of cellular crescents in renal specimens of AAV patients. Moreover, neutrophils from AAV patients exhibited an aberrant FAO phenotype and a down-regulated peroxisome proliferators-activated receptor (PPAR)- α pathway, as compared with healthy controls. GW7647, a PPAR α agonist, could alleviate AAV serum-induced neutrophil CD11b activation and PANoptosis.

Conclusions: CD11b was a pivotal PANoptosis-related gene in AAV. The level of activated CD11b on neutrophils was associated with the disease activity of AAV patients.

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Targeting neutrophil cytoskeletal dysregulation in ANCA-associated Vasculitis

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Background/Aims: In ANCA associated vasculitis (AAV), pathogenic ANCA IgG activates neutrophils, driving endothelial injury; this may be amplified at sites of tissue hypoxia such as inflamed vasculature. Because neutrophil immune functions are tightly linked to their actin cytoskeleton, targeting dysregulated cytoskeletal pathways may offer a novel therapeutic approach.

Methods: We profiled neutrophil transcriptional signatures from healthy controls (HC), patients in remission (rAAV), and patients with active AAV (aAAV) using poly(A) RNA-Seq. Neutrophils were primed (TNF), treated with the cdc42 inhibitor ML141 (or vehicle) and stimulated with MPO-/PR3-ANCA IgG under normoxia (21% O₂) or hypoxia (1% O₂). F-actin polymerisation (AF488-Phalloidin) and NETosis (H3Cit) were visualised. Experimental autoimmune vasculitis (EAV) was induced by human MPO immunisation followed by sub-nephritogenic nephrotoxic serum (NTS) at day 14. ML141 (1mg/kg) or vehicle was administered IP daily (days 14-28). Disease severity, autoimmunity, leucocyte biomechanics (real-time deformability cytometry), and angiogenesis (aortic ring assay) were assessed on day 28.

Results: Neutrophils from patients with aAAV or MPO-/PR3-ANCA stimulated HC displayed significant upregulation of actin capping/polymerisation genes (CAPG, DAAM2, RHOC, CDC42EP5) under both oxygen tensions. ANCA stimulation induces significant neutrophil actin polymerisation, filopodia formation and NETosis, with enhanced ANCA effects at 1% O₂. At both oxygen tensions, ML141 completely inhibited ANCA induced cytoskeletal changes and NETosis. In vivo, ML141 prevented EAV-induced leucocyte stiffening, reduced glomerular and pulmonary leucocyte infiltration and prevented lung haemorrhage. ML141 treatment partially normalised EAV-induced enhancement of aortic ring sprouting, suggesting prevention of vascular remodelling linked to inflammation.

Conclusions: ANCA and hypoxia synergistically enhance neutrophil pathogenicity. ML141 suppresses these effects in vitro and prevented decreased leucocyte deformability and significantly decreased glomerular and pulmonary leucocyte infiltration in experimental disease. Targeting the neutrophil actin cytoskeleton in AAV may limit leucocyte trapping in microvasculature, in turn preventing inflammation and vascular damage.

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Gene therapy for controlled DNase1 expression using a branaplam-inducible switch in an adeno-associated virus vector protects against experimental MPO-ANCA glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: We have previously shown that the breakdown of extracellular DNA (ecDNA) through delivery of an adeno-associated virus (AAV) vector encoding constitutively activated expression of DNase1, ameliorates disease in experimental anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) associated vasculitis. While this provides proof-of principle, constitutive expression raises potential safety concerns during remission. To address this, we aimed to enhance control of DNase1 expression by incorporating an inducible molecular switch, responsive to the oral drug branaplam. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of branaplam-inducible AAV-DNase1 vector in experimental ANCA-associated vasculitis.

Methods: Dose-testing studies were first performed in C57/BL6 mice to identify the dose of branaplam required to induce DNase1 expression. Subsequently, a 20-day model of experimental anti-myeloperoxidase (MPO) glomerulonephritis was utilised. Mice were randomised to receive either constitutively active DNase1 AAV Vector, a branaplam-inducible DNase1 vector with or without branaplam (oral gavage), or control luciferase vector (n=8 per group). Serum DNase1 levels and hepatic vector expression was analysed. Kidney injury was evaluated through histology, albuminuria and quantification of infiltrating leukocytes (CD4+ T cells, macrophages, neutrophils). Renal neutrophil extracellular trap (NET) production was determined by confocal microscopy for MPO/H3Cit/PAD4 and DNA.

Results: A single branaplam dose at 9mg/kg induced an increase in serum DNase1 activity compared to endogenous DNase1 in the mice. In anti-MPO glomerulonephritis, inducible DNase1 expression initiated on day 16, after establishment of autoimmunity to MPO, resulted in systemic DNase1 elevation which significantly reduced glomerular injury, albuminuria, MPO-ANCA titres and MPO-specific effector CD4+ T cell (all p<0.05 vs controls). Moreover, NET production and renal leukocyte infiltration were significantly reduced (all, P<0.05) compared to controls.

Conclusions: Branaplam-inducible DNase1 AAV gene therapy effectively reduced disease activity in experimental ANCA-vasculitis, providing a flexible strategy to regulate therapeutic expression. This approach represents an important step toward the safe clinical translation of gene therapy for ANCA-associated vasculitis.

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Nrf2 activation mitigates experimental AAV by reducing ROS, NET Formation and Th17 responses

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)–associated vasculitis (AAV) features necrotizing vascular inflammation in which ANCA-triggered neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) drive endothelial injury and amplify autoimmunity via reactive oxygen species (ROS). Nuclear factor erythroid 2–related factor 2 (Nrf2) orchestrates antioxidant defences. We investigated whether pharmacologic activation or genetic loss of Nrf2 modulates NET formation and vascular damage in AAV.

Methods: Human neutrophils were pretreated with the Nrf2 activator bardoxolone methyl and stimulated with ANCA; NET formation, intracellular ROS, and signalling were quantified by live-cell imaging and biochemical assays. Protection against NET-induced cytotoxicity was assessed in human renal glomerular endothelial cells (HRGECs). Neutrophils from wild-type (WT) or Nrf2-deficient mice were challenged with anti-myeloperoxidase (MPO) antibody. In vivo, bardoxolone was administered to an ANCA-transfer AAV model and to spontaneous AAV-prone SCG/Kj mice. Kidney diseases were evaluated biochemically and histologically, including tissue ROS, NQO1 expression, NET accumulation, endothelial integrity, and apoptosis. Immunophenotyping of splenocytes was performed by flow cytometry. To test genetic causality, SCG/Kj mice carrying a germ-line Nrf2 deletion were generated and analysed.

Results: Pharmacologic Nrf2 activation suppressed ANCA-induced NETosis by limiting intracellular ROS and upregulating the antioxidant enzyme NQO1, whereas Nrf2-deficient neutrophils showed exaggerated NET release. Bardoxolone directly protected HRGECs from NET-mediated cytotoxicity. In both AAV models, Nrf2 activation ameliorated glomerulonephritis, reduced tissue ROS, and decreased glomerular NET burden. Conversely, Nrf2 deficiency exacerbated spontaneous vasculitis. Nrf2 activation also restrained splenic T-cell expansion and reduced renal Th17 infiltration, indicating immunomodulatory effects beyond neutrophils.

Conclusions: Activation of Nrf2 mounts an antioxidant program that curtails ROS-dependent NETosis, preserves endothelial viability, and attenuates experimental AAV. These findings position Nrf2 as a mechanistically grounded therapeutic target and support clinical evaluation of Nrf2 activators as adjunctive therapy to limit NET-driven vascular injury in AAV.

Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-induced neutrophil extracellular traps exhibit distinct morphological and functional characteristics compared to those induced by anti-phosphatidylserine/prothrombin antibodies

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) is a type of autoantibody that induces neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), and ANCA-induced NETs contribute to the development of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) by damaging vascular endothelial cells. Anti-phosphatidylserine/prothrombin antibody (aPS/PT), one of the antiphospholipid antibodies often detected in antiphospholipid syndrome (APS), is thought to promote thrombosis by inducing NETs and thereby contributing to immunothrombosis. We hypothesized that the divergent pathological outcomes of vasculitis and thrombosis result from differences in the characteristics of NETs induced by these autoantibodies. This study aimed to compare the morphology, the potential of platelet activation, and the cytotoxicity to vascular endothelial cells of NETs induced by ANCA and aPS/PT.

Methods: Neutrophils were stimulated by ANCA or aPS/PT to induce NETs. After immunofluorescent staining, the area and circularity of NETs were analysed using ImageJ. Washed platelets were added during NET induction, and then platelet activation trapped in NETs was assessed by CD61 and CD62P staining. The viability of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) exposed to supernatants of NETs induced by ANCA and aPS/PT was also assessed.

Results: NETs induced by ANCA had a smaller area and higher circularity than those induced by aPS/PT. The platelets trapped in aPS/PT-induced NETs were more activated than those trapped in ANCA-induced NETs. The cytotoxic effects on HUVEC were comparable between the supernatants of ANCA-induced NETs and aPS/PT-induced NETs.

Conclusions: NETs induced by ANCA and aPS/PT showed differences in morphology and platelet-activating potential. NETs induced by ANCA, which are small and round, may contribute to pathogenesis of AAV in the microvasculature of the kidneys and lungs. In contrast, NETs induced by aPS/PT, which are large and radial with strong platelet-activating potential, are suggested to contribute to thrombosis in APS by promoting platelet activation in the systemic vasculature.

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Visomitin as a novel NET-targeted therapy for MPO-ANCA vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Microscopic polyangiitis is a subtype of AAV and is characterised by loss of tolerance to the neutrophil protein myeloperoxidase. It frequently causes glomerulonephritis, leading to renal failure if inadequately treated. Current induction therapies such as cyclophosphamide and rituximab are broadly immunosuppressive, leading to higher risk of infection. Neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) are increasingly recognised as key drivers of glomerular inflammation in AAV, and there are currently no treatments that target them. Visomitin (SkQ1), a mitochondria-specific antioxidant, scavenges excess mitochondrial reactive oxygen species and therefore reduces NET release. We aimed to assess its therapeutic potential as a targeted and safer therapy for AAV.

Methods: A 20-day mouse model of AAV was used to compare the efficacy of visomitin with cyclophosphamide *in vivo*. Renal injury and leukocyte recruitment were assessed histologically, and serum ANCA levels were ascertained using an ELISA. Effects on neutrophil functions were examined using human neutrophils *in vitro*. To assess its immunosuppressive effects, a mouse influenza model was used to evaluate viral clearance and lung inflammation following prophylactic treatment.

Results: *In vivo*, visomitin reduced glomerular injury, glomerular leukocyte infiltration, and circulating ANCA levels (all $p < 0.05$). *In vitro*, visomitin inhibited NET formation without impairing resting neutrophils and phagocytosis. In influenza models, visomitin-treated mice displayed viral load comparable to untreated flu controls. There was also no difference in pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and KC) in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid between the two groups. In contrast, cyclophosphamide treatment impaired viral clearance and maintained high levels of pulmonary inflammation.

Conclusions: Visomitin alleviated structural glomerular damage in experimental AAV while preserving host defence against influenza. These findings support visomitin as a novel, NET-targeted induction therapy for AAV, with the potential to reduce infection-associated morbidity that is frequently present in current treatment regimes.

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Early MPO inhibition prevents organ damage in experimental ANCA vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Myeloperoxidase (MPO) is both an autoantigen and a driver vascular injury in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Targeting MPO activity may offer a novel therapeutic strategy.

Methods: We investigated the selective MPO inhibitor AZM198 in a well-characterised rat model of experimental vasculitis. Disease was induced by human MPO immunisation followed by sub-nephritogenic nephrotoxic serum (NTS) challenge at day 14. AZM198 was administered orally (125 mg/kg/day) in three regimens (n=5-8/group): prevention (day 7–27), early intervention (day 16–35), and late intervention (day 25–35). Disease assessments (26h after last dosing) included proteinuria, haematuria, glomerular and pulmonary injury scores, and MPO activity in plasma and kidney.

Results: AZM198 significantly attenuated disease in prevention and early intervention settings, but not late intervention. In prevention, both proteinuria and haematuria at day 28 were reduced versus vehicle ($p < 0.05$). The proportion of normal glomeruli increased from 35% to 59%, while severely abnormal glomeruli were reduced from 16% to 10% with AZM198 ($p < 0.05$). Lung injury scores were also lower ($p < 0.05$). In early intervention, both proteinuria and haematuria at day 35 were significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$) and renal histology improved (61% severely abnormal glomeruli in controls versus 12% with AZM198, $p = 0.01$). These benefits correlated with reductions in MPO activity and activity/mass ratio in plasma and kidney, while antibody titres and MPO antigen levels were unaffected. A strong positive correlation between renal MPO activity and proteinuria reinforced the pathogenic role of MPO-driven oxidative injury. Late intervention failed to alter renal outcomes, although modest protection against lung injury was observed.

Conclusions: These findings confirm MPO activity as a mechanistic driver of organ injury in AAV and identify early MPO inhibition as a therapeutic window of opportunity to limit disease progression and has the potential to complement current therapy.

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BTK inhibition ameliorates MPO-ANCA IgG induced glomerulonephritis, lung capillaritis, lung microabscesses and lung granulomatosis in a mouse model of granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: In vitro studies using human ANCA show that ANCA IgG activates neutrophils by Fcγ receptor engagement (Porges AJ, et al: J Immunol 1994;153:1271–1280). BTK Inhibitors (BTKi) block neutrophil activation by disrupting Fcγ receptor signaling. We hypothesized that BTKi would block disease induction in our mouse model of MPO-ANCA IgG induced granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) with glomerulonephritis (GN), lung capillaritis, lung microabscesses, and lung granulomatosis (Hu P, et al. Kidney Int. 2024;106:870-886).

Methods: Wild type B6 mice were given i.v. mouse MPO-ANCA IgG on day 0 and day 1, and i.e. BTKi (Ibrutinib purchased from MedChemExpress) or vehicle alone on day -1, day 0 and daily until humanely sacrificed on day 3 (n=12) or day 7 (n=12), using equal numbers for bTKi versus vehicle alone. Postmortem histopathologic evaluation focused on lungs and kidneys.

Results: On day 3, mice that received MPO-ANCA IgG and vehicle alone had lung capillaritis, microabscesses, and haemorrhage. No granulomatosis developed by day 3. No mice that received MPO-ANCA IgG and BTKi developed lung disease by day 3. On day 7, mice that received MPO-ANCA IgG and vehicle alone had GN with necrosis and crescents, and all had lung granulomatosis. All microabscesses were replaced by granulomas by day 7. Mice that received MPO-ANCA IgG and BTKi had minimal GN and three had no GN. Mice that received BTKi had no lung disease at 7 days.

Conclusions: BTKi ameliorates MPO-ANCA IgG induced GN, lung capillaritis, lung microabscesses, and lung granulomatosis. A likely mechanism for BTKi amelioration of ANCA disease is blocking neutrophil activation by disrupting Fcγ receptor signalling.

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Inhibition of interleukin-21 ameliorates renal injury in a rat model of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is characterized by the production of ANCAs and necrotizing small-vessel vasculitis. Interleukin (IL)-21 is a cytokine that broadly affects immune cells. In AAV, IL-21 is considered to contribute to the pathogenesis by promoting B cell differentiation and proliferation, leading to increased antibody production, and by facilitating the differentiation of CD4-positive T cells into T helper 17 (Th17) cells. Standard treatments for AAV include glucocorticoids and immunosuppressants; however, cases of resistance and relapse necessitate new therapeutic developments. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of anti-rat IL-21 aptamer (Apt), an IL-21 inhibitor, on a rat model of AAV.

Methods: Four-week-old Wistar Kyoto rats were immunized with human myeloperoxidase (MPO) to induce MPO-AAV. Treatment began on day 21, and blood, urine, and tissue samples were collected on day 42. B cell subset analysis, quantification of neutrophil extracellular trap (NET) formation, and assessment of renal tissue injury were performed.

Results: Administration of anti-rat IL-21 Apt suppressed the differentiation of non-switched early plasmablasts, but did not reduce MPO-ANCA titres significantly. The rates of glomerular lesion and intraglomerular deposition of NETs were significantly reduced in the Apt-treated rats compared to the non-treated rats. A decreasing trend was also observed in peripheral blood NET-forming neutrophils and urinary neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin levels. Furthermore, glomerular IL-17 expression and macrophage infiltration were significantly decreased by IL-21 inhibition.

Conclusions: These findings suggest that anti-rat IL-21 Apt ameliorates renal injury in AAV by suppressing the pathological cascade involving Th17 cell differentiation, IL-17-mediated macrophage activation, and subsequent neutrophil priming and NET-formation. Targeting IL-21 can be a novel therapeutic strategy for AAV.

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Establishing a murine model of propylthiouracil-induced MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis in humanised mice

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Background/Aims: Propylthiouracil (PTU), a widely used antithyroid drug, has been implicated in the induction of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in humans by inducing loss of tolerance to myeloperoxidase (MPO). However, how PTU induces loss of tolerance and MPO-ANCA production remains unclear. We aimed to develop a PTU-induced mouse model of MPO-AAV to better understand the pathogenesis of PTU-induced AAV.

Methods: hMPO.hPR3.hFCGR2A.Tg mice that were knocked in for both human MPO and human PR3, as well as transgenic for FcγRIIIa were treated with PTU (0.5 mg/ml) in drinking water for 28 days. Phorbol-12-myristate 13 acetate (PMA: 50 ng/day), G-CSF (6 µg/day) and LPS (0.5 µg/g) were administered as adjuvant treatments (PMA: day 0, 7; G-CSF: day 0, 7, 13, 14; LPS: day 14). Experiments ended at day 28. Serum mouse anti-hMPO antibodies were measured by ELISA, kidneys were assessed histologically for features of glomerulonephritis and intrarenal leukocytes were examined by flow cytometry.

Results: hMPO.hPR3.FCGR2A.Tg mice developed serum mouse anti-hMPO antibodies after PTU and PMA administration, but serum mouse anti-hMPO titres were more prominent in mice receiving the combination of PTU, PMA, G-CSF and LPS. In this group (n=6), 2 mice developed haematuria and albuminuria, but did not develop statistically significant kidney impairment. Mice developed focal abnormalities in 15.6±6.6% of glomeruli, including proliferative changes without crescent formation. While total CD45+ intrarenal leukocytes were not increased across the group, the most significantly affected mouse (functionally and histologically, with 48% of glomeruli affected) exhibited higher proportions of intrarenal Ly6G+ CD11b+ neutrophils and CD4+ T cells.

Conclusions: Administering PTU with PMA, G-CSF and LPS to hMPO.hPR3.hFCGR2A.Tg mice induced mouse anti-hMPO antibodies and kidney abnormalities. This model, with further refinement, can effectively be used to investigate the mechanisms and mediators underlying PTU-induced MPO-AAV.

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Assessing the effects of glucocorticoids on atheroma formation in crescentic glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: Crescentic glomerulonephritis (CGN) is associated with autoimmune conditions, including ANCA-associated vasculitis and SLE, which are known to be associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). The mainstay of treatment for many of these autoimmune conditions are glucocorticoids (GC), which are themselves associated with an increased risk of CVD, along with a host of other side effects.

It remains unclear if the increased frequency of CVD in patients with CGN is a result of the underlying inflammatory process, the GC used in their treatment, or both. We aim to investigate this association to establish the respective contributory roles of both CGN and GC in the development of CVD, and assess the effect of alternative therapeutics in this setting.

Method: Atheroma-susceptible APOE^{-/-} mice were injected with saline or nephrotoxic serum and fed a high fat diet (HFD) with or without prednisolone or a myeloperoxidase-inhibitor (MPOi). Blood pressure, serum, urine and kidney histology were used to assess kidney disease. Aortas, stained with Oil RedO, were imaged to quantify the extent of CVD. Aortic RNA was extracted and sequenced to establish gene expression profiles.

Results: Our model showed the significant effect of increasing age and high-dose prednisolone on the development of atheroma compared to controls on HFD alone and mice treated with MPOi. There was no difference in atheroma between mice with CGN on HFD and controls. There was no significant difference in systolic blood pressures between the groups. Differential expression of several genes occurred between treatment and control groups.

Conclusion: Mice given prednisolone have significantly more atheroma in both the presence and absence of kidney disease, an effect not associated with increase in systolic blood pressure. Use of an MPOi was associated with reduced atheroma formation. Differential gene expression in the presence of steroids may account for the differences observed.

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Comparison of the therapeutic effects of anti-ApoA2 and recombinant VasSF in a mouse model of Kawasaki disease

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Background/Aims: Kawasaki disease (KD) is a severe systemic vasculitis typically treated with high-dose intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg). However, human plasma-derived IVIg faces challenges, including infection risk and supply instability, spurring the need for alternative recombinant antibody therapies. We previously developed a recombinant antibody candidate, VasSF, targeting apolipoprotein A-2 (ApoA2) and demonstrated its efficacy in a spontaneous crescentic glomerulonephritis (SCG/Kj) model. We also reported the therapeutic efficacy of an anti-ApoA2 antibody in a *Candida albicans* water-soluble fraction (CAWS)-induced KD mouse model. In this study, we compared the therapeutic efficacy of an anti-ApoA2 antibody and VasSF in the KD mouse model.

Methods: Kawasaki disease-like coronary arteritis was induced in C57BL/6 mice by intraperitoneal administration of CAWS. Mice were treated with an anti-ApoA2 antibody, VasSF, human IgG, or PBS. The incidence and histopathological severity of vasculitis were assessed. Serum cytokine and chemokine concentrations were measured using a Bio-Plex assay.

Results: Administration of anti-ApoA2 antibody significantly reduced the incidence and severity of coronary arteritis in a concentration-dependent manner compared with the control group. Serum concentrations of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, M-CSF, and MIP-1 α , were also significantly reduced. However, in this Kawasaki disease model, VasSF administration showed variable effects on vasculitis and inflammatory marker concentrations, making the results inconclusive.

Conclusions: Anti-ApoA2 antibody effectively suppresses the development of coronary arteritis in KD mouse models and is a promising therapeutic candidate with fewer side effects than IVIg. While VasSF has shown efficacy in other vasculitis models, it did not demonstrate significant efficacy in this KD model, suggesting that the underlying pathogenetic mechanisms may be different. Further research into ApoA2 and related targets is needed to develop new treatments for KD.

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Phenotypic and transcriptomic alterations of circulating monocytes in proteinase 3-ANCA-positive granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Proteinase 3 (PR3)-ANCA-associated granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a small-vessel vasculitis characterized by frequent relapses and progressive organ damage. Monocytes are implicated in GPA pathogenesis; however, their role across different disease states remains unclear. This study used single-cell multi-omics to characterize circulating monocyte subsets in GPA patients and to identify phenotypic and molecular signatures associated with disease activity.

Methods: Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from untreated patients with active GPA (n = 12), in remission (n = 11), and healthy controls (HCs; n = 12) were analysed using a 35-color spectral flow cytometry panel. Complementary AbSeq profiling was performed on PBMC samples from active GPA (n = 5), remission (n = 5), and HCs (n = 5) to integrate surface protein and transcriptomic data.

Results: Spectral flow analysis revealed increased proportions of classical monocytes (cMO) and reduced proportions of non-classical monocytes (ncMO) in active GPA versus HCs. Compared to HCs, active GPA patients had upregulated SLAMF7 expression on cMO, while CD40 was elevated on intermediate monocytes (iMO) and ncMO. Conversely, their cMO exhibited reduced expression of HLA-DR and CD86.

AbSeq profiling confirmed reduced HLA-DR and CD86 expression on cMO in active GPA versus HCs and further identified CD226 and CD32B/C downregulation, whereas CD272 and CD49 upregulation across subsets. GPA patients in remission displayed elevated CD40 expression versus HCs.

Transcriptomic profiling of cMO and iMO demonstrated upregulation of CXCL3, BCL2A1, and PIM1, alongside downregulation of immune-regulatory genes EGR1/2 and PRDM1 in active GPA versus HCs. GPA patients in remission showed elevated SLAMF7 expression in cMO and iMO versus HCs, suggesting persistent immune activation despite clinical quiescence.

Conclusions: Monocyte profiling reveals distinct immune alterations in active GPA and evidence of persistent activation during remission. Integration of spectral flow and AbSeq data with clinical parameters is ongoing.

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Patterns of macrophage polarization induced by serum from patients with giant cell arteritis and Takayasu's arteritis

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Background/Aims: Macrophages are central to the pathogenesis of large-vessel vasculitides, including giant cell arteritis (GCA) and Takayasu's arteritis (TAK). Defining patterns of macrophage polarization induced by patient serum may reveal disease-specific immune signatures and therapeutic targets.

Methods: Purified monocytes from healthy donors were differentiated into macrophages (M0) and polarized toward M1, M2a, M2b, or M2c phenotypes using standard cytokine stimuli. These served as the training dataset. Flow cytometry assessed phenotype-defining markers: CD40 (M1), CD206 (M2a), HLA-DR (negative in M2b), and CD163 (M2c). Macrophages exposed to serum from patients with GCA (n=40), TAK (n=40), or healthy controls (HC, n=19) were analysed as test samples. Data were extracted from FlowJo™ workspaces into R, arcsinh-transformed, and analysed with a K-Nearest Neighbours classifier (k=10) trained on M0–M2c macrophages. Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) was applied for dimensionality reduction, and statistical differences were assessed using Fisher's exact and Mann–Whitney U tests.

Results: Macrophages exposed to HC serum polarized into more diverse phenotypes, with higher proportions of M2a- and M2c-like subsets. Serum from patients with GCA maintained macrophages in an undifferentiated M0-like state, while serum from TAK favoured an increase in M2b-like macrophages, consistent with immune complex stimulation. M1 prevalence was negligible across all groups, but HC demonstrated a modest 4- to 6-fold increase compared to vasculitis sera. Statistically significant group differences were observed for all subsets except M1 between GCA and TAK. Overall, HC promoted regulatory and repair-associated polarization, GCA limited differentiation, and TAK induced a broader, more heterogeneous profile.

Conclusions: Serum from patients with GCA and TAK drives distinct macrophage polarization compared to HC. These findings suggest macrophage phenotyping may uncover disease-specific immune dysregulation and holds promise as a tool to identify therapeutic targets in large-vessel vasculitis.

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Hepatocyte growth factor promotes IL-6 production in adventitial fibroblasts and exacerbates large vessel vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Previous studies have demonstrated that hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) contributes to the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis by acting on synovial fibroblasts and promoting IL-6 production. However, the role of HGF in large vessel vasculitis (LVV) remains unclear. This study aimed to investigate the involvement of HGF in the pathogenesis of LVV by examining its expression and functional effects on fibroblasts in the vascular wall.

Methods: Patients diagnosed with LVV who visited Osaka Metropolitan University Hospital between May 2021 and March 2025 were enrolled in this study, and serum samples were collected cross-sectionally. HGF and its receptor c-Met expression in temporal artery specimens were examined by immunohistochemistry. Human aortic fibroblasts were stimulated with HGF, and IL-6 production was quantified by real-time PCR.

Results: A total of 35 serum samples were analysed (GCA: n=15; TAK: n=20). The median age of patients was 58 years, and the median prednisolone dose was 6 mg/day. Serum HGF levels were significantly elevated in LVV patients compared to healthy controls (P=0.042), but no significant difference was observed between GCA and TAK (P=0.68). Immunohistochemical analysis of temporal artery specimens revealed that HGF was predominantly produced by adventitial fibroblasts and myofibroblasts. The proportion of HGF-positive CD90+ fibroblasts was significantly higher in biopsy-positive arteries than in biopsy-negative arteries (P=0.0044). While CD68+ macrophages also contributed to HGF production, CD90+ fibroblasts exhibited a significantly greater proportion of HGF positivity (P=0.03). HGF receptor c-Met expression was predominantly observed in fibroblasts in the adventitia. In vitro stimulation of human aortic fibroblasts with HGF resulted in a dose-dependent increase in IL-6 production (P=0.0018).

Conclusions: These findings suggest that HGF may contribute to the pathogenesis of LVV by targeting fibroblasts in the vascular adventitia and enhancing IL-6 production. The HGF-c-Met axis could be a potential target for further investigation.

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Changes in urinary sCD163 and plasma endotrophin levels with avacopan treatment for granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) with kidney involvement

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Background/Aims: In the Phase 3 ADVOCATE trial, patients with kidney disease due to GPA/MPA in the avacopan arm had greater improvement in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) at week (W) 52 and faster reduction in albuminuria than those in the prednisone taper arm. Biomarker analysis, including markers of kidney inflammation and fibrosis, may help elucidate mechanisms underlying this differential response.

Methods: In ADVOCATE, 268 (81%) of 330 patients had kidney involvement at baseline and were randomized to a prednisone taper (n=134) or avacopan regimen (n=134) with allowances for glucocorticoids in both arms. Urinary soluble CD163, a macrophage activation marker, was measured by Luminex assay and normalized to urinary creatinine (UsCD163/Cr). Plasma endotrophin, an inflammation and fibrosis marker, was measured by PRO-C6 ELISA. Both biomarkers were evaluated over 52 weeks across baseline eGFR subgroups: <30, 30-59, and >59 mL/min/1.73 m².

Results: Baseline UsCD163/Cr and plasma endotrophin levels were higher in patients with lower baseline eGFR (p<0.01 for both). In patients with an eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73m², UsCD163/Cr declined by W4 in both arms with a suggested faster decline in the avacopan arm; however, percent change from baseline was not significantly different. Across all eGFR subgroups in the avacopan arm, plasma endotrophin peaked at W4, then progressively declined; in the prednisone taper arm, plasma endotrophin initially decreased at W4, peaked at W26, and then declined at W52. For patients in the avacopan arm, endotrophin levels were significantly higher at W4 for all eGFR subgroups and lower at W26 for the eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73m² subgroup vs the prednisone taper arm (interaction p<0.01).

Conclusions: This secondary analysis suggests both treatment regimens affect UsCD163/Cr (macrophage activation) in a directionally similar manner; however, early differences in plasma endotrophin levels may indicate divergent effects on fibrotic remodelling, potentially influencing outcomes, but this requires further investigation.

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Can we define renal remission more accurately in patients with acute AAV using personalised urinary soluble CD163?

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Background/Aims: The clinical utility of minimally invasive biomarkers of remission in patients with acute AAV and associated renal involvement is limited. We sought to longitudinally profile one such emerging biomarker of M2-macrophage activation, urinary soluble CD163 (usCD163), to define individual variations over time in relation to a) traditional biomarkers of renal remission and b) immunosuppression (IS) received.

Methods: Incident adult patients with de-novo/relapsing acute AAV with renal involvement were recruited at diagnosis, almost all IS-naïve excluding steroids, and followed up for 1 year (including until remission). Traditional surrogate markers were prospectively recorded (haematoproteinuria, serum creatinine, C-reactive protein, PR3/MPO autoantibodies, BVAS, nephrologists' assessment of remission). Commercially available ELISA kits were used according to manufacturer's instructions to quantify usCD163 (DuoSet DY1607; R&D systems) with values normalised to urine creatinine and assessed for positivity based on a previously described cutoff of ≥ 250 ng/mmol.

Results: 10 patients were recruited with a mean age (SD) of 59 (15) years; 40% male and 50% white. Eight presented with de-novo disease, remainder with relapse. All patients were ANCA positive for anti-PR3 (n=6) or anti-MPO (n=4). Clinical phenotypes comprised GPA (n=5), MPA (n=4) and EGPA (n=1). Patients were studied for a median (IQR) of 267 (239-363) days. The median (IQR) time to peak and to achieve negativity of usCD163:Cr was 0 (0-14) days and 80 (49-175) days, respectively. After achieving usCD163:Cr negativity, 60% of patients received additional induction IS. usCD163:Cr negativity predated the median time taken to achieve normalisation of all aforementioned traditional biomarkers.

Conclusions: There are individual variations in time taken and IS required to achieve usCD163 negativity. usCD163:Cr negativity predates normalisation of other traditional biomarkers of renal remission. Declaring clinical remission to guide personalised induction IS, in the absence of a biopsy, may be achieved more confidently by correlating usCD163:Cr with traditional (and other emerging) biomarkers.

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Urinary Soluble CD163 as a biomarker of renal disease activity in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis - A systematic review and metanalysis.

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Background/Aims: Active glomerulonephritis (GN) in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is determined by urinalysis abnormalities, proteinuria, creatinine levels, and histologic findings. Renal damage may be a confounding factor when assessing disease activity. Urinary soluble (us)CD163 is a macrophage marker with diagnostic properties for detecting active GN in AAV. This study aims to determine the diagnostic accuracy of usCD163 for detecting active GN in AAV.

Methods: A systematic review was conducted using the main databases up to August 2025, according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) recommendations. Studies evaluating usCD163 as a biomarker of active GN in AAV in the English literature were included. The Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score version 3 and renal biopsy were reference standards. Two researchers independently selected abstracts using the Rayyan software. Risk of bias was assessed by the QUADAS-2 tool version 5.3. The bivariate model of meta-analysis aimed to generate a summary receiver operator curve (SROC) using the R software. A test consequence graphic was also performed.

Results: Ninety-eight manuscripts were found, nine were eligible for full analysis, and six fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Only one study had a prospective design. The usCD163 cutoffs varied widely (0.3-350ng/mmol of creatinine). All studies had an unclear risk of bias in several domains, and few had a high risk of bias in some domains. Pooled sensitivity and specificity were 0.83 (95% confidence interval [95%CI]: 0.77- 0.88) and 0.90 (95%CI: 0.77-0.96), respectively. Heterogeneity was moderate ($I^2 = 38.6\%$). SROC area under the curve was 0.89 (95%CI: 0.79-0.94). Positive and negative likelihood ratios were 8.582 and 0.193, respectively. A positive usCD163 test increased post-test probability by 25-100%.

Conclusions: usCD163 showed good accuracy as a diagnostic tool to detect active GN in AAV. However, studies had a considerable risk of bias, and cutoff values varied widely.

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Urinary soluble CD14 discriminates active disease from remission in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a relapsing autoimmune disease in which neutrophil and monocyte activation leads to kidney inflammation and damage. Early detection of renal relapse is critical for patient management, yet current tools rely on invasive biopsy or delayed clinical markers. Urinary biomarkers offer a promising, non-invasive alternative. Our group has established soluble CD163 (sCD163) as a urinary biomarker for renal involvement in AAV. Soluble CD14 (sCD14), a pattern recognition receptor shed during systemic inflammation, may provide complementary value. We hypothesised that including sCD14 could strengthen the predictive power of urinary biomarker panels.

Methods: Urinary sCD14 was measured by ELISA in 532 patients with granulomatosis with polyangiitis or microscopic polyangiitis, and in 12 age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HC) from the RITA-Ireland Vasculitis Biobank. Concentrations were normalised to urine creatinine and integrated with existing biomarker and clinical datasets. Mann–Whitney and Dunn’s multiple comparisons tests were used for group comparisons. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis assessed the ability of sCD14 to discriminate active disease from remission and to differentiate renal from non-renal involvement.

Results: Urinary sCD14 levels were elevated in active disease: median, (IQR), 115.4 (272.1-42.63) compared with remission 24.36 (74.09-6.72, $p < 0.0001$) and healthy controls 16.6 (92.06-2.96, $p < 0.001$). Urinary sCD14 discriminated active AAV from remission (non-normalised AUC = 0.76; normalised AUC = 0.72) but did not discriminate between patients with and without renal involvement in active disease (non-normalised AUC = 0.52; normalised AUC = 0.56).

Conclusions: We found elevated urinary sCD14 in patients with active AAV. The lack of discrimination between renal and non-renal vasculitis suggests sCD14 is filtered by, but not produced in, the kidney and thus likely does not reflect active glomerular inflammation.

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Changes in myeloperoxidase (MPO)-specific antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) levels before and after treatment and their association with Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS)

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Background/Aims: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA), especially myeloperoxidase autoantibodies (MPO-ANCA), are key serological markers for diagnosing and managing microscopic polyangiitis (MPA). Although their value in distinguishing active from inactive disease and predicting relapses is unclear, MPO-ANCA are commonly used for monitoring disease status. This study evaluated a chemiluminescence immunoassay (CIA) for detecting MPO-ANCA IgG to assess its role in disease monitoring.

Methods: Sera from Spanish patients diagnosed with MPA [n=57 unique patients with baseline (at time of diagnosis) and/or follow-up (post-treatment) samples], disease controls (n=100), and healthy individuals (HI, n=100) were tested on the QUANTA Flash MPO CIA (Inova Diagnostics, San Diego, USA; Intended use for diagnosis). Among the MPA group, only 41 patients with both baseline and follow-up specimens were available. The Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS >6 = active disease) and the interval between baseline and follow-up were recorded for all MPA patients at blood sampling.

Results: At diagnosis, MPO-ANCA were detected in 100.0% of MPA patients (41/41) and in none of the disease controls or healthy individuals. Among MPA patients with available paired results, notable differences were observed on MPO-ANCA levels between baseline and follow-up ($p=0.0101$). When comparing antibody levels between inactive vs. active disease, significant difference was also observed ($p=0.0479$). A modest but significant correlation was found between MPO-ANCA levels and BVAS (Spearman's $r_s=0.28$; $p=0.0056$). Moreover, when all available MPA datapoints were stratified by number of days after treatment (≤ 90 vs >90 days), MPO-ANCA levels were found to be significantly higher during the earlier period compared to the later period of treatment ($p=0.0243$).

Conclusions: In this cohort, MPO-ANCA IgG levels dropped significantly after treatment and were higher in active versus inactive disease. While promising for MPA monitoring, MPO-ANCA titres should be interpreted with caution. A prospective longitudinal study is needed to validate and expand its clinical use.

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Impact of avacopan on serum S100A8/A9 levels in MPA/GPA: evidence for a potential novel biomarker of neutrophil-mediated inflammation

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Background/Aims: S100A8/A9 (calprotectin), a heterodimeric complex of the intracellular calcium-binding proteins S100A8 and S100A9, is abundantly expressed in neutrophils and released extracellularly upon neutrophil extracellular trap (NET) formation. Recently, S100A8/A9 has been reported as an important marker for neutrophil-mediated inflammation in microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA). Avacopan, an oral C5a receptor inhibitor, is a novel therapeutic option enabling substantial glucocorticoid (GC) reduction while maintaining disease control. However, its effect on neutrophil-derived biomarkers remains poorly defined. We aimed to evaluate changes in serum S100A8/A9 before and after remission induction therapy with avacopan.

Methods: Serum S100A8/A9 levels were measured at baseline and 3 months after treatment in patients with MPA/GPA receiving avacopan, using an ELISA kit (CY-8107, MBL, Japan). Patients were categorized into three subgroups: GC with rituximab (RTX, n = 23), GC with cyclophosphamide or methotrexate (CY/MTX, n = 4), and avacopan add-on monotherapy (n = 4). Paired comparisons between baseline and month 3 were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Two-sided p-values < 0.05 were considered significant.

Results: Thirty-one patients were included. Median age was 74.0 years; 15 (48.4%) were female, and 23 (74.2%) had MPA. Median BVAS at baseline was 10.0 [6.0–16.0]. All patients showed clinical improvement, with 30 (96.8%) achieving BVAS = 0 at 3 months. Serum S100A8/A9 levels significantly decreased from 5605 [4659–8517] ng/mL at baseline to 3345 [2266–4848] ng/mL at 3 months (p < 0.001). Median reductions were –2317 [–327 to –4842] in the GC+RTX group, –2385 [–417 to –5037] in the GC+CY/MTX group, and –3622 [–454 to –5499] in the avacopan add-on group.

Conclusions: Serum S100A8/A9 decreased significantly after avacopan therapy across treatment subgroups. These findings suggest that S100A8/A9 may serve as a biomarker reflecting suppression of neutrophil-mediated inflammation by avacopan in MPA/GPA.

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Urinary complement biomarkers (C3a/Cr and C5a/Cr) as novel predictors of renal and patient outcomes in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) frequently causes rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis. Complement component C5a plays a central role in AAV pathogenesis, but longitudinal changes in urinary complement levels during induction therapy remain unclear. We aimed to investigate the association of urinary complement excretion with baseline pathology, disease activity, treatment response, and renal outcomes.

Methods: We retrospectively analysed 57 patients diagnosed with AAV between March 2019 and July 2025. Median age was 74 years, and median eGFR was 17.7 (IQR 8.3–29.9) mL/min/1.73m². MPO-ANCA was positive in 54 patients, including 13 also positive for PR3-ANCA. Renal biopsy was performed in 47 cases, and urine samples before and after induction therapy were available in 20 cases. Urinary C3a and C5a were measured by ELISA, normalized to urinary creatinine, and expressed as U-C3a/Cr and U-C5a/Cr. Groups were dichotomized by median values, and continuous variables were analysed using Cox proportional hazards regression. Skewed ratios were log-transformed. The primary endpoint was a composite of end-stage kidney disease requiring dialysis and all-cause mortality.

Results: Thirteen events occurred during a median follow-up of 540 days. Kaplan-Meier analysis stratified by median values showed significantly higher event rates in the high U-C3a/Cr (P=0.007) and U-C5a/Cr group (P=0.004). Cox analysis confirmed higher U-C3a/Cr (HR 2.44, 95%CI 1.52–4.11) and U-C5a/Cr (HR 1.79, 95%CI 1.22–2.65) were independently associated with poor outcomes. In biopsy cases, only high U-C5a/Cr group inversely correlated with the percentage of normal glomeruli, and positively with both cellular crescents and tubulointerstitial lesions, respectively. In paired-sample analysis, both U-C3a/Cr and U-C5a/Cr decreased after therapy, with reductions correlating with declines in MPO-ANCA (P=0.003, 0.001) and improvements in eGFR (P=0.021, 0.034) measured at 6 months.

Conclusion: Urinary complement, particularly U-C3a/Cr and U-C5a/Cr, reflects disease severity, predicts renal outcomes, and may serve as a non-invasive biomarker of treatment response in AAV.

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Low concentrations of anti-C5aR1 antibodies are associated with early ischemic events in giant cell arteritis (GCA)

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is associated with increased mortality and morbidity rates, underscoring the need to develop more effective glucocorticoid-sparing therapies. Recent studies showed overexpression of complement pathway compounds such as complement 5a and the corresponding receptor C5aR1 in an in vitro GCA artery model. In ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), low serum concentrations of apparently physiologically antagonistic anti-C5aR1 antibodies are associated with disease activity and relapse. Inhibition of C5aR1 with avacopan reduces the need for glucocorticoid and improves renal recovery. The present study aimed to analyse C5aR1 concentrations in GCA.

Methods: Serum concentrations of anti-C5aR1 and - as a control - anti-C3aR antibodies were determined in patients with GCA (n=30; [active disease n=18; patients in remission n=12] and healthy donors (n=225). Clinical data were assessed at the time of serum sampling and during follow-up over 42 months.

Results: In GCA, anti-C5aR1 antibody concentrations were decreased compared to healthy controls ($P < 0.0001$), contrasting with those of anti-C3aR antibodies. Specifically, GCA patients with an inflammatory response characterized by fever, weight loss, haemoglobin level < 11.0 g/L and erythrocyte sedimentation rate > 85 mm/h showed the lowest anti-C5aR1 concentrations ($P < 0.0001$). GCA patients with anti-C5aR1 antibody concentrations lower than 0.60 U/ml at baseline were at increased risk of early ischemic events ($P = 0.0328$; log-rank test and Mantel-Cox proportional hazards model).

Conclusions: Low concentrations of anti-C5aR1 antibodies are associated with an increased risk of early ischemic events in GCA. The potential of anti-C5aR1 antibodies as a biomarker and efficacy of C5aR1 inhibition as glucocorticoid-sparing therapy in GCA must be clarified by future studies.

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Serum calprotectin in paediatric inflammation: a cross-disease comparison

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Background/Aims: Calprotectin, a proinflammatory protein secreted mainly by neutrophils, is a sensitive marker of inflammation. While faecal calprotectin is established in gastrointestinal diagnostics, serum calprotectin is emerging as a biomarker for systemic inflammatory diseases. This study aimed to compare serum calprotectin levels in different paediatric inflammatory diseases and evaluate its role as a diagnostic and discriminative marker.

Methods: This prospective study included 185 children: 31 with systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis (sJIA), 62 with polyarticular juvenile idiopathic arthritis (pJIA), 18 with childhood-onset systemic lupus erythematosus (cSLE), 76 with IgA vasculitis (IgAV), 15 with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), 6 with IL-1-mediated autoinflammatory diseases (AID), and 20 healthy controls. Serum calprotectin was measured by turbidimetric assay. Group differences were assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Median serum calprotectin levels ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) were: sJIA 2.30 (0.50–110.61), pJIA 1.19 (0.30–19.27), cSLE 1.39 (0.31–6.29), IgAV 1.99 (0.46–21.76), IBD 1.62 (0.40–5.80), AID 1.26 (0.56–232.5), and controls 1.00 (0.57–1.43). Children with sJIA and IgAV had significantly higher levels than controls ($p < 0.01$); sJIA also differed from pJIA ($p = 0.004$). By disease activity, median levels were: sJIA active 9.47 vs. remission 1.08, pJIA active 2.50 vs. remission 1.03, cSLE active 3.77 vs. remission 1.21, and IgAV active 3.53 vs. remission 1.25 (all $p < 0.05$). Active phases in sJIA, pJIA, cSLE, and IgAV showed significantly higher calprotectin compared to remission. Active disease patients had elevated levels compared to controls, while remission patients had levels similar to controls.

Conclusion: Serum calprotectin effectively distinguishes active from remission phases in sJIA, pJIA, cSLE, and IgAV, supporting its utility as a diagnostic and monitoring biomarker in pediatric systemic inflammation. Further studies are warranted to validate its broader clinical application.

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The association of calprotectin with vascular injury and remodelling in clinically-isolated aortitis

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Background/Aims: Clinically-isolated aortitis (CIA), defined as inflammation of the aortic wall in the absence of systemic disease, is often discovered on surgical pathology after resection of an aortic aneurysm. The pathogenesis of CIA remains largely unknown. Neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) have been implicated in the pathophysiology of vasculitis and vascular injury. Calprotectin, a circulating marker of NET formation, is a promising biomarker in NET-driven diseases. This study aimed to investigate the role of calprotectin in CIA pathogenesis.

Methods: Plasma calprotectin and endothelial activation markers (ICAM-1, VCAM-1) were measured in CIA patients (n=28) along with healthy controls (n=34). In vitro, plasma-derived and recombinant calprotectin were tested on human aortic endothelial (HAOEC) and smooth muscle cells (HASMC) to assess activation, proliferation, migration, endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EndoMT), and calcification.

Results: Circulating calprotectin levels were significantly higher in CIA patients compared to controls.. Among 14 patients with longitudinal imaging, 3 had progression of aortic disease, 2 of whom had high calprotectin. Patients with CIA showed higher levels of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1. Calprotectin levels correlated with CRP ($r=0.63$, $p<0.001$). Mechanistic studies revealed that plasma from calprotectin-high CIA patients activated HAOECs, increasing surface expression of ICAM-1 ($p<0.01$) and VCAM-1 ($p<0.05$). Exposure to recombinant calprotectin upregulated expression of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 transcripts ($p < 0.05$ for both). Calprotectin exposure resulted in i) increased expression of mesenchymal markers consistent with the induction of EndoMT ii) promotion of endothelial cell proliferation and migration. In HASMCs, the addition of recombinant calprotectin increased intracellular calcium deposition, suggesting a role in promoting vascular stiffening.

Conclusions: Calprotectin is elevated in CIA patients and may contribute to disease pathogenesis by activating aortic endothelial cells, triggering proliferation, migration, and EndoMT, while driving microcalcification in smooth muscle cells. Our findings suggest a neutrophil-driven pathway of aortic injury in CIA, supporting further investigation of calprotectin as a potential biomarker and therapeutic target.

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Prognostic value of urine retinol binding protein in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Renal involvement in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) reflects disease severity and is defined by pauci-immune extracapillary glomerular lesions. Glomerular injury is usually accompanied by tubulointerstitial damage, a key determinant of renal prognosis. Standard urinary markers such as the protein-to-creatinine ratio or albuminuria do not specifically indicate tubular injury. Retinol-binding protein (RBP), normally reabsorbed by proximal tubules, appears in urine when tubular injury occurs. We assessed whether urinary RBP (uRBP) at diagnosis correlates with histological tubular injury and predicts renal outcome in AAV.

Methods: We retrospectively included adults with biopsy-proven AAV and available uRBP measurements between January 2014 and June 2024 at Tenon Hospital, Paris. Clinical data were prospectively recorded at kidney biopsy. Two blinded pathologists graded tubular injury using the Kudose score. The primary endpoint was end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), defined as long-term kidney replacement therapy or transplantation, censored for death.

Results: Ninety patients (median age 67 years) were included; 70.3 % had MPO-ANCA. At biopsy, the median uRBP/creatinine ratio was nine-fold above normal (<0.25 mg/mmol), with a median serum creatinine of 3.4 mg/dL. The uRBP/creatinine ratio correlated with the Kudose score ($r^2 = 0.12$). During a median 109-month follow-up, 14 patients (15.5 %) developed ESKD. In univariable logistic regression, each 1 mg/mmol increase in uRBP/creatinine was associated with higher odds of ESKD (OR = 1.18; 95 % CI 1.07–1.30; $p = 0.001$). Using a 1.68 mg/mmol cut-off, this association remained significant in multivariable analysis, independent of age and ANCA renal risk score.

Conclusions: Urinary RBP/creatinine at diagnosis correlates with tubular injury and independently predicts renal outcome in AAV. This simple biomarker may help assess the tubulointerstitial component and guide prognosis. Inclusion of a second centre is planned to strengthen statistical power and external validity. Because uRBP/creatinine is not specific to AAV, broader clinical applications are conceivable.

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Comparison of serum immunoglobulin levels in patients with large vessel arteritis

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Background/Aims: The pathological difference between giant cell arteritis (GCA) and Takayasu arteritis (TAK) has not been fully elucidated. We previously reported differences in inflammatory involvement in the vessel specimen (Kurata A et al. *Mod Rheumatology*, 2019), suggesting distinct immunological characteristics. In the present study, we evaluate differences in serum immunoglobulin isotypes in patients with GCA and TAK.

Methods: Patients aged over 18 years with GCA and TAK who presented with initial onset or disease flares at our hospital were included. Patient characteristics and laboratory data, including serum immunoglobulin levels, were analysed using statistical analyses.

Results: A total of 27 patients with GCA and 13 patients with TAK were included. The median (IQR) age was 72 (66--76) years in GCA and 28 (19--45) years in TAK. Among patients with GCA, 6 (22.2%) patients had polymyalgia rheumatica and 2 (7.4%) patients had rheumatoid arthritis and 1 (3.7%) patient had sarcoidosis, while 3 (23.1%) patients had ulcerative colitis and 1 (7.7%) patient had rheumatoid arthritis in TAK. Immunosuppressant use at enrolment was observed in 4 (14.8%) patients in GCA and 4 (30.8%) patients in TAK. The mean \pm SD white blood cell count (7454.1 ± 2049.9 / μ L vs. 8075.4 ± 1848.9 / μ L, $p=0.36$), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (84.6 ± 38.3 mm/ hr vs. 77.8 ± 43.0 , $p=0.63$), and serum C-reactive protein level (5.6 ± 4.3 mg/dL vs. 6.2 ± 4.4 mg/dL, $p=0.72$) were comparable between groups. The mean \pm SD serum IgG, IgA, and IgM levels were 1569.9 ± 355.2 mg/dL vs. 1685.2 ± 703.9 mg/dL ($p=0.49$), 297.7 ± 120.1 mg/dL vs. 338.8 ± 216.6 mg/dL ($p=0.45$) and 98.3 ± 47.9 mg/dL vs. 172.3 ± 84.0 mg/dL ($p=0.0014$) in GCA and TAK, respectively.

Conclusions: These findings suggest that differences in lymphocyte profiles between GCA and TAK may influence serum IgM levels.

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Elevated trimethylamine N-oxide levels are associated with vascular calcification and disease progression in patients with Takayasu arteritis

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Background/Aims: Trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO) is a gut microbial-dependent metabolite of dietary choline, phosphatidylcholine, and L-carnitine. Elevated TMAO levels have been associated with vascular calcification, chronic kidney disease, and the progression of several vascular diseases. However, the role of TMAO in Takayasu arteritis (TAK) remains unclear. This study aimed to assess the association between plasma TMAO levels and quantitative aortic calcification values as well as disease progression in patients with TAK.

Methods: We retrospectively enrolled 62 patients with TAK and 62 age- and sex-matched healthy volunteers. Plasma levels of choline and TMAO were measured using liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry. Whole body aortic calcification was quantified using the Agatston score, and follow-up CT imaging was performed.

Results: There was no significant difference in plasma choline levels between patients with TAK and healthy volunteers. However, TMAO levels were significantly higher in patients with TAK compared to healthy volunteers (197 [124–394] ng/mL vs. 124 [86–243], $p=0.024$). In patients with TAK, TMAO levels were significantly correlated with Agatston scores ($r=0.273$, $p=0.032$). Patients with TAK were divided into two groups based on the median TMAO level (200 ng/mL) for subgroup comparisons. The higher TMAO group ($n=31$) had higher Agatston scores (4095 [995–18206] vs. 1171 [98–9467] ng/mL; $p=0.041$), and a higher number of vascular lesions associated with TAK (70% vs. 32%; $p=0.002$) compared to the lower TMAO group ($n=31$). During the 12-month follow-up, progression in Agatston scores was significantly greater in the higher TMAO group than in the lower TMAO group (25% [15–92] vs. 2% [0–9], $p=0.024$). Similarly, the percent decline in eGFR was greater in the higher TMAO group than in the lower TMAO group (–13% [–23 to –1] vs. –2% [–9 to 5], $p=0.006$).

Conclusions: Elevated TMAO levels could be associated with vascular calcification and disease progression in patients with TAK.

P-313

Proteomic profiling identifies IL-6, CSF1, and TNFSF14 as markers of disease activity in treatment-naive giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is characterized by granulomatous inflammation and remodelling of large arteries. The diagnosis and monitoring of GCA rely on clinical assessment and inflammatory markers such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP). However, these markers lack disease specificity and may even be normal in patients with active GCA. Moreover, the current treatments target inflammation but not the remodelling. This study aimed to explore the immunological proteomic profile in the plasma of patients with treatment-naive GCA to identify molecular signatures linked to disease activity. These signatures could lay the groundwork for improved diagnostic tools and novel therapeutic targets.

Methods: Plasma samples from 37 treatment-naive GCA patients and 18 age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HCs) were analysed using Olink proximity extension assays of cytokines and immune surveillance markers, covering 89 proteins. Differential expression analysis was performed to compare the protein levels between GCA and HCs, and differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) were subjected to pathway enrichment analysis. Correlation analyses were conducted between protein levels and clinical parameters.

Results: Following quality control, 73 proteins remained for downstream analysis. Principal component analysis showed separation between the GCA and HC groups. 26 DEPs were upregulated in GCA compared to HCs, such as IL-6, CSF1, TNFSF14, and MMP12, while 8 DEPs were downregulated, including GZMB, FLT3LG, and TNFSF10. Pathway analysis revealed enrichment of cytokine–cytokine receptor interaction and cell chemotaxis in GCA. IL-6, CSF1, and TNFSF14 positively correlated with CRP and ESR, while CSF1 and EPO were inversely correlated with haemoglobin levels.

Conclusions: Treatment-naive GCA exhibits a distinct inflammatory proteomic profile compared to HC. TNFSF14 (LIGHT), a mediator involved in T cell co-stimulation and stromal remodelling, is of particular interest. Given its roles in both inflammation and remodelling, TNFSF14 warrants further investigation in GCA.

P-314

VAP2 and SDF-1a/CXCL12 are serum risk factors for coronary artery lesion (CAL) formation in Kawasaki disease patients

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Background/Aims: Kawasaki disease (KD) is characterized by acute systemic vasculitis, primarily affecting the coronary arteries. The most serious complications are coronary artery lesions (CAL), including coronary arterial dilatation, aneurysm, and stenosis, which develop in 25% of untreated patients. Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) treatment markedly reduces CAL incidence to 2.5%. However, the mechanism of IVIG's beneficial effect on KD is largely unknown. Recently, we identified a clone (VasSF) of recombinant single chain fragments of the variable region of human immunoglobulin G that significantly improved vasculitis symptoms in SCG/Kj mice (Koura et al, CEI 2024). VasSF binds VAP2 (24 kDa) which is an aberrant form of apolipoprotein A2 in serum of AAV (Suzuki J et al, MVR 2024). In the present study, we investigated whether VAP2 and related molecules could be associated with CAL formation in KD patients.

Methods: The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of 34 KD patients enrolled during acute and remote phases were investigated.

Results: The overall prevalence of initial IVIG non-responder was 11 (40.1%) and coronary artery lesions was 8 (29.6%). Western blotting showed VasSF binding to VAP2 and 17-kDa molecules in the sera of KD patients mainly during the acute phase. Interestingly, the CAL formation group showed a correlation only between VAP2 and SDF-1 ($R^2=0.5700$, $p=0.049$) in 78 cytokine analyses.

Conclusions: Association with VAP2 and SDF-1 α suggested in developing CAL in KD patients. Further studies are needed to evaluate whether VAP2 and SDF-1 α indeed plays an important role in the pathogenesis of KD.

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Profiling of novel autoantibodies for prediction of disease activity in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Autoantibodies are the hallmark of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) and used in the clinic for diagnosis and classification. The pathogenic role of these autoantibodies has previously been suggested, and autoantibodies are used as biomarkers for disease activity. As part of the Personalisation of Relapse risk in autoimmune DISEase (PARADISE) consortium, we aimed to investigate novel and known autoantibodies in AAV to be used as biomarkers for disease activity.

Methods: Plasma samples (n=1221) from 535 AAV patients and 66 healthy controls were collected from the RITA-Ireland Vasculitis Biobank. Samples were screened for autoantibodies using our in-house bead-array including 369 antigens corresponding to 272 proteins. Samples were analysed close to diagnosis (AAV vs HC) and longitudinally. Samples from AAV patients were further stratified into four post-diagnosis time categories (1, 3, 5-year, and all-time) and modelled against future relapse. Within each category, Lasso regression with repeated resampling was used to assess the relative importance of autoantibodies, quantified by their selection frequency across resamples.

Results: We identified novel autoantibodies with higher prevalence in the AAV group compared to healthy controls, including validation of autoantibodies discovered in our previous work. Of those classified as anti-MPO positive on clinical assay, we confirmed 98%, indicative of assay robustness. We did not observe an association between organ pattern and novel autoantibody profile. The Lasso-based resampling analysis highlighted a subset of antibodies consistently selected across multiple time categories, suggesting their potential as stable biomarkers. Finally, the autoantibody profile of samples from AAV patients at active disease versus remission also revealed a preliminary association of specific autoantibodies.

Conclusions: This study identified several novel autoantibodies and their possible association with disease activity.

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Torque Teno virus viraemia in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Torque Teno Virus (TTV) is a widely prevalent, non-pathogenic virus whose replication is strongly influenced by host immune status. TTV has been proposed as a potential biomarker of immune function. In ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) where relapse risk and immunosuppression are difficult to monitor, TTV may provide a useful indicator of disease activity and treatment response.

Methods: We analysed TTV viremia in 326 serial samples from two independent cohorts: RITA-Ireland vasculitis biobank (RIV) (n=175: 55 at diagnosis, 116 in remission, 4 at relapse, and 64 healthy controls) and IDIBELL, Barcelona (n=151: 21 at diagnosis, 100 in remission, and 30 healthy controls). TTV viral load (log₁₀ copies/ml) was assessed across disease stages and correlated with clinical and serological variables.

Results: In both cohorts, TTV viremia was detectable across all disease stages, with peak levels observed at 6–12 months (RIV) and 3–9 months (IDIBELL) after diagnosis. Higher TTV viremia was associated with lower lymphocyte counts and reduced IgG levels (RIV cohort). In IDIBELL, TTV correlated inversely with CRP (r=-0.48, p=0.045) and with time since last disease activity (r=-0.327, p<0.001). Elevated TTV levels at 6–12 months post-diagnosis in the RIV cohort were linked to an increased probability of relapse beyond 24 months. No significant associations were found between TTV levels and baseline renal function or most clinical phenotypes.

Conclusions: TTV viremia reflects immune status in AAV, with dynamic changes according to time from diagnosis. Higher levels during early remission appear to identify patients at increased risk of relapse. These findings support TTV as a potential biomarker of immune monitoring in AAV. Further studies are warranted to assess its relationship with immunosuppressive therapy and relapse prediction.

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Blood cell signatures of disease activity in ANCA-associated vasculitis using automated hematologic profiling analysis with Sysmex XN-9000®: preliminary results from a monocentric cohort

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Background/Aims: To determine whether routine hematologic parameters and Cell Population Data (CPD) differentiate active from remitted GPA/MPA, and to explore subclinical activity during remission.

Methods: We retrospectively and prospectively collected blood samples from adult GPA/MPA patients at a single centre (January 2022-January 2024) and healthy control (HC). ANCA-negative patients and those with conditions affecting neutrophils maturation (certain medications, ongoing infection, malignancy, other autoimmune diseases, organ transplantation, dialysis or plasmapheresis) were excluded. Patients were classified as active or inactive (BVASv3=0). Samples were analysed on Sysmex XN-9000®, for complete blood count, CPD, and extended inflammatory parameters, including immature granulocytes (IG).

Results: Ninety-six samples were collected: 24 in active/relapsing patients (19 GPA; 5 MPA), 72 from remission patients (58 GPA; 14 MPA), plus 333 HCs samples. Among remission patients, 44.3% were on rituximab, 6.9% on azathioprine, and 48.6% in treatment-free remission (TFR). Active patients showed higher neutrophil counts/percentage (NE, NE%), IG and IG% than both HC and remitted patients (all $p < 0.0001$). Compared with active disease, remitted patients had lower NE, NE %, IG and IG % (all $p \leq 0.0001$), neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR, $p = 0.037$), platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR, $p = 0.002$) and monocyte-to-lymphocyte ratio (MLR, $p = 0.004$), but higher platelet counts/parameters ($p < 0.0001$), and monocyte structural parameters ($p < 0.0001$). Differences in NE and IG were also seen between HC and remission patients. TFR patients had higher NE, IG ($p < 0.0001$ and $p < 0.011$), NLR, MLR and PLR ($p < 0.0001$, $p = 0.001$, $p = 0.007$), than HC. In remission, NE counts or structural parameters did not vary by age, ANCA status at sampling, relapse history, remission duration, follow-up length or treatment (RTX or AZA).

Conclusions: Elevated NE, IG, and inflammatory ratios effectively discriminate active from remitted AAV and reveal residual subclinical immune activation during prolonged remission, supporting the utility of automated hematologic profiling for disease monitoring.

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Systemic and local immune profiling in ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Relapse in AAV is driven by autoreactivity in the adaptive immune system, resulting in a relapsing phenotype, but the specific cellular correlates of this are not clear. We aimed to define immune cell biomarkers that integrate both local and systemic immune repertoires in patients who relapse and those who do not.

Methods: Urine and PBMCs were sampled from patients recruited to the RITA Ireland Vasculitis Biobank. Immune cells were isolated from urine to act as a proxy for the local kidney environment. PBMCs were analysed by spectral cytometry and T cell function by intracellular cytokine staining and cytokine release assays. Models were built that explored the relationship between these readouts and relapse propensity.

Results: In 82 patients with AAV, a significantly higher number of urinary immune cells (T cells, monocytes, neutrophils) than age-matched healthy controls (n = 39). However, this was independent of current or previous kidney involvement, and prior cyclophosphamide exposure. There was no clear association with subsequent renal relapse. We also found that patients with AAV in remission produced less IFN- γ , TNF- α and IL-17 in response to combined anti-CD3/anti-CD28 stimulation than healthy controls, which was correlated with subsequent relapse propensity.

Conclusions: Our data from local immune profiling of the urinary tract indicate that, despite being in clinical remission, AAV patients have elevated urinary immune cells, even in those without known renal vasculitis. This possibly suggests the presence of a persisting subclinical immune response at some point in the urinary tract. Our preliminary findings from the systemic profiling suggest that T cells from AAV patients in remission are functionally compromised in their effector cytokine production. Future work will determine if this is reflected in the expression of exhaustion markers in these patients.

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Impact of treatment with upadacitinib on biomarkers identified by proteomics in giant cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: The impact of upadacitinib (UPA), a Janus Kinase inhibitor, on immune mediators driving giant cell arteritis (GCA) pathogenesis was assessed in the SELECT-GCA study, focusing on the IL-6 and IFN γ pathway proteins.

Methods: Plasma samples were collected from consenting patients treated with UPA 15 mg with glucocorticoids tapered over 26 weeks and placebo (PBO) tapered GC over 52 weeks at baseline and weeks 2, 12, 24, and 52. A multiplexed assay was used to quantify 45 protein biomarkers, and a mixed model for repeated measures was used to compare biomarkers between UPA and PBO-treated patients and treatment responders/non-responders. The least-square mean biomarkers between UPA and PBO were contrasted, and significant pharmacodynamic markers had a false discovery rate (FDR) ≤ 0.05 .

Results: UPA significantly reduced IL-6 levels compared to PBO, and this reduction was more pronounced in responders versus non-responders. Circulating IFN γ increased with UPA; however, IFN γ -modulated chemokines CXCL9, CXCL10, and CXCL11 decreased significantly with UPA and tended to increase with PBO. UPA reduced IL-18, amplifying the effect of IFN γ on CXCL9, CXCL10, and CXCL11. However, no difference was seen comparing responders and non-responders. CCL7 was reduced with UPA versus PBO; however, the difference between responders and non-responders was not significant by FDR. PBO showed progressive increases in IL-6, CCL7, CXCL9, and CXCL10, with no apparent reduction below baseline levels for CXCL11 and IL-18.

Conclusions: UPA treatment inhibited IL-6 and downstream proteins of IFN γ (CXCL9, CXCL10, CXCL11, IL-18), indicative of a decrease in T-helper 1 cytokines. The molecular effect was observed by week 2, suggesting rapid onset of action. Investigation into the impact of UPA on other modulated biomarkers is warranted. Results suggest that the efficacy of UPA for GCA is related to modulation of IL-6, IFN γ pathway proteins, and CCL7.

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Biomarkers of innate immune activation to identify non-response to rituximab in granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Innate immune activation contributes to vascular inflammation in granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) through neutrophil extracellular traps, immune complexation (IC), and endothelial injury. Its role in response to rituximab (RTX) remains unclear. This study evaluated changes in innate immune markers before and after RTX and assess their ability to predict remission and treatment response.

Methods: Ten plasma biomarkers reflecting neutrophil and platelet activation, endothelial injury, and IC were measured pre- and 6–12 months post-RTX. Biomarkers were log-transformed or dichotomized when skewed. Longitudinal changes were analysed with mixed-effects models. Non-response was defined as <50% reduction in the BVAS/WG; non-remission as BVAS/WG >0. ROC curves and Youden index thresholds were used to derive cutoffs. A simple additive score (0–4 positive biomarkers) and a weighted logistic regression score were tested; performance was compared using AUCs and DeLong's test.

Results: Forty patients with GPA were included (median age 53 [IQR 38–65], 58% female, 90% White). Thirty-four (85%) were PR3-ANCA+, three (7.5%) MPO-ANCA+, and three (7.5%) missing. Median BVAS/WG decreased from 3.0 pre-RTX to 0.0 post-RTX. Ten patients (25%) did not achieve remission and nine (23%) failed to respond. Post-RTX, CitH3-DNA, IC, and NE-DNA decreased significantly, while VCAM increased. Baseline biomarkers did not predict outcomes. A combined score of four biomarkers (CitH3-DNA, VCAM, IC, NE-DNA) best identified non-responders, with AUCs from 0.77 (non-remission) to 0.65 (non-response). For lack of remission, sensitivity was 0.93, specificity 0.60, PPV 0.88, and NPV 0.75; for lack of response, sensitivity 0.97, specificity 0.33, PPV 0.83, and NPV 0.75. Weighted scores did not outperform the simple additive score.

Conclusion: A simple additive biomarker score of innate immune activation identifies GPA patients at risk of poor outcomes after RTX. This approach may enable stratification of non-responders prior to B-cell-depleting therapy, but requires external validation before clinical application.

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Untargeted metabolomics reveals potential biomarkers in ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis

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Background/Aims: The precise mechanisms underlying anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated glomerulonephritis (AAGN) remain unclear, and reliable biomarkers for evaluating disease activity and treatment response are lacking. This study aimed to identify valuable biomarkers and explore the metabolic alterations associated with AAGN using untargeted metabolomics.

Methods: This prospective cohort study was conducted in two phases: discovery and validation phases. Urine and plasma samples were collected from 92 AAGN patients, 60 patients with lupus nephritis (LN), 30 with IgA nephropathy (IgAN), 30 with minimal change disease (MCD), and 60 healthy controls (HC). Samples were analysed using ultraperformance liquid chromatography (UPLC) and tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS). Multivariate analysis was performed using orthogonal partial least squares discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA), and differential metabolites were selected based on variable importance in projection ($VIP \geq 1$), $P < 0.05$, and fold change ($FC \geq 1.5$ or $FC \leq 0.67$). Metabolites were further annotated using the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) database to identify key pathways.

Results: All metabolites in urine and plasma samples including hydrophilic compounds and hydrophobic compounds were identified. A total of 44 plasma and 23 urine metabolites were consistently altered in AAGN patients compared to all control groups (HC, LN, IgAN, and MCD). Both L-citrulline and homovanillic acid sulfate (sodium salt) were significantly elevated in plasma and urine samples from AAGN patients. KEGG analysis identified phenylalanine metabolism as a key pathway associated with AAGN. Additionally, seven plasma and sixteen urine metabolites were identified as potential biomarkers of disease activity, while thirty-three plasma and nine urine metabolites may serve as candidate predictors of treatment response.

Conclusions: AAGN patients exhibit specific plasma and urinary metabolic profiles. Phenylalanine metabolism may play an important role in AAGN pathogenesis. Several metabolites identified in this study show promise as non-invasive biomarkers for assessing disease activity and predicting treatment response.

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Distinct transcriptomic signatures differentiate small-vessel inflammation in normal temporal arteries between ANCA-associated vasculitis and giant-cell arteritis

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Background/Aims: Temporal artery biopsy (TAB) is the procedure with the highest specificity for the diagnosis of giant cell arteritis (GCA). Occasionally, the TAB shows small vessel vasculitis (SVV) surrounding a normal temporal artery as the only pathological finding. Ultimate diagnosis remains uncertain. This study aimed to identify differentially expressed genes in TAB with SVV from patients with GCA and other systemic vasculitis including ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV).

Methods: 51 patients with TAB showing SVV were subjected to a pre-established diagnostic algorithm. The algorithm led to the following classification: 19 GCA; 20 systemic vasculitis; and 12 could not be classified. TAB samples from 16 SVV patients (8 classified as GCA[SVV-GCA] and 8 systemic vasculitis [SVV-SV]: 4 AAV and 3 other vasculitis) and 16 controls with negative temporal artery biopsies, were used for RNA isolation and microarray hybridization. Data processing and differential expression profiling ($p < 0.001$), unsupervised hierarchical clustering and principal component analysis (PCA) were implemented.

Results: We compared gene expression in normal temporal arteries and the different subgroups of SVV. The expression level of 313 genes was found to be significantly different between normal arteries and SVV-GCA, whereas the expression level of 544 genes was significantly different between normal arteries and SVV-SV. Unsupervised hierarchical clustering of these groups, resulting in their classification into different clusters, each corresponding to their respective phenotype. An additional clustering was performed comparing SVV-GCA and SVV-SV, distinguishing them into two different clusters. Sub-analysis between SVV-GCA vs SVV-AAV, and SVV-GCA vs SVV-other vasculitis showed significant differences in expression level of 15 and 30 genes, respectively.

Conclusions: SVV surrounding a spared TA is an equivocal finding. After a detailed diagnostic work-up most patients can be diagnosed with GCA, AAV or other systemic vasculitis although diagnosis remains uncertain in some cases. Cluster analysis of the gene expression profile differentiates diagnostic subgroups of SVV.

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Patterns of skin lesion transcriptomics in different forms of vasculitis

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Background/Aims: Classification of different vasculitides relies heavily on clinical patterns of disease without incorporating biologic data about associated immune dysregulation. This study examined the biologic relationship between transcriptomic profiling of skin lesions and clinical diagnosis across different vasculitides.

Methods: Patients with vasculitic skin lesions of different morphologies were recruited into a multi-centre prospective observational cohort. RNA was extracted from 4-6mm punch biopsies of affected skin using the TRIzol™ method, followed by library preparation (NEBNext Ultra II RNA kit, New England Biolabs) and bulk sequencing (Nextseq 2000/NovaseqXPlus (Illumina)). Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to visualize the dataset. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were studied in association with diagnosis. Interferon-alpha and -gamma signatures were generated using MSigDB Human Pathway Gene-sets.

Results: The analysis included 67 patients with isolated cutaneous small-vessel vasculitis (CSVV) (n=15), IgA vasculitis (IgAV) (n=17), VEXAS (Vacuoles, E1-enzyme, X-linked, Autoinflammatory, Somatic) syndrome (n=10), ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) (n=9), eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) (n=6), polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) (n=6), or urticarial vasculitis (UV) (n=4). PCA showed i) VEXAS samples clustering independently and ii) no clear clustering by skin lesion morphology. Only VEXAS and EGPA had a substantial number of significant and high-fold change DEGs relative to the other vasculitides. Gene ontology analysis revealed significant upregulation of cytokine signaling / innate immune activation in EGPA and interferon response in VEXAS. Across the whole cohort, increased interferon response scores were associated with ear, nose, and throat (p=0.06) or cardiac (p=0.08) involvement. VEXAS, EGPA, and PAN had elevated interferon signature scores. Correlation between interferon-alpha and -gamma scores (R = 0.96, p<2.2e-16) revealed diseases with stronger interferon-alpha (VEXAS) or interferon-gamma (EGPA) signatures.

Conclusions: Analysis of tissue-level transcriptomics across systemic vasculitides reveals shared and divergent pathophysiology, particularly related to interferon signalling. Incorporation of biological data into clinical assessment may aid precision-medicine approaches in vasculitis.

Case Reports and Case Series (presented as posters)

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C-001

Renal to cardiac involvement: a challenging case of ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background: Cardiac involvement in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is rare, and cardiac complications remain under-recognized. Myocarditis is challenging to diagnose due to non-specific symptoms. Cardiac MRI provides a sensitive, non-invasive method for early detection.

Case Presentation: We report a case of 45-year-old male with PR3-ANCA GPA, diagnosed in 2007 with ENT disease and retrobulbar granuloma. Initial treatment included cyclophosphamide (CyP) followed by azathioprine alongside long-term glucocorticoids (GC). Rituximab (RTx) was administered for relapsing ENT disease and cranial nerve palsies in 2012 and 2014, complicated by severe hypogammaglobulinemia.

In April 2020, he presented with dyspnoea and severe AKI (creatinine 472 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; baseline 62 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), haematoproteinuria (urine PCR 284 mg/mmol) and rise in PR3-ANCA from undetectable to 3.2 AI/L. Re-induction with high-dose GC, CyP, RTx and plasma exchange improved kidney function. He underwent cardiac MRI in August 2020 for non-specific chest pain and elevated Troponin T (37 ng/L), revealing myocardial oedema in the inferolateral and basal walls. Treatment was escalated to intravenous immunoglobulin alongside further RTx. Repeat Cardiac MRI in 2021 showed resolution of myocardial oedema but low-grade uptake in the inferolateral wall with adjacent fibrosis. Troponin T remained elevated (25-30 ng/L) despite normalization of kidney function (creatinine 72 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), though chest pain gradually resolved over 12 months.

A kidney biopsy in 2024, prompted by persistent proteinuria, revealed segmental and global glomerulosclerosis without active inflammation. Cardiac MRI in 2025 showed only myocardial scarring. He remains on six-monthly rituximab, weekly IVIG (30 g), and cardiovascular protection including ACE/SGLT2 inhibitors.

Conclusions: This case highlights the challenge in managing relapsing AAV with myocardial involvement. Delayed cardiac symptoms suggest possible treatment resistance and delayed myocardial response to aggressive therapy. The severe kidney manifestation masked cardiac symptoms and standard diagnostics. Early incorporation of cardiac MRI into diagnostic pathways for high-risk patients may facilitate earlier detection and improved outcomes.

C-003

There's no magic, it's all in the gums – a case report on strawberry gingivitis

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Background: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a rare, granulomatous, necrotizing, small vessel vasculitis that predominantly affects the upper, lower respiratory tract and kidneys. It is associated with anti-neutrophilic cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) in around 95% of patients. Oral lesions are present in 6-13% patients with GPA, however, only 2% patients present with oral cavity lesions as the first sign of the disease, making it a rare presentation.

Case presentation: We present a 56-year-old woman with a background of coeliac disease, asthma, and psoriasis. Since 2020, she was under investigation for recurrent otitis media, chronic sinusitis, hearing loss, gingival inflammation, intermittent dysphagia, and oral ulcers. Her symptoms significantly improved with short courses of steroids, only to recur on stopping steroids. Her investigations revealed normal full blood count, ESR, CRP, hepatitis screen, and negative immunology (including ANCA). A barium swallow study indicated mild oesophageal dysmotility. CT chest showed mild bronchial wall thickening in the lower lobes, consistent with inflammatory changes. CT sinuses and MRI neck revealed bilateral patchy opacification of the ethmoid air cells, right-sided internal mastoiditis, and bilateral mastoid effusions. When reviewed in rheumatology clinic, oral examination revealed characteristic “strawberry gingivitis”. A PET-CT showed increased uptake in the mouth, parotid and submandibular glands, esophagitis, and airway chondritis. Gingival biopsy demonstrated severely inflamed gingival tissue with erosions, but no evidence of dysplasia or malignancy. A diagnosis GPA was made and she was treated with steroids and Mycophenolate Mofetil.

Conclusions: Although oral lesions are not part of the classification criteria for GPA, strawberry gingivitis is a rare, but pathognomic oral manifestation of GPA. If present, it is often seen at initial presentation, and may precede other organ involvement, thus aiding early diagnosis. A negative ANCA may occur in 5% of GPA patients, and tissue biopsy should be sought on suspicion of diagnosis.

C-004

At the crossroads of infection and vasculitis: a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge

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Case Presentation: A 30 year old woman with bilateral hearing loss, seropurulent ear discharge, tinnitus and vertigo, was diagnosed as chronic suppurative otitis media and received multiple courses of antibiotics, with partial response. Subsequently she developed multiple cranial nerve palsies in the form of facial deviation to left, difficulty in moving tongue, difficulty with speech and swallowing. She also had polyarthrititis, nasal blockage and nasal crusting. Anti-neutrophilic cytoplasmic antibodies were negative. Imaging revealed bilateral otomastoiditis, sinusitis and extensive skull base inflammation. Nasal biopsy showed broad aseptate hyphae suggestive of mucormycosis. She was treated with liposomal amphotericin B followed by posaconazole.

Six months later, she developed epistaxis, haemoptysis and shortness of breath. On evaluation, there was haemoglobin drop, elevated serum creatinine, proteinuria, microscopic haematuria and cross-sectional imaging of chest revealed diffuse alveolar haemorrhage. Anti-proteinase3 antibodies were strongly positive. She was diagnosed as granulomatosis with polyangiitis and treated with four sessions of plasma exchange, intravenous methyl prednisolone pulse followed by oral steroids, and cyclophosphamide.

However, two months later, she developed profuse bleeding into oral and nasal cavities, requiring multiple blood transfusions. Source of bleed was obscure despite nasal and upper gastrointestinal endoscopies and bronchoscopy. MR angiogram of base of skull revealed a pseudoaneurysm in left internal carotid artery, stent was deployed in the pseudoaneurysm by digital subtraction angiography. Simultaneously, she had a relapse of the vasculitis with diffuse alveolar haemorrhage and worsening hearing impairment, and was treated with increasing dose of steroids.

She received nine doses of cyclophosphamide and was on rituximab maintenance. Her renal function and cranial nerve palsies improved, with mild residual disability. However, she had a relapsing disease, with multiple minor relapses and recurrence of diffuse alveolar haemorrhage, so maintenance treatment was increased to rituximab 1g 4 monthly.

Conclusions: This case highlights that mucormycosis can mimic GPA and rarely co-occur with GPA.

C-005

Haemorrhagic bullae: a rare cutaneous manifestation of PR3-positive ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background: Cutaneous manifestations occur in approximately 35% of patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV), presenting most commonly as palpable purpura, and may represent the earliest sign, relapse, or the sole clue in ANCA-negative or limited disease. Haemorrhagic bullae are rare, often signifying severe or multisystem involvement. We report a PR3-positive AAV case presenting with initial presentation of haemorrhagic bullae, with sinonasal, renal, and ocular systemic involvement.

Methods: A 36-year-old woman with seropositive rheumatoid arthritis presented with a 10-day history of haemorrhagic bullae, progressing from both feet proximally to the sacrum and hands, associated with polyarthralgia, intermittent epistaxis, and recent episcleritis. Past history included lower-limb rash of uncertain aetiology requiring rituximab and recent ectopic pregnancy. Dermatological exam revealed multiple tense haemorrhagic bullae across bilateral lower legs extending to the sacrum with bilateral lower limb oedema. Systemic examination was otherwise normal, with no pulmonary or gastrointestinal features.

Results: Investigations showed leukocytosis ($12.2 \times 10^9/L$), neutrophilia ($8.9 \times 10^9/L$), eosinophilia ($0.7 \times 10^9/L$), CRP 76 mg/L, ESR 70 mm/hr, with normal renal function. PR3-ANCA was strongly positive (>194 IU), with positive rheumatoid serology (anti-CCP 46 U/mL, RF 120 IU). ANA, ENA, anti-dsDNA, anti-GBM, C3/C4 and MPO-ANCA were normal. Urinalysis revealed haemoproteinuria (RBC 678/ μ L, ACR 87.6 mg/mmol, PCR 173 mg/mmol). Renal biopsy showed pauci-immune necrotizing glomerulonephritis (7/10 glomeruli, one crescent). Skin biopsy showed non-specific urticarial reaction with negative direct immunofluorescence. Differentials included bullous vasculitis, drug-induced, infectious and immunobullous disorders. Oral prednisolone 50mg, acyclovir, and topical mometasone furoate were commenced. With PR3 positive AAV diagnosis, prednisolone was escalated to 75mg with rituximab infusions organised. Multidisciplinary input guided management, with sustained improvement at discharge and follow-up.

Conclusions: Haemorrhagic bullae are a rare but significant cutaneous manifestation of AAV and should prompt urgent systemic evaluation. Negative skin biopsy does not exclude AAV; early multidisciplinary input and timely diagnosis are key to favourable outcomes.

C-006

From red eye to red flag: severe relapse of granulomatosis with polyangiitis after scleritis

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Case Presentation: A 46-year-old male was diagnosed with PR3 positive granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) after presenting with bilateral scleritis in March 2022. He had positive PR3 antibodies, with pulmonary nodules and mild haematuria and proteinuria without reduction in serum creatinine at diagnosis. He received induction therapy with high dose prednisolone, then was commenced on methotrexate and then switched to mycophenolate as a steroid sparing agent. He continued mycophenolate with low dose prednisolone and remained in remission. He was slowly weaned off prednisolone in December 2024.

In February 2025, he presented with active arthritis and tenosynovitis and resumed prednisolone at 15mg daily. After progression in symptoms in March 2025 with persistent myalgia and arthralgias with elevated C-reactive protein of 40 but without imaging features of inflammatory arthritis, prednisolone was increased to 25mg daily and he was commenced on avacopan. Despite resumption of prednisolone, he presented with a left thalamic ischaemic stroke secondary to vasculitis in April 2025 and received pulse methylprednisolone and rituximab 1000mg. This progressed to a severe flare of GPA with pulmonary haemorrhage, new renal impairment and left eye episcleritis and he received further pulse methylprednisolone, second dose rituximab and six cycles of cyclophosphamide with clinical and biochemical remission. Mycophenolate was ceased and he remains on a slow prednisolone taper and avacopan with plan for maintenance six monthly rituximab infusions.

Conclusion: Patients with less severe disease at diagnosis are still at risk of organ-threatening complications from relapse of granulomatosis with polyangiitis. This case study highlights key management issues including treatment of severe relapse with pulmonary haemorrhage in this context, management of thrombotic events and the role of avacopan.

C-007

An unusual CATch: A case of ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Case Presentation: A 67-year-old gentleman with history of renal cell carcinoma, right radical nephrectomy developed acute kidney injury. A kidney biopsy done elsewhere showed focal necrotizing and crescentic glomerulonephritis with immune complex deposition (IgG, C3, kappa, lambda) with 10% crescents. He was diagnosed with post-infectious glomerulonephritis and treated with glucocorticoids (GC).

He presented to our institution with worsening renal function, progression to dialysis, congestive heart failure, rashes, sinus symptoms. Testing showed a strongly positive p-ANCA and PR3, elevated rheumatoid factor (RF), normal C3, C4, negative CTD serologies, anti-GBM antibodies, cryocrit. Sinus imaging showed moderate mucosal thickening of bilateral anterior ethmoid and maxillary sinuses. Chest CT showed bilateral lower lobe consolidations suggestive of pulmonary oedema and superimposed aspiration pneumonia. He was diagnosed with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) and started on GC and rituximab. Subsequently, he developed acute aortic insufficiency requiring transcatheter aortic valvular replacement, and cardiomyopathy. He reported having multiple cats. Testing for *Bartonella quintana* was positive by both serology and serum cell free DNA by next generation sequencing. Diagnosis was revised to AAV secondary to *Bartonella* infection. He was started on doxycycline and GC were tapered. Several months later, his cardiac function improved, and his renal function is recovering with decreased dialysis needs.

Conclusions: In a series of 24 cases of *Bartonella* infective endocarditis by Beydon and colleagues, 83% were diagnosed with AAV with PR3 ANCA positivity in 75%, RF in 85% and hypocomplementemia in 82%. Immune complexes were noted on renal biopsy in 76%. While *Bartonella henselae* is more commonly associated with infections from cats, *Bartonella quintana* has also been associated with cat bites.

Renal biopsy is an important tool to confirm the diagnosis and evaluate for potential mimics. Atypical features of AAV such as immune complex deposition on renal biopsy and hypocomplementemia should prompt evaluation for alternate aetiologies.

C-008

Wunderlich syndrome accompanied by multiple aneurysms as the initial manifestation of microscopic polyangiitis

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Background: Wunderlich syndrome is characterized by spontaneous, non-traumatic renal haemorrhage confined to the subcapsular and perirenal spaces, often presenting with acute abdominal pain. Although rare, it represents a potentially life-threatening emergency. The most common causes are renal tumours, particularly angiomyolipomas and renal cell carcinomas, followed by vascular diseases such as systemic vasculitides, including polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) and, less frequently, microscopic polyangiitis (MPA).

Case Presentation: A 68-year-old woman with a medical history of chronic migraine and community-acquired pneumonia presented with a 4-kilogram weight loss, subjective fever, abdominal and lumbar pain, oliguria, Raynaud phenomenon, livedo reticularis, and lower limb paraesthesias. Laboratory tests showed severe anaemia (haemoglobin 3.2 g/dL) requiring transfusion, leukocytosis with neutrophilia, elevated C-reactive protein (11.7 mg/dL), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (69 mm/h), and normocomplementaemic acute kidney injury requiring dialysis. Contrast-enhanced CT revealed the presence of large bilateral subcapsular renal hematomas, which were compressing the parenchyma and proximal ureters, along with multiple medium-calibre vessel aneurysms in the thorax and abdomen (internal mammary arteries, intercostal arteries, right gastric artery, branches of the superior mesenteric artery, inferior mesenteric artery, and bilateral renal arteries). Meanwhile, MR angiography revealed right vertebral artery stenosis (V1–V2). Infectious and malignant aetiologies were excluded. Initially, PAN was suspected; however, the presence of anti-MPO antibodies (78.5 U/mL) supported the diagnosis of MPA. The patient was treated with intravenous methylprednisolone pulses followed by cyclophosphamide, which allowed dialysis withdrawal. Despite this, she developed multiple infectious complications during hospitalization, ultimately leading to death.

Conclusions: Although MPA is classically considered a small-vessel vasculitis, it may also involve medium-sized vessels and manifest as spontaneous renal haemorrhage, thereby mimicking PAN. This case underscores the importance of careful diagnostic differentiation between these entities given their distinct prognostic and therapeutic implications, and highlights that infectious complications remain a major cause of mortality in patients under immunosuppression.

C-009

Pancreatic inflammatory mass as an unusual manifestation of granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a necrotizing ANCA-associated vasculitis that typically affects the respiratory tract and kidneys. Pancreatic involvement is extremely rare. We present a patient with GPA who developed otologic, pulmonary, and pancreatic manifestations, highlighting the diagnostic complexity and therapeutic response.

Case Presentation: A 47-year-old obese male presented with progressive bilateral hearing loss and recurrent otitis media. Corticosteroids demonstrated some effectiveness, but the patient experienced clinical deterioration, with multiple cranial neuropathies (cranial nerves VII and VIII) and a cavitated solitary pulmonary nodule. Subsequently, he developed abdominal pain, prompting abdominal MRI, which revealed a 55 mm heterogeneous lesion in the pancreatic tail, poorly circumscribed, partially infiltrating the splenic hilum, and associated with a 3 cm focal splenic infarction, without ductal dilatation.

Laboratory studies showed strong positivity for PR3-ANCA (92.5). Otologic biopsy revealed extensive necrosis with severe acute inflammatory infiltrate and microabscesses, but no granulomas, dysplasia, or malignancy. A pancreatic biopsy revealed haemorrhagic tissue with pancreatic parenchyma largely replaced by dense neutrophilic infiltrates forming microabscesses, ductal repair changes, and fibrohyalinized stroma. No granulomas, dysplasia, malignancy, or IgG4-related disease were observed. Special stains were negative for microorganisms.

The patient received intravenous methylprednisolone pulses (500 mg for 3 days), cyclophosphamide (1 g IV), and oral prednisone (50 mg/day). Clinical improvement ensued with resolution of abdominal pain and partial recovery of hearing.

Conclusions: Pancreatic involvement in GPA is rare, with fewer than 60 cases reported worldwide. Our case contributes to the growing recognition of this unusual manifestation, which has been proposed as a subtype of autoimmune pancreatitis (type 4). It is crucial to be aware of this condition in order to differentiate it from other serious illnesses such as pancreatic cancer, tuberculosis, or IgG4-related disease. This will help to prevent unnecessary surgical procedures.

C-010

ANCA-associated vasculitis with pulmonary involvement and gross haematuria secondary to silica exposure: a report of two cases

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Background: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) has been linked to several environmental factors. Of particular interest is occupational exposure to silica, as this can cause lung and kidney disease independently and, in some cases, contribute to the development of secondary AAV.

Methods: Case series.

Results: We present two cases of underground gold miners with chronic exposure to silica who developed AAV with renal and pulmonary involvement. The first was a 41-year-old male who consulted for low back pain, weight loss, lower limb oedema, dyspnoea, foamy urine and gross haematuria. His proteinuria was 8.3 g/day, and his anti-MPO was 98.9 U/mL. The kidney biopsy revealed pauci-immune extracapillary glomerulonephritis. High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) revealed multiple centrilobular nodules, and transbronchial biopsies confirmed the presence of pneumoconiosis. He was diagnosed with anti-MPO (+) AAV with pulmonary silicosis and high suspicion of silica nephropathy. He received high-dose methylprednisolone, rituximab, and prednisolone. Subsequent follow-up without changes on the HRCT. The second case was a 54-year-old male with microscopic polyangiitis, with an anti-MPO level of 74.4 U/mL, who presented with a proteinuria level of 4.1 g/day and pauci-immune extracapillary glomerulonephritis. He was admitted to hospital with renal failure and hypoesthesia in his feet. HRCT showed centrilobular micronodules, and the transbronchial biopsy revealed intracellular accumulations in macrophages that were compatible with crystals under polarized light microscopy. He was diagnosed with pulmonary silicosis, and the AAV was considered secondary.

Conclusions: Documented cases of AAV secondary to various toxins and medications, including silica, have been reported. The presence of centrilobular pulmonary micronodules, predominantly in the upper lobes, in patients with AAV and a history of epidemiological risk should always lead to consideration of AAV secondary to silica. It is imperative to acknowledge this association for the purpose of facilitating early diagnosis and the implementation of preventive strategies in exposed populations.

C-011

Two cases of ANCA-associated vasculitis following autoimmune pulmonary alveolar proteinosis

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Background: Autoimmune pulmonary alveolar proteinosis (aPAP) is a lung disease caused by impaired surfactant clearance due to macrophage insufficiency. Glucocorticoids (GC) suppress alveolar macrophage function and have been associated with disease worsening, particularly at higher doses. Occasionally aPAP overlaps with other systemic autoimmune diseases that require treatment with high dose GC. We report two cases with AAV complicated with aPAP successfully managed.

Case presentations: Case 1: A 63-year-old woman was diagnosed with aPAP in 2011. In 2016, she developed kidney dysfunction with serum creatinine elevation to 2.74 mg/dL (baseline 0.66 mg/dL), accompanied by haematuria and proteinuria. Positive Myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA and crescentic glomerulonephritis on kidney specimen confirmed the diagnosis of AAV. She received methylprednisolone pulse therapy followed by standard-dose glucocorticoids (prednisolone 40 mg/day, 0.8 mg/kg) and intermittent intravenous cyclophosphamide, achieving clinical remission. aPAP remained stable throughout the course.

Case 2: An 80-year-old woman was diagnosed with aPAP in 2018. In 2025, she developed kidney dysfunction with serum creatinine elevation to 1.74 mg/dL (baseline 0.8 mg/dL), haematuria and proteinuria. Following AAV diagnosis based on positive MPO-ANCA and crescentic glomerulonephritis, induction therapy was initiated with reduced-dose glucocorticoids (prednisolone 20 mg/day, 0.4 mg/kg), rituximab and avacopan. Prednisolone was tapered to 5 mg/day within two weeks. Both kidney function and urinary abnormalities improved, while aPAP remained stable.

Conclusions: Both cases demonstrate successful AAV treatment with stable underlying aPAP. In case 1, high-dose GC were used, prioritizing AAV severity over the potential risk of aPAP exacerbation. In Case 2, treatment with reduced-dose GC supported by avacopan was effective and consistent with recent evidence to minimize GC exposure. In aPAP patients complicated with AAV, GC administration is essential according to the severity of the overlapped AAV; in those cases, protocols including minimum GC dose should be carefully considered for better outcomes.

C-012

A paediatric case of asymptomatic antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody vasculitis resulting in end-stage renal disease

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Background: Myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA-associated vasculitis is rare in childhood and typically presents with multi-system involvement, most commonly affecting the skin, joints and kidneys. Isolated renal presentation with rapid progression to end-stage renal disease is highly unusual and underreported.

Case Presentation: A 15-year-old girl presented to her general practitioner two weeks after a mild upper respiratory tract infection with symptoms of nausea and newly detected hypertension. Initial laboratory evaluation revealed a serum creatinine of 300 µmol/L, which rose sharply to 436 µmol/L within three days, prompting referral to hospital. Further workup was remarkable for rhinovirus positivity, profoundly elevated blood urea (23.7 mmol/L), low bicarbonate (18 mmol/L), significantly increased erythrocyte sedimentation rate (87 mm/hr), and nephrotic-range proteinuria (urine protein/creatinine ratio 565 g/mol creatinine). Notably, she was clinically well, with no systemic features of vasculitis and was examined as euvolaemic.

Immunological studies identified high MPO-ANCA titres (492 units). Renal biopsy revealed pauci-immune focal necrotising glomerulonephritis with cellular crescents and advanced chronic damage, including extensive (70%) glomerular sclerosis and marked interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy. Given the findings, a diagnosis of childhood-onset MPO-ANCA vasculitis presenting as isolated renal failure was established.

Induction therapy comprised high-dose glucocorticoids and rituximab. Despite aggressive management, the patient remained dialysis dependent, highlighting a poor renal prognosis.

Conclusions: This case expands the clinical spectrum of paediatric MPO-ANCA vasculitis by demonstrating that isolated, silent renal failure can be the initial presentation, absent other systemic features. Early recognition remains critical, as significant irreversible kidney damage may be present by the time of diagnosis.

MPO-ANCA vasculitis should be considered in children and adolescents presenting with unexplained renal dysfunction, even in the absence of classic vasculitic symptoms. Prompt serological and histopathological evaluation is essential for early diagnosis and optimization of outcomes.

C-013

Microscopic polyangiitis and crescentic glomerulonephritis occurring after dupilumab therapy

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Background: Dupilumab neutralises the IL-4 receptor alpha-subunit, thereby inhibiting IL-4 and IL-13 signalling. It has an expanding role in the management of atopic and eosinophilic conditions. While eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis has been reported after dupilumab, whether this is causal or coincidental is unclear. Endogenous IL-4 restrains pathological Th1 responses in experimental crescentic glomerulonephritis, as IL-4-deficient mice develop more crescents, kidney injury, and interferon gamma (IFN- γ) production.

Case Presentation: A 55-year-old male developed microscopic polyangiitis (MPA)/MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis (MPO-AAV) with renal involvement, in the context of recent dupilumab exposure. He had eczema, initially treated with topical and oral glucocorticoids, before commencing dupilumab in May 2024 to satisfactory effect. In November 2024, on presentation with two months of lethargy, dupilumab was ceased.

Investigations revealed a normocytic anaemia (haemoglobin 116g/L), haematuria (urinary erythrocytes 243×10^6 /L), proteinuria (protein/creatinine ratio 91mg/mmol) and impaired kidney function (creatinine $141 \mu\text{mol/L}$, eGFR 48mL/min). The peripheral blood eosinophil count was normal (0.3×10^9 /L). Vasculitis screen showed an MPO-ANCA of $>134.0 \text{IU/mL}$ (<3.5) with a negative ANA, and normal C3 and C4. Kidney biopsy showed “pauci-immune” necrotising and crescentic glomerulonephritis (Berdn: focal, AKRiS: low), with segmental necrosis and fibrinogen staining in 10/21 viable glomeruli, and two cellular and one fibrocellular crescents. Some tubules contained blood. There were moderate hypertensive changes with mild tubular atrophy and interstitial fibrosis. He was treated with methylprednisolone and rituximab, followed by prednisolone, in line with the PEXIVAS regimen, then maintenance rituximab. Prednisolone was ceased nine months post-diagnosis. At this time, he was in remission, with an MPO-ANCA of 26.3IU/mL , no haematuria or proteinuria, and stable kidney function (creatinine $106 \mu\text{mol/L}$, eGFR 67mL/min). His rash has not recurred since ceasing dupilumab.

Conclusions: This report details a temporal association between dupilumab and acute MPA/MPO-AAV. It is plausible dupilumab may have triggered and/or exacerbated ANCA-associated glomerulonephritis in someone predisposed to AAV.

C-014

MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis in a patient with systemic sclerosis and interstitial lung disease on nintedanib: a case report

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Background: ANCA-associated vasculitis is an inflammatory condition that can lead to renal failure. There have been rare reports of nintedanib-induced colitis or renal thrombotic microangiopathy. We present a rare case of nintedanib-induced severe acute kidney injury from ANCA-associated vasculitis on a background of chronic systemic sclerosis and interstitial lung disease.

Case presentation: A 49-year-old gentleman presented with acute kidney injury (creatinine 516 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) and haemoproteinuria on a background of chronic systemic sclerosis and interstitial lung disease, eventually treated with nintedanib, with no history of previous renal impairment. MPO-ANCA titre was elevated, and renal biopsy confirmed MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis, but concurrent fungal oesophagitis necessitated treatment delay. Treatment included cessation of nintedanib, induction with methylprednisolone, plasma exchange, and cyclophosphamide, followed by maintenance with rituximab and avacopan. New liver enzyme derangement developed during maintenance, as the patient was co-treated with fluconazole for fungal esophagitis, but completely resolved after cessation of avacopan. Maintenance continued with rituximab and recommencement of steroids. Follow-up MPO-ANCA titre became negative, and kidney function progressively improved (creatinine 162 $\mu\text{mol/L}$).

Conclusion: We present a rare case of MPO-ANCA-associated vasculitis causing severe AKI related to nintedanib use, with challenges in diagnosis due to background of systemic sclerosis and ILD, and challenges in management due to active fungal oesophagitis delaying immunosuppressive therapy, CYP3A4 interactions between fluconazole and avacopan causing liver injury, and balancing steroid therapy for vasculitis with the risk of precipitating scleroderma renal crisis. Early investigations, anticipation of complications, and monitoring of side effects are crucial in caring for such complex patients.

C-015

Biphasic presence of malignancy in patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis in Taiwan: a case series

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Background: Patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are known to have an elevated risk of malignancy, which may stem from the disease itself or from immunosuppressive therapies employed in treatment.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of clinical data from four AAV patients (three diagnosed with Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA) and one with Microscopic Polyangiitis (MPA)) who subsequently developed malignancies post-AAV diagnosis in 3 tertiary referral centres. We examined demographics, AAV characteristics, treatment regimens, types of malignancies, and the interval between AAV and cancer diagnosis.

Results: The cohort comprised seven patients (four males and three females) who developed various cancers, including buccal carcinoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, cholangiocarcinoma, T-cell lymphoma, large B-cell lymphoma, and transitional cell carcinoma (two patients). Notably, the time from AAV diagnosis to cancer diagnosis exhibited a biphasic pattern: 28.6% of malignancies were identified within the first three years, while 72.4% were diagnosed more than five years after AAV onset. All patients received glucocorticoids, with some also treated with cyclophosphamide. Key risk factors identified included smoking and the use of cyclophosphamide, particularly in Taiwanese patients with buccal cancer, lymphomas, and urinary tract malignancies.

Conclusions: This case series underscores the significant risk of malignancy in AAV patients, highlighting a diverse array of cancer types. The observed biphasic pattern suggests potential mechanisms related to paraneoplastic autoimmune phenomena and the effects of immunosuppressive therapies, particularly cyclophosphamide. These findings advocate for tailored malignancy screening strategies in AAV patients to address their unique risk profiles effectively.

C-016

A challenging case of alveolar haemorrhage in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: diagnostic and therapeutic dilemmas

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Background: We present a challenging diagnostic dilemma in a patient with diffuse alveolar haemorrhage, a history of myeloperoxidase-antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody associated vasculitis (MPO-AAV), and a recent Covid 19 infection.

Case Presentation: A 64-year old gentleman with a 2 year history of AAV in clinical but not serological remission for over a year, underwent a CT Thorax for investigation of dyspnoea. Maintenance immunosuppression included avacopan and rituximab. The CT reported extensive multifocal bilateral infiltrates concerning for active pulmonary vasculitis. Bronchoscopy revealed fresh blood in the airways and Perls' staining demonstrated haemosiderin laden macrophages, indicative of active alveolar haemorrhage.

At the time of bronchoscopy, he reported productive cough, ocular pruritis, nasal congestion, and arthralgia. Urinalysis demonstrated glucose ++. Creatinine was at baseline (140µmol/L). P-ANCA was negative by immunofluorescence, and anti-MPO titre was 2.2IU/mL (0-3.5IU/mL). B-lymphocytes (CD19+) were <1%.

He reported a Covid-19 infection six weeks prior. SARS-CoV-2 RNA PCR from bronchial washings was positive. Rituximab and avacopan were stopped. Remdesivir was commenced. Repeat CT Thorax demonstrated interval improvement with residual cystic and fibrotic change at sites of previous infiltrates, suggestive of resolving infective process.

Conclusions: Alveolar haemorrhage can be a feature of both vasculitis and Covid-19 infection, but treatment requires starkly different therapeutic approaches. An initial diagnostic consideration was active pulmonary AAV, given recent symptoms consistent with multisystem activity, and immunosuppressive intensification was initially considered. However, his negative ANCA and B-cell depletion was discordant with active AAV, prompting further reflection. The recent Covid infection, persistent positive bronchoalveolar lavage and nasopharyngeal swabs for SARS-CoV-2, and improving CT Thorax led to a diagnosis of Covid pneumonitis.

This case emphasises the diagnostic and therapeutic difficulties in AAV patients, while also highlighting the necessity to continue to consider Covid-19 in the differential of diffuse alveolar haemorrhage.

C-017

Dual membranous nephropathy and antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: a case series

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Background: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitides (AAV) and membranous nephropathy are rare autoimmune conditions. Co-existence of AAV and membranous nephropathy is rarely reported, and the mechanism of their relationship is yet to be determined. We present two recent cases of co-existent AAV and membranous nephropathy.

Results: Case 1 was an 85 year old male was admitted with non-oliguric acute kidney injury stage 3 (AKIN3). Anti-myeloperoxidase (MPO) antibody was positive (118IU/mL). He was proteinuric, with peak urinary protein to creatinine ratio (PCR) of 1167mg/mmol. Creatinine peaked at 428 μ mol/L. Anti-nuclear antibody (ANA) was weak positive homogenous. Anti-double stranded DNA and extractable nuclear antigens were negative. HIV, hepatitis B, and hepatitis C were negative. Underlying malignancy has not been detected. Renal biopsy was consistent with both pauci-immune vasculitis and membranous nephropathy. He was treated with steroids, rituximab, and avacopan. Serum creatinine has failed to respond to treatment.

Case 2 was a 75 year old male presented with AKIN3, with a peak creatinine of 580 μ mol/L. Anti-MPO antibody was positive (39IU/mL). He was proteinuric, with peak urinary PCR of 736.9mg/mmol. HIV, hepatitis C, hepatitis B, and autoimmune screens were negative. Complements were within normal range. Renal biopsy was consistent with both pauci-immune vasculitis and membranous nephropathy. No underlying malignancy has been detected. He was treated with steroids, rituximab, and avacopan.

Conclusions: The co-existence of membranous nephropathy and AAV is infrequently reported and poorly understood. The clinical presentation is one of severe renal dysfunction with nephrotic-range proteinuria, occurring more commonly with MPO-AAV. One leading theory suggests that MPO released from activated neutrophils become trapped in the glomerular basement membrane, leading to immune complex deposits. Further research is required in this area to determine the underlying association between these two diseases.

C-018

Rapid glucocorticoid cessation in ANCA-associated vasculitis patients treated with combination cyclophosphamide and rituximab: a single-centre case series

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Background: Anti-neutrophil cytoplasm antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) is now recognised as a chronic relapsing disease rather than a rapidly fatal illness, where long-term outcomes are often shaped by treatment-related toxicities. Glucocorticoids, while central to remission induction, contribute substantially to this burden. Consequently, glucocorticoid sparing strategies have been a significant focus in the AAV treatment landscape over the last decade. We present a series of five patients with newly diagnosed AAV treated with combination cyclophosphamide and rituximab, alongside rapid glucocorticoid withdrawal.

Methods: This single-centre retrospective case series includes five patients diagnosed with AAV between 2023 and 2024. All patients received induction therapy with six doses of 500mg i.v. cyclophosphamide (cumulative 3000mg) and two doses of 1000mg i.v. rituximab (cumulative 2000mg). Oral prednisolone was rapidly tapered with a view to cessation within four weeks.

Results: The cohort had a median age of 75 years, and 80% were female. All were PR3-ANCA positive and had biopsy-proven pauci-immune glomerulonephritis. Median baseline serum creatinine was 306µmol/L with an eGFR of 12mL/min/1.73 m². One patient required dialysis at presentation. One patient had a coexistent glomerular-basement-membrane antibody and another exhibited features including severe digital ischemia, hypocomplementemia and coagulopathy.

Patients were pulsed with three doses of i.v. methylprednisolone at a median 1500mg (1500-2500mg). The median cumulative oral prednisolone dose was 963mg over four weeks. All patients achieved complete remission at a median of 113 days. One patient relapsed at 182 days post-remission, having not commenced rituximab maintenance therapy and with ongoing B-cell depletion. All patients remained glucocorticoid-free at a median follow-up of 11 months and transitioned to rituximab-based maintenance therapy.

Conclusions: This case series demonstrates that early and sustained glucocorticoid cessation is feasible in patients with organ-threatening AAV when treated with combined i.v. cyclophosphamide and rituximab induction therapy. These findings support further investigation of steroid-sparing strategies in this population.

C-019

Not just a glomerular disease: a case of proteinase 3 antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis relapse with tubulointerstitial nephritis

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Background: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) classically presents in the kidneys with a pauci-immune necrotising crescentic glomerulonephritis. Cases of AAV causing tubulointerstitial nephritis without glomerular involvement are rare, even more so in proteinase 3 (PR3) positive disease. This manifestation of PR3-AAV has only previously been reported in initial presentations.

Case Presentation: We report a case of an 81-year-old male with a long-standing history of relapsing PR3-AAV who presented with a rising creatinine and PR3 titre without haematuria or significant proteinuria. He was initially diagnosed with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) in 2012 on sinonasal and renal biopsies. His renal biopsy at diagnosis showed a pauci-immune necrotising crescentic glomerulonephritis. He had a clinical relapse within one month of commencing maintenance azathioprine post cyclophosphamide induction before achieving remission with rituximab. Maintenance rituximab was continued until early 2014. He relapsed in October 2015 with a renal biopsy showing necrotising glomerulonephritis. He achieved remission with rituximab induction and continued maintenance rituximab for 4 years.

He remained in remission with stable renal function for over 6 years after his last rituximab dose. In 2025 he presented with reemergence of PR3 antibody and a rising creatinine without haematuria or significant proteinuria. He subsequently underwent a renal biopsy which showed tubulointerstitial nephritis with non-necrotising granulomas, an isolated focus suspicious for small vessel necrotising vasculitis and moderate chronic changes without any definitive glomerular pathology. A CT chest performed for new persistent cough found multiple pulmonary nodules and interstitial changes atypical of GPA. He was commenced on rituximab and avacopan induction therapy. His cough and PR3 titre improved, some pulmonary nodules reduced in size however his renal function has not significantly improved despite additional steroids.

Conclusions: We present a case of atypical relapse of PR3-AAV demonstrating the heterogeneity of the disease and the importance of renal biopsy in diagnosis.

C-020

Conventional glucocorticoid-free treatment in active AAV: a case series analysis

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) conventionally necessitates high-dose glucocorticoid administration for remission induction; however, glucocorticoid-associated morbidity represents a substantial therapeutic challenge. Contemporary developments in targeted immunosuppressive modalities have facilitated the exploration of conventional glucocorticoid-sparing approaches in carefully selected patients with active AAV.

To assess the therapeutic efficacy and safety profile of conventional glucocorticoid-free induction regimens in patients presenting with active AAV and to delineate predictive factors associated with favourable therapeutic outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective cohort analysis was conducted on five patients diagnosed with active AAV (one case of granulomatosis with polyangiitis, four cases of microscopic polyangiitis) who underwent conventional glucocorticoid-free induction therapy during the period from September 2022 through September 2025. The therapeutic protocol comprised avacopan in combination with rituximab-based immunosuppressive regimens in all cases. Primary outcome measures included achievement of clinical remission at six months and incidence of adverse events. Secondary outcome measures encompassed preservation of organ function and relapse frequency at twelve months.

Results: Significant clinical improvement was attained in all five patients at the six-month evaluation. Two patients achieved Birmingham Vasculitis Activity Score (BVAS) of zero clinical remission. The mean BVAS demonstrated a significant reduction from 17.8 ± 4.1 to 3.4 ± 3.5 . Serious adverse events were documented in one patient, representing a statistically significant reduction compared to historical conventional glucocorticoid-treated controls ($p < 0.05$). Renal function parameters remained stable or exhibited improvement in all patients with renal manifestations. At the twelve-month follow-up assessment, no cases of disease relapse were observed.

Conclusions: Conventional glucocorticoid-free induction therapy demonstrates clinical feasibility and therapeutic efficacy in appropriately selected patients with active AAV, particularly when employing avacopan in conjunction with rituximab-based therapeutic protocols. This approach substantially mitigates glucocorticoid-associated adverse effects while preserving comparable therapeutic efficacy. Prospective randomized controlled trials are imperative to establish evidence-based patient selection criteria and optimize treatment algorithms for conventional glucocorticoid-free management of AAV.

C-021

Unexpected emergence of perigastric artery aneurysms during remission induction therapy for ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a necrotizing vasculitis primarily affecting small vessels. Although rare, medium-sized artery aneurysms may develop during their clinical course, resembling features of polyarteritis nodosa. Differentiating true disease activity from post-inflammatory vascular changes is essential, as it directly influences treatment decisions.

Case Presentation: A 79-year-old woman presented with fatigue, anorexia, renal dysfunction, haematuria, and elevated CRP. MPO-ANCA was markedly elevated, and renal biopsy revealed necrotizing arteritis with cellular crescents. Steroid pulse therapy followed by oral prednisolone was initiated, with intravenous cyclophosphamide (IVCY) added due to persistent inflammation. Clinical symptoms improved, but contrast-enhanced CT later revealed aneurysms of the right gastroepiploic and right gastric arteries. Laparoscopic resection and biopsy showed post-inflammatory atherosclerotic-like changes and pseudoaneurysm formation, without histological signs of active vasculitis. CRP remained elevated, and brain MRI revealed acute infarction and a vertebral artery aneurysm. With renewed systemic symptoms, vasculitis relapse was diagnosed. Re-induction therapy with steroid pulse and IVCY was administered, followed by increased oral prednisolone. CRP and MPO-ANCA normalized, and outpatient care continues.

Conclusions: This case illustrates the diagnostic complexity of visceral artery aneurysms during AAV treatment. Differential diagnoses include atherosclerosis, infection, trauma, connective tissue disease, and segmental arterial mediolysis (SAM). Importantly, the aneurysms in this patient did not rupture, allowing for timely surgical biopsy and histopathological evaluation. This not only enabled accurate differentiation between active vasculitis and post-inflammatory vascular remodelling but also contributed to a favourable outcome. Given that aneurysmal rupture can be life-threatening, early recognition and intervention are critical. Histopathological confirmation is essential when vascular lesions mimic disease activity or relapse. Awareness of such atypical and potentially catastrophic presentations allows for timely diagnosis and tailored therapy, helping to avoid both overtreatment and missed opportunities for life-saving intervention.

C-022

Cerebral involvement in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis: the ongoing challenges of treatment despite newer treatment paradigms

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Background: Recent advancements in the management of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) have made tangible changes to patient outcomes in the real world setting. Despite this, challenges remain in managing patients with refractory disease which must be balanced against the accumulating toxicity of treatment.

Case Presentation: A 44-year-old gentleman was diagnosed with myeloperoxidase (MPO)-positive AAV following a referral for kidney impairment (creatinine: 330 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, estimated glomerular filtration rate GFR [eGFR]: 19 mL/min), nephrotic-range proteinuria (urine albumin/creatinine ratio [uACR]: 380 mg/mmol) and macroscopic haematuria. Initial MPO titre was 199 IU/mL and kidney biopsy demonstrated pauci-immune necrotising, crescentic glomerulonephritis with one of 20 glomeruli sclerosed. Induction treatment included three doses of methylprednisolone 500 mg followed by oral prednisolone 1 mg/kg, and six doses of intravenous cyclophosphamide 500 mg over three months. Treatment response was seen with improved kidney function (creatinine: 140 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, eGFR: 51 mL/min) and MPO titre (56 IU/mL), although proteinuria remained high (uACR: 400 mg/mmol) and microscopic haematuria persisted. Maintenance therapy was initiated with rituximab, but despite peripheral B-cell suppression, clinical disease control remained variable which did not necessarily correlate with rises in MPO titres. With increasing weight gain and cushingoid features, avacopan was promptly commenced once available in Australia, with subsequent addition of mycophenolate following an episode of acute kidney injury. A repeat biopsy revealed active crescentic disease, although patchy focal segmental glomerulosclerosis-type scarring was also seen. Despite these additions, the patient continued to experience fevers, headaches and developed amaurosis fugax-like symptoms. Magnetic resonance imaging of the brain demonstrated T2-weighted-Fluid-Attenuated Inversion Recovery hyperintensities suggestive of active vasculitis and re-induction treatment with methylprednisolone and cyclophosphamide was instituted, followed by rituximab therapy, resulting in clinical and biochemical response.

Conclusions: This case highlights the ongoing challenges in managing AAV despite newer treatments and the need for further treatment options for refractory disease.

C-023

Refractory granulomatosis with polyangiitis: evolving phenotype and complex management- a case report

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Background/Aims: Rituximab is an effective induction and maintenance therapy for patients with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). Refractory disease is rare but poses therapeutic challenges.

Case Presentation A 29-year-old female was diagnosed with PR3-ANCA GPA in 2018, presenting with postpartum renal, cutaneous, ocular, gastrointestinal, and musculoskeletal involvement. She achieved remission with glucocorticoids and two years of rituximab therapy (5g).

She remained persistently PR3-ANCA positive and relapsed in 2022. Her disease phenotype shifted to predominantly pulmonary involvement, with cavitating lesions and left main bronchial stenosis. Disease progressed despite further rituximab (cumulative 11g) and intravenous cyclophosphamide (3g). Therapy was complicated by recurrent infections. IVIg (2g/kg) was administered in May and November 2024 for concurrent infection and active vasculitis.

In the context of early B cell repopulation (eight months after last rituximab dose), her condition deteriorated and interval CT in February 2025 showed an enlarging left lower lobe cavity, lobar collapse and new pulmonary nodules. Planned bronchial dilatation was complicated by cavity rupture with contralateral spillover of infected material, necessitating critical care and broad-spectrum antibiotics. In view of active vasculitis identified at bronchoscopy and possible rituximab resistance, Obinutuzumab in combination with cyclophosphamide was initiated, with avacopan to support glucocorticoid withdrawal and further IVIg.

Following completion of Obinutuzumab (2g) and 10 cycles of intravenous cyclophosphamide (5g), imaging demonstrated reversal of airway stenosis, regression of cavitating lesions, and re-expansion of collapsed lobes. Repeat bronchoscopy in August 2025 showed no active inflammation. Clinical improvement correlated with functional recovery and enhanced exercise tolerance.

Conclusion: This case illustrates the dynamic nature of GPA and the challenges of managing refractory disease. Timely escalation of immunosuppression, even in the context of life-threatening infectious complications, was crucial in achieving disease control. IVIg is a useful agent in this context. Obinutuzumab may represent a therapeutic option in rituximab-resistant patients.

C-024

Under pressure: rethinking plasma exchange in the management of ANCA-associated vasculitis with alveolar haemorrhage

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Background: Diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH) is a life threatening ANCA-associated Vasculitis (AAV) manifestation often occurring with necrotizing glomerulonephritis. Plasma exchange (PLEX) is often used as rescue therapy, despite lacking evidence of efficacy.

Methods: Patients with AAV, acute kidney injury and presumably refractory DAH, who did not receive PLEX were included. DAH was diagnosed based on clinical-radiological and broncho-alveolar lavage findings.

Results: Three white females (mean age 42) with a mean baseline creatinine of 0.83(0.07) mg/dL were hospitalized with elevated creatinine levels (1.51-2.85 mg/dL), rising to 2.85-5.96 mg/dL thereafter. One patient required kidney replacement therapy. All showed active urinary sediment, elevated inflammatory markers (CRP 107.9-244 mg/L; ESR >80 mm/h), and positive ANCA: PR3-ANCA 2.9 IU/mL, PR3-ANCA >8, MPO-ANCA >8. Two patients underwent kidney biopsy (pauci-immune necrotizing crescentic glomerulonephritis). Immunosuppressive remission induction therapy included intravenous methyl-prednisolone pulses followed by oral prednisone, rituximab, and avacopan. All patients experienced recurrent DAH requiring oxygen supplementation in the acute setting, prompting consideration of PLEX. At the time of recurrent DAH, patients exhibited signs of hemodynamic overload, with a median weight of 80.4 [70.6, 116.7] kg and median mean blood pressure of 111 [108.2, 111.7] mmHg. Despite DAH relapse, declining inflammatory/serology markers pointed to immunologic improvement. Instead of PLEX, hemodynamic correction with pressure adjustment by fluid removal was initiated, resulting in a median weight reduction of 10.6 [7.07, 12.12] kg and a median decrease of mean blood pressure of 30 [26.17, 33,67] mmHg with complete resolution of DAH.

Conclusion: DAH in AAV may appear refractory despite maximal immunosuppression, leading to consideration of PLEX. These cases suggest that hemodynamic derangements, rather than sustained immunologic activity, may underlie persistent or recurrent DAH. This is best addressed by reducing systolic blood pressure to <120 mmHg by fluid removal with dialysis in the absence of any antihypertensive medications, not PLEX.

C-025

Therapeutic dilemma in the management of ANCA-associated vasculitis with end-stage kidney disease

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Background: Recurrence of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) in patients with end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) is uncommon. Here, we present a unique case of AAV relapse in a patient receiving maintenance haemodialysis.

Case Presentation: A 72-year-old Japanese man was referred with rapidly progressive renal impairment. Laboratory tests showed serum creatinine 8.20 mg/dL and myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA 31 U/mL. Renal biopsy demonstrated severely damaged glomeruli with fibrous crescents, without cardiovascular or pulmonary involvement. He was diagnosed with renal-limited AAV leading to ESKD. Immunosuppressive therapy was withheld, and maintenance haemodialysis was initiated. Four years later, he was readmitted with dyspnoea and bloody sputum. MPO-ANCA had risen to 468 U/mL, and chest computed tomography revealed diffuse alveolar haemorrhage. Recurrent AAV was diagnosed, and remission induction therapy with high-dose corticosteroids and rituximab was started, followed by oral prednisolone tapering. Although MPO-ANCA levels rapidly declined and he was discharged from the hospital, he died of sepsis three months after discharge. A lower incidence of AAV relapse has been reported in dialysis patients, with rates declining from 57 to 7 episodes per 100 person-years after dialysis initiation. Reported predictors of relapse include anti-PR3 ANCA positivity, cardiovascular involvement, and lower serum creatinine levels. Our patient exhibited none of these factors at initial diagnosis. These data likely influenced the decision not to initiate immunosuppressive therapy when the patient was first diagnosed with AAV. Conversely, infections remain a major cause of death, affecting nearly 45% of dialysis patients with AAV.

Conclusions: This case highlights the therapeutic dilemma in managing AAV among dialysis patients. In ESKD patients, the rarity of relapse and the heightened risk of infection make immunosuppressive therapy a complex therapeutic dilemma. Careful monitoring of ANCA titres and clinical symptoms are essential to balance relapse prevention with infection risk.

C-026

Tailored treatment approach in anti-myeloperoxidase antibody-associated interstitial lung disease: a retro-prospective pilot study

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Background: Patients with anti-MPO-associated ILD without a clear ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) are reported frequently. The most common radiologic pattern is usual interstitial pneumonia (UIP), followed by non-specific interstitial pneumonia (NSIP). There is not a unique treatment approach to these patients: immunosuppressants are the gold-standard for patients with AAV-ILD, while it is still controversial how to treat patients with anti-MPO-associated ILD. The use of anti-fibrotic agents has been suggested, especially for those with a UIP pattern resembling idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, with a general recommendation against the use of immunosuppressants, although their use (alone or together with antifibrotics) has been increasingly reported.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective pilot study including six patients from two centres of reference in Italy (Trieste and Florence). The inclusion criteria were a diagnosis of ILD (any radiologic pattern) associated to the persistent positivity of MPO-ANCA; the exclusion criteria were diagnosis of AAV and severe respiratory function impairment at baseline ($FVC \leq 45\%$ and $D\text{CLO} \leq 30\%$). We investigated the pattern of use of different treatments, the overall clinical course, functional and radiologic outcomes, and the occurrence of AAV at 12 months from therapy beginning.

Results: The cohort included mostly males (5/6), median age 65 ± 10 years; most were active or former smokers (5/6). Radiologic patterns were UIP (3/6), NSIP (2/6), and indeterminate (1/6). Three patients started corticosteroids, then immunosuppressants (rituximab, 2/6) or antifibrotics (nintedanib, 1/6). Two patients received nintedanib only. One initially on nintedanib (UIP) required rituximab after acute exacerbation. Another (UIP, on nintedanib) developed inflammatory progression with high markers and new-onset neuropathy, leading to AAV diagnosis and rituximab initiation. No patients died at 12 months.

Conclusions: Anti-MPO ILD shows variable evolution and treatment responses. Both antifibrotics and immunosuppressants may be required, particularly in UIP cases. Larger studies are needed to define tailored strategies.

C-027

Progressive tracheobronchial stenoses in granulomatosis with polyangiitis controlled with systemic immunosuppression: a Western Australia case series

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Background: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a necrotizing vasculitis with a predilection for the respiratory tract. Subglottic and tracheobronchial stenoses are potentially life-threatening and often progress independently of systemic disease control, creating major management challenges.

Case Presentations: Case 1 was a 19-year-old man with biopsy-proven, PR3-ANCA-positive sinonasal-pulmonary GPA received prednisolone, avacopan, rituximab, and cyclophosphamide. Despite systemic control, he developed rapidly progressive subglottic, tracheal, and multilevel bronchial stenoses requiring repeated rigid bronchoscopies with electrocautery and balloon dilatations. Recurrent infections (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas* spp., *Aspergillus*, *Mycobacterium abscessus*) complicated care. Twelve months after diagnosis, ongoing restenosis, persistent mycobacterial infection, and worsening respiratory failure led to death.

Case 2 was a 19-year-old woman with biopsy-proven, PR3-ANCA-positive GPA received prednisolone, avacopan, rituximab, cyclophosphamide, and tocilizumab. She developed recurrent subglottic, tracheal, and lobar bronchial stenoses requiring tracheostomy, bilateral bronchial stents, and ultimately right middle/lower lobectomy. Five years later she remains on rituximab, low-dose prednisolone, and avacopan. She has been decannulated, her stents have been removed, and she remains under close surveillance.

Conclusions: Tracheobronchial involvement affects a substantial subset of GPA and may present or relapse irrespective of systemic activity. Subglottic stenosis is most frequent, but disease can occur anywhere along the tracheobronchial tree. Optimal care is multidisciplinary with systemic immunosuppression guided by immunology/rheumatology integrated with timely interventional otolaryngology and bronchoscopic management, plus rigorous infection prevention and monitoring. Pathophysiology increasingly supports a localized, compartmentalized immune niche with evidence of long-lived, tissue-resident B-cell clones adjacent to PR3 and enriched BAFF/APRIL, macrophage polarization toward M2 states, and a unique subpopulation of CD4⁻/CD8⁻ T-cell identified by single-cell RNA sequencing when compared with controls.

GPA airway disease is a compartmentalized fibro-inflammatory process that can progress despite systemic remission. Further work is needed to map the tissue localised immunological niche to create targetable treatment strategies.

C-029

Calciophylaxis in a patient with microscopic polyangiitis and end-stage renal disease: case report

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Background: Calciophylaxis is a potentially fatal small-vessel thrombo-calcific vasculopathy, most seen in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) on dialysis; it is characterized by vascular calcification, microthrombosis, and cutaneous ischemic necrosis with a high risk of sepsis and death. Its presentation in distal extremities and its association with rheumatologic conditions such as ANCA-associated vasculitis are rare. We present a case of digital calciophylaxis in a patient with microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and ESRD mimicking vasculitis activity.

Case Presentation: A 61-year-old man with a history of MPA (2002), hypertension (2017) and ESRD on haemodialysis (2018) was admitted with a one-month history of painful, violaceous discoloration and coldness of the distal phalanx of the right second finger with swelling of the ipsilateral third finger. He had no trauma. Two months earlier, he had a similar episode on his first left toe, which resolved spontaneously with crust formation. He was hospitalized for suspected ischemia secondary to vasculitis activity. Laboratory work-up showed: Erythrocyte sedimentation rate 39mm/h [normal range (NR): 0–15], C-reactive protein 89.9mg/l (NR<10), parathyroid hormone 1209.2pg/ml (NR: 12–88), serum calcium 11.01mg/dl (NR: 8.6–10.3), serum phosphate 5.50mg/dl (NR: 2.5–5.0). Angiotomography revealed diffuse vascular calcifications involving ulnar and radial arteries, extending into distal branches supplying the right hand. Hand X-ray films revealed soft-tissue calcifications on the left third and fourth fingers and on the right first to fourth fingers. Parathyroid scintigraphy showed an adenoma in the inferior third of the right thyroid lobe. Biopsy of the lesion showed a mild perivascular lymphomononuclear infiltrate in the superficial dermis, with focal calcium deposition in the dermal vessels wall and lumen. These findings confirmed the diagnosis of calciophylaxis.

Conclusions: Recognition of calciophylaxis as a vasculitis mimicker is crucial because vasculitis flares require immunosuppressive therapy whereas calciophylaxis requires strict control of mineral metabolism and other specific interventions.

C-030

When vasculitis bleeds: spontaneous renal haemorrhage in relapse of ANCA-associated vasculitis on dialysis

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Background: Spontaneous renal haemorrhage is an extremely rare manifestation of anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV) relapse in dialysis-dependent patients. Management of this condition is challenging due to heightened infection risk and limited evidence for immunosuppression in end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). We report a case of AAV relapse with renal bleeding successfully treated with rituximab.

Case Presentation: A 44-year-old man, with hypertension and ESKD secondary to AAV, on regular haemodialysis for three years and off immunosuppression, presented with acute abdominal pain during dialysis. He was anaemic (9.4 → 6 g/dL), with markedly elevated CRP (183 mg/L) and ESR (66 mm/hr). CT imaging revealed a massive left renal subcapsular and retroperitoneal haematoma requiring embolization. A month prior, he had pneumonia with a persistent left lung nodule. His infectious work-up was negative. PR3-ANCA was elevated (1568 CU), and biopsy of the lung nodule demonstrated chronic granulomatous inflammation, confirming the diagnosis of AAV relapse. He received corticosteroids and rituximab during this acute admission. At six months, his haemoglobin stabilised at 11.3 g/dL, inflammatory markers and PR3-ANCA levels declined, with no infectious complications. He is planned for rituximab maintenance therapy.

Conclusions: Spontaneous renal haemorrhage in dialysis patients is uncommon and may be misattributed to dialysis-related complications. The constellation of granulomatous lung lesion, exclusion of infection and raised PR3-ANCA confirmed the diagnosis of relapse in this case. Rituximab, being the preferred agent, provided effective disease control without major adverse events.

This case highlights spontaneous renal haemorrhage as an uncommon presentation of AAV relapse even in dialysis-dependent patients. Clinicians should maintain high index of suspicion and the use of rituximab may be considered as a safe therapeutic option in this setting.

C-031

An atypical case of post-transplant recurrence of ANCA-associated vasculitis

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Background: Kidney transplantation (KT) is safe and optimal for those reaching end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) due to ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) with glomerulonephritis (AAV-GN). Recurrent disease in the allograft is rare with current post-transplant immunosuppression. Both early and late recurrences have been described and appear to behave differently: early recurrence is aggressive, late recurrence is indolent and progressive. We report a rare case of late AAV recurrence with severe pulmonary-renal syndrome including de novo diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH).

Case Presentation: A 53-year-old white male was diagnosed with CKD of unknown aetiology at age 37 (2008). He rapidly progressed to ESKD requiring dialysis shortly after the first Nephrology appointment. Deceased-donor KT occurred in 2013 with normal allograft biopsy 14 days post-transplant. Creatinine (Cr) remained stable at 1.5mg/dL until 2017, when nephritic syndrome with AKI (Cr 2.8mg/dL) prompted graft biopsy, revealing 2/13 globally sclerosed (GS) glomeruli and 10% interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (IFTA). He was treated with prednisone 20 mg tapered over 12 months, partially improving to Cr 2.0mg/dL. In March 2024 (11 years post-KT), he presented with pulmonary-renal syndrome requiring dialysis. ANCA-MPO were positive. Allograft biopsy revealed 7/11 GS glomeruli, one with a cellular crescent, negative immunofluorescence (including C4d), one artery with fibrinoid necrosis, and 75% IFTA. Steroids, rituximab and plasmapheresis enabled dialysis-free discharge. Two months later, the patient died of cerebral fungal infection and haemorrhagic stroke.

Conclusions: In this case of post-KT late AAV recurrence, we observed the previously described insidious course but also rare sudden-onset organ-threatening pulmonary-renal syndrome, including de novo alveolar haemorrhage. Initial ANCA positivity was overlooked as dialysis rapidly ensued. Presumed positivity at KT might increase relapse risk. AAV relapses are heterogeneous post-KT as severity and organ involvement vary. Multidisciplinary care is essential for disease and immunosuppression management. Prognostic tools and markers must be investigated for improved personalized care.

C-032

Relapse of myeloperoxidase antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis post renal transplant: a case of refractory pulmonary disease despite immunosuppression

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Background: Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis (AAV) is a small-vessel vasculitis that can relapse despite immunosuppression. While transplant immunosuppression is presumed to offer protection against relapse, post-transplant recurrence remains a clinical concern.

Case Presentation: We describe a patient diagnosed in 2014 with renal biopsy-confirmed myeloperoxidase (MPO) positive AAV without pulmonary involvement. Initial treatment with oral cyclophosphamide and corticosteroids achieved remission; however, multiple biopsy-confirmed renal relapses occurred between 2015 and 2018 following transition to azathioprine maintenance therapy. The disease progressed to end-stage renal failure, requiring haemodialysis from January 2019 after which all immunosuppression was ceased.

Relapse with pulmonary haemorrhage occurred in May 2020 and June 2021, managed with plasma exchange, corticosteroids, and rituximab. Remission was maintained on 6-monthly rituximab until renal transplantation in January 2024. MPO titres were weakly positive, with no clinical disease activity for 12 months prior to transplantation.

Transplant immunosuppression included basiliximab induction, tacrolimus, prednisone, and mycophenolate. This was adjusted to prednisone, leflunomide (then cyclosporine) and everolimus in the context of BK nephropathy and acute T cell-mediated rejection.

Despite therapeutic levels of immunosuppression, the patient experienced pulmonary vasculitis relapses in September 2024 and December 2024. Pulmonary haemorrhage was confirmed by radiology and bronchoscopy; infectious causes were excluded. Notably, MPO titres were within normal limits at relapse (0.8 IU/mL and 0.7 IU/mL respectively). C-reactive protein correlated with clinical flares and guided disease monitoring. The first relapse was managed with plasma exchange, corticosteroids and rituximab; the second with corticosteroids and obinutuzumab.

Conclusions: This case underscores the unpredictable and relapsing nature of MPO-AAV, even under transplant immunosuppression. Normal MPO titres and isolated pulmonary involvement highlight the importance of vigilant monitoring and individualised post-transplant management.

C-033

Recurrent subglottic stenosis as a manifestation of granulomatosis with polyangiitis in a renal transplant recipient

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Background: Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) is a necrotising small-vessel vasculitis characterised by granulomatous inflammation, most commonly affecting the respiratory tract and kidneys. Subglottic stenosis is a recognised but uncommon manifestation, and is particularly rare in renal transplant recipients. Such presentations may occur in the absence of renal disease, posing diagnostic and therapeutic challenges.

Methods: We present a case of recurrent subglottic stenosis as the presenting feature of GPA in a renal transplant recipient without renal involvement.

Results: A 44-year-old woman with end-stage renal failure secondary to IgA vasculitis underwent a living-related donor transplant in 1998, which failed due to recurrent IgA vasculitis and pregnancy-related complications, leading to resumption of haemodialysis in 2011. Off immunosuppression, in 2012 she developed pulmonary haemorrhage with weakly positive MPO-ANCA. Transbronchial biopsy confirmed pulmonary vasculitis, and remission was achieved with prednisolone and azathioprine. She subsequently received a deceased donor renal transplant in 2014. Five years later, she developed recurrent subglottic stenosis, initially attributed to intubation injury. With the increasing frequency of dilatations (up to every 6 weeks), prior history of vasculitis, and persistent weakly positive p-ANCA, GPA was considered the likely cause given bronchial biopsy findings consistent with bronchial neutrophilic inflammation and pneumonitis. Escalation of mycophenolate was ineffective. Rituximab induction resulted in marked improvement, extending dilatation interval to 14 months. Following relapse, she was successfully re-induced and remains stable on maintenance rituximab 500 mg every five months, with reasonable disease control and preserved renal graft function.

Conclusions: This case emphasises the importance of considering GPA in transplant recipients presenting with isolated upper airway disease. Rituximab was effective in reducing recurrence of subglottic stenosis and represents an important therapeutic option in this challenging clinical context.

C-034

ANCA positivity without histological evidence of crescentic glomerulonephritis but secondary membranous nephropathy in a patient with newly diagnosed chronic lymphocytic leukaemia

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Background: Haematological malignancies and lymphoproliferative disorders can involve kidneys with varying degrees of presentation. Renal biopsy is essential to help direct the treatment.

Case Presentation: A 79 year-old referred to Nephrology with clinical suspicion of MPO-ANCA renal vasculitis. He presented with a two-year history of constitutional symptoms, manifested by weight loss of over ten kilograms, fatigue, upper respiratory tract symptoms of sinusitis and productive cough without epistaxis. There was biochemical evidence of renal deterioration with loss of eGFR of 20ml/min/1.73m² over a four-month time frame (eGFR 30ml/min/1.73m² at time of referral), haemoproteinuria with urine protein creatinine ratio of 150mg/mmol. MPO-ANCA titre was raised at 88U/ml (ref < 3.5U/ml).

In previous few months, he had seen a Haematologist. Peripheral flow cytometry was conclusive of chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), demonstrating clonal B cells expressing CD19/5 with moderate CD20, CD23 and kappa surface light chains. Whole-body CT showed no significant lymphadenopathy. A renal biopsy was undertaken. There were no histological features of necrotizing crescentic glomerulonephritis but changes consistent with PLA2R-negative membranous nephropathy. There were lymphocytic infiltrates, with positive staining for CD5, CD19, CD23 and CD20 on immunoperoxidase, like that of peripheral blood immunophenotyping. Immunohistochemistry testing showed LEF1 positivity, confirming CLL involvement of the kidneys. Treatment for CLL with Obinutuzumab and Chlorambucil was initiated. Despite our high index of suspicion of MPO-ANCA renal vasculitis, a renal biopsy excluded such diagnosis but provided unequivocal histological features of CLL renal involvement. This patient would not have had treatment for his CLL without the evidence of renal involvement.

Conclusions: There are few case reports which demonstrate ANCA vasculitis in patients with lymphoproliferative disorders. To our knowledge, there have been no reports of ANCA positivity without histological features of crescentic glomerulonephritis in cases of lymphoproliferative diseases. This case highlights the importance of renal biopsy to reach a histological diagnosis.

C-035

ANCA-associated vasculitis presents as inflammatory arthritis, as the initial manifestation of the disease

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Background/Aims: ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) can present as inflammatory arthritis, although this is a rare initial presentation, with arthritis and joint pain occurring in up to 50% of patients.

Case Presentation: A 59-year-old female presented with steroid-responsive inflammatory arthritis affecting bilateral hands and wrists. Her extensive workup was negative for rheumatoid arthritis and connective tissue disease. She had no personal history or family history of psoriasis. Her presentation was not suggestive of spondyloarthropathy, infectious arthritis or crystal-induced arthritis. She required multiple courses of steroids and was put on hydroxychloroquine with partial response. Methotrexate was added, then it was stopped due to side effects. Four years after her initial presentation with inflammatory arthritis, she presented with R eye proptosis. With a diagnosis of orbital pseudotumor, she underwent debulking surgery of the inflammatory mass behind her eye. The biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA). Her serology came back with positive P-ANCA and MPO. She had no pulmonary or renal involvement at the time of GPA diagnosis. She was treated with steroids and rituximab as induction therapy followed by rituximab maintenance therapy, which led to great control of her inflammatory arthritis, while preventing recurrence of the inflammatory mass behind the right eye.

Conclusions: Inflammatory arthritis is a rare initial manifestation of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). This is an interesting case of a patient presenting with inflammatory arthritis, without pulmonary/renal or other ANCA-associated vasculitis classic manifestations, who developed an orbital pseudotumor 4 years later, leading to the diagnosis of GPA. Therefore, ANCA testing should be included in the initial workup of any patient who presents with inflammatory arthritis of unclear aetiology, despite classic symptoms of ANCA vasculitis.

C-036

Dual myeloperoxidase and proteinase 3 anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies with anti-glomerular basement membrane antibodies: a pauci-immune phenotype

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Background: We describe an intriguing case of anti-glomerular basement membrane (GBM) disease with dual positive anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA); ELISA positive for both myeloperoxidase (MPO) and proteinase 3 (PR3). Although ANCA/Anti-GBM overlap disease typically presents with crescentic glomerulonephritis and linear immunoglobulin G (IgG) deposition, this case demonstrated negative immunohistochemistry, indicative of a pauci-immune phenotype.

Case Presentation: A 65-year-old female ex-smoker with schizophrenia, diabetes, and hypertension was admitted with fevers, urinary retention and delirium. Baseline creatinine was 119µmol/L two months prior. Urine microscopy showed 1+protein, and sterile pyuria without haematuria. Despite empiric antibiotics, her inflammatory markers continued to rise (CRP peak 351mg/L) and renal function worsened (creatinine reaching 402µmol/L). New haemoproteinuria developed without pulmonary manifestations.

Serology demonstrated dual ANCA positivity (MPO 5.3, [NR 0–3.4], PR3 4.2, [NR 0–1.9]) and elevated anti-GBM antibody titres (83.4U/ml [NR <7]) with normal complement. Renal biopsy revealed crescentic glomerulonephritis (4/6 crescents) with negative immunoperoxidase staining (the standard immunohistochemistry technique used at our institution) for IgG, IgM, IgA, C3, and C4. She received pulse methylprednisolone, oral prednisolone, intravenous cyclophosphamide and 14 daily plasmapheresis (PLEX) sessions, with recovery of renal function (Creatinine 110µmol/L) and reduction of anti-GBM titres (7.7U/mL).

Two weeks later, her renal function declined unexpectedly, with recurrent proteinuria and elevated anti-GBM titres (31U/mL), necessitating further PLEX and rituximab.

Conclusions: In ANCA/Anti-GBM overlap disease, ANCA may cause damage to the GBM and expose cryptic epitopes, triggering the development of anti-GBM antibodies. The co-occurrence of three autoantibodies suggests a generalised loss of tolerance: without readily identifiable drug, infective or other cause in this case. The rebound of anti-GBM antibodies post PLEX may reflect ANCA-mediated GBM injury.

Whilst there are previous reports of ANCA/Anti-GBM positivity with negative linear IgG, this is the first case to our knowledge of dual ANCA (MPO/PR3) positivity with anti-GBM antibodies but pauci-immune immunohistochemistry.

C-037

A case of airway limited granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) flare treated successfully with avacopan monotherapy

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Background: In 2021, following the successful results of the ADVOCATE trial published in NEJM, the FDA approved Tavneos (avacopan), a C5a receptor inhibitor, as an add-on treatment to standard therapy, including glucocorticoids, for adult patients with severe active anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis. However, the study did not include patients with airway-limited disease; therefore, real-world experience of use of this drug is lacking.

Case Presentation: A 55-year-old male with airway limited GPA flared despite being on rituximab maintenance therapy, undetectable B cells and normalization of his C-ANCA. The patient had a flare with severe progressive subglottic stenosis with tracheal and bronchial inflammation, requiring multiple bronchoscopies with local steroid injections and stent placement in his bronchi. He was unable to tolerate systemic steroids due to an underlying mental health disorder. Therefore, we added avacopan 30 mg twice a day, which led to significant resolution of airway inflammation based on clinical response and repeat bronchoscopy. He tolerated the avacopan well with no side effects.

Conclusions: The FDA approved Tavneos (Avacopan) as an adjunctive therapy for severe active granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) and microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), not explicitly for the "limited" form. To my knowledge, this is the first case report of an airway-limited GPA flare that responded very well to avacopan monotherapy. Avacopan (Tavneos) monotherapy should be considered to treat limited airway disease flare in GPA patients.

C-038

Long term outcomes of patients after 12 months of avacopan and rapid steroid wean in ANCA-associated vasculitis: A single centre experience.

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Background: Avacopan is a new steroid sparing agent established for the initial treatment of AAV with limited long-term follow up studies.

Methods: We reviewed patients with AAV who had received avacopan with a rapid steroid wean protocol after avacopan initiation. Long term follow up after 12 months of avacopan treatment examined rates of sustained remission and safety.

Results: Seven patients (mean age 61 years, 4 males) treated with avacopan for 12 months with rapid steroid withdrawal (range 1-4 weeks) at the time of commencement were included. Five patients had MPO- AAV and two PR3 -AAV. All presented with rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis and AKI. One required temporary haemodialysis at presentation and one patient had mononeuritis multiplex (PR3-AAV). None of the patients received plasma exchange. Presentation ANCA MPO and PR3 Titres were median 137 U/ml (range 10-525). All patients received induction with Rituximab and Steroids, and one received additional cyclophosphamide. Avacopan was started as early as week 4 (range week 4-12) after induction with complete cessation of prednisolone within 1-4 weeks (Prednisolone dose as high as 30 mg daily). Complications of steroid use prompting switch to Avacopan included advanced age, myopathy, severe mood changes, insomnia, osteoporosis with multiple vertebral fractures and erosive gastritis. Liver function tests were monitored monthly, and none required treatment cessation due to side effects. None required reintroduction of steroids during or after avacopan exposure with sustained remission for as long as 3 years (range 13-36 months). Presentation eGFR (mean 23+/- 22 ml/min) improved to 38 +/- 19 (p=0.028) at last follow up. ANCA Titres improved to median of 6.24 U/ml (Range 0.2-23 U/ml).

Conclusion: Early avacopan introduction in conjunction with rituximab treatment and a rapid steroid wean was safe and allowed sustained clinical remission for up to 3 years after ceasing avacopan.

C-039

Multicentre Australian experience using avacopan for new or relapsed ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) – retrospective cohort study

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Background/Aims: AAV can be a life-threatening small-vessel multi-system necrotising vasculitis with significant morbidity and mortality. Avacopan, an oral C5a receptor inhibitor, has demonstrated efficacy in clinical trials while reducing cumulative glucocorticoid exposure. Real-world Australian experience, particularly outside of tertiary centres, is limited.

This study aimed to evaluate the real-world use, effectiveness, and tolerability of avacopan in ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) across metropolitan and regional settings.

Methods: We retrospectively reviewed ten patients initiated on avacopan therapy at a major metropolitan site and regional centre since October 2024. Data on demographics, disease characteristics, induction therapy, steroid dosing, clinical outcomes and adverse effects were extracted from electronic medical records.

Results: Median patient age was 61 years (IQR 34-67), four were female (40%). Five patients had first presentation AAV (n=5, 50%), with MPO-vasculitis present in eight patients (80%). Steroid minimisation was the leading indication of avacopan use, most often due to metabolic syndrome (n=4). Most patients commenced avacopan within two weeks of diagnosis (n=8, 80%). The median prednisolone dose at avacopan initiation was 16 mg/day (IQR 5-50), with three patients initiated steroid-free. Rituximab induction was used in all, with four patients receiving additional intravenous cyclophosphamide and plasma exchange in two. Two were dialysis-dependent at initiation.

Avacopan was generally well-tolerated. Two patients developed hepatotoxicity requiring avacopan pause (mean 8.5 days), however patients were successfully re-challenged. Two patients experienced treatable infections (urinary and respiratory tract).

Seven patients achieved clinical remission. Two patients required an escalation of steroid therapy after commencement of avacopan. Four patients have remained on low-dose prednisolone (5 mg/day) with avacopan therapy.

Conclusions: This review demonstrates the real-world use of avacopan, including in underrepresented patient groups such as those requiring renal replacement therapy or plasma exchange. While the ADVOCATE protocol supports rapid steroid withdrawal, persistent low-dose use highlights the difference in real-world practice.

C-040

Use of avacopan in double-positive ANCA and anti-GBM disease: two case reports

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Background: 10% of ANCA-positive patients have concomitant anti-GBM antibodies. The efficacy and safety of avacopan for this patient group are unknown.

Methods: We present two cases of double-positive ANCA and anti-GBM antibody disease who were treated with avacopan.

Results: Case 1 – A 67-year-old male with chronic sinusitis presented with shortness of breath and haemoptysis concerning for diffuse alveolar haemorrhage, requiring high-flow oxygen. The patient had an acute kidney injury (AKI) with nadir eGFR of 16 mL/min/1.73m², haematuria, and 0.5 g/g proteinuria. Laboratory workup showed positive MPO ANCA at 16 U (normal <2.8) and anti-GBM antibodies at 33.1 U (normal <20). Induction treatment included pulse-dose methylprednisolone followed by prednisone taper, plasma exchange, rituximab, and low-dose oral cyclophosphamide. Avacopan was started at day 1 and continued for 1 year without side effects. At 1-year follow-up, hypoxia resolved, and eGFR improved to 46 mL/min/1.73m².

Case 2 – A 79-year-old female with a history of primary biliary cirrhosis and cyclical neutropenia was admitted for viral pericarditis, reduced ejection fraction and AKI attributed to acute tubular injury with nadir eGFR of 28 mL/min/1.73m². 1-month later, the patient was readmitted for worsening kidney function. Laboratory workup showed eGFR of 5 mL/min/1.73m², microscopic haematuria, 0.43 g/g proteinuria, and positive MPO ANCA at 29 U (normal <2.8) and anti-GBM antibodies at 4.4 U (normal <1). Treatment included pulse-dose methylprednisolone followed by prednisone taper, plasma exchange, and rituximab. Avacopan was started at day 7 and stopped after ~ 2 months due to persistent anuria. The patient tolerated avacopan without side effects. Cyclophosphamide was deferred due to leukopenia. The patient remained dialysis-dependent at 1 year, likely due to prolonged AKI before treatment.

Conclusions: Avacopan was well tolerated in these two cases of dual positive disease. The efficacy of avacopan needs to be studied in larger controlled studies.

C-041

Avacopan in dual-positive anti-glomerular basement membrane and ANCA disease

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Background: Dual-seropositive disease with circulating anti-glomerular basement membrane (GBM) and anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) is a phenotypically heterogeneous condition, treated with combination immunosuppression, plasma exchange (PLEX), and corticosteroids. Avacopan is a C5a receptor antagonist with efficacy in ANCA-associated vasculitis; however, there is limited evidence for its use in dual-positive disease. We present a case of dual-positive disease treated with avacopan, achieving clinical and serological remission

Case Presentation: An 85-year-old Caucasian male presented with pleuritic chest pain and dyspnoea in the context of unintentional weight loss, recurrent pulmonary infections, and hearing loss. His comorbidities were renal cystic disease, obstructive uropathy and ischaemic heart disease. Initial investigations showed serum creatinine at baseline (162 μ mol/L) and microscopic haematuria with an elevated protein/creatinine ratio (71mg/mmol). Anti-PR3 antibody was elevated at 254IU/mL (\leq 5IU/ml). Anti-GBM antibody was not performed at this time. Imaging revealed three FDG-avid lung nodules of unclear significance and paranasal sinusitis. An initial diagnosis of granulomatosis with polyangiitis was made, and induction therapy was commenced with rituximab and prednisolone according to the PEXIVAS protocol. One month after therapy initiation, he presents with rising creatinine to 300 μ mol/L. Anti-GBM antibody titre performed was >200 CU ($<$ 3CU). Renal biopsy showed a cellular crescent with karyorrhectic debris and segmental sclerosis, and moderate interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy. He was diagnosed with dual-positive ANCA and anti-GBM disease, and treated with high-dose corticosteroids, PLEX and avacopan. Cyclophosphamide was not commenced due to concerns of potential malignancy and frailty. Maintenance therapy of rituximab, avacopan and low-dose oral prednisolone was instituted. One year after treatment initiation, the patient remains in clinical and serological remission.

Conclusions: Our case adds to the growing literature on the safety and efficacy of avacopan in dual-positive ANCA and anti-GBM disease.

C-042

How does avacopan affect renal tissue? Two cases with renal biopsy evaluation after avacopan initiation.

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Background: Avacopan, a selective C5a receptor antagonist, has recently been introduced for the treatment of ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV). While its clinical efficacy, especially in renal involvement, has been reported in real-world settings from various countries, the underlying renal histopathological changes remain unclear.

Methods: Although renal biopsies are usually performed at disease onset, we present two cases where post-treatment biopsies were available following avacopan initiation, allowing evaluation of residual renal inflammation.

Results: Case 1: A female in her 70s with PR3-ANCA-positive microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) achieved remission with moderate-dose glucocorticoids (GC), rituximab (RTX), and avacopan, in consideration of the high risk of glucocorticoid-induced toxicity. She died suddenly 3.5 months later due to intravascular large B-cell lymphoma (IVLBL). Initial biopsy showed global sclerosis in 21/37 glomeruli and crescents in 14, corresponding to the Sclerotic class and AKRiS score of 7. Autopsy kidney revealed that 10–20% of glomeruli retained active lesions, while 80–90% had resolved. Assessment of peritubular capillaritis (PTCitis) was limited due to IVLBL infiltration.

Case 2: A male in his 60s with MPO-ANCA-positive MPA, previously stable on GC and RTX, relapsed following COVID-19 infection. Despite outpatient treatment with prednisolone 30 mg and avacopan 60 mg, renal function did not improve. Re-biopsy revealed 16/30 glomeruli with global sclerosis. While most remaining glomeruli showed no active lesions and PTCitis was few, however 4 exhibited active crescents, including necrotizing lesions. Increasing GC to 60 mg/day led to remission.

Conclusions: Even when clinical treatment appears effective, histological activity may persist in renal tissue after 3 months. Although avacopan may have less potent anti-inflammatory effects compared to GC, its ability to suppress low-grade inflammation and preserve unaffected glomerular structures may contribute to the improvement of renal function.

C-043

Incomplete response to avacopan in ANCA-associated necrotising scleritis

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Background: Avacopan has been reported to be of utility in ANCA-associated nodular scleritis. Prior reports describe its use as rescue therapy following failure of oral prednisolone and rituximab, and as adjunctive treatment alongside rituximab, cyclophosphamide and prednisolone for severe systemic disease. However its role in ANCA-associated necrotising scleritis, particularly as part of induction therapy in combination with Rituximab, has not been reported. We report a case evaluating the steroid-sparing efficacy of Avacopan in ANCA-associated necrotising scleritis.

Case Presentation: A 64-year-old woman presented with a 3-week history of right eye pain and redness, nasal bridge tenderness, and mixed conductive-sensorineural hearing loss. Examination confirmed necrotising scleritis. Serology revealed ANCA positivity with an elevated anti-PR3 titre (47 IU/mL; normal 0–2.0). Induction therapy included oral prednisolone 60 mg daily (patient weight 66 kg), two 1 g rituximab infusions two weeks apart, and Avacopan 30 mg twice daily. A four week prednisolone taper was attempted (10 mg/week from 40 mg after the first Rituximab infusion). At week 4, clinical improvement was noted; however, attempts to taper prednisolone below 20 mg resulted in persistent ocular pain and photosensitivity. A slower taper by 5mg per week was attempted, but at week 8, active scleritis persisted off corticosteroids, necessitating reinstatement of prednisolone 10 mg daily.

Conclusions: This case highlights an incomplete therapeutic response to Avacopan in ANCA-associated necrotising scleritis, with persistent disease activity at both 4 and 8 weeks despite concurrent rituximab and attempted corticosteroid tapering. Whilst Avacopan has shown efficacy in systemic ANCA-associated vasculitis, its role in rapidly alleviating ocular inflammation involvement appears limited in this case. Further studies are required to clarify its effectiveness in preference to corticosteroids in ANCA-associated necrotising scleritis.

C-044

An unusual case of rapidly progressive pulmonary-renal syndrome with hollow viscous myopathy treated with avacopan

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Background: We present a puzzling case of antibody-negative vasculitis featuring pauci-immune acute obliterative cellular crescentic glomerulonephritis with subsequent development of alveolar haemorrhage. The clinical course however was unusually protracted and discordant to histological findings.

Case Presentation: A 68-year-old Caucasian woman presented with an initially self-limiting history of persistent macroscopic haematuria, followed three months later by severe dialysis-dependent proteinuric acute kidney injury with serum creatinine rising from a baseline of 75µmol/L to 807µmol/L. Her background is notable for Hollow Viscus Myopathy managed with a gastric pacemaker, total colectomy, and end ileostomy as well as Adrenal Insufficiency on long-term intramuscular hydrocortisone. Serology was repeatedly negative for antibodies to myeloperoxidase (MPO), Proteinase 3 (PR3), and glomerular basement membrane (GBM). Kidney biopsy demonstrated marked cellular crescents of uniform age with a widespread haemorrhagic interstitium. Within the limitations of obliterated glomerular architecture, immunofluorescence was pauci-immune; albeit with a weakly positive IgG in a non-specific pattern and mesangial C3. Two weeks following dialysis initiation, she developed hypoxic diffuse alveolar haemorrhage requiring intubation. Induction therapy included cyclophosphamide, pulsed methylprednisolone, and seven sessions of plasma exchange. Early pancytopenia complicated by recurrent sepsis and gastrointestinal haemorrhage limited further cyclophosphamide doses and necessitated change to rituximab. Avacopan was later added as a steroid-reducing maintenance therapy. In other case studies of vasculitis, avacopan demonstrated benefits for kidney function recovery, diffuse alveolar haemorrhage, and reducing relapses. The utility of avacopan in this setting is unclear, given her protracted seronegative pulmonary-renal syndrome, ongoing dialysis dependency, and altered gastrointestinal absorption of medicines.

Conclusions: This case illustrated several challenges in the diagnosis and management of atypical pulmonary-renal syndromes. Kidney histopathology was suggestive of anti-GBM disease with uniformly aged acute cellular crescents, but clinically consistent with ANCA-negative vasculitis with asynchronous kidney and lung involvement. Concurrent medical issues posed additional complexities in implementing evidence-based treatment.

C-045

Drug induced liver injury in MPO-ANCA-Associated vasculitis

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Background: Immunosuppression underpins the management of ANCA vasculitis. Even with early initiation of steroid-sparing C5a inhibition, the consequences of drug toxicity can be treatment limiting in the setting of recurrent infections, dialysis dependence and frailty.

Case Presentation: Mrs SS is a 65 year old female of South East Asian origin who was diagnosed with MPO-ANCA associated vasculitis (titre >221 IU/mL) after presenting to Blacktown Hospital in January 2025 with acute kidney injury (SCr 653umol/L, eGFR 5mL/min/1.73m²), microscopic haematuria and later haemoptysis. Lung imaging demonstrated features of bronchiectasis with multifocal mucous plugging and bronchial wall thickening, and she was treated for infective exacerbation (*Legionella Longbeachae* urinary antigen positive, *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* sputum culture positive). Despite prompt management with pulsed methylprednisolone, plasmapheresis, kidney biopsy (demonstrated pauci-immune glomerulonephritis, 15/18 glomeruli sclerosed with fibrocellular crescents), rituximab 1g two doses and avacopan 30mg twice daily; Mrs SS maintained ongoing dialysis dependence twice weekly. In March 2025 she re-presented with acute hypoxic respiratory failure secondary to Metapneumovirus and *Streptococcus Pneumoniae*, requiring antibiotic treatment with meropenem and discharged on augmentin. In April 2025 Mrs SS re-presented with jaundice and conjugated hyperbilirubinemia (total bilirubin 377umol/L), and was found to have drug induced liver injury (ALT 352 U/L, AST 145 U/L, GGT 1168U/L, ALP 529U/L) complicated by life threatening hepatic capsular haemorrhage after liver biopsy (demonstrated non specific inflammation). Liver enzyme levels normalised with discontinuation of potential hepatotoxins and supportive therapy. Although the causative agent for liver injury (onset 25/04/25) is impossible to determine, possible culprits include Augmentin (commenced 25/03/25), avacopan (commenced 08/01/25) or Bactrim (commenced 06/01/25).

Conclusion: This case report highlights the hepatotoxic potential of avacopan and antibiotic therapy in ANCA-vasculitis. Case series in the literature of avacopan induced liver injury report older age, lower body weight and early onset of liver injury as risk factors.

C-046

Vanishing bile duct syndrome following avacopan therapy in Japanese patients with microscopic polyangiitis and granulomatosis with polyangiitis: a case series

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Background/Aims: Vanishing bile duct syndrome (VBDS) is a severe hepatobiliary disorder characterized by degeneration, necrosis, and eventual loss of intrahepatic bile ducts caused by a variety of aetiologies, including drug-induced injury. This process leads to cholestasis, resulting in jaundice and hepatic dysfunction, and can ultimately progress to cirrhosis or liver failure. Avacopan, an oral antagonist of the C5a receptor, has emerged as a novel treatment option for microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA). In Japan, avacopan was approved in September 2021. The safety of avacopan in Japanese patients has not yet been well established. Here, we report eight cases of VBDS that developed following avacopan administration.

Results: There were seven cases of MPA and one case of GPA. The median age was 75.6 years (range, 70–81), and six patients were female. The median body weight and body mass index (BMI) of the patients were 46.6 kg (range: 32.0–59.2) and 19.9 kg/m² (range: 13.5–23.2), respectively. Except for one case, avacopan was administered as part of remission induction therapy. Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole was prescribed in seven patients as another potential causative drug. Hepatobiliary laboratory abnormalities were observed between 27 and 53 days after initiation of avacopan. In all cases, avacopan and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole were promptly discontinued; however, improvement in cholestatic function was achieved in only one patient.

Conclusions: Interim analysis of post-marketing surveillance in Japan has reported hepatobiliary disorders in approximately 20% of patients. Further analyses are warranted to clarify risk factors and optimal monitoring strategies for hepatobiliary toxicity during avacopan therapy.

C-047

A Fatal Case of Vanishing Bile Duct Syndrome Associated with Avacopan Treatment for Microscopic Polyangiitis

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Background/Aims: Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) is a small-vessel vasculitis characterized by rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis (RPGN) and diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH). Management involves a balance between treatment efficacy and adverse events. We report a fatal case of MPA complicated by avacopan-associated vanishing bile duct syndrome (VBDS) in an 80-year-old Japanese male.

Methods: The patient, whose BMI was 18.3 kg/m², presented with MPA. He underwent a triple-therapy regimen of prednisolone (PSL), rituximab, and avacopan. PSL was tapered using the PEXIVAS reduced-dose regimen to minimize glucocorticoid toxicity. Avacopan was introduced for its remission-inducing and steroid-sparing effects (ADVOCATE trial).

Results: MPA flare characterized by DAH and RPGN was observed. Remission with PSL, rituximab, and avacopan (60 mg/day) was achieved. However, avacopan was discontinued on day 59 of treatment because of elevated liver enzymes. Subsequently, liver function deteriorated significantly within days (AST 300 U/L, ALT 558 U/L, T-Bil 9.9 mg/dL) and liver biopsy revealed findings consistent with drug-induced liver injury (DILI) and VBDS. Despite further treatment with PSL, ursodeoxycholic acid, and mycophenolate mofetil, liver function continued to deteriorate, and he succumbed to death on day 25 of treatment.

Conclusion: This case highlights potentially fatal adverse effects of avacopan. The previously reported higher incidence of avacopan-associated DILI in Japanese patients (16.7–26.7%) compared to the ADVOCATE trial (5.4%) suggests a potential genetic predisposition. This risk may be further amplified in high-risk groups as was found in our patient (80 years old, BMI 18.3 kg/m², onset at 59 days), including elderly patients and those with a low BMI, especially with an early onset of symptoms. Our case emphasizes the critical need for meticulous liver function monitoring during avacopan treatment and the consideration of other, safer immunosuppressive agents in patients with multiple high-risk factors for administration of avacopan.

C-048

A gut feeling: eosinophilic gastroenteritis as the masquerading presentation of ANCA-negative EGPA

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Background: Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare vasculitis with a heterogeneous clinical presentation. Gastrointestinal involvement is an uncommon manifestation, particularly as the primary symptom in ANCA-negative patients. Diagnosis is often challenging due to clinical overlap with other eosinophilic disorders, leading to potential delays in therapy.

Methods: A 56-year-old female with a history of adult-onset asthma and chronic eosinophilic rhinosinusitis presented with a one-year history of debilitating epigastric pain, nausea, and vomiting, unresponsive to standard gastritis therapy. A comprehensive workup was performed, including serial blood counts, ANCA serology (p-ANCA, c-ANCA, PR3-ANCA), and extensive endoscopic evaluation with biopsies taken from the oesophagus, stomach, duodenum, ileum, and colon.

Results: Laboratory investigations revealed persistent peripheral eosinophilia with absolute eosinophil counts peaking at 2,304 cells/ μ L. Serological tests for p-ANCA, c-ANCA, and PR3-ANCA were consistently negative. Histopathology from esophagogastroduodenoscopy demonstrated diffuse, marked eosinophilic infiltration without evidence of vasculitis or necrosis. Histopathology from prior sinus surgery also confirmed prominent eosinophilic infiltrates. The constellation of adult-onset asthma, eosinophilic rhinosinusitis, peripheral eosinophilia, and biopsy-proven multi-organ eosinophilic infiltration led to a diagnosis of ANCA-negative EGPA. The patient's gastrointestinal symptoms were refractory to high-dose intravenous corticosteroids but showed significant and sustained resolution following the initiation of Rituximab.

Conclusions: This case highlights that severe, refractory eosinophilic gastroenteritis can be the primary manifestation of ANCA-negative EGPA. This diagnosis should be considered in patients with unexplained eosinophilic gastrointestinal inflammation, particularly with a history of asthma or sinus disease. Negative ANCA serology does not preclude the diagnosis when eosinophilic features dominate. A high index of suspicion is crucial for timely diagnosis and initiation of effective immunomodulatory therapy, such as Rituximab in steroid-refractory cases.

C-049

When eosinophils go rogue: highlighting the overlapping clinical features and treatment paradigms in anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody negative eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis and lymphocytic hypereosinophilic syndrome.

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Background: Hypereosinophilic syndrome (HES) is a heterogeneous disorder encompassing multiple subtypes characterised by eosinophilia greater than $1.5 \times 10^9/L$ on two occasions with evidence of end-organ dysfunction. Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) negative eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) and lymphocytic HES are rare and complex pathologies with multisystem involvement often indistinguishable from a clinical perspective with limited specific biomarkers of disease. Whilst treatment of these conditions is on a case-by-case basis, Interleukin-5 antagonists have become available as targeted mediators of eosinophilic driven inflammation.

Methods: We reviewed two cases of HES admitted under our inpatient Clinical Immunology and Allergy team at Canberra hospital between 2024-2025. Patient one was an 80-year-old woman with a background of breast cancer and asthma. Patient two is a 32-year-old with a background of asthma and eczema.

Results: Patient one had constitutional symptoms with eosinophilic mediated renal, cardiac, pulmonary, peripheral nerve, gastrointestinal, and muscle related organ damage. Peak eosinophilia was $29.41 \times 10^9/L$. A renal biopsy showed extravascular eosinophilic tubular microabscesses and diffuse eosinophilic infiltrate. A clonal T-cell receptor gene rearrangement population was identified. She received pulse methylprednisolone and mepolizumab. She passed away months later from cardiac complications.

Patient two had constitutional symptoms with eosinophilic mediated cardiac, pulmonary, sinus, peripheral nerve, and dermatological related organ damage. Peak eosinophilia was $14.26 \times 10^9/L$, ANCA negative, Troponin 2782 ng/L, and a skin biopsy showed fibrinoid debris with eosinophilic vasculitis. He was treated with pulse methylprednisolone, Rituximab, and mycophenolate.

Conclusions: ANCA negative EGPA and lymphocytic HES are subtypes of HES with overlapping clinical presentations and multi-organ involvement without clear disease biomarkers to distinguish them. These two conditions require multidisciplinary assessment of aetiology and complications to prevent substantial risk of morbidity and mortality. In the era of eosinophil targeted therapy, further research is required to identify useful biomarkers for subtypes of HES.

C-050

A case of treatment-resistant eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis and severe cardiac involvement refractory to multiple therapies

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Background: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare vasculitis characterised by asthma, peripheral eosinophilia and systemic organ involvement. Eosinophilic myocarditis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality.

Case Presentation: A 35-year-old man presented with purpuric rash, abdominal pain, dyspnoea and a history of asthma. Investigations revealed eosinophils $34 \times 10^9/L$, troponin 500ng/L and negative anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies. Cardiac magnetic resonance imaging confirmed a non-dilated left ventricle with widespread myocardial oedema consistent with eosinophilic myocarditis. Bone marrow biopsy showed 50–60% eosinophils without clonal morphology. Eosinophilia fluorescence in situ hybridisation panel was negative.

He received intravenous (IV) methylprednisolone and oral corticosteroids (1mg/kg), achieving only transient improvement, with eosinophilia recurring when the prednisolone was reduced below 40mg. Over 3 months, despite 6 doses of IV cyclophosphamide (cumulative 6g) in combination with mepolizumab 300mg every 4 weeks, he experienced frequent relapses with recurrent eosinophilia, colitis and myocarditis requiring repeated steroid pulses, complicated by episodes of sepsis. Owing to refractory disease, 5 cycles of plasma exchange were undertaken without benefit, followed by 4 additional doses of IV cyclophosphamide.

Interval cardiac imaging at 6 months demonstrated an inflammatory right atrial thrombus, for which he was anticoagulated, and persistent late gadolinium enhancement consistent with ongoing myocardial inflammation despite prednisolone 20mg with mycophenolic acid 760mg bd. Given the cumulative steroid burden and refractory disease, alemtuzumab 30mg was trialled but led to a paradoxical eosinophil rise. Imatinib was approved for 2 months without improvement.

Benralizumab was then initiated at 8-weekly intervals, later increased to 4-weekly due to breakthrough eosinophilia, achieving stable control. Six months later eosinophils are $<1 \times 10^9/L$ on benralizumab and prednisolone 15mg daily, his lowest maintenance dose.

Conclusions: This case highlights the challenge of managing aggressive, multi-organ EGPA with refractory hyper eosinophilia. It underscores the limited efficacy of multiple therapies and the role of benralizumab in severe, refractory disease.

C-051

Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis presenting with myositis.

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Background: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a systemic necrotizing vasculitis that affects small to medium sized vessels. Myalgias are often a common symptom of EGPA. However, it is rarely the main presenting symptom and typically not associated with weakness. We describe a rare case of a patient presenting with eosinophilic myositis, who subsequently developed EGPA.

Methods: Review the past clinical history and literature.

Results: A 59-year-old male with no relevant past history and no known drug allergies was admitted to the Stroke Unit for suspected lacunar ischemic stroke. The patient has a low-grade fever of up to 37.8°C and blood tests show elevated acute-phase reactants. He reports generalized syndrome and leg pain over the past week. A thoracoabdominal Computed Tomography (CT) scan was performed, with findings compatible with an inflammatory process of the small airways affecting the middle lobe and both lower lobes. Blood tests were performed, which showed eosinophilia (15.6%, $2 \times 10^9/L$) with tumour markers (negative), serologies (negative) and autoimmunity with positive antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies PR3-ANCA (antiproteinase-3). Suspecting possible myopathy, secondary to vasculitis, a biopsy of the left medial gastrocnemius muscle was performed, which showed necrotizing vasculitis with eosinophil infiltrate. Treatment with methylprednisolone and azathioprine was started, in addition to a rehabilitation program with satisfactory progress.

Conclusions: Our case report and literature review highlights the importance of recognizing myositis as an initial presenting symptom of EGPA, providing an opportunity for early diagnosis and treatment to reduce risk of further disease progression and morbidity. The presence of PR3-ANCA may indicate a subtype of EGPA with particular clinical and prognostic characteristics.

C-052

Recurrent haemoptysis due to hypertrophied bronchial artery as onset of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background: Eosinophilic Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (EGPA) is primarily characterized with late-onset asthma in nearly all patients (95–100%). Causes of haemoptysis in EGPA patients are pulmonary capillaritis and diffuse alveolar haemorrhage affecting to 4% of patients.

Methods: We described the first clinical case report of a hypertrophied bronchial artery secondary to EGPA.

Results : A 77 year-old woman referred for consultation for suspected food allergy due to episodes of rash. She did not respond to antihistamines. On the other hand, in the last month she reported asthenia and muscle weakness in the lower extremities. In the last two weeks, she had paraesthesia and numbness in her left foot and the right hand. She also had self-limited episodes of recurrent haemoptysis probably related to parenchymal sequelae due to a history of hydatidosis. She was diagnosed of asthma during 10 years and she was on treatment with fluticasone and vilanterol with no frequent exacerbations or nasal symptoms. Laboratory tests showed peripheral eosinophilia (43%), with elevated CK, myoglobin and C-reactive protein and elevated BNP. ANCA-P (anti-myeloperoxidase) antibodies were positive. A skin biopsy was performed, compatible with cutaneous vasculitis. Computed Tomography Pulmonary Angiography (CTPA) was performed and showed a hypertrophied bronchial artery (3.5 mm) originating from the anterior aortic margin at T6 level and heading towards the right hilum. A bronchial artery embolization was performed. Methylprednisolone and mepolizumab were started. The patient is stable with no new episodes of haemoptysis after 3 months of treatment.

Conclusions: Hypertrophied bronchial artery could be a cause of haemoptysis secondary to EGPA.

C-053

A case of EGPA-associated glomerulonephritis treated with glucocorticoids and an anti-IL-5 Agent

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Background: While anti-IL-5 agents are established for treating non-severe eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA), their role in severe manifestations, such as glomerulonephritis, remains unclear.

Methods: We report the case of EGPA with renal involvement treated with medium-dose of glucocorticoids and an anti-IL-5 agent.

Results: This is a 75-year-old woman with a history of probable eosinophilic sinusitis who presented with worsening renal function, proteinuria, haematuria, and neuropathy. Laboratory findings included an eosinophil count of 3,290/ μ L, a creatinine level of 1.33 mg/dL, and positive MPO-ANCA. A kidney biopsy revealed pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis, and nerve conduction studies were consistent with mononeuritis multiplex. A diagnosis of EGPA was made, and the patient was treated with moderate-dose glucocorticoids and mepolizumab, based on her preference to avoid immunosuppressive agents during the COVID-19 pandemic. Following treatment, the patient's renal function improved, with her creatinine level decreasing to 0.9 mg/dL, and ANCA became negative. Glucocorticoids were successfully tapered and discontinued after 10 months. Her disease has remained in remission for three years on mepolizumab monotherapy. Throughout this period, her ANCA titres have remained negative.

Conclusions: This case demonstrates the successful treatment of severe, ANCA-positive EGPA with renal involvement using a combination of moderate-dose glucocorticoids and an anti-IL-5 agent, without immunosuppressants. This outcome suggests that the role of anti-IL-5 agents in severe EGPA warrants further investigation. The results of the upcoming E-MERGE trial are eagerly awaited to provide more definitive evidence.

C-054

When youth meets vasculitis: a rare case of early-onset EGPA

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Background: Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) is a rare ANCA-associated vasculitis that usually presents in the fourth decade of life with asthma, eosinophilia and multi-organ involvement. It is very uncommon in younger patients. We describe the case of a 24-year-old gentleman with an unusual early-onset presentation of EGPA, aiming to highlight the diagnostic challenges and importance of timely treatment.

Methods: This is a single case report. Clinical history, laboratory findings, treatment and follow-up were reviewed and summarised.

Results: The patient, a 24-year-old student, had an atypical presentation which was fairly acute first developed asthma, cough, wheeze and nasal congestion three months prior to admission. He experienced >2 stone weight loss over one year and later developed right knee pain, vasculitic rash on hands and a leg, and progressive sciatica-like symptoms leading to left foot drop. Blood tests showed marked eosinophilia ($11 \times 10^9/L$) and raised inflammatory markers, with negative ANCA and ANA. No Raynaud's or CTD features present. His imaging (CT TAP) showed no lung pathology or malignancy. Other aetiologies such as infection were excluded.

He was diagnosed with EGPA and commenced on high-dose corticosteroids with rituximab induction (in July–August 2025). He has currently ongoing physiotherapy rehabilitation. The patient responded very well with recovery of foot strength, improvement in systemic symptoms and remains under follow-up on tapering steroids and maintenance therapy. If progressive disease, plan is to go for Cyclophosphamide.

Conclusions: This case highlights an unusual early-onset presentation of EGPA in a 24-year-old, manifesting with peripheral neuropathy and systemic features. Clinicians should consider EGPA even in younger adults presenting with asthma, eosinophilia and neuropathy, as early diagnosis and prompt immunosuppression can significantly improve outcomes. Another point to highlight is CYC use can effect Gonadal function in both sexes. We need to counsel/ discussion about cryopreservation.

C-055

Neurocognitive and cardiac manifestations in eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis

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Background: Memory loss is a distressing symptom in adulthood that can be a sign of an underlying cranial dysfunction or an even wider systemic issue.

Methods: The patient's history, tests and treatments were gathered following verbal consent and documentation in records.

Results: This is a case of a 48-year old Caucasian male with a history of adult-onset asthma and nasal polyposis presenting with transient global amnesia (TGA). Investigations revealed a normal computed tomography (CT) scan of brain, raised white cell count and eosinophilia. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain was planned, but patient self-discharged and consulted a private neurologist. During this consultation, he was found to have angina-like symptoms and splinter haemorrhages. Tests revealed persistent eosinophilia and growth of *Micrococcus Luteus* in blood culture prompting re-admission to his local hospital within 2 weeks from initial presentation.

Although suspicious of infective endocarditis, the combination of a negative transthoracic echocardiogram, eosinophilia ($2.6 \times 10^9/L$), elevated troponin (147 ng/L), high fractional exhaled nitric oxide (252 ppb), and multiple territory embolic infarcts in MRI of the brain, led to a working diagnosis of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA) with myocarditis and cerebral embolic infarcts. He received intravenous methylprednisolone and subsequently prednisolone before transferring to a tertiary hospital under the care of a vasculitis specialist.

Further tests excluded infective endocarditis and the diagnosis of EGPA was supported by a positive p-ANCA, low PR3 titre and cardiac MRI showing non-ischaemic dilated cardiomyopathy secondary to EGPA. Induction cyclophosphamide was given and his symptoms gradually improved. The patient will receive outpatient cyclophosphamide infusions with interval cardiac MRI for monitoring.

Conclusion: This case highlights that cardiac and cranial nerve system involvement in EGPA is rare but possible. Aggressive immunosuppressive therapy is necessary with severe disease and CNS involvement; however, deep-seated infections must be fully investigated before initiation of immunosuppressive treatment.

C-056

The late surprise

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Background: EGPA is an eosinophil rich small vessel vasculitis that typically manifests with sinopulmonary disease, with a subset of patients presenting with other manifestations e.g. neuropathy, glomerulonephritis and/or cardiac involvement. We describe a case of EGPA with late cardiac involvement 26 years after the initial diagnosis of EGPA.

Case Presentation: Mrs U, a 75-year-old ethnically European female presented with syncope, on the background of well controlled ANCA negative EGPA on long term maintenance therapy with tapering mycophenolate. Her initial presentation in 1998 was with eosinophilia, asthma with sinopulmonary involvement. Her last clinical flare was in 2022 with constitutional symptoms and eosinophilia. As part of her syncope investigation, she was noted to have eosinophilia, elevated CRP, Troponin and BNP. Further work up with a cardiac MRI demonstrated a subacute thrombus at distal LV and RV, LV myocardial scar (by LGE), and oedema at distal LV and apex. This typical “sandwich” appearance of eosinophilic myocarditis can be seen in EGPA. Her eosinophil cationic protein was significantly elevated at >200 ug/L. Given the cardiac imaging findings, known history of EGPA, rising eosinophilia and normal coronary angiogram, we managed her as EGPA with late, new onset cardiac involvement. She was treated with combination therapy with corticosteroid, rituximab and warfarin. Mrs. U made a sustained clinical, biochemical and radiological improvement with the combination therapy. Mepolizumab and Benralizumab are being considered as maintenance therapy but there are no international guidelines currently on this as yet. Monitoring serum biomarkers to aid precision medicine may be useful in the future in the management of EGPA.

Conclusions: This case highlights the diagnostic, monitoring and management strategy of late onset cardiac involvement with EGPA. We will also review the current relevant literature on presentation, diagnosis (serology, imaging, biopsy and ancillary tests), management and ongoing research in this field.

C-057

A rare case of undifferentiated connective tissue disease with low level PR3-ANCA then subsequent diagnosis of anti-GBM Disease

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Case Presentation: A 62 year old male was seen in May 2024 by Rheumatologist for joint swelling and rash. He was diagnosed with undifferentiated connective tissue disease. (ANA weakly positive, strongly positive IG M >679, beta 2 glycoprotein IG M >400, low C4 <0.03 (0.14-0.54 g/L) and pr3 of 8.6 (0-3 IU/ml). He was given hydroxychloroquine.

He then presented to us with pulmonary renal syndrome acute renal failure around October 2024. He was dialysis dependent soon after the presentation. His Anti-GBM titre came back as 500 U/ml (0-7). His haemoglobin had dropped from 120 to 86 g/l but he denied haemoptysis. He was also on oxygen 2 -3 litres. HRCT revealed multi focal areas of consolidation and inflammatory appearing lung nodule.

He had diarrhoea too and was diagnosed with Clostridium Difficile which was started treated with oral vancomycin. Patient was started on intravenous antibiotics intravenous to cover for chest infection.

He had 3 pulses of methylprednisolone and weaning dose of oral prednisolone as well as Dialysis line for Dialysis and Plasma Exchange. Once antibiotics were over, we also started cyclophosphamide with cotrimoxazole cover for 3 month. 14 session of PLEX were done . His Anti-GBM titres are now negative and he is still dialysis dependent.

C-058

A rare case of membranous nephropathy coexisting with anti-glomerular basement membrane disease

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Case Presentation: A 76-year-old patient with a history of Primary Membranous Nephropathy (MN) diagnosed 20 years ago, was treated with Cyclophosphamide with good effect. In 2022, he had a cysto-prostatectomy with ileal conduit formation due to muscle invasive bladder cancer. In May 2023, he was admitted to the hospital with vomiting, flank pain and cloudy urine. Urine culture grew Klebsiella and he was treated with intravenous antibiotics. He also had an Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) Stage 3 and Non-Contrast CT Kidney Ureter Bladder showed right sided hydronephrosis. Following Uro-Radiology Multidisciplinary Team's discussion, patient underwent a right sided nephrostomy. Unfortunately, he became and remained dialysis dependent via a tunnelled line. Subsequently, he developed haemoptysis with new oxygen requirement. CT Pulmonary Angiogram (CTPA) showed congestive lung appearances with ground-glass opacification, bronchitis change, interlobular septal thickening and no evidence of pulmonary embolism possibly suggesting Pulmonary Haemorrhage. His Anti-Glomerular Basement Membrane (Anti-GBM) titres were requested due to haemoptysis and results came back positive > 680 U/ml. At the same time, it was worth noting that there was a flare up of MN as evidenced by increased Anti-Phospholipase A2 Receptor Antibody level (PLAR2). The cause of his AKI was multifactorial namely Obstructive Uropathy, Sepsis, MN, as well as Anti-GBM disease. He had intravenous Methylprednisolone for three consecutive days followed by a weaning regime of oral Prednisolone and then had Plasma Exchange (PLEX) due to ongoing haemoptysis. He also had his first dose of Rituximab and was discharged. His Anti-GBM titres on discharge was 268 U/ml. Unfortunately, 12 days later he was readmitted with further haemoptysis and had further PLEX and second dose of Rituximab.

Conclusions: Co-existence of MN followed by Anti-GBM disease is a rare occurrence postulated to be either genetic or immune complex related effect on GBM. Treatment focused on controlling Anti-GBM disease involvement in lungs.

C-059

Infection-triggered anti-GBM antibody positivity without vasculitis: a case report

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Case Presentation: This case highlights the importance of interpreting anti-glomerular basement membrane (GBM) titres with caution, ensuring correlation with clinical findings and biopsy evidence, particularly in the context of concurrent infection. We describe a 46-year-old man with a long history of poorly controlled type 1 diabetes mellitus and presumed diabetic kidney disease who presented with acute kidney injury (AKI) in the setting of severe sepsis due to bronchopneumonia. His baseline eGFR of 45 mL/min/1.73 m² had declined to 9 mL/min/1.73 m² over 10 days.

Given strongly positive anti-glomerular basement membrane (GBM) serology, he was treated empirically with plasma exchange and immunosuppression for possible anti-GBM-associated vasculitis, in addition to prolonged antibiotics for his bronchopneumonia. Renal biopsy was not pursued at that time due to underlying mental health issues.

Immunosuppression was continued for six months, complicated by intercurrent infections. On follow-up, his eGFR improved to 35 mL/min/1.73 m², and anti-GBM titres became negative.

Eighteen months later, he re-presented with a similar clinical picture of AKI, bronchopneumonia, and recurrent positive anti-GBM serology. This time he was agreeable to biopsy. CT chest revealed a calcified bronchial lesion, and bronchoscopy raised concern for malignancy; however, histology confirmed *Actinomyces* infection. Renal biopsy subsequently showed no evidence of vasculitis. Both his renal function and anti-GBM titre improved with targeted antimicrobial therapy alone.

Conclusions: This case suggests that chronic infection with *Actinomyces* was the likely trigger for anti-GBM antibody production. Chronic infections are known to activate autoreactive T and B cells, promoting autoantibody formation - a mechanism well described in the literature.

C-060

Seronegative relapsed anti-glomerular basement membrane disease

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Case Presentation: A 28-year-old male with no comorbidities presented with a five-week history of haemoptysis, dyspnoea, acute kidney injury and haematuria. His medical history included a previously treated episode of antibody-positive anti-GBM disease in 2018. He had received plasma exchange, pulse methylprednisolone and subsequent tapering course of prednisolone and cyclophosphamide (cumulative dose 6700mg), until anti-GBM titres remained negative. He achieved remission within 6 months, renal function normal throughout.

He re-presented in 2023 with pulmonary haemorrhage, haemoglobin 63g/L, creatinine peak 289 µmol/L, proteinuria (~1.4g/mmol) and anti-GBM negative. Renal biopsy demonstrated linear IgG GBM staining and crescentic glomerulonephritis on immunofluorescence, consistent with anti-GBM disease and minimal chronic damage. Although seronegative for anti-GBM, he was treated with seventeen sessions of plasma exchange, pulse methylprednisolone with tapering prednisolone, cyclophosphamide (cumulative dose 7750mg), and rituximab, with treatment guided by resolution of haemoptysis and improvement in renal function, serum albumin and proteinuria. He achieved remission at three months.

Anti-GBM disease is typically a monophasic illness. The ELISA test for anti-GBM antibodies is highly sensitive (>95%) and specific (>97%) wherein α3(IV)NC1 is primarily targeted. KDIGO recommends plasma exchange until anti-GBM titres are no longer detectable. However, management is challenging for seronegative anti-GBM disease due to its rarity and lack of evidence-based guidelines, and may be under recognised due to variations in antibody epitopes or antigenic targets.

Laminin-521 (LM521) has been identified as a new autoantigen in anti-GBM disease. However, its frequent co-occurrence with α3(IV)NC1 antibodies complicates efforts to establish its role in the disease's pathogenesis. The breakthrough detection of LM521 in the absence of α3(IV)NC1 antibodies constitutes a significant advancement.

Conclusion: Our case highlights the need to consider atypical relapsed anti-GBM disease in pulmonary-renal syndrome even in seronegative patients that have previously been anti-GBM antibody positive. Further understanding of LM521 or other potential unidentified pathogenic epitopes is needed.

C-061

Treatment of dual-positive anti-glomerular basement membrane and ANCA disease using rituximab in addition to plasma exchange, corticosteroids, and cyclophosphamide

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Background: Anti-glomerular basement membrane (anti-GBM) disease is a rare autoimmune disorder characterised by pathogenic circulating autoantibodies against the glomerular basement membrane. Standard of care generally includes glucocorticoids, plasma exchange, and cyclophosphamide to rapidly reduce pathogenic autoantibody levels. Rituximab has been described as a viable option for refractory disease. This is the first published case report of a transgender man with anti-GBM disease. Despite a number of poor prognostic factors, the patient achieved renal recovery using rituximab in addition to standard care.

Case Presentation: A 21-year-old transgender man (female sex) presented with bilateral flank pain and oliguria. Investigations revealed an initial creatinine of 374 µmol/L which doubled to 619 µmol/L by day 3 of admission. Anti-GBM titre was strongly positive at 688 U/mL and MPO antibody titre was low positive. Renal biopsy revealed diffuse, crescentic glomerulonephritis with 23 of 32 (71%) glomeruli containing cellular crescents and immunohistochemistry consistent with anti-GBM glomerulonephritis.

The patient was treated with plasma exchange (total of 37 exchanges), 3g of IV methylprednisolone induction in divided doses followed by 1mg/kg oral prednisolone daily, and 100mg oral cyclophosphamide daily. The patient commenced haemodialysis on day 10. Despite an initial decline, the anti-GBM titre increased to 127 U/mL 21 days after first plasma exchange. The patient was then given 1g IV rituximab in 2 doses, 14 days apart. The anti-GBM titre steadily declined and became undetectable within 1 month. By 6 months, there was evidence of renal recovery and the patient ceased dialysis. At 2 years, the patient's creatinine is 157 and eGFR 53.

Conclusion: This case report adds to the existing evidence supporting the use of rituximab for treatment of refractory anti-GBM disease.

C-062

Two cases of ANCA-positive anti-GBM disease in patients with Sjögren's disease carrying HLA-DRB1*1501

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Background: Anti-glomerular basement membrane (GBM) disease and Sjögren's disease (SjD) have been linked to HLA-DRB1*1501, but their coexistence is rarely documented. Anti-GBM disease is occasionally accompanied by anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA), suggesting overlap with ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV).

Case Presentations: Case 1: A 76-year-old woman presented with acute kidney injury (serum creatinine 3.26 mg/dL) accompanied by haematuria. Both anti-GBM antibodies (91.9 U/mL) and myeloperoxidase (MPO)-ANCA (13.0 U/mL) were detected. Kidney biopsy showed crescentic glomerulonephritis with linear capillary IgG deposition. Furthermore, positivity for anti-SS-A/B antibodies and a positive Schirmer's test, along with T cell and plasma cell infiltration into kidney interstitial tissue, revealing the presence of SjD related interstitial nephritis. The patient was given the standard treatment for GBM disease comprised corticosteroids, cyclophosphamide and plasma exchange, but kidney function did not recover.

Case 2: A 71-year-old woman with a 10-year history of SjD presented with kidney dysfunction (serum creatinine 1.68 mg/dL) and haematuria. MPO-ANCA (290 U/mL) and anti-GBM antibodies (13.8 U/mL) were detected. Kidney biopsy showed pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis, without linear IgG deposition. Treatment with corticosteroids, rituximab, and avacopan for predominant AAV induced remission.

HLA typing of both cases revealed the presence of HLA-DRB1*1501.

Conclusions: We first report patients carrying HLA-DRB1*1501 with concurrent SjD, with ANCA and anti-GBM antibody. This HLA allele may provide an immunogenetic background predisposing to SjD and anti-GBM disease pathology, whereas it is not recognised as a susceptibility gene for AAV. In case 1, GBM disease was predominant, while in case 2, AAV was predominant. In the former, ANCA positivity might represent a secondary phenomenon related to anti-GBM-induced neutrophil activation. In the latter, pre-existing ANCA-mediated neutrophil activation in the glomeruli might have led to epitope spreading and anti-GBM autoantibody production. Taken together, careful evaluation of immunogenetic background and ANCA status is important in patients with systemic autoimmune diseases.

C-063

Case report: giant cell arteritis and persistent placoid maculopathy - multimodal imaging and management challenges

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Case Presentation: A myopic 59 year-old woman presented with temporal headaches, photopsias and central visual abnormalities in her left eye with jaw claudication, fevers, erythrocyte sedimentation rate 22 and C reactive protein 26. Ultrasound showed thickening of the right temporal artery wall. Temporal artery biopsy confirmed the presence of giant cell arteritis (GCA). Ophthalmic findings were not typical of arteritic ischaemic optic neuropathy.

MRI excluded cerebral vasculitis. Retinal photography, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), OCT Angiography, Fundus Fluorescein Angiography and Indocyanine Green Angiography showed macular placoid lesions involving the outer retina, retinal pigment epithelium and sub-foveal choroidal circulation with the primary lesion thought to be at the level of the choriocapillaris. A diagnosis of persistent placoid maculopathy (PPM) in the setting of GCA was made.

Management has included pulsed intravenous methylprednisolone (PIVMP) followed by tapering oral prednisolone, tocilizumab (ceased-diverticulitis), methotrexate (ceased-deranged liver enzymes), PIVMP again, leflunomide (ceased-peripheral neuropathy), secukinumab (ceased-steroid sparing failure) and now upadacitinib with 7.5mg prednisolone and repeated intravitreal dexamethasone implants.

Photopsias are reduced but persist, neovascularisation is thus far absent but vision has not returned to normal and imaging confirms that the choriocapillaris has failed to reperfuse.

Conclusions: Two previous associations of PPM with GCA have been reported, suggesting common vasculitic aetiologies. Large vessel vasculitis in GCA is accompanied by occlusion of the vasa vasorum as well as occlusion of the arterial lumen both by inflammatory infiltration and by the mass effect of neovascularisation within the vessel wall. In this patient visual symptoms have occurred as a result of irreversible non perfusion of the macular choriocapillaris which may be analogous to the vasa vasorum. Immunosuppression is preventing progression of the placoid lesions and to date has prevented neovascularisation. It has not allowed reperfusion of the choriocapillaris. Vasa vasorum injury in GCA may also be permanent.

C-064

Polymyalgia rheumatica and large vessel vasculitis coexistence: insights from a case in regional Victoria

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Background: Polymyalgia rheumatica (PMR) is characterised by onset of symmetrical pain and morning stiffness affecting the shoulders and hip girdle, alongside a wasting syndrome of fever, anorexia and weight loss. A proportion of patients with PMR also have subclinical large vessel vasculitis (LVV). We present a case from regional Victoria where 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose (18F-FDG) Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging was pivotal in confirming PMR with concurrent LVV.

Case presentation: A 64-year-old man from regional Victoria presented with a 3-month history of profound 18kg weight loss, abdominal pain, fatigue, bilateral shoulder pain without temporal headache or jaw claudication. Examination showed pain and stiffness with shoulder girdle movements, but no synovitis or temporal artery tenderness. Laboratory tests revealed elevated inflammatory markers, normocytic anaemia, mild hypoalbuminaemia and elevated IgG4 levels. Colonoscopy confirmed mild diverticulitis as the cause for rectal wall thickening initially identified on CT. Shoulder MRI revealed signal abnormalities involving the rotator cuff muscles with a negative myositis and extended autoimmune screen. Subsequent 18F-FDG-PET demonstrated uptake in a PMR distribution, at the shoulders and trochanteric regions, with additional increased arterial wall uptake in the thoracic aorta and bilateral subclavian arteries consistent with LVV. The patient was commenced on high-dose prednisolone and an IL-6 inhibitor tocilizumab with clinical and biochemical improvement.

Conclusion: This case highlights the diagnostic challenges of identifying PMR with overlapping LVV. The patient had a complex presentation, requiring the exclusion of vasculitis mimics. The use of 18F-FDG-PET was pivotal in detecting PMR with concomitant extra-cranial LVV, changing the patient's treatment trajectory. Despite its diagnostic value, access to PET in regional settings can be limited by cost, geographic and logistical challenges. Current prediction models for identifying subclinical GCA or LVV in PMR demonstrate modest accuracy, underscoring the need for advanced imaging modalities to improve detection, refine diagnostic pathways, and guide individualised management.

C-065

An atypical presentation of giant cell arteritis: a case report

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Case Presentation: A 62-year-old man presented with a two-week history of progressive bilateral temporal swelling. There was no history of headache, vision loss, jaw claudication or constitutional symptoms. Upon admission, physical examination revealed significant bilateral temporal swelling which was mildly tender on palpation with a normal ocular and otoscopic examination bilaterally. Initial investigations revealed elevated inflammatory markers C-reactive protein 160mg/l (normal <10mg/l) and Erythrocyte Sediment Rate 58mm (normal <12mm). Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) of the brain and orbits revealed significant myositis of the temporal muscles bilaterally with abnormal enhancement of the bilateral superficial temporal arteries, highly suggestive of Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA). Bilateral temporal artery biopsy was pursued; however, a Temporalis muscle biopsy was not performed due to concerns for risk of functional complications outweighing the yield of sampling. Positron Emission Tomography-Computed Tomography revealed inflammation in the bilateral Temporalis muscles, but no evidence of extra-cranial involvement.

Differential diagnosis included infection, infiltrative process, or a paraneoplastic myositis. Temporal artery biopsy was consistent with active GCA, confirming the diagnosis.

The patient was treated with oral corticosteroid therapy at a dose of 1mg/kg. There was significant clinical improvement in the temporal region swelling and reduction in inflammatory markers with corticosteroid monotherapy within 72 hours. Subcutaneous Tocilizumab 162mg weekly was added as additional therapy and corticosteroid therapy weaned.

Conclusions: Our case highlights the importance of considering temporal swelling as a first clinical presentation of GCA. Temporalis muscle involvement in GCA although previously described histologically(1) and radiologically (2), is not well reported as an isolated clinical manifestation. Additionally, this case highlights the key role MRI can play in identifying atypical presentations of cranial GCA.

C-066

Pneumocystis jirovecii and Aspergillus fumigatus co-infection in a patient with giant-cell arteritis

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Background: Giant Cell Arteritis (GCA) is a systemic necrotizing vasculitis for which the only effective treatment is systemic corticosteroids. We evaluated a patient with GCA who eventually died from pulmonary aspergillosis and pneumocystis after 6 weeks beginning corticosteroid treatment and tocilizumab . Reports of such co-infection are rare in the literature.

Methods: Review the clinical past history and literature.

Results: An 82-year-old patient presented with a severe headache in the occipital region and radiated to the frontal area on both sides. she also reported blurred vision. She also experienced jaw pain and fatigue when chewing. She was seen in the dental department with a tongue ulcer. The analysis showed elevated acute phase reactants with CRP of 74.4 mg/L. A Doppler ultrasound showed a periarterial hypoechoic halo suggestive of arteritis in the right frontal branch and possible halo sign in the left vertebral, V1 portion. PET scan confirmed arteritis in vertebral arteries. A diagnosis of GCA was made and treatment with steroids and subcutaneous tocilizumab was started. Six weeks into treatment, the patient was readmitted with pneumonia with bilateral infiltrates on Thoracic CT . Bronchoscopy with bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) was performed and CRP was positive for pneumocystis jirovecii and aspergillus fumigatus. Treatment was started with isavuconazole 200 mg/24 hours, clindamycin 450 mg/6 hours and primaquine 30 g/ 24 hours. Two weeks after starting treatment, the patient developed shock and died.

Conclusions: A high index of suspicion for infections with opportunistic organisms should be maintained in patients with GCA receiving corticosteroids and tocilizumab.

C-067

“Salvage” therapy with tocilizumab in giant cell arteritis with threatened vision despite glucocorticoids: more evidence is needed before routine use

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Background: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is a major cause of irreversible blindness in adults. For threatened vision despite early initiation of glucocorticoids, clinicians may administer off-label tocilizumab therapy before a diagnosis of GCA is confirmed. This expensive approach, largely based on case reports, may not improve patient outcomes.

Case Presentation: A 70-year-old male with type 2 diabetes, hypertension, hyperlipidaemia and 25 pack-year smoking history was admitted with delayed presentation of acute right lateral medullary stroke. There were non-stenotic plaques in vertebral arteries bilaterally on CT angiography. C-reactive protein was 57.5mg/L. He was managed with dual antiplatelet therapy. Visual acuity at the time was 6/7.5 (right) and 6/15 (left).

Sixteen weeks later, he was re-admitted with worsening ataxia, vertigo and new left sided limb weakness. C-reactive protein was 63.5mg/L, erythrocyte sedimentation rate was 62mm/hr; CT angiography showed interval progression of multifocal stenoses affecting bilateral vertebral arteries and left internal carotid artery. A diagnosis of GCA was finally considered, with subsequent FDG-PET showing uptake in these vessels. There was no light perception in the left eye, with retinal detachment and a pale optic disc. Right eye acuity was 6/9.5, with normal optic disc and retinal vessels. Pulsed intravenous methylprednisolone 1g daily for three days was initiated. Transient visual obscurations were reported after the second dose of intravenous methylprednisolone. “Salvage” therapy with intravenous tocilizumab 8mg/kg was administered based on published case report data prior to referral to our service.

Four weeks later, visual acuity and ophthalmic examination findings had not significantly changed.

Conclusions: Fulminant vision loss during initial pulse glucocorticoid therapy may not represent treatment failure, and may simply reflect the severity of late-presenting GCA. Although urgent acute tocilizumab appears to be an attractive option given supportive case reports, publication bias needs to be considered in the absence of randomized control trial evidence.

C-068

Real world case series of upadacitinib for refractory giant cell arteritis

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Background: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) is commonly refractory to conventional immunosuppression. Whilst IL-6 inhibition has advanced management, relapse remains common, particularly post-cessation. There is a clear unmet need for novel therapeutic approaches for refractory GCA. Upadacitinib recently demonstrated superiority over placebo (46.4% vs 29.0% sustained remission, 52-weeks) in newly diagnosed or relapsing cases who had not previously failed IL-6 inhibition. The benefit of upadacitinib in refractory GCA has yet to be reported.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective review of refractory GCA patients, defined as inadequate response to methotrexate, mycophenolate and tocilizumab, treated with upadacitinib. Baseline and outcome data were extracted from electronic hospital records. All cases were diagnostically confirmed by temporal artery biopsy or large vessel imaging and were followed up for at least 6 months. The primary outcome was sustained remission at 6 months, defined as lack of clinical relapse and prednisolone dose (<5mg), in line with EULAR-2018 definitions.

Results: N=4 patients were identified (mean age 72.5 years SD 11.56, female 3/4, mean disease duration 6.75 years SD 2.99). N=2 patients were histologically confirmed, and n=2 were diagnosed on PET/CT. Sustained remission was achieved by 3/4 patients (median prednisolone dose 4mg IQR 2.25-6.25), including one patient achieving steroid free remission. One patient experienced a possible minor relapse and was switched to mycophenolate, following 7 months of treatment. All cases tolerated upadacitinib well with no evidence of gastrointestinal upset, cytopenias or significant infections.

Conclusions: We present positive real-world experience of using upadacitinib in a small but challenging cohort of refractory GCA, encompassing both cranial and large-vessel phenotypes.

C-069

Novel use of vasodilators in managing tongue ischaemia in giant cell arteritis

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Background: Tongue ischaemia and infarction are rare but serious complications of giant cell arteritis (GCA) and may occur despite high dose corticosteroid therapy. We present a case of biopsy-proven GCA in which vasodilatory therapy was successfully used alongside corticosteroids, tocilizumab and upadacitinib, to prevent progression to tongue infarction.

Case Presentation: An 82 year old female with comorbidities of hypertension and dyslipidaemia presented with bitemporal headache, jaw and tongue claudication, weight loss and left eye visual loss. Examination revealed left sided arteritic ischaemic optic neuropathy (AION). Inflammatory markers were elevated, and Computed Tomography (CT) brain with angiography was unremarkable. Pulsed methylprednisolone 1000mg daily was initiated on admission. Despite ongoing pulsed corticosteroid, she developed right eye visual loss on day 4, with features of evolving AION. Tocilizumab 400mg intravenous was administered and pulsed methylprednisolone was continued for a total of 5 days.

On day 5 she developed acute tongue ischaemia with severe tongue pain, pallor and lactatemia. A topical glyceryl trinitrate patch was applied to the neck, resulting in rapid restoration of tongue perfusion and normalisation of lactate level. On day 6 she was commenced on 3 consecutive daily doses of intravenous Iloprost and Upadacitinib 15mg daily was added. Her right eye vision stabilised and her ischaemic tongue symptoms gradually resolved. Temporal artery biopsy confirmed active GCA. She was discharged on a tapering course of corticosteroids, tocilizumab and nifedipine, without recurrence of tongue symptoms.

Conclusions: Tongue ischaemia is a rare and challenging manifestation of GCA. Vasodilatory therapy may serve as a useful adjunct to immunosuppression in restoring perfusion and preventing infarction.

C-070

Coronary artery disease presented with heart failure in a patient with Takayasu arteritis: a case report

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Background: Takayasu's Arteritis (TAK) is a form of large vessel vasculitis, mainly affecting the aorta and its major branches. Coronary arteries may be involved in patients with TAK and present with atypical symptoms.

Methods: Electronic medical chart, laboratory database, and image study review.

Results: We present the case of a 55-year-old woman with a history of TAK diagnosed at 53 years of age. The initial presentations upon diagnosis included retinal ischemia, highly elevated ESR & CRP levels, and wall thickening over the brachiocephalic, left common carotid, left subclavian arteries orifice, and aortic arch. She suffered from an ischemic stroke due to occlusion of the vertebral artery 2 months after the diagnosis and started receiving steroids, methotrexate, and tocilizumab for control of her TAK.

The patient's ESR and CRP levels decreased rapidly within normal limits after initiating treatment, and her clinical conditions remained stable under weekly methotrexate and tocilizumab. However, she suffered from intermittent dyspnoea a month before our assessment, but without the presence of cough, chest tightness, or angina. A chest computed tomography detected bilateral pleural effusion, while cardiac sonography revealed regional akinesia with impaired contractility of the left ventricle. A cardiac magnetic resonance imaging was arranged, with findings suggestive of recent myocardial infarction and ischemic cardiomyopathy. Chronic ischemia in the apex, anteroseptal, and apical anterior walls was also noted on the thallium scan.

Coronary angiography was eventually performed, revealing a total occlusion of the proximal left anterior descending artery. A drug-eluting stent was placed successfully. Her cardiopulmonary symptoms diminished after the procedure.

Conclusions: TAK patients face increased heart disease risk due to potential valvular issues, myocarditis, pericarditis, or coronary lesions. As seen in our case, clinical signs and risk factors may be atypical. Symptoms like dyspnoea warrant further evaluation, even if inflammatory markers are normal.

C-071

Takayasu arteritis presenting as acute middle cerebral artery stroke in a young woman: a case report

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Background: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a rare large-vessel vasculitis predominantly affecting young women. It may present with constitutional symptoms such as fever, weight loss, and fatigue, but can progress to vascular stenoses resulting in limb ischaemia, coronary disease, and cerebrovascular events. Stroke occurs in up to one-third of patients, most often due to carotid or vertebral artery involvement, with middle cerebral artery (MCA) infarcts recognised but relatively uncommon. Stroke in young patients should therefore prompt consideration of vasculitis to enable timely diagnosis and treatment.

Methods: A 30-year-old woman presented with acute onset dense right hemiplegia, neglect, and aphasia, with a National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale score of 14. CT imaging demonstrated a left MCA infarct with occluded M1/M2 branches. She received intravenous thrombolysis, resulting in significant neurological recovery. Repeat angiography demonstrated recanalisation of M1/M2 but revealed left common carotid artery occlusion and aortic arch thickening. CT aortic angiography confirmed diffuse wall thickening involving the aortic arch, brachiocephalic, subclavian, and pulmonary arteries. On the basis of radiological abnormalities and elevated inflammatory biochemical markers, she was diagnosed with TAK with ACR/EULAR 2022 classification score of 7.

Results: Her MCA infarct was attributed to large-vessel occlusion secondary to left common carotid artery involvement. High-dose corticosteroids and cyclophosphamide were initiated (10 doses, cumulative 6.6 g) over a 7 month follow up period. Due to re-emerging carotidynia and rising C-reactive protein upon tapering corticosteroids, she was transitioned to tocilizumab, with good clinical and biochemical recovery. There was no further vascular progression on follow-up imaging after 16 months.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of considering TAK in young patients presenting with stroke without conventional risk factors. Advanced vascular imaging is critical for diagnosis, and prompt immunosuppressive therapy is essential to reduce morbidity. Biologics such as tocilizumab provide effective long-term control while minimising glucocorticoid burden.

C-072

Synovitis-Acne-Pustulosis-Hyperostosis-Osteitis (SAPHO) syndrome, Takayasu arteritis and myocarditis: An infrequent association

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Background: Synovitis-Acne-Pustulosis-Hyperostosis-Osteitis (SAPHO) syndrome is a rare autoinflammatory disorder involving osteoarticular and cutaneous manifestations. Its association with large-vessel vasculitis or myocarditis is extremely uncommon. We report a case of SAPHO syndrome in an adolescent complicated by Takayasu arteritis and acute myocarditis.

Methods: Case report.

Results: A 17-year-old female initially presented with a painful swelling in her clavicle, elevated inflammatory markers and nail psoriasis. She was diagnosed with SAPHO syndrome based on characteristic imaging findings, including clavicular hyperostosis, osteolysis, and enthesopathy of the costoclavicular ligament. Treatment with methotrexate and NSAIDs achieved partial remission. After discontinuing therapy, she began to experience progressive dyspnoea. The patient's echocardiogram revealed the presence of pleural effusion and severe systolic dysfunction (LVEF 25%). Cardiac MRI showed partial recovery of ventricular function and large-vessel vasculitis involving the descending aorta, subclavian, renal, and mesenteric arteries, consistent with Takayasu arteritis. The transient recovery of ventricular function was attributed to myocarditis. Additionally, a renal biopsy performed for proteinuria demonstrated NSAID-induced tubulointerstitial nephritis. Management with corticosteroids, methotrexate, and aspirin improved her symptoms. However, a hypertensive crisis complicated by posterior reversible encephalopathy required escalation to pulse methylprednisolone and tocilizumab, resulting in clinical and biochemical remission.

Conclusions: This case illustrates a rare overlap of SAPHO syndrome, Takayasu arteritis, and myocarditis, likely linked through innate immune dysregulation and cytokine-driven inflammation. Clinicians should suspect vasculitis in patients with SAPHO presenting with systemic or vascular features. Early recognition and prompt management are essential to prevent irreversible injuries.

C-073

Takayasu arteritis with multi-vessel occlusion and cerebral involvement: a case report of endovascular intervention and immunosuppressive therapy

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Background: Takayasu arteritis is a rare idiopathic chronic vasculitis of large arteries, particularly the aorta and its major branches. It occurs predominantly in young women under 40 years of age in Southeast Asia, Mediterranean, and the Middle East region. The uncontrolled inflammation can lead to both stenosis and aneurysm of affected arteries, which make treatment become complicated, requiring combination of medical, interventional, and surgical approaches.

Case Presentation: Here we present a rare case of 44-year-old female, who had type V Takayasu disease, manifesting clinically by subclavian steal syndrome and refractory renovascular hypertension, was successfully treated by hybrid management. Laboratory investigations showed elevated inflammatory markers, anaemia and severely decreased renal function. Computed tomography angiography indicated severe stenosis of the left subclavian artery, significant stenosis of the right renal artery, complete occlusion of the left renal artery and occlusion of all remaining branches of the aorta. Brain magnetic resonance imaging demonstrated stenosis of ophthalmic segment of the left carotid and left middle cerebral artery with old left temporal lobe infarction. Based on clinical and para-clinical evidence, the patient was indicated for revascularization with stents in right renal artery and left subclavian artery. Immunosuppressants with methotrexate and corticosteroids, combined with antiplatelet agents were also prescribed. After recanalization, patient's symptoms improved and her blood pressure was stable. The doses of immunosuppressants were tapered monthly. After 8 months, inflammatory markers reduced to normal, haemoglobin increased and renal function recovered. No stent restenosis and relapse episodes happened during 15 months follow-up.

Conclusions: This case highlights the importance of multidisciplinary approach in treatment Takayasu arteritis. While medicine addresses the underlying inflammation, intervention can directly restore blood flow with minimal invasiveness and high success rate. Therefore, the combination of medical therapy and endovascular intervention plays a pivotal role in minimizing the risk of complications and improving long - term outcomes.

C-074

Too much of a good thing – or just enough? Quad-strength adalimumab for refractory Takayasu's arteritis.

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Background: Adalimumab (ADA) is an effective, safe treatment for refractory Takayasu's arteritis (TA). Despite standard 40mg SC weekly dosing, over 15% of patients relapse. Dose escalation to 80mg SC weekly is used in severe Crohn's disease and hidradenitis suppurativa, with good safety evidence.

Case Presentation: A 43-year-old female was diagnosed with TA in 2007. Over the subsequent 17 years, partial control of large vessel inflammation was achieved with azathioprine, mycophenolate, and tocilizumab; however, the patient remained largely steroid dependent, with progressive stenosing and inflammatory disease. She had bilateral common carotid occlusion, aortitis with severe aortic regurgitation, bilateral subclavian stenosis and superior mesenteric artery occlusion. She has required an aorto-bicarotid bypass and tissue aortic valve repair 2011, transcatheter aortic valve implantation 2020 and left subclavian artery angioplasty 2023.

High-dose prednisone was required for major relapses, typically accompanied by carotidynia. She was glucocorticoid-dependent with at least 5mg prednisone daily from 2018-2022 and accumulated significant glucocorticoid-associated toxicities. In 2021, ADA was initiated at 40mg SC weekly and continued until February 2024 when she had a major relapse. This relapse was refractory to high-dose prednisone, mycophenolate, and cyclophosphamide. In July 2024, ADA was increased to 80 mg SC weekly. Prednisone was tapered and ceased in September 2024. Disease activity and treatment doses is plotted (Figure 1).

As of September 2025, the patient is glucocorticoid-free on weekly 80mg SC ADA and remains clinically stable, without carotidynia and suppressed inflammatory markers. Her most recent PET, June 2025, demonstrates resolution of aortic inflammation and stable mildly increased FDG avidity confined to the vertebral and subclavian arteries. There were no identified adverse effects of ADA.

Conclusions: This case illustrates the role of dose escalation of ADA in inducing sustained glucocorticoid-free remission in severe relapsing TA. Further studies are warranted on the use of high-dose ADA in Takayasu's arteritis.

C-075

Regression of vascular wall thickening with upadacitinib in a patient with paediatric-onset Takayasu arteritis and ulcerative colitis

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Background: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a rare large-vessel vasculitis that may coexist with ulcerative colitis(UC), suggesting overlapping pathogenic mechanisms. While anti-TNF agents are commonly used in both diseases, alternative therapies are needed in refractory cases. Upadacitinib, a selective JAK-1 inhibitor, is approved for moderate-to-severe UC and is suggested to be effective in case reports of TAK.

Case Presentation: An 18-year-old female was diagnosed with UC five years earlier after presenting with bloody mucoid stools. Glucocorticoids and mesalazine were initiated. While glucocorticoid tapering, relapses occurred, and azathioprine(2.5 mg/kg) was added. As the response to azathioprine was inadequate, intravenous infliximab (5 mg/kg every 8 weeks) was started but discontinued at the third month due to primary unresponsiveness. Then, subcutaneous adalimumab(40 mg biweekly) was initiated. While UC remained in remission, she developed lower limb weakness and claudication in November 2022. Imaging revealed diffuse wall thickening of the bilateral carotid and subclavian arteries, thoracic aorta extending to the iliac bifurcation consistent with Takayasu arteritis (TAK). She received six cycles of intravenous cyclophosphamide(1 g each), and subsequently continued adalimumab(40 mg biweekly) combined with methotrexate(15 mg weekly). TAK-related symptoms improved.

In December 2023, colonoscopy revealed active pancolitis. Vascular imaging showed persistent wall thickening. Adalimumab was intensified to 40 mg weekly. In May 2024, she reported ongoing bloody stools three times daily. Colonoscopy confirmed active UC. Given prior failure of two anti-TNF agents, upadacitinib was initiated by discussing with gastroenterology (45 mg/day induction, 30 mg/day maintenance) Within three months, UC symptoms had fully resolved. At 12 months, imaging demonstrated regression of vascular wall thickening, and the patient remained in remission for both conditions.

Conclusion: This case highlights the potential of upadacitinib in refractory TAK with coexisting UC. Beyond clinical remission, regression of vascular inflammation suggests possible structural benefit with upadacitinib in decreasing progression to irreversible stenosis or occlusion.

C-076

Tocilizumab use in pregnant patients with Takayasu arteritis

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Background: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) is a large-vessel vasculitis predominantly affecting females of reproductive age. Tocilizumab is a monoclonal antibody used in synthetic disease modifying anti-rheumatic drug (DMARD) refractory cases. Pre-clinical data suggest potential teratogenicity of tocilizumab, however this has not been replicated in clinical studies. Most trial data on tocilizumab use in pregnancy arises from its use in COVID-19 but was limited to single doses. The American College of Rheumatology (ACR) conditional guidance is to continue tocilizumab up until conception and cease upon confirmation of pregnancy. We describe the use of tocilizumab at conception and throughout pregnancy in individuals with TAK.

Methods: 169 cases of TAK were identified from a single UK centre from 2016-2024. Women who received tocilizumab during pregnancy were screened. Data regarding disease, medications, and pregnancy outcomes were collected.

Results: 51/169 (30%) of TAK patients were prescribed tocilizumab between 2016-2025. 9/169 had concomitant use of tocilizumab during pregnancy. Two women received intravenous tocilizumab (8mg/kg 4-weekly) and seven received subcutaneous tocilizumab 162mg weekly. Multidisciplinary team (MDT) decision making regarding tocilizumab continuation included patients, rheumatologists, obstetricians and obstetric physicians. Tocilizumab was continued in pregnancy in 8/9 women where the risk of disease flare was considered high. Eight women have delivered to date with no maternal flares, congenital malformations or foetal losses. Three women were delivered preterm; one where tocilizumab was stopped in third trimester to avoid transplacental transfer; one for placental abruption and another for foetal cardiac trigeminy (tocilizumab continued throughout pregnancy for both).

Conclusions: The use of tocilizumab in TAK is well established, however, in pregnancy withdrawal may not be feasible. We describe maternal and neonatal outcomes with tocilizumab continuation.

C-077

Safe usage of tocilizumab in pregnant women with Takayasu arteritis: 5 case studies

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Background: Takayasu arteritis (TAK) predominantly affects young women. Pregnancy in patients with TAK is associated with hypertension, preeclampsia, preterm delivery, and delayed foetal development. In particular, increased disease activity of TAK is a risk factor for worse perinatal outcomes and increased maternal blood pressure. Therefore, we need to control the disease activity of TAK before conception. We previously reported the efficacy of tocilizumab (TCZ) in refractory patients with TAK (ARD2018, Rheumatology2020). However, the benefit and safety of TCZ use in patients with TAK in pregnancy are still unclear.

Methods: The dose of prednisolone (PSL) was reduced under TCZ treatment as much as possible. We confirmed the disease activity by FDG-PETCT prior to conception. After comprehensive examinations, five patients were allowed to become pregnant.

Results: All five women with refractory TAK were able to reduce the dosage of PSL to 5-10 mg before pregnancy using TCZ. The cardiovascular risks during pregnancy were very high in all cases: severe stenosis of the ostial right coronary artery in case 1, pulmonary hypertension due to bilateral pulmonary artery stenosis in case 2, chronic hypertension and severe resistance to glucocorticoid treatment in case 3, severe aortic regurgitation in case 4, and past cardiac surgery (coronary artery bypass grafting and aortic valve replacement in case 5. All five cases continued TCZ without relapse of TAK or the appearance or worsening of hypertension during pregnancy. Four women delivered vaginally under epidural anaesthesia at full term, and the remaining one delivered by caesarean section. All five women were kept in good condition for the 1-year follow-up after delivery. Their neonates showed no signs of congenital anomalies or immunological disorders at birth and progressed with no developmental problems for 1 year.

Conclusion: TCZ throughout pregnancy may lead to favourable clinical courses and pregnancy outcomes in patients with TAK.

C-079

Polyarteritis nodosa-like organ-threatening vasculitis following mumps: successful management with angioembolization and immunosuppression

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Background: Polyarteritis Nodosa (PAN) is a rare form of medium vessel vasculitis, which occurs idiopathically or in association with viral infections such as hepatitis B

Case Presentation: A 19-year-old male presented with a right perinephric hematoma. He had a recent bout of mumps nearly six weeks earlier, complicated by right epididymo-orchitis with torsion, necessitating an orchidopexy. A CT aortogram revealed multiple aneurysms in both kidneys, liver, and pancreas, along with renal and splenic infarcts. He also experienced labile hypertension, mononeuritis multiplex, and generalized tonic-clonic seizures due to posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES). He was treated with angioembolization and immunosuppression through pulse therapy with methylprednisolone and intravenous cyclophosphamide.

On the 16th day of hospitalization, he faced a new left perinephric haemorrhage, which led to circulatory shock. It was effectively managed with angioembolizations and comprehensive supportive care. The CT aortogram displayed new aneurysms in different arterial systems (intercostal, bronchial, pulmonary, internal mammary, and vertebral), prompting an urgent addition of intravenous Tocilizumab. Elective embolization of the perilous aneurysms was completed successfully. With this rigorous treatment approach, the patient stabilized, followed by ongoing oral steroids and monthly doses of cyclophosphamide, alongside an additional dose of tocilizumab administered after one month.

At the six-month follow-up, the patient has survived with mild renal impairment. A repeat CT aortogram revealed the complete resolution of most of the aneurysms. However, he subsequently developed right ureteric obstruction secondary to ischemic injury or embolization material, leading to hydronephrosis and urinoma.

Conclusions: This case exemplifies a rare instance of PAN-like medium vessel vasculitis following mumps that resulted in life-threatening complications. The condition progressed despite conventional immunosuppression, presenting a significant therapeutic challenge. However, the patient achieved stabilization through decisive interventions, including multiple therapeutic angioembolizations, high-dose steroids, monthly cyclophosphamide, and the strategic use of tocilizumab.

C-080

Occult clear cell renal carcinoma presenting as treatment-resistant polyarteritis nodosa

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Background: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) is a systemic necrotizing vasculitis of medium-sized arteries. It is characterized by transmural inflammation and fibrinoid necrosis. Its aetiology includes infectious, autoimmune, and paraneoplastic causes. Paraneoplastic vasculitis is most often linked to hematologic malignancies; however, its association with clear cell renal carcinoma is exceptionally rare. We present a case of a patient with refractory PAN, ultimately attributed to an underlying renal neoplasm.

Methods: Case report.

Results: A 71-year-old woman with a medical history of diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and peripheral arterial disease has been experiencing constitutional symptoms, livedo racemosa, digital ischemia, and acral necrosis since 2018. Arteriography revealed distal occlusions and stenosis that are consistent with medium-vessel vasculitis. Laboratory workup showed markedly elevated acute-phase reactants with negative autoimmune and infectious panels. A diagnosis of PAN was established, and the patient received glucocorticoids and intravenous cyclophosphamide. Despite initial improvements, the patient experienced relapses with azathioprine and methotrexate, leading to progressive ischemia and multiple amputations, including bilateral below-knee amputations. In 2024, she was admitted with new ischemic lesions, and histopathology confirmed transmural necrotizing vasculitis. Refractory disease was diagnosed after the failure of cyclophosphamide and rituximab. Given the relapsing course, a paraneoplastic aetiology was suspected. An abdominal MRI revealed a right renal mass, and a subsequent biopsy confirmed clear cell renal carcinoma (cT1aN0M0). Due to the patient's surgical risk, the decision was made to proceed with a microwave ablation procedure. At the nine-month follow-up, the patient remained clinically stable on methotrexate and prednisone, with normalization of inflammatory markers.

Conclusions: This case underscores the significance of recognizing malignancy in patients with vasculitis who have not responded to multiple immunosuppressive treatments. The temporal relationship between tumour ablation and remission strongly suggests a paraneoplastic mechanism. Early recognition may facilitate timely cancer diagnosis and improve outcomes in treatment-resistant PAN.

C-081

Acute necrotising pancreatitis as a rare first presentation of PR3-ANCA positive Polyarteritis Nodosa (PAN)

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Background: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) is a systemic necrotizing vasculitis that typically affects medium-sized muscular arteries. Unlike some other vasculitides, PAN is not associated with antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA). Here we report a rare case of acute necrotising pancreatitis as first presentation of PAN with an elevated serum PR3-ANCA titre.

Case Presentation: A 48 -year-old male presented with abdominal pain, deranged liver function tests and a raised amylase. CT scan showed evidence of acute pancreatitis with evidence of pancreatic necrosis on interval scan. He subsequently developed an acute kidney injury with creatinine peaking at 202 $\mu\text{mol/l}$. Serum PR3-ANCA titre was elevated at 12.0 U/ml.

The patient was treated for a presumed PR3-ANCA associated vasculitis with intravenous methylprednisolone and avacopan. Whilst waiting for inpatient rituximab infusion, he developed recurrent episodes of per rectal (PR) bleeding requiring blood transfusions. Abdominal and renal angiograms showed multiple microvascular aneurysms in the small vessels of the proximal jejunum and both renal arteries respectively, in keeping with vasculitis. Due to the paucity of data for the treatment of PAN with rituximab, he was treated with intravenous cyclophosphamide with subsequent improvement in renal function, haemoglobin and overall clinical condition.

Conclusions: This case demonstrates the ongoing challenges of diagnosing PAN due to the heterogenic nature of the condition and the importance of considering the prototypical ANCA negative vasculitides such as PAN in the differential for small to medium vessel vasculitis as this can have significant implication on treatment strategy and patient outcomes.

C-082

Recurrent endocarditis: a rare manifestation of Behçet's disease

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Background: Behçet's disease (BD) is a multisystem inflammatory disorder characterized by recurrent oral and genital aphthae, ocular disease and skin lesions. Rarely, it may present as the life-threatening, predominantly cardiovascular variant known as Hughes-Stovin syndrome (HSS), characterized by the association of multiple pulmonary artery aneurysms and peripheral venous thrombosis.

Case Presentation: In 2017, a 38 year old man was diagnosed with HSS/BD on the basis of recurrent oral and genital ulceration, pulmonary artery aneurysms, arterial and venous thromboses and non-infective endocarditis necessitating a tricuspid valve replacement. Following induction of remission with high dose prednisolone and intravenous cyclophosphamide, he remained well on infliximab and methotrexate for several years. In October 2024, these were paused for elective hernia repair surgery.

In February 2025, he represented with two weeks of fever (40 °C), dry cough and oral ulcers.

Laboratory tests revealed raised inflammatory markers (CRP 94mg/L, WBC $13.4 \times 10^9/L$).

Transthoracic echocardiography demonstrated a large mobile mass attached to the prosthetic tricuspid valve with moderate regurgitation. CT revealed a 20 mm mediastinal lesion, right lower lobe consolidation, and bilateral pulmonary emboli. He was started on broad-spectrum antibiotics with no improvement. Multiple blood cultures were negative. Since non-infective endocarditis was part of his initial HSS/BD presentation, he was started on high-dose prednisolone (60mg daily) which led to rapid clinical improvement and normalization of inflammatory markers within days. A further course of cyclophosphamide consolidated this remission, and he has now transitioned back to infliximab and methotrexate maintenance with sustained response. In due course, he will require a further valve replacement/repair.

Conclusions: This is a rare case highlighting a non-infective vegetation on a prosthetic valve as a manifestation of HSS/BD in the context of interruption of anti-TNF treatment. Caution is required when pausing therapy, even in patients who have been in stable remission for many years.

C-083

Behçet disease vs spondyloarthritis: should we wait until treatment non-responsiveness before considering the alternative diagnosis?

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Background: Sacroiliitis is one of musculoskeletal findings in Behçet Disease (BD), with the prevalence varying between studies. On the other hand, sacroiliitis is a main feature of axial spondyloarthritis (ax-SpA). This may lead to misdiagnosis or delayed-diagnosis of BD. Here we report a case of BD presenting articular involvement and radiographic sacroiliitis that was previously treated as ax-SpA, although the patient had other features of BD.

Case Presentation: A 44-year old female present to the rheumatology clinic with inflammatory back pain, peripheral arthritis and oral ulcers. The patient was evaluated for ESR, CRP, RF, anti-CCP, ANA and anti-dsDNA revealing normal findings, pelvic imaging shown bilateral sacroiliitis, thus a diagnosis of SpA was made and she was treated with secukinumab. Unfortunately, she experienced intolerance and was clinically unresponsive after the fifth dose. When the patient received a second opinion, symptoms of uveitis, and dyspareunia were also identified, pathergy test was negative. Patient then considered as having BD and treatment was initiated with colchicine. Some improvement was seen, but back pain and dyspareunia symptoms persisted. Azathioprine was added and the patient improved.

Conclusions: The diagnosis of BD is often challenging since its manifestations may also be found in other conditions. The prevalence of each clinical manifestation varies between studies. Sacroiliac joint involvement is not frequent but also not rare, with the prevalence ranging from 0-63%, depending on study design (eg a lack of control group) and imaging methods. Genetically, HLA-B27 may also be found in both SpA and BD. Some reviews suggest that BD is part of SpA. Our patient was not responding to SpA treatment, suggesting that BD is a separate entity. Despite some similar manifestations in both BD and SpA, such as uveitis and gastrointestinal symptoms, thorough history taking may aid the distinction between BD and SpA, including the presence of oral ulcers and genitourinary symptoms.

BD is often misdiagnosed as the symptoms can masquerade as other diseases. Detailed and thorough history taking may assist and distinguish BD from other diseases.

C-084

Behçet's angiopathy: from an abdominal aortic aneurysm to Hughes-Stovin syndrome

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Background: Behçet's syndrome (BS) is a complex vasculitis with a distinctive vascular involvement. It's a syndrome, not a single condition, because it includes a range of different clinical phenotypes. The "vascular phenotype" or "Behçet's angiopathy" identifies patients with venous thrombosis associated with arterial aneurysms. This case report aimed to describe distinctive vascular manifestations, including pulmonary artery aneurysms and recurrent thromboembolic events, in the context of Behçet's disease.

Methods: The clinical records of a patient with Behçet's syndrome and vascular involvement were reviewed.

Results: A 54-year-old male patient with a medical history of saccular abdominal aortic aneurysm, recurrent thromboembolic events, and thrombophlebitis was admitted to the emergency department with acute resting dyspnoea and haemoptysis, but without fever. Acute pulmonary embolism was documented in a segmental branch of the left lower lobe, associated with aneurysms of the right pulmonary artery in the upper and lower lobes. These aneurysms displayed vessel wall thickening, and one of them exhibited eccentric partial luminal thrombosis surrounded by consolidation, suggesting associated alveolar haemorrhage. The patient underwent pulmonary arteriography, embolization, and endovascular repair with coils for the aneurysm in the right lower lobe. During hospitalization, findings consistent with Behçet's syndrome were discovered. He received immunosuppressive treatment, including IV steroid pulses and IV monthly cyclophosphamide, which successfully reduced the size of the pulmonary aneurysm as seen on the 2-month follow-up. The treatment also prevented recurrent episodes of thromboembolic events or haemoptysis.

Conclusions: This case underscores the significance of considering Behçet's syndrome in patients with atypical vascular manifestations, including arterial aneurysms, recurrent thrombophlebitis, and thrombosis. A multidisciplinary approach is crucial for the prognosis of these patients.

C-085

Efficacy and safety of JAK inhibitors in Behçet syndrome: A case report and systemic review

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Background/Aims: Tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (TNFi) are a key treatment modality for major organ involvement, as well as for resistant mucocutaneous and articular manifestations that significantly impair quality of life in Behçet's Syndrome (BS). In cases of inadequate response, and with emerging evidence on the involvement of multifactorial immune mediators and activation of the Janus kinase (JAK) signalling pathway in BS, JAK inhibitors (JAKi) have been introduced through pilot studies and case reports. We aimed to investigate the efficacy and safety profile of JAKi through a systematic literature review.

Methods: The systematic literature review was registered in PROSPERO under the identification number CRD420251000172. All articles published in PubMed, EMBASE, and the Cochrane Library up to March 6, 2025, that reported the use of JAKi in patients with BS and provided treatment outcomes were included. The search was conducted using the keywords: "Behçet AND (JAK OR tofacitinib OR baricitinib OR upadacitinib OR filgotinib OR Janus)." Two independent investigators screened 306 articles, and a total of 18 articles reporting on 91 patients, along with one case report from our centre, were included. Four patients (4.3%) had a prior history of JAKi use.

Results: The primary indication for initiating JAKi therapy was uveitis in 18 patients (19.6%), vascular involvement in 22 (23.9%), and gastrointestinal involvement in 46 (50%). The remaining 5 patients received JAKi due to refractory mucocutaneous and/or articular involvement. In addition to the failure of conventional treatments, 57.1% of patients had failed at least one anti-TNF monoclonal antibody. The clinical remission rates were 82.6% for gastrointestinal, 83.3% for ocular, and 90.9% for vascular involvement. Serious adverse events were reported in 6 patients (6.5%). No thrombotic events were reported.

Conclusions: Although these results support JAKi as promising targeted synthetic DMARDs, randomized controlled trials are needed to establish their efficacy and safety profile in BS.

C-086

Isolated left subclavian artery aneurysm mimicking large-vessel vasculitis

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Background: Subclavian artery aneurysms are rare vascular abnormalities that may mimic large-vessel vasculitis clinically and radiologically. Differentiating inflammatory from non-inflammatory aetiologies is essential to avoid unnecessary immunosuppression. Distinguishing features are particularly relevant in regions where Takayasu arteritis is common, and aneurysmal lesions are frequently presumed to be vasculitic in origin.

Methods: We retrospectively reviewed the clinical presentation, examination, laboratory investigations, and imaging of a patient with a supraclavicular pulsatile mass. Evaluation included systemic review for vasculitis features, detailed vascular examination, inflammatory markers, autoimmune serology, and CT angiography with three-dimensional reconstruction.

Results: A 40-year-old woman presented with a progressively enlarging, pulsatile swelling in the left supraclavicular region for seven months. She had no fever, weight loss, trauma, or connective tissue disease. Examination revealed a 15×15 cm pulsatile mass with all pulses palpable and no distal ischemia. There were no features of vasculitis such as claudication, pulse deficits, bruits, blood pressure asymmetry, or systemic involvement.

Inflammatory markers were normal. Autoimmune workup, including anticardiolipin IgG/IgM and β 2-glycoprotein I IgG/IgM antibodies, was negative. CT angiography revealed a large aneurysmal dilatation of the left subclavian artery without stenosis, occlusion, or additional aneurysms; three-dimensional reconstruction confirmed the morphology. Differential diagnoses considered included Takayasu arteritis, atherosclerotic aneurysm, mycotic aneurysm, and post-traumatic aetiology. Following multidisciplinary review, the patient was scheduled for elective surgical repair.

Conclusions: Although radiologically resembling large-vessel vasculitis, the absence of systemic features, normal inflammatory markers, and negative serology favoured a non-inflammatory aneurysm. Isolated subclavian artery aneurysm is an uncommon but important vasculitis mimic. This case underscores the importance of integrating clinical, laboratory, and imaging data, and highlights the role of multidisciplinary decision-making to ensure appropriate surgical management while avoiding inappropriate immunosuppression.

C-087

Childhood DADA2 Vasculitis with Recurrent Strokes: Genetic Confirmation and Biologic Response

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Background: Deficiency of adenosine deaminase 2 (DADA2) is a rare monogenic vasculitis that may present with recurrent childhood strokes. Biologic therapy with TNF inhibitors has improved outcomes, but treatment response can vary. We report a genetically confirmed paediatric case with multiple strokes, highlighting infliximab failure and subsequent stabilization with adalimumab.

Methods: Clinical data, laboratory results, neuroimaging, genetic analysis, and treatment course were retrospectively reviewed. Management involved multidisciplinary input, including rheumatology, neurology, and thoracic medicine for pre-biologic tuberculosis screening.

Results: A 9-year-old girl first presented to our institute on 26 June 2024 with diplopia and lateral deviation of the left eye. She had suffered two earlier strokes: an acute lacunar infarct in the midbrain involving the 3rd nerve nucleus in 2020, and another in March 2024 involving the medial left thalamus and subthalamic region, without haemorrhagic transformation or mass effect. Labs showed haemoglobin 9.2 g/dL, ESR 8 mm/hr, and normal renal and liver function. ANA, ANCA, and antiphospholipid antibodies were negative. Genetic testing confirmed DADA2.

After negative TB screening, she was started on infliximab 100 mg intravenously (five doses at 2-monthly intervals). In May 2025, while on infliximab, she developed a new acute lacunar infarct in the right paramedian superior midbrain, with chronic infarcts in the left thalamus, midbrain, and hemipons on MRI.

Therapy was switched to adalimumab 40 mg subcutaneously every 2 weeks. After six doses, she remains clinically stable with no new cerebrovascular events. She is ambulant and neurologically stable, maintained on adalimumab, low-dose prednisolone, and aspirin.

Conclusions: This case highlights the severe cerebrovascular phenotype of paediatric DADA2 and the challenges in biologic selection. Failure of infliximab with stabilization on adalimumab underscores the need for individualized TNF blockade. Early recognition, genetic confirmation, and timely therapy switch are critical to preventing disabling strokes.

C-088

Paediatric autoimmune lymphoproliferative syndrome with superior mesenteric artery thrombosis and probable secondary antiphospholipid syndrome: expanding the vascular spectrum of immune dysregulation

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Background: Autoimmune lymphoproliferative syndrome (ALPS) is a rare immune dysregulation disorder with lymphoproliferation and autoimmunity. Vascular complications are infrequently described. We report a genetically confirmed paediatric ALPS case complicated by superior mesenteric artery (SMA) thrombosis and persistent antiphospholipid antibody positivity, consistent with probable secondary antiphospholipid syndrome (APS).

Methods: Clinical, laboratory and imaging data were retrospectively reviewed from inpatient records. This included hematology, immunology (including antiphospholipid and ANA testing), radiology, histopathology, genetic confirmation, treatment and outcomes. Parental consent was obtained.

Results: An 11-year-old boy with genetically confirmed ALPS (documented double-negative T cells, CASP10 variant, cytopenias) presented with severe abdominal pain, diarrhea and malnutrition. Examination revealed generalized lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly and abdominal tenderness. Investigations showed anaemia, thrombocytopenia and elevated markers. ANA (Hep-2, IIF) was cytoplasmic 3+, while the subsequent ANA profile was negative.

Antiphospholipid antibody testing demonstrated: Initial: anticardiolipin (aCL) IgG 34.6 GPL, aCL IgM 9.0 MPL, β 2GP1 IgG 19.2 units, β 2GP1 IgM 16.4 units, and weakly positive lupus anticoagulant. Repeat (after 12 weeks): aCL IgG 22.6 GPL (persistent low-titre positivity), aCL IgM 8.6 MPL, β 2GP1 IgG/IgM <1.0 units; repeat LAC awaited.

CT angiography revealed complete SMA occlusion with jejunal ischemia and a mobile mitral valve mass (21×11 mm). Colonoscopy showed chronic colitis; jejunal biopsy revealed ulceration with granulation tissue and fibroblastic proliferation. SMA thrombosis was considered multifactorial, related to ALPS with probable APS overlap. The cardiac lesion was suggestive of non-bacterial thrombotic endocarditis. Management included intravenous antibiotics, antiparasitic therapy for cryptosporidium, low-dose corticosteroids, anticoagulation and nutritional rehabilitation. Sirolimus is under consideration for immunomodulation. The patient improved clinically.

Conclusions: This case illustrates that ALPS can present with severe vasculopathic complications including large-vessel thrombosis and cardiac thrombotic lesions, with probable APS overlap. Recognition of vascular manifestations in immune dysregulation is critical for timely anticoagulation, judicious immunosuppression and multidisciplinary care.

C-089

Recurrent optic neuritis as the first manifestation of relapsing polychondritis

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Background: Optic neuritis can be an initial manifestation of relapsing polychondritis (RP), although it is considered an uncommon ocular manifestation of the rare systemic autoimmune disease.

Case Presentation: A 46-year-old male presented with recurrent left eye optic neuritis of unclear aetiology. He required multiple courses of high-dose systemic steroids. Later on, he started having recurrent episodes of the left earlobe inflammation with pain and swelling, leading to deformity of his L earlobe.

With suspicion for RP diagnosis, serum Collagen Type II Antibody was checked, which came back highly positive, leading to the diagnosis of RP. He was successfully treated with rituximab and methotrexate as steroid-sparing agents.

Conclusions: Physicians should consider RP in patients with recurrent optic neuritis, as the condition often presents with non-specific ocular symptoms, and ocular inflammation can be an early indicator of underlying RP.

C-090

From vasculitis to VEXAS: insights from a systematic review

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Background: VEXAS (Vacuoles, E1 Enzyme, X-linked, Autoinflammatory, Somatic) is an autoinflammatory syndrome caused by somatic mutation in UBA1. Since its discovery, VEXAS and vasculitis' association has remained uncertain. Giant cell arteritis (GCA) was initially reported among presenting features, but subsequent screening of VEXAS mutations in a GCA cohort failed to identify any cases, highlighting this ambiguity. Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) and ANCA-associated vasculitis have been described in a limited number of patients, while leukocytoclastic vasculitis represents the most frequently reported vasculitic manifestation within the typical VEXAS phenotype.

Methods: We conducted a systematic literature review of published cases of VEXAS associated with vasculitis. The objectives were to (i) characterize the spectrum of vasculitis subtypes reported in VEXAS patients and their clinical presentations, and (ii) analyse all available cases to determine whether objective and indisputable evidence of vasculitis could be established.

Results: Of 91 articles screened, 40 were included after a two-step selection process. Across these reports, 180 patients were diagnosed with both VEXAS and vasculitis, mostly men (98%), with a median age of 70,5 years, typically presenting with fever, chondritis, pulmonary infiltrates and macrocytic anaemia.

Among them, 54 presented leukocytoclastic vasculitis (30%), 5 GCA (2.8%), 10 PAN (5.6%), 12 ANCA-associated vasculitis (6.7%) and 2 immunoglobulin A vasculitis (1%). The majority had unclassified vasculitis. Clinical presentation most often began with vasculitis, occasionally without hematologic disorders at onset, refractory or relapsing vasculitis despite standard therapies. To define VEXAS and association of vasculitis, we reconstructed the chronological sequence of clinical events and the available histopathological evidence of vasculitis by contacting the original study authors.

Conclusion: Our systematic review demonstrates a recurrent but heterogeneous feature of vasculitis in VEXAS patients. Boundary between true vasculitis and VEXAS-related vasculitic mimics remains blurred. Ongoing study contacting the authors of the cases report is warranted to clarify the pathophysiological links between VEXAS and Vasculitis.

C-091

Orbital mass and saddle nose - don't judge a book by its cover

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Background/Aims: EAF is a rare and slowly progressive disease typically involving respiratory mucosa of the sinonasal tract. Orbital involvement has been reported, with histopathological features varying in type and extent depending on clinical age of the lesion, with EAF suggested to be part of the IgG4-related disease (IgG4-RD) spectrum.

Methods: Case presentation and literature search on orbital EAF.

Case presentation and Results: A 58-year-old male presented with exophthalmos and saddle nose deformity with normal mucosa and nasal septum. Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antigen (ANCA) was negative and serum immunoglobulin G subclass 4 (IgG4) level slightly elevated. PET scan showed an extraconal orbital mass and focus alongside the nasal septum with soft tissue thickening. The first orbital specimen revealed storiform fibrosis with lymphoplasmacellular infiltrate with prominent eosinophils and in the second specimen an increased IgG4/IgG ratio and decreased IgG2/IgG4 ratio, suggestive for eosinophilic angiocentric fibrosis (EAF). Yet, because of granulomas in the second specimen and smudgy necrosis and neutrophils in the former specimen, also granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA) was considered. The patient received prednisolone and one rituximab cycle. The orbital mass was initially stable, but showed progression after 3 years, revealing extensive fibroconnective tissue with dense storiform fibrosis and dense lymphoplasmacellular inflammation, including apparent increase of IgG4 plasma cells with eosinophils. However, in this biopsy neutrophils and necrosis were more prominent, but without granulomas. The patient received treatment with prednisolone and rituximab again.

Fifteen of the 33 identified EAF cases, including this patient, were male patients. All patients revealed orbital involvement, with additional sinonasal disease in 19 patients. Three patients had positive ANCA, including one patient with anti-PR3. Two patients had an increased level of serum IgG4. Biopsies of 7 patients showed IgG4-RD features.

Conclusions: Differentiating EAF from GPA can be clinically and (histo)pathologically challenging, with combined serology, imaging, morphology and immunohistochemistry aiding in the diagnostic and therapeutic process.

C-092

The silent mass: unmasking IgG4-related kidney disease in a complex autoimmune patient

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Background: IgG4-related disease is a rare systemic condition characterized by immune-mediated fibroinflammatory lesions that can affect essentially any organ. Renal involvement (IgG4-RKD) may mimic malignancy due to mass-like infiltrates. The aetiology is uncertain, and the diagnosis may be challenging, especially in cases with normal serum IgG4.

IgG4-RKD typically presents as retroperitoneal fibrosis with obstructive uropathy, tubulointerstitial nephritis or membranous nephropathy.

Case Presentation: A 49-year-old woman with stricturing small intestinal Crohn's disease on Adalimumab and psoriatic arthritis with psoriasis was found to have an infiltrative left perinephric mass on CT during preoperative assessment for hernia repair.

PET-CT showed high metabolic activity in the lesion. Laboratory tests showed elevated CRP, ESR, creatinine, normal serum IgG4, negative immunology and no monoclonal bands on SPE. Urinalysis positive for microscopic haematuria. DMSA scintigraphy demonstrated a non-functioning left kidney. Percutaneous biopsy demonstrated non-specific chronic inflammation and fibrosis. Given persistent diagnostic uncertainty and the concern for malignancy or xanthogranulomatous pyelonephritis, the patient underwent radical left nephrectomy. Histology showed storiform fibrosis, obliterative phlebitis, and a dense lymphoplasmacytic infiltrate. Immunostaining demonstrated >30 IgG4-positive plasma cells/ HPF and an IgG4+/IgG+ ratio above 40%, confirming the diagnosis of IgG4-RKD. Following surgery, serum creatinine levels stabilized. Given the histological findings and the patient's ongoing immunosuppressive treatment with adalimumab, no additional therapy was recommended.

Conclusions: This case illustrates the diagnostic challenge of IgG4-RK in unilateral renal involvement with autoimmune comorbidities. The diagnosis was missed because of normal serum IgG4 and inconclusive biopsy findings, but was confirmed through definitive surgical histology. Histological findings, in conjunction with the absence of exclusion criteria and the presence of typical organ involvement, supported classification under the 2019 ACR/EULAR criteria, with a total score over 20 points. IgG4-RD should remain in the differential diagnosis for infiltrative renal masses, as early recognition is essential to avoid misdiagnosis and to appropriate management.

C-093

Erdheim-Chester disease: a rare mimic of IgG4-related disease

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Background: Aortitis is a rare but critical manifestation of systemic inflammatory disease, most associated with large vessel vasculitides such as Takayasu arteritis and giant cell arteritis. When accompanied by multiorgan inflammation and fibrosis, the differential diagnoses broaden to include immune-mediated conditions such as immunoglobulin G4-related disease (IgG4-RD) and rare histiocytic neoplasms.

Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD) is a clonal histiocytic neoplasm driven by mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway mutations and characterised by multisystem tissue infiltration and inflammation. Like IgG4-RD, ECD can involve the aorta and its major branches, as well as the retroperitoneum, lungs, pituitary, and adrenal glands. However, its most common manifestation is bilateral long bone osteosclerosis, seen in 95% of cases.

We discuss a rare presentation of radiographically bone-sparing ECD to highlight the clinical and radiologic overlap with IgG4-RD, which poses diagnostic challenges and may delay access to effective mutation-targeted therapies.

Case presentation: We report a diagnostically challenging case of a middle-aged woman with a five-month history of bilateral ureteric obstruction, weight loss, and fatigue. Extensive further investigation revealed progressive retroperitoneal fibrosis, aortitis involving major branches, interstitial lung disease, and adrenal and pituitary involvement, but notably no skeletal disease. Subsequent omental biopsy confirmed ECD, with a pathogenic MAP2K1 mutation detected. The patient was commenced on tapering prednisolone and trametinib, a mutation-targeted therapy compassionately accessed through hospital funding. A repeat whole-body PET/CT at six months revealed complete metabolic response with no evidence of active ECD.

Conclusion: This case highlights the diagnostic complexity of bone-sparing ECD, a rare phenotype representing fewer than five percent of cases. Its clinical mimicry of vasculitis and other inflammatory disorders can obscure the underlying neoplastic process, delaying diagnosis and access to effective targeted treatment. In patients with systemic inflammation and inconclusive serology, early consideration of ECD is essential to guide appropriate investigations and timely therapy.

C-094

A case of aortitis and acute coronary syndrome secondary to Erdheim-Chester Disease

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Background: Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD) is a rare neoplastic histiocytic disorder which is mediated by mutations in the Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase (MAPK) pathway. We present a case of ECD in a patient presenting with aortitis and acute coronary syndrome.

Case presentation: A 78-year-old man presented with seven months of exertional dyspnoea, angina, leg claudication, bony pain, rash and constitutional symptoms. Examination revealed carotid and subclavian bruits, signs of decompensated heart failure and upper limb rashes. Initial investigations revealed a raised C-reactive protein level of 118 mg/L (reference range (rr) <5mg/L), and troponin level of 145 ng/L (rr<15ng/L). The electrocardiogram was consistent with ischaemia and echocardiography showed a reduced left ventricular ejection fraction (30%). Further investigation with computed tomography coronary angiogram demonstrated extensive soft tissue density mural thickening of the coronary arteries and aorta consistent with vasculitis. 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography (FDG PET) captured patchy irregular FDG activity throughout the walls of multiple arteries including the aorta and revealed uptake in the cervical lymph nodes and long bones. Biopsy of a PET avid lymph node and skin showed histopathological and immunohistochemistry features of ECD, with next generation sequencing of the skin tissue identifying a somatic BRAF Val600Glu mutation confirming the diagnosis.

Conclusions: An inflammatory response often accompanies ECD, likely driven by oncogene-induced senescence (OIS). OIS is a protective mechanism against oncogenic events whereby there is cell-cycle arrest, induction of pro-inflammatory molecules and a profound local inflammatory response. Arterial involvement occurs in 50 to 80% of cases and coronary arteries may be involved in 30% to 50% of patients. Given the complexity and multifaceted nature of his disease, multiple subspecialty teams were involved.

In cases of patients with newly diagnosed aortitis, rare inflammatory causes such as ECD should be considered, particularly when inflammatory changes are extensive and involve aortic branches and smaller arteries.

C-095

Single centre audit of patients diagnosed with isolated abdominal aortitis

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Background/Aims: Isolated abdominal aortitis is a rare condition with varied aetiology including inflammatory, infectious, and malignant causes. This audit aimed to review patients diagnosed with isolated abdominal aortitis on imaging at Fiona Stanley Hospital, examining referral pathways, investigations, management approaches, final diagnoses, and 12-month follow-up outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective single-centre audit was conducted of patients with CT or PET imaging positive for isolated abdominal aortitis between July 1, 2021 and July 1, 2024. Patients were identified from radiology records and excluded if they had systemic vascular involvement or aortitis on imaging which onset outside the specified timeframe. Data collected included demographics, clinical presentation, imaging findings, laboratory investigations, differential diagnoses, treatment, and surveillance imaging.

Results: Twelve patients met inclusion criteria from 33 initially identified cases. Eight were male (67%), median age was 67.5 years (range 49-91). Eight cases were diagnosed on PET imaging, four on CT. Three patients were asymptomatic, and three had pre-existing autoimmune conditions. Median baseline CRP was 21 mg/L (range 1-226). Clinical differential diagnoses included large vessel vasculitis, IgG4-related disease, infective aortitis, and atherosclerosis. Comprehensive serological screening was performed in all cases. Four patients received prednisolone therapy, including two with probable IgG4-related disease and two with possible infective/inflammatory aortitis.

Conclusions: This audit demonstrates the diagnostic complexity of isolated abdominal aortitis, requiring extensive investigation to differentiate between inflammatory, infectious, and other aetiologies. Standardised diagnostic and management protocols may improve patient outcomes in this challenging condition.

C-096

Diagnostic dilemma in young-onset aortic aneurysmal disease : a case of Loeys-Dietz syndrome complicated by inflammatory large vessel vasculitis

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Background : Genetic aortopathies are often considered as differential diagnosis of large vessel vasculitides(LVV), but their coexistence is rarely reported.

Case presentation: A 36-year-old male with acute back pain, was diagnosed with Stanford Type B aortic dissection. Initially, he underwent thoracic endovascular aortic repair(TEVAR, Zone 2). However, two years post-procedure, back pain recurred. CT-angiography revealed aneurysmal expansion of thoracic and abdominal aorta. Follow-up imaging over next year revealed progressively enlarging aneurysms.

Clinical examination revealed hypermobile joints, sallow skin, and easy bruisability. Genetics(WES) for congenital aortopathies were sent. Despite absence of systemic features, he tested positive for pathergy(1+) and HLA-B51. Inflammatory markers were also elevated: CRP(39mg/L), ESR(105mm/hr), raising suspicion for LVV. Steroids (1 mg/kg) and mycophenolate (2 g/day) were initiated, leading to reduced inflammatory markers and enabling staged TEVAR(Zone 0–5) and completion EVAR(Zone 5–10).

Genetic testing later confirmed Loeys-Dietz Syndrome(LDS) with pathogenic TGF β 2 mutation (Exon 4, C1134 G>C, heterozygous), leading to discontinuation of immunosuppression.

Six-months later, imaging revealed a new left common iliac aneurysm and elevated ESR/CRP (105/39). Due to radiological progression and elevated inflammatory markers, immunosuppression was recommenced with 1mg/kg steroids with taper. Within three months, his ESR and CRP levels reduced to 7 and 8, respectively and by 6 months, Imaging showed regression of thoracic aneurysm (3 × 4 cm to 2.2 × 3.3 cm) and abdominal aneurysm (8.6 × 10 cm to 7.9 × 5.9 cm). However, tapering steroids to 7.5 mg/day led to recurrent inflammation (ESR 75, CRP 22).

Conclusions: Genetic aortopathies like LDS may coexist with inflammatory LVV. TGF- β mutations may impair T regulatory cell subsets, reducing peripheral tolerance. Dysregulated TGF- β activity can cause aortic medial destruction and cryptic neoantigens exposure. Coupled with HLA-B51 positivity, this may trigger autoimmune/autoinflammatory vascular pathology. Case reports of LDS with inflammatory bowel disease, elevated ESR/CRP are described.

C-097

Localized multifocal vasculitis identified in hysterectomy and lymph node dissection for cervical adenocarcinoma

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Case presentation: We report a rare case of multifocal vasculitis involving the female reproductive tract, identified incidentally in a 52-year-old woman undergoing hysterectomy, bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, and lymph node dissection for cervical adenocarcinoma. Histopathological examination revealed vasculitic changes affecting multiple reproductive tract sites, as well as perinodal vasculitis within excised lymph nodes. No clinical or serological evidence of systemic autoimmunity was present.

Conclusions: This case highlights an unusual, localised form of vasculitis associated with gynaecological malignancy, underscoring the importance of thorough histopathological evaluation in oncologic resections and raising questions about potential paraneoplastic or tissue-restricted immune mechanisms.

C-098

Recurrent pauci-immune pulmonary capillaritis: a severe and rare form of localized vasculitis

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Background: Pulmonary capillaritis (PC) is a histopathological finding characterized by inflammatory infiltration of the capillary walls. It is the most frequent mechanism of diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH), with autoimmune, vasculitic, infectious, and miscellaneous aetiologies. The pauci-immune isolated form (PIIC), which is rare and of unknown incidence, is diagnosed through a process of elimination in DAH without direct systemic involvement or autoimmunity/infection positivity, with fewer than 25 cases reported. Treatment is extrapolated from antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV), using corticosteroid pulses and immunosuppressive agents such as cyclophosphamide (CYC) or rituximab.

Case presentation: A 45-year-old woman, with a medical history of surgically treated myasthenia gravis and chronic anaemia due to uterine bleeding, presented with five days of progressive dyspnoea and three months of haemoptysis. The findings were consistent with DAH. Studies showed only a positive lupus anticoagulant; she received high-dose steroids, acetylsalicylic acid, and azathioprine (AZA), with subsequent clinical improvement. Two months later, she developed ventilatory failure and new DAH. Autoimmune (ANA, ANCA, anti-GBM, and antiphospholipid) and infectious profiles were negative. Bronchoalveolar lavage (hemosiderin-laden macrophages) and transbronchial biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of PIIC. She developed a secondary *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infection, which was successfully treated with antibiotics. She subsequently received CYC pulses (1 g monthly for the first 3 months) with a positive response and no recurrence during follow-up.

Conclusion: Isolated PIIC is a rare and challenging entity. To ensure the accuracy of diagnoses, it is essential to exclude autoimmune, infectious, and miscellaneous aetiologies, along with histological confirmation. Immunosuppression, as extrapolated from the management of pulmonary vasculitis, serves as the therapeutic cornerstone. In this case, CYC therapy proved effective, consistent with the limited evidence from previous reports.

C-099

Clinical spectrum and autoimmune associations of urticarial vasculitis in a Colombian cohort

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Background/Aims: Urticarial vasculitis is an immune complex-mediated small-vessel vasculitis. Palacio et al, reported 32 patients in Colombia, with a female predominance (83.4%), symptoms such as angioedema (62.5%), arthralgias (25%), and arthritis (20%). ANA positivity was observed in 29.2% of cases, with 21% classified as HUV. The most prevalent treatment modalities were antihistamines (79.2%) and glucocorticoids (41%). Our objective was to describe the demographic, clinical, and treatment characteristics of patients with urticarial vasculitis.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Medellín, Colombia. Patients diagnosed with urticarial vasculitis between 2015 and 2025 were included. The diagnosis was based on persistent urticarial lesions and histopathological findings. Descriptive statistics were applied.

Results: Thirteen patients were included; median age was 43 years (IQR 27.5); 76.9% were women. Associated conditions included LES in one case, Sjögren's syndrome in two cases, and MGUS in one case. The majority of the subjects (69.2%) were classified as NUV, (30.8%) as hypocomplementaemic variant. Two fulfilled the modified Schwartz (1989). The median disease duration was 7 months (IQR 58).

The most prevalent clinical manifestations were angioedema (46.1%) and arthritis (46.1%). Additional findings included purpura (30.8%), constitutional symptoms (38.5%), Raynaud's phenomenon (15.4%), livedo reticularis (15.4%), myalgias (7.7%), asthma (7.7%) and peripheral neuropathy (7.7%). The mean C3 level was 53 ± 11 mg/dL, and the mean C4 level was 7.4 ± 2.4 mg/dL. Forty-six percent had positive ANA (1:80–1:160). The median ESR was 10 mm/h (IQR 67) and CRP 0.7 mg/dL (IQR 8.35). The most prescribed treatment was colchicine (53.8%), followed by azathioprine (46.1%).

Conclusions: Our cohort confirms the female predominance of urticarial vasculitis and provides novel data on hypocomplementaemic forms and HUUVS in Latin America. These findings highlight the clinical heterogeneity of the disease and the need for further regional studies.

C-100

Self-limiting large vessel vasculitis following Campylobacter infection: case report and literature review

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Background: Endovascular Campylobacter infections are severe conditions requiring prolonged antibiotic therapy. We describe a patient with postinfectious, reactive large vessel vasculitis after Campylobacter infection, with rapid and spontaneous remission without immunosuppression.

Methods: We present a case and performed a literature review on Campylobacter-associated and postinfectious, reactive large vessel vasculitis. Relevant publications were identified through PubMed/MEDLINE and Embase up to 29 August 2025; additional references were retrieved manually from key articles.

Results: A 65-year-old woman was admitted with myalgia and fever of unknown origin. Three weeks earlier, she experienced self-limiting diarrhea. On admission, CRP was 366 mg/L, and a mild anaemia and leukocytosis were detected. Chest radiography was unremarkable and repeated blood and urine cultures remained negative. Persistent high-grade fever under cefuroxime prompted imaging, and a PET-CT on day 4 of admission showed extensive large vessel vasculitis of the aorta, its main branches and the iliac arteries. Simultaneously, stool PCR identified Campylobacter spp. Antibiotics were discontinued. Remarkably, the patient showed rapid improvement without immunosuppression. CRP normalized in two weeks, and PET-CT after four months demonstrated complete resolution of vasculitis.

Most Campylobacter endovascular infections (>80%) are caused by *C. fetus*. These represent localized endovascular infection with positive blood cultures in 89-100% of cases and poor prognosis. One case of post-infectious, reactive vasculitis after Campylobacter coli has been described, necessitating long term immunosuppressive therapy. Several studies suggest an association between large vessel vasculitis and infections in the year prior to onset of symptoms, especially upper respiratory tract infections including COVID-19, and herpes zoster virus.

Conclusion: Accumulating data suggest infectious triggers may precede large vessel vasculitis. Although Campylobacter infections are frequently associated with reactive arthritis, this is only the second case of post-Campylobacter large vessel vasculitis described in literature, and the first with complete remission without immunosuppression.

C-101

Ticks on the trail, trouble on the track: secondary vasculitis presenting as epididymo-orchitis

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Background: Infectious triggers of vasculitis are uncommon but clinically important. Spotted fever group (SFG) rickettsioses, including *Rickettsia honei* and *Rickettsia australis* in Australia, are transmitted by tick bites and usually present with fever, rash, or eschar. While often considered mild, unusually severe cases have been reported with complications such as renal failure, purpura fulminans, and severe pneumonia, suggesting illness may not always be as benign. Epididymo-orchitis due to vasculitis has rarely been linked to rickettsial disease and, while described in scrub typhus, has not previously been reported in association with SFG rickettsioses.

Case Presentation: A 68-year-old man with hypertension, dyslipidaemia, monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS), and psoriasis presented with five weeks of fevers, drenching sweats, weight loss, and scrotal pain after bushwalking and water activities south of Sydney. Initial ultrasound suggested epididymo-orchitis and he was treated with ciprofloxacin, without resolution. On admission, infectious diseases investigations included negative Cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus polymerase chain reaction (PCR), Q fever, syphilis, HIV, and hepatitis serology. A sexually transmitted infection screen was also negative, with varicella serology consistent with past infection and mumps serology negative; rickettsial serology was pending. Computer tomography of chest, abdomen, pelvis and vasculitis screen were unremarkable. Positron emission tomography revealed medium-to-small-vessel uptake in both lower limbs, suggestive of vasculitis. Rickettsial serology subsequently returned strongly positive, with a spotted fever group titre of 1:256, suggestive of recent infection. He was treated with doxycycline for seven days, with defervescence and symptom resolution.

Conclusions: This case demonstrates SFG rickettsial infection presenting as epididymo-orchitis with secondary small- to medium-vessel vasculitis. Epididymo-orchitis has been described with scrub typhus, but not previously with SFG rickettsiae. Clinicians should consider rickettsial infections in febrile patients with vasculitis and negative autoimmune screen, particularly in endemic Australian regions, as prompt recognition and treatment are important to avoid complications.

C-102

A case of life-threatening small/medium vessel systemic vasculitis following Oxford AstraZeneca COVID vaccine – 4 years follow-up

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Background: During the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent immunization efforts, reports of vasculitis following COVID vaccination emerged. Most describe mild-moderate illness, with primarily cutaneous manifestations. We describe the case of a gentleman who developed acute life-threatening small/medium vessel systemic vasculitis following COVID vaccination.

Case Presentation: Our previously healthy 54-year-old patient presented in 2021 with a 2 day history of purpuric rash, lower limb swelling, and arthritis. He denied infective symptoms, drug use and COVID swab was negative on admission. One week prior to his symptoms, he had received the first dose of Oxford AstraZeneca COVID vaccine.

Bloods showed a high WCC, ESR, CRP. His infection, drugs, joint aspiration, and blood borne viruses screen were all negative. Skin biopsy showed florid leukocytoclastic vasculitis with negative direct immunofluorescence. His autoimmune screen was entirely negative.

His condition deteriorated with large volume upper GI bleeding (causing haemorrhagic shock) requiring 10 units blood transfusion. Abdominal CT revealed active haemorrhage in gastric fundus which required embolization of left gastric artery.

His condition further deteriorated with type 1 respiratory failure - pulmonary haemorrhage and vasculitis (on PET-CT), myopericarditis (on cardiac MRI), inflammatory myositis (on MRI lower limbs) and peripheral neuropathy (on nerve conduction studies).

He was diagnosed with severe/life-threatening small/medium vessel systemic vasculitis and treated with IV Methylprednisolone and EuroLupus IV Cyclophosphamide, followed by maintenance prednisolone and MMF. He made a remarkable recovery and was discharged with mild residual neuropathy. He managed to wean down prednisolone to 5mg daily and stopped Mycophenolate. He has now been under follow-up for 4 years, with no recurrence of symptoms. He subsequently had 5 Pfizer-BioNTech m-RNA COVID vaccines with no side effects.

Conclusion: Severe life-threatening systemic vasculitis is rare following COVID-19 vaccination. The EuroLupus regimen is highly effective, and immunosuppression can potentially be withdrawn. Vaccine related vasculitis should not discourage subsequent immunizations.

C-103

Crystal-cryoglobulinemic vasculitis with proximal light chain proximal tubulopathy: a case report of treat first, confirm later

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Case presentation: A 52-year-old male was referred into hospital with rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis (RPGN) with a creatinine decline of 91 μ mol/L to 411 μ mol/L over 2 months. He had a background smouldering myeloma and seronegative arthropathy. Concurrently, he had a developed a length dependent peripheral neuropathy, and bilateral lower limb vasculitic-appearing rashes. Initial workup showed a urine ACR 369g/mol, stable IgG Kappa monoclonal protein concentration of 8g/L, an elevated kappa/lambda ratio of 3.1 (kappa 140mg/l and lambda 43mg/l). Both his C3 and C4 were low (0.44 and 0.09g/l). He was negative for hepatitis B, C and HIV serologies. Kidney biopsy showed membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis with wire-loop lesions and hyaline thrombi which was suspicious for cryocrystalglobulinaemia and light chain proximal tubulopathy. IF for IgG subtypes showed restriction to IgG3 with kappa predominance. Electron microscopy confirmed the presence of rhomboid crystals in the endothelial cells and light chain crystalline proximal tubulopathy, with no evidence of fibrillary or microtubular substructure. The Diagnosis was Crystal-cryoglobulinemic vasculitis with proximal light chain proximal tubulopathy.

Due to the rapid decline in kidney function, he was treated with pulsed 250mg methylprednisolone plasma exchange and empiric cyclophosphamide. He required one session of haemodialysis. Following histological confirmation, he was commenced on clone-directed therapy with VCD (Velcade [bortezomib]/cyclophosphamide/dexamethasone). He is in his last cycle of therapy with serum creatinine of 150 μ mol/L. He remains well with no progression of his neuropathy.

Conclusions: This case underscores the importance of early recognition of RPGN, as timely treatment is critical for achieving favourable outcomes in a condition otherwise associated with a guarded renal prognosis. Although serum cryoglobulins were negative in this instance, it is notable that cryoglobulins may be absent in up to 25% of cases. Therefore, clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion.

C-104

Retinal vein occlusion as a very unusual manifestation of cryoglobulinaemic vasculitis secondary to Sjögren's syndrome

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Background: Cryoglobulinemic vasculitis (CV) is a rare disease characterized by the involvement of small-calibre vessels. In most cases, it is associated with a combination of circulating mono- and/or polyclonal immunoglobulins, resulting from various systemic diseases such as chronic hepatitis C virus infection, or Sjögren's syndrome (SS). Clinical manifestations vary, with dermatological involvement being the most common. Ocular involvement is rare. We present a case of central retinal vein branch occlusion in a patient with CV secondary to SS.

Case presentation: A 44-year-old woman with a medical history of dry symptoms for over 15 years presented with recurrent purpura of the lower extremities and left foot drop. Laboratory work-up revealed C4 hypocomplementemia, marked positivity for both anti-Ro and anti-La antibodies and elevated rheumatoid factor. Electromyography of lower limbs showed axonal polyneuropathy. The diagnosis of SS was confirmed by salivary gland biopsy and presence of mixed cryoglobulinemia was detected at 7 days of incubation.

During hospitalization, she presented with episodes of severe headache, eye floaters, and sudden visual acuity change. A contrast-enhanced brain MRI showed irregularity of the left M1, and retinal fluorescein angiography revealed occlusion of the retinal vein branch in the upper periphery of the right eye, as well as sequelae from ischemic occlusion of the upper nasal retinal vein branch of the left eye, associated with active ipsilateral retinal neovascularization. Involvement due to CV was suspected, and treatment with pulses of glucocorticoids and rituximab was initiated, showing clinical improvement. At the 15-day follow-up visit, the ocular symptoms had resolved and visual acuity was stable.

Conclusions: Retinal involvement in VC is uncommon but, if not recognized in time, it can be associated with irreversible vision loss. This is the first case of retinal vein occlusion associated with VC secondary to SS that the authors are aware of.

C-106

Paediatric hypocomplementaemic urticarial vasculitis syndrome associated with systemic lupus erythematosus: two cases from Johannesburg, South Africa

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Background/Aims: Hypocomplementaemic urticarial vasculitis syndrome (HUVS) is an exceptionally rare paediatric condition marked by persistent urticarial lesions, low complement levels, and systemic symptoms such as arthritis, abdominal pain, pulmonary disease, glomerulonephritis, uveitis, or episcleritis. HUVS may occur alone or with autoimmune diseases, infections, and malignancies. This report presents two female patients from Johannesburg, South Africa, showing features of both Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) and HUVS. One patient developed urticaria initially, while the other developed it later during her illness.

Case presentations: The first patient, aged 11, had a six-week history of a pruritic rash, fever, headaches, fatigue, and abdominal pain. Examination revealed palmar vasculitis and urticarial wheals. Laboratory tests showed a positive ANA (1:1280), positive anti-Sm, RNP antibodies, and dsDNA antibodies (126 IU/ml), low C3 (0.54 g/l), low C4 (0.03 g/l), and positive C1q antibody (42 RU/ml). Skin biopsy confirmed leukocytoclastic vasculitis. She met the EULAR/ACR 2019 criteria for SLE and criteria for the diagnosis of HUVS.

The second patient, aged 10, initially had oral ulcers, discoid lupus lesions, and palmar vasculitis. Urticarial lesions developed 18 months later. Laboratory results showed lymphopenia ($0.77 \times 10^9/l$), positive ANA (1:640), positive SSA and low positive RNP antibodies, positive anticardiolipin antibodies, later positive dsDNA antibodies (128 IU/ml), low C3 (0.31 g/l), low C4 (<0.02 g/l), and positive C1q antibodies (93 RU/ml). Skin biopsy indicated urticarial vasculitis. She also fulfilled criteria for the diagnosis of SLE and HUVS.

Both patients received chloroquine, azathioprine, and prednisone. Despite initial improvement, both experienced multiple flares. The first attained full remission with dapsons and mycophenolate mofetil (MMF), while the second still experiences subtle flares on dapsons and MMF and Rituximab is now being considered.

Conclusion: HUVS in children is rare and difficult to treat, especially when associated with SLE. These cases illustrate the disease's complexity and treatment challenges.

C-107

Retiform Purpura in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: A Clinical Manifestation of Lupus Associated Vasculitis

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Background: Retiform purpura, which can occur due to small vessel vasculitis, may be an uncommon initial presentation of systemic lupus erythematosus(SLE). Early identification is crucial for timely immunosuppressive treatment. Screening for organ involvement is essential to prevent damage and to guide therapy in suspected vasculitis. This case highlights that SLE may present with retiform purpura due to secondary vasculitis, often with subclinical organ involvement.

Case presentation: A 10-year-old boy with one year history of chronic immune thrombocytopenic purpura developed acute onset petechial rash involving upper and lower limbs, face, and trunk following a febrile illness. On examination retiform purpura was noted over the affected areas. Laboratory investigations showed anaemia, thrombocytopenia, positive ANA, anti-dsDNA, low complements, and trace proteinuria. ESR was 103mm/hr and CRP was 21mg/L. Skin biopsy confirmed vasculitis; renal biopsy showed lupus nephritis. Antiphospholipid testing revealed low-positive anticardiolipin IgG, while other markers were negative. He was treated with intravenous methylprednisolone followed by oral prednisone, hydroxychloroquine, methotrexate and IV cyclophosphamide. Maintenance therapy continued with mycophenolate mofetil.

This patient presented with retiform purpura, requiring prompt intervention to prevent further skin necrosis and halt the vasculitis cascade. Upon suspecting SLE, intravenous methylprednisolone was initiated without any delay. Laboratory results, including low complement levels and skin biopsy findings, indicated secondary vasculitis. Renal involvement, with a 'full house' immunofluorescence pattern, was also identified. Treatment was escalated to intravenous cyclophosphamide due to ongoing vasculitis and renal involvement. Significant clinical and laboratory improvement was observed within two weeks.

Conclusions: Early, aggressive management of lupus vasculitis is crucial to minimize morbidity and mortality. In SLE, retiform purpura can occur due to secondary vasculitis. The most common vasculitis in lupus erythematosus is small vessel vasculitis, driven by circulating immune complexes or antibodies targeting cell surface components. These complexes deposit in the microvasculature, activating complement and triggering inflammation.

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P-118: Having had research or personal support provided by an industry in the research presented/product to be discussed.

P-119: TM, AO: CSL Vifor employees YKOT: The LUMC received an unrestricted research grant from GlaxoSmithKline, CSL Vifor and Novartis for investigator-initiated studies conducted by Prof. Dr. Y.K.O. Teng. The LUMC received consulting fees from AstraZeneca, Alexion, GSK, Novartis, Otsuka Pharmaceuticals, CSL Vifor on consultancies delivered by Prof. Dr. Y.K.O. Teng. ND: Speaker fees, consultancy/advisory board fees and/or financial support for conference attendance from CSL Vifor, AstraZeneca, Bayer, Boehringer-Ingelheim, Roche, Otsuka Pharmaceuticals and GlaxoSmithKline KdeK: N/A FA: Advisory board, consulting fees, honoraria for presentations or support for attending meetings from CSL Vifor, AstraZeneca, Bayer and Boehringer Lilly.

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P-121: A financial interest in a product to be discussed (directly or indirectly) Masayoshi Harigai: Consultant fee and Speaker's fee (KISSEI PHARMACEUTICAL CO., LTD., AbbVie Japan), Research grant not related to avacopan and Speaker's fee(Chugai Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd.)/ Hiroaki Dobashi: Speaking fees, and/or honoraria (KISSEI PHARMACEUTICAL CO., LTD, Abbvie, Asahi Kasei Pharma, UCB Pharmaceutical, Ayumi Pharmaceutical, GlaxoSmithKline, Novartis Pharma, Eli Lilly Japan, AstraZeneca)/ Keiju Hiramura: Research Funding (Asahi Kasei, Chugai, Kyowa Kirin, Nippon Kayaku, Otsuka), Honoraria (Asahi Kasei, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Japan, GlaxoSmithKline, Kissei, Otsuka), Consultancy (GlaxoSmithKline, Otsuka)/ Naoto Tamura: Grants (ASAHI KASEI PHARMA Corp., Chugai Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd.), Honoraria (AstraZeneca plc., AbbVie Inc., KISSEI PHARMACEUTICAL CO., LTD., GlaxoSmithKline K.K., Eli Lilly Japan K.K., UCB Japan Co. Ltd.) Being or having been an employee of a company with a financial interest Kazunori Abe, Hiroaki Endo: Employee (KISSEI PHARMACEUTICAL CO., LTD.) Having had research or personal support provided by an industry in the research presented/product to be discussed Masayoshi Harigai: Research support for a clinical trial (KISSEI PHARMACEUTICAL CO., LTD.)/ Hiroaki Dobashi: Research Funding (Abbvie, Chugai Pharmaceutical).

P-122: Consulting: AbbVie, Alexion, Amgen, ArGenx, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol Myers Squibb, Capstan, GlaxoSmithKline, iCell, Interius, Kinevant, Kyverna, Lifordi, Lilly, Melodia, Neovii, Neutrolis, Novartis, NS Pharma, Otsuka, Protalix, Q32, Quell, Regeneron, Sanofi, Sparrow, Takeda; Research Support: AbbVie, Amgen, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol Myers Squibb, Electra, GlaxoSmithKline, Neutrolis, Q32, Takeda; Stock options: Kyverna, Q32, Lifordi, Neutrolis, Serpass, Sparrow; Royalties: UpToDate.

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P-127: Amgen, Bristol Myers Squibb Foundation, GlaxoSmithKline (Grant/Research Support); Fresenius Kabi (Speaker/Honoraria); Sanofi (Consultant/Intellectual Property/Patents).

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P-134: D.J. has received consultancy or lecture fees from Amgen, AstraZeneca, Bristol-Meyers Squibb, Chemocentryx, CSL Vifor, Novartis, Otsuka, Roche and Takeda. R.J. has research grants from CSL Vifor and Roche, Consultancy/Honorarium from CSL Vifor, Alexion, Roche, Alentis, Novartis and R.S research grants from GlaxoSmithKline and Union Therapeutics, all outside of the submitted work. L.F has honorarium from CSL ViFoR. The remaining authors declare no conflicts of interest.

P-136: RJ has investigator-initiated study collaboration with Roche and has received research grants from GSK, CSL Vifor, advisory board fees from CSL Vifor and GSK and Honoraria from Roche. DJ has

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P-141: CP reports receiving consulting and speaker fees from Amgen, GSK, Otsuka, and Pfizer; served on advisory boards from Amgen, AstraZeneca, CSL Vifor, GSK, Novartis, NS Pharma, and Otsuka; and received educational grants from GSK, Otsuka, Pfizer. AB reports receiving consultancy fees and speaker fees from Amgen, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Chiesi, GSK, Novartis, Sanofi Regeneron, and research grants from AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, and GSK. BH received speaker fees and/or consultancies from AbbVie, Amgen, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol Myers Squibb, Chugai, GSK, InflaRx, Janssen, MSD, Novartis, Pfizer, Phadia, Roche and CSL Vifor. NK reports receiving consulting fees and research support from AbbVie, Bristol Myers Squibb, and

Sanofi; consulting fees only from GSK, Mallinckrodt Pharmaceuticals, Otsuka Pharmaceuticals, and Roche. DJJ reports consultancy fees and speakers' fees from AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Chiesi, GSK, and Sanofi Regeneron, and research grants from AstraZeneca. DRWJ reports receiving speaker fees and/or consultancies from Amgen, AstraZeneca, Bristol Myers Squibb, Boehringer Ingelheim, ChemoCentryx, Chugai, GSK, Novartis, Roche, Takeda, and Vifor Pharma; advisory board member for Aurinia, Chinook, GSK, and Takeda. PN reports that his institution received grant support from AstraZeneca, Cyclomedica, Equillium, Foresee, Genentech, Sanofi and Teva; he has also received honoraria from Arrowhead Pharmaceuticals, AstraZeneca, CSL Behring, GSK, and Sanofi. US reports receiving consulting fees from Amgen, argenx, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, and CSL Vifor; and research grants from Amgen, AstraZeneca, Bristol Myers Squibb, Genentech, GSK, NorthStar Medical Radioisotopes, Novartis, and NS Pharma. BT reports receiving consulting fees from AstraZeneca, GSK, Novartis, and Vifor Pharma. LBS, PJ, AL, SN, and CW are employees of AstraZeneca, and may own stock or stock options. MEW reports receiving consulting, advisory, or speaking honoraria from the following: Allakos, Amgen, Areteia Therapeutics, Arrowhead Pharmaceuticals, AstraZeneca, Avalo Therapeutics, Celldex, Connect Biopharma, Eli Lilly, Equillium, GSK, Incyte, Kinaset, Kymera, Merck, Phylaxis, Pulmatrix, Rapt Therapeutics, Recludix Pharma, Regeneron Pharmaceuticals, Roche/Genentech, Sanofi/Genzyme, Sentien, Sound Biologics, Tetherex Pharmaceuticals, Uniquity Bio, Upstream Bio, Verona Pharma, and Zurabio. PAM reports receiving consulting fees from AbbVie, Alpine Pharmaceuticals, Amgen, argenx, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol Myers Squibb, CSL Behring, GSK, iCell, Interius BioTherapeutics, Kinevant Sciences, Kyverna, Metagenomi, Neutrolis, Novartis, NS Pharma, Q32 Bio, Quell Therapeutics, Regeneron Pharmaceuticals, Sanofi, Sparrow Pharmaceuticals, Takeda Pharmaceuticals, Visterra; research support from AbbVie, Amgen, AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol Myers Squibb, Eicos, Electra, GSK, Neutrolis, Takeda; stock options from Kyverna, Q32, Lifordi, Sparrow Pharmaceuticals; and royalties from UpToDate.

P-143: Speaking fees.

P-147: Having had research or personal support provided by an industry in the research presented/product to be discussed (speaker fees).

P-148: CO has lectured for AZ, GSK, Sanofi, Novartis; course fees from Boehringer. DJ has received grants from AstraZeneca, GlaxoSmithKline and Roche; consulting fees from Astra-Zeneca, Chemocentryx, GSK, Novartis, Otsuka, Takeda, Roche, Vifor; honoraria from GlaxoSmithKline and Vifor; participation on advisory boards for Chinook, GlaxoSmithKline and Takeda and stock options from Aurinia. AE has participated on advisory boards for AZ, consultancy for CSL-VIFOR.

P-149: Disclosures: CO has lectured for AZ, GSK, Sanofi, Novartis; course fees from Boehringer. DJ has received grants from AstraZeneca, GlaxoSmithKline and Roche; consulting fees from Astra-Zeneca, Chemocentryx, GSK, Novartis, Otsuka, Takeda, Roche, Vifor; honoraria from GlaxoSmithKline and Vifor; participation on advisory boards for Chinook, GlaxoSmithKline and Takeda and stock options from Aurinia. AE has participated on advisory boards for AZ, consultancy for CSL-VIFOR.

P-150: A financial interest in a product to be discussed (directly or indirectly).

P-151: A financial interest in a product to be discussed (Peter Merkel), Being an employee of a company with a financial interest (Tomohiko Murashige, Tara Keane, Takashi Hosono, Tomonori Uno).

P-155: Ana Romero is an employee of AbbVie and may own stock or stock options.

P-157: SES has received research funding related to clinical trials from Amgen and GlaxoSmithKline (OCEAN), consulting fees from Sanofi and Abbvie (all funds toward research support), advisory board fees from Sanofi and Amgen (all funds toward research support), speaker fees from Fresenius Kabi (all funds toward research support). SES is a co-inventor of patent US63/620,471 (provisional application) filed by Sanofi biotechnology.

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P-215: TII (Toshiko Ito-Ihara):TII has received the speakers bureau for Kissei Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. SH (Shintaro Hirata): SH has received speaker's fees, consultancy fees, or research grants from AbbVie, Asahi-Kasei Pharma, Astellas, AstraZeneca, Ayumi, Bristol Myers Squibb, Boehringer Ingelheim, Chugai, Daiichi-Sankyo, Eisai, Eli Lilly, Gilead Sciences, GlaxoSmithKline, Janssen, Nihon-Shinyaku, Novartis, Otsuka Pharmaceutical, Pfizer, Sandoz, Taisho, Tanabe-Mitsubishi, and UCB. He is a member of the Speakers Bureau for AbbVie, Asahi-Kasei Pharma, Astellas, AstraZeneca, Ayumi, Bristol Myers Squibb, Boehringer Ingelheim, Chugai, Daiichi-Sankyo, Eisai, Eli Lilly, Gilead Sciences, GlaxoSmithKline, Janssen, Nihon-Shinyaku, Novartis, Otsuka Pharmaceutical, Pfizer, Sandoz, Taisho, Tanabe-Mitsubishi, and UCB. He has served as a paid instructor for AbbVie. He has worked as a consultant for Eisai and UCB. He has received grant or research support from Asahi-Kasei Pharma, Chugai, Otsuka Pharmaceutical, and Taisho. He does not own shares in any company and is not employed by any company. MM (Mayuko Moriyama): MM is a member of the Speakers Bureau for Eisai Co. Ltd, Taisho Pharma Corporation, Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma Corporation, Eli Lilly and Company, and Ayumi Pharma Corporation. YK (Yutaka Kawahito): YK has received research grants from Asahi Kasei and Chugai. He has received speaker's fees from Asahi Kasei, Chugai, Pfizer, Novartis, Kissei, and Viatrix. PM (Peter Merkel): PM has served as a consultant for AbbVie, Alexion, Amgen, ArGenx, AstraZeneca, Boehringer-Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Capstan, GlaxoSmithKline, iCell, Interius, Kinevant, Kyverna, Lifordi, Lilly, Melodia, Neovii, Neutrolis, Novartis, NS Pharma, Otsuka, Protallix, Q32, Quell, Regeneron, Sanofi, Sparrow, and Takeda. He has received research support from AbbVie, Amgen, AstraZeneca, Boehringer-Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Electra, GlaxoSmithKline, Neutrolis, Q32, and Takeda. He holds stock options in Kyverna, Q32, Lifordi, Neutrolis, Serpass, and Sparrow. He also receives royalties from UpToDate. ST (Satoshi Teramukai): ST has received grants or contracts from Tarsus Pharmaceutical, TOWA Pharmaceutical, and Sun Contact Lens. He has received payments or honoraria for lectures, presentations, Speakers Bureau activities, manuscript writing, or educational events from Daiichi-Sankyo, Sanofi, Kringle Pharma, Kaneka, AtWorking, Sound Wave Innovation, Human Life Code, Eye-Lens, and Boehringer Ingelheim.

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